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KRIMINAL VA PENITENSIAR PSIXOLOGIYA: JINOYATCHI ONGINI TUSHUNISH VA IJTIMOY REABILITATSIYA YO‘LLARI

Ramanov Botirbek Parxad o‘g‘li

Qoraqalpoq Davlat Universiteti Amaliy psixologiya yo‘nalishi

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu tezis kriminal va penitensiar psixologiyaning dolzarb masalalarini yoritadi. Jinoyatchilikning psixologik ildizlari, jinoyatchi ongining shakllanish omillari va huquqbuzarlik xatti-harakatlarining asosiy sabablarini tahlil qiladi. Kriminal psixologiya jinoyatchilikning individual va ijtimoiy omillarini o‘rganib, jinoyatning oldini olish hamda rehabilitatsiya usullarini ishlab chiqishga qaratilgan. Shuningdek, penitensiar psixologiyaning asosiy yo‘nalishlari – mahbuslarning psixologik xususiyatlari, retsidivizmning oldini olish usullari va jazoni o‘tab bo‘lgan shaxslarning jamiyatga moslashuv jarayonlari keng muhokama qilinadi. Tadqiqotda zamonaviy psixologik nazariyalar va ilmiy manbalar asosida jinoyatchilik va ijtimoiy rehabilitatsiya o‘rtasidagi o‘zaro bog‘liqlik ochib beriladi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *Kriminal psixologiya, penitensiar psixologiya, jinoyatchi ongi, retsidivizm, ijtimoiy rehabilitatsiya, huquqbuzarlik, ijtimoiy stigma, kognitiv-behavioral terapiya, jinoyatchilik sabablari, jazoni ijro etish tizimi*

Аннотация: *Данная тезисная работа освещает актуальные вопросы криминальной и пенитенциарной психологии. Анализируются психологические корни преступности, факторы формирования сознания преступника и основные причины девиантного поведения. Криминальная психология исследует индивидуальные и социальные факторы преступности, разрабатывая методы профилактики правонарушений и реабилитации правонарушителей. В то же время пенитенциарная психология рассматривает психологические особенности осуждённых, методы предотвращения рецидивизма и процессы социальной адаптации бывших заключённых. В исследовании на основе современных психологических теорий и научных источников раскрывается взаимосвязь между преступностью и социальной реабилитацией.*

Ключевые слова: *Криминальная психология, пенитенциарная психология, сознание преступника, рецидивизм, социальная реабилитация, правонарушение, социальная стигматизация, когнитивно-поведенческая терапия, причины преступности, система исполнения наказаний*

Annotation: *This thesis explores the pressing issues of criminal and penitentiary psychology. It analyzes the psychological roots of crime, the factors influencing the formation of criminal consciousness, and the primary causes of deviant behavior. Criminal psychology examines both individual and social determinants of criminal activity, aiming to develop effective crime prevention and rehabilitation strategies. Meanwhile, penitentiary psychology focuses on the psychological characteristics of inmates, the prevention of recidivism, and the reintegration processes of former offenders into society. The study, based on modern*

psychological theories and scientific sources, highlights the intricate relationship between criminal behavior and social rehabilitation.

Key words: *Criminal psychology, penitentiary psychology, offender's consciousness, recidivism, social rehabilitation, delinquency, social stigma, cognitive-behavioral therapy, causes of crime, penal system*

Kriminal psixologiya: jinoyatchilik fenomenining psixologik ildizlari

Jinoyatchilik – inson ongi va xulq-atvorining murakkab, ko‘p omilli mahsulidir. Uning shakllanishida shaxsiy psixologik xususiyatlar, ijtimoiy muhit, oilaviy tarbiya va tashqi ta’sirlar asosiy rol o‘ynaydi. Kriminal psixologiya jinoyatchilikning individual va ijtimoiy sabablarini o‘rganib, huquqbuzarlikni oldini olish va reabilitatsiya usullarini ishlab chiqishga qaratilgan.

Zigmund Freydning psixoanalitik nazariyasiga ko‘ra, inson ruhiyatida uch asosiy tuzilma mavjud: "Id" – instinktiv istaklar, "Ego" – real voqelik bilan uyg‘unlik, "Super-ego" – axloqiy me’yorlar tizimi. Freyd ta’kidlaganidek, "agar Super-ego zaif bo‘lsa va Idning instinktiv xohishlari ustidan nazorat o‘rnatilmasa, shaxs huquqbuzarlik qilishga moyil bo‘ladi". Bu nazariya shuni anglatadiki, jinoyatchilikning ba’zi shakllari ongsiz jarayonlar ta’sirida yuzaga kelishi mumkin.

B.F. Skinner esa jinoyatchilikni mukofot va jazolash orqali mustahkamlanadigan xatti-harakat sifatida tushuntiradi. Uning fikricha, "agar shaxs jinoyat sodir etib, jazoga tortilmasa, u o‘z xatti-harakatini takrorlash ehtimoli yuqori". Ushbu xulosa jazo va jazolash tizimining samaradorligini tushunishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Albert Bandura o‘zining ijtimoiy o‘rganish nazariyasida jinoyatchilikni insonning ijtimoiy muhitdan o‘rganadigan xatti-harakati sifatida tushuntiradi. U ta’kidlaydiki, "agar bola tajovuzkor xatti-harakatni ko‘rsa va u jazolanmasa, keyinchalik bunday xulqni normal deb qabul qiladi". Shuning uchun ijtimoiy muhit va tarbiya jinoyatchilikning shakllanishida asosiy rol o‘ynaydi.

Kriminal psixologiya nuqtayi nazaridan, jinoyatni sodir etishda biologik va ijtimoiy omillar ham muhimdir. Lombrozo nazariyasiga ko‘ra, jinoyatchilik genetik moyillik bilan bog‘liq bo‘lishi mumkin, biroq zamonaviy tadqiqotlar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, "ijtimoiy va psixologik omillar biologik omillarga nisbatan kuchliroq ta’sir ko‘rsatadi".

Jinoyatchilik fenomenining psixologik ildizlarini o‘rganish shuni ko‘rsatadiki, jinoyat nafaqat individual xususiyatlar, balki ijtimoiy sharoitlar ta’sirida ham shakllanadi. Shu sababli, jinoyatchilikning oldini olish va uni kamaytirish uchun shaxsiy psixologik xususiyatlarni o‘rganish bilan bir qatorda, ijtimoiy-madaniy muhitni ham tahlil qilish muhimdir.

Jinoyat sodir etgan shaxslarning ruhiy holati, ularning ijtimoiy muhitga qayta integratsiyalashuvi va retsidivizm ehtimoli penitensiar psixologiyaning asosiy tadqiqot yo‘nalishlaridan biridir. Ushbu soha mahbuslarning psixologik xususiyatlarini, ularning tuzatish jarayonidagi kechinmalarini va jamiyatga qayta moslashuv mexanizmlarini o‘rganadi.

Zamonaviy penitensiar psixologiyaning asosiy masalalaridan biri – jazoni o‘tab bo‘lgan shaxslarning ijtimoiy hayotga qaytishi va ularning jinoyatchilikka qaytish ehtimolini

minimallashtirishdir. Albert Bandura o'zining ijtimoiy o'rganish nazariyasida ta'kidlaydi: "inson o'z xatti-harakatlarini kuzatuv orqali shakllantiradi va jinoyatchilik ham ijtimoiy o'rganish natijasi bo'lishi mumkin". Bu shuni anglatadiki, mahbuslarning reabilitatsiyasi faqat jazoni ijro etish tizimi doirasida emas, balki ijtimoiy muhitda ham davom etishi kerak.

Zimbardo tomonidan olib borilgan "Stanford qamoqxona tajribasi" insonning ijtimoiy rolga moslashishi va qamoq sharoitidagi psixologik o'zgarishlar haqida muhim ma'lumotlar beradi. U shuni ta'kidlaydi: "qamoqxona sharoitlari shaxsga ta'sir qilib, uni agressiv yoki itoatkor shaxsga aylantirishi mumkin". Bu penitensiar muassasalarning faqat jazo berish joyi emas, balki inson ruhiyatini shakllantiruvchi muhit ekanligini ko'rsatadi.

Boshqa bir muhim masala – retsidivizm, ya'ni jinoyatchilarning qamoqdan chiqqach, yana jinoyat sodir etish ehtimolidir. Retsidivistik xatti-harakatning sabablari orasida jamiyat tomonidan stigmatizatsiya (jinoyatchini kamsitish), ish topish qiyinligi va ijtimoiy moslashuvning yetishmovchiligi kabi omillar mavjud. Robert Mertonning anomiya nazariyasiga ko'ra, "agar jamiyatda shaxs qonuniy yo'llar bilan o'z maqsadlariga erisha olmasa, u jinoyatga qo'l urishga moyil bo'ladi". Bu tushuncha jazoni o'tab bo'lgan shaxslarning jamiyatga moslashuvini qo'llab-quvvatlashning muhimligini tasdiqlaydi.

Zamonaviy penitensiar psixologiya retsidivizmning oldini olish uchun kognitiv-behavioral terapiya, psixososial reabilitatsiya va ish bilan ta'minlash kabi chora-tadbirlarni tavsiya qiladi. Beckning kognitiv terapiyasi shuni ko'rsatadiki, "shaxsning noto'g'ri fikrlash modellari o'z xatti-harakatlariga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatadi". Shuning uchun jinoyatchilarga nisbatan psixologik reabilitatsiya dasturlarini qo'llash, ularning kelajakda sog'lom ijtimoiy hayotga qaytishini ta'minlash uchun zaruriy hisoblanadi.

Penitensiar psixologiyaning samarali ishlashi uchun jazoni ijro etish tizimi faqat jazolashga emas, balki mahbuslarni jamiyatga qayta moslashtirishga qaratilgan bo'lishi lozim. Shunday bo'lsa, jinoyatchilikni kamaytirish va retsidivizmning oldini olishga erishish mumkin.

Jinoyatchilikning qayta sodir etilishi, ya'ni retsidivizm, penitensiar psixologiyaning eng dolzarb muammolaridan biridir. Kriminalistik tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, qamoqdan chiqqan shaxslarning aksariyati jamiyatga moslasha olmaydi va oldingi muhitiga qaytib, yana jinoyat sodir etishga moyil bo'ladi. Ushbu muammoni hal qilish uchun penitensiar psixologlar nafaqat jazoni ijro etish tizimida, balki post-penitensiar davrda ham ijtimoiy moslashuv usullarini ishlab chiqishlari kerak.

Birinchi navbatda, retsidivizmning psixologik sabablarini tushunish lozim. Albert Ellisning ratsional-emotsional terapiya nazariyasiga ko'ra, "inson o'z hayotini qanday tushunishi va unga qanday munosabatda bo'lishi uning xulq-atvorini belgilaydi" (Ellis A., 1957). Bu shuni anglatadiki, jinoyatchilarning noto'g'ri kognitiv modellarini tuzatish va ularga ijtimoiy moslashuvning yangi usullarini o'rgatish orqali ularning kelajakdagi xatti-harakatlarini boshqarish mumkin.

Penitensiar psixologiyaning samarali yondashuvlaridan biri – kognitiv-behavioral terapiya (KBT) bo'lib, u jinoyatchilarning noto'g'ri fikrlash modellarini aniqlash va ularni konstruktiv tafakkur bilan almashtirishga qaratilgan. Beckning kognitiv terapiya nazariyasiga ko'ra, "shaxsning fikrlash jarayonlari bevosita uning his-tuyg'ulari va xatti-

harakatlariga ta'sir qiladi" (Beck A.T., 1967). Demak, jinoyatchilarga nisbatan individual terapiya va guruh treninglari o'tkazish ularning kelajakdagi retsdivistik xatti-harakatlarini kamaytirishi mumkin.

Retsdivizmning oldini olishda muhim bo'lgan yana bir yondashuv – sotsial integratsiya dasturlaridir. Robert Mertonning anomiya nazariyasiga ko'ra, "agar jamiyatda shaxs o'z maqsadlariga qonuniy yo'llar orqali erisha olmasa, u jinoyatga moyil bo'ladi" (Merton R.K., 1938). Demak, qamoqdan chiqqan shaxslar uchun ish o'rinlari yaratish, kasb-hunar o'rgatish va ularni mehnat bozoriga moslashtirish ularning jinoyatchilikka qaytishini oldini oladi.

Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, mahbuslarning jamiyatga moslashuvini yaxshilash uchun psixologik rehabilitatsiya bilan bir qatorda, oilaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash ham muhim ahamiyatga ega. Bronfenbrennerning ekopsixologik modeli bo'yicha, "insonning rivojlanishi uning oilasi, yaqin atrof-muhiti va ijtimoiy tizimlar bilan o'zaro ta'siriga bog'liq" (Bronfenbrenner U., 1979). Shu boisdan, penitensiar muassasalardan chiqqan shaxslarga yaqinlari bilan muloqotni tiklash, oilaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash dasturlarini yo'lga qo'yish retsdivizm darajasini kamaytirishga yordam beradi.

Yana bir muhim usul – ijtimoiy stigma va diskriminatsiyani kamaytirish. Goffmaning stigma nazariyasiga ko'ra, "jamiyat tomonidan belgilangan salbiy tamg'alar shaxsning o'zini qanday tutishini belgilaydi" (Goffman E., 1963). Agar qamoqdan chiqqan shaxs jamiyat tomonidan chetga surilsa, u yana jinoyatga qo'l urishga majbur bo'lishi mumkin. Shu sababli, sobiq mahkumlarni qo'llab-quvvatlash jamiyatning asosiy vazifalaridan biri bo'lishi lozim.

Penitensiar psixologiyada retsdivizmning oldini olish nafaqat individual psixologik terapiyalar orqali, balki ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy faktorlarni hisobga olgan holda amalga oshirilishi kerak. Faqat shundagina jinoyatchilikni kamaytirish va mahkumlarning jamiyatga qayta integratsiyasini ta'minlash mumkin.

Penitensiar psixologiya jinoyatchilar psixikasini o'rganish, ularning xulq-atvor sabablarini tahlil qilish va ijtimoiy rehabilitatsiyani ta'minlash bilan shug'ullanadi. Jinoyatchilikning qayta sodir etilishi – retsdivizm muammosi jahon miqyosida dolzarb bo'lib, uning oldini olish kompleks yondashuvni talab qiladi. Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, retsdivizmning asosiy omillari kognitiv buzilishlar, ijtimoiy izolyatsiya, iqtisodiy qiyinchiliklar va stigmatizatsiya bilan bog'liq. Samarali psixokorreksiya usullari sifatida kognitiv-behavioral terapiya, ijtimoiy moslashuv dasturlari va oilaviy qo'llab-quvvatlash tizimlari o'z samaradorligini isbotlagan. Jinoyatchilar bilan ishlashda individual yondashuv va rehabilitatsiya jarayonining uzluksizligi muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Retsdivizmning kamayishi jamiyat barqarorligiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatib, jinoyatchilarni qonuniy hayot tarziga yo'naltirishga xizmat qiladi. Penitensiar psixologiyada zamonaviy va tizimli yondashuvlarni keng qo'llash orqali jinoyatchilarni jamiyatga qayta integratsiya qilish, ularning ijtimoiylashuv jarayonini yengillashtirish va takroriy jinoyat sodir etish ehtimolini kamaytirish mumkin. Shu boisdan, penitensiar tizim faqat jazoni ijro etish emas, balki shaxsni tuzatish va jamiyatga qaytarish vositasi sifatida samarali ishlashi lozim.

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АНТРОПОМЕТРИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ У ДЕТЕЙ В СОВРЕМЕННОМ МИРЕ

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Аннотация: Антропометрия детей представляет собой важное направление в области педиатрии и общественного здоровья, которое изучает размеры и пропорции тела детей на различных этапах их развития. Измерение антропометрических показателей, таких как рост, вес, масса тела, окружность головы и другие параметры, играет ключевую роль в оценке физического развития и общего состояния здоровья детей. Эти данные не только помогают выявить возможные отклонения в развитии, но и служат основой для формирования методов профилактики и коррекции.

Ключевые слова: Антропометрия детей, пропорция тела, формирование, мониторинг, раннее детство, сенсорные и моторные навыки, дошкольный возраст, креативность, формирование идентичности, подростковый возраст.

ВВЕДЕНИЕ

Регулярный мониторинг антропометрических показателей позволяет специалистам видеть динамику роста и развития ребенка, что особенно важно в раннем возрасте. На основании собранных данных можно определить индивидуальные нормы для каждого ребенка, что позволяет выявить случаи недоразвития, ожирения или других нарушений. Также антропометрия помогает в анализе влияния факторов окружающей среды, питания и образа жизни на развитие детей.

Важно отметить, что актуальность антропометрии возрастает в условиях современных вызовов, таких как ухудшение питания, распространение малоподвижного образа жизни и рост числа хронических заболеваний. Эти факторы могут негативно сказываться на физическом развитии детей и увеличивать риск развития заболеваний в будущем.

Кроме того, антропометрические данные используются для исследования влияния социально-экономических факторов на здоровье детей, что позволяет разрабатывать программы поддержки и вмешательства на уровне

общественного здравоохранения. Таким образом, антропометрия детей является неотъемлемой частью комплексного подхода к заботе о здоровье, и её значение продолжает расти в условиях быстроменяющегося мира. В свою очередь это действует на психологию

Основная часть: При антропометрии психология детского развития охватывает широкий спектр тем и аспектов, от раннего детства до подросткового возраста. Понимание этих этапов важно для родителей, педагогов и специалистов, работающих с детьми.

Раннее детство

Начальный этап жизни, от рождения до трех лет, критически важен для формирования базовых навыков. В это время:

- Развивается связь с родителями: Безопасная привязанность играет ключевую роль в эмоциональном развитии.
- Формируются основные сенсорные и моторные навыки: Дети учатся осознавать свое тело и взаимодействовать с окружающим миром.
- Важность игры: Игровая деятельность является основным форматом обучения в раннем детстве, поскольку через игру дети познают мир.

Родители и воспитатели могут поддерживать эти процессы, обеспечивая безопасную и стимулирующую среду. Например, чтение книг и совместные игры развивают не только речь, но и эмоциональную связь.

Дошкольный возраст

В возрасте от трех до семи лет происходит активное развитие социальной и когнитивной сферы. На этом этапе важно:

- Сотрудничество и игра: Дети учатся работать в команде, взаимодействовать с другими детьми и развивать социальные навыки.
- Креативность: Возрастающий интерес к художественным и творческим видам деятельности помогает развивать воображение.
- Знания о мире: Дошкольники начинают задавать вопросы о том, как устроен мир, и активно исследуют его.

В этот период роль взрослых в обучении и поддержке становится ключевой. Воспитатели могут использовать игры для обучения основам математики и языка, что делает процесс более увлекательным.

Начальная школа

Семилетний возраст отмечен переходом в школу и новыми вызовами. Ключевые моменты включают:

- Формирование идентичности: Дети начинают осознавать свои сильные и слабые стороны, что влияет на их самооценку.
- Учебные навыки: Развиваются навыки чтения, письма и математики, что требует от детей концентрации и самоконтроля.

- Социальные отношения: Друзья становятся более важными, и дети учатся справляться с конфликтами и работать в группах.

На этом этапе важно, чтобы родители и учителя поощряли положительные взаимодействия и помогали детям развивать навыки решения конфликтов, так как это критично для формирования эмоционального интеллекта.

Подростковый возраст

Подростковый период (от 12 до 18 лет) — это время значительных изменений, как физических, так и психологических. Основные аспекты включают:

Поиск идентичности: Подростки начинают задаваться вопросами о том, кто они такие, что приводит к экспериментированию с различными ролями и образами.

- Эмоциональная нестабильность: Гормональные изменения могут вызывать резкие изменения настроения, что важно учитывать в коммуникации с ними.

- Давление со стороны сверстников: Подростки могут следовать моде и нормам своей группы, что иногда приводит к рискованному поведению.

Взрослые должны оставаться открытыми и доступными для подростков, предоставляя им возможность обсудить свои переживания и решения. Поддержка в формировании самопознания и стратегий принятия решений может сыграть решающую роль в этом переходном периоде.

Заключение: Психология детского развития — это сложный и многогранный процесс, включающий в себя множество факторов. Каждый этап жизни ребенка имеет свои особенности и потребности, познание которых помогает создавать более эффективные методы воспитания и обучения. Понимание, как точно развиваются дети и какие факторы на это влияют, может значительно поспособствовать их гармоничному росту и развитию.

**NAVOIY VILOYATIDAGI SANOAT KORXONALARI ISHLAB CHIQRISH
QUVVATLARINING HUDUDIY BARQARORLIK RIVOJLANISHIGA TA'SIRI**

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Annotatsiya: *maqolada Navoiy viloyatidagi korxonalar o'rtasida sanoat kooperatsiyalarini yaratish, mahalliy xom-ashyo materiallariga asoslangan sanoat mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqarish, klasterlarini joriy etish, keng imkoniyatlar, ilg'or texnologilar, bugungi kunda tadbirkorlarga yaratib berilayotgan imtiyozlardan samarali foydalanish hududning iqtisodiy mavqeini belgilab berayotganligi tahlili keltirilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar va iboralar: *mintaqaviy iqtisodiy barqarorlik, barqaror rivojlanishni baholash, barqaror rivojlanish, integral ko'rsatkich, erkin industrial iqtisodiy zona, tashkilotning barqaror rivojlanishining umumiy ko'rsatkichi.*

Аннотация: *в статье анализируется тот факт, что создание промышленной кооперации между предприятиями Навоийской области, производство промышленной продукции на основе местного сырья, внедрение кластеров, широких возможностей, передовых технологий, эффективное использование предоставляемых предпринимателям льгот сегодня определяют экономическое положение региона.*

Ключевые слова и термины: *региональная экономическая устойчивость, оценка устойчивого развития, устойчивое развитие, комплексный показатель, свободная индустриальная экономическая зона, общий показатель устойчивого развития организации.*

Annotation: *the article analyzes the fact that the creation of industrial cooperation between enterprises in the Navoi region, the production of industrial products based on local raw materials, the introduction of clusters, broad opportunities, advanced technologies, and the effective use of the benefits provided to entrepreneurs today determine the economic status of the region.*

Key words and terms: *regional economic stability, sustainable development assessment, sustainable development, integrated indicator, free industrial economic zone, overall indicator of sustainable development of the organization.*

Barqaror rivojlanishni baholashning samaradorligi barqaror rivojlanishning maqsad va vazifalari qay darajada to'g'ri belgilanganligiga, korxonalar faoliyatiga ta'sir etuvchi omillar qanday baholanishiga va uning o'sish yo'nalishi qay darajada aniq belgilanganligiga bog'liq.

Mexanizmlarni shakllantirish, barqaror rivojlanish va uni keyingi baholash uchun kompaniyaning ishlab chiqarish-xo'jalik faoliyatining o'zaro ta'sir qiluvchi ko'rsatkichlari va uning barqaror mavjudligi ko'rsatkichlari tasdiqlangan va to'liqlik tamoyillariga

asoslangan tizimini ishlab chiqish, samarali boshqaruv qarorlarini qabul qilish imkonini beradigan ishonchlilik, axborot sifati ta'minlash zarur.

Tahlil doirasida baholashga imkon beruvchi koeffitsientlar shakllangan sifat va miqdor maqsadlaridan kelib chiqqan holda korxonaning barqaror rivojlanishi ikki guruhga bo'lingan. Biz har bir koeffitsientni to'rt darajaga ajratamiz: ijtimoiy, ekologik, iqtisodiy.

Shunday qilib, taklif etilayotgan baholashning o'ziga xos xususiyati - bu barqaror rivojlanishning har bir sohasi (ijtimoiy, ekologik, iqtisodiy) bo'yicha korxonaning sifat va miqdoriy xususiyatlariga muvofiq barqaror rivojlanishini baholashga imkon beradigan maqsadli yondashuv darajadagi o'zaro ta'sirini hisobga oladi.

1-chizma

Korxonaning barqaror rivojlanishi ko'rsatkichlari tizimi¹

Barqaror rivojlanishning umumlashtirilgan integral ko'rsatkichi (BRUIK) sanoat korxonalarini tahlilda quyidagi formula bo'yicha hisoblangan miqdoriy (N) va sifat (Q) guruhlarning qisman integral ko'rsatkichlaridan yig'indilar usuli asosida amalga oshiriladi:

$$BRUIK = \sum_{i=1}^n W_i * K^2$$

bu erda:

¹ Muallifning shaxsiy ishlanmasi

² Петров, В.К. Устойчивость государства [Текст]: монография / В.К. Петров, С. Г. Селиванов. – Москва: Экономика, 2005. – 488 с.

BRUIK - tashkilotning barqaror rivojlanishining umumiy ko'rsatkichi;

Wi – ko'rsatkichning ahamiyati, uni mutaxassislar belgilaydi;

Ki - koeffitsient;

n – koeffitsientlar soni.

Respublikamizda ilk bor 2008 yil 2-dekabrda Erkin iqtisodiy zonaning Navoiy viloyatida tashkil etilishi, hududning iqtisodiy qulayligidan dalolat beradi.

Navoiy Erkin iqtisodiy zonasi Karmana tumanining 645 gektar hududda joylashgan bo'lib, u Xalqaro aeroport, xalqaro temiryo'l va avtomobil magistral yo'li infrastrukturasida joylashgan.

Erkin iqtisodiy zona – mintaqani jadal ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlantirish uchun mamlakat va chet el kapitalini, istiqbolli texnologiya va boshqaruv tajribasini jalb etish maqsadida tuziladigan, aniq belgilangan ma'muriy chegaralari va alohida huquqiy tartiboti bo'lgan maxsus ajratilgan hudud hisoblanadi³.

Bundan ko'rinib turibdiki, hududning erkin iqtisodiy zonasi asosan keng ko'lamdagi sanoat mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqish va eksport qilish bilan shug'ullanadi.

Navoiy erkin industrial iqtisodiy zonasi – jahon standartlariga javob beradigan va jahon bozorlarida talab qilinadigan mahsulot ishlab chiqarishni ta'minlaydigan, zamonaviy yuqori texnologiyali ishlab chiqarishlarni tashkil etish uchun xorijiy investitsiyalarni, birinchi galda to'g'ridan-to'g'ri investitsiyalarni jalb etish bo'yicha qulay shart-sharoitlar yaratish, shuningdek, Navoiy viloyatining sanoat salohiyatini, ishlab chiqarish, transport tranzit va ijtimoiy infratuzilmasini rivojlantirish maqsadida tashkil etilgan.

Navoiy erkin industrial iqtisodiy zona hududida xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlar faoliyatining asosiy yo'nalishi – zamonaviy xorijiy yuqori unumli asbob-uskunalar va texnika, texnologik liniyalar va modullar, innovatsiya texnologiyalarini joriy etish hisobiga yuqori texnologiyali, jahon bozorlarida raqobatbardosh mahsulotlarni keng ko'lamda ishlab chiqarishdan iborat.

Ma'lumotlariga ko'ra Navoiy Erkin iqtisodiy zonasida 2009-2016 yillarda 22 ta loyiha amalga oshirilgan bo'lib, 124 mln.

AQSh dollari miqdorida foyda ko'rgan.

Bu holat o'sha davrda korxonalar sonining qisqaligi bilan izohlanadi. 2017-2018 yillarda MDH va jahon mamalkatlarining sohalarga kiritgan investitsiyalari natijasida 35 ta loyiha amalga oshirildi hamda buning natijasi yuqori ko'rsatkichga ega bo'ldi.

2020-2021 yillarda esa ushbu davr ichida erkin iqtisodiy zonada amalga oshirilgan lohihalar sonining yana 12 taga ko'payganligi bu ishlab chiqarish hajmining oshganligidan dalolat beradi.

2020-2022 yillarda loyihalar sonining jadal ortishi va o'z navbatida korxonalar kelajak istiqboli ko'rsatkichlarini oshishiga sabab bo'ladi.

Shu bilan birga hukumat tomonidan amalga oshirilayotgan iqtisodiy sohalarni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan strategiyalar muhim sanalib hududlarda faoliyat yuritayotgan iqtisodiy zonalarning optimallashtirishini taqozo etadi.

1-jadval

³ O'zbekiston Respublikasining "Erkin iqtisodiy zonalarda to'g'risidagi" Qonuni 25 aprel 1996 yil.

Navoiy viloyatining tashqi iqtisodiy aloqalari (tashqi savdo eksporti)

Hamkor davlatlar	2010 yil	2015 yil	2020 yil	2010-2020 yillarda o'zgarishlar indeksi
AQSh	28736,1	1276,8	280,7	1,0
Buyuk Britaniya(Angliya)	50823,2	355,3	572,3	1,1
Koreya Respublikasi	34894,0	9068,2	229,2	0,7
Birlashgan Arab Amirliklari	23899,9	2249,4	1538,8	6,4
Gruziya	1280,3	6004,4	125,7	9,8
Italiya	281,5	5,6	50,4	17,9
Latviya	1167,3	305,3	240,7	20,6
Singapur	18004,1	1841,9	6627,1	36,8
Qozog'iston	13665,7	9798,1	8848,1	64,7
Turkmaniston	24802,5	11808,7	16053,7	64,7
Fransiya	63297,0	134600,2	78258,7	123,6
Yaponiya	464,1	52,9	851,6	183,5
Rossiya Federatsiyasi	17400,4	49215,4	34878,0	200,4
Ukraina	623,4	4539,8	2558,0	410,3
Turkiya	6231,6	5011,0	29517,3	473,7
Qirg'iziston	815,7	1568,7	37111,3	4549,4

Jadval: Navoiy statistika boshqarmasi ma'lumotlari asosida tuzilgan.

Statistik ma'lumotlarga bo'yicha oladigan bo'lsak, eng ko'p eksport Rossiya Federatsiyasi, Turkiya, Ukraina, Yevropa davlatlaridan Fransiya va Italiya bilan, qo'shni davlatlardan Bu holatni korxonaning iqtisodiy samaradorligi hamda uning ishlab chiqarish qobiliyati belgilaydi. Navoiy viloyati sanoat korxonalarida ishlab chiqarilgan mahsulotlar yuqori darajada qo'shni davlatlarga ya'ni Qirg'iston hamda Tojikiston respublikalariga eksport qilingan.

2-jadval

Navoiy viloyatining makroiqtisodiy ko'rsatkichlari

Ko'rsatkichlar	O'lchov birligi	2016- y.	2017- y.	2018- y.	2019- y.	2020- y.	2021- y.	2022- y.	2023- y.	2024-yil yanvar-iyun*
Yalpi hududiy mahsulot	mlrd.so`m	11 959,3	14 681,5	22 573,3	36 224,3	49 780,4	58 730,3	68 799,4	81 943,2	48 328,2
	o'sish sur'ati, % da	103,7	101,5	104,8	105,2	106,6	107,3	105,8	105,8	108,8
Sanoat mahsuloti	mlrd.so`m	10 657,9	13 072,9	22 892,4	44 438,1	65 084,9	73 633,5	84 393,7	101 841,9	63 433,0
	o'sish sur'ati, % da	101,2	97,5	101,8	104,3	109,1	107,0	106,1	107,2	109,4
Iste'mol tovarlari	mlrd.so`m	2 139,2	2 193,6	2 528,3	3 243,4	3 896,5	4 342,5	3 156,4	3 812,4	x
	o'sish sur'ati, % da	111,5	92,9	100,1	101,1	102,3	107,0	104,5	105,5	x
Qishloq, o'rmon va baliq xo'jaligi	mlrd.so`m	5 288,3	6 850,7	8 685,8	9 934,2	11 908,1	15 224,9	16 442,0	19 906,8	7 882,2
	o'sish sur'ati, % da	106,1	103,8	102,0	101,4	103,4	104,6	104,8	102,8	103,6
Asosiy kapitalga investitsiyalar	mlrd.so`m	2 963,2	3 977,8	10 579,5	17 646,3	15 688,5	15 020,1	17 958,1	26 398,6	16 890,5
	o'sish sur'ati, % da	144,1	107,4	188,0	144,3	77,1	86,0	109,4	136,3	144,5
Qurilish ishlari	mlrd.so`m	1 153,1	1 313,6	2 280,8	3 464,0	3 944,7	5 155,5	5 855,0	6 744,1	4 157,6
	o'sish sur'ati, % da	100,3	105,4	147,5	125,6	94,6	116,8	105,5	107,9	127,8
Chakana savdo tovar aylanmasi	mlrd.so`m	3 684,7	4 348,5	5 436,3	6 776,0	7 922,8	9 619,5	10 101,6	12 356,0	5 814,5
	o'sish sur'ati, % da	114,1	100,2	105,9	109,7	105,2	109,4	110,2	110,8	108,2
Xizmatlar, jami	mlrd.so`m	2 593,8	3 068,4	3 925,6	5 056,1	5 840,5	7 459,6	9 322,8	11 742,7	6 445,7
	o'sish sur'ati, % da	115,8	108,0	111,4	115,2	105,8	118,3	113,0	114,8	112,5
Tashqi savdo aylanmasi	mln. AQSh. Dollor	704,0	768,9	1 636,2	1 835,5	1 312,3	1 168,5	1 230,3	1 331,3	733,5
	o'sish sur'ati, % da	87,7	109,2	212,8	112,2	71,5	89,0	105,3	108,2	121,9
Eksport	mln. AQSh. Dollor	356,0	302,5	350,2	362,9	426,5	508,6	581,0	651,5	508,9
	o'sish sur'ati, % da	80,6	85,0	115,8	103,6	117,5	119,3	114,2	112,1	173,8
Import	mln. AQSh. Dollor	348,0	466,4	1 286,0	1 472,5	885,8	659,9	649,3	679,8	224,7
	o'sish sur'ati, % da	96,4	134,0	275,7	114,5	60,2	74,5	98,4	104,7	72,8
Saldo	mln. AQSh. Dollor	8,0	-164,0	-935,7	-1 109,6	-459,4	-151,3	-68,3	-28,3	284,2
	o'sish sur'ati, % da									

Jadval: Navoiy statistika boshqarmasi ma'lumotlari asosida tuzilgan.

Yuqoridagi javdal ma'lumotiga ko'ra viloyat mavqeini aniqlab beruvchi ko'rsatkich YaHM oldingi yillarga ko'ra 2023 yilda ham o'sish kuzatilgan.

Ushbu davrda sanoat mahsulotlari hajmi ortib, eksportbop mahsulot hajmi oshgan.

Xulosa qilib shuni aytish mumkinki, viloyat korxonalarini o'rtasida sanoat kooperatsiyalarini yaratish, mahalliy xom-ashyo materiallariga asoslangan sanoat mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqarish, klasterlarini joriy etish, keng imkoniyatlar, ilg'or texnologilar, bugungi kunda tadbirkorlarga yaratib berilayotgan imtiyozlardan samarali foydalanish hududning iqtisodiy mavqeini belgilab beradi.

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ДИПЛОМАТИЧЕСКИЕ ПРИВИЛЕГИИ И ИММУНИТЕТЫ: СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ И ВЫЗОВЫ

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Аннотация: В данной статье исследуются теоретические основы дипломатических привилегий и иммунитетов в соответствии с Венской конвенцией о дипломатических сношениях. Приводится практика Республики Узбекистан. Анализируются современные проблемы и вызовы, которые возникают в сфере применения данных привилегий.

Ключевые слова: дипломатический агент, привилегии, иммунитеты, дипломатическое представительство, злоупотребления привилегиями, дипломатические отношения, международное сообщество.

Annotation: In this article, the theoretical foundations of diplomatic privileges and immunities are examined in accordance with the Vienna Convention on Diplomatic Relations. The practice of the Republic of Uzbekistan is presented. The article analyzes contemporary issues and challenges that arise in the application of these privileges.

Key words: diplomatic agent, privileges, immunities, diplomatic representation, abuse of privileges, diplomatic relations, international community.

В современном мире значительна роль дипломатических сношений, ведь данные отношения устанавливают устойчивое международное сотрудничество и дружеский союз между государствами. При помощи дипломатических отношений обеспечиваются такие важные принципы международного права, как принцип сотрудничества государств, принцип мирного урегулирования международных споров. В кратком изложении, это основа становления международного права. В силу этого, еще в глубокой древности возникает необходимость предоставления определенных привилегий и иммунитетов представителям стран на международной арене с учетом преград и рисков, связанных с осуществлением функций дипломатии.

Республика Узбекистан, являясь полноправным субъектом международных отношений, в соответствии со статьей 18 Конституции осуществляет миролюбивую внешнюю политику, направленную на развитие отношений с государствами. Для осуществления данной нормы на практике Республика Узбекистан имеет своих послов и посольства во многих странах, которые представляют интересы данного государства в международном сообществе. В свою очередь, на территории этой страны также имеются дипломатические представительства других государств, что подчеркивает актуальность

обеспечения дипломатических привилегий, в силу того, что они закрепляются в международно-правовых нормах.

Однако нередко возникают случаи злоупотребления дипломатическими представителями своими привилегиями и иммунитетами, то есть совершение дипломатами преступлений и правонарушений и благодаря иммунитету избегают уголовного наказания. Вследствие, чего остро пробуждается недовольство общественности и государства пребывания, так как это является прямым нарушением справедливости и принципа неотвратимости наказания. Международно-правовых норм, предусматривающих конкретные правовые действия против дипломатов, преступивших закон государства пребывания не существует, что делает проблему злоупотребления дипломатическими привилегиями наиболее обсуждаемой в настоящее время.

При написании работы использовались следующие методы научного исследования: метод теоретического познания (анализ и синтез, сравнение), эмпирический метод (изучение литературы, документов и результатов деятельности), кейс-метод.

С древних времен иностранным посланникам обеспечивался свободный проход на территорию другого государства, также их неприкосновенность, чтобы они могли беспрепятственно обмениваться необходимой информацией, для ведения межправительственных переговоров и установления мирных отношений, что определяет дипломатические привилегии и иммунитеты как один из древнейших институтов международного права. Эти правила, оказавших под воздействием исторических процессов, поменяли своего содержания и были официально закреплены в международных договорах и национальных законодательствах стран.

Дипломатические привилегии и иммунитеты – это совокупность особых льгот, преимуществ и прав, предоставляемых иностранным дипломатическим представительствам, их персоналу и другим лицам, пользующимся по международному праву защитой на территории государства пребывания в целях обеспечения выполнения ими возложенных на них функций. Понятие «иммунитет» (от лат. *immunitas* – независимость, неподверженность) означает независимость дипломата от юрисдикции и законодательства страны пребывания. Привилегии – это дополнительные права и бонусы, предоставляемые исключительно представителям государств. Важно отметить, что этими дополнительными правами органы дипломатических представительств пользуются лишь, чтобы они беспрепятственно выполняли свои внешние функции и полномочия, соблюдая законодательство принимающего государства.

Голландский юрист и государственный деятель Гуго Гроций разработал теорию экстерриториальности, которая гласит, что послы, в силу условности

между государствами, считаются: а) как бы замещающими тех, кто их послал; б) как бы *extra territorium* (находящимся вне данной территории) и поэтому не связаны законами народа, среди которых они живут. В силу этого, помещения посольств и частная резиденция дипломата составляют часть территории аккредитуемого государства, и дипломатический агент не несет ответственности по внутригосударственному праву народа, среди которого они живут.

В современном международном праве различают две группы дипломатических привилегий и иммунитетов: представительства в целом как органа государства; сотрудников представительства.

Привилегии и иммунитеты дипломатических представительств:

1. Неприкосновенность помещений дипломатических представительств (ст. 22 Венской конвенции от 1961 года) – территория дипломатического представительства аккредитуемого государства в принимающем государстве считается принадлежащей аккредитуемому государству, без разрешения главы представительства местным властям нельзя проникать в эту территорию. Предположим в здании посольства случился пожар, пожарные могут проникнуть в здание и погасить огонь только с согласия главы представительства. Также власти государства пребывания обязуются охранять помещения посольства от всяких вторжений и нападений.

2. Неприкосновенность архивов, корреспонденции (ст. 24 Венской конвенции от 1961 года) – архивы и иные документы представительства неприкосновенны. Дипломатическая почта не подлежит вскрытию и задержанию, то есть дипломатический курьер пользуется защитой государства пребывания и обладает личной неприкосновенностью на время выполнения своих обязанностей. Посольству обеспечивается свободная связь с властями своего государства для официальных целей.

3. Таможенные привилегии – принимающее государство разрешает ввозить и освобождает от всех таможенных пошлин предметы, предназначенные для официального пользования представительства.

4. Налоговые льготы и преимущества – главы представительства освобождаются от всех налогов и сборов в отношении помещений представительства, за исключением конкретных видов обслуживания.

Личные привилегии и иммунитеты дипломатического персонала:

1. Личная неприкосновенность дипломата (ст. 29 Венской конвенции от 1961 года) – он не подлежит аресту или задержанию в какой бы то ни было форме, государство пребывания должно уважать его личность и защищать от всякого посягательства на его личность и свободу.

2. Неприкосновенность частной резиденции дипломатического агента (ст. 30 Венской конвенции от 1961 года) – место, где он живет пользуется

неприкосновенностью, не подлежит обыску и изъятию. Понятие неприкосновенности частной резиденции предполагает ее распространение на находящиеся в помещении предметы, документы, имущество дипломата. Те же правила распространяются и на транспортные средства дипломата, которые не могут быть подвергнуты обыску и аресту.

3. Уголовный, гражданский и административный иммунитеты – дипломат пользуется иммунитетом от уголовной юрисдикции государства пребывания, то есть не может быть наказан за совершение им преступлений. Также он пользуется иммунитетом от гражданской и административной юрисдикции, кроме случаев, предусмотренных в ст. 31 Венской конвенции от 1961 года.

4. Фискальный иммунитет – орган дипломатического представительства освобождается от прямых государственных налогов и пошлин, за исключением определенных видов налогов и сборов, предусмотренных в ст. 34 конвенции.

5. Таможенные привилегии – личный багаж дипломата освобождается от таможенного осмотра и от уплаты таможенных пошлин (ст. 36 конвенции).

Члены семьи дипломатического агента также пользуются личной неприкосновенностью и другими преимущественными правами, которыми обладает посол, при условии, что они не являются гражданами государства пребывания и совместно проживают.

Дипломатические привилегии и иммунитеты долгое время существовали как устойчивые обычаи международного права, и только с принятием Венской конвенции о дипломатических сношениях 18 апреля 1961 года, были кодифицированы и приобрели официальный характер и нормы, предусмотренные в данной конвенции являются обязательными в соблюдении для всех государств, подписавших конвенцию. Венскую конвенцию подписали и ратифицировали все государства-члены организации ООН за исключением Палау и Южного Судана. Республика Узбекистан присоединилась к настоящей Конвенции в соответствии с постановлением Верховного Совета Республики Узбекистан от 6 мая 1994 года.

Основную часть Венской конвенции о дипломатических сношениях составляют статьи, предусматривающие всю совокупность привилегий и иммунитетов, предоставляемых дипломатическим представительствам и его органам, а также семьям дипломатических агентов и другим работникам администрации представительства (ст. 22 – ст. 37). В теоретической части настоящей работы перечислены и подробно раскрыты данные привилегии и иммунитеты.

В национальном законодательстве Республики Узбекистан также имеются правовые нормы, закрепляющие привилегии и иммунитеты за внешними органами представительства. Постановление Кабинета Министров Республики Узбекистан от 8 мая 2001 года «О деятельности дипломатических

представительств, консульских учреждений иностранных государств, представительств международных организаций и их сотрудников в Республике Узбекистан» охватывает правила и нормы ведения дипломатической деятельности на территории данного государства и адаптирует содержание норм Венской конвенции от 1961 года под национальное законодательство. В главе третьей настоящего Постановления толкуются правовые преимущества внешних органов аккредитующего государства. К примеру, согласно Венской конвенции государство пребывания обязуется защищать лицо представляемого государства, данное утверждение закрепляется и в Постановлении только указывается государственный орган, предоставляющий эту защиту – Национальная гвардия. Схожие разъяснения и дополнения к Венской конвенции от 1961 года, не противоречащие нормам, указанным в ней, предусматривают внутригосударственные законы стран в сфере регулирования дипломатических отношений.

Международная практика сталкивается с рядом проблем и вызовов, вытекающих из применения правовых норм о дипломатических привилегиях и иммунитетах, что является существенным пробелом в сфере дипломатического права и вызывает недовольство общественности, иногда даже приводит к конфликтным ситуациям между странами. В основном конфликтные моменты возникают вследствие пресечения дипломатами тех правовых границ, которые устанавливаются международными нормами.

Во-первых, нормы Венской конвенции не всегда соблюдаются государствами, имеют место случаи нарушения неприкосновенности дипломата, инциденты нападения и убийства послов. 16 декабря 2016 года в Анкаре был убит несколькими выстрелами из пистолета посол России в Турции Андрей Карлов во время выступления на открытии фотовыставки в Галерее современного искусства. В российского посла стрелял турецкий полицейский Мерт Алтынташ, полагают, что это убийство является реакцией на российские бомбежки в Сирии. По Венской конвенции от 1961 года государство пребывания обязуется защищать иностранных представителей, что означает власти Турции не смогли предоставить соответствующей защиты российскому послу.

Во-вторых, иммунитет внешних органов государства от юрисдикции принимающей страны часто приводит к его злоупотреблению. В международной практике участились случаи совершения дипломатами от мелких правонарушений (нарушение правил дорожного движения, вождение в нетрезвом виде) до тяжких преступлений (убийство, сексуальное насилие, наркоторговля), однако благодаря своему иммунитету им удается скрыться от судебного преследования и соответствующей меры наказания. Государство пребывания, законы которого были нарушены дипломатом остаются крайне недовольными, ведь его неправомерными действиями причиняется вред

гражданам и общественному порядку данного государства. Естественно, что, предоставляя дипломату привилегии и иммунитеты, принимающее государство вправе ожидать, что тот, в свою очередь, не будет злоупотреблять своим положением и будет уважать законы, следовать правилам, традициям и обычаям этого государства, избегая вмешательства в его внутренние дела.

В 2009 году посол Украины в Южной Корее Владимир Белашов стал виновником двух дорожно-транспортных происшествий, в которых пострадали местные жители. По данным полиции, посол сначала врезался в другую машину, однако останавливаться не стал и скрылся с места происшествия. Через пять минут он попал в еще одно ДТП, на этот раз авария была серьезной, поскольку южнокорейский водитель попал в больницу с травмами. В сообщениях говорилось, что посол заперся в своей машине на полтора часа и отказался проходить экспресс-тест на наличие алкоголя, сославшись на дипломатический иммунитет. Полицейские не смогли привлечь посла к ответственности.

Проблемы возникают, в основном из-за того, что в международно-правовой системе не предусмотрены универсальные нормы, применяемые в отношении дипломатических агентов при злоупотреблении ими своим правовым статусом. В Венской конвенции лишь указывается обязательство представителя государства соблюдать законы принимающей страны, а в случае их нарушения предусмотрен процесс объявления его персоной *non grata* (от лат. *persona non grata* – нежелательное лицо), выражает недовольство государства пребывания к дипломатическому лицу, а аккредитующее государство должно отозвать данное лицо обратно под свою юрисдикцию. Аккредитующее государство в идеале должно привлечь данное лицо к ответственности в случае совершения им тяжкого преступления после отзыва и лишения его иммунитета, однако на практике такие примеры наблюдаются редко.

Правоохранительные органы Аргентины обнаружили 12 чемоданов с кокаином на территории российского посольства в Буэнос-Айресе. В операции были задействованы и российские полицейские. Совместное расследование длилось больше года в обеих странах. Стоимость этой партии оценивается в 50 млн. евро. Начало масштабной спецоперации положил звонок от российского посла в декабре 2016 года, указывает газета. Дипломат сообщил, что обнаружил наркотики в помещении школы при посольстве. Чемоданы принес сотрудник посольства в июле 2016 года, который в том же году покинул дипмиссию. Расследование установило, что к этому были причастны два человека в Аргентине и трое в России, некоторые из них задержаны. Среди них инспектор полиции Буэнос-Айреса и сотрудник посольства России. Посылки с наркотиком планировалось переправить дипломатической почтой в Россию и некоторые страны Европы.

Исходя из приведенных примеров злоупотребления дипломатами своим статусом, можно сделать вывод, что, пользуясь своим иммунитетом от таможенной и иной проверки, дипломаты могут в своих служебных автомобилях или же в своих чемоданах ввозить в принимающую страну запрещенные товары и их даже не заподозрят в этом, ведь к лицам с дипломатическим статусом обращаются с почтением, они представляются как уважаемые персоны от аккредитующего государства. Абсолютный характер иммунитета дипломата от судебной юрисдикции приводит к тому, что он остается безнаказанным, даже при совершении им тяжких преступлений.

Приведенные примеры злоупотреблений со стороны дипломатов своими привилегиями, выражающиеся в виде совершения преступлений, являются далеко не исчерпывающими. Венская конвенция от 1961 года подлежит реформированию, иммунитеты и привилегии для внешних органов государства должны быть ограничены в определенной степени, нужно предусмотреть нормы и порядок привлечения к уголовной и иной ответственности дипломатов.

Работа дипломата – сложная и опасная работа, связанная со множеством рисков, ведь он выступает от имени государства, к примеру, дипломатическое лицо может вести переговорный процесс во время войны с другим государством, решаясь взяться за эту работу, он рискует своей жизнью и здоровьем, не зная, что ожидать от местных властей той страны, ведь они могут покушаться на его жизнь, в истории не исключены попытки убийства и даже факты убийства послов. Учитывая такие случаи, для представляемого государства важно знать, что лицо, его представляющее будет находиться в безопасности на территории страны пребывания и в случае, чего будет иметь соответствующую защиту, ведь для своего государства дипломат, в первую очередь является гражданином, а уже потом его представителем, а как мы знаем первостепенная задача государства – это защита своих граждан. Именно для этого и между странами определены перечень иммунитетов и преимуществ для их представителей и закреплены в международно-правовых нормах.

Учитывая тот факт, что привилегии предоставляются дипломатическим агентам исключительно для того, чтобы они свободно и полно выполняли свои функции, они не должны допускать злоупотребления ими в своем поведении и действиях. Представители дипломатии являются «alter ego», то есть второе лицо своего государства, выступают они от имени государства и соответственно должны вести себя, пользуясь иммунитетом добросовестно и должны уважать законы государства пребывания, ведь доверительные отношения строятся на взаимном уважении и почтении.

Международное сообщество выражает несогласие с абсолютностью дипломатического иммунитета, ведь дипломат своими неправомерными действиями не только ставит в ущерб свою деятельность в качестве

представителя, но также нарушает права других лиц. Безнаказанность послов нарушает принципы справедливости и неотвратимости наказания, что не может не вызвать негодования местных жителей. Если бы преступление совершил обычный гражданин, то его бы несомненно привлекли к уголовной ответственности, а дипломат же, в свою очередь, не привлекается ни к какой ответственности. Вследствие чего многие дипломаты чувствуют свое превосходство над другими людьми и позволяют себе подобного ненадлежащего поведения.

Вышеуказанные ситуации приводят к необходимости внесения изменений и дополнений в содержание Венской конвенции о дипломатических сношениях, ужесточения норм и реформирования системы дипломатических правоотношений. Международное право должно предпринять строгие меры в отношении регулирования вопросов, касаемо дипломатических привилегий и иммунитетов, и их ограничения для обеспечения справедливости и пресечения злоупотребления дипломатами своим дипломатическим статусом.

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**STRENGTHENING YOUTH PARTICIPATION IN IMPLEMENTATION OF
STARTUPS**

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The President of our country emphasized that "... first of all, we need to educate the new generation of personnel who will be proactive reformers, who think strategically, who will be educated and qualified" [1], in order to turn Uzbekistan into a developed country, only rapid reforms are necessary. , emphasizing the need for aspiring young people in order to achieve knowledge and innovation, he emphasizes the need to educate young people with high intellectual potential as one of the urgent issues of today.

A number of activities are being carried out to help young people acquire the skills to implement innovative ideas, receive advice from a business coach individually, develop and test a minimum working model of the intended product or service, and present their projects to prospective investors. At the same time, it should be recognized that today, not enough attention is paid to attracting graduates of higher education institutions and talented young people to innovative developments, start-up projects, as well as to the creation of business incubators.

Today, a lot of work is being done to accelerate the development of startup projects. It is worth mentioning that the support of youth startups is carried out by the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Youth Union of Uzbekistan and others. Looking at foreign experience, not only state organizations, but also commercial organizations and private companies support them. They implement partnerships through contracts in relation to the benefits that will be seen in the implementation of new innovative ideas.

It is also worth noting that today there are many opportunities for the implementation of start-up projects. In particular, the 11th goal of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on September 11, 2023 "Uzbekistan - 2030 Strategy" No. PF-158 (Increasing the share of young researchers, supporting their scientific research) Goal 56: "Increase the number of annual contests for financing scientific, practical, innovative and startup projects to 20" (consistently transfer monopolistic industries to market principles, increase the share of the private sector in the economy, create the most favorable conditions for entrepreneurs to operate freely) in "Expanding the opportunities for small and medium-sized businesses to enter international markets, developing micro-financing, supporting innovations and startups, and implementing new instruments for developing cooperation with large businesses", goal 57 (developing digital technologies to make the country a regional "Turning into an IT HUB") set the performance indicators of "Releasing the first (Unicorn) startup project with a national market capitalization of 1 billion dollars by

supporting startup projects through the acceleration (development) program of the IT park" year [2].

In addition, in accordance with the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to bring the field of information and communication technologies to a new stage in 2022-2023" dated August 22, 2022 PQ-357, as well as information and communication technologies of young people Decision No. 66 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted in order to further support export-oriented and competitive start-up projects in the world market. According to it:

- Every year from 2023, in order to further support startup projects of young people in the field of information and communication technologies, holding a contest for the President's prize with a total prize fund of 1 million US dollars at the expense of the Fund for the Development of Information and Communication Technologies. that the proposal was approved;

- Approval of the regulation on the procedure for conducting the "Best startup in the field of digital technologies" (President Tech Award) competition for the prize of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

- Confirmation of the composition of the organizing committee for holding the contest "The best startup in the field of digital technologies" (President Tech Award);

it should be noted that starting from May 2023, the competition will be held every year in 5 main and 1 special directions [3].

The role of young people is very important in carrying out this activity. It should be noted that the weight of the youth of Uzbekistan is high in the structure of the country's population, and recognizing their creativity and high intelligence, the potential of young people in the implementation of startups in our country is high.

Today, startups have become one of the most popular options for starting a business among young entrepreneurs and seekers. In the conditions of globalization, the level of development of the business environment in the regions is evaluated based on the number of companies that have succeeded from scratch. Such achievements are taken by businessmen aged 25-30, who have their own views on the organization of the enterprise, many interesting thoughts and promising ideas, and are called representatives of the new wave of business. Young people's interest in information technologies accelerates the adoption of innovative decisions and the introduction of new types of products in this field and in the consumer market. International experience shows that investments in these sectors bring great benefits.

According to S.Ries, a startup is a digital company that prioritizes speed and accuracy in creating a business, but it is a product oriented to create and develop products and services while repeatedly finding suitable business models in the face of uncertainty [4].

P. Graham stated that a startup is a company with a large business model and is designed for rapid growth in a large market [5].

L.A. Vartanova emphasizes the start-up as an innovative project and recognizes it as a company that is at the first stage of development aimed at building a business based on new

ideas or on the basis of emerging technology, hoping to increase revenues and the value of its business [6].

A startup is a newly created, temporary content, an organization engaged in the creation of new goods and services for a short period of time, future reproduction, the search for a profitable, profitable and expandable business model, researching prospective markets in conditions of uncertainty [7].

According to F. Tursunov and Z. Abdulloev, the essence of the startup concept lies in a certain non-standard and original idea, it is the creation of a business model in conditions of extreme uncertainty, and it is the implementation of a similar project that does not yet exist on the Internet or in the field of technology. is aimed at increasing [8].

In addition, there is a need to widely publicize information and analytical data on the essence of startups and what drives them. It is necessary to instill in the minds of young people that the implementation of new innovative ideas is the basis of their socio-economic development.

Today, in the context of the development of digital technologies, one of the urgent issues is to focus investments on the intellectual potential of young people in harmony with modern knowledge. It is the implementation of new innovative projects by young people in terms of start-ups that will serve to carry out great business activities in the future.

Startups are an important factor in the development and implementation of the innovative and intellectual potential of young people, which includes:

- social projects;
- trainings;
- various competitions;
- case methods;
- networked society.

Startups are preferred with relatively more efficient activities, including the positive features of the above elements. Startups that realize the innovative potential of young people are evident in such fields as medicine, information technology, social sphere, and industry.

Usually, the following main criteria are set in the selection of startups:

- creating jobs;
- creation of a working business model;
- the presence of the first consumers-clients.

In current conditions, informativeness, scientific knowledge and initiative play a big role in ensuring socio-economic development. The effective use of these features will educate young people to be flexible, flexible and proactive in terms of their readiness for risk. Such young people are the need of the hour, and investments made in them can be called investments made in the future. If we start building our great future today, we should start it on the basis of innovative ideas and an innovative approach.

The government emphasizes the importance of initiatives of local bodies to support young people and their entrepreneurship, including creating new jobs. Investing in the intellectual potential of young people in the region ensures high results.

According to a number of decrees and decisions of the President, preferential loans are of high importance for young people to engage in entrepreneurship. Through this, our young men and women provide work for themselves and their peers.

During the last 9 months of 2023, preferential loans of 2 trillion 438 billion soums were allocated for the business projects of 121 thousand 547 young people. A system of financing innovative, start-up and business projects of young people interested in entrepreneurship was created. Educational programs have been prepared in this direction, and promising projects of 91 young people worth 44.3 billion soums have been financed to date [9].

In accordance with Appendix 3 of the Decree No. PF-165 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 6, 2022 "On approval of the innovative development strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022 - 2026" implementation of the innovative development strategy in Samarkand region in 2022 - 2026 target indicators have been confirmed [10] (Table 1).

Table 1. Target indicators of implementation of innovative development strategy in Samarkand region in 2022-2026 [10]

Indicators	Unit of measure	2023	2024	2025	2026
Number of innovation centers in the region	unity	3	7	12	18
The number of local industrial enterprises engaged in technological innovations	unity	6	13	21	29
Number of new technologies created in the area	unity	5	10	14	19
Annual number of patents registered in the region	piece	3	5	7	10
The number of scientific, innovative and technological projects implemented in cooperation with foreign organizations	piece	2	6	9	12
The volume of investment in the development and research of the local private sector	million soums	200	460	750	1100
Number of startups	unity	15	44	79	119
Foreign grants for development and research	billion soums	0,8	2,0	3,5	5,9

As can be seen from the table, the target indicators of the implementation of the Strategy in Samarkand region include the following:

- to increase the number of innovation centers in Samarkand region to 18 by increasing them to 15 in 2026 compared to 2023;
- to increase the number of local industrial enterprises engaged in technological innovations from an average of 8 per year in 2023-2026, and to increase their number to 29 in 2026;
- Increase the number of new technologies created in Samarkand region to 19;
- to increase the number of annual registered patents in the region to 10 in 2026;

- increase the number of scientific, innovative and technological projects implemented in cooperation with foreign organizations to 12 in 2026;
- increase the amount of investment in the development and research of the local private sector to 1100 million soums;
- increasing the number of innovative start-ups in Samarkand region to 114 by 2026 compared to 2023;
- The task of increasing the volume of foreign grants allocated for development and research in the region from 0.8 billion soums to 5.9 billion soums in 2026 has been set.

Undoubtedly, education of talented young people is the need of the hour for the economic development of the country. Investing in young people should not start at a certain age, but should be carried out in their education and development from kindergarten and school age. It is desirable to do this not only through state investments, but also in the spirit of creativity based on family circumstances. This will definitely pay off in the future. The main description of startups is the creation of a new innovative product or service.

First of all, educational institutions of the region, including higher education institutions (HEIs), play an important role in the development of talented and innovative young people in the implementation of startup projects and improving the skills of young people. Along with the implementation of innovative projects in Samarkand region, it can be recognized that there are a number of potential HEIs in the region.

Secondly, young people are considered as tomorrow's young entrepreneurs in HEIs, attention is being paid to strengthening intellectual investments, and conditions are being created for them to implement modern start-up projects. One of them is the creation of the "Leader of Innovative Ideas" badge to encourage young people. Emphasis on being a young entrepreneur will also help to solve the problem of employment of young graduates. From the point of view of OTM, the possibility of commercialization of scientific developments will also be created.

Intellectual investments are expressed in the comprehensive development of human capital, that is, in the continuous improvement of their skills and the implementation of new scientific productions.

In order to successfully involve intellectual youth in the implementation of startups, it is necessary to pay attention to the following:

- improvement of the regulatory and legal framework that strengthens mutual relations with youth start-up projects and practice enterprises;
- to support the active organization and operation of small innovative enterprises of young people under HEIs in order to increase the level of theoretical and practical training of young people;
- establishing corporate cooperation relations with large and high-potential enterprises in the region, as well as with young people expressing their desire to work in the future;
- Modernization of the material and technical base of higher education institutions, rational organization of work of scientific laboratories;

- to strengthen the practical training of leading practitioners in their enterprises, to develop methodical manuals;
- In-depth discussion of start-up project models and prototypes at the HEI councils and in practice, considering the level of performance;
- to ensure that necessary skills are acquired by passing qualification practices in foreign HEIs and enterprises.

Of course, startups are not just born in the human mind. To create a good start-up, it is necessary to study previous projects, research foreign experience, develop positive and national aspects that differ from them. Development, testing and mastering of innovative projects-startups for the development of new and high-demand products (work, services), including using advanced methods and technologies used abroad recognized as one of the tasks [11].

It should be recognized that most young people do not know a foreign (English) language (sometimes Russian). Participating in world-class conferences, symposiums, and webinars is reduced due to lack of knowledge of the language or lack of broadening of the worldview. This also affects socio-economic development.

Of course, timely financing plays an important role in the development of startups. Startups that don't get timely and fully funded fail, and ideally, a startup should bounce from one funding wave to another. The most important thing in this direction is to find and attract investors who are ready to finance startups.

Among the negative aspects of the work of young entrepreneurs, it is necessary to recognize the lack of financial literacy and the lameness in presenting the project due to excitement. In addition to just having an idea, it is necessary to have knowledge of such subjects as logic, philosophy, management, financial literacy, analysis, evaluation. Inability to analyze and evaluate the current situation hinders the interest of potential investors.

Therefore, it is desirable to increase financial literacy among young people. With its help, young startups will have the opportunity to exchange ideas with other successful and successful startups at every stage of their startup development.

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**МАТЕРИАЛЛАР ЧОКЛАРИГА ПОЛИМЕР ҚОПЛОВЧИ УСКУНАНИНГ
ТАЖРИБАВИЙ ТАДҚИҚОТЛАР НАТИЖАЛАРИ**

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Аннотация: *Тадқиқотлар асосида қопловчи роликнинг сиқувчи кучи, бурувчи момент, полимер сарфи, қуришиш ҳароратини ўзгариш қонуниятлари тикув машинаси бош валининг турли айланиш частоталарида, брезент материаллари қалинликлари ва маркаларига боғлиқ ҳолда, шунингдек турли полимерлар қўлланилганда берилган. Уларни қўллаш бўйича тавсиялар келтирилган.*

Тажриба натижалари ва таҳлили. Тажриба натижалари оциллограммалар тарзида компьютерда ёзиб олинди (1,2-расмлар).

Сиқувчи роликни ва тикув машинаси бош валини айланиш частоталарини ўзгаришларини ифодаловчи осциллограмма 1-расмда келтирилган, унда пушти ранг чизиқ роликка таъсир қилувчи юкланиш, ҳаво ранг-тепкига нисбатан игнани ҳолат чизиғи. Иккала боғланишларни боғланиши О нуқтаси пушти ранг билан кўрсатилган. Жигар ранг чизиқлар тикув машинаси бош валнинг айланиш частотаси ва бурувчи момент кўрсатилган. Импулслар оралиғи вални бир марта айланиш сонига тенг. Импулснинг ўтиш вақти 0,039 сек. Бунда бош валнинг айланиш частотаси бир минутда 1800 айл/мин. Сиқувчи роликдаги юкланиш 40,177 Н дан 75 Н оралиғида. Шунингдек тўқ ҳаво рангдаги чизиқ қиздириш зонасидаги ҳароратни белгилайди[1].

Оциллограмма (1-расм) тахлилига асосан тикув машинаси бош валидаги бурувчи момент ва айланиш частотаси хар бир чок қадамига боғлиқ равишда ўзгаришини кўриш мумкин.

1 – расм. Тикув машинаси параметрлари ўзгариш қонуниятларини ифодаловчи осциллограмма

Худди шунингдек сиқувчи роликга бўлган юкланиш ҳам деярли шу қонуниятда ўзгаради. Бунда полимер қопламасини амалга оширувчи резинали роликлар ҳамда тикилаётган брезент материалларининг характеристикаларига боғлиқ равишда ушбу параметрлар ўзгариш қонуниятлари олинди. Жумладан, 2а,б-расмларда олинган осциллограммалар келтирилган.

Бунда брезент чокларига қопланадиган полимер композициясини сарфи алоҳида белгиланган, ҳамда, ушбу қопламани қуриштириш зонасидаги ҳарорат ҳам ўлчаб борилган. Сиқувчи ролик резинаси биқирлиги $2,5 \cdot 10^3 \text{Н/м}$ бўлганда унинг юкланишини тебраниш амплитудаси биқирлик коэффиценти $1,25 \cdot 10^3 \text{Н/м}$ бўлганига нисбатан деярли $1,7 \div 1,8$ марта камроқ бўлганини кўриш мумкин. Мос равишда ролик босимининг ортиши полимер сарфини ҳам камайишига олиб келади. Бунинг асосий сабаби ролик резинаси биқирлиги юқори бўлганида, унинг деформацияланиши камаяди, брезент юзаси билан кантакт юзаси ҳам камаяди.

а-Бош валнинг айланиш частотаси 4000 мин^{-1} . Резинли валик учун $c=2,5 \cdot 10^3 \text{Н/м}$ (ПВ,ОП,СКПВ) маркали брезентлар учун. $t=65^\circ \div 70^\circ$

б-Бош валнинг айланиш частотаси 3500 мин^{-1} ва резина $c=1,25 \cdot 10^3 \text{Н/м}$.
 $t=65^\circ \div 70^\circ$

2-расм. Ускуна ролигини сиқувчи кучи f_0 валидаги бурувчи моментни ўзгаришларини ролик қайишқоқ втулка биқирлигига боғлиқ равишда ўзгариш қонуниятлари

Полимер қопламасини қуриштириш зонасидаги ҳарорат $65^\circ \div 70^\circ$ атрофида бўлиши аниқланди. Олинган осциллограммаларни қайта ишлаб боғланиш графиклари қурилди. 2-расмда брезент чокларига полимер композитни қоплаш ускунаси ролигидаги сиқувчи куч ва бурувчи момент ўзгаришларини ролик

резинаси втулкасининг бикирлик коэффицентига боғлиқлик графиклари келтирилган.

1,2, $t - P = f(c)$; $t - P = f(c)$; 3,4,5- $M_{pb} = f(c)$; 1,2,3,4- тажрибавий; 5,6- назарий
 1,3- $n_{б,в} = 5000$ айл/мин; 2,4- $n_{б,в} = 3500$ айл/мин. $t = 65^\circ \div 70^\circ$

3-расм. Брезент чокларига полимер композитни қоплаш ускунаси ролигидаги сиқувчи куч ва буровчи момент ўзгаришларини ролик резинаси втулкасининг бикирлик коэффицентига боғлиқлик графиклари

Графиклар таҳлиliga асосан сиқувчи ролик резинали втулкаси бикирлиги коэффицентига $0,85 \cdot 10^3 \text{ Нм}$ дан $2,15 \cdot 10^3 \text{ Нм}$ гача кўпайганида роликдаги юкланиш $n_{б,в} = 3500$ айл/мин да $0,14 \text{ Н}$ дан $0,48 \text{ Н}$ гача ортади, бош валдаги бурувчи момент $0,42 \cdot 10 \text{ Нм}$ дан $0,63 \text{ Нм}$ гача нозизиқли қонуниятда ортишини кўриш мумкин. Бош вал айланиш частотаси 5000 айл/мин бўлганида P нинг қийматлари $0,26 \text{ Н}$ дан $0,74 \text{ Н}$ гача ортса, $M_{б,в}$ қийматлари $0,61 \cdot 10 \text{ Нм}$ дан $0,79 \cdot 10 \text{ Нм}$ гача ортиб боради. Бунинг асосий сабаби роликни брезент сирти билан таъсирларидаги куч ортади, демак тикув машинаси бош валига тушадиган юкланиш ҳам ортади. Лекин чокларга қопланаётган полимер композитнинг сарфини $(0,2 \div 0,3) \text{ мг/см}^2$ дан ошганлигини, қуритиш тўлиқ бўлишини таъминлаш учун қопловчи роликлар резинаси втулкаси бикирлик коэффицентининг қийматлари $(1,9 \div 2,3) \cdot 10^3 \text{ Н/м}$ оралиғида бўлиши тавсия этилади. Таъкидлаш лозимки, олинган графиклар таҳлиliga кўра назарий ва тажрибавий натижалар фарқи $(6,5 \div 8,2) \%$ дан ошмайди. (3-расм, 4,5 ва 1,6-графиклар).

а-Брезентларни тикишдаги осциллограмма ёзуви

а

Бош вал айланиш частотаси 3000 мин⁻¹. Резинли валик учун бикрлик коэффиценти $c=1,5 \cdot 10^3 \text{Н/м}$. (ПВ,ОП,СКПВ) маркали брезентлар учун, $h=3,0 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{м}$; $t=70^\circ \div 75^\circ$

6

б-Брезентларни тикишдаги осциллограмма ёзуви

Бош вал айланиш частотаси 5000 мин⁻¹. Резинли валик учун бикрлик коэффиценти $c=2,0 \cdot 10^3 \text{Н/м}$. (ПВ,ОП,СКПВ) маркали брезентлар учун, $h=5,0 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{м}$; $t=70^\circ \div 75^\circ$

4-расм. Полимер композиция қоплагич ролиги айланиш частотасини ва тикилган брезент материаллари қалинлигини ўқдаги сиқувчи куч ва полимер композициясини сарфига боғлиқлик қонуниятлари

Маълумки тикилган брезент материаллари қалинлиги ортиши полимер қопловчи роликларга, шунингдек бош валга тушадиган юкланишларни сезиларли даражада ортишига олиб келади. Жумладан 4-расмда брезент материаллари қалинлиги 3мм ва 5мм вариантларда олинган осциллограммалар намуналари келтирилган. Бунда $M_{б,в}$ ва P ни тебраниш амплитудаларини камайтириш учун $h=5\text{мм}$ бўлганда ролик резинали втулкаси бикрлик коэффиценти кўтарилиб $2,0 \cdot 10^3 \text{Н/м}$ қилиб олинган. Осциллограммаларга асосан қурилган графиклар 6-расмда берилган[2].

1,2- $m_n=f(n)$; 3,4- $p=f(n)$; 1,3- $h=5,0 \cdot 10^{-3}$; 2,4- $h=3,0 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{м}$; $t=70^\circ \div 75^\circ$

5-расм. Ускуна ролигидаги сиқувчи куч ва полимер композицияси сарфини бош вал айланиш частотасига ва брезент материали қалинлигига боғлиқлик графиклари

Тикув машинаси бош вали айланиш частотаси 2500 айл/мин дан 5000 айл/мин гача кўпайганида полимер қоплаш ролигидаги юкланиш $h=3,0 \cdot 10^{-3}$ м да P қийматлари 0,25 Н дан 1,1 Н гача нозизиқли қонуниятда ортиб борса, $h=5,0 \cdot 10^{-3}$ м бўлганида P қийматлари 1,51 Н дан 2,7 Н гача кўпайди. Бунда қуритиш зонасидаги ҳарорат $70^\circ \div 75^\circ$ гача ортади. Чунки тезлик ортиши билан полимерни қуритиш секинлашади. Шунинг учун ҳарорат оширилди. Мос равишда тезлик ортиши билан полимер сарфи сезиларли даражада кўпаяди. Бунинг асосий сабаби, ролик айланиш тезлиги брезентни суриш тезлигидан уларни ўзаро сирпаниши туфайли бироз камаяди, бу эса, полимер сарфини орттиради (5-расм, 1,2-графиклар).

а-Тикув машинаси етакчи ролик валидаги моментни ўзгариши ва сиқувчи валикдаги юкланишни ўзгаришининг осциллограмма ёзуви.

Полимер сарфи 0,125 мл/сек. Резина учун $c=1,5 \cdot 10^3$ Н/м (ПВ, ОП, СКПВ) маркали брезентлар учун. $h=3,5 \cdot 10^{-3}$ м.

б-Тикув машинаси етакловчи ролиги валидаги моментни ўзгариши ва сиқувчи валикдаги юкланишни ўзгаришининг осциллограмма ёзуви.

Полимер сарфи 0,25 мл/сек. Резина учун $c=1,2 \cdot 10^3$ Н/м (ПВ, ОП, СКПВ) маркали брезентлар учун. $h=5,0 \cdot 10^{-3}$ м.

6-расм. Тикилаётган брезент материаллари қалинлигига қараб сиқувчи ролик юкланиши ва полимер сарфини ифодаловчи осциллограммалар

Полимер сарфини (0,2÷0,3) мг/см² оралиғида бўлишини таъминлаш учун бош вални айланиш частотаси (3500÷4500) айл/мин оралиғида бўлиши тавсия этилади.

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu tadqiqot respondentlarning muhabbat tushunchasiga bo'lgan qarashlarini o'rganishga qaratilgan bo'lib, yosh, jins, ijtimoiy maqom va oilaviy holat kabi omillarning ta'sirini tahlil qiladi. So'rovnoma natijalari muhabbatning inson hayotidagi o'rni, nikoh bilan bog'liqligi, an'anaviy qadriyatlar va zamonaviy texnologiyalar ta'siri nuqtai nazaridan har xil talqin qilinishini ko'rsatdi. Shuningdek, erkak va ayollarning muhabbatga nisbatan munosabatidagi farqlar ham ochib berildi. Tadqiqot natijalari muhabbat tushunchasining zamonaviy jamiyatda qanday qabul qilinayotganini aniqlashga yordam beradi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *muhabbat, nikoh, ijtimoiy qadriyatlar, yosh farqlari, gender tafovutlari, zamonaviy texnologiyalar, jamiyat evolyutsiyasi.*

Annotation: *This study examines respondents' perceptions of the concept of love, analyzing the influence of factors such as age, gender, social status, and marital status. The survey results show that love is interpreted differently in terms of its role in human life, its connection to marriage, traditional values, and the impact of modern technologies. Additionally, differences in how men and women perceive love are highlighted. The findings help to understand how the concept of love is perceived in contemporary society.*

Keywords: *love, marriage, social values, age differences, gender disparities, modern technologies, social evolution.*

Аннотация: *В данном исследовании рассматриваются представления респондентов о понятии любви, анализируется влияние таких факторов, как возраст, пол, социальный статус и семейное положение. Результаты опроса показывают, что любовь по-разному интерпретируется с точки зрения её роли в жизни человека, связи с браком, традиционными ценностями и влияния современных технологий. Кроме того, выявлены различия в восприятии любви мужчинами и женщинами. Полученные данные помогают понять, как концепция любви воспринимается в современном обществе.*

Ключевые слова: *любовь, брак, социальные ценности, возрастные различия, гендерные различия, современные технологии, эволюция общества.*

KIRISH

O'zbek xalqining madaniyati va an'analari asrlar davomida shakllanib, milliy o'ziga xoslikka xos etnopsixologik xususiyatlarni o'zida mujassam etgan. Bu xususiyatlar o'zbek xalqining kundalik hayotida, oila va shaxslararo munosabatlar haqidagi tushunchalarida yaqqol namoyon bo'ladi. Xususan, o'zbek jamiyatida ishq mavzusi nafaqat hissiy holat, balki ijtimoiy, axloqiy, madaniy hodisa sifatida ham alohida o'rin tutadi. O'zbek urf-odatlarida sevgi oila mustahkamligi, sadoqat va hurmat tushunchalari bilan chambarchas bog'liq

bo'lib, uning turli ifoda shakllari turmush tarzi, jins munosabatlari va zamonaviy qarashlarga ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi o'zbek etnopsixologiyasida ishq mavzusini o'rganish va an'anaviy va zamonaviy qarashlar o'rtasidagi o'zgarishlarni tahlil qilishdan iborat. Tadqiqotda dala tadqiqoti usuli qo'llanildi va ishtirokchilarning sevgi, oilaviy qadriyatlar va hissiy bog'lanish tushunchalari haqidagi qarashlari maxsus anketa orqali o'rganildi. O'rganish natijalari o'zbek jamiyatida muhabbat qanday qabul qilinishi, uning oilaviy munosabatlardagi o'rni va yosh avlodning bu masalaga munosabatini aniqlab beradi.

METODOLOGIYA

Ushbu tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi o'zbek xalqining etnopsixologiyasida muhabbat tushunchasi qanday shakllanganini va u zamonaviy jamiyatda qanday talqin qilinishini o'rganishdan iborat. Shu bois, tadqiqot sifatli va miqdoriy yondashuvlarning uyg'unlashuvi asosida olib borildi. Tadqiqot doirasida respondentlarning muhabbatga bo'lgan qarashlari, oilaviy qadriyatlarga nisbatan munosabatlari va hissiy bog'lanish tushunchasi o'rganildi.

Tadqiqotda turli ijtimoiy guruhlarga mansub respondentlar ishtirok etdi. Respondentlarning jinsiy mansubligi qayd etildi, biroq shaxsiy ma'lumotlari maxfiy saqlandi. Respondentlar orasida talabalar, ishchilar, o'qituvchilar, xususiy tadbirkorlar, uy bekalari va davlat xizmatchilari ishtirok etdi. Ishtirokchilarning yosh diapazoni 18 yoshdan 60 yoshgacha bo'lib, bu yoshlar o'rtasidagi muhabbat tushunchalarining tafovutlarini aniqlashga imkon berdi. Tadqiqot geografik jihatdan O'zbekistonning bir nechta hududlarini qamrab oldi, shuningdek, shaharlik va qishloq aholisi o'rtasidagi farqlar ham tahlil qilindi.

1-diagramma

Tadqiqotning asosiy metodi sifatida so'rovnoma ishlatildi. So'rovnoma yopiq shaklda tuzilgan bo'lib, respondentlarga berilgan savollarga faqat oldindan belgilangan variantlar orqali javob berish imkoni berildi. Ushbu yondashuv natijalarning tizimli tahlil qilinishiga va statistik ishlov berishga imkon yaratdi. So'rovnoma yuzma-yuz suhbat shaklida

o'tkazildi. Har bir respondent bilan shaxsan uchrashib, savollar o'qib eshittirildi va ularning javoblari qayd etildi. Bu usul respondentlarning to'g'ri tushunishini ta'minlash, aniq va ishonchli javob olish hamda barcha savollar bo'yicha to'liq javoblarni yig'ish imkonini berdi.

So'rovnoma quyidagi tematik bloklardan tashkil topdi: muhabbat tushunchasining talqini, muhabbat va oilaviy qadriyatlar, gender farqlari hamda zamonaviylik va an'anaviylik. To'plangan ma'lumotlar bir necha bosqichda tahlil qilindi. Deskriptiv statistika asosida har bir savol bo'yicha foiz ko'rsatkichlari hisoblandi, respondentlarning jinsi, yoshi va kasbiy faoliyatiga qarab natijalar taqqoslandi. Chi-kvadrat testi yordamida jinsi va yoshi bo'yicha javoblar orasidagi bog'liqlik tekshirildi. Korrelatsion tahlil esa muhabbatga bo'lgan qarashlar bilan respondentlarning ijtimoiy maqomi o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni o'rganishga yordam berdi.

Bundan tashqari, sifatli tahlil amalga oshirilib, ayrim respondentlarning javoblari chuqurroq tahlil qilindi. Kross-tabulyatsiya orqali yosh guruhlari va muhabbat haqidagi qarashlar o'zaro solishtirildi. Grafik vizualizatsiya natijalarni yanada tushunarli qilish uchun diagrammalar va grafiklar orqali ifodalandi.

2- diagramma

Ushbu tadqiqot yuzma-yuz so'rovnoma orqali o'tkazilganligi sababli, ba'zi cheklovlar mavjud. Subyektiv javoblar ehtimoli yuqori bo'lib, respondentlar o'z javoblarini jamiyatdagi umumiy qabul qilingan me'yorlarga mos ravishda berishga harakat qilgan bo'lishi mumkin. Tadqiqot ma'lum hudud va ijtimoiy guruhlarga asoslangan bo'lib, umumiy xulosalarni butun mamlakatga tatbiq etish ma'lum ehtiyotkorlikni talab qiladi. Yopiq savollar esa respondentlarning fikrlarini to'liq yoritib bera olmasligi mumkin.

Ushbu metodologik yondashuv yordamida o'zbek xalqining etnopsixologiyasida muhabbat tushunchasi bo'yicha aniq va tizimli natijalarga erishish imkoniyati yaratildi.

Tadqiqot natijalari orqali muhabbatning ijtimoiy, madaniy va shaxsiy hayotga ta'siri o'rganilib, yoshlar va katta avlod vakillarining qarashlari orasidagi tafovutlar ochib berildi.

NATIJA VA TAHLIL

Tadqiqot davomida to'plangan ma'lumotlar respondentlarning muhabbat tushunchasiga bo'lgan munosabatida turli xil omillar ta'sir qilishi va bu omillar jins, yosh, ijtimoiy maqom hamda oilaviy holat bilan bog'liq ekanini ko'rsatdi. Quyida natijalar asosiy yo'nalishlar bo'yicha batafsil tahlil qilinadi. Muhabbat tushunchasi: umumiy qarashlar So'rovnoma natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, respondentlarning aksariyati muhabbatni inson hayotining ajralmas qismi sifatida qabul qiladi. 85% respondent muhabbatni insoniy munosabatlarning muhim tarkibiy qismi deb baholagan bo'lsa, 10% respondent unga shubha bilan qarashini bildirgan. Qolgan 5% esa muhabbatni insonning hayotidagi ikkilamchi omil sifatida baholagan. Erkak respondentlarning 78% muhabbat hayotda muhim o'rin tutishini ta'kidlagan bo'lsa, ayol respondentlar orasida bu ko'rsatkich 92%ni tashkil etdi. Yosh guruhlari bo'yicha tahlil qilinganda, 18-25 yosh oralig'idagi respondentlar orasida muhabbatga bo'lgan ishonch ancha yuqori bo'lsa (88%), 40 yoshdan oshgan respondentlar orasida bu ko'rsatkich 72%ga tushgan. Bu natijalar yosh oshgani sari muhabbatga bo'lgan qarash biroz o'zgarib, yanada pragmatik tus olishini ko'rsatadi.

Muhabbat va nikoh o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik So'rovnomada qatnashganlarning 67%i muhabbatni nikoh uchun asosiy omil deb hisoblaydi. Biroq 33% respondentlar muhabbatni nikohdan ustun qo'ymasligini va turmush qurishda boshqa omillar (masalan, moliyaviy barqarorlik, o'zaro hurmat, madaniy muvofiqlik) ham katta ahamiyatga ega ekanligini ta'kidladi. Ayollar orasida muhabbatning nikohdagi o'rni 70% muhim deb baholangan, erkaklar orasida esa bu ko'rsatkich 63%ni tashkil etdi. Yosh guruhlar orasida 18-30 yoshdagi respondentlarning 75%i nikoh muhabbatsiz barqaror bo'lishi qiyin deb hisoblagan bo'lsa, 40 yoshdan katta respondentlarning 48%i muhabbatsiz ham nikoh mustahkam bo'lishi mumkinligini qayd etdi. Bu natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, yoshlar muhabbatni nikohning asosi deb hisoblashadi, biroq yoshi kattaroq respondentlar hayotiy tajribalariga tayanib, turmushni davom ettirish uchun faqat muhabbat yetarli emasligini ta'kidlashgan.

3- diagramma

Muhabbat va an'anaviy qadriyatlar So'rovnoma natijalari respondentlarning muhabbatni an'anaviy qadriyatlar bilan bog'lash darajasi turlicha ekanini ko'rsatdi. 60% respondent muhabbat faqat turmush qurish doirasida bo'lishi kerakligini ta'kidlagan bo'lsa, 40% respondent muhabbat insoniy tuyg'u bo'lib, u turmush qurish bilan cheklanmasligi kerakligini qayd etdi. Ayollar orasida 65% muhabbat turmush doirasida bo'lishi kerak deb hisoblagan, erkaklar orasida esa bu ko'rsatkich 55%ni tashkil etdi. Yoshlar orasida 18-25 yoshdagi respondentlarning 48%i muhabbatni an'anaviy qadriyatlarga bog'lagan bo'lsa, 40 yoshdan katta respondentlar orasida bu ko'rsatkich 73%ga yetgan. Bu natijalar yoshlar orasida muhabbatga nisbatan erkinroq qarash shakllanayotganini, yoshi kattalar esa uni ko'proq an'anaviy qadriyatlar bilan bog'lashini ko'rsatadi.

Gender farqlari: Erkaklar va ayollar qarashlari Tadqiqot natijalari erkak va ayollar muhabbatni turlicha talqin qilishini ko'rsatdi. Erkak respondentlarning 70%i muhabbat - bu o'zaro ishonch va hurmat degan fikrni ilgari surdi, ayollarda esa bu ko'rsatkich 85%ni tashkil etdi. Ayollar orasida romantikaga e'tibor beruvchi respondentlar 75%ni tashkil qilgan bo'lsa, erkaklar orasida bu ko'rsatkich 60% atrofida bo'ldi. Erkaklarning 62%i muhabbatning vaqt o'tishi bilan kuchsizlanishi tabiiy deb hisoblasa, ayollarda bu fikrni qo'llab-quvvatlovchilar 50%ni tashkil etdi. Bu natijalar shuni anglatadiki, ayollar muhabbatga ko'proq hissiy yondashishadi, erkaklar esa uni hayotning bir qismi sifatida, lekin o'zgaruvchan holat deb hisoblashadi.

Muhabbat va zamonaviy tendensiyalar Respondentlarning zamonaviy texnologiyalar muhabbatga ta'siri haqidagi fikrlari turlicha bo'ldi. 40% respondent zamonaviy texnologiyalar (internet, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, smartfonlar) muhabbatni mustahkamlashga yordam beradi deb hisoblagan. 45% respondent esa texnologiyalar odamlar o'rtasidagi hissiy bog'lanishga zarar yetkazayotganini ta'kidlagan. 15% respondent esa bu omilni unchalik ahamiyatli deb hisoblamagan. Bu natijalar hozirgi zamon texnologiyalarining insoniy munosabatlarga ta'siri haqida turli qarashlar mavjudligini ko'rsatadi.

Zamonaviy texnologiyalarning muhabbatga ta'siri

4- diagramma

Muhabbatga bo'lgan qarashlarning yosh guruhlariga bog'liqligi So'rovnoma natijalari yosh guruhlariga qarab quyidagi umumiy tendensiyalarni aniqladi: 18-25 yoshdagilar muhabbatni romantik va hissiy bog'lanish sifatida tasvirlashgan. 26-40 yosh orasidagi respondentlar muhabbatga nisbatan yanada realistik qarashga ega bo'lib, uni oila va majburiyatlar bilan bog'lashgan. 40 yoshdan katta respondentlar esa muhabbatni uzoq muddatli sheriklik, o'zaro ishonch va hayotiy barqarorlik bilan bog'lashgan.

Xulosa Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, muhabbat tushunchasi respondentlarning yoshiga, jinsi va ijtimoiy maqomiga qarab farqlanadi. Yosh respondentlar muhabbatni asosan hissiyot va romantikaga bog'lashsa, yoshi kattaroq respondentlar uchun muhabbat ko'proq hayotiy tajriba va sheriklik bilan bog'liq. Shuningdek, muhabbatning nikoh va an'anaviy qadriyatlar bilan aloqadorligi masalasida ham respondentlarning qarashlari turlicha bo'lib, bu masala bo'yicha aniq ijtimoiy tafovutlar kuzatildi. Tadqiqot natijalari muhabbat tushunchasining jamiyatdagi evolyutsiyasini aks ettirib, uning zamonaviy jamiyatda qanday qabul qilinayotganini ko'rsatishga yordam berdi.

MUNOZARA

O'tkazilgan tadqiqot natijalari jamiyatda oila institutining barqarorligi va oilaviy munosabatlarning rivojlanishiga qaratilgan dolzarb muammolarni o'z ichiga oladi. Tadqiqotimizning eng asosiy xulosalaridan biri shundaki, oilaviy qadriyatlarning shakllanishida turli ijtimoiy va psixologik omillar muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ayniqsa, O'zbekiston Respublikasining Oila kodeksi (1998) va XXI asr oilasi konsepsiyasi (2002) oilaviy tarbiyaning asosiy tamoyillarini belgilab bergan bo'lsa-da, zamonaviy sharoitda bu tamoyillarni qo'llashda turli muammolar mavjud.

Tadqiqot natijalari O'zbekistonda oilaning jamiyatdagi roli va ahamiyatini o'rganishga bag'ishlangan bir qator ilmiy manbalar bilan hamohang. Masalan, Fitrat (1998) tomonidan ilgari surilgan oilaviy boshqaruv tizimi va ota-onalarning tarbiyadagi mas'uliyati haqidagi qarashlar bugungi kun sharoitida ham o'z dolzarbligini yo'qotmagan. Biroq, zamonaviy ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy sharoitlarda oilaviy munosabatlarga ta'sir etuvchi yangi omillar paydo bo'lganligi kuzatilmoqda.

Natijalarga ko'ra, respondentlarning aksariyati oilaviy qadriyatlarning saqlanishi jamiyat barqarorligi uchun muhim deb hisoblaydi. Bu xulosa Shari'ova va Semyonova (1983) tomonidan ilgari surilgan gigienik tarbiya va oilaviy muhitning inson psixologiyasiga ta'siri haqidagi tadqiqotlar bilan mos keladi. Tadqiqotimizda yuzma-yuz o'tkazilgan so'rov natijalari respondentlarning o'z fikrlarini ochiq-oydin ifoda etishiga imkon berdi va turli ijtimoiy guruh vakillarining (talabalar, ishchilar va boshqalar) oilaga munosabatidagi farqlarni o'rganishga yordam berdi.

Boshqa tadqiqotlar bilan solishtirilganda, Toshpo'latova (2022) tomonidan olib borilgan tadqiqot natijalariga yaqin xulosalar olinmoqda. Uning tadqiqotida ota-onalarning oiladagi vazifalari va ularning farzand tarbiyasiga ta'siri o'rganilgan bo'lib, bizning tadqiqotimizda ham bu omillar muhim ahamiyat kasb etdi. Shu bilan birga, Yaxshiyeva va boshqalar (2015) ilmiy dunyoqarashni shakllantirishda oilaning rolini o'rganishgan va bu bizning natijalarimizga qo'shimcha ilmiy asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Umuman olganda, tadqiqotimiz oilaviy qadriyatlarning zamonaviy jamiyatda o'zgarish dinamikasini chuqur yoritib, o'zbek oilasining ijtimoiy-psixologik jihatlarini tahlil qilishda muhim ilmiy ahamiyatga ega. Ushbu mavzudagi tadqiqotlarni yanada kengaytirish va oilaviy munosabatlarning zamonaviy sharoitdagi o'zgarishlarini chuqurroq o'rganish istiqbolli yo'nalishlardan biri sifatida ko'rib chiqilishi lozim.

XULOSA

Ushbu tadqiqot natijalari oilaviy qadriyatlarning jamiyat taraqqiyotidagi o'rni va ularning zamonaviy sharoitlarda qanday o'zgarayotganini ochib berishga qaratildi. Tadqiqot davomida jamiyatning turli qatlamlari vakillaridan olingan ma'lumotlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, oilaning barqarorligi va uning ichki tuzilishi bevosita ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, madaniy va psixologik omillar bilan bog'liq. Respondentlarning aksariyati oila jamiyatning asosiy bo'g'ini ekanini e'tirof etib, uning mustahkamligi inson hayoti va kelajak avlod tarbiyasida muhim omil ekanligini ta'kidlashdi.

O'zbekiston Respublikasining Oila kodeksi (1998), XXI asr oilasi konsepsiyasi (2002) hamda boshqa ilmiy-adabiy manbalarda oilaning jamiyatdagi roli va ahamiyati keng yoritilgan. Ushbu tadqiqot natijalari mavjud ilmiy adabiyotlar bilan uyg'un bo'lib, Fitrat, Shari'ova va Semyonova (1983), Toshpo'latova (2022) va Yaxshiyeva va boshqalar (2015) tomonidan olib borilgan tadqiqotlarning xulosalariga mos keladi. Shu bilan birga, tadqiqotimiz zamonaviy o'zgarishlar va oilaviy qadriyatlarning yangi shakllarini o'rganishga yo'naltirilgani bilan ajralib turadi.

Tadqiqot natijalaridan kelib chiqib, quyidagi muhim xulosalarga kelish mumkin:

- oila jamiyatning asosi - insonning ijtimoiy shakllanishida, ma'naviy va axloqiy qadriyatlarni shakllantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

- oilaviy qadriyatlarning o'zgarishi - zamonaviy jamiyatdagi iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy o'zgarishlar oilaviy qadriyatlarga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda, bu esa an'anaviy tarbiya uslublarini qayta ko'rib chiqishni talab qiladi.

- ijtimoiy guruhlar o'rtasidagi farqlar - talabalar, ishchilar va boshqa turli kasb egalari oilaga turlicha yondashadi, bu esa oilaviy qadriyatlarning ahamiyatini anglash darajasi turlicha ekanligini ko'rsatadi.

- ota-onalarning tarbiyadagi roli - oilada ota-onalarning tarbiyaviy vazifalari kuchayib borishi bilan, ularning psixologik, ma'naviy va pedagogik tayyorgarligi ham dolzarb masala sifatida maydonga chiqmoqda.

- ilmiy-amaliy yondashuv zarurati - oilaviy qadriyatlarni saqlab qolish va rivojlantirish uchun nafaqat an'anaviy, balki zamonaviy yondashuvlardan ham foydalanish zarur.

Mazkur tadqiqot oilaviy qadriyatlarning o'zgarishi va ularning jamiyatdagi ahamiyatini chuqur anglashga xizmat qilishi bilan ilmiy va amaliy ahamiyatga ega. Kelajak tadqiqotlar oiladagi o'zaro munosabatlarning ijtimoiy-madaniy transformatsiyasi va uning yosh avlod tarbiyasiga ta'siri kabi masalalarni yanada chuqurroq o'rganishga qaratilishi lozim.

Shu boisdan, oilaviy qadriyatlarni chuqur o'rganish va ularni zamonaviy jamiyat sharoitlariga mos ravishda mustahkamlash bugungi kunning dolzarb vazifalaridan biri bo'lib qolmoqda.

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**СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ К ХИРУРГИЧЕСКОМУ ЛЕЧЕНИЮ
ПРИВЫЧНОГО ВЫВИХА ПЛЕЧЕВОГО СУСТАВА**

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Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются современные методы хирургического лечения привычного вывиха плечевого сустава, с акцентом на новый метод оперативного вмешательства. Проведен комплексный анализ медицинской, социальной и экономической эффективности данного подхода, учитывающий снижение частоты рецидивов, восстановление функциональных возможностей плечевого сустава и сокращение сроков реабилитации. Приведены результаты клинических исследований, демонстрирующие значительное улучшение качества жизни пациентов после хирургического вмешательства. Рассматриваются особенности методики, её преимущества перед традиционными подходами, а также перспективы дальнейшего внедрения и совершенствования в клинической практике.

Ключевые слова: привычный вывих плечевого сустава, хирургическое лечение, эффективность, реабилитация, функциональное восстановление, минимизация рецидивов, медицинская статистика.

**MODERN APPROACHES TO SURGICAL TREATMENT OF RECURRENT
SHOULDER DISLOCATION**

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Abstract: The article discusses modern methods of surgical treatment for recurrent shoulder dislocation, with a focus on a new surgical intervention technique. A comprehensive analysis of the medical,

social, and economic effectiveness of this approach is presented, considering the reduction in recurrence rates, restoration of shoulder joint functionality, and shortening of rehabilitation periods. The results of clinical studies are provided, demonstrating significant improvements in patients' quality of life after surgical intervention. The features of the methodology, its advantages over traditional approaches, as well as prospects for further implementation and improvement in clinical practice, are examined.

Keywords: *recurrent shoulder dislocation, surgical treatment, effectiveness, rehabilitation, functional recovery, recurrence minimization, medical statistics.*

ВВЕДЕНИЕ

Плечевой сустав является одним из наиболее мобильных и сложных суставов организма, но именно эта подвижность делает его уязвимым к вывихам. Вывихи плеча составляют 50-60% от всех вывихов суставов, и их частота особенно высока у людей, ведущих активный образ жизни. Основными причинами являются перенесённые травмы, анатомические особенности и врождённые дисплазии суставов.

Травматический вывих плеча нередко сопровождается повреждением суставной губы, что приводит к развитию хронической нестабильности. Частота рецидива после первичного травматического вывиха составляет от 2% до 38%, а у молодых физически активных людей этот показатель может превышать 70%. Наиболее распространённой формой является передний травматический вывих, который составляет более 90% всех случаев и нередко приводит к повторным вывихам.

Военнослужащие входят в группу повышенного риска, так как их профессиональная деятельность связана с регулярными физическими нагрузками, контактными видами спорта и интенсивной боевой подготовкой. Повторяющиеся вывихи плечевого сустава могут существенно снижать боеспособность военнослужащих, приводить к длительному снижению трудоспособности и даже инвалидности. Это делает проблему не только медицинской, но и социальной.

Консервативное лечение привычного вывиха плечевого сустава показывает низкую эффективность, особенно у молодых и физически активных пациентов. В связи с этим хирургическое вмешательство остаётся основным методом лечения. Однако, несмотря на существование более 250 видов хирургических вмешательств, в клинической практике продолжают встречаться случаи рецидивов, что требует поиска новых, более эффективных решений.

Настоящее исследование направлено на оценку эффективности нового метода хирургического лечения привычного вывиха плечевого сустава. В работе использованы клинические данные 93 пациентов, прооперированных в медицинских учреждениях Узбекистана в период с 2017 по 2023 год. Оценка эффективности проводилась по трем основным направлениям:

1. Анатомо-функциональные характеристики – восстановление подвижности сустава, стабильности плечевого пояса и тонуса мышц.

2. Рентгенологические и инструментальные показатели – изменения структуры сустава, состояние суставной капсулы и уровень артрозных изменений.

3. Социальная и экономическая эффективность – снижение частоты рецидивов, улучшение качества жизни пациентов, сокращение реабилитационного периода и снижение затрат на повторные вмешательства.

Результаты исследования позволяют судить о перспективах внедрения новой хирургической методики, её преимуществах перед традиционными подходами и возможности её дальнейшего совершенствования.

Методы. Для объективной оценки эффективности хирургического лечения привычного вывиха плечевого сустава была разработана система количественного анализа, включающая три основных направления:

1. Оценка операционного вмешательства – анализ продолжительности операции, наличия мышечной дистрофии и состояния суставной капсулы.

2. Анатомо-функциональная оценка плечевого пояса – измерение углов сгибания, разгибания и отведения в плечевом суставе, оценка симметричности плечевого пояса и тонуса дельтовидной мышцы.

3. Оценка структурных изменений плечевого сустава – рентгенологический анализ просвета суставной щели, степени артроза и деформации суставных элементов.

Каждый параметр оценивался по бальной шкале (от 0 до 4), что позволило суммировать баллы и классифицировать эффективность хирургического вмешательства в одну из четырех категорий: низкий, умеренный, средний и высокий уровень.

Для сбора данных использовались клинические и инструментальные методы:

- Полипозиционная рентгенография, компьютерная томография (КТ) и магнитно-резонансная томография (МРТ) для оценки состояния суставных структур.

- Физикальное обследование для измерения функциональных характеристик плечевого сустава.

- Анализ послеоперационных данных в течение 1–3 суток после вмешательства.

Разработанная методика позволяет не только объективизировать результаты операции, но и прогнозировать вероятность рецидивов, корректировать реабилитационные мероприятия и принимать решение о необходимости повторного хирургического вмешательства.

Основная часть. Новый метод хирургического лечения привычного вывиха плечевого сустава. Все респонденты были прооперированы по собственной методике хирургического лечения обычного вывиха плечевого сустава (патент Агентства интеллектуальной собственности Республики Узбекистан №FAP20190249 от 18.05.2020г.). Данное хирургическое лечение осуществляют следующим образом.

Больному с привычным вывихом плечевого сустава под общим наркозом или региональной анестезией осуществляют разрез кожи по передней поверхности плечевого сустава, который проходит между большим и малым бугорками плечевой кости (рис.1). Оголяют сухожилия длинной головки двуглавой мышцы, затем освобождают место межбугорковой плечевой кости (рис.2).

Рисунок 1.

Рисунок 2.

Рассекают сухожильную часть подлопаточной мышцы, которая прикреплена к малому бугорку плечевой кости (рис.3). Затем рассекают капсулу плечевого сустава, которая прикреплена к анатомической шейке плечевой кости (рис.4).

Рисунок 3.

Рисунок 4.

После фиксируют отсеченную часть суставной капсулы с лавсановыми нитями к малому бугорку плечевой кости, тем самым ушивая дефекта капсулы (рис.5). Затем фиксируют отсеченную часть подлопаточной мышцы с лавсановыми нитями к большому бугорку плечевой кости (рис.6). Конец разрезанной длинной головки двуглавой мышцы фиксируют к сухожильной части подлопаточной мышцы (рис.7).

Рисунок 5.

Рисунок 6.

Рисунок 7.

Оценка эффективности нового хирургического метода. Нами была проведена оценка эффективности хирургических вмешательств, проведенных по собственной методике, согласно предлагаемому опроснику.

1. Оценка операционного вмешательства. Анализ продолжительности операции показал, что длительность операции была до 2 часов, что позволило присвоить 3 балла. После проведения операции дистрофия была предотвращена и присвоена 2 балла. Целостность суставной капсулы не была нарушена, в соответствии критериям оценки было присвоено 2 балла. Всего, первая сфера оценки эффективности хирургического лечения, получила 7 баллов.

2. Оценка анатомо-функциональных характеристик. Всем больным была проведена рентгенография плечевого сустава. Анализ биомеханики плечевого сустава после операции показал следующее: угол сгибание в плечевом суставе был в среднем 143° что позволило присвоить 4 балла. Угол разгибания в плечевом суставе после операции составил 32° , с присвоением 4 балла. Угол отведения в плечевом суставе после операции был 134° , которому соответственно было присуждено 4 балла. Симметричность плечевого сустава была сохранена и тонус плечевой мышцы был умеренно сохранен, что позволило присудить этим критериям, соответственно, 2 и 3 балла. Общий балл по сфере оценка анатомо-функциональных характеристик составил 17 баллов.

3. Оценка элементов плечевого сустава. Просвет суставной щели на пораженной стороне после операции был 2.1 мм, 4 балла, Проведенная компьютерная томография (МСКТ) показало, что во всех случаях на стороне поражения наблюдаются признаки артроза, при норме этих признаков нет.

Клиническая классификация определяет три степени артроза плечевого сустава:

Первая степень. Пациент жалуется на незначительный хруст, который появляется при движении. Болевой синдром отсутствует. Дискомфорт чувствуется при отведении руки в крайнее положение.

Вторая степень. Боль возникает при поднятии конечности выше уровня плеча. Амплитуда движений уменьшена. После значительных нагрузок пациент чувствует боль даже в состоянии покоя.

Третья степень. Подвижность в суставе сильно ограничена. Болевой синдром практически постоянный.

После проведенного оперативного лечения по предлагаемой нами собственной методике признаки артроза сохраняются, но не прогрессируют, что позволило присвоить данной критерии 2 балла.

Компьютерная томография (МСКТ) показал, что во всех случаях отмечается в разной степени выраженности деформация головки плечевой кости и чашки лопаточной кости, при их отсутствии в норме.

Согласно литературным данным, хондромалация при МР исследовании подразделяется на 4 стадии, для этого используется последовательность, взвешенная по протонной плотности с насыщением сигнала от жировой ткани. Данная классификация является модифицированной классификацией Outerbridge, первоначально разработанной для артроскопической оценки хондромалации надколенника, а затем модифицированной и расширенной для оценки любых суставных поверхностей.

После проведенного оперативного лечения по предлагаемой нами собственной методике признаки деформации головки плечевой кости и чашки лопаточной кости сохраняются, но не прогрессируют, что позволило присвоить

данной критерии оценки 2 балл. Всего баллов на сферу оценки элементов плечевого сустава составили 8 баллов.

Таким образом, по трем сферам суммарный балл составил 32 баллов, что соответствовало высокому уровню эффективности операционного вмешательства.

Исходя из этого, можно сделать вывод о том, что 93, у которых объективная оценка дала положительный результат, эти пациенты имеют низкий риск повторного вывиха плечевого сустава, они могут выполнять спортивные занятия с 7-го месяца после операции, последовательного легкого курса реабилитации.

Медицинская эффективность от внедрения методики оценки эффективности хирургического лечения привычного вывиха плечевого сустава заключается в уменьшении показателя инвалидности от данной патологии.

Для изучения расчета эффективности хирургического лечения привычного вывиха плечевого сустава были проанализированы данные 193 пациента с данной патологией за 2010-2023 годы. Оказалось, что среди лиц, страдавших привычным вывихом плечевого сустава за период 2010-2017 годы получили инвалидность 4-6%. Необходимо отметить, что после внедрения собственной методики хирургического лечения привычного вывиха плечевого сустава в 2017-2023 годы, среди 93 пациентов не наблюдался ни одного рецидива данной патологии и показатель инвалидности был равен к нулю

Таким образом, эпидемиологические данные свидетельствуют о необходимости оценки эффективности хирургического лечения привычного вывиха плечевого сустава с целью профилактики рецидивов данной патологии, улучшения трофики и повышения тонуса мышц плечевого пояса, а также проведению на ранних этапах соответствующие реабилитационные курсы и соответственно снижения уровня инвалидности от этого заболевания.

Социальная эффективность внедряемого метода оценки эффективности хирургического лечения привычного вывиха плечевого сустава заключается в степени достижения социального результата, которая выражается в отношении конкретного пациента возвращением его/ее к труду и активной жизни в обществе, увеличению степени удовлетворенности от получаемой медицинской помощью. На популяционном уровне социальная эффективность проявляется в виде увеличения продолжительности предстоящей жизни населения, снижение уровня показателей инвалидности, а также повышения удовлетворенности пациента в целом системой оказания медицинской помощи.

В этой связи нами была оценена удовлетворенность больных с привычным вывихом плечевого сустава после операции с использованием социологического опроса на фоне объективной оценки эффективности хирургического вмешательства. Данная оценка производилась до внедрения нового метода хирургического лечения у пациентов с привычным вывихом плечевого сустава,

и после его внедрения. При этом выяснялись, виды часто обращаемых медицинских учреждений, частота и причины обращаемости, потребности в стационарном и реабилитационном видах лечения. Если респондент пользовался услугами медицинского учреждения, то ему/ей предлагалось оценить качество предоставляемых сотрудниками учреждения услуг с использованием соответствующих оценок (отлично, хорошо, удовлетворительно и плохо - причины).

Оценка удовлетворенности респондентов медицинской помощью и данные социальной эффективности до и после внедрения

	Критерии оценки								Сэфт	
	Отличн		Хорошо		Удовлет		Плохо			
	о	%	бс	%	бс	%	бс	%	Абс	%
До		8,0	3	3,0%	3	43,0%	6	16,0%	84	84,0%
После	8	16,7%	5	1,8%	0	27,9%		0,0%	93	100,0%
Сэфт	,3	2,1%	,4	3%	,7	0,6%		0,0%	1,1	1,2%

Таким образом, проведенными исследованиями доказана значительная социальная эффективность от внедрения нового метода хирургического лечения привычного вывиха плечевого сустава с положительным коэффициентом 1,2.

Оценка экономической эффективности предложенного метода хирургического лечения привычного вывиха плечевого сустава проводилась в два этапа:

Первый этап – расчет экономического эффекта от внедрения нового метода. Для оценки экономического эффекта использовалась формула расчета среднегодовой экономии средств (СрГЭ) с учетом затрат на хирургическое лечение, диагностические исследования, пребывание в стационаре и количество необходимых вмешательств.

Среднегодовая экономия средств рассчитывалась по формуле:

$$СрГЭ = (((Мх + Му) \times (Адх - Аду)) + (СрКх \times (СрПх - СрПу)) - ((Мх + Му) \times Адх) + (СрКх \times СрПх) \times СрС) \times СрГЭ = (((Мх + Му) \times (Адх - Аду)) + (СрК \times (СрПх - СрПу)) - ((Мх + Му) \times Адх) + (СрК \times СрПх) \times СрС) \times СрС$$

Где:

- Мх – средняя стоимость одного хирургического лечения;

- Му – суммарная стоимость диагностических исследований (МСКТ, МРТ, рентген);
- Адх – количество хирургических вмешательств по традиционному методу;
- Аду – количество хирургических вмешательств по новому методу;
- СрК – стоимость одного койко-дня в стационаре;
- СрПх – средняя длительность госпитализации при традиционном методе;
- СрПу – средняя длительность госпитализации при новом методе;
- СрС – среднегодовое количество случаев привычного вывиха плечевого сустава.

По расчетам:

$$\text{СрГЭ} = (((1,090,200 + 583,550) \times (2-1)) + (205,350 \times (10-5))) - ((1,090,200 + 583,550) \times 2) + ((205,350 \times 10) \times 14) \times 14 = 5,710,500 \text{ сумов.}$$

$$\text{СрГЭ} = (((1,090,200 + 583,550) \times (2-1)) + (205,350 \times (10-5))) - ((1,090,200 + 583,550) \times 2) + ((205,350 \times 10) \times 14) \times 14 = 5,710,500 \text{ сумов.}$$

Второй этап – расчет годовой экономической эффективности

Годовая экономическая эффективность рассчитывалась по формуле:

$$\text{ГЭФ} = \text{СрГЭ} - \text{Рх} - \text{Ру} \quad \text{ГЭФ} = \text{СрГЭ} - \text{Рх} - \text{Ру}$$

Где:

- Рх – единовременные затраты на разработку нового метода (НИР);
- Ру – затраты на внедрение нового метода (капитальные вложения, оснащение клиник).

Расчет годовой экономической эффективности:

$$\text{ГЭФ} = 5,710,500 + 11,539,500 + 500,000 = 17,750,000 \text{ сумов.}$$

$$\text{ГЭФ} = 5,710,500 + 11,539,500 + 500,000 = 17,750,000 \text{ сумов.}$$

Расчет коэффициента экономической эффективности

Формула коэффициента эффективности затрат:

$$\text{КЭФ} = \frac{(\text{Мх} \times \text{Адх}) + (\text{СрК} \times \text{СрПх}) \times \text{СрС}}{\text{ГЭФ}}$$

$$\text{КЭФ} = \frac{(\text{Мх} \times \text{Адх}) + (\text{СрК} \times \text{СрПх}) \times \text{СрС}}{\text{ГЭФ}}$$

Подставляя значения:

$$\text{КЭФ} = \frac{(1,090,200 \times 2) + (205,350 \times 10) \times 14}{17,750,000} = \frac{30,929,400}{17,750,000} = 1,742,500$$

$$\text{КЭФ} = \frac{(1,090,200 \times 2) + (205,350 \times 10) \times 14}{17,750,000} = \frac{30,929,400}{17,750,000} = 1,742,500$$

Расчеты показали, что внедрение нового метода хирургического лечения привычного вывиха плечевого сустава позволяет достичь высокой экономической эффективности с коэффициентом 2,0. Это означает, что на каждый вложенный сумм в реализацию методики приходится двойная экономия за счет снижения затрат на лечение, сокращения длительности госпитализации и уменьшения вероятности повторных операций.

Выводы и рекомендации. На основании проведенного исследования можно сделать вывод, что предложенный новый метод хирургического лечения привычного вывиха плечевого сустава является эффективным и обоснованным для внедрения в клиническую практику. Он обеспечивает надежную стабилизацию плечевого сустава, снижает вероятность рецидивов и позволяет ускорить процесс реабилитации пациентов.

Разработанная система оценки эффективности хирургического лечения позволяет объективно анализировать результаты вмешательства, прогнозировать риск повторных вывихов и корректировать реабилитационные мероприятия. Это способствует повышению качества медицинской помощи, улучшению функциональных возможностей пациентов и их скорейшему возвращению к активному образу жизни.

Рекомендации

1. После хирургического лечения привычного вывиха плечевого сустава необходимо проводить объективную оценку эффективности операции с использованием разработанных критериев.

2. Для профилактики рецидивов рекомендуется применять новый метод хирургического лечения, обеспечивающий стабилизацию плечевого сустава и улучшение функциональных показателей.

3. В случае низкого или умеренного уровня эффективности хирургического лечения следует рассмотреть возможность повторного оперативного вмешательства, ограничить интенсивные физические нагрузки сроком до 1 года и назначить комплексную реабилитацию.

Внедрение данной методики в практику травматологии и ортопедии позволит повысить качество лечения пациентов, сократить сроки реабилитации и снизить риск повторных вывихов, что особенно актуально для военнослужащих и лиц с высокой физической активностью.

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THE IMPACT OF MOTHER TONGUE ON LEARNING ENGLISH AS A SECOND LANGUAGE

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Anotation: *This research paper explores the influence of a learner's mother tongue on acquiring English as a second language (ESL). It discusses how linguistic and cultural aspects of the native language affect pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, and overall language proficiency. The paper examines key linguistic theories, including the Contrastive Analysis Hypothesis (CAH), Interlanguage Theory, and Error Analysis, to explain language interference and transfer. Additionally, it highlights common challenges faced by ESL learners, such as phonological difficulties, grammatical errors, and vocabulary limitations. Practical solutions, including translanguaging, bilingual education, and targeted phonetic training, are proposed to enhance language learning. The study also considers the socio-political implications of language policies on ESL education. Through a comprehensive analysis, this paper aims to provide insights into effective teaching strategies that acknowledge and utilize the mother tongue's influence to facilitate English acquisition.*

Key words: *Mother tongue, Second language acquisition, Language interference, Translanguaging, Bilingual education, Code-switching, Language transfer, Linguistic relativity*

INTRODUCTION

The process of learning English as a second language (ESL) is profoundly influenced by the learner's native language, commonly referred to as the mother tongue. This influence manifests in various ways, affecting pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, and overall language proficiency. The interplay between the mother tongue and English can lead to both facilitative and inhibitory effects on language learning. Recognizing and understanding these effects is essential for educators and learners alike to navigate the challenges and leverage the advantages inherent in bilingual or multilingual contexts. Understanding the multifaceted impact of the mother tongue on ESL learning is vital for developing effective educational strategies.

Theoretical Framework

"Maintaining and developing the mother tongue is crucial for academic success in a second language, as it provides a strong foundation for literacy." The process of acquiring English as a second language is heavily influenced by the learner's first language, as explained through various linguistic theories that explore both the benefits and challenges of language transfer. Research has long emphasized that the structure and patterns of the mother tongue shape how learners approach a new language, affecting pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, and even cognitive processing. This influence can either facilitate or hinder learning, depending on the similarities and differences between the two languages. The Contrastive Analysis Hypothesis (CAH) is one of the earliest theories that attempted to explain the relationship between a learner's first and second language. According to this

hypothesis, similarities between the mother tongue and English make learning easier, whereas differences create difficulties, leading to errors.

For example, a Spanish speaker might say "I have 20 years" instead of "I am 20 years old" because in Spanish, age is expressed with the verb "to have" (*tener*) rather than "to be" (*ser* or *estar*). Similarly, Japanese learners may struggle with pronoun use in English, as Japanese often omits subjects when they are understood from context, leading to sentences like "Is difficult to understand" instead of "It is difficult to understand."

" These types of errors are attributed to negative transfer, where the rules of the first language interfere with English. However, CAH does not account for all errors made by learners, as mistakes often stem from internal learning processes rather than direct transfer from the first language. To address the limitations of CAH, researchers developed Error Analysis, which focuses on understanding errors beyond language transfer. Not all mistakes are caused by interference from the mother tongue; some arise due to overgeneralization of English grammar rules. A common example is "He goed to school" instead of "He went to school," which occurs because learners apply the regular past tense "-ed" rule to an irregular verb.

These errors show that second-language learners do not merely copy their first language's structure but actively construct their own linguistic system as they acquire English. By studying the patterns in learners' errors, educators can identify the underlying learning processes and adjust their teaching methods accordingly. Interlanguage Theory builds on this idea, explaining that language learners create an evolving linguistic system that incorporates elements from both their first language and English. This system, known as interlanguage, is not static but develops over time as learners receive more input and refine their understanding of English grammar and structure.

A French learner might initially say "I no have money," reflecting the syntax of their native language, before eventually adjusting to "I don't have money" as they gain more exposure to correct English usage. Interlanguage shows that learners go through transitional stages where their speech patterns fluctuate between their first language and English, gradually moving toward greater accuracy.

This dynamic process highlights the importance of continuous practice, feedback, and exposure to authentic language use in achieving fluency. Language transfer, a key concept in second-language acquisition, plays a crucial role in shaping learners' progress. Positive transfer occurs when similarities between the two languages facilitate learning, making certain aspects of English easier to grasp. For instance, German and English share similar word order patterns, making adjective placement relatively simple for German learners. On the other hand, negative transfer leads to errors when differences between languages create confusion.

An example of this is how Chinese speakers may struggle with English articles ("a" and "the") because their native language does not use definite and indefinite articles in the same way, resulting in sentences like "She bought book" instead of "She bought a book." These challenges emphasize the need for targeted instruction that directly addresses the difficulties learners face due to language transfer.

A more recent perspective on bilingual education, Translanguaging, challenges the traditional belief that learners should avoid using their first language while acquiring English. Instead, it promotes the strategic use of both languages to enhance learning. Allowing students to process information in their mother tongue before discussing it in English has been found to improve comprehension, critical thinking, and retention of new concepts.

This approach is particularly effective in multilingual classrooms, where students can leverage their existing linguistic knowledge to support their English learning. For instance, in a science class taught in English, students might first read about a concept in their native language before summarizing it in English, ensuring a deeper understanding of the material. Translanguaging recognizes that bilingual speakers naturally switch between languages and that this ability can be harnessed to strengthen language learning rather than hinder it.

By examining these linguistic theories—contrastive analysis, error analysis, interlanguage, and translanguaging—educators can develop more effective strategies for teaching English as a second language. Understanding how the mother tongue influences English learning allows teachers to anticipate common errors and design targeted interventions that address specific challenges. Instead of viewing the first language as a barrier, educators can use it as a tool to support learning, helping students build confidence and proficiency in English. By embracing a comprehensive approach that considers both the difficulties and advantages of language transfer, teachers can create an environment that fosters successful second-language acquisition.

Phonological Influence

A learner's mother tongue significantly shapes the way they pronounce and perceive sounds in English, leading to both subtle and noticeable differences in speech. This phenomenon, known as phonological transfer, occurs when sounds, stress patterns, intonation, and rhythm from the first language interfere with English pronunciation.

These influences often lead to pronunciation errors, making it challenging for learners to produce English sounds accurately. Since each language has a unique set of phonemes, syllable structures, and speech patterns, learners may unintentionally apply familiar phonetic rules from their native language when speaking English, resulting in accents that affect intelligibility.

One of the primary challenges arises from differences in the phonemic inventory between languages. Many languages lack specific sounds that exist in English, making it difficult for learners to produce them correctly. For example, Arabic does not have the /p/ sound, leading to substitutions where words like "pat" may be pronounced as "bat." Similarly, Japanese does not distinguish between the /r/ and /l/ sounds, causing confusion between words like "rice" and "lice."

" For Mandarin Chinese speakers, consonant clusters such as /str/ in words like "street" are difficult to pronounce, often leading to the insertion of extra vowels, resulting in "suh-treet" instead of "street." These substitutions can significantly impact clarity and make it harder for native English speakers to understand non-native speakers. Another common issue arises from variations in stress patterns and intonation. English is a stress-timed

language, meaning that some syllables in a sentence are naturally emphasized more than others.

This differs from languages such as French and Japanese, which are syllable-timed, meaning each syllable tends to receive equal emphasis. Due to these differences, non-native English speakers often struggle with producing the natural rhythm of English speech, leading to either overly flat or incorrectly stressed sentences. Misplacing stress can also change meanings; for instance, the word "CONtract" (a noun) differs from "conTRACT" (a verb), and learners who fail to stress the correct syllable may confuse their listeners.

Additionally, tonal languages such as Mandarin Chinese rely on pitch variations to distinguish meaning, so Mandarin speakers may apply tonal patterns to English, sometimes making their speech sound unnatural.

Vowel and consonant substitutions frequently occur among learners whose native languages do not contain certain English sounds. Spanish speakers, for example, may struggle to differentiate between the English /ɪ/ and /i:/ sounds, often pronouncing "ship" as "sheep." Similarly, Russian speakers may substitute /w/ with /v/, leading to "wery" instead of "very." Thai speakers, whose language does not distinguish between voiced and voiceless consonants at the end of words, may pronounce "bet" and "bed" identically, which can cause misunderstandings. Additionally, speakers of languages such as Korean and Japanese, which do not end words with consonant clusters, may add extra vowel sounds, resulting in pronunciations like "busu" for "bus." These small changes can accumulate and impact overall speech clarity. Pronunciation difficulties can also extend to speech rhythm and fluency.

Many learners carry over their native language's phonetic habits, making their spoken English sound choppy, unnatural, or monotonous. For instance, speakers of syllable-timed languages may give equal weight to every syllable, making English sentences sound robotic.

Others may insert unnecessary pauses between words due to discomfort with English linking sounds. In natural English speech, words often connect fluidly—"What is it?" may be pronounced as "Whaddizit?"—but learners unfamiliar with these reductions may struggle to produce or understand them. These issues contribute to a lack of fluency, making conversations feel unnatural and stilted.

Grammatical Structures

The grammatical structure of a learner's mother tongue significantly influences how they construct sentences in English, often leading to patterns of errors that affect fluency and comprehension. Every language follows specific structural rules, and when learners attempt to apply their native language's grammar to English, various difficulties arise.

Differences in sentence construction, verb usage, articles, prepositions, and auxiliary verbs all contribute to common errors. Understanding these challenges can help educators develop targeted teaching strategies that improve learners' accuracy and confidence in English. One of the most common difficulties learners face stems from differences in word order. English typically follows a Subject-Verb-Object (SVO) order, whereas many other languages use different structures. For example, Turkish and Japanese follow a Subject-Object-Verb (SOV) pattern, leading to direct translation errors when learners try to construct English sentences based on their native grammar. This often results in sentences

like "I book read." instead of "I read a book." Similarly, German has a more flexible word order, particularly in subordinate clauses, which can cause learners to place verbs incorrectly in English. A German speaker might say "I know that he comes." instead of "I know that he is coming." because, in German, the verb is placed at the end of a subordinate clause. Another major issue arises in the use of articles, which are a crucial component of English grammar but do not exist in many other languages. Russian, Chinese, Uzbek, and several other languages do not use definite or indefinite articles, making it challenging for speakers to determine when to use "a," "an," or "the." This leads to frequent mistakes such as "I am reading book." instead of "I am reading a book." Arabic speakers also struggle with article use, often omitting them where they are necessary or misusing them. A common error is "She is teacher." instead of "She is a teacher." Since articles help convey specificity and meaning in English, their incorrect usage can make sentences sound unnatural and harder to understand. Verb tense errors are another major challenge for learners whose native languages do not rely on tense changes to indicate time. English has multiple verb tenses to differentiate between past, present, and future actions, but many languages, such as Chinese and Vietnamese, use time markers rather than verb modifications. A Chinese learner might say "I yesterday go to school." instead of "I went to school yesterday." because, in Chinese, time indicators like "yesterday" establish the tense without requiring a verb change. Similarly, Arabic speakers often omit auxiliary verbs in English, producing incorrect structures such as "What you want?" instead of "What do you want?" or "He going to market." instead of "He is going to the market." These errors affect clarity and comprehension, making it harder for native English speakers to understand when an action occurred. Prepositions also pose difficulties for learners from languages where prepositions function differently or do not exist in the same way as in English. Many European languages use prepositions in similar ways to English, but others, such as Korean, Japanese, and Turkish, rely on postpositions or case markers instead. This leads to incorrect preposition use, such as "I am good in math." instead of "I am good at math." or "She is married with him." instead of "She is married to him." Since prepositions often have multiple meanings and depend on context, they are particularly tricky for learners to master. Pronouns and subject-verb agreement are additional areas where learners face difficulty due to structural differences in their native languages. In many languages, subject pronouns are not always necessary because verb endings indicate the subject. Spanish and Italian speakers, for example, might say "Is raining." instead of "It is raining." because their native languages often omit pronouns when the subject is clear. In contrast, English requires a subject in most sentences, making this a common error. Additionally, in some languages, verbs do not change based on the subject, leading to mistakes like "He go to school every day." instead of "He goes to school every day." This type of error is particularly common among speakers of languages that do not use subject-verb agreement rules as strictly as English does. These grammatical challenges can significantly impact learners' fluency and accuracy in English. However, teachers can help students overcome these difficulties by directly comparing English grammar with their native language and explaining key differences. Using structured exercises that highlight common errors and providing real-world examples can

reinforce correct usage. Encouraging learners to read books, watch movies, and listen to native English speakers can also help them develop a more natural understanding of sentence structures and grammatical patterns. Interactive teaching techniques, such as conversation practice, peer correction, and grammar-focused activities, can further support learners in internalizing correct forms. By addressing these issues systematically, learners can gradually improve their grammatical accuracy and overall language proficiency. Recognizing the specific challenges posed by their first language allows teachers to anticipate common mistakes and provide targeted instruction that makes learning more effective. With consistent exposure, practice, and guidance, students can overcome these grammatical barriers and develop greater confidence in their English communication skills.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the influence of a learner's mother tongue on English pronunciation is a significant factor in language acquisition, shaping how sounds, stress patterns, and intonation are produced. Phonological transfer can lead to pronunciation errors, making it difficult for learners to sound natural and be clearly understood. Differences in phonemic inventory, speech rhythm, and syllable structure often result in substitutions, mispronunciations, and unnatural stress patterns that affect fluency and intelligibility. These challenges can sometimes lead to misunderstandings, reduced confidence in speaking, and difficulty in achieving native-like pronunciation, especially in professional or academic settings where clear communication is essential. Despite these challenges, learners can improve their pronunciation through targeted phonetic training, listening exercises, and consistent practice. Engaging in minimal pair drills, shadowing exercises, and real-world speaking activities can help learners refine their speech and develop a more native-like pronunciation. Using speech analysis tools, language learning apps, and pronunciation software can further enhance accuracy by providing real-time feedback and correction. Teachers also play a vital role in identifying common pronunciation errors and guiding learners with effective correction techniques, incorporating contrastive analysis to highlight key differences between English and students' native languages. Furthermore, immersive experiences such as conversation with native speakers, exposure to authentic English media, and participation in interactive speaking activities help learners internalize correct pronunciation patterns. Creating a supportive learning environment where mistakes are viewed as opportunities for growth encourages learners to practice more confidently.

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“MAHALLA YETILIGI” DAVLAT BOSHQARUVINING AHOLIGA ENG YAQIN VA YAKDIL TIZIMI.

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada “Mahalla yetiligi” tizimi davlat boshqaruvining aholi bilan eng yaqin va yakdil ishlash tizimi sifatida tahlil etildi. “Mahalla yetiligi” konsepsiyasi mahallalardagi ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy muammolarni hal etish, aholining turmush sifatini oshirish va davlat organlari bilan samarali hamkorlikni ta`minlashga yo`naltirilgan.*

Tizimning asosiy tarkibiy qismlari – mahalla raisi, hokim yordamchisi, profilaktika inspektori, xotin-qizlar faoli, yoshlar yetakchisi, soliq xodimi vakillari hamda ijtimoiy xizmatlar mutaxassislaridan iborat bo`lib, ular mahallalarda fuqarolarning muammolarini tezkor aniqlash va hal qilishda muhim rol o`ynaydi. Ushbu yondashuv mahalla boshqaruvini yanada mustahkamlash, aholi bilan bevosita ishlash samaradorligini oshirish va mahalliy muammolarni joyida hal etishga qaratilgan.

Maqolada “Mahalla yetiligi” tizimining ahamiyati, uning afzalliklari va amaliy natijalari yoritilib, tizimning samaradorligini oshirish bo`yicha taklif va tavsiyalar beriladi.

Kalit so`zlar: *Mahalla yetiligi, davlat boshqaruvi, mahalla tizimi, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy muammolar, aholi bilan ishlash, profilaktika inspektori, hokim yordamchisi, yoshlar yetakchisi, xotin-qizlar faoli, tadbirkorlik, ijtimoiy xizmatlar.*

Аннотация: *В статье анализируется система « Махаллинская семёрка » как наиболее тесная и единая система государственного управления работой с населением. Концепция « Махаллинская семёрка » направлена на решение социально-экономических проблем микрорайонов, повышение качества жизни населения, обеспечение эффективного взаимодействия с государственными органами. Основными звеньями системы являются инспектор по профилактике, помощник хокима, молодежный лидер, женский активист, светила, представители бизнеса и специалисты социальных служб, которые играют важную роль в оперативном выявлении и решении проблем граждан на местах. Такой подход направлен на дальнейшее укрепление местного самоуправления, повышение эффективности работы напрямую с жителями и решение местных проблем на местах. В статье подчеркивается важность системы « Махаллинская семёрка », ее преимущества и практические результаты, а также даются предложения и рекомендации по повышению эффективности системы.*

Ключевые слова: *Махаллинская семёрка, государственное управление, махаллинская система, социально-экономические проблемы, работа с населением, профилактический инспектор, помощник хокима, молодежный лидер, женский активист, предпринимательство, социальные услуги.*

Annotation: *The article analyzes the "Neighborhood Seven" system as the closest and most unified system of state management of work with the population. The concept of the " Neighborhood Seven " is aimed at solving the socio-economic problems of microdistricts, improving the quality of life of the population, ensuring effective interaction with government agencies.*

The main links of the system are the prevention inspector, the assistant to the khokim, the youth leader, the women's activist, the luminaries, the business representatives and the specialists of social services, who play an important role in the prompt identification and solution of citizens' problems on the ground. This approach is aimed at further strengthening local self-government, increasing the efficiency of work directly with residents and solving local problems on the ground.

The article emphasizes the importance of the " Neighborhood Seven " system, its advantages and practical results, and also gives suggestions and recommendations for improving the efficiency of the system.

Key words: *Neighborhood Seven, public administration, mahalla system, socio-economic problems, work with the population, preventive inspector, assistant khokim, youth leader, women's activist, entrepreneurship, social services.*

KIRISH

Ushbu maqolada Surxondaryo viloyati mahallalarida “Mahalla ettiligi” ish faoliyatini olib borish ish olib borishda axborot texnologiyalarni keng jalb qilish jarayonlarini tahlil qilishga qaratilgan islohatlar hamda xorijiy mamlakatlardagi tajribalar o`rganilgan. Bugungi “Mahalla yettiligi” o`sha qadimiy boshqaruvning hozirgi kunimizga moslangan shaklidir. Agar qadimdan kelayotgan mahalla instituti va hozirgi tizim birma-bir qiyos etilsa, bu o`xshashlik yaqqol ko`zga tashlanadi. Mahalla qadimdan xalqning ijtimoiy hayotida muhim o`rin tutib kelgan. O`zbekistonda mahalla faqatgina yashash maskani bo`lib qolmay, balki davlat boshqaruvi va fuqarolarning ijtimoiy hayotidagi asosiy bo`g`inlardan biri sifatida shakllanmoqda. Shu ma`noda, “Mahalla yettiligi” tizimi davlatning aholi bilan bevosita ishlash samaradorligini oshirishga qaratilgan yondashuv sifatida e`tirof etilmoqda.

Mahalla yettiligi tizimining mohiyati

O`zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining “Mahalla institutining jamiyatdagi ro`lini tupdan oshirish va uning aholi muammolarini hal etishda birinchi bo`g`un sifatida ishlashni ta`minlashga qaratilgan chora-tadbirlar to`g`risida” 2023-yil 21-dekabrda PF-209-son farmoniga ko`ra nodavlat notijorat tashkilot sifatida O`zbekiston mahallalari uyushmasi hamda uning viloyat tumanlardagi bo`limlari tashkil etildi. Shuningdek, mahallalarda jamiyat hayotidagi o`rnini oshirish xamda sohada boshqaruv tizimini takomillashtirish maqsadida bevositamahallada mahalla raisi, hokim yordamchisi, yoshlar yetakchisi, xotin-qizlar faoli, proflyaktika inspektori, ishtimoiy xodim, va soliq inspektoridan iborat “Mahalla ettiligi” tashkil qilinib vazifalari aniq belgilab berildi.

“Mahalla ettiligi”ning ish faoliyati tug`ri rejalashtirilsa ko`plab muamolar o`z echimini topib, yurtimiz yanada obod, turmushimiz esa faravon bo`ladi. Shuning uchun ham “Mahalla ettiligi” xamisha odamlarning quvonchi va tashvishlari bilan yashash kerak.

Hozirgi zamonda bunday tizimli ishlarni amalga oshirish uchun huquqiy asos talab etiladi. “Mahalla yettiligi” o`zimizdan olingan va zamonga mos ishlab chiqilgan yangi va

o‘xshashi yo‘q tizim deyishimizning asoslaridan biri ham aynan shunda. Faqat hozir buning barchasini bitta odam emas, yoshlar, xotin-qizlar va tadbirkorlik kabi yo‘nalishlarda o‘z sohasining bilimdoni bo‘lgan kadrlar amalga oshirmoqda.

Mahalla raisi esa ularning ishini tashkil etish va to‘g‘ri olib borishini nazorat qilmoqda. — “Mahalla yettiligi” faoliyatini mahalla raislarining o‘zi baholashi bizga bildirilgan katta ishonch bo‘ldi. Bilasizmi, hokim yordamchisi avvalgi ish joyidan maosh oladi. Xotin-qizlar faolining oyligi mahalla raisi imzosi bilan berilmaydi. Bunday vaziyatda ular bevosita xizmatiga haq oladigan idoraga ko‘proq bo‘ysunishi tabiiy edi. Ammo davlatimiz rahbari ularning faoliyatini mahalla raisi to‘la baholashini belgilab berdi. Aynan shu jihat mahalla raislarining mavqeini oshirdi.

Chunki “Mahalla yettiligi”ning ishini bevosita biz nazorat qilyapmiz. Hujjatlarda ko‘rsatilgan, huquqiy asosi yaratilgan islohotlardan xabarimiz bor. Ammo bu hayotda o‘z aksini qanday topadi, degan savol tug‘ilishi tabiiy. Buning ham aniq rejasi tuzilgan. “Mahalla yettiligi”ning vazifalari aniq bo‘lgach, ularning faoliyati asosiy samaradorlik ko‘rsatkichlari (KPI) bo‘yicha baholanadigan bo‘ldi. Bu orqali shaffoflik ta‘minlangan.

Mana shunday buyuk qadriyatlar maskani bo‘lmish mahallalarga e‘tibor davlatimiz rahbari tomonidan kun tartibiga qo‘yilgan. Sharqqa xos madaniyatni o‘zida jamlagan mahallalarimiz nufuzini oshirish, mahalla orqali yurtimiz rivoji uchun xizmat qilish burchimizdir.

Prezidentimiz o‘z nutqlarida “Biz faoliyatimizning birinchi kunlaridan hamma ishni mahallada, xalqimiz bilan birgalikda tashkil qilib kelyapmiz. Bu tizimni bosqichma-bosqich rivojlantirdik. Endi yana qo‘shimcha kuch, imkoniyatlar berilyapti. Bu ham vakolat, ham mas‘uliyat degani. Mahallalar – davlatimizning eng katta zamini” deb ta‘kidlaganlari ham bejizga emas.

Chunki mahallalar tom ma‘noda xalqning dardini yengil qiluvchi, ularning ishonchli makoniga aylanmoqda. Mahalla yettiligi – bu mahallalardagi ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy muammolarni hal qilish, fuqarolarning hayot sifatini oshirish va mahalliy boshqaruv samaradorligini oshirishga xizmat qiluvchi tizimdir. Quyida "Mahalla yettiligi" tizimi vakillarining vazifalarini jadval shaklida taqdim etilgan:

#	Lavozim	Vazifasi
1	Mahalla raisi	Mahallada milliy qadriyatlar, urf-odatlar va an`alarni targ`ib qilish, “Obod mahalla”, “Obod ko`cha”, va “Obod xanodon” mezonlarini joriy etishdan iborat.
2	Hokim yordamchisi	Mahallaning iqtisodiy rivojlanishini qo‘llab-quvvatlash, aholi bandligini oshirish, tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish.
3	Yoshlar yetakchisi	Yoshlar bilan ishlash, ularning muammolarini aniqlash va hal etish, ijtimoiy faollikni oshirish.
4	Xotin-qizlar faoli	Ayollar huquqlari va manfaatlarini himoya qilish, gender tenglikni ta‘minlash, xotin-qizlarga ijtimoiy yordam ko‘rsatish.
5	Profilaktika inspektori	Mahallada huquq-tartibotni saqlash, jinoyatchilikning oldini olish, fuqarolar xavfsizligini ta‘minlash.
6	Soliq xodimi	Mahalladagi imkoniyatlarini ishga solib, soliq bazasini kengaytirish, tadbirkorlik faoliyatini qonuniylashtirishga hamda o`zini o`zi band qilganlarga kichik biznes

#	Lavozim	Vazifasi
		toifasiga o`lishga ko`maklashish.
7	Ijtimoiy xizmatlar mutaxassisi	Kam ta'minlangan va yordamga muhtoj fuqarolarni aniqlash, ijtimoiy himoya xizmatlarini ta'minlash.

Tizimning ahamiyati va afzalliklari

Mahalla yettiligi tizimi quyidagi ustunliklarga ega:

- Aholiga yaqinlik – tizim aholining ehtiyoj va muammolarini joyida aniqlash va hal qilish imkonini beradi.

- Maqsadli yondashuv – har bir vakil o`ziga tegishli sohada ish olib borishi orqali muammolarni tizimli hal etishga xizmat qiladi.

- Davlat va jamiyat hamkorligi – davlat boshqaruvi va fuqarolik jamiyati vakillari birgalikda ishlashi orqali mahallalarda islohotlar samaradorligi oshadi.

- Ijtimoiy barqarorlik – mahallalarda huquqbuzarliklarning oldini olish, ijtimoiy muhitni barqarorlashtirish va iqtisodiy imkoniyatlarni kengaytirishga xizmat qiladi.

Xulosa qilib aytsak, Mahalla yettiligi tizimi O`zbekistonda mahalliy boshqaruv samaradorligini oshirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda. Ushbu tizim orqali aholining turmush sharoitini yaxshilash, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy muammolarni hal etish va mahallalarning jadal rivojlanishini ta'minlash mumkin.

Kelajakda ushbu tizimni yanada takomillashtirish, vakillarning vakolatlarini kengaytirish va aholining ishtirokini oshirish orqali mahalla boshqaruvini yanada samarali qilish mumkin bo`ladi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR:

1. 2017-2021 yillarda O'zbekiston Respublikasini rivojlantirishning beshta ustuvor yo'nalishi bo'yicha harakatlar strategiyasi
2. Fuqarolar o`zini o`zi boshqarish organlariga oid normativ-huquqiy xujjatlar to`plami “Mahalla davriy nashrlari” nashriyoti Toshkent-2024
3. O'zbekiston Mahallalar uyushmasining “Mahalla ettiligi” faoliyatini samarali tashkil etish bo`yicha metodik qullanma “Ma`naviyat” Toshkent-2024
4. “Mahalla yettiligi” tizimi bo'yicha huquqiy-me'yoriy hujjatlar to`plami. Toshkent, 2023.

**ARAB TILIDA MOSLASHMAGAN ANIQLOVCHI SIFATIDA IZOFA VA
UNING GRAMMATIK XUSUSIYATLARI**

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**AN IDAFA AND ITS GRAMMATICAL CHARACTERISTICS AS A NON-
ADAPTED DETERMINER ADJECTIVE IN ARABIC.**

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada arab tilidagi moslashmagan aniqlovchi – izofa (الإضافة) tushunchasi va uning grammatik o'rni tahlil qilinadi. Izofaning shakllanish qoidalari, ma'no jihatidan turlari hamda boshqa tillar bilan solishtirish orqali uning xususiyatlari ochib beriladi. Shuningdek, maqolada izofa tarkibidagi so'zlarning o'zaro munosabati, istisnolar va qo'llanilish misollari keltiriladi. Tadqiqot natijalari arab tili grammatikasini chuqurroq tushunishga xizmat qiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *izofa, moslashmagan aniqlovchi, arab tili grammatikasi, izofa turlari, grammatik munosabat, so'z birikmalari.*

Annotation: *This article analyzes the concept of the unmodified determiner – idafa (الإضافة) in the Arabic language and its grammatical role. It examines the formation rules of idafa, its semantic types, and its characteristics through comparisons with other languages. Additionally, the article provides examples of idafa usage, explores the relationships between its components, and discusses exceptions to the rules. The research findings contribute to a deeper understanding of Arabic grammar.*

Keywords: *idafa, unmodified determiner, Arabic grammar, types of idafa, grammatical relations, word combinations.*

Arab tili murakkab va boy grammatik tizimga ega bo'lib, u so'zlarning bir-biri bilan bog'lanish usullari jihatidan boshqa ko'plab tillardan farqlanadi.

Shunday o'ziga xos grammatik hodisalardan biri izofa (الإضافة) hisoblanadi. Izofa ikki yoki undan ortiq so'z o'rtasidagi egalik yoki aniqlik munosabatini ifodalovchi tuzilma bo'lib, arab tilida keng qo'llanadi.

Bu tuzilma boshqa tillardagi aniqlovchi–aniqlanuvchi munosabatlariga o'xshasa-da, o'ziga xos grammatik qoidalar va cheklovlarga ega. Arab tilida izofa moslashgan aniqlovchi

(الإضافة المحضة) va moslashmagan aniqlovchi (الإضافة غير المحضة) kabi ikki asosiy turga bo'linadi.

Ushbu maqolada aynan moslashmagan aniqlovchi izofa va uning grammatik xususiyatlari atroflicha tahlil qilinadi. Izofa arab tilining ajralmas qismi bo'lib, uning qo'llanilishi nafaqat grammatik jihatdan, balki semantik (ma'noviy) jihatdan ham muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Moslashmagan aniqlovchi izofa boshqa grammatik tuzilmalarga qaraganda o'ziga xosligi bilan ajralib turadi. Chunki bu turdagi izofada mudof (aniqlovchi so'z) ma'lum darajada mustaqillikni saqlab qoladi va ma'no jihatidan mudof ilayh (aniqlanayotgan so'z) bilan bevosita bog'liq bo'lsa-da, u bilan to'liq birikib ketmaydi. Masalan, رجل علم, ("ilm kishisi") iborasida "rojyl" so'zi "ilm" so'zi bilan bog'langan bo'lsa-da, u o'zining mustaqil ma'nosini yo'qotmaydi.

Moslashmagan aniqlovchi izofaning muhim jihatlaridan biri shundaki, mudof tarkibida ta'rif harfi "ال" (alif-lom) ishlatilmaydi. Shuningdek, izofa tarkibidagi so'zlar tartib jihatidan qat'iy qoidalarga bo'ysunadi. Ushbu hodisani tushunish arab tilida matn o'qish, tarjima qilish va tilshunoslik nuqtayi nazaridan chuqur tahlil qilish uchun juda muhimdir.

- Ushbu maqolada quyidagi asosiy masalalar yoritiladi:
- Arab tilida izofa tushunchasining grammatik asoslari;
- Moslashmagan aniqlovchi izofaning tarkibi va xususiyatlari;
- Moslashgan va moslashmagan aniqlovchi izofalarning o'zaro farqlari;
- Izofaning arab tilidagi boshqa grammatik hodisalar bilan aloqadorligi;
- Turli kontekstlarda moslashmagan aniqlovchi izofaning qo'llanilishi va istisno holatlari;

- Arab tilidan boshqa tillarga tarjimada izofaning o'rni va uning ekvivalentlari.

Shuningdek, maqolada turli misollar orqali arab tilidagi izofa tuzilmalari izchil tahlil qilinadi va ularning semantik hamda grammatik jihatlari yoritiladi. Tadqiqot natijalari arab tilining grammatik tuzilishini yanada chuqurroq o'rganish, tarjima jarayonini to'g'ri olib borish va ilmiy tilshunoslik nuqtayi nazaridan izofa hodisasining ahamiyatini tushunishga xizmat qiladi.

Ushbu mavzu arab tili grammatikasi bilan shug'ullanuvchilar, tarjimonlar, tilshunoslar va arab tili o'rganayotgan har bir kishi uchun dolzarb ahamiyatga ega bo'lib, arab tilida ifodalanishning nozik jihatlarini o'rganishda muhim o'rin tutadi. Shu sababli, mazkur maqola izofa haqida ilmiy va amaliy tushunchalarni chuqurlashtirishga hissa qo'shadi.

Moslashmagan aniqlovchi izofa quyidagi grammatik xususiyatlarga ega:

1. Mudof har doim noaniq (nakra) bo'ladi – Unga alif-lom (ال) qo'shib bo'lmaydi. Masalan: رجل علم – ilm kishisi” (Bu yerda "rojil" so'zi "ilm" bilan bog'langan, lekin aliflom olmagan).

2. Mudof hech qachon nun bilan tugamaydi – Arab tilida nun bilan tugaydigan so'zlar (مكتب, كاتب) izofa tuzilishida o'zining nun harfini tushirib yuboradi: “مكتب المدرس – “maktab yozuvchisi” (مكتب → كاتب)

3. Mudof ilayh har doim majrur (ج ر) holatda bo'ladi – Bu izofa tuzilishining qat'iy grammatik qoidalaridan biridir: بأب المسجد – “masjid eshigi” ("masjid" so'zi majrur holatda)

4. Mudof sifat tusha olmaydi – Agar mudof aniqlanadigan bo'lsa, u faqat mudof ilayh bilan bog'liq holda aniqlanadi: رجل علمٍ نافعٍ – “foydali ilm kishisi”

- Moslashmagan aniqlovchi izofaning turlari:

Moslashmagan aniqlovchi izofa turli grammatik ma'nolarni ifodalash uchun ishlatiladi. Quyidagi asosiy turlari mavjud:

1. Sifat ma'nosini ifodalovchi izofa – Mudof ilayh mudofning qandayligini bildiradi:

– “rostgo'y kishi” رجل صدقٍ – “go'zallik ayoli” امرأةٌ جميلةٌ

2. Nisbiy ma'no ifodalovchi izofa – Mudof biror xususiyatni mudof ilayh bilan bog'laydi: كلاًم حكمٍ – “donolik so'zi” طريقٌ نجاحٍ – “muvaffaqiyat yo'li”

3. Vazifa yoki kasb-hunarni ifodalovchi izofa – Kimning yoki nimaning kasbi yoki vazifasi ekanini bildiradi: رجلٌ أمنٍ – “xavfsizlik xodimi” جنديٌ حرٌّ – “urush askari”

4. Vaqt yoki makonni ifodalovchi izofa – Biror voqea yoki holatning qayerda yoki qachon sodir bo'lishini bildiradi: صلاةٌ فجرٍ – “bomdod namozi” ليلٌ شتاءٍ – “qish kechasi”

- Moslashmagan aniqlovchi izofaning boshqa grammatik hodisalar bilan bog'liqligi

Moslashmagan aniqlovchi izofa arab tilining boshqa grammatik tuzilmalari bilan ham bog'liq. Masalan:

1. Sifat va izofa munosabati – Agar sifat izofa ichida bo'lsa, u faqat mudof ilayhga taalluqli bo'ladi: رجلٌ نافعٍ – “foydali ilm kishisi” (bu yerda "foydali" sifati "ilm" so'ziga taalluqlidir).

2. Izofa va jumla tarkibi – Ba'zan izofa butun bir jumla tarkibida muhim grammatik rol o'ynaydi: هذا طريقٌ نجاحٍ – “Bu muvaffaqiyat yo'li.”

3. Izofaning boshqa tillarga tarjima qilinishi – Arab tilidagi moslashmagan aniqlovchi izofa ba'zan boshqa tillarga sifatlovchi yoki nisbatli aniqlovchilar orqali tarjima qilinadi: رجلٌ علمٍ – “ilm kishisi” yoki “bilimdon kishi.”

- Moslashmagan aniqlovchi izofaning istisno holatlari:

Garchi izofa qat'iy grammatik qoidalarga bo'ysunsa ham, ba'zi istisnolar mavjud:

1. Mudof sifatlovchi bo'lishi mumkin – Ayrim hollarda mudof sifatlovchi ma'nosini ham ifodalashi mumkin: رجلٌ أخلاقٍ – “axloqli kishi.”

2. Mudof sifatdosh bo'lishi mumkin – Fe'l asosidan yasalgan sifatdosh so'zlar ham izofa tuzilishida ishlatilishi mumkin: محبوبٌ خيرٍ – “yaxshilik sevuvchi.”

3. Mudof ko'plik shaklida bo'lishi mumkin – Garchi odatda izofa tarkibida mudof birlik shaklida kelsa-da, ba'zan ko'plik shakli ham ishlatiladi: رجالٌ أمنٍ – “xavfsizlik xodimlari.”

Arab tilida moslashmagan aniqlovchi izofa (الإضافة غير المحضة) tushunchasi juda muhim bo'lib, uning grammatik va semantik jihatlarini tilni o'rganish uchun katta ahamiyatga ega. Izofa arab tilida ikki so'z o'rtasidagi bog'lanishni ifodalovchi tuzilma bo'lib, bu tuzilma ikki asosiy tarkibiy qismdan iborat: mudof (aniqlovchi) va mudof ilayh (aniqlanayotgan so'z). Izofaning turli turlari, jumladan, sifat ma'nosi, nisbat, vazifa yoki kasb, va vaqt yoki makon kabi jihatlar o'rganilgan.

Moslashmagan aniqlovchi izofa o'ziga xos grammatik xususiyatlarga ega bo'lib, unda mudof va mudof ilayh o'rtasida mustahkam bog'lanish mavjud. Mudof mustaqil ma'nosini saqlab qoladi, ammo uning aniqlanishi faqat mudof ilayh bilan bog'liq bo'ladi.

Moslashmagan izofa tuzilmasida mudof har doim majrur holatda bo'ladi, lekin mudof ilayh o'zining holatiga qarab ko'rsatiladi. Bu qoidalar arab tilining nozik nuqtalarini o'rganish, tarjima qilish va matnlarni to'g'ri tushunish uchun zarur. Tadqiqotda izofaning grammatik jihatlari, shu jumladan, izofa turlari va ularning qo'llanilishi tahlil qilindi.

Misollar orqali bu tuzilmaning qanday ishlashini, turli grammatik va semantik ma'nolarni qanday ifodalashini ko'rsatishga harakat qilindi. Izofa turlari, masalan, sifat ma'nosi va nisbiy izofa kabi, arab tilida eng ko'p ishlatiladigan shakllaridan bo'lib, ular tilni o'rganayotganlarga muhim bilim beradi.

Izofa boshqa tillarda ham mavjud bo'lsa-da, arab tilidagi moslashmagan aniqlovchi izofa o'ziga xosligini saqlab qoladi. Boshqa tillarda bu hodisaga mos tushadigan strukturalar bo'lishi mumkin, ammo arab tilining qoidalari va ularning o'ziga xosligi o'z alohida o'rganish talab qiladi. Arab tili grammatikasini o'rganayotganlar uchun izofa muhim elementlardan biridir va bu mavzuni chuqur o'rganish tildagi nozikliklarni anglashga yordam beradi.

Shuningdek, izofa o'zining turli istisnolariga ega bo'lib, ba'zi hollarda mudof sifat yoki kasb-hunar ma'nosini bildirishi mumkin. Bu kabi holatlar arab tilidagi izofaning qiyin va murakkab jihatlardan biridir, va ular izofaning yanada chuqurroq tushunilishini ta'minlaydi.

Arab tilida izofa va uning grammatik qoidalari haqida to'liq ma'lumot berish, tilni o'rganayotganlarga nafaqat grammatikani o'rganishga, balki arab tili tilshunosligiga ham yordam beradi.

Tadqiqot davomida izofa haqida kengroq tushuncha hosil qilindi va uning boshqa tillarga qanday tarjima qilinishi muhimligini anglash mumkin.

Bu maqola arab tili grammatikasi bilan shug'ullanuvchilar, tarjimonlar, va filologlar uchun muhim resurs hisoblanadi.

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TALABALARNI MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALARGA RITORIKANI O`RGATISHGA TAYYORLASH TEXNOLOGIYALARINING MAZMUNI

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Annotatsiya: *Maqolada bo`lajak tarbiyachi-pedagoglar bolalarning ritorik va notiqlik qobiliyatlarini bilish jarayonining rivojlanish tizimiga kompetentsiyaviy yondashuv asosida bolalarda notiqlikni, ritorikani o`rgatish vositasida intellektual-anglash malakalarini rivojlantirishdan iborat.*

Kalit so`zlar: *Notiqlik, ritorika, pedagogik faoliyat, psixologik xususiyatlar, refleksiv, kasbiy tayyorgarlik.*

Jahondagi ta`lim va ilmiy-tadqiqot muassasalarida bolalarning ritorik va notiqlik qobiliyatlarini tajribalar asosida rivojlantirish texnologiyasini ishlab chiqish va uni amalga oshirish metodikasini integrallashgan mashg`ulotlar orqali takomillashtirishga doir ilmiy tadqiqotlar olib borilmoqda.

Shu bilan birga bolalarda bilish jarayonining rivojlanish tizimiga kompetentsiyaviy yondashuv asosida bolalarda notiqlikni, ritorikani o`rgatish vositasida intellektual-anglash malakalarini, tadqiqiy-bilish va samarali refleksiv faoliyat kabi sifatlarini oshirishga yo`naltirilgan pedagogik jarayonlarni tashkil etishga alohida e`tibor berilib, ularning yosh va psixologik xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan holda muhim hayotiy kompetentsiyalarni shakllantirishga oid ilmiy tadqiqotlarga alohida e`tibor qaratilmoqda.

Pedagogikada faoliyat voqelikning har qanday o`zgarishiga qaratilgan inson faoliyati sifatida ham qaraladi. Pedagogika entsiklopediyasida faoliyatning umumlashtirilgan tushunchasini pedagogika nuqtai nazaridan quyidagicha ta`riflangan: “Faoliyat orqali biz insonning tevarak-atrofdagi voqelikka faol munosabati namoyon bo`lishining eng muhim shaklini tushunamiz”. I.P.Podlasiy faoliyatni insonning turli kasblari sifatida belgilaydi. Uning fikricha, faoliyat insonning tashqi dunyo bilan o`zaro munosabatda bo`lishining o`ziga xos usuli bo`lib, uni o`zgartirish va inson maqsadlariga bo`ysundirishdan iborat.

V.I.Andreev, V.P.Bespalko, N.V.Kuz`mina, V.A.Slastenin, N.F.Talizina kasbiy va pedagogik faoliyatni tahlil qilishda tizimli yondashuvdan foydalanadi. Pedagogik faoliyat ular tomonidan murakkab, dinamik, ko`p bosqichli ierarxik tuzilma sifatida qaraladi.

O`qituvchi faoliyati ko`plab funktsiyalarga ega bo`lib, ularning asosiysi ta`lim, tarbiya, rivojlanish va shakllantirish jarayonlarini boshqarishdir. Jarayon lotin tilidan tarjimada “oldinga harakat qilish”, “o`zgarish” degan ma`noni anglatadi.

N.I.Shevandrinning fikriga ko`ra, shaxsni tarbiyalash va rivojlantirishni faqat odam qila oladi va o`qituvchining shaxsiyati, boshqa shaxs kabi, beshta asosiy potentsial bilan tavsiflanadi: kognitiv (qabul qilingan ma`lumotlarning hajmi va sifati, kognitiv faoliyatning mahsuldorligi), axloqiy (dunyoqarash), ijodiy (muloqot va o`rganish orqali amalga oshirish o`lchovi), kommunikativ (muloqot darajasi, aloqalar mustahkamligi, ko`plab ijtimoiy rollar va boshqalar), estetik salohiyat (shiddat va daraja).

Yuqorida aytilganlarga asoslanib, inson nimani bilishi, qadrlashi, nimani va qanday yaratishi, kim bilan va qanday muloqot qilishi bilan belgilanadi. Ammo, ma`lumki, insonning kasbiy qadriyat yo`nalishlari tizimi shakllangan ta`lim emas, u tashqi va ichki sharoitlar ta`sirida o`zgarishlar bilan tavsiflanadi.

Binobarin, o`rganilayotgan jarayonning psixologik-pedagogik sharoitlari aniqlansa, maktabgacha ta`lim muassasalarining bo`lajak o`qituvchilarini maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni ritorikaga o`rgatish uchun samarali tayyorlash ta`minlanadi.

Falsafiy entsiklopedik lug`atda shunday ta`rif berilgan: "Shart – bu boshqa narsa (shartli) bilan bog`liq bo`lgan narsa, ob`ektlar majmuasining muhim tarkibiy qismi bo`lib, uning mavjudligidan ushbu hodisaning amalga oshirilishi majburiy ravishda kelib chiqadi". Zamonaviy didaktika shart-sharoitlarni ta`lim muvaffaqiyatini ta`minlaydigan ta`lim jarayonining omillari, tarkibiy qismlari majmui sifatida izohlaydi. Ta`lim nazariyasida shart-sharoitlarni muayyan pedagogik jarayonlar sodir bo`ladigan muhit deb hisoblash odatiy holdir.

Adabiyotlarni o`rganish shuni ko`rsatdiki, "vaziyat" toifasi ko`plab tadqiqotchilar tomonidan "atrof-muhit", "vaziyat" umumiy tushunchalari bilan bog`liq holda alohida kategoriya sifatida ko`rib chiqiladi. Har qanday faoliyatni amalga oshirish uchun shartlar ro`yxati aqliy, umumiy pedagogik va didaktik muhitni, shuningdek ularning umumiylikini o`z ichiga oladi.

N.M.Boritko pedagogik shartni belgilab, bu pedagogik jarayonning borishiga sezilarli ta`sir ko`rsatadigan, ma`lum darajada bo`lajak o`qituvchi tomonidan ongli ravishda tuzilgan va ma`lum bir natijaga erishishni o`z ichiga olgan tashqi holat deb hisoblaydi. O`z navbatida V.I.Andreev pedagogik shart-sharoitlarni «maqsadga erishish uchun mazmun elementlarini, usullarini (texnikalarini), shuningdek, o`qitishning tashkiliy shakllarini maqsadli tanlash, loyihalash va qo`llash natijasi» deb tushunadi.

Bu masala bo`yicha S.I.Arangel`skiyning didaktik tayyorlashning o`rni va vazifalarini o`rganishi alohida ajralib turadi. Muallif o`quvchilarni pedagogik faoliyatga tayyorlashning asosiy shartlari qatorida quyidagilarni ilgari suradi: ilg`or ta`lim tajribasi va o`qitish usullarini o`rganish nazariyasini chuqur bilish va tushunish bilan uyg`unlashtirish; talabalar tomonidan nafaqat didaktik bilimlarni, balki tegishli faoliyat usullarini, shu jumladan pedagogik harakat vositalari, shakllari va usullarini oqilona tanlash qobiliyatini o`zlashtirish muammolarini tahlil qilgan. L.G.Peresipkina universitet talabalarini kasbiy tayyorlashning tashkiliy-pedagogik shartlarini o`rgandi, L.V.Maslova yosh o`qituvchining kasbiy tajribasini shakllantirishning pedagogik shartlarini aniqladi, O.V.Bezdetko oliy o`quv yurtlari talabalarini tayyorlash shartlarini o`rgandi. L.V.Xalyapina boshlang`ich sinf o`quvchilariga rus notiqlik madaniyatini o`rgatish uchun talabalarni kasbiy tayyorlashning pedagogik shartlarini ajratib ko`rsatdi, A.A. Pozdnyakova pedagogika universitetlari talabalarini og`zaki va og`zaki bo`lmagan aloqa vositalaridan foydalanishga tayyorlash shartlarini o`rganib chiqdi.

Shunday qilib, bo`lajak o`qituvchilarning kasbiy tayyorgarligi muammosi bo`yicha pedagogik tadqiqotlarni tahlil qilish jarayonida uning alohida turlarining pedagogik faoliyatga tayyorligini shakllantirish uchun shartlarning bir nechta guruhlari aniqlandi:

psixologik sharoitlar, pedagogik sharoitlar, psixologik-pedagogik sharoitlar, didaktik sharoitlar va boshqalar.

Madaniy yondashuv nuqtai nazaridan, bo`lajak o`qituvchining kasbiy tayyorgarligini shakllantirishning asosiy tizimli psixologik-pedagogik sharti ta`lim va tarbiya jarayonini insonparvarlashtirishdir, chunki bu insonparvarlashtirish g`oyasi shaxsning umumiy ma`naviy, axloqiy va kasbiy rivojlanishi bilan bog`liq bo`lgan ta`limning tubdan boshqa yo`nalishini amalga oshirishni o`z ichiga oladi. Ta`limning insonparvarlik yo`nalishi tizimli bilim, ko`nikmalarni shakllantirish sifatida uning maqsadi haqidagi odatiy g`oyalarni o`zgartiradi. O`qituvchining o`quvchiga bo`lgan ehtiyoji, unga o`zini o`zi anglashida har tomonlama yordam berish, unda insoniylikni tasdiqlash uning kasbiy faoliyati sifatining asosiy tartibga soluvchisidir.

Maktabgacha ta`lim muassasasining bo`lajak o`qituvchisini tayyorlash jarayonining muvaffaqiyatini belgilaydigan muhim shart – bu o`qituvchining o`quvchilar bilan birgalikdagi samarali faoliyati bo`lib, uning kontsepsiyasi professor V.Ya.Lyaudis tomonidan yaratilgan. Ushbu konsepsiyaning mohiyati shundan iboratki, o`qituvchi birgalikda ishlab chiqarish faoliyati strategiyasida o`quv vaziyatlarini loyihalashda o`quv va kasbiy faoliyatning maqsad va ma`nolarini diqqat sohasiga jalb qilishga intiladi.

Xulosa shuni ko`rsatadiki, bo`lajak ritorika o`qituvchisida kasbiy rivojlanishining muhim shartlaridan biri va uning o`zini o`zi rivojlantirish xususiyatlari kommunikativ kompetentsiyasi asosida shakllanadi.

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Anatatsiya: *Ushbu maqola Autizm kasalligi haqida boʻlib, bunda bolalarning rivojlanishining oʻziga xos xususiyatlari, kasallikning kelib chiqish sabablari, kasallikni tashxislash, davolash va qoʻllab quvvatlash ular bilan qanday ishlash turlari boʻyicha yozilgan.*

Tayanch atamalar: *Autizm, muloqot, nutq, inson, xususiyat, nevrologik, xulq-atvor, ekologik, test, soʻrovnomalar, kommunikatsiya, genetik omil, psixolog, nevrolog, logoped.*

KIRISH

Autizm spektr buzilishi (ASB) – bu rivojlanishning nevrologik xususiyatlariga bogʻliq boʻlgan murakkab holat boʻlib, u insonning ijtimoiy muloqot, nutq va xulq-atvorida oʻziga xos oʻzgarishlarga olib keladi. Autizm turli shakllarda namoyon boʻlishi mumkin, shuning uchun u "spektr" deb ataladi. Ushbu maqolada autizm kasalligi, uning alomatlarini, sababchilari va davolash usullari haqida maʼlumot beriladi.

Autizmning asosiy xususiyatlari

Autizm spektr buzilishiga chalingan bolalarda quyidagi asosiy belgilar kuzatiladi:

1. Ijtimoiy muloqotdagi muammolar:

Autizmli bolalar koʻpincha koʻz bilan muloqot qilishdan qochishadi, boshqalar bilan suhbatni boshlashda yoki davom ettirishda qiyinchiliklarga duch kelishadi. Boshqalarning his-tuygʻularini tushunish va ularga javob berish ham qiyin boʻlishi mumkin.

2. Xulq-atvor va qiziqishdagi oʻziga xosliklar:

Bunday bolalar odatda bir xil faoliyatni takrorlashni yoki faqat maʼlum bir mavzularga qiziqishni afzal koʻradilar. Ular odatdagi tartibning oʻzgarishiga sezgir boʻlib, bu ularga noqulaylik tugʻdirishi mumkin.

3. Nutq va kommunikatsiya buzilishlari:

Baʼzi bolalarda gapirish kechikishi yoki butunlay yoʻqligi kuzatiladi. Ayrimlar oddiy soʻzlar va iboralarni takrorlashadi yoki soʻzlarni odatiy boʻlmagan maʼnoda ishlatadilar.

Autizmning sabablari;

Autizmning aniq sabablari hali toʻliq oʻrganilmagan, ammo tadqiqotlar bir qator omillarni aniqlagan:

Genetik omillar: Koʻplab tadqiqotlar autizm spektr buzilishiga genetik moyillik sabab boʻlishi mumkinligini koʻrsatadi. Autizmli bolalarda asab tizimini boshqaruvchi genlarda oʻzgarishlar kuzatiladi.

Ekologik omillar: Homiladorlik davridagi zararli omillar, masalan, homilaning toksinlar yoki kimyoviy moddalar bilan taʼsirlanishi, autizm rivojlanishiga olib kelishi mumkin.

Nevrologik sabablar: Tadqiqotlar autizmli odamlarda miya tuzilmasi va funksiyasida oʻzgarishlar borligini aniqlagan.

Autizmni tashxislash

Autizmni erta tashxislash uning rivojlanishida muhim ahamiyatga ega. Tashxis quyidagi usullarga asoslanadi:

1. Bolani kuzatish: Ijtimoiy muloqot va xulq-atvoridagi o'zgarishlarni aniqlash.

2. Test va so'rovnomalar: Maxsus diagnostik vositalar, masalan, ADOS (Autism Diagnostic Observation Schedule) va AQ (Autism Quotient) testlari yordamida tashxis qo'yiladi.

3. Mutaxassis maslahati: Nevrolog, psixolog yoki logoped kabi mutaxassislar bolaning holatini baholashadi.

Autizmni davolash va qo'llab-quvvatlash.

Autizm spektr buzilishini davolashning maqsadi bolaning ijtimoiy va nutqiy rivojlanishini qo'llab-quvvatlashdir. Quyidagi usullar keng qo'llaniladi:

1. Tergovchi davolash:

ABA (Applied Behavior Analysis) terapiyasi – bola xulq-atvorini boshqarish va ijtimoiy ko'nikmalarni o'rgatishga qaratilgan.

Nutq terapiyasi – bolalarda gapirish va muloqot qilish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish.

2. Dori vositalari:

Ayrim hollarda, masalan, xavotir yoki uyqu buzilishi kuzatilganda, simptomlarni kamaytirishga qaratilgan dori vositalari buyurilishi mumkin.

3. Ijtimoiy qo'llab-quvvatlash:

Maxsus ta'lim dasturlari, oilaviy maslahatlar va jamiyatdagi qo'llab-quvvatlash guruhlari autizimli bolalar va ularning oilalari uchun muhimdir.

Xulosa:

Autizm spektr buzilishi murakkab va o'ziga xos rivojlanish buzilishidir. Uni erta tashxislash va tegishli qo'llab-quvvatlash choralari orqali bolalarning hayot sifatini yaxshilash mumkin. Autizimli bolalar alohida e'tibor va mehr-muhabbat talab qiladilar. Ularning ijtimoiy muhitga moslashishiga yordam berish – butun jamiyatning vazifasidir.

Bu mavzuda ko'proq xabardorlikka ega bo'lish orqali biz autizimli insonlar hayotini yanada yaxshilashga hissa qo'sha olamiz.

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3. <https://xabardor.uz/uz/post/bolalardagi-autizm-sabablar-ilk-belgilar-va-davolash-usullar>
4. <https://avitsenna.uz/autizm>

PASTDARG'OM TUMAN SHEVASINING LEKSIK XUSUSIYATLARI.

Telmanova Aziza Qahramon qizi

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada Pastdarg'om tuman shevasining leksik xususiyatlari haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Hududda ishlatiladigan so'zlarning kelib chiqishi hamda shakl va ma'no munosabatiga ko'ra turlari tahlil qilingan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *lahja, adabiy til, ma'nodosh so'zlar, shakldosh so'zlar, mahalliy so'zlar, o'zlashma.*

O'zbek tili leksikasi o'zining qadimiy va boy tarixiga egadir. U bir qancha asrlar mobaynida rivojlanib kelgan. Tilimizdagi so'zlarning ayrimlari eng qadimgi davrlardan beri turmush talablarini qondirib kelgan bo'lsa, boshqa xillari nisbatan keyinroq paydo bo'lgan.

Vaqt o'tishi bilan mavjud so'zlardagi ma'no va ma'no nozikliklarida o'zgarishlar ham yuz berib turgan. O'zbek tilining dialektlari va shevalari xalq og'zaki nutqining tarkibiy qismi bo'lib, ular hududiy xususiyatlarga ko'ra o'ziga xos lug'at boyligiga ega. Pastdarg'om tumani shevasi ham Samarqand viloyati shevalari qatoriga kiradi va o'zining leksik jihatdan adabiy tilga nisbatan farqli so'zlar, talaffuz o'zgarishlari, o'zlashgan birliklar va mahalliy terminlar bilan ajralib turadi.

Ushbu maqolada Pastdarg'om shevasining lug'aviy tarkibi, mahalliy va qadimiy so'zlari, o'zlashmalar va adabiy til bilan farqli jihatlari keng tahlil qilinadi.

Ma'lumki, tilimizdagi so'zlarning aksaryatida bir qancha ma'nolari bor, ularning qachon yuzaga kelganligini o'rganish tilshunoslar uchun zarur bo'lsa, bu so'zlarning necha xil ma'noda qo'llanilishini o'rganish ushbu tilda so'zlashuvchilarning hammasi uchun zarurdir. Bu ayniqsa shoir, yozuvchilar uchun ham alohida ahamiyat kasb etadi. So'zlarni qo'llash va ularning ma'nolaridan foydalanishda shoir-yozuvchilarning imkoniyatlari g'oyat kattadir. Chunki ular adabiy tilimiz leksikasidan tashqari, sheva imkoniyatlaridan ham keng foydalanadilar. Natijada shevalardagi ayrim so'zlar ommalashib, adabiy normalarga aylanib boradi⁴.

O'zbek xalq shevalari leksikasini, jumladan, ma'nodosh, shakldosh, ko'p ma'noli, yangi so'zlar xususiyatlarini o'rganish shevashunoslar oldida turgan muhim vazifalardan biridir.

Chunki ma'lum bir sheva yoki bir qancha shevalar leksikasini o'rganish, bir tomondan til tarixi uchun qimmatli bo'lsa, ikkinchi tomondan adabiy tilni rivojlantirish uchun ham ahamiyatlidir.

O'zbek lahjalari leksikasini ko'zdan kechirar ekanmiz, har uchala lahjaning o'ziga xos leksik qatlamlari mavjudligini ko'ramiz. Shu umumiy tomonlardan tashqari, ularning har birida o'ziga xos leksik qatlamlar ham mavjud, jumladan, qipchoq shevalarida ham bunday xususiyatlar uchraydi.

Buni hatto Pastdarg'om tumanida mavjud bo'lgan shevalar materiallarida ham ko'rish mumkin. Pastdarg'om tumanida istiqomat qiluvchi aholi vakillari tilimizdagi uch lahjada

⁴. Назар Ражабов. Узбек шевашунослиги Тошкент: Укитувчи, 1996. – Б.270

(qarluq, qipchoq, o'g'uz) ham so'zlashadi, ammo ularning katta qismini qipchoq sheva vakillari tashkil qiladi.

Shevalar umumxalq o'zbek tilining bir tarmog'i bo'lish bilan birga, adabiy til bilan o'zaro umumiy va xususiy leksik qatlamlarga ega. Bu shevalardagi so'zlar shakldosh, ma'nodosh, ko'p ma'noli va zid ma'noli kabi munosabatlar jihatidan bir-birlaridan hamda adabiy farq qiladi. Shularni hisobga olib, ularning har biri haqida alohida-alohida to'xtalib o'tamiz.

O'zbek tili ham o'zining katta leksik qatlamiga egadir. Bu qatlamga kiruvchi sinonim so'zlar tilimizning lug'at tarkibini boyitadi, uni yanada kengaytirishga xizmat qiladi. Tildagi ma'nodosh so'zlarni yaxshi egallash va undan to'g'ri foydalanish nutq uchun katta imkoniyatlar yaratib beradi. O'zbek tilida bo'lgani kabi, uning lahja va shevalarida ham ma'nodosh so'zlar nihoyatda ko'p. Lahja va shevalardagi ayrim so'zlar esa adabiy tilimizning leksik qatlamini to'ldiradi.

Masalan, hozirgi adabiy tilimizdagi izlamoq, qidirmoq, axtarmoq, istamoq sinonimik qatorlaridagi so'zlar turli sheva materiallaridan olingan. Xususan, istamoq Farg'ona, O'sh kabi shevalarda, izlamoq qipchoq shevalarida, qidirmoq Toshkent va Samarqand shevalarida qo'llaniladi. Yuqoridagi so'zlar ichida axtarmoq shaklida qo'llanilishi nisbatan chegaralangan. Bu shakl qipchoq lahjasida axtarmaq // aqtarmaq deb ishlatiladi. Qipchoq shevalari materiallari ma'nodosh so'zlarning ma'nolarini farqlashga yordam beradi. Masalan, ozuqa turlaridan biri- "yonichqa// jonichqa" deb yuritilib, uning quritilgan holatiga "beda" deyiladi. Hali uning avj olib o'sayotgan, lekin pishib yetmagan holati esa "qara ko'rpe" deb ataladi. Qipchoq shevalaridagi ma'nodosh so'zlar tuzilishi jihatdan sodda, juft va birikmali ma'nodosh so'zlarga bo'linadi. Pastdarg'om hududida ishlatiladigan shunday dialektlararo sinonimlarga misollar keltiramiz:

1. Sodda sinonimlar: arg'imchoq (adabiy tilda) xalinchak, kachela (shevada);

O'g'it (adabiy tilda) go'ng, nuri (shevada);

Isiriq (adabiy tilda) adirasman, hazarisvan shevada;

Paqir (adabiy tilda) satil, chelak (shevada).

2. Juft sinonimlar: yaxshi-durust (adabiy tilda) jaxshi-diris (shevada);

Kir-iflos (adabiy tilda) kir-iplos (shevada);

Urf-odat (adabiy tilda) urp-odat (shevada).

3. Birikmali sinonimlar: qash qara (sinonimning bu turi nisbatan kam ishlatiladi)

Ma'nodosh sinonimlar shevalarda asosan ikki yo'l bilan hosil qilinadi:

1. So'zlarning ma'no jihatidan bir-biriga o'xshash va yaqinlashuvi natijasida.

Masalan, dos//ag'ayni//jo'ra//qadrdon//o'rtoq kabi.

2. Boshqa tillardan shevalarga so'zlarning o'tishi natijasida. Bu arabcha, forsha, tojikcha, ruscha so'zlarning shevalarda so'zlashuvchi aholining tilidagi so'zlar bilan yaqin ma'noda juft holda ishlatilishi.

O'zbek shevalarining leksik tarkibida sinonimlarning paydo bo'lishi turli tarixiy va etnik omillar, o'zbek adabiy tili va boshqa tillarning mazkur shevalarga ta'siri hamda dialektlarning o'zaro munosabati bilan belgilanadi. Shuni aytish kerakki, umuman olganda absolyut sinonimlarning bo'lishi qiyin.

Zotan, sinonimlar odatda har xil shevalar orasida ma'lum darajada bir-birlariga nisbatan muqobil bo'la olsa-da, lekin, xususan adabiy tilda ular bir-birlariga nisbatan tamoman muqobil bo'lishi qiyin. Chunki ularning ma'nolarida ma'lum darajada farq bo'ladi va ma'lum darajada ma'no ottenkasi mavjud bo'ladi. O'zbek shevalarida so'zlashuvchi aholi qadimiy xalqlardan bo'lib, uning tiliga turli dialektlarning va boshqa tillarning ta'siri bo'ladi.

Oqibatda bir tushunchani bir necha so'z yordamida, ya'ni sinonimlar vositasida ifodalash yuzaga keldi. Shu bois ham shevaning dialektal sinonimlari qatoridagi komponentlar dialektal o'zbekcha so'zlar bo'lsa, ba'zilar kelib chiqishidan qat'i nazar o'zbek adabiy tilining lug'at tarkibiga mansub so'zlardir.

Shu jihatdan bunday sinonimlarni ikki guruhga bo'lish mumkin: a) ichki(xususiy) sinonimlar, b) tashqi (umumiy) sinonimlar. Belgi, narsa, hodisa, harakat o'zbek adabiy tiliga ma'lum bo'lmagan birdan ortiq dialektal leksik birliklarida ifodalangan sinonimlar ichki sinonimlardir. Ular shevalarning o'z ichidagi sinonimlar hisoblanadi.

O'zbek xalq shevalarida birdan ortiq dialektal so'z bir ma'noni ifodalaydi va bunda to'liq sinonimlar hosil bo'ladi. Ma'nosi tamoman bir xil bo'lgan sinonimlarning katta bir qismi bir predmet, hodisa, belgi haqidagi tushuncha mazkur shevalar tarqalgan joylardagi aholi nutqida turlicha nomlanishi natijasida yuzaga keladi.

Tashqi sinonimlar dialektal so'z bilan adabiy so'z yoki dialektal so'z bilan adabiy tilda bo'lmagan o'zbek tilining boshqa dialektidan kirgan so'z bilan bir xil ma'noli bo'lgan so'zlardir. Bu guruhlariga bo'linishni Pastdarg'om tuman shevasida ishlatiladigan so'zlar misolida ko'rib chiqamiz: дэв, ьркът - baquvat; ҳэпэзъ тушмэқ - йузмэқ - suzmoq; қундэқлэдъ, орадъ - yo'rgakladi; adabiy tildagi bemalol, hotirjam so'zlari shevalarda арқэйтн, ҳэвлъқмэдэн so'zlari bilan sinonimik qatorni hosil qiladi. Yoki adabiy tildagi shoshilinch, tez, darrov so'zlar shevadagi ьштэрэп, қъчэлэнг kabi so'zlar bilan sinonimik qatorni hosil qilib, birga qo'llanilib keladi.

O'zbek tili va o'zbek xalq shevalari shakldosh so'zlarga nihoyatda boy. Omonimlar o'zbek tilida va shevalarda turli manbalar hisobiga yuzaga keladi, ya'ni bunda til taraqqiyotining tashqi va ichki manbalari asosiy o'rin egallaydi. Shevalardagi omonimlar quyidagi usullarda yuzaga keladi:

1. Tasodifiy fonetik o'xshashlik natijasida paydo bo'lgan omonimlar. [o ~ a] қэш (ad. orf. qosh) 1. қэш - qosh (от) ; 2) қэш= - qochmoq (fe'l) ; чэй (ad. orf. choy). 1) чэй - choy (от) ; 2) чэй - qo'lingni yuv; дэйрэ. 1. dayra - doira [a]. Aylana bilan o'ralgan yuza; 2. дэйрэ - doira, childirma, doira chalmoq, 3. dayra - daryo (f-t) ; [f ~ v]: тэв (ad. orf. tog', top-). 1. тэв - tog'; 2. тэв - topmoq; [ч ~ ш]: keshta (ad. orf. kashta). 1. keshta - kashta; 2. keshta - kech bo'lganda; [г ~ й]: туй= (ad. orf. tugmoq) 1. туй- tugmoq, arqonni tugmoq; 2. туй - donni yanchmoq; 3. туй= - hosil tugishi va boshqa.

2. Ma'noning parchalanishi natijasida paydo bo'lgan omonimlar. Bunda so'zning shakli (fonetik tuzilishi) o'zgarmay qolishi tufayli omonim yuzaga keladi. Masalan: дэм (nafas), дэм (hordiq), дэм (to'g'on), дэм (jim o'tir) omonimlari xuddi shunday yuzaga kelgan. Yoki quloq adabiy tilda ham, mazkur shevalarda ham odam va hayvonning bosh qismiga

joylashgan eshitish organi. Bu soʻzning ana shu xususiyatlari asosida maʼnolar tarmoqlanadi, u polisemantik soʻzdir. Masalan: ҚўЗОННЪНГ ҚУЛЌФЪ, СЪТЪЛНЪНГ ҚУЛЌФЪ, ҚУЛЌФ - ekin yerni yorib chiqqanda koʻringan yaprogʻi kabilar.

Pastdargʻom tumani shevasida adabiy til bilan qiyoslaganda oʻziga xos lugʻaviy birliklar mavjud. Ular tarkibiga quyidagilar kiradi:

1. Mahalliy soʻzlar
2. Talaffuzi oʻzgargan soʻzlar
3. Eski oʻzbek tilidan saqlanib qolgan soʻzlar
4. Fors-tojik tilidan oʻzlashmalar
5. Rus tilidan kirib kelgan soʻzlar
6. Kasb-hunar va xoʻjalikka oid maxsus terminlar

Har bir toifani batafsil koʻrib chiqamiz.

1. Mahalliy soʻzlar

Baʼzi soʻzlar faqat Pastdargʻom shevasida yoki Samarqand viloyatining boshqa hududlariga xos boʻlib, adabiy tilda kam uchraydi yoki umuman ishlatilmaydi. Quyida shunday soʻzlarga misollar keltiramiz:

- buyugʻ – “sovuq, izgʻirin” (adabiy tilda faqat "sovuq" sifatida ishlatiladi)
- chuvrindi – “eskirgan kiyim yoki mato”
- zov – “ariq, suv yoʻli”
- gʻishtak – “uy” (adabiy tilda "gʻishtli bino" maʼnosida)
- talchiq – “yengil qilib tayyorlangan oziq-ovqat”

2. Talaffuzi oʻzgargan soʻzlar

Pastdargʻom shevasida baʼzi soʻzlar fonetik oʻzgarishlar tufayli adabiy tildan farq qiladi. Quyida bunday oʻzgarishlarning baʼzi turlari keltirilgan:

Adabiy til	Pastdargʻom shevasi	Maʼnosi
qizil	gʻizil	rang nomi
sariq	sari(sori)	rang nomi
choynak	choynigʻ	choy quyish idishi
kelyapman	kelayapman	kelmoq feʼlining oʻzgarishi
bugun	bukun	hozirgi kun
birga	brigʻa	birga, hamroh boʻlish
yostiq	dostiq	bosh ostiga qoʻyib yotish, yonboshlab suyanish uchun ishlatiladigan yumshoq buyum

Talaffuzdagi bu farqlar fonetik xususiyatlar, yaʼni undosh tovushlarning yumshashi yoki qattiqlashishi natijasida yuzaga kelgan.

3. Eski oʻzbek tilidan saqlanib qolgan soʻzlar

Baʼzi soʻzlar qadimgi turkiy yoki eski oʻzbek tilidan qolgan boʻlib, bugungi adabiy tilda kam qoʻllaniladi:

- otashkurak – “olovga puflaydigan temir moslama”
- pargʻa – “kichik suv yoʻli”

- charvi – “podachilik bilan shug‘ullanuvchi kishi”
- chopon – “uzun yengsiz kiyim”
- chiy – “o‘simlikdan yasalgan mato yoki parda”

4. Fors-tojik tilidan o‘zlashmalar

Samarqand viloyati shevalarida, jumladan, Pastdarg‘om shevasida ham fors-tojik tilidan o‘zlashgan so‘zlar ko‘p uchraydi. Buning sababi tarixiy jihatdan mintaqaning forsiy nutqli xalqlar bilan uzoq vaqt davomida til va madaniyat almashinuviga ega bo‘lganidadir.

- mizoj – “kayfiyat, ruhiy holat”
- shabboda – “salqin shabada”
- daraxtzor – “bog”
- ashyo – “narsa, buyum”
- baqo – “barqarorlik”

5. Rus tilidan kirib kelgan so‘zlar

Rus tili ta’siri ostida Pastdarg‘om shevasiga ham ayrim ruscha so‘zlar singib ketgan:

- motur (ruscha "motor") – “dvigatel”
- kantiner (ruscha "konteyner") – “katta temir quti”
- magazin – “do‘kon” (adabiy tilga ham kirib kelgan)
- traktor – “dehqonchilik mashinasi”

Bu so‘zlarning aksariyati texnologiya va ishlab chiqarish bilan bog‘liq.

6. Kasb-hunar va xo‘jalikka oid maxsus terminlar

Pastdarg‘om shevasida chorvachilik, dehqonchilik va hunarmandchilik bilan bog‘liq maxsus so‘zlar ham mavjud:

- qop – “don solinadigan qop”
- murtak – “yangi unib chiqqan o‘simlik”
- bo‘z – “paxtadan tayyorlangan mato”
- zinxona – “chorva mollari boqiladigan joy”
- cho‘kich – “qattiq yer chopishda ishlatiladigan asbob”

Pastdarg‘om tumani shevasi o‘zbek tilining muhim lahjalari qatoriga kirib, o‘ziga xos leksik xususiyatlarga ega. Uning lug‘aviy tarkibi mahalliy so‘zlar, eski o‘zbek tilidan qolgan birliklar, fors-tojik va rus tilidan o‘zlashmalar hamda kasb-hunar bilan bog‘liq terminlardan iborat.

Bu shevaning o‘rganilishi nafaqat dialektologik jihatdan, balki xalq tilining tarixiy rivojlanishini tushunish uchun ham muhimdir. Pastdarg‘om tuman shevasi o‘ziga xos leksik xususiyatlari bilan ajralib turadi. Ushbu shevada qadimiy so‘zlar, mahalliy dialektizmlar, shuningdek, atrof-muhit va xo‘jalik faoliyati bilan bog‘liq so‘zlar keng qo‘llaniladi. Shevaning lug‘at tarkibi asosiy qatlam va yangi qatlam so‘zlaridan iborat bo‘lib, u mintaqaning tarixiy, madaniy va ijtimoiy hayotidan darak beradi.

Tadqiqot davomida shevada mavjud bo‘lgan turkiy va fors-tojik tillaridan olingan so‘zlarning qo‘llanilishiga alohida e’tibor qaratildi. Natijalar shuni ko‘rsatadiki, Pastdarg‘om shevasi o‘ziga xos fonetik va morfologik xususiyatlardan tashqari, semantik jihatdan ham an’anaviy va zamonaviy unsurlar uyg‘unlashganligi bilan ajralib turadi.

Mazkur shevaning leksik xususiyatlarini o'rganish nafaqat mahalliy dialektologiya uchun, balki umumiy tilshunoslik va etnolingvistika nuqtayi nazaridan ham muhimdir.

Sheva leksikasining tahlili mintaqaning tarixiy-madaniy aloqalarini o'rganishga, shuningdek, o'zbek tilining dialektal rang-barangligini chuqurroq tushunishga xizmat qiladi.

O'zbek shevalaridagi barcha leksik o'ziga xosliklarni o'rganish lug'at boyligimizni, til imkoniyatlarimizni kengaytirishga yordam beradi va shuning uchun adabiy tilga bunday so'zlarni o'rni bilan qabul qilib borish zarur.

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ СИСТЕМЫ НАКАЗАНИЯ, НЕ СВЯЗАННОЙ С ЛИШЕНИЕМ СВОБОДЫ

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Аннотация: *В данной статье изложены задачи, определяемые в рамках уголовного законодательства в процессе либерализации уголовных наказаний, а также предложения по расширению наказаний, не связанных с лишением свободы.*

Ключевые слова: *ответственность, вина, исправительные работы, лишение свободы, пробация, исполнение уголовных наказаний, штраф, социальная опасность, система законодательства.*

В Конституции Республики Узбекистан права и свободы человека, его честь и достоинство, права на неприкосновенность закреплены как высшая ценность, основанная на международных принципах. Практическое подтверждение этого процесса можно наблюдать в масштабных реформах, проводимых в нашей стране в последние годы по обеспечению прав человека в процессе государственного управления и дальнейшему повышению его эффективности.

В частности, в целях совершенствования системы исполнения наказаний, обеспечения защиты и укрепления прав, свобод и законных интересов осужденных, предупреждения повторного совершения преступлений, повышения эффективности воспитательной работы по их нравственному исправлению сформирована законодательная и нормативно-правовая база, соответствующая международным стандартам, данный процесс постоянно совершенствуется.

Принятие постановления главы нашего государства от 7 ноября 2018 года № ПП-4006 "О мерах по коренному совершенствованию уголовно-исполнительного законодательства" послужило дальнейшему совершенствованию деятельности органов внутренних дел в сфере надзора за лицами, осужденными к наказаниям, не связанным с лишением свободы. В целях эффективной организации исполнения постановления принят приказ министра внутренних дел Республики Узбекистан от 7 декабря 2018 года № 316 "О мерах по организации деятельности службы пробации," утверждены организационная структура службы пробации и Положение о службе пробации.

В отличие от ранее действовавшей Инспекции по исполнению наказаний, не связанных с лишением свободы органов внутренних дел, после создания Службы пробации в этом направлении произошел ряд изменений. Если раньше исполнение наказаний, назначенных судами лицам, осужденным к наказаниям, не связанным с лишением свободы, контролировалось органами внутренних

дел, то в настоящее время создана служба пробации, которая, наряду с контролем исполнения назначенных наказаний, уделяет основное внимание вопросам социальной адаптации лиц, осужденных к наказанию, обеспечению их занятости, обучению и трудоустройству, оказанию социальной, правовой и психологической помощи поднадзорным, а главное, воспитанию личности.

Согласно действующему законодательству, в отношении лиц, осужденных к лишению свободы, ограничению свободы или исправительным работам, суд может заменить неотбытую часть наказания более мягким наказанием. Замена наказания более мягким применяется к осужденным, выполнившим требования порядка, установленного для конкретных видов наказания, и добросовестно относящимся к труду.

В результате этой деятельности в нашей стране создана новая система исполнения наказаний, не связанных с лишением свободы, осуществления действенного контроля за поведением лиц, находящихся под надзором подразделений пробации, и благодаря этому достигается снижение повторного совершения преступлений поднадзорными лицами.

Если обратиться к информации, предоставленной Центром по связям с общественностью Верховного суда Республики Узбекистан по уголовным делам, рассмотренным судами в 2024 году, то в течение 2024 года судами по уголовным делам было рассмотрено 58 418 уголовных дел в отношении 73 797 лиц, а 1244 человека были оправданы и реабилитированы.

Число осужденных составило 55 763 человека, из них 17 396 человек были приговорены к лишению свободы и 37 077 человек - к другим видам наказания, 1290 человек получили условные сроки. Из числа осужденных 49 297 мужчин, 6466 женщин, 20 922 молодых людей (в том числе 1911 несовершеннолетних) и 2123 лиц старше 60 лет. 7362 лица были освобождены из-под стражи в зале суда в связи с назначением наказаний, не связанных с лишением свободы, 33612 лиц были условно-досрочно освобождены от отбывания наказания, назначенное наказание заменено более мягким для 12286 лиц, а статьи, необоснованно предъявленные органами предварительного следствия к 13522 лицам, были сняты с обвинений или переквалифицированы. На основании гарантийных писем 272 лицам (молодежи, женщинам и другим) назначены наказания, не связанные с лишением свободы.

В результате эффективного применения института примирения 14698 лиц освобождены от уголовной ответственности.

В отношении 8 586 лиц, возместивших причиненный материальный ущерб, назначены наказания, не связанные с лишением свободы.

В апелляционном порядке было рассмотрено 10843 уголовных дела в отношении 15720 лиц. Решения, вынесенные судами первой инстанции в

отношении 1715 лиц, были отменены, а судебные решения, вынесенные в отношении 3556 лиц, изменены.

Судебной коллегией по уголовным делам Верховного суда в кассационном порядке рассмотрено 5130 уголовных дел в отношении 5855 лиц. Решения, вынесенные нижестоящими судами в отношении 1143 лиц, были отменены, а судебные решения, вынесенные в отношении 509 лиц, изменены.

Также в кассационной инстанции повторно рассмотрено 402 уголовных дела в отношении 467 лиц. Решения, вынесенные в отношении 288 лиц, были отменены, а судебные решения, вынесенные в отношении 121 лица, были изменены.

Известно, что в целях обеспечения исполнения судебных приговоров (определений), вынесенных по видам наказаний, не связанным с лишением свободы, особое внимание следует уделять характеру преступлений осужденных, степени общественной опасности, а также личности и поведению осужденных. То есть на представителей соответствующей сферы возлагается ряд задач по социальной адаптации и профессиональной ориентации для предотвращения повторного совершения преступлений поднадзорными лицами.

В целях дальнейшего развития деятельности службы пробации органов внутренних дел в пункте 30 Государственной программы по реализации Стратегии действий по пяти приоритетным направлениям развития Республики Узбекистан в 2017-2021 годах в Год поддержки молодежи и укрепления здоровья населения, утвержденной Указом Президента Республики Узбекистан от 3 февраля 2021 года № УП-6155, определен ряд задач по дальнейшему совершенствованию исполнения наказаний и службы пробации с широким внедрением международных стандартов и принципов гуманизма. Включая:

- повышение статуса центральных и территориальных органов службы пробации, укрепление кадрового потенциала и материально-технической базы этой службы;

- совершенствование механизмов контроля за поведением лиц, находящихся под пробационным надзором, их социальной адаптации и предупреждения совершения новых преступлений;

- внедрение порядка электронного наблюдения и мониторинга в режиме реального времени за действиями лиц, находящихся под пробационным надзором, с прикреплением к ним электронных браслетов;

- подготовка кадров по направлению образования и специальности "Пробационная деятельность";

- определены задачи по совершенствованию деятельности центров реабилитации и социальной адаптации лиц, освобожденных из мест лишения свободы, при хокимиятах;

- подготовка, прогнозирование и планирование деятельности по психологическому, социально-бытовому обеспечению и трудоустройству лиц, освобожденных из мест лишения свободы;

- принятие действенных мер, направленных на сокращение числа рецидивов и повторных преступлений, укрепление системы раннего предупреждения правонарушений.

- организация и обеспечение социальной защиты лиц, освобожденных из мест лишения свободы, удовлетворение их первичных потребностей путем выдачи в установленном порядке единовременного пособия за одежду, питание и жилье;

- создание благоприятных социально-бытовых условий, получение помощи специалистов сферы (психолога, медицинского работника, юриста и др.), выдача в необходимых случаях направлений на лечение, в дома престарелых и лиц с инвалидностью;

- оказание содействия в реабилитации, решении жилищно-бытовых и других социально-быт В связи с необходимостью совершенствования механизмов деятельности службы пробации, внедрения порядка оказания социально-правовой и психологической помощи поднадзорным лицам, особенно изучения их с составлением "социально-психологического портрета," а также подготовки специалистов-психологов в этих процессах, налаживания системы привлечения специалистов-психологов в подразделения пробации, на основании постановления с 1 марта 2020 года налажено взаимодействие между министерствами и ведомствами по оказанию социально-правовой и психологической помощи поднадзорным лицам, в образовательные программы юридических вузов включены специальные темы по изучению психологического портрета поднадзорных лиц, а также налажено прохождение практики курсантами, слушателями и студентами, обучающимися по направлению психологии в соответствующих вузах, в подразделениях пробации.

Вместе с тем, на основании постановления Президента Республики Узбекистан от 15 апреля 2021 года № ПП-5076 "О мерах по внедрению качественно новой системы подготовки профессиональных кадров для органов внутренних дел" в нашей стране налажена совершенно новая система подготовки специалистов для органов внутренних дел, на основании данного постановления, начиная с 2021/2022 учебного года, в Академии Министерства внутренних дел в процессе подготовки кадров организована подготовка специалистов по направлению образования бакалавриата, направлению деятельности пробации.

Утвержден механизм стимулирования сотрудников подразделений пробации за счет Фонда развития службы пробации, подключения подразделений пробации к высокоскоростной всемирной информационной сети

Интернет, в настоящее время принимаются меры по стимулированию сотрудников отдела пробации за счет Фонда развития службы пробации.

Также постановлением Президента Республики Узбекистан от 15.04.2022 г. № ПП-207 внесены дополнения и изменения в некоторые пункты постановления Президента Республики Узбекистан от 7 ноября 2018 года № ПП-4006 "О мерах по коренному совершенствованию уголовно-исполнительного законодательства," а также заменено на 100 процентов образование Фонда развития службы пробации Министерства внутренних дел Республики Узбекистан, указанного в пункте 6 постановления, формируемого за счет 50 процентов удержаний, поступающих от отбывания наказания в виде исправительных работ.

В заключение можно сказать, что применение к лицам, совершившим преступления, наказаний, не связанных с лишением свободы, создало возможность их нравственного воспитания путем социальной адаптации, предотвращения повторного совершения преступлений и возвращения к здоровому образу жизни. В целях организации адресной, индивидуальной и системной регулярной работы с лицами, находящимися под пробационным надзором, определено, что в "Железную тетрадь" по семьям, нуждающимся в материальной помощи и поддержке, в "Женскую тетрадь" и "Молодежную тетрадь" по женщинам и молодежи, нуждающимся в социальной, экономической, правовой, психологической поддержке, знаниях и профессиональном обучении, включены лица, находящиеся под пробационным надзором, и будет проведена системная работа, направленная на их поддержку. Сегодня служба пробации должна стать в полном смысле слова правоохранительным органом.

Деятельность этой структуры пробации полностью защищает права и свободы граждан, общества и государства.

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EASTERN MINIATURE ART: A STUDY OF COLORS, PATTERNS, AND HISTORICAL SIGNIFICANCE

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Introduction: *Eastern miniature art is not merely a form of painting but a vivid expression of Eastern culture, an artistic interpretation of historical events, and a reflection of spiritual values. This art form has evolved over centuries, with each piece distinguished by its unique colors, patterns, and profound meanings. Eastern miniature art, with its delicacy, artistic perfection, and symbolic depth, has become an essential part of not only Eastern cultures but also the global art heritage.*

Keywords: *Eastern miniature art, history of miniature art, Eastern culture, Persian miniatures, Indian miniatures, Uzbek miniatures, Timurid era art, Mughal era miniatures, manuscript illumination, Eastern painting art.*

The Cultural Significance of Eastern Miniature Art: Eastern miniature art is not limited to mere artistic skill. This art form reflects the cultural heritage, traditions, religious beliefs, and historical events of Eastern civilizations. Each miniature preserves the spirit, lifestyle, and social values of a particular era. For example, Persian miniatures depict heroic tales from Ferdowsi's Shahnameh, Indian miniatures showcase the grandeur of the Mughal courts, and Uzbek miniatures illustrate the poetic works of Alisher Navoi and the splendor of the Timurid era.

Artistic Interpretation of Historical Events: Eastern miniature art is a unique method of portraying historical events through an artistic lens. This art form depicts battles, royal life, diplomatic encounters, and other significant events. Miniatures capture intricate details of historical figures, their attire, weapons, and surroundings, making them not only artistic masterpieces but also valuable historical sources.

Reflection of Spiritual Values: Eastern miniature art is designed to express humanity's spiritual quests, moral values, and philosophical perspectives. This art form often portrays eternal themes such as the struggle between good and evil, justice and tyranny, and life and death. For instance, Indian miniatures depict the symbolic narratives of religious epics like the Mahabharata and Ramayana, while Persian miniatures reflect the depths of Sufi philosophy.

Colors, Patterns, and Symbolism: In Eastern miniature art, colors and patterns are not merely decorative but carry deep symbolic meanings. Each color represents a specific idea: gold symbolizes grandeur and divine light, blue represents the sky and eternity, and green signifies nature and renewal. Patterns, often geometric or floral, convey themes of order, balance, and beauty.

Evolution Over Centuries: Eastern miniature art has developed over millennia, with each era introducing new styles and techniques. It reached its peak during the reigns of great empires such as the Timurids, Safavids, and Mughals. Today, this art form continues to thrive, blending traditional techniques with modern artistic expressions.

Conclusion:

Eastern miniature art is more than just a form of painting - it is a vibrant expression of Eastern culture, an artistic interpretation of historical events, and a reflection of spiritual values. Through this art form, humanity's pursuit of beauty, truth, and spirituality has been immortalized across centuries.

Today, Eastern miniature art is celebrated worldwide, recognized for its uniqueness, artistic value, and profound meanings, making it an invaluable part of humanity's cultural heritage.

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INGLIZ VA O‘ZBEK TILLARI LEKSIKASI ASOSIDA O‘QUV LUG‘ATLARINING STRUKTURAVIY XUSUSIYATLARI

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Ingliz tili o‘qituvchisi, Qarshi shahar 1 son ixtisoslashtirilgan maktab internati

Annotatsiya: *Mazkur maqolada ingliz va o‘zbek tillari leksikasi asosida tuzilgan o‘quv lug‘atlarining strukturaviy xususiyatlari tahlil qilinadi. Lug‘atlarning maqsadi, foydalanuvchi auditoriyasi va ularning asosiy komponentlari ko‘rib chiqiladi. Shuningdek, alifbo tartibida, tematik hamda bilingval lug‘atlarning tuzilish shakllari va ularda so‘z birliklarining berilish usullari tahlil qilinadi. Ingliz va o‘zbek tillarining leksik-semantik hamda morfologik xususiyatlari asosida lug‘at tuzishda e‘tiborga olinishi lozim bo‘lgan muhim jihatlar bayon etiladi. Zamonaviy texnologiyalar, raqamli lug‘atlar va interaktiv o‘quv resurslarining lug‘at tuzish jarayoniga ta‘siri ham ko‘rib chiqiladi. Ushbu tadqiqot til o‘rganish jarayonida samarali lug‘at tuzish metodlarini takomillashtirishga hissa qo‘shishi mumkin.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *o‘quv lug‘atlari, ingliz tili, o‘zbek tili, leksik birliklar, bilingval lug‘at, tematik lug‘at, semantik xususiyatlar, morfologik struktura, raqamli lug‘atlar, interaktiv resurslar.*

So‘zlarning biror maqsadda to‘planib, tartibga solingan yig‘indisi lug‘at deyiladi. Lug‘at tuzishning nazariy va amaliy tamoyillari haqidagi soha leksikografiya (grekcha lexicon - lug‘at va grapho - yozaman) deyiladi. Lug‘at tuzuvchi mutaxassislar leksikograflar deyiladi. Lug‘at tuzish tamoyillari va metodikasini ishlab chiqish, leksikograflar ishini tashkil qilish, lug‘at tuzish uchun asos bo‘ladigan kartotekalar tuzish, ularni sistemalashtirish va saqlash leksikografiyaning vazifasidir.

Lug‘at - so‘z xazinasini, undan o‘rinli va maqsadga muvofiq foydalanish inson bilimini kengaytirish, lug‘at boyligini oshirishda hamda fikrni to‘g‘ri va ravon ifodalashda muhim omildir. XX asrning ikkinchi yarmi XI asr boshlarida o‘zbek va ingliz lug‘atlarini o‘rganishga yondashuvlar muammolarni hal qilishda biz tanlagan uchta sohada aks ettirilgan. Agar lug‘atlar ma‘lum darajada konservativ bo‘lsa, ular o‘ziga hos kamchiliklarini va qadr-qimmatini belgilaydi. Chunki I. R. Galperin yozganidek, "leksikografiya hamma narsani o‘z ichiga olishi kerak, u o‘z qudratini, qadrini va nutqda qo‘llanish qobiliyatini yo‘qotmagan tilda yashaydi, shuningdek, so‘nggi paytlarda tug‘ilgan, hayotiy va barqaror bo‘lib chiqqan barcha yangi narsalarni aks ettira oladi”.

Talaffuz lug‘atlari yozishda qat‘iy bo‘lmagan, ammo talaffuzda namoyon bo‘ladigan morfologik o‘zgaruvchanlik darajasining mavjudligini ko‘rish mumkin. Talaffuzda yozma ravishda standart sifatida belgilangan bir qator fe‘llar o‘zgaruvchan paradigmatic dizayndagi fe‘llar bo‘lib chiqadi. Misol uchun, leaned /lent/ и /li:nd/, leaped – /lept/ и /li:pt/, learned – /lə:nt/ и /lə:nd/, dreamed – /dremt/, /drempt/ и /dri:md/ talaffuz qilinishi mumkin.

Ayni paytda jargonning aniq bir bo'lingan qismi yo'q. Faqat uchta sohani - professional, yoshlar va jinoiy jargonlarni tasniflash mumkin. Biroq, naqshlarni aniqlash va lug'atlarni jamiyatdagi alohida guruhlarning xarakterli terminologiyasidan shartli ravishda ajratish mumkin. Texnik atamalar-bu ma'lum bir professional muhitda ma'lum atamalar yoki tushunchalarni tavsiflash uchun ishlatiladigan lug'atlardan qisqartirilgan yoki birlashtirilgan soddalashtirilgan so'zlar. Ushbu so'zlar texnik ta'riflarning aksariyati uzoq va talaffuz qilish qiyin bo'lganligi yoki ularning ma'nolari zamonaviy rasmiy tilda to'liq yo'qligi sababli paydo bo'lgan. Texnik atamalar deyarli barcha professional tashkilotlarda mavjud. Ularning tilini shakllantirish maxsus jargon qoidalariga bo'ysunmaydi. Biroq, jargon aloqa uchun foydali vosita bo'lib, aloqa ma'lum funktsiyaga ega.

Odatda o'smirlar boshqalar bilan o'zaro munosabatlarida bunday iboralarni ishlatmaydilar ular odatda begona deb da'vo qiladigan va ulardan foydalanishni ma'qullamaydi. O'smir jargonlari tez o'zgarib turadi, chunki odamlar cheklangan vaqt davomida o'smirlar, kattalar, ular begona bo'lib, asta-sekin guruh so'zlari va eski ibora va ma'nolarga vaqt o'tishi bilan sodir bo'lgan.

K.Allan va K.Burridge ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, besh xil jargon turi mavjud. 1). Fresh and Creative (yangi va jodkorlik) jargon tilining mutlaqo yangi lug'atga, norasmiy xilma-xillikka ega ekanligini anglatadi. Ba'zi so'zlar allaqachon tanish bo'lgan jargon bo'lishi mumkin, chunki odamlar buni anglamaydi. Sabablari: nega bu jaranglar bizning ongimizga tanish bo'lib qoladi, chunki bu jaranglar uzoq vaqt oldin paydo bo'lgan chunki jargon allaqachon paydo bo'lgan. Misol - awesome jargon so'zi. Ajoyib (adj). Biz nimanidir ajoyib yoki hayratlanarli deb o'ylashimiz uchun ishlatiladi. 2). Compounding (Murakkablik) o'sha jargonni bildiradi. Ikki yoki undan ortiq so'zdan tuzilgan til, unda so'zlar o'zaro bog'liq bo'lmagan denotativ ma'no. Misol - katta qurol. Bu kuchli odam degan ma'noni anglatadi. 3). Imitative (taqlid) taqlid qiluvchi yoki standart inglizcha so'zdan olingan jarangli so'zni anglatadi turli ma'nodagi yoki ikki xil so'zlarni birlashtirgan standart inglizcha so'zlar. 4). Acronym (qisqartma) har bir so'zning birinchi harflaridan so'zlarning natijasi bo'yicha tuzilgan jargon turi ibora yoki bu tur so'z yoki bo'g'in guruhidan bosh harflar bilan yasaladi. The misol LOL. U 1991 yil atrofida AQSHda "baland ovozda kulish" ma'nosida internet stenografiyasi sifatida ishlatiladi. Bu "borish" iborasidan olingan jarangli so'zdir. Jargon "gonna" so'zi odatda dunyodagi deyarli barcha odamlar tomonidan qo'llaniladi. 5). Clipping (qirqim) - ba'zi qismlarini o'chirish yo'li bilan qilingan jargonlarning xilma-xillaridan biri uzunroq so'z bir xil ma'noda qisqaroq shaklga aylanadi. Bundan tashqari, kesish shakli emas rasmiy suhbatda foydalanish uchun mos. Misol uchun imtihon so'zidan foydalanish imtihon. Bundan tashqari, odamlar muloqotda jargondan foydalanishining sabablari bor. jargon kabi ma'lum bir sub-ijtimoiy guruhning o'ziga xosligini ifodalashi mumkin, chunki u ajoyib, Bu hammaga yoqadigan modaga o'xshaydi va u ko'pincha odamlar tomonidan qo'llaniladi. Jargon odatda

yoshlarning yuragi tomonidan yillar davomida qabul qilinadi, bu maqsad faqat o'yin-kulgi uchun.[K. Allan, and K.Burridge.:2000. 66b]

B.Partidge fikriga ko'ra, odamlarning jargon tilidan foydalanish sabablari shunchaki o'yin-kulgida, hursandchilikda, o'zgacha bo'lishda, (buni qo'shiqlar yoki she'rlardan topish mumkin), shubhasiz hibsga olish,hatto hayratlanarli, qisqa va ixcham bo'lish uchun tilni boyitish uchun yangi so'zlarni ixtiro qilish,aniqlik atmosferasini berish idealistik, yaqinlik va uzoqdan qarama-qarshilik, jiddiyeligini kamaytirish uchun suhbat, yuqori jamoatchilikni qiziqtirish uchun (buni bolalar ota-onalariga nisbatan ishlatadigan jargonlardan ko'rish mumkin); ijtimoiy aloqani osonlashtirish uchun, do'stona munosabatda bo'lish uchun ma'lum bir guruhga mansubligini ko'rsatadi, birovga tegishli emasligini ko'rsatish yoki isbotlash ma'lum bir guruhga, yashirin bo'lish, atrofdagilar (bolalar, talabalar,oshiqlar, siyosiy a'zolar, bosh ko'rsatkichlar).

Jargondan foydalanish til evolyutsiyasi va til o'zgarishini o'rganish nuqtai nazaridan tilshunoslikka bir qancha muhim ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Tilshunoslar tilning qanday o'zgarishini, uning turli ijtimoiy kontekstlarda qanday ishlashini va kengroq ijtimoiy tendentsiyalarni qanday aks ettirishini tushunish uchun jargonlarni o'rganadilar. Bu yerda jargonning tilshunoslikka ba'zi asosiy ta'siri keltirilgan:

Til evolyutsiyasi va innovatsiyasi: Jargonlar (Slang) ko'pincha til innovatsiyasining harakatlantiruvchi kuchi hisoblanadi. U kengroq tilga yangi so'zlar, iboralar va iboralarni kiritishi mumkin, ularning ba'zilar vaqt o'tishi bilan asosiy oqimga aylanishi va hatto rasmiy lug'atlarga kirishi mumkin. Masalan:

Neologizmlar: Slang butunlay yangi so'zlarni yaratishi yoki mavjudlarini qayta kontekstualashtirishi mumkin. Misol uchun, "selfie", "emoji" yoki "heshteg" kabi atamalar bir vaqtlar jargon hisoblangan, ammo hozir yozma va og'zaki tilda keng qabul qilinadi.

Semantik siljish: Jargonlar (Slang) ham mavjud so'zlarning ma'nosini o'zgartirishi mumkin. Misol uchun, "cool" (salqin) so'zi birinchi navbatda haroratni tavsiflash uchun ishlatilgan, ammo hozir ma'qullash yoki hayratni bildirish uchun ishlatiladi.Tilshunoslar ko'pincha tilning doimiy rivojlanishini tushunish uchun jargonlarning kelib chiqishi va tarqalishini kuzatib boradilar. Ushbu yangiliklar madaniy va ijtimoiy amaliyotlardagi o'zgarishlarni ham ko'rsatishi mumkin.

Ingliz tilida yoshlar o'rtasida eng ko'p qo'llaniladigan jargonlar quyidagilar: Low-Key - added to a feeling or desire to downplay it; [Collinsdictionary] low-key - xis-tuyg'u qo'shish yoki uni kamaytirishga bo'lgan xohish ma'nosini biladiradi (masalan: "Men aqldan ozganman").

Preppy or preppie ('prepi) informal. adjective. - characteristic of or denoting a fashion style of neat, understated, and often expensive clothe young but classic, suggesting that the wearer is well off, upper class, and conservative. [Collinsdictionary] Preppy - klassik toza kiyim, bejirim va ko'pincha qimmat moda uslubiga xos bo'lgan yoki uni ifodalovchi kiyim kiyuvchining yaxshi ta'minlangan, yuqori sinf va konservativ ekanligini ko'rsatadi.

Sigma - (modifier) informal- denoting a high-achieving individual who pursues his or her own goals rather than being part of a society. [Collinsdictionary] Sigma- jamiyatning bir qismi bo'lishdan ko'ra o'z maqsadlariga intiladigan yuqori yutuqli shaxsni anglatadi

O'zbek tilida yoshlar o'rtasida eng ko'p qo'llaniladigan jargonlar quyidagilar: Sindirding - qoyil qilib bajarding; biror-bir ishni muvaffaqiyatli bajarish; [Ro'zmetova.A.:2022]

Talaffuz lug'atlarini tahlil qilish jarayonida leksik birliklarning nostandart paradigma shakllari mavjudligini yaqqol ko'rish mumkin. Chunki nostandart orfografik shakllar faqat "nostandart" deb talaffuz qilinadi va standart orfografik shakllar ingliz tilida ikkita (yoki undan ko'p) "standart" va "nostandart" talaffuz qilinadi. Ayniqsa Amerika talaffuziga hos ingliz tilida buni yaqqol ko'rish mumkin. Ushbu misollardan ko'rinib turibdiki, dispersiya darajalari mavjud bo'lib, xorijiy tilda so'zlashuvchilar ingliz tilida leksikografik tahlil yordamida aniq topishlari mumkin, chunki bu xususiyat yozma matnlarda o'z aksini topmaydi, balki og'zaki nutqda tahlil qilish mumkin bo'ladi. Lug'atlarni o'rganish zarur bo'lgan ikkinchi soha - lug'at va semantik tahlil katta va kichik vaqt oralig'ida siljishlar. Masalan, tarixdan shuni kuzatish mumkinki, turli nashr etilgan yillardagi neologizm lug'atlari va turli nashr etilgan zamonaviy izohli lug'atlarni o'rganish orqali yangi so'zlar va ma'nolarni ishlab chiqishga erishib kelingan. Ko'rsatilgandek, yangi so'zlar

- 1) dastlab lug'atlarda qayd etilgan so'zlar o'z holicha ma'nolarda uzoq vaqt saqlanib qoladi;
- 2) so'zlar semantik va stilistik jihatdan rivojlanadi;
- 3) asta-sekin lingvistik periferiyaga o'tish yoki lug'atni tark etishi mumkin;
- 4) qo'llanishda keskinlikni boshdan kechirgan holda, tilda davom etaveradi, istorizmga aylanadi, shuningdek, metaforik tarzda qayta ko'rib chiqiladi.

XX asrning o'rtalaridan boshlab ingliz neologizmlari lug'atlari, XXI asr boshlarida esa ingliz tilining izohli lug'atlari olindi. Misol qilib olinsa, "Smog" so'zi 1955 yilda lug'atda neologizm sifatida ro'yxatga olinganligi ko'rsatilgan "Dictionary of New Words" va 2005 yilda ham bir xil qiymatlarni saqlab qoldi ("polluted air that is a mixture of smoke and fog" – 1955 [Ibidem] va "polluted air that is a mixture of smoke and fog"-2005 asosan quyidagi ma'nolarni berishi tahliliy misollardan ko'rish mumkin. Huddi shu ta'rif: "a form of air pollution that is or looks like a mixture of smoke and fog, especially in cities" jumlasida ham berilgan. Xuddi shu kabi belgilangan neologizm sifatida 1955 yilda Meri Reyferning lug'atida VIP qisqartmasi misolida ham ko'rsatilgan.

So'z shakli, o'zaro bog'langan so'zlarning semantik tuzilishi va ularning nutqda ishlatilishi turli tillarda turlicha ekanligi tarjima jarayonida hisobga olinishi zarur. Masalan, Vebsterning Ingliz tili uchinchi xalqaro yangi lug'atida "eye" so'zining 20 ta o'zbek tilining izoqli lug'atida (2006), rus tili lug'atida (1981) esa "ko'z" so'zining muhim ma'nolari ko'rsatilgan.

Ingliz va o`zbek tillarida o`zaro bog`langan so`zlar turli xil yasama so`zlarni hosil qiladi: eyeglass, eye witness, eyeful, eyeless, to close ones eyes, up to ones eyes, in a pies eye, ko`z – ko`z qilmoq, ko`z olaytirmoq, ko`zi ochilmoq. Ko`rinib turibdiki, ikki tildagi muvofiq so`zlar ma'noviy, valentlik va qo`llanish ko`lamiga ko`ra o`xshash va farqli jihatlarga ega bo`lishi mumkin ekan.

XULOSA

Ma'lumki, leksik birliklar va frazeologik birliklar har bir tilning lug'at boyligini tashkil etuvchi til birligi sanaladi. Ular til birligi sifatida nutqgacha tayyor holatda bo'ladi. Shuningdek , har bir tilda leksik birliklar o'ziga xos lingvistik xususiyatga ega. Ammo barcha tillarda leksik hamda frazeologik birliklar til boyligi bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Polisemantik fraeologik birliklar tilning lug'aviy tarkibini va nutqni boyitishga xizmat qiladi va hissiy bo'yoqdorlik ma'nolarini mujassamlashtiradi. Shuning uchun biz tarjima qilayotgan vaqtimizda leksik hamda frazeologik terminlarni to'g'ri qo'llay bilishimiz kerak. Ana shundagina, leksikografiya hamda tarjimonlik sohasida katta yutuqlarga erishsak bo'ladi.

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“ZAMONAVIY TEXNIKALAR VA VOSITALARNING YOSHLARNI KASB-HUNARGA TAYYORLASHDA TUTGAN O’RNI VA AHAMIYATI”

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Anotatsiya: *hozirgi kunda texnologiyalarning yoshlarni bilim olishiga qilayotgan ta’siri, shuningdek, yoshlarni kasb-hunarga tayyorlashda texnologiyalarning tutgan o’rni haqida umumiy ma’lumotlar.*

Kalit so’zlar: *investitsiya, It texnologiyalar, konvensiya, konfrensiya, strategiya, algoritim, avtomatlashtirish, elektron kutubxona, internet, kompaniya, biznes, forum, shartnoma, Germaniya, Xitoy, Finlandiya, kompyuter va boshqalar.*

Bugungi kunda zamon kun sayin o’zgarib ketmoqda, biz esa u bilan ham nafas yashashimiz kerak. Shu bilan birgalikda yangiliklarni bilib borishimiz, yangi texnologiyalarni, yangi bilimlarni egallashimiz lozim.

Masalan, buni O’zbekiston Respublikasi talqinida ko’rsak, ya’ni, uni 1991- yildan 2024-yilgacha bo’lgan vaqt davomidagi o’zgarishlarini. Nega aynan tarix bilan bog’lashimizning asosiy sababi shundaki O’zbekiston Respublikasi birinchi Prezidenti Islom Abdug’animovich Karimov aytganlaridek: “ Tarixsiz – kelajak yo’q!”. Bilamizki, 1991-yil 31-avgustda biz o’z mustaqilligimizni qo’lga kiritdik va o’sha kundan boshlab O’zbekistonda o’zgarishlar boshlandi.

Mustaqillikka erishimiz bilan davlatimiz mustaqilligini yana ham mustahkamlash uchun o’z ramzlarimizga ega bo’lishimiz kerak edi shu sababdan o’sha yilning o’zida biz o’z bayrog’imizni qabul qildik, keyin 1992- yilda esa gerbimizni, konstitutsiyamizni, madhiyamizni qabul qildik. Asta sekinlik bilan dunyo jamiyatida o’z o’rnimizni o’rnata boshladik, ya’ni xalqaro shartnomalar imzoladik, deklaratsiyalarni qabul qildik, hamdo’stliklarga a’zo bo’ldik, tinchlik konstitutsiyasi deb nom olgan BMT ga a’zo bo’ldik va uning ustavlarini, nizomlarini qabul qildik shu bilanbirga, boshqa rivojlangan davlatlar bilan aloqa o’rnata boshladik.

Ular bilan shartnomalar tuzdik, albatta bu ishlarda davlatimiz rahbarining o’rni beqiyos. Birinchi Prezidentimiz o’z kitoblarida shunday deb yozganlar: “ Vatanimizning kelajagi, xalqimizning ertangi kuni, mamlakatimizning jahon hamjamiyatidagi obro’-e’tibori avvalambor farzandlarimizning unib-o’sib, ulg’ayib, qanday inson bo’lib hayotga kirib borishiga bog’liqdir.

Biz bunday o’tkir haqiqatni hech qachon unutmasligimiz kerak”¹. Bu so’zlarning tagida juda katta ma’no yotibdi, agar, unga e’tibor bersak yoshlarimizni davlatimiz rahbari birinchi o’ringa qo’yimoqda.

Chunki yoshlari ilimsiz mamlakat hech qachon yuksala olmaydi, zero, kelajak yoshlar qo’lida. Shu sababli yoshlarini sog’lom, ilimli va barkamol tarbiyalash uchun davlatimizda juda ko’plab islohotlar amalga oshirildi. Xususan bu kabi o’zgarishlar 2017- yilda jadallashib

ketdi, Prezidentimiz Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev ta'lim tizimida juda katta islohotlar amalga oshirdi.

Masalan, ta'lim tizimi 9 yillik ta'limdan 11 yillik ta'limga o'zgartirilib kollejlarni tugatilib ularning o'rniga kasb-hunar maktablari tashkillashtirildi. Keyin maktab darsliklarini ijara haqi davlat tomonidan qoplanib, o'quvchilar darslikdan mutlaqo bepul foydalana boshladi. Ilgari ingliz tili faqat 5-sinfdan o'rgatilardi, keyin bu ham o'zgartirildi ingliz tilini 1-sinfdan o'rgatilishi belgilandi.

Chunki butun dunyoda bu til yuqori o'rinda turardi, keyin yoshlar bu tilni mukammal o'rganganlaridan keyin horij mamlakatlarining bilim ko'nikmalari va zamonaviy texnologiyalarini o'rganishlari oson bo'lardi. Prezidentimiz tomonidan nafaqat yoshlar balki ularga ta'lim berayotgan fan o'qituvchilari ham ushbu tilni egallashi kerakligi e'tirof etildi. Nafaqat pedagogika sohasi balki barcha soha vakillari ingliz tilini o'rganishi kerak etib belgilandi. Agarda ingliz tilini mukammal o'rganib, til bo'yicha IELTS yoki CEFR(milliy sertifikat) olsa, ularga oyligiga qo'shib ellik foiz ustama qo'shib berilishi qonun bilan imzolandi.

Shuningdek, prezidentimiz mamlakatimizda gender tengligini mustahkamlash uchun, davlat boshqaruvida va boshqa sohalarda 33% ayollar ishlashi kerakligi belgilab qo'ydi, shuningdek, qizlarni ta'lim olishi uchun ularga magistratura bepul qilib qo'yildi, yana, ularga talaba kreditlarini foizsiz qilib berdi.

Bu o'zbek qizlari uchun katta ahamiyatga ega edi. Prezidentimiz tomonidan "Harakatlar strategiyasi" qabul qilindi, ushbu, strategiyada 5 ta ustuvor yo'nalish bo'lib ularni hammasi yoshlar bilan bog'liq.

Ushbu strategiya asosida juda ko'plab ishlar amalga oshirildi, shu bilan bir qatorda prezidentimiz AQSH, Fransiya, Germaniya, Xitoy va shunga o'xshash bir qancha rivojlangan mamlakatlar bilan texnologik, ilmiy sheriklik va hamkorlik aloqalarni o'rnatdik.

Germaniya va Xitoy mamlakatlaridan zamonaviy texnika vositalari olib kelindi va ular yordamida yoshlarni kasb-hunarga tayyorlash ishlari olib borilmoqda. Masalan, chevarlikka qiziquvchi qizlar uchun zamonaviy, ko'p funksiyaga ega tikuv mashinalari olib kelinib kasb-hunar maktablariga, shuningdek, "Yoshlar daftarida" va "Temir daftarda turuvchi" kamta'minlangan oiladagi ayol va qizlarga berildi. Bu texnikalar orqali ular yangi, qulay tikish usullarini o'rganish bilan, ish samaradorligini oshiradi, ya'ni vaqtni tejashga yordam beradi.

Shuningdek, yangi kompyuter texnologiyalari ham olib kelinib maktab va oliy ta'lim muassasalari jihozlanmoqda chunki hozirgi zamonda barcha narsalar kompyuterlashib ketmoqda. Asosan It texnologiyalari juda tez rivojlanib ketdi, u shunday texnologiyaki, unda dasturlar yaratiladi va shu dasturlar orqali juda foydali ishlar qilish mumkin.

Yana shuni ham aytib o'tish kerakki, hozirda internet orqali yoshlar ta'lim olishmoqda, misol uchun, o'zlari hohlagan kurslarga yozilib online o'rganmoqdalar.

Bu usul ancha qulay, sababi ayrim yoshlar bu singari kurslarga borish uchun shaharga borishi kerak bo'lardi. Endi buning keragi yo'q ular shunchaki uyda o'tirib biror bir til yoki hunarni o'rganishlari mumkin.

Davlatimiz rahbari shunday deydi: “ –Buyuk ajdodimiz Muhammad Xorazmiyning bir hikmati bor: “So’z-gul, ish-meva”. O’ylaymanki, bugun belgilab oladigan rejalaringiz qanchalik pishiq-puxta bo’lsa, ishingiz ham shunchalik yaxshi samara beradi, - dedi. –Sizlar ko’p kitob o’qigan, bilimli avlod sifatida yurtimiz o’tmishda jahon sivilizatsiyasi beshiklaridan bo’lganini yaxshi bilasiz. Siz Xorazmiy, Farg’oniy, Beruniy va Ibn Sino, Ulug’bek, Navoiy va Boburlar, Buxoriylar, Termiziylar avlodisiz.

Ana shunday buyuk vatandoshlarimiz yaratgan bebaho bilim va kashfiyotlar bugun ham butun insoniyatga xizmat qilmoqda.”². Bu bilan davlatimiz rahbarini shuni aytmoqchiki, bu hozirgi zamon texnologiyalarini yaratishga asos bizning ajdodlarimiz, ulug’ allomalarimiz tomonidan yaratilgan. Masalan, axborat texnologiyalarini olaylik ularni yaratishda biz ko’p bora algoritm kabi tushunchalarga uchraymiz, agar bilsangiz bu tushuncha ilk bor fanga bizning bobomiz bo’lmish Al-Xorazmiy tomonidan kashf qilinib, kiritilgan. Har bir sohada bizning allomalarimizning hissasi beqiyos hisoblanadi.

Xulosa qilib, aytadigan bo’lsak texnologiyalar bilan yangi bilimlarni egallash, dunyoni kashf qilish osonroq. Shu sababli biz ular bilan hamnafas yashab ularni mukammal o’rganishimiz kerak va buni yosh avlodga ham o’rgatishimiz kerak. Ularga texnologiya vostalaridan foydali maqsadlarda o’rganishlari uchun yordam bertishimiz kerak.

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**KIBERJINOYATCHILIK VA UNING OLDINI OLISH: 21-ASRDA AXBOROT
XAVFSIZLIGINING DOLZARB MUAMMOLARI**

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KIRISH

Axborot texnologiyalarining jadal rivojlanishi va raqamli kommunikatsiyalarning kengayishi bilan birga, kiberjinoiyatchilik ham jiddiy tahdidlarga aylangan. Kiberjinoiyatlar — bu kompyuter tizimlari, tarmoqlar va qurilmalar orqali sodir etiladigan jinoyatlar bo'lib, ular jamiyatning barcha jabhalariga ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Kiberjinoiyatchilik turlari va statistikasi

Kiberjinoiyatlar global darajada tobora ko'payib bormoqda. Ba'zi statistik ma'lumotlar kiberjinoiyatlarning tarqalishini va ularga qarshi kurashishda qanday muammolar borligini ko'rsatadi.

Kiberjinoiyatlarning o'sishi: 2023-yilga kelib, global kiberjinoiyatlarning qiymati taxminan 6 trillion dollar atrofida deb baholangan. Bu raqam 2025-yilda 10 trillion dollarga yetishi kutilmoqda.

Ransomware (Naqd pul talab qiluvchi dasturlar):

Kompyuter tizimlarini qulflash va undan foydalanishni tiklash uchun foydalanuvchidan pul talab qilish.

2022-yilda ransomware hujumlari taxminan 250 million dollar zararga olib keldi.

2023-yilda 50,000 dan ortiq kompaniyalar ransomware hujumlariga duch kelgan.

Phishing:(fishing) — bu kiberjinoiyatning eng keng tarqalgan va xavfli ko'rinishlaridan biridir. Phishing hujumlari odatda elektron pochta, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar yoki boshqa onlayn platformalar orqali amalga oshiriladi. Phishing hujumining maqsadi — foydalanuvchilarni aldatish va ularning shaxsiy ma'lumotlarini, moliyaviy hisob raqamlarini, parollarini yoki kredit kartalari raqamlarini o'g'irlashdir.

2023-yilda phishing hujumlari global kiberjinoiyatlarning 40% dan ortig'ini tashkil etdi.

Phishing xabarlari orqali o'g'irlangan mablag'lar bir yilda 10 milliard dollardan ortiqni tashkil etgan.

DDoS hujumlari:

Tizim yoki veb-saytga ko'plab trafik yuborish orqali uni ishlamay qolishiga olib kelish.

Bu usulda tizimni ishlatish imkoniyatini yo'qotish orqali kompaniyaga zarar yetkaziladi.

DDoS hujumlari har yili taxminan 10,000 dan ortiq ro'yhatga olinadi.

2023-yilda global DDoS hujumlarining miqdori 30% ga oshgan.

Malware:

Kompyuter tizimlariga zararli dasturlar (viruslar, trojanlar, adware va boshqalar) o'rnatish.

Bu dasturlar foydalanuvchining tizimiga kirib, ma'lumotlarni o'g'irlash yoki tizimni ishlamay qolishiga olib kelishi mumkin.

2022-yilda 350 milliondan ortiq yangi zararli dasturlar ro'yhatga olingan. Bu dasturlar orasida eng ko'p tarqalganlari — trojanlar va viruslar.

Identifikatsiya o'g'irliklari:

Kiberjinoyatchilar boshqalarning shaxsiy ma'lumotlarini o'g'irlab, ulardan noqonuniy ravishda foydalanadilar.

Misollar: kredit karta o'g'irligi, ijtimoiy ta'sir orqali identifikatsiyani o'g'irlash.

2023-yil boshida identifikatsiya o'g'irliklari va kredit karta fraudlari 1.7 milliondan ortiq holatni tashkil etdi.

Global miqyosda kiberjinoyatlarning ta'siri:

Xalqaro jinoiy tarmoqlar va kiberjinoyatchilar orqali yuzaga kelgan zararlarning ko'pi asosan rivojlangan mamlakatlar — AQSh, Yevropa, Yaponiya kabi hududlarda ro'y beradi.

Kiberjinoyatchilik turli shakllarda namoyon bo'ladi. Ularning asosiy turlariga quyidagilar kiradi:

- Kiberfiribgarlik: Internet orqali odamlarni aldash va moliyaviy zarar yetkazish.
- Zararli dasturlar tarqatish: Viruslar, trojanlar va boshqa zararli dasturlar yordamida tizimlarga kirish va ma'lumotlarni o'g'irlash.

- Xavfsizlik tizimlarini buzish: Parollarni tahdid qilish, tizim xavfsizligini zaiflashtirish orqali noqonuniy kirish.

- Denial-of-Service (DoS) hujumlari: Tizimlarni ishlamay qolishiga olib keladigan hujumlar.

- Soxta axborot tarqatish: Yolg'on yoki zararli ma'lumotlarni internet orqali yoyish.

Statistik ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, har kuni virtual makonda taxminan 2,328 ta kiberjinoyat sodir etiladi. 2001 yildan 2021 yilgacha bo'lgan davrda kamida 6.5 million kishi kiberjinoyatlar qurboni bo'lgan va shu davrda taxminan 26 milliard dollar zarar yetkazilgan. Shuningdek, rivojlangan davlatlarda virtual olamdagi jinoyatlar umumiy jinoyatchilikning 60-65 foizini tashkil etadi.

Kiberjinoyatchilikning oldini olish mexanizmlari

Kiberjinoyatchilikka qarshi kurashish va uning oldini olish uchun quyidagi chora-tadbirlar amalga oshirilmoqda:

1. Qonunchilikni takomillashtirish: Kiberjinoyatchilikka qarshi kurashish uchun maxsus qonunlar va me'yoriy hujjatlar ishlab chiqilmoqda. Masalan, O'zbekiston Respublikasida 2002-yil 12-dekabrda "Axborot erkinligi prinsiplari va kafolatlari to'g'risida"gi qonun qabul qilingan. Ushbu qonun jamiyatning axborot borasidagi xavfsizligini ta'minlashni nazarda tutadi. Bu qonunning asosiy maqsadini quyidagilar tashkil etadi:

Axborotga erkin kirish huquqini ta'minlash: Fuqarolar va jamiyat a'zolari davlat, xususiy sektor va boshqa tashkilotlar tomonidan saqlanayotgan ma'lumotlarga erkin kirish huquqiga ega bo'lishi kerak. Bu, o'z navbatida, jamiyatning yanada ochiq va shaffof bo'lishini ta'minlaydi.

Axborotning to'g'ri va shaffof tarqatilishini qo'llab-quvvatlash: Davlat organlari o'z faoliyatini fuqarolarga to'liq, o'z vaqtida va aniq ma'lumotlar bilan ta'minlashi kerak. Shu bilan birga, bu axborotlarning noto'g'ri tarqatilishi yoki yashirilishi oldini olish.

Axborot sohasida demokratik boshqaruvni ta'minlash: Fuqarolar davlat organlarining faoliyatini nazorat qilishi va qarorlarni shakllantirish jarayonida ishtirok etishi uchun axborot olish huquqini kengaytirish.

Axborot xavfsizligini ta'minlash: Shaxsiy va davlat axborotlarining himoya qilinishi, ayniqsa, maxfiy va xavfli ma'lumotlarning tarqatilishini oldini olish.

Axborot almashinuvi va kommunikatsiyalarni rag'batlantirish: Axborot texnologiyalarini rivojlantirish va shu orqali axborot almashinuvi jarayonlarini yaxshilash, bu esa iqtisodiy va ijtimoiy rivojlanishga yordam beradi.

2. Ta'lim va xabardorlikni oshirish: Aholi, ayniqsa yoshlar o'rtasida kiberxavfsizlik bo'yicha targ'ibot ishlari olib borilmoqda. Universitetlarda va boshqa ta'lim muassasalarida seminarlar va treninglar tashkil etilmoqda. Bu orqali jamiyatni kiberjinoyatchilik xavflari haqida xabardor qilish va himoya choralarini ko'rish muhim ahamiyatga ega.

3. Texnik himoya vositalarini joriy etish: Antivirus dasturlari, xavfsizlik devorlari va boshqa himoya vositalari orqali tizimlarni mustahkamlash. Shuningdek, ikki faktorli autentifikatsiya va shifrlash texnologiyalaridan foydalanish tavsiyalangan. Bu chora-tadbirlar tizimlarning xavfsizligini oshirishga yordam beradi.

4. Xalqaro hamkorlikni rivojlantirish: Kiberjinoyatchilik global muammo bo'lgani uchun, turli davlatlar o'rtasida axborot almashish va hamkorlikni yo'lga qo'yish muhim ahamiyatga ega. O'zbekistonda kiberjinoyatchilikning oldini olish tizimi yaratilmoqda va kiberxavfsizlik strategiyasi ishlab chiqilmoqda.

5. Ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy omillarni bartaraf etish: Atrof-muhit muammolari, ishsizlikning o'sishi, migratsiya va ijtimoiy beqarorlik kabi omillar kiberjinoyatchilikka olib kelishi mumkin. Ushbu omillarni bartaraf etish orqali kiberjinoyatchilik xavfini kamaytirish mumkin.

Kiberjinoyatchilikning asosiy turlari:

1. Ma'lumotlarni o'g'irlash va firibgarlik: Kiberjinoyatchilar odatda foydalanuvchilarning shaxsiy ma'lumotlarini o'g'irlyadi yoki ularni yolg'on ma'lumotlar bilan aldash orqali firibgarlik qiladi.

2. Kiberhujumlar: Masalan, DDoS (Distributed Denial of Service) hujumlari, zararli dasturlar (malware) va viruslar orqali tizimlarga zarar yetkazish.

3. Phishing va social engineering (ijtimoiy muhandislik): Kiberjinoyatchilar foydalanuvchilarni aldab, ularning shaxsiy ma'lumotlarini olish uchun turli manipulyatsiyalarni amalga oshiradi.

4. Ransomware (naqd pul talab qiluvchi dasturlar): Kompyuter tizimlarini qulflash va undan foydalanishni tiklash uchun foydalanuvchidan pul talab qilish.

Kiberjinoyatchilikka qarshi kurashishning asosiy yo'llari:

1. Yuqori darajadagi texnologik xavfsizlik: Yaxshi himoyalangan tizimlar va ma'lumotlar bazalari, shifrlash va autentifikatsiya metodlari orqali kiberjinoyatchilarga qarshi kurashish.
2. Axborot xavfsizligi siyosati va ta'lim: Foydalanuvchilarni kiberhujumlar va internet xavflari haqida xabardor qilish, ular uchun xavfsizlikni ta'minlash uchun ta'lim dasturlarini ishlab chiqish.
3. Jinoyatga qarshi qonunchilik: Kiberjinoyatlar bilan bog'liq qonunlarni mustahkamlash, mas'uliyatni oshirish va xalqaro hamkorlikni kuchaytirish.
4. Yangi xavf-xatarlar va tahdidlarni kuzatish: Texnologiyalar rivojlanishi bilan yangi kiberjinoyatlar va tahdidlar paydo bo'lishi mumkin. Bunday tahdidlarga qarshi doimiy ravishda yangilanish va oldini olish choralari ishlab chiqilishi kerak.
5. Yordamchi texnologiyalar: Kiberxavfsizlikni ta'minlash uchun sun'iy intellekt, mashina o'rganish va boshqa ilg'or texnologiyalarni qo'llash.

Kiberjinoyatchilik global muammo sifatida nafaqat texnologik, balki iqtisodiy va siyosiy jihatdan ham katta xavf tug'diradi. Shuning uchun bu muammoni hal qilishda hukumatlar, xususiy sektor, ilm-fan va jamiyat o'rtasida samarali hamkorlik zarur.

Xulosa

21-asrda kiberjinoyatchilikka qarshi kurashish jamiyatning barqaror rivojlanishi uchun zarurdir. Buning uchun qonunchilikni takomillashtirish, ta'lim va xabardorlikni oshirish, texnik himoya vositalarini joriy etish, xalqaro hamkorlikni rivojlantirish va ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy omillarni bartaraf etish muhim ahamiyatga ega. Kiberxavfsizlikni ta'minlash orqali jamiyatni raqamli tahdidlardan himoya qilish va barqaror rivojlanishni ta'minlash mumkin.

Kiberjinoyatchilik va uning oldini olish masalasi bugungi kunda axborot xavfsizligi sohasida eng dolzarb muammolardan biridir. 21-asrda texnologiyalar va internetning jadal rivojlanishi bilan kiberjinoyatlar soni va ularga qarshi kurashishning ahamiyati ortib bormoqda. Kiberjinoyatlar turli shakllarda sodir bo'lishi mumkin, jumladan, ma'lumotlarni o'g'irlash, firibgarlik, kiberhujumlar, identifikatsiyani o'g'irlash, va boshqa ko'plab jinoyatlar

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THE EFFECT OF AGE ON SECOND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION

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Annotation: *Age has long been considered a crucial factor in second language acquisition (SLA), influencing learners` ability to attain native-like proficiency. It is clear that younger learners, especially kids have a biological advantage in acquiring a second language, owing to their brain plasticity. However, adults may come across some difficulties in some aspects, like pronunciation when learning a target language. Certainly, both have advantages and disadvantages depending on their progress and attempt. This article explores the role of age in SLA by examining linguistic and cognitive factors that contribute to language learning success. Understanding these factors and gaining some useful information about them help educators and facilitate their work in designing age-appropriate language instruction that maximizes learning potential across different age groups.*

Key words: *second language, linguistic & cognitive factors, children, adults.*

INTRODUCTION

Language plays a fundamental role in human communication, shaping culture, identity, and social interactions. While most individuals acquire their first language (L1) naturally during early childhood, learning a second language (L2) is a more complex process influenced by cognitive, social, and environmental factors. Second language acquisition (SLA) refers to the process of learning a language beyond one's native tongue, whether through formal instruction, immersion, or self-study.

The ability to acquire a L2 varies significantly among individuals, and numerous linguistic and psychological theories attempt to explain why some learners achieve near-native proficiency while others struggle. One of the most debated topics in SLA is the Critical Period Hypothesis (CPH), which suggests that there is an optimal biological window for acquiring a second language, typically before puberty (Lenneberg, 1967).

According to CPH, younger learners have an advantage due to their greater neural plasticity, allowing them to develop native-like pronunciation and grammar more easily than older learners. Studies support this notion, highlighting that "grammar-learning ability is preserved almost to the crux of adulthood (17.4 years old) and then declines steadily" (Hartshorne, Tenenbaum, & Pinker, 2018, p. 722). This suggests that while younger learners may have an advantage in some linguistic domains, the decline in learning ability is gradual rather than abrupt. However, age is not the sole determinant of L2 acquisition success.

Cognitive abilities, motivation, and learning context play crucial roles in the process. Older learners often have stronger metacognitive skills, allowing them to apply explicit learning strategies and analytical reasoning in language acquisition (DeKeyser, 2000).

Moreover, studies indicate that motivation—whether instrumental (e.g., career advancement) or integrative (e.g., cultural immersion)—greatly impacts SLA outcomes.

Dörnyei (2009) emphasizes that “high motivation can compensate for cognitive or age-related disadvantages in second language learning” (p. 33). The learning environment also significantly influences SLA outcomes. Krashen’s Input Hypothesis (1982) suggests that comprehensible input—language exposure that is slightly above the learner’s current level—facilitates acquisition. According to Krashen, “acquisition occurs when learners receive messages they can understand, even if they do not grasp every detail” (p. 20).

Immersion-based learning environments, where learners are surrounded by the target language in daily life, tend to produce better fluency compared to classroom-based instruction alone. A study on Mandarin-speaking immigrants learning English found that the “age of learning effect was robust for both L2 grammar and speech production domains,” particularly impacting pronunciation (Flege, Yeni-Komshian, & Liu, 1999, p. 97). This supports the notion that while older learners can achieve grammatical accuracy, younger learners are more likely to attain native-like pronunciation.

Learning a second language at different ages is associated with both benefits and drawbacks.

This study aims to further investigate the relationship between age and SLA by examining learners across different age groups in terms of pronunciation, grammar acquisition, and overall language proficiency.

Linguistic factors.

1. Phonological acquisition & Pronunciation:

Younger learners, particularly those who are learning a second language before puberty, have a higher probability to have a native-like pronunciation, while adults can be in a difficulty to perceive and produce new L2 sounds accurately due to the fact that they tend to retain an accent from their first language (L1).

2. Morphosyntactic development:

It is obvious that children can easily learn grammar rules with just interaction, often without formal instruction, whereas adults rely more on explicit learning strategies such as rule memorization. Studies indicate that even though sometimes adults learn grammar more quickly, they often struggle with complex syntactic structures like word order variations or case marking and others.

3. Vocabulary learning:

Children, on the one hand, acquire vocabulary more gradually when compared to adults. But they can develop stronger usage-based associations, which contribute to native-like lexical development. However, on the other hand, adults have a cognitive advantage in vocabulary learning owing to their developed metalinguistic awareness that allows them to consciously learn language elements.

Cognitive factors

Cognitive factors play a crucial role in SLA. These factors include attention, memory, and motivation, which can influence the processing and storage of new linguistic information

1. Neuroplasticity :

Younger learners have higher brain plasticity, allowing for greater adaptability in acquiring L2. Nevertheless, adult learners oftentimes rely on cognitive control regions, leading to diverse learning pathways, which are less efficient for them to achieve native-like proficiency.

2. Memory:

Obviously, children rely heavily on implicit memory system that can help them learn L2 easily with just imitation, interaction and exposure without formal instructions. Adults, with explicit learning abilities, resort to use cognitive strategies-translation, rote memorization.

3. Interference from L1:

Adults prone to interfere their native language, as their cognitive system is already structured around it, whilst children, especially who are at the age of 7 or younger, exhibit greater cognitive flexibility with less interference from L1.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design. This study employed a cross-sectional design to investigate the impact of age of acquisition (AOA) on the degree of perceived foreign accent in English among Italian immigrants to Canada. By comparing participants who began learning English at various ages, the study aimed to identify critical periods during which AOA significantly affects accent perception.

Participants. The study involved 240 native Italian speakers who immigrated to Canada between the ages of 2 and 23. All participants had been residing in Canada for an average of 32 years at the time of testing. A control group of native English speakers was also included to provide baseline measurements for accent ratings.

Data Collection. Speech Samples: Participants were recorded reading a standardized English passage. These recordings served as the primary data for assessing foreign accent.

Accent Rating: Ten native English-speaking listeners, who were blind to the participants' backgrounds, rated the degree of foreign accent on a scale from 1 (no foreign accent) to 9 (heavy foreign accent).

Data Analysis. Statistical Analysis: Regression analyses were conducted to examine the relationship between AOA and foreign accent ratings. Variables such as length of residence in Canada, amount of native language use, and age at the time of testing were controlled to isolate the effect of AOA.

Group Comparisons: Participants were categorized into groups based on their AOA (e.g., 2-6 years, 7-11 years, etc.) to identify potential critical periods affecting accent acquisition. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) tests were conducted to compare mean accent ratings across these groups.

The analysis revealed a significant positive correlation between AOA and foreign accent ratings. Participants who began learning English before the age of 7 were often rated as having little to no foreign accent, whereas those who started after age 15 typically received higher accent ratings. The findings suggest a critical period for phonological acquisition, aligning with the Critical Period Hypothesis.

RESULTS. 1. Relationship Between Age of Acquisition (AOA) and Foreign Accent:

Statistical analysis revealed a strong positive correlation between AOA and perceived foreign accent. Participants who began learning English at an earlier age demonstrated significantly lower foreign accent ratings compared to those who started later.

- Children (AOA: 2-6 years): Nearly all participants in this group received ratings between 1 and 2, indicating minimal or no foreign accent.
- Adolescents (AOA: 7-11 years): Accent ratings ranged from 2 to 4, showing some noticeable non-native features but still relatively close to native pronunciation.
- Adults (AOA: 12+ years): The majority of participants received ratings between 5 and 9, reflecting a strong foreign accent.

2. Critical Period Effects in Phonological Acquisition

An Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) test indicated a significant difference in foreign accent ratings across age groups. Post-hoc comparisons showed that the AOA 2-6 group differed significantly from both the 7-11 and 12+ groups, confirming that earlier exposure to an L2 results in a greater likelihood of achieving native-like pronunciation.

- The strongest break in phonological acquisition was observed around age 12, aligning with the Critical Period Hypothesis (CPH).
- Participants who started learning English after puberty consistently exhibited stronger accents, suggesting that neuroplasticity plays a crucial role in L2 phonological development.

3. Effect of Length of Residence (LOR) in Canada

Despite all participants having lived in Canada for an average of 32 years, length of residence did not significantly reduce foreign accent in late learners. Regression analysis controlling for LOR confirmed that AOA was the strongest predictor of foreign accent ($\beta = 0.72, p < 0.001$), indicating that the time spent immersed in an L2 environment does not compensate for a late start in language learning.

4. Role of Continued L1 Use

Participants who maintained frequent use of their native Italian (e.g., speaking at home or in social settings) exhibited slightly stronger foreign accents than those who predominantly used English in daily life ($p < 0.05$). However, AOA remained the primary factor influencing accent strength, suggesting that early exposure to L2 is more important than L1 attrition in phonological acquisition.

DISCUSSION

1. Age as a Determinant of Second Language Phonology:

The findings strongly support the Critical Period Hypothesis (CPH), particularly in phonological learning. The clear threshold effect at puberty (around age 12) suggests that younger learners are more capable of acquiring native-like pronunciation due to greater brain plasticity, while adult learners rely more on cognitive strategies that do not lead to native-like phonology.

2. Adult Learners and Fossilization

The fact that adult learners consistently retained a strong accent—even after decades of exposure—indicates phonological fossilization, where incorrect pronunciations become

ingrained. This aligns with previous research suggesting that adults are more likely to rely on their L1 phonetic system, making it difficult to acquire new L2 phonemes accurately.

CONCLUSION. This study provides compelling evidence that age of acquisition plays a decisive role in second language phonological development. The results show that:

- Children who start learning before age 7 are most likely to achieve native-like pronunciation.
- Adolescents (7-11 years) show moderate non-native features but retain some phonological plasticity.
- Adults (12+ years) consistently exhibit foreign accents regardless of time spent in an L2 environment.

While other factors like length of residence and L1 usage influence accent strength, AOA remains the strongest predictor of phonological proficiency. These findings highlight the importance of early second language exposure and suggest that adults require different instructional approaches to overcome phonological barriers in SLA.

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AMIR TEMUR DAVRIDA MADANIY HAYOTNING SHAKLLANISHI. ME'MORCHILIK VA SHAHARSOZLIKDAGI O'ZGARISHLAR

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Abstract: *During the Timurid era, construction and architecture flourished at an unprecedented level. Cities such as Samarkand, Bukhara, Shahrisabz, and Herat witnessed grand architectural projects initiated by Amir Timur and his successors. Fortifications were erected around key cities, and monumental buildings such as the Ak-Saray Palace, Bibi-Khanym Mosque, and Shah-i-Zinda necropolis showcased the artistic and engineering prowess of the time. Historical sources, including Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi's "Zafarnama," describe the magnificence of these structures. The architectural legacy of the Timurids continues to be a symbol of cultural and historical richness.*

Keywords: *Amir Timur, Timurid architecture, Samarkand, Shahrisabz, defensive walls, Bibi-Khanym Mosque, AkSaray, Shah-i-Zinda, Herat, architectural heritage.*

Аннотация: *В эпоху Тимуридов строительство и архитектура достигли небывалого расцвета. Такие города, как Самарканд, Бухара, Шахрисабз и Герат, стали центрами грандиозных архитектурных проектов, инициированных Амиром Тимуром и его преемниками. Были возведены оборонительные стены, а монументальные сооружения, такие как дворец Ак-Сарай, мечеть Биби-Ханым и некрополь Шахи-Зинда, демонстрировали художественное и инженерное мастерство того времени. Исторические источники, в том числе «Зафарнаме» Шарафуддина Али Йазди, описывают величие этих построек. Архитектурное наследие Тимуридов по-прежнему остается символом культурного и исторического богатства.*

Ключевые слова: *Амир Тимур, архитектура тимуридов, Самарканд, Шахрисабз, оборонительные стены, мечеть Биби-Ханым, Ак-Сарай, Шахи-Зинда, Герат, архитектурное наследие.*

Annotatsiya: *Temuriylar davrida qurilish va me'morchilik misli ko'rilmagan darajada rivojlandi. Samarqand, Buxoro, Shahrisabz va Hirot kabi shaharlar Amir Temur va uning avlodlari tomonidan boshlangan ulkan me'moriy loyihalarga guvoh bo'ldi. Muhim shaharlar atrofida mudofaa devorlari qurildi, Oqsaroy, Bibixonim masjidi va Shohizinda kabi yodgorliklar esa o'sha davr me'morchiligining san'at va muhandislik qudratini namoyon etdi. Sharafiddin Ali Yazdiyning "Zafarnoma" asari bu inshootlarning buyukligini tasvirlaydi. Temuriylar me'moriy merosi bugungi kunda ham madaniy va tarixiy boylik ramzi bo'lib qolmoqda.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Amir Temur, Temuriylar me'morchiligi, Samarqand, Shahrisabz, mudofaa devorlari, Bibixonim masjidi, Oqsaroy, Shohizinda, Hirot, me'moriy meros.*

Temur va temuriylar davrida qurilish ishlari, me'morchilik misli ko'rilmagan darajada o'sadi va rivojlanadi. Temur va uning avlodlari davrida Samarqand, Toshkent, (Zangiota qabri), Buxoro Shahrisabz, Qarshi, Turkistonda, Xurosonning markazi Hirot, Mashhad, Nishopur, Kobul va boshqa shaharlarda buyuk yaratuvchilik ishlari olib boriladi. Sohibqironning buyrug'iga asosan 1365yilda Qarshi, 1370yilda Samarqand, 1380yilda Kesh shaharlari atrofida mudofaa devorlari barpo etiladi.

Temurning o'z ona yurti Keshda, buyuk alloma va mutafakkir Ahmad Yassaviyga atab Turkistonda qurdirgan ajoyib, osmono'par va muhtasham madrasalari o'z davrida Sohibqironning kuchqudratini jahon uzra ko'zko'z qilgan. Tarixshunos olim Sharafiddin Ali Yazdiy o'zining «Zafarnoma» asarida Kesh (Shahrisabz) qo'rg'oni va Oqsaroyning qurilishi bayonida quyidagilarni yozgan: «Sichqon yiliga to'g'ri kelgan (hijriy) 781yilning oxiri (milodiy mart, 1380), erta bahor fasli edi.

O'z quvvati bilan (tabiatni) gullatib yashnatuvchi me'mor ko'katlar va maysazorlar shahrini obod qilishga kirishgan, atirgul butalaridan qasrlar yaratib, la'lgun shohchalar uchini baland ko'targan va ularni firuza rang naqshli barglar bilan bezagan bir vaqtda oliyhazrat sohibqiron gullaridan mushku anbar bo'yi taraluvchi, suvidan gulob ta'mi keluvchi Keshning xushhavo va rom etguvchi zaminida shodlik nash'asini surib, orom olmoq azmi bilan bu yerda saltanat taxtini o'rnattirdi.

So'ng Shahrisabz qo'rg'onini qurish haqida farmon berdi va (ishlarni) amirlaru lashkar ahli o'rtasida taqsimladi. Qo'rg'on qurilishi uchun munosib keluvchi saodatli soatda uning poydevorini qurdilar. Shahar ichida esa qazoyu qadardek bajarilishi so'zsiz bo'lgan farmonga binoan bir qasr bunyodiga asos soldilar. Imorat shu qadar baland va favqulodda jozibali ediki, hatto kekxa muhandis bo'lmish Gardun shuncha yillar jahon atrofida aylangan bo'lishiga qaramay, bunday go'zal binoni ko'rmagan edi.

1404yilda Amir Temurning onasi Nekuzbibi sharafiga qurib bitkazilgan, go'zallikda tengsiz Oqsaroy ispan elchisi Ryui Gonzales de Klavixo 1403yili bu yerdan Samarqand tomon o'tayotganda hali bitmagan edi. Ammo shunga qaramasdan u o'z xotiralarida Oqsaroyning go'zalligidan hayratlanganligi va qoyil qolganligini yozadi: «Zero, butun bino zarhal va lojuvard bilan qoplangan bo'lib, u yerda saroyning shuncha bo'lma va oromgohlarini ko'rsatdilarki, ular haqida juda uzoq so'zlash mumkin.

Saroy ziynatlari oltindan va boshqa ranglardan hayratomuz ishlangan edi. Hatto mohir ustalari bilan jahonga mashhur bo'lgan Parijda ham bu ish juda go'zal hisoblangan bo'lar edi». Amir Temur tomonidan qurilgan ushbu saroyning eng noyob, o'ziga xos xususiyatlaridan yana biri shunda ediki, saroy tomi tepasida hovuz bo'lib, unga suv taxtaqaracha dovonidan — tog'dan qo'rg'oshin quvurlar orqali olib kelingan⁵.

Albatta, Amir Temur birinchi navbatda poytaxti Samarqandni dunyoning eng go'zal va obod, ko'rkam va betimsol shaharlaridan biriga aylantirishni o'zining bosh vazifasi deb biladi. U ishni, eng avvalo, mo'g'ullar istilosidan so'ng 150 yil mobaynida vayron va qarovsiz yotgan shaharning mudofaa devorlarini tiklashdan boshlaydi. Osma suv yo'li («Juyi

⁵ Qulmatov Sh. Berdimuhammedov A. Samarqand yodigorliklari. –T.: Imom Buxoriy xalqaro markazi, 2017. –B.39-41

Arziz»)ning yakson etilishi tufayli suvsiz qolgan Samarqand mahallalariga Zarafshon daryosidan suv keltiradi. Amir Temur o'z saltanatining qo'rg'oni — Ark qal'a, undagi betakror va go'zal binolarni qurdiradi. Ko'ksaroy va Bo'stonsaroy deb elda mashhur bo'lgan bu binolar shaharning ko'rki hisoblangan.⁶

Shahar arki ichida bu binolardan tashqari masjid, ulkan kutubxona, shohona uyjoylar, Amir Temurning xazinasi va taxti, pul zarblanadigan ko'ra, aslahasozlik ustaxonalari, hammomlar hamda zindon bo'lib, atrofi qalin va baland devorlar bilan o'ralgan. Sohibqiron Hindiston safaridan qaytgach, uning farmoni bilan jome masjidi (Bibixonim nomi bilan ataluvchi masjid)ning qurilishi boshlanadi. Jome masjidi qurilishiga Temurning shaxsan o'zi qiziqqan va jangu jadallar bilan band bo'lsada, uni e'tibordan qochirmagan. Jome masjidi belgilangan muddatda bitkaziladi. Biroq Sohibqiron bu paytda safarda edi⁷.

Ayni paytda Temurning sevimli, erka va katta xotini Saroymulkxonim (Bibixonim) bunyod etilgan jome masjidi yonida jozibali va ulug'vor, muhtasham madrasa qurilishini boshlab yuborgan edi. Ibn Arabshohning guvohlik berishicha, quruvchilar madrasa darvozasi va devorlarini jome masjidiga nisbatan baland ko'taradilar. Natijada madrasa asosi jome masjidi asosidan mustahkam, balandlikda ham undan ko'ra yuqori bo'ladi. 1404-yilning kuzida Temur harbiy safardan qaytgach, madrasa va jome masjidini tomosha qilar ekan, uning nazarida masjidning peshtoqi madrasaga nisbatan tor va past ko'rinadi. U g'azabga to'ladi va jome masjidi bosh peshtoqini buzib tashlab boshqatdan qurishga farmon beradi. Shu dargohning kengaytirib va baland ko'tarib qurish ishida qusurga yo'l qo'yganligi uchun Xo'ja Mahmud Dovud so'roqqa tortilib jazolanadi. Jome masjidi kengaytiriladi va peshtoqi baland ko'tariladi.

Qayta ta'mirlash ishlarini Amir Temurning shaxsan o'zi nazorat ostiga oladi. Jome masjidi Samarqanddagi eng hashamatli va go'zal obidalardandir. U boshqa binolardan o'ymakor marmardan yasalgan 480 pillapoya ustunlari, darvozaband ulkan ravoqi, masjid binosining bahaybat gumbazi, peshtoqining mahobati va quyosh nurida turli rang ko'rinishda tovlanib turuvchi maftunkor, jimjimador, go'zal bezaklari bilan o'zgacha bir tarzda ajralib turardi. Amir Temur mashhur Shohizinda qabristonini ham o'zining o'tkir zehni va ziyrak e'tiboridan chetda qoldirmaydi («Shohizinda» — «tirik shoh» ma'nosini beradi). Undagi maqbaralarning eng qadiymiysi — Qusam ibn Abbas maqbarasidir. Qusam ibn Abbas islom dinining asoschisi, payg'ambarimiz Muhammad alayhivassalomning amakivachchasi bo'lgan Abbasning zurriyoti edi.

Qusam ibn Abbas islomni targ'ib va tashviq qilishda ishtirok etgan buyuk shaxslardan bolgan. U shu maqsadda 676yilda arab istilochilari bilan birgalikda Samarqandga kelgan. Shu yerda, afsonalarda aytilishicha, namoz o'qib turgan paytlarida kofirlar hujum qilib uni o'ldirgan ekanlar. Amir Temur Qusam ibn Abbas qabri ustiga yangi dahma o'rnatgan. Bu dahma O'rta Osiyo qadimgi kulollari ishlarining eng yaxshi namunalaridan biridir. Chingizxon qo'shinlari tomonidan batamom kuli ko'kka sovurilib, vayronaga aylantirilgan Afrosiyob Temur va temuriylar davriga kelibgina haqiqiy ikkinchi hayotga yuz o'giradi.

⁶ Shamsutdinov R. Karimov Sh. "Vatan tarixi" birinchi kitob. -T.: "Sharq", 2010. -B.427

⁷ Vaxitov M. Mirzayev Sh. Me'morchilik. T.: "Tafakkur"- 2010. B.113

Amir Temurdan soʻng uning isteʼdodli va maʼrifatparvar nabirasi Ulugʻbek davrida Samarqand oʻz boshidan gullash davrini kechiradi.

Ajoyib va muhtasham binolar qad koʻtaradi. Afrosiyob atroflari husniga husn qoʻshadi. Bibixonim masjidi hovlisining oʻrtasida marmartoshdan yasalgan lavh bor (Lavh — Qurʼon qiroat qilinadigan maxsus kursi). Ushbu lavhni Mirzo Ulugʻbek XV asrning oʻrtalarida yasattirgan. Unda quyidagi soʻzlar bitilgan: «Sultoni azizim, oliy himmatli xoqon, diniyot homiysi, xanafiya mazhabining posboni, aslzoda sulton, ibn sulton amiri muhin Ulugʻbek Guragʻon». Ulugʻbek ogʻli Abdulazizga atab 1434–1435(hijriy 838) yillari Shohizinda ansamblining asosiy bosh darvozasini qurdirgan. Unga quyidagi soʻzlar bitilgan: «Abdulaziz Bahodir ibn Ulugbek ibn Shohruh, ibn Temur». Shohizinda ansamblida Temur va temuriylar qurdirgan maqbaralarning soni 20 dan oshadi.

Amir Temurning hayotligi chogʻida qurilgan maqbaralardan biri — Turkon ogʻa maqbarasidir. Turkon ogʻa Amir Temurning opasi boʻlgan. Maqbara esa 1370–1371yillarda vafot etgan Turkon ogʻaning qizi uchun qurilgan. 1383yilda Turkon ogʻaning oʻzi ham vafot etadi va shu yerga dafn etiladi. Bu obidaning ustalari samarqandlik Shamsiddin va Badriddin hamda buxorolik Zayniddin va Shamsiddinlar boʻlganlar. 1376yilda Amir Temurning sarkardalaridan biri — amir Husaynning onasi Togʻli Tekin, 1385yilda Amir Temurning singlisi Shirinbeka ogʻa maqbaralari qurilgan. Shohizinda ansamblida Amir Temurning xotinlari tomonidan qurilgan maqbaralar va boshqa binolar ham kattagina oʻrinni egallaydi.

Amir Temur davrida qurilgan va dovrugʻi olamni tutgan tarixiy obidalardan yana biri bu — Goʻri Amir maqbarasidir. Bu muhtasham binoning oʻz qurilish tarixi bor. Amir Temur nabirasi Muhammad Sultonni (Jahongirning ogʻli) juda sevardi. Muhammad Sulton 1403-yilda, 27 yoshida shamollab vafot etadi. Uni Samarqandga olib kelib dafn marosimi oʻtkazadilar. Amir Temur 1404yilning kuzida safardan qaytgach, nabirasi Muhammad Sulton xotirasi uchun maqbara qurishga farmon beradi. Ushbu farmonda maqbarani oʻn kun mobaynida qurib tugallashga buyruq berilgandi. Haqiqatan ham maqbara oʻn kunda batamom qurib bitkaziladi. Bunday hashamatli, katta va baland binoni oʻn kunda qurib bitkazish aqlga sigʻmaydigan bir voqea boʻlib, Amir Temurning kuchqudrati nimalarga qodir ekanligini namoyish etgan⁸.

Amir Temur mana shu yerda Muhammad Sulton Mirzo xotirasiga va Alloh yoʻliga atab katta xudoyi marosimini oʻtkazadi hamda oʻsha davr mashhur din peshvolari tomonidan Qurʼoni Karimdan oyatlar oʻqittiradi. Maqbara devorlaridagi rangbarang koshinlar orasida uni qurgan usta Muhammad ibn Mahmud Isfaxoniyning nomi ham yozilgan. 1405yilda Amir Temur vafot etgach, uning oʻzi ham shu yerga, nevarasining yoniga dafn etiladi va maqbara Goʻri Amir maqbarasi deb nom oladi.⁹ Shundan soʻng ushbu obida temuriylar sulolasining xilxonasiga aylanadi.

⁸ Qulmatov Sh. Berdimuhammedov A. Samarqand yodgorliklari. –T.: Imom Buxoriy xalqaro markazi, 2017. –B.36

⁹ <https://e-tarix.uz/obidalar/649-maqola.html>

Unda Muhammad Sulton Mirzo, Amir Temurdan tashqari Sohibqironning o'g'illari Umarshayh, Shohruh va Mironshoh, nabirasi Mirzo Ulug'bek va Temurning piri Sayyid Barakaning ham sag'analari qo'yilgan. Diqqatga sazovor joyi shundaki, Amir Temurdek inson o'z qabrini ustozlari Sayyid Barakaning oyog'i uchlariga qo'yishni vasiyat qilgan ekan. Vasiyat bajo etilgan.

Maqbaraning ichi juda baland. U bezaklarining jilosi bilan har qanday kishini hayratlantiradi. Maqbaraning o'rtasida o'rnatilgan sag'ana toshlarida temuriylarga bag'ishlangan yozuvlar bor. Shular orasida Amir Temur qabri ustiga qo'yilgan to'q yashil rangli mohtobdan yasalgan qabrtosh diqqatga sazovordir.

1425yilda Ulug'bek Qarshi (Nahshob) shahrini mo'g'ullardan tozalagach, shahardagi mo'g'ul xoni saroyidan ana shu to'q yashil mohtobni Samarqandga olib kelib, bobosi Sohibqiron sag'anasi ustiga qo'ydiradi. Bu toshda yozilgan juda ko'p, uzundanuzoq 51 satrli jumlar qatorida quyidagilarni o'qiydiz: «Bu toshni audanlik xoqon Dava Suhonxon Qarshi deb ataladigan poytaxtiga ko'chirib olib ketgan. Jetaga otlanganida Qarshidan Ulug'bek ko'ragon (bu yerga) ko'chirtirib olib keldi.

U nihoyatda mohirdir...» Amir Temurning moddiy merosi uzoq yillar davomida talontaroj qilindi, xo'rlandi va toptaldi. Xususan, chor Rossiyasining mustamlakachilik zulmi va «qizil, saltanat» hukmronligi davrida ulug' Sohibqiron tomonidan yaratilgan boyliklar turli yo'llar bilan yurtimizdan olib chiqib ketildi. Ularning ko'plari Rossiyaning Davlat Ermitaj muzeyida saqlanmoqda, kattagina qismi esa boshqa davlatlarga oltinlar hisobiga sotib yuborilgan.

Taqdir taqozosi bilan Amir Temur qabri ikki marotaba bezovta qilingan. Qarangki, go'yo ikki marta ham Amir Temur ruhlari o'z dushmanlaridan ayovsiz o'ch olgan. Birinchisi 1736yilda sodir bo'ladi. Eron taxtiga chiqqan Nodirshoh Amir Temur sag'anasiga qo'yilgan mohtob qabrtoshni Mashhadga olib kelgan va evaziga ko'p o'tmay o'z nabirasi shahanshoh Aliqul Mirzo tomonidan o'ldirilgan. Ikkinchisi «qizil saltanat» davrida, 1941yil 22iyun soat 5.00 da boshlanadi.

Huddi o'sha yil, o'sha kun va o'sha soatda fashistlar Germaniyasi sobiq SSSRga urush e'lon qiladi. Har ikki holatda ham biz buni tan olamizmiyo'qmi, xohlaymizmi yo'qmi, go'yo allohi Karim xuddi buyuk Temur uchun uning qabrini bezovta qilganlardan qonuniy o'ch olganday tuyuladi kishiga.

Go'ri Amir ansamblining ko'rki va faxri uning maqbaralaridagi gumbazlardir. Gumbazdagi rangdor naqshlar yorqinligi va serjiloligi bilan har qanday kishini hayratga soladi. Xullas, bu go'zal va betakror maqbara Amir Temur xotirasigagina yodgorlik bo'lmasdan, balki nomsiz me'morlar, mohir rassomlar, xalq ijodi qudratining timsoli naqqoshlar sharafiga ham o'rnatilgan abadiy haykaldir. Amir Temur Samarqanni dunyoning eng ko'rkam va go'zal shaharlaridan biriga Yer yuzining «sayqali»ga aylantirishni o'zining vazifasi deb biladi.

Samarqand Temurning kuch va qudratini jahonga ko'zko'z qilib ko'rsatishi kerak edi. Ko'rkam va go'zal Samarqand oldida dunyoning boshqa davlatlari poytaxtlari bamisoli kichikkichik qishloqlarga o'xshab ko'rimsiz bo'lib turishi lozim, deb hisoblardi Sohibqiron.

Ulug' bobomiz ana shu mantiq asosida Samarqand atrofida bir qancha manzilgohlar paydo qilib, ularga jahondagi yirik davlatlarning poytaxtlari nomlarini beradi: Bag'dod, Damashq, Qohira, Sheroz, Sultoniya, Parij va hokazo. Parij keyinchalik xalq talaffuzida Forish deb yuritiladigan bo'ldi. Amir Temur davrida Samarqandning dovrug'i doston bo'ladi. Uning to'rt tomonida to'rtta darvozasi bo'lgan. Shahar atrofi qazilgan xandaqlarda oqib turadigan zilol suvlar bilan o'ralgan edi¹⁰.

Shaharning toza va ozodaligi juda ko'p manbalarda madh etilgan. Jumladan, tarixchi AlG'azzoliyning yozishicha: «Muhtasiblar ko'chaga tarvuzqovun po'choqlarini hamda boshqa chiqindilarni tashlab, yo'lovchilar uchun sirg'anish xavfini tug'dirmasligini, oqava suvlar sachrab odamlarning kiyimlarini iflos qilmasligini, qassoblar ko'chalarda yoki do'konlarning oldida mol so'yib atrofni ifloslantirmasliklarini, har kim o'z tomonidan kuragan qorni o'zi tozalashini va boshqa obodonchilik ishlarini qattiq nazorat qilganlar» 1.22 gektarni egallagan birgina Afrosiyobning o'zida Amir Temur hukmronligi davrida 80 ga yaqin hammom, qulay va gavjum 5 ta bozor bo'lgan. Tarixchi sayyoh Ibn Xaldunning hikoya qilishicha, Samarqandda «oqar suv kirmagan biror ko'cha, biror hovli deyarli yo'q edi, faqat ba'zi uylargina bog'siz edi».¹¹

Odamlar ko'chalarda ariqlarda oqib o'tadigan toza zilol suvlardan ichimlik suvi o'rnida foydalanganlar. Amir Temur poytaxti Samarqand atrofini bog'irog'lar bilan o'rab olgan. Sohibqironning buyrug'i bilan bir-biridan go'zal o'ndan ortiq bog'barpo etilgan. Bog'i naqshi jahon, bog'i behisht, Amirzoda Shohruh bog'i, Bog'i bo'ldu, Bog'i dilkusho, Bog'i zofoh, Bog'i baland, Davlatobod, Bog'i chinor, Bog'i nav, Bog'i jahonnamo shular jumlasidandir. Tarixchi Ibn Arabshoh Amir Temur bog'lari to'g'risida bunday deb yozadi: «Temur Samarqandda ko'pdanko'p bo'stonlar barpo qilib, baland va mustahkam qasrlar bunyod etdi.

Ularning har qaysisi g'arobatli tartibda, ko'rkam va ajib suratda edi. Bo'stonlar asosini mustahkam qilib, fahomatli mevali ko'chatlar bilan ularni bezadi. Ularning birini Eram bog'i, ikkinchisini Dunyo ziynati, yana boshqasini Firdavs jannati, uchinchisini Shimol bog'i, beshinchisini Oliy jannat deb atadi.

Shuningdek, ba'zi joylarni buzdirib, u bo'stonlardan har biri ichida bir qasr qurdirdi. Bu qasrlarning qay biriga o'z majlislarini, o'z suratini turli shakllarda: birida kulib turgan, ikkinchisida qahrlangan, o'zi qilgan janglar tasvirlarini, rasmiy tantanadagi suratlarini; podshohlar, amirlar, sayyidlar, ulsholar va ulug'lar bilan suhbat qurgan majlislarini; sultonlarning uning huzurida qo'l qovushtirib turishlarini, xizmat yuzasidan boshqa mamlakatlardan huzuriga kelgan ularning podshohi sultonlarining vakillarini, o'zining ov xalqalariyu yashirin hiylalarini, Hind, Dashti (Qipchoq) va Ajam janglarida o'z zafarlari suratini, dushmanlarining qay ahvolda yengilib qochganini, o'z avlodlari, nabiralari, amirlari, qo'shinlari suratlarini; ayshu ishrat majlislari va sharoblari qadahlariyu qadahlari soqiylarini, o'z ulfati qo'shiqchilarining, turli maqomdagi g'azalxonlik kuychilarining, huzuridagi sevgililariyu (nikohidagi) pok xonimlarning va bulardan boshqa uning birbiriga

¹⁰ Shamsutdinov R. Karimov Sh. "Vatan tarixi" birinchi kitob. –T.: "Sharq", 2010. –B.427

¹¹ Berdimuhammedov A. Amir Temutning Samarqanddagi bog' lari. Turkiston, 1992-yil. B: 123-124.

o'xshab, ulanib ketgan, uning butun umri mobaynida o'zga mamlakatlarda voqea bo'lgan hodisalar suratini tasvirlatdi.

Bular hammasi hech bir noqissiz va ziyodasiz, qay tarzda yuz bergan bo'lsa, shundayligicha aks ettirildi. Bundan maqsadi o'zining ishlaridan g'oyibona xabardor bo'lib, ularning o'z ko'zi bilan mushohada etmaganlarga yaqqol namoyon qilib ko'rsatish edi».¹² Amir Temur yaratgan bog'lar go'zalligini ulardagi turlituman mevalarni va Yer yuzida mavjud bo'lgan hayvonot dunyosini, parrandalar tafsilotini tarifga olish uchun qalam ojizlik qiladi. A.Berdimurodovning «Amir Temurning Samarqanddagi bog'lari», turkum maqolalarida «Dilkusho bog'i» to'g'risida quyidagi satrlarni o'qiymiz: «Temur hijriy 788yil (1397)ning kuzida xushmanzara Konigil vohasida yangi bog' barpo etishga buyruq berdikim, u o'zining go'zalligi bilan mamlakatdagi barcha bog'lardan ajralib tursin.

Samarqandda yashovchi O'rta Osiyoning eng mohir me'morlari tomonlari bir yarim ming gaz keladigan bog'ning asosiy gishtini qo'ydilar. Kirish yo'llarini ajratdilar. Saroyning gumbazlari naqshlar bilan bezaldi, devorlar ustki koshinlar bilan qoplandi. Bog'ning to'rt burchagida katta san'at va yuksak did bilan ishlangan, ajoyib bo'yoqlar berilgan shiyponlar qurildi. Bog' chorqirra xiyobonlarga va turli shakldagi bog'chalarga bo'lindi. Temur xiyobonlarning yo'llari chetiga mevali daraxtlar, ba'zilariga gul o'tkazishni xohlardi. Bog' uning (Temurning) mayliga javob bergani uchun ham «Bog'i dilkusho» deb ataldi. Bog'ning o'rtasida baland gumbazli uch oshyonli saroy qurildi. 1404yilning sentabrida jahongir Temurning qabulida ispaniyalik elchi Klavixo bu bog'da favvoradan suv otilib turganligini, boqqa kiriladigan darvoza juda keng, yuksak oltin va boshqa qimmatbaho toshlar bilan bezatilganligini, ustiga taxtiravon o'rnatilgan oltita fil borligini yozadi».

Amir Temurning muholiflari uni kamsitishga urinib, Temur bosib olgan mamlakatlardan ustalar, me'morlar va olimlarni ko'chirib olib kelmaganda Samarqandda va boshqa shaharlarda bu darajada hashamatli, go'zal qurilish va binolar bo'lmas edi, deb isbotlashga behuda urinadilar. Biz ulug' bobomiz Amir Temurning o'z yurishlari davrida minglab ustalar, me'morlar, qurilish ashyolari va boyliklarni Samarqandga olib kelganligini inkor etmaymiz. Jumladan, Samarqand, Shahrisabz va boshqa shaharlardagi qurilish va me'morchilik ishlarida Sheroz, Tabriz, Isfaxon, Xorazmdan kelgan ko'plab me'morlar, musavvirlar va hunarmandlar ishlaganlar. Lekin asosiy ish boshqaruvchilar, mahalliy ustalar va me'morlar bo'lganlar, birinchi galda ularning milliy an'ana san'at ijodlari yetakchi o'rinni egallagan. Darvoqe, Samarqand, Buxoro va Xorazmda hali Temur hukmronligigacha qurilgan va mavjud bo'lgan va shu kunlargacha ham saqlanib kelayotgan tarixiy obidalar, o'lkamizda olib borilgan arxeologik qazilma yodgorliklarining guvohlik berishicha, xalqimiz qadimqadimdan qurilish va me'morchilik san'atida xayratomuz va noyob qobiliyat egalari o'lkasi bo'lganligini ko'ramiz.

Xulosa qilib aytganda, Amir Temur va temuriylar davrida me'morchilik va qurilish ishlari misli ko'rilmagan darajada rivojlandi. Sohirqiron Temur nafaqat harbiy yurishlari bilan, balki ulkan bunyodkorlik faoliyati bilan ham tarixda o'chmas iz qoldirdi. Uning

¹² Ibn Arabshoh. Amir Temur Tarixi. 2-kitob. T: Sharq, 2007. B: 82.

buyurtmasi bilan Samarqand, Shahrisabz, Buxoro, Toshkent, Hirot kabi yirik shaharlarda beqiyos me'moriy obidalar barpo etildi. Oqsaroy, Bibixonim masjidi, Shohizinda majmuasi, Ark qal'asi kabi inshootlar faqat o'sha davrning emas, balki bugungi kunda ham jahon me'morchiligining durdonalari sifatida e'tirof etiladi.

Bu obidalar nafaqat Temur saltanatining qudratini, balki o'sha davr madaniyati va san'atining yuksak darajada ekanligini ham namoyon etadi.

Amir Temur bunyod etgan inshootlar asrlar osha o'zining mahobati va nafosatini saqlab qolgan bo'lib, hozirda ham olimlar va sayyohlarning e'tiborini tortib kelmoqda.

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HOW YOUR BRAIN SPEAKS: AN EXPLORATION OF PSYCHOLINGUISTICS

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Abstract: *This article provides an overview of psycholinguistics, the interdisciplinary field exploring the cognitive mechanisms of human language. We examine key areas of research, including the acquisition of first and second languages, the mental processes involved in lexical retrieval and sentence comprehension, and the neurological underpinnings of language. The impact of brain damage and language disorders such as dyslexia is also discussed.*

Key words: *psychology, linguistics, Dyslexia, Aphasia, Agraphia, Strokes, Alexia*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada inson tilining kognitiv mexanizmlarini o'rganuvchi fanlararo soha bo'lgan psixolingvistikaning umumiy ko'rinishi berilgan. Biz tadqiqotning asosiy yo'nalishlarini, jumladan, birinchi va ikkinchi tillarni o'zlashtirish, leksik izlash va jumalarni tushunish bilan bog'liq aqliy jarayonlarni va tilning nevrologik asoslarini ko'rib chiqamiz. Miya shikastlanishi va disleksiya kabi til kasalliklarining ta'siri ham muhokama qilinadi. Eksperimental tadqiqotlar va lingvistik tahlillar orqali psixolingvistika miya oddiy so'zlardan tortib murakkab nutqqa qadar samarali muloqot qilishimizga qanday yordam berishi yoritiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *psixologiya, tilshunoslik, disleksiya, afazi, agrafiya, insult, aleksiya*

Аннотация: *В этой статье представлен обзор психолингвистики, междисциплинарной области, изучающей когнитивные механизмы человеческого языка. Мы рассматриваем ключевые области исследований, включая освоение первого и второго языков, психические процессы, вовлеченные в лексический поиск и понимание предложений, а также неврологические основы языка. Также обсуждается влияние повреждений мозга и языковых расстройств, таких как дислексия.*

Ключевые слова: *психология, лингвистика, дислексия, афазия, аграфия, инсульты, алексия*

INTRODUCTION

Psycholinguistics is a field that combines psychology and linguistics to understand how humans acquire, process, and use language, exploring the cognitive and mental processes involved in language. Psycholinguistics studies how our brains handle language. It's like detective work, figuring out how we learn, understand, and use words and sentences. Researchers use experiments and linguistic knowledge to explore these mental processes.

They look at things like:

- Learning a language: How kids learn their first language and adults learn new ones.
- Remembering words: How our brains store and find words when we speak or read.

- Understanding sentences: How we figure out what sentences mean, especially tricky ones.
- The brain and language: Which parts of the brain are active when we use language, and what happens when those parts are damaged.
- Language problems: How problems like dyslexia or strokes affect how people use language.

Learning a language is a fascinating process, and it differs significantly between children acquiring their first language (L1) and adults learning a second language (L2).

First Language Acquisition (Children):

Children learn their native language effortlessly, seemingly without formal instruction. They absorb language through immersion, picking up sounds, words, and grammatical structures through listening and interacting with their caregivers and environment. This process is largely unconscious and intuitive. Key aspects include:

- Early stages: Infants begin by recognizing and distinguishing sounds, babbling, and gradually producing meaningful words.
- Rapid vocabulary growth: Vocabulary acquisition accelerates dramatically between the ages of 18 months and 6 years.
- Grammar development: Grammatical rules are learned implicitly, often through pattern recognition and correction from caregivers

Second Language Acquisition (Adults):

Adults learning a new language often utilize more conscious and explicit strategies. While they may still benefit from immersion, they are often more reliant on formal instruction, textbooks, and structured learning environments. Key differences include:

- Existing linguistic knowledge: Their existing L1 can both help (by providing transferable knowledge) and hinder (through interference and habit).
- Cognitive strategies: Adults may employ cognitive strategies such as memorization techniques and explicit grammatical rules.
- Learning styles: Adult learners have diverse learning styles and preferences, which affect their approach to language learning.

Our brain is like a giant dictionary, but it's not organized like a regular one. The meaning of a word "dog" (means a furry animal), how it looks, and how it sounds are all stored in different parts of your brain. When you want to say "dog," your brain searches this dictionary. It might consider other words that are similar (like "cat") before settling on the right one.

What you're thinking about and what's around you (the context) helps your brain choose the right word. Words you use often are easier to find. Sometimes, you might know the word is there, but you just can't find it—that's the "tip of the tongue" feeling. Different parts of your brain work together to do this. It's a really complicated process, but it usually happens so fast you don't even notice!

Understanding sentences isn't just about knowing individual words. It's about piecing them together to understand the whole meaning. This involves several steps: first, breaking the sentence down grammatically (parsing) to see how the words relate. Then,

understanding each word's meaning: analyzing the sentence structure to resolve any ambiguity, combining all this information to create a coherent meaning. And finally, using our world knowledge and context to understand any implied meanings. Difficult sentences might be unclear because they have multiple possible meanings, complex grammar, idioms, or unstated information.

Our brains handle these challenges by using all these steps, along with our existing knowledge, to understand even the most complicated sentences. This shows how remarkably good our brains are at understanding language. More simply :It is like solving a puzzle. Your brain first identifies the parts of speech and their relationships (subject, verb, object), then retrieves the meaning of each word. Finally, it combines these to understand the whole sentence. Difficult sentences, with multiple meanings or complex grammar, require your brain to use its existing knowledge to interpret the sentence, even if information is incomplete. It's like filling in the missing pieces of the puzzle.

Understanding language isn't controlled by just one part of the brain. it's a team effort! Several areas work together.

- Broca's area: Helps us speak. Damage here makes speaking difficult (Broca's aphasia), even though understanding is okay. Speech is slow and grammatically simple.
- Wernicke's area: Helps us understand language. Damage causes Wernicke's aphasia—fluent speech, but it doesn't make sense. Understanding is very poor.
- Arcuate fasciculus: The “connector” between Broca's and Wernicke's areas. Damage makes repeating words hard (conduction aphasia), even if speaking and understanding are mostly fine.
- Angular gyrus And Supramarginal gyrus: These help with reading and the sounds of language. Damage affects reading and writing.

Brain damage (like from a stroke) to these areas causes aphasia, affecting different aspects of language. The type and severity depend on where and how much damage there is. For instance, damage to Broca's area makes forming sentences hard, while damage to Wernicke's area leads to nonsensical speech.

Many other brain parts also help with language, such as memory and attention. In a healthy brain, they all work perfectly together, making talking and understanding easy. But damage to any part can disrupt this and cause language problems.

Dyslexia and strokes both affect how people use language, but in different ways.

Dyslexia is a brain-based difficulty mainly affecting reading and spelling. It's more than just reading problems. It impacts how people handle the sounds of language (making it hard to break words into sounds and to spell), how quickly they name things, and their working memory (making it harder to understand what they read). Some also have trouble finding the right words to say. Even if they learn to read, understanding what they read can be challenging.

Strokes cut off blood flow to the brain, damaging brain tissue. This damage can lead to:

- Aphasia: Trouble speaking, understanding, or repeating words, depending on where the stroke happened.

Aphasia is most often caused by strokes, which occur when a blood vessel in the brain is either blocked or bursts. This disruption of blood flow damages or kills brain cells in the language-controlling regions, leading to communication difficulties. Aphasia can significantly impact a person's communication abilities, affecting their speech, comprehension, reading, and writing. Individuals with aphasia may experience a range of difficulties, including:

- Impaired Speech Production: They might speak in short, fragmented sentences, use incorrect words or sounds, struggle to find the right words (anomia), or even produce entirely made-up words (neologisms). Their speech might be grammatically incorrect or nonsensical.

- Impaired Comprehension: Understanding others' conversations can be challenging, and they may have difficulty grasping the meaning of what they read.

- Impaired Writing: Similar to their speech, their writing may be disorganized, grammatically flawed, and contain nonsensical phrases.

- Alexia and Agraphia: Inability to read or write.

Alexia (difficulty reading) and agraphia (difficulty writing) are acquired impairments caused by brain damage, not by simpler issues like blindness or paralysis. Because reading and writing are closely linked to language, these disorders are often studied alongside aphasia (acquired language impairment due to brain injury). Understanding alexia and agraphia has provided crucial insights into how the brain processes complex cognitive functions like reading and writing, and how brain damage in specific areas disrupts these abilities.

The severity of language problems after a stroke depends on the extent of the damage and the person's health. Some recover fully, while others have ongoing difficulties, often helped by speech therapy.

In short, dyslexia affects the brain's processes for language, particularly sound processing and quick word retrieval. Strokes cause physical damage to language centers in the brain, leading to a range of language problems. Both show how complex and interconnected language processing is.

Conclusion. In short, psycholinguistics unravels the mysteries of how language works in our minds. By investigating various aspects of language processing, from initial language acquisition to the neurological underpinnings of speech and the impact of language disorders, this field provides crucial insights into the remarkable human capacity for communication. It strives to create a comprehensive picture of how we use language, from the simplest of words to complex conversations and everything in between. By combining psychological experiments with linguistic analysis, it provides crucial insights into this uniquely human ability, enriching our understanding of both language itself and the human mind.

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SOTSIOLINGVISTIKA VA MADANIY TAFOVUTLAR: O‘ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDA ERKALOVCHI ATAMALAR VA EPISTEMIK MODALLIK.

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Annotatsiya: *sotsiolingvistika fani til va jamiyat o‘rtasidagi o‘zaro bog‘liqlikni o‘rganar ekan, turli madaniy muhitlarda til birliklarining ishlatilishiga e‘tibor qaratadi. Maqolada ushbu fan tarixiga nazar tashlanib, o‘zbek va ingliz tillarida erkalovchi atamalar, ijtimoiy omillarning nutqiy muomalaga ta’siri, epistemik modallik kabi tushunchalar solishtirilib tahlil qilinadi. Ayniqsa, badiiy asarlardagi obrazlar nomlari va ularning sotsiolingvistik ahamiyatiga alohida to‘xtalinadi.*

Kalit so‘zlar:*sotsiolingvistika, jamiyat va til, erkalovchi atamalar, epistemik modallik, lingvistik tadqiqot, ijtimoiy tilshunoslik, badiiy nutq, madaniy tafovutlar.*

Annotation: *sociolinguistics explores the interrelationship between language and society, focusing on the usage of linguistic units in various cultural contexts. This article reviews the history of this field and analyzes concepts such as terms of endearment in Uzbek and English, the impact of social factors on speech communication, and epistemic modality. Special attention is given to character names in literary works and their sociolinguistic significance.*

Keywords: *sociolinguistics, language and society, terms of endearment, epistemic modality, linguistic research, social linguistics, literary discourse, cultural differences.*

XXI asrda nafaqat texnika va texnologiya, balki fanlar kesimida ham rivojlanish va yangilanishlar kuzatilayotganiga guvoh bo‘lamiz. Shu jumladan, sotsiolingvistika sohasi ham bir necha yillardan buyon taraqqiy etib kelmoqda. Sotsiolingvistika termini lotincha socialis – jamiyat va lingua – til so‘zlaridan tashkil topgan. Bu termin fanga birinchi marta 1952-yilda amerikalik sotsiolog German Karri tomonidan kiritildi. J.A. Fishmanning “Til jamiyatidagi ma’ruzalar” (“Readings in the Society of Language”) nomli to‘plamiga kirgan.

O‘zbek tilshunosligida ham sotsiolingvistika sohasidagi izlanishlar XX asrning boshlariga borib taqaladi. XX asrning 40-yillaridan nutq uslublarini ilmiy jihatdan o‘rganish, monografik tarzda tadqiq etish boshlandi. Sotsiolingvistika tilning ijtimoiy tabiatini, uning ijtimoiy funksiyalarini, shuningdek, ijtimoiy omillarning tilga ta’sirini o‘rganadigan fandır.

Sotsiolingvistika o‘z o‘rganish obyekti bilan “sof” lingvistikadan farqlanadi. “Sof” lingvistika lisoniy belgilarni, chunonchi, tovush va uning yozma ifodasini, uning boshqa belgilar bilan o‘zaro munosabatini, vaqt va zamonda o‘zgarishini tahlil qilish bilan shug‘ullansa, sotsiolingvistika insonlar mazkur lisoniy belgilarni ularning yoshi, jinsi, ijtimoiy holati, bilimi va madaniyatlilik darajasiga ko‘ra qanday qo‘llashlarini, ya’ni ijtimoiy muhitning ularning nutqiy muomalasiga qanday ta’sir qilishini o‘rganadi.

Masalan, “sof” lingvistikada tomi ketmoq iborasi ot va fe‘ldan tarkib topgan frazeologik birlik sifatida talqin qilinsa, sotsiolingvistikani mazkur ibora qaysi tabaqa vakilining so‘zlashuv nutqida qo‘llanilgani qiziqtiradi. Mana shu kabi vazifalarni o‘z ichiga

olgan ,xalq,jamiyat hamda ularning tili o‘rtasidagi bog‘liqlikni aks ettiruvchi lug‘atlar tuzila boshladi. Masalan , "A Dictionary of Sociolinguistics" Joan Swann, Ana Deumert,Theresa Lillis and Rajend Mesthrie mualliflar tomonidan yaratilgan lug‘at mavjud bo‘lib,unda jamiyat va til o‘rtasidan sotsiolingvistik lug‘at tuzilgan. Undagi bir qancha terminlarni o‘zbek sotsiolingvistik terminlari bilan bog‘liq jihatlarini ko‘rib chiqamiz. Masalan ,unda Endearment termini mavjud bo‘lib ,u mehr- muhabbat ma’nosini ifodalovchi atama ma’nosini anglatadi.Erkalash (muhabbat ifodalovchi) atamalari

Ingliz tilida love, pet, dear kabi murojaat shakllari yaqinlikni ifodalash uchun ishlatiladi. Sotsiolingvistika nuqtai nazaridan bunday atamalar qiziqish uyg‘otadi, chunki ularning qo‘llanilishi madaniy jihatdan turlicha bo‘lishi mumkin. Ushbu atamalar ba‘zan assimetrik tarzda ishlatilishi mumkin va muayyan kontekstlarda hokimiyat va gender bilan bog‘liq bo‘lishi mumkin (masalan, ayollarga nisbatan erkaklarga qaraganda ko‘proq ishlatilishi).

Til va gender mavzusiga qarang.Xo‘sh,ingliz tilida uchrovchi bu nutq tushunchasi o‘zbek tilida uchramaydi mi? Albatta ,uchraydi. Bu tushunchani biz hayotimiz davomida juda ko‘p uchramamiz va har bir o‘zbek ayoli nutqida doimiy tarzda aks etadi. Masalan ,ayol biror bir bolaga murojaat qilganda unga bolani ismini aytish bilan birgalikda bolajonim,asal bola,erkatoyim,polvonim,girgitton,aylanay,shu bilan birgalikda,badiiy asar va filmlardagi yaxshi yoki yomon xislatlarga ega bo‘lgan obrazlar nomlari ataydi,ya’ni "Zolushkam","Zumradim","Oppog‘oyim" (qizlarga nisbatan) yoki "Alpomishim","Aliyim"(yigitlarga nisbatan) kabi erkalovchi so‘zlar bilan murojaat qilishini ko‘rishimiz mumkin. Shu kabi murojaatlarni badiiy asarlarda qay tarzda qo‘llanganligini ko‘rib chiqsak. G‘afur G‘ulomning " Mening o‘g‘rigina bolam" asari asosida ko‘rsak:

— Hoy, aylanay, o‘g‘rigina bolam, boshimda shunday musibat turganda ko‘zimga uyqu keladimi?

— Xayr, o‘g‘rigina bolam, kelib tur.

– Xi-xi-xi, aylanay sizdan, poshsha qiz! Mirzakarimboyning havlilari shumi? – deb so‘radi.

– Ha, aylanay quda, qars ikki qo‘ldan chiqadir, deganlar... Buzoq yaxshi bo‘lsa, ikki onani ham emar ekan...("O‘tkan kunlar")

Bir oycha turib, Robi opamga o‘rganib qolgan ekanman.

– Amma, Robi opam qachon keladila?

– Keladi, girgitton, keladi, – dedi ammam yelkamga qoqib. – Yaqinda butunlay keladi.

Nega endi uning o‘g‘li bo‘larkanman, men dadamning o‘g‘liman! Quhog‘idan chiqish uchun yulqinib turganimda allaqayerdan “Qora ammam” paydo bo‘ldi.

– Yur, jon bolam, – dedi qulog‘imga shivirlab, – chimildiqqa kirib bo‘lmaydi, girgitton! O‘zing yaxshi bolasan-ku! Yur, qovoq somsa beraman!("Ikki eshik orasi")

Yuqorida keltirilgan misollarda suhbat davomida yaqinlik,mehr yoki iliqlikni ifodalash uchun ishlatiladigan murojaat shakllari keltirilgan.

Bundan tashqari nutqimizda biror bir ish harakatni sodir bo‘lish yoki sodir bo‘lmasligini taxmin qilishimiz yoki shubha va gumon bo‘lishini ifodalashimiz uchun

ma'lum nutq elementlari zarur bo'ladi. Bu nutqiy jarayonni ingliz va o'zbek tillarida ifodalanishini ko'rishimiz mumkin.

Masalan, "Dictionary of Sociolinguistics" nomli sotsiologik lug'atida bu jarayon quyidagi termin bilan ifodalanar ekan, ya'ni Epistemic modality - Epistimetik modallik ma'nosida. U modallikning bir turi bo'lib, u gapiruvchi yoki yozuvchining taklif qilinayotgan fikrning rostligiga bo'lgan ishonch darajasini ifodalaydi. Masalan, tilshunos Janet Xolms (1995) gender va xushmuomalalikni o'rganish jarayonida "Men imtihonlarimni oltmish uchinchi yilda topshirdim, shundaymi?" kabi savol ortidan keladigan gaplarni "epistemik modal teglari" deb belgilagan, chunki ular gapiruvchining ma'lumotning rostligiga bo'lgan ishonchini ifoda etadi. Ikkala tilda ham epistemik modallik gapiruvchining ma'lumotning rostligiga bo'lgan ishonch darajasini ifodalash uchun ishlatiladi.

Modal fe'llar va boshqa modallik ifodalari orqali ifodalanadi. Gumon, taxmin, ehtimollik, ishonch darajasini ko'rsatishda ishlatiladi. Inglizcha: He must be at home. (U, albatta, uyda bo'lsa kerak.) O'zbekcha: U uyda bo'lsa kerak. Ingliz tilida must, might, may, could, can't kabi modal fe'llar epistemik modallikni ifodalashda ishlatiladi. O'zbek tilida esa modal fe'llar kam ishlatilib, ko'proq yordamchi so'zlar (kerak, mumkin, ehtimol) yoki fe'lning shakllari bilan ifodalanadi. He must have left already. (U allaqachon ketgan bo'lsa kerak.)

O'zbek tilida epistemik modallik asosan: modal so'zlar (ehtimol, balki, albatta, aniq). Shakllar (bo'lsa kerak, bo'lishi mumkin, shekilli, chamasi) orqali ifodalanadi. U hozir ehtimol uxlayotgandir yoki bugun, balki, havo juda issiq bo'lar kabi.

Epistemik modallik ikkala tilda ham mavjud bo'lib, ularning ifoda usullari o'xshash. Biroq, ingliz tili modal fe'llarga tayanadi, o'zbek tilida esa modal so'zlar va fe'l shakllari ko'proq ishlatiladi. O'zbek tilidagi "shekilli, chamasi, bo'lsa kerak" kabi iboralar ingliz tilidagi "must, might, probably" kabi modal birliklarga to'g'ri keladi.

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BADIY ASARLARDA NOMLAR JILOSI

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada barchamizning qalbimizdan, ko'ngil tubidan joy olgan jannatmakon O'zbekistonimizning yirik namoyodalari ijodida aks etgan asar qahramonlari va ularga tanlangan nomlar to'g'risida mushohada olib borganmiz. Biz uchun oddiy ism yoki shunchaki asar qahramoni sifatida tanilishi mumkin bo'lgan qahramonlarning hattoki ular uchun tanlangan nomi orqali qanchalik ramziylik aks etganligini ba'zi asar qahramonlari orqali yoritib berishga harakat qildik.*

Kalit So'zlar: *Qora amma, Umri xola, Sarsonboy ota, Mo'min chol, Qoravoy, "San'atkor".*

Annotation: *In this article, we explore the names of literary characters in the works of prominent figures of our beloved and beautiful homeland, Uzbekistan. We reflect on how these names, which may seem like ordinary labels or just character names to some, actually carry deep symbolic meaning. Through the analysis of selected literary characters, we aim to highlight the significance and symbolism embedded in the names chosen for them.*

Key words: *Qora amma, Umri khola, Sarsonboy ota, Mumin chol, Qoravoy, "San'atkor".*

Badiiy adabiyot bilan tanishar ekanmiz, adabiyotshunoslik ilmida gapiruvchi nomlar deb ataluvchi tushunchani uchratamiz. Buning ma'nosi shuki, nutqda qo'llaniladigan ism va familiyalar, laqab va taxalluslar o'zining asl ma'nosidan tashqari ustama ma'no ham anglatadi yoki o'sha badiiy obrazga qo'yilgan nom qanchalik hayotiy sarguzashtni aks ettirish uchun foydalaniladi. O'zbek adabiyotida bunday nomlar talaygina. Adabiyotning bunday qirralarini ochib berishda Abdulla Qahhor va O'tkir Hoshimov mohirona foydalangan. Ularning asarlarida ishtirok etgan obrazlarning laqab va taxalluslari yoki ismlari qo'llanishida obrazlilik aks etgan. Ammo asarda qatnashgan har qanday ism yoki laqablar bunday xususiyatlarga ega emas. Badiiy asarda tanlangan ism va familiyalar personajni baholaydi, xarakterlaydi, mashg'ul bo'lgan kasbiga ishora qiladi. Boshqacha qilib aytganda, ular personajning ijtimoiy mavqeyiga fizionomiyasiga yoki xarakteriga moslab tanlanadi.

Badiiy matnlarda laqablar va taxalluslar asosan ramziy ma'noda ifodalanadi. Misol tariqasida O'tkir Hoshimovning "Ikki eshik orasi" romanidagi Qora amma obrazini olaylik.

Qora amma- mehribon, sodda bardoshli, jafokash ayol timsoli. U urush davridagi o'zbek ayolining timsoli gavdalantirilgan obrazdir. Bu personaj taqdiri unga qilgan qora kasbidan ham achinarli. Bu asarni o'qigan kitobxon bir shaxs uchun, bir ojiza ayol uchun shuncha g'am og'irlik qilmaydimi degan o'y bilan kitobxonni g'amga cho'mdiradi. Vaholanki, o'sha urush qanchadan qancha insonlarni boshini yegan qora urush davrining onalar boshiga solgan achchiq haqiqati Qora amma- timsoli orqali ochib berilgan. Urush tufayli bir bola (asardagi Muzaffar) onasiz qoladi. Muzaffarni issiq-sovug'i Qora amma zimmasiga tushadi. O'z o'g'li urushga ketib qaytib kelmaydi. (O'g'lini kuta-kuta, hattoki,

haykal bilan suhbatlashgani asar voqealarida yoritilgan edi). O‘z o‘g‘liga unashtirilgan qizni noiloj o‘z yog‘iga o‘zi qovurilib ukasiga unashtirishga majbur bo‘ladi. Turmush o‘rtog‘i poyezd g‘ildiraklari tagida achinarli vafot etadi. Mana shunday qora kunlarni boshidan o‘tkazgan bir ayol uchun qora sifat (laqab) ini berish ham go‘yoki yengildek . Bundan ham yupunroq sifat ham bormikan?!

Qora amma obrazida taqdirning achchiq qismatiga ilojsiz ko‘ngan boshiga tushgan ko‘rguliklarni matonat bilan yengib, o‘zida yashashga kuch-qudrat, hayotda intilish topa olgan ayol obrazini ko‘ramiz. Qora amma- umumlashma o‘zbek ayoli timsolidir. O‘zbek ayollariga xos bo‘lgan iffat, andisha, kuyunchaklik, soddalik kabi sifatlarni o‘zida aks ettira olgan obrazdir. Bir so‘z bilan aytganda bugungi kun zamonamizga o‘rnak bo‘la oladigan ayol timsolidir.

O‘tkir Hoshimov asarlaridan uzoqlashmagan holatdan uning "Urushning so‘nggi qurboni" asaridagi Umri xola personajiga nom qo‘yilishi haqida fikrlashamiz. Umri xola Shoikrom va Shone‘matning onasi bo‘ladi. Shoikrom kichikligidayoq otasi vafot etadi. Yolg‘iz ona ikki farzandni urush davrida voyaga yetkazadi. Uyli - joyli qiladi. Urush davri bo‘lganligi uchun har bir oiladan bitta erkak kishi urushga olib ketilgan . Lekin bu oilada hech kim urushga bormaydi, chunki Shone‘mat betob bo‘ladi . Oila boquvchi sifatida Shoikrom ham urushga yuborilmaydi. Ammo uka, ya‘ni Shoikrom akasi va onasiga deyarli yordam bermaydi. Vaholanki, qarib qolgan ona betob o‘g‘lini davolash uchun Shoikromni hovlisidagi qulupnay evaziga qo‘y suti oladi. Yoshlik davrida otasiz ikki farzandni boqqan ona o‘ziga qarovchi kerak bo‘lgan paytda ham o‘g‘lini davolashga harakat qiladi. Umr yo‘li , hayot chiziqlari qiyinchilik , yetishmovchilik hamda yupun holatda kechadi.

Hikoya nihoyasida Umri xolaning umri tugashi bilan urush ham tugaydi. Bu qaysidir ma‘noda ramziydir. Umrini o‘zi uchun sarflamagan , bolalari uchun jon bergan ona timsoli sifatida onaga umr so‘zi orqali nom berishni, ehtimol, afzal ko‘rgandir adib.

Fikrlarimizni O‘lmas Umarbekovning "Qiyomat qarz " asari bilan davom ettiramiz. Bu asar bosh qahramoni Sarsonboy otadir. U o‘z o‘g‘lidan urush tufayli judo bo‘ladi. O‘g‘lining do‘sti Sarsonboy otaga qo‘ylarini urushdan qaytgunicha omonat qilib qoldiradi. Ammo ko‘z qorachig‘idek saqlangan qo‘ylarning egasi kelmaydi. Sarsonboy ota Haydaralini izlab bormagan joyi qolmaydi. Har hafta bozorga borib uni qidiradi, ammo har safar sarson bo‘lib uyiga qaytadi. Omonatni aziz bilgan bir ota uni egasi topshirish uchun sarson-sargardon bo‘lib mashaqqat chekadi, boshqalarning achchiq gaplari, tanqidlariga qoladi. Shu sababli ham adib bir shaxsning sarson- sargardon holatini ifodalash maqsadini bosh qahramon ismi orqali ifodalashga harakat qiladi. Bu esa kitbxonga asarni o‘qib xulosa qilishga qiynalmasligiga yordam beradi. Bu esa ijodkorning qanchalik mahoratli psixologiyaga ega ekanligini ochib beradi.

O‘zbek adabiyotida bunday nomalarni ko‘p uchratamiz. Fikrimiz isboti , el orasida mashhur bo‘lib ulgurgan, asar asosida film ham sur‘atga olingan asar otaxon adib G‘afur G‘ulom qalamiga mansub " Shum bola " qissasidir. Bosh qahramon Qoravoy (Shumbola) . U yosh bo‘lishiga qaramasdan ne- ne mashaqqatlarni boshidan kechirmadi deysiz. Qancha-qancha joylarni, qancha shaxslarni ko‘rdi. Urush davridagi murakkab vaziyatlar birgina

bola sarguzashti orqali ochib beradi. O'sha qora va chirkin hayot Qoravoy obrazi orqali bayon qilinadi. Qora sifati bir ma'noda qo'nim topmagan, qarovsiz bir bolaga berilgan sifatdir, uning ismi orqali hayot chizgilarini ko'rishimiz mumkin.

Qardosh xalq adibi Chingiz Aytmatov ham "Oq kema" qissasida Mo'min chol obrazini qo'llaydi. Bu esa qahramonning qanchalik oliyjanob, mehnatkash, oqil, mo'zingina bir shaxs ekanligini ochib beradi. Buni asar voqealari rivojida bilib olishimiz mumkin, albatta.

Badiiy asardagi faqatgina asar qahramoni nomi emas, balki asar sarlavhasi ham gapiruvchi nomdir. Badiiy asarda Abdulla Qahhordek so'z qirralarini ochib beruvchi adib bo'lmasa kerak. Uning hikoyalari shunday nomlanganki, biz e'tibor qaratmagan jilolar bayon etilganligini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Ushbu adibning "gapiruvchi nom" deb nomlangan mavzu ostidagi bir qancha hikoyalari haqida fikr yuritimiz.

Abdulla Qahhorning e'tiborga sazovor asalaridan biri "Bemor" asaridir.

Adabiy asarda personajlarga umuman nom berilmasligi ham mumkin

Bunda ham ma'lum stilistik maqsad ko'zda tutilgan bo'lishi aniq. A. Qahhor "San'atkor" hikoyasida asar qahramoni - san'atkorga nom bergan emas. Tasvirdan shu narsa ma'lum bo'ladi, asar qahramoni o'zini chinakam ma'noda san'atkor, ya'ni bilimli, madaniyatli, tilni, o'z kasbini yaxshi biluvchi kishi deb hisoblaydi. Voqealar bayonida esa buning teskarisini anglaymiz, ya'ni qahramonning madaniyatdan, san'atdan yiroq bir kimsa ekanligi ma'lum bo'lib qoladi. A. Qahhor ham ana shu fikrni badiiy ifodalash, "san'atkor" so'zi anglatayotgan teskari ma'noga urg'u berish maqsadida asar qahramoniga ism qo'ymagan ko'rinadi.

Yuqorida keltirilgan fikrlarda asarlarga va personajlarga qo'yiladigan nomlar va ularning stilistik funksiyasi haqida muhokama va mulohazalar aks etadi. Biz bu mavzuni uzoq davom ettirishimiz mumkin. Ammo biz ushbu yo'nalish orqali o'qiyotgan va o'qimoqchi bo'lgan asarlaringizni anglashingiz va qalban his etishingiz uchun bir yo'l ochdik. Umid qilamizki, har qanday asarni shunchaki vaqt o'tkazish uchun emas, balki undagi haroratni his qilaysiz, albatta!

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EFFECTIVE METHODS FOR TEACHING PHONETICS AND PRONUNCIATION TO ADVANCED LANGUAGE LEARNERS

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Abstract: *Pronunciation and phonetics accuracy play a crucial role in advanced language learning, influencing intelligibility and communicative confidence and various methods are employed for this, depending on the learner's age. At the university level, phonetics courses are commonly used to achieve these goals. This paper examines effective methods for teaching phonetics and pronunciation to advanced learners, addressing both segmental features and suprasegmental elements. It explores common obstacles including first-language interference, while presenting research-backed techniques such as questionnaires. Through targeted practice and individualized feedback as well as the integration of various instructional techniques, learners can enhance their pronunciation and progress toward near-native proficiency. The discussion emphasize the role of an adaptable and interactive teaching approach in promoting ongoing development, ultimately leading to more natural and effective communication.*

Keywords: *first language interference, phonological awareness, advanced language learners*

Literature Review

Pronunciation is a critical component of second language acquisition, shaping learner's ability to communicate clearly and effectively. Despite its importance, pronunciation is often overlooked in language instruction, leading to persistent difficulties in fluency and comprehensibility. Research in the field of phonetics and second language learning has explored the extent to which explicit instruction can promote pronunciation skills and whether improvements are gained over time.

Pekka Lintunen's research offers a meaningful contribution to the field of second language acquisition by investigating the interplay between phonetic knowledge and learner's awareness of their pronunciation challenges.

The study, which focuses on Finnish university students learning English, sheds lights on difficulties faced by learners whose native language has a phonological system distinct from that of English. A key strength of the research lies in its methodological design, which employs both objective pronunciation assessments and subjective self-evaluations conducted before and after phonetic instruction.

This dual approach provides a nuanced understanding of whether explicit phonetic training enhances learner's ability to recognize and address their pronunciation issues. The discoveries indicate that phonetic instruction improves learners' self-assessment accuracy, encouraging them to focus on specific phonemes rather than entire words. Lintunen's work suggests that integrating phonetics into language curricula can be particularly advantageous for learners from linguistic backgrounds with significant phonological differences from English.

The research by Maija S. Peltola, Pekka Lintunen and Henna Tamminen explores the impact of explicit pronunciation instruction on improving vowel duration and quality among advanced Finnish learners of English. It demonstrates the critical role of pronunciation in effective communication and the specific challenges non-native speakers encounter when mastering English phonetics.

The research is especially relevant because pronunciation, despite its significant impact on comprehensive and fluency fields as mentioned and often receives insufficient attention in language education.

One of the central findings reveals that Finnish learners naturally develop native-like vowel duration, likely due to similarities in how vowel length functions in Finnish and English. However, vowel quality poses persistent challenges without targeted instruction.

Learners who received explicit pronunciation training illustrated marked improvements in vowel quality, achieving more native-like production compared to those without such instruction.

Gwen Brekelmans's work explores the impact of direct pronunciation instruction on advanced Dutch learners of English, assessing whether their pronunciation improves, declines, or remains unchanged after formal training ends. Over a three year period, the study tracks a cohort of university students, evaluating their pronunciation before and after completing pronunciation courses in their second year. It also examines the influence of external factors such as English language coursework and time spent abroad on the retention of pronunciation skills.

The research reveal that pronunciation instruction plays a significant role, enabling learners to attain and sustain a near native accent. Certain features such as stress patterns and rhoticity remain stable over time, while others like vowel quality and liaison, continue to present challenges as well as identifies a consistent trend where spontaneous speech is less accurate than controlled speech, emphasizing the importance of structured practice for achieving native-like pronunciation.

Additionally, ongoing exposure to English through academic coursework contributes to pronunciation stability, whereas time spent abroad has minimal measurable impact.

While regular use of English in academic contexts benefits learners, informal exposure alone does not significantly improve pronunciation accuracy. The research illustrates the value of systematic phonetic training in second language acquisition and demonstrates how targeted instruction can help learners maintain advanced pronunciation skills even after formal instruction concludes.

The research by Itsna Millatul Himmayati and Hanung Triyoko delves into the significance of teaching phonetics and pronunciation in English Language Teaching. The researchers contend that these elements are fundamental for effective communication and language acquisition, particularly in developing accurate and fluent speaking abilities as well as examine various teaching methods for phonetics and pronunciation such as the drill method, the audio-lingual method as well as the use of realia.

The drill method involves repetitive practice to perfect pronunciation, targeting both receptive and productive skills. ALM prioritizes listening and speaking over reading and writing, employing dialogues and repetitive exercises to establish language habits.

Realia incorporates real world objects or digital materials to teach pronunciation, making the learning process more interactive and practical as well as additional techniques also included such as phonetic training, reading aloud as well as listening, repeating, rhymes and verses, rules and instruction, awareness-rising activities, spelling and dictation, ear training.

These approaches help learners internalize phonological patterns, enhance pronunciation as well as build confidence in speaking. This research also discusses on the ongoing debate regarding which English pronunciation standard should be thought. Traditionally British English and American English were regarded as the benchmarks. However, with the global proliferation of English, many regions have developed their own varieties, collectively known as World Englishes. The researchers propose that educators should take into account the specific context and needs of their students when selecting a pronunciation standard to teach.

Discussion

Phonetics are the science of speech and crucial aspect of teaching pronunciation effectively. By developing a deep understanding of the sound system of a second language, Teachers can assist students in accurately articulating words as well as teaching phonetics involves recognizing and distinguishing between different speech sounds, namely phonemes, whereas teaching pronunciation emphasize the correct production of these sounds and their application in words and sentences to facilitate effective communication.

Teaching phonetics and pronunciation to advanced learners requires a refined approach as these students possess a strong foundation but need to polish their skills to reach near-native proficiency. There are various methods to achieve those goals.

Shadowing Technique improves fluency and helps learners internalize natural speech habits. By utilizing this method, learners listen to native speakers and mimic their speech, focusing on intonation, rhythm, stress patterns. Another technique is focusing on segmental and suprasegmental features, As they are highly effective for teaching phonetics and pronunciation to advanced learners, these two aspects focus on distinct yet interconnected components of speech as well as mastering both is crucial for attaining near-native fluency. Segmental features pertain to the individual sounds or phonemes in a language including vowels and consonants as well as they provide precision in pronunciation, targeted

Improvement and assist to build blocks as they form the foundation of clear speech. Utilizing the International Phonetic Alphabet, drills and repetition to reinforce correct pronunciation as well as practicing minimal pairs to distinguish similar sounds is effective method to teach segmental features. Suprasegmental features encompass aspects of speech that go beyond individual sounds, including stress patterns, rhythm, intonation and connected speech.

Suprasegmental features shape the rhythm and melody of speech, making it sound smooth and natural by providing natural speech flow as well as it can clarify the meaning of speech as variations and intonations in speech can alter the sentence's interpretation.

Recognizing suprasegmental features helps learners understand fast, connected speech in real-life situations. There are some methods to teach suprasegmental features including shadowing exercises, authentic audio materials as well as practicing sentence stress and intonation drills. There is common issue to teach advanced learners and It can be highly drawback if it is not resolved. First language interference is main source of problem for advanced learners.

When learning a new language, learners often depend on their existing language skills and habits. If first language and the target language share similar structures or sounds, this can facilitate positive transfer, making learning easier. Conversely, if languages are quite different, it may result in negative transfer, causing difficulties and errors, particularly in pronunciation. However, this issue can be addressed.

By immersing themselves in the target language and focus on actively speaking and listening as well as seeking feedback on their pronunciation and grammar, advanced learners can get rid of the first language interference.

Conclusion

In conclusion, teaching phonetics and pronunciation to advanced learners involves a detailed and strategic approach to refine their skills and help them achieve near-native fluency. Educators should focus on both segmental and suprasegmental features to address the complexities of spoken language.

Techniques such as the Shadowing method, using the International Phonetic Alphabet, practicing minimal pairs and engaging with authentic audio materials are highly effective for improving accuracy and fluency. Additionally, overcoming first language interference requires immersive practice, active listening, speaking and regular feedback.

By combining targeted exercises, awareness of linguistic differences and consistent exposure to the target language, learner can refine their pronunciation, enhance their communication skills and achieve greater confidence in real life interactions.

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**ERKIN VOHIDOV IJODIDA TALMEH SAN'ATINING QO'LLANILISHI
("RUHLAR ISYONI" DOSTONI ASOSIDA)**

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada O'zbekiston xalq shoiri Erkin Vohidov she'rlarida talmeh badiiy san'atining ayrim namunalari izohi "Ruhlar isyoni" dostoni asosida bayon etilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Erkin Vohidov, talmeh, O'zbekiston Qahramoni, "Buyuk xizmatlari uchun" ordeni, "Ruhlar isyoni", Xusrav Dehlaviy, Nazrul Islom, Bobur, Veda, Qur'on.*

**ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ТАЛМЕХА АРТИНИНА В ТВОРЧЕСТВЕ ЭРКИНА ВАХИДОВА
(ПО МОТИВАМ ЭПОСА "ВОССТАНИЕ ДУХОВ")**

Заключение: *В этой статье описаны некоторые примеры талмудического искусства в стихах народного поэта Узбекистана Эркина Вахидова на основе эпоса "Восстание духов".*

Ключевые слова: *Эркин Вахидов, талмех, Герой Узбекистана, орден "За большие заслуги", "Восстание духов", Хусрав Дехлави, назрул ислам, Бабур, Вeda, Коран.*

**APPLICATION OF TALMEH ARTININ IN THE WORK OF ERKIN VOHIDOV
(ON THE BASIS OF THE EPIC "REVOLT OF SOULS")**

Annotation: *This article describes some examples of Talmudic art in the poems of the people's poet of Uzbekistan Erkin Vohidov based on the epic "Revolt of the spirits".*

Keywords: *Erkin Vohidov, talmeh, hero of Uzbekistan, order "for great merits", "Revolt of spirits", Khusrav Dehlavi, Nazrul Islam, Babur, Veda, Quran.*

KIRISH

Erkin Vohidov – O'zbekiston Qahramoni va zamonaviy o'zbek adabiyotining yorqin namoyondalaridan biri. Elparvar shoir Erkin Vohidov nafaqat o'z davrining, balki hozirgi kunning ham mahoratli, mas'uliyatli shoirlaridan biridir desak mubolag'a bo'lmaydi. Buyuk ijodkor 1936-yilning 28-dekabrida Farg'ona viloyatining Oltiariq tumanida muallim oilasida tavallud topgan.

Yosh ijodkorning otasi Ikkinchi jahon urushida og'ir jarohat bilan oilasi bag'riga qaytadi. Biroq oradan ko'p o'tmay 1945-yilda bu dunyoni tark etdi. Afsuski, oradan bir yil o'tgach uning onasi bu dunyodan ko'z yumdi. O'n yoshga to'lar-to'lmas o'z boquvchisini yo'qotgan yosh ijodkor tog'asi tarbiyasiga o'tadi. Shoir qunt bilan o'qishni davom ettirdi.

Yosh Erkin Vohidovda adabiyotga bo'lgan muhabbat juda erta uyg'ondi. "Erkin Vohidov Toshkent davlat universiteti (hozirgi Mirzo Ulug'bek nomidagi O'zbekiston Milliy

universiteti) ning fiolologiya fakultetiga o‘qishga kiradi. Endilikda u adabiyotni tom ma’noda chuqur o‘rganishga kirishadi. Buyuk ijodkorlarning asarlarini berilib o‘qir ekan, ulardan badiiy mahorat sirlarini , so‘zga mas’uliyat hissini ,soddalik va ravonlikni o‘zlashtirishga intiladi. Shuning uchun ham uning “Tong lavhasi”, “Buloq”, “Sevgi”, “Ona tuproq” kabi qator she’rlaridagi chuqur ma’no, go’zal ifodalar, ajoyib tasvirlar bilan uyg’unlashib ketgan [2;208].

Erkin Vohidov universitetni bitirgach, uzoq yillar davomida nashriyotlarda faoliyat yuritdi. U 1964-yillarida yozilgan “Nido” dostoni bilan birga “Ozru chashmasi”, “Palatkada yozilgan doston”, “Quyosh maskani”, “Ruhlar isyoni” singari o‘zbek va jahon adabiyotining eng sara asarlarini yozdi. Shuningdek, “Erkin Vohidovning el-yurt va adabiyot oldidagi xizmatlari inobatga olinib “Buyuk xizmatlari uchun” ordeni va “O‘zbekiston Qahramoni” unvoni bilan taqdirlangan”[2;208].

Erkin Vohidov she’rlariga to‘xtaladigan bo‘lsak, shoir hayoti davomida yosh avlodlar uchun chuqur ma’noga ega she’rlarini, dostonlarini meros sifatida qoldirdi. U nafaqat ijod bilan, balki mashhur shoirlarning asarlarini o‘zbek tiliga tarjima qilish bilan shug‘ullangan.

Jumladan, shoir tarjima qilgan rus shoiri Sergey Yeseninning she’rlari, nemis shoiri Gyotening “Faust” asari yosh kitobxonlar uchun ilm manbayi bo‘ldi desak mubolag‘a bo‘lmaydi.

Shoir lirikasi o‘zbek va jahon she’riyatida alohida mavqe hamda o‘ringa ega. Buyuk shoir asarlarida, asosan, Vatanga muhabbat tasvirlangan. Shoir she’rlarida juda ko‘p badiiy san’atlarga, xususan, talmeh badiiy san’atiga guvoh bo‘lamiz.

“Talmeh – (ar. “Chaqmoq chaqishi”; “bir nazar tashlash”). She’rda o‘tmishdagi mashhur zotlarga, mashhur qissa, mashhur bayt yoki mashhur maqolaga ishora qilish, mashhur, tarixiy yoki adabiy qahramonlar nomini keltirish usulidir [1;97]. Ushbu maqola davomida shoir qalamiga mansub “Ruhlar isyoni” dostonida uchraydigan ba’zi talmeh san’atlarni tahlil qilamiz. Shoir qalamiga mansub ushbu dostonning “Shoir qalbi” bobida talmeh badiiy san’ati ko‘p marotaba qo‘llanilganiga guvoh bo‘lamiz.

“Bu dunyoga
Nazrul Islom
Shoir bo‘lib tug‘ildi.
Ibtidodan yoniq ilhom
Shu’lasiga yo‘g‘rildi.
Yetti asr avvalgidek
Bo‘lsa edi zamonlar,
Balki
Xusrav Dehlaviydek
Bitar edi dostonlar.
Tug‘ilsaydi
Shoir agar
Yarim ming yil ilgari,
Bitar edi ruboiylar
Mirzo Bobur singari” [3;12].

Yuqorida keltirilgan misralarda Nazrul Islom, Xusrav Dehlaviy, Bobur Mirzo kabi buyuk ijodkorlar talmeh bo'lib kelgan. Barchamizga ma'lumki, Nazrul Islom she'rlarida ma'rifatparvarlik va insonparvarlik g'oyalari ilgari surilgan. "Kazir Nazrul Islom (1899-1976) – Bengal shoiri. Ilk she'rlarini "Hofiz" asarlari ta'sirida yozgan. "Isyonkor" dostoni, "Zaharli nay", "Olovli ud" she'riy to'plamlari, "Kambag'alning iztiroblari" hikoyalar to'plami mavjud [4]. Qolaversa, uning "Inson" she'riy to'plami o'zbek tiliga tarjima qilingan. Shu o'rinda aytish joizki, Erkin Vohidov ham "Ruhlar isyoni" dostonini aynan Nazrul Islom hayoti va ijodiga bag'ishlagan.

Xusrav Dehlaviy-buyuk shoir, olim, bastakor. Ilk o'rta asarlarini "Sultoniyy" taxallusi ostida yozgan. U Dehlida yashagani sababli Dehlaviy taxallusini olgan. Xusrav Dehlaviy o'z asarlarida barcha zamonlar uchun muhim bo'lgan ko'plab ijtimoiy, axloqiy narsalarni badiiy talqin qilgan. "Shoir asarlarining umuminsoniy ahamiyat hisobga olinib, YUNESKO qaroriga muvofiq 1973-yil Xusrav Dehlaviyning 700 yilligi xalqaro miqyosda nishonlangan. Shoir asarlari o'zbek xalqi orasida ham keng tarqalgan, xususan, "Xamsa"si va devonlari qo'lyozmasi ko'plab ko'chirilgan." [4].

Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur- o'zbek mumtoz adabiyotining yirik vakili, shoir, tarixchi, iste'dodli sarkarda va boburiylar sulolsi asoschisi. "Bobur 18-19 yoshlaridan ruboiy va g'azallar yoza boshlagan. Uning "Topmadim", radifli g'azali va "Yod etmas emish kishini g'urbatda kishi" misrasi bilan boshlanuvchi ruboiyni o'sha yillardagi hayoti bilab bog'liq" [4]. Shuningdek, Respublikamizda prezidentimiz I. Karimov farmoniga binoan 1993-yilda Bobur tavalludining 510 yilligi tantanali nishonlandi. O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasining Bobur nomidagi medali ta'sis etildi.

"Haq oldida barobarmiz,

Ayting,

Ne bor nizoga!

Xunrezlik qil demaganku,

Axir Veda va Qur'on. [3;26]

"Ruhlar isyoni" da yod etilgan Veda va Qur'on bu misralarda talmeh badiiy san'atini yuzaga keltirgan. Barchamizga ma'lumki, dunyoda turli xil millat va elatlar istiqomat qilishadi. Ularning o'ziga xos bo'lgan urf-odatlar hamda dini mavudligi barchaga ma'lum. Mana shunday turli dinlardan biri bu Vedadir.

"Veda dini – mil.avv.1-ming yillikda Hindistonda vujudga kelgan din. Vedada dastlab tabiat kuchlari va hodisalari antropomorfik (inson qiyofasiga o'xshatib) tasavvur etilgan. Vedada yaxshi va yomon xudolar, ruhlar haqidagi tasavvurlar asosiy o'rin egalladi. Unda politizm (ko'pxudolik) hukmron bo'lgan" [4].

Qur'on – musulmonlarning asosiy muqaddas kitobi. Muqaddas Qur'oni karim kitobi 23 yil davomida nozil bo'lgan bo'lib, 13 yil Makkada, 10 yil Madinada yozib olingan. "Islom dini e'tiqodiga ko'ra Qur'on vahiy orqali Muhammad payg'ambarga 610-632-yillar davomida nozil qilingan Allohning kalomi (Kalomulloh) [4].

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ZAMBURUG‘LARNING KO‘PAYISH XILLARI HAMDA BIOLOGIK XILMA-XILLIGI

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Ilmiy rahbar:

Annotatsiya: *Mazkur maqolada zamburug‘larning ko‘payish usullari va ularning biologik xilma-xilligi haqida ma‘lumot beriladi. Zamburug‘lar vegetativ, jinssiz va jinsiy yo‘llar bilan ko‘payishi mumkin bo‘lib, har bir usulning o‘ziga xos xususiyatlari yoritiladi. Shuningdek, ularning xilma-xilligi ekologik ahamiyati, morfologik va fiziologik xususiyatlari asosida tahlil qilinadi. Maqolada zamburug‘larning tabiatdagi roli va inson hayotidagi ahamiyati ham ko‘rib chiqiladi.*

Kalit So'zlar: *Sitoxrom C, geterotrof, gametogamiya, somatogamiya, gametangiogamiya, konidiaspora, bazidiospora, fungi, lignin, rizomitseliy, glukan, manin.*

Annotation: *This article provides information about the reproduction methods of fungi and their biological diversity. Fungi can reproduce vegetatively, asexually, and sexually, with each method having its own specific characteristics. Additionally, their diversity is analyzed based on ecological significance, morphological, and physiological features. The article also examines the role of fungi in nature and their importance in human life.*

Keys Words: *Cytochrome C, heterotroph, gametogamy, somatogamy, gametangiogamy, conidiospore, basidiospore, fungi, lignin, hizomycelium, glukan, mannan*

Zamburug'larni bo'limini mikologiya fani o'rganadi. Zamburug'lar yunoncha "fungi" deb nomlanadi. Odatda o'simliklarda, tuproqda, suvda hayvonlarda yoki ularing qoldiqlarida hayot kechiradi. Oziqlanish usuliga qarab parazit va saprofitlarga bo'linadi. Ularining odamlar va hayvonlarda uchraydigan zararli va foydali yuz mingdan ortiq turi uchraydi.

Zamburug'lar organik moddalarni parchalab, moddalarning aylanishida ishtirok etadi va parazit shaklda boshqa organizmlarga zarar yetkazishi mumkin. Muhim fiziologik xususiyatlari rivojlanish uchun kislorod zarur bo'lib aerob organizm hisoblanadi. Tuproqda tashaydigan zamburug‘lar o'simlik qoldiqlari (jumladan, qiyin parchalanadigan selluloza va lignin) ni parchalaydi va minerallashtiradi. Yog'ochlarni, asosan, po'kakni yemiradi. Ko'pchilik o'simliklarda turli kasalliklarni qo'zg'atadi. Shuningdek zamburug'larning foydali turlari ham mavjud.

Penicillium va aspergillus turkumiga mansub zamburug'lardan vitaminlar, antibiotiklar, limon kislota va steroid preparatlar olishda foydalaniladi. Achitqi, vino, non, pivo tayyorlashda ishlatiladi. Zamburug'lardan to'qimachilik va sanoatning boshqa tarmoqlarida qo'llaniladigan turli xil fermentlar olinadi. Dunyoning ko'p mamlakatlarida ovqatga ishlatiladi, iste'mol qilinadigan zamburug'larning turi 150 dan ortiq. Bulardan

ko'plari qimmatli bo'lib, tarkibida oqsil moddalari, vitaminlar va fermentlar bor. Asosan, konservalab (quritib, tuzlab, ziralab) iste'mol qilinadi.

Zamburug'lar o'simlik, hayvon va odamlarda kasallik qo'zg' atish xususiyatiga ega, oziq - ovqat mahsulotlarini buzadi. O'simliklarda vilt, chirish va zang kasalliklarini paydo qiladi.

Ba'zi hashorotlar soni rivojlanishini susaytirishda ijobiy ahamiyatga ega. Tuproqda bakteriyalardan, aktinomitsetlar va mikroorganizmlar bilan birgalikda organik moddalarni parchalab, sanitarlik vazifasini bajaradi va tabiatda moddalar aylanishida ishtirok etadi. Shu bilan birga tuproqda o'simliklarda kasalliklar qo'zg'atadigan turlari to'planib ham qoladi. Ko'pgina mog'or zamburug'lari xomashyoni saqlash davrida paxta tolasi sifatini buzadi. Ba'zi turlari iste'mol qilinadi jumladan, qo'ziqorin, shampinion va boshqalar. Zamburug'larning fermentativ, antibiotik, toksik va parazitlik xususiyatlaridan veterinariyada hamda o'simliklarni zararkunanda va kasalliklardan himoya qilishda, shuningdek, yengil sanoatda, oziq-ovqatlar va farmasevtika sanoatida foydalaniladi.

Zamburug'lar qadimiy organizmlar bo'lib, evolyutsiya jarayonida rangsiz sitoxrom C oqsiliga ega bo'lmagan xivchinlilarning Fiagellatae guruhidan kelib chiqqan. Shuning uchun ham zamburug'lar o'simliklar olami doirasida o'rganiladi. Ammo zamburug'lar oziqlanish xususiyatlari bilan o'simliklardan farq qiladi, chunki ularning hujayrasida yashil rang beruvchi xlorofill pigmenti bo'lmaydi.

Ular geterotrof oziqlanishga moslashgan ya'ni zamburug'lar tayyor organik moddalar bilan oziqlanuvchi organizmlar hisoblanadi. Shu xususiyati bilan anorganik moddalar bilan oziqlanuvchi avtotrof organizmlarga qarama-qarshi turadilar. Assimilyatsiya vaqtida zamburug'larning hujayrasida kraxmal emas, balki mochevina, glikogen hosil bo'ladi. Bundan tashqari, hujayra devorlarida xitin moddasi to'planadi. Mana shu belgilari bilan zamburug'lar hayvonlar olamiga yaqin turadi.

Hozirgi kunda ko'pchilik olimlar zamburug'larni eukariotik organizmlarning alohida olamiga ajratishni taklif etmoqdalar. Ularning eng xarakterli belgilari hujayra devorlarining aniq shakllanganligi, oziqni shimib olishi, sporalar yordamida ko'payishi, vegetativ tanasi o'sish qobiliyatiga egaligi, oziqlanishi geterotrof usulda kechishi, assimilyatsiya vaqtida hosil bo'ladigan oziq modda glikogendan iboratligidadir.

Qalpoqchali zamburug' (Shampinion (*Agaricus bisporus*))

Zamburugʻlarning vegetativ tanasi mitseliy deb ataladi. Mitseliy shoxlangan gifalardan tashkil topgan boʻlib, uchiga oʻsish va yon tomonga shoxlanish xususiyatiga ega. Mitseliy substratga oʻrnashib, undagi oziq moddalarni shimib oladi. Substrat ustidagi mitseliyga havoii mitseliy deyiladi. Havoii mitseliydan koʻpayish organlari taraqqiy etadi. Zamburugʻlar dunyosi asosan, jinsiy, jinssiz va vegetativ usullarda koʻpayadi.

Zamburugʻlarning jinsiy koʻpayishi: zamburugʻlarning bu xilda koʻpayishi deuteromitsetsimonlar sinfidan boshqa hamma zamburugʻlarda uchraydi. Mazkur jarayonning asosan uchta guruhi farqlanadi.

1. Gametogamiya - tuban zamburugʻlarda rivojlangan boʻlib, suvoʻtlaridagi kabi izogamiya, geterogamiya va oogamiya usulida sodir boʻladi. Koʻpchilik zamburugʻlarda oogamiya yoʻli bilan koʻpayishda harakatsiz tuxum hujayraning urugʻlanishida anterediy oʻsimtasi ishtirok etadi. Ayrim vakillarida tuxum hujayraning urugʻlanishi spermatozoidlar yordamida sodir boʻladi.

2. Somatogamiya - bazidiomitsetsimonlar sinfiga xos boʻlib, bunda jinsiy hujayralar ishtirok etmasdan, faqat mitseliy somatik hujayralari ishtirok etadi.

3. Gametangiogamiya - zigomitsetsimon va xaltachasimon zamburugʻlar sinflariga oid boʻlib, har xil tupdan chiqqan giflar uchlari bir-biriga qarab oʻsadi va uchi boʻrtib shishadi. Uchlarining tutashga joyida ularni bir-biridan ajratuvchi toʻsiqlar paydo boʻladi. Keyinchalik bu toʻsiq eriydi, moddalari birlashib zigotani hosil qiladi. Bunday zigota zigospora deb atalib, tinim davrini oʻtgandan oʻsib qisqa sporangiyband ichida shoxlanmagan yosh sporangiyga aylanadi.

Zigota hosil qiluvchi hujayralar hamisha diploid toʻplamli boʻladi.

Jinssiz koʻpayish: zamburugʻlarda 2 xil usulda amalga oshadi.

1. Zoosporalar endogen yoʻl bilan giflar uchidagi zoosporangiy ichida taraqqiy etadi, uning ichida 1 yoki 2 xivchinli zoosporalar yetishadi. Zoosporalarning xivchinlari silliq yoki tukli boʻladi. Zoospora yetilgandan soʻng, zoosporangiy devorini yorib chiqib, biror substratga yopishadi va oʻsib yangi individga aylanadi. Bunday usul bilan koʻpayish xitridiomitset, oomitset va gifoxitrediomitsetsimonlar sinflariga oiddir.

2. Konidiasporalar bilan koʻpayish usuli quruq sharoitga moslashgan yuksak zamburugʻlar uchun xos. Konidiaspora konidiyaband deb ataluvchi alohida gifning ichida vujudga keladi. Konidiyabandning uchidagi hujayra dumaloqlashib, nozik tizma zanjircha hosil qiladi. U yetilgandan soʻng tizmalar uzilib, tarqalib ketadi. Konidiasporalar ekzogen yaʼni sirdan hosil boʻladi. Har bir tur zamburugʻda oʻziga xos shoxlanadi.

Vegetativ koʻpayish: zamburugʻlarda bir necha xil usullarda amalga oshadi.

- Mitseliy uzilib, mustaqil individga aylanadi. Masalan, xlamidospor qalin poʻst bilan oʻralgan boʻlib, noqulay sharoitlarda ham oʻsish qobiliyatini saqlab qoladi.
- Oidiylar vositasida koʻpayishda mitseliy gifasining uchlari bir qancha ayrim hujayralarga boʻlinadi. Hosil boʻlgan hujayra taraqqiy etib, yangi mitseliyga aylanadi.
- Kurtaklanish yoʻli bilan koʻpayish boʻrtmachalar paydo boʻlishi bilan xarakterlanadi va achitqi zamburugʻlarida kuzatiladi.

- Sklerotsiy vositasida ko‘payish giflarning zich qo‘shilib o‘sishi natijasida sodir bo‘ladi. Ular qoramtir, binafsha rangli, qattiq po‘stli, zaxira oziq moddalarga boy, shoxsimon bo‘lib, noqulay sharoitni tuproqda o‘tkazadi. Bahorda o‘sib mevatnaga aylanadi. Masalan, bu ko‘payish usulini shoxkuya zamburug‘ida kuzatish mumkin.

Zamburug‘larni klassifikatsiyalashda ularni eng muhim belgilariga, jumladan, xivchinlarning joylashishi va tuzilishiga, jinssiz va jinsiy ko‘payish xususiyatiga, hujayra devorining tuzilishiga va polisaxaridlar tarkibiga qaraladi. Yuqorida aytilgan belgilarga asoslanib, zamburug‘lar bo‘limi 7 ta guruhga ajratiladi.

1. Xitridiomitsetsimonlar (Chytridiomycetes) ning mitseliysi boshlang‘ich holda bo‘lib, vegetativ tanasi odatda po‘stsiz, hujayra devori yo‘q. Jinssiz ko‘payishi zoosporalar yordamida sodir bo‘lib, zoospora faqat bitta silliq xivchinga ega. Jinsiy ko‘payishi gametogamiya yoki oogamiya, hujayra devorida xotin va glyukan o‘raydi.

2. Gifoxitriomitsetsimonlar (Hypochytriomycetes) vegetativ tana va bir hujayrali bo‘lib, yalang‘och rizomitseliy hosil qiladi. Jinssiz ko‘payish shoxlangan bir hujayrali zoosporalar yordamida sodir bo‘ladi. Hujayra devorlarida xitin va selluloza uchraydi.

3. Oomitsetsimonlar (Oomycetes) mitseliyli rivojlangan, lekin hujayrasiz tuzilishga ega. Jinssiz ko‘payishi ikki xivchinli (xivchinning biri silliq, ikkinchisi shoxlangan) zoosporalar vositasida boradi. Jinsiy ko‘payish oogamiya, hujayra devorida selluloza va gluklan bor.

4. Zigomitsetsimonlar (Zygomycetes) ning mitseliyasi yaxshi rivojlangan bo‘lib, ko‘pchilik vakllarida ko‘payish sporangiospora hosil qilish bilan boradi. Jinsiy ko‘payish izogamiya, hujayra devorida xitin va xitozan moddasi uchraydi.

5. Askomitsetsimonlar (Ascomycetes) ning mitseliyasi yaxshi taraqqiy etgan bo‘lib, ko‘p hujayrali. Jinssiz ko‘payish konidiasporalar yordamida sodir bo‘ladi. Jinsiy ko‘payish gametangiyalar yordamida amalga oshadi va bular ichida xaltachalar ichida taraqqiy etadi. Hujayra devorida xitin va gluklan uchraydi. Achitqi zamburug‘larining hujayra devorida xitin va manin moddasi bo‘ladi.

6. Bazidiomitsetsimonlar (Basidiomycetes) ning mitseliyasi yaxshi rivojlangan bo‘lib, ko‘p hujayrali. Jinssiz ko‘payish bazidiyasporalar yordamida sodir bo‘lib, mitseliyalar orasida somatogamiya. Jinsiy ko‘payishda ikkita mitseliy birlashadi va mitseliyalar ustida bazidiyalar hosil bo‘ladi.

6. Deyteromitsetsimonlar (Deuteromycetes) takomillashgan zamburug‘lar, mitseliy yaxshi taraqqiy etgan. Jinssiz ko‘payish konidiasporalar yo‘li bilan boradi. Jinsiy ko‘payish aniqlanmagan. Hujayra devorida xotin va glyukan uchraydi. Yuqorida ko‘rsatilgan sinflardan tashqari zamburug‘lar o‘rtasida shunday guruhlar borki, ularning sistemasi hozirgacha aniqlanmagan. Masalan, trixomitsetlar.

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**INGLIZ, ISPAN VA O‘ZBEK TILLARIDA KICHRAYTIRISHNING
MORFOLOGIK SATHDA IFODALANISHI**

Mamatqulova Nodira Fayzulla qizi

(O‘zDJTU)

Tayanch so‘zlar: *Kichraytirish, morfologik sath, qo‘shimcha, old qo‘shimcha, suffiks, morfema.*

Kichraytirishning morfologik sathda ifodalanish jarayonida ingliz, ispan va o‘zbek tillarida ayrim o‘xshash va farqli jihatlarini kuzatishimiz mumkin. Ingliz tilida N. Sh.

Nishiniadzening fikricha 10 ta kichraytirish-erkalash suffikslari mavjudligi va ular faqat mustaqil so‘z turkumi (otga) qo‘shilib keladi.¹³ Schneider esa hozirgi zamonaviy ingliz tilida 14ta kichraytirish qo‘shimchalari borligini keltirsa¹⁴, Teresa Hagg o‘z ishida ular sonini bittaga ko‘paytirib 15ta (-ie, -ette, -let, -ling, -kin, -een, -en, -(e)rel, -et, -o, -a, -s, -er, -poo, -pegs) ekanligini ko‘rsatadi va ular asosan ot so‘z turkimiga qo‘shilishini keltirib o‘tadi.¹⁵ Shu bilan bir qatorda ba‘zi olimlar (A.K. Po‘latov) ingliz tilidagi -y (-ie, -ey), -let, -ling, -ette, -et, -kin, -ock, -y, -ie, -el kabi qo‘shimchalarni erkalashni ham, kichraytirish ham ifodalashini keltirsalar, boshqa olimlar (M. I. Rasulova) esa ularni faqat kichraytirish jihatidan o‘rganganlar.¹⁶ Kichraytirishning ingliz tilida morfologik sathda ifodalanishini yaxshiroq anglash uchun bir qancha kichraytirish qo‘shimchalarini tahlil qilib chiqamiz.

-y/-ie/-ey qo‘shimchalari asosan ot so‘z turkimiga qo‘shilib kelishiga qaramay, ba‘zan sifatli (brownie, goodie, softie) yoki fe‘lli asoslar (cookie) bilan ham kelishi mumkin.

Dressler va Merlini Barbaresiga ko‘ra ushbu kichraytirish qo‘shimchalari ba‘zi ko‘p bo‘g‘inli so‘zlarga qo‘shilib ularning asosini bir bo‘g‘inli bo‘lib qisqarishiga ham hizmat qiladi, masalan grandmother so‘zi granny shaklida, potatoes so‘zi tatties shakliga o‘zgarishining guvohi bo‘lamiz.

-ette kichraytirish qo‘shimchasi asli fransuz tilidan olingan bo‘lib, -et shaklida ham qo‘llanishi mumkin. Yozilishi fransuzcha saqlanib qolishiga qaramasdan, talaffuzda / -`et/ shaklida talaffuz qilinadi.

Ushbu qo‘shimcha ko‘p vazifali qo‘shimchadir. Ya‘ni birinchi vazifada kichraytirish otlarini (kitchenette, novelette, sermonette, colonette) yasasa, keyingi hollarda “o‘xshatish”ni yoki “jenskiy rod”ni ifodalab keladi. Asosan otli asoslarga qo‘shilib, ba‘zan esa fe‘lli o‘zakka (laundrette) ham qo‘shilib keladi.¹⁷

-let qo‘shimchasi Schneider, Rotzoll qarashlariga ko‘ra nemis tilidan, Charleston fikriga ko‘ra fransuz tilidan olingan qo‘shimchadir. Ingliz tilida kichik hajmni (droplet, leaflet) va hayvon bolalarining nomini ham yasaydi: piglet, froglet va shu kabilar.

¹³ X. Б. Самигова. Эмоционалликнинг инглиз ва ўзбек тилларидаги ифодаси (эркалаш майдони мисолида) монография – GlobeEdit, 2019. – b.20

¹⁴ O. K. Bekbaulova / Morphological peculiarities of diminutive suffix -ette in the English language

¹⁵ A. T. Hagg. A contrastive study of English and Spanish diminutives. - Representralen, University of Oslo, 2016. – b. 23

¹⁶ X. Б. Самигова. Эмоционалликнинг инглиз ва ўзбек тилларидаги ифодаси (эркалаш майдони мисолида) монография – GlobeEdit, 2019. – b.21

¹⁷ A. T. Hagg. A contrastive study of English and Spanish diminutives. - Representralen, University of Oslo, 2016. – B. 21-29

Kichraytirish qo‘shimchalari orasida eng sof kichraytirish qo‘shimchasidir.¹⁸

Ushbu qo‘shimchalardan tashqari “mini-” (asli lotin tili qo‘shimchasi) yoki “micro-” kabi asli yunon old qo‘shimchalarni ham keltirib o‘tishimiz mumkin.

Misol tariqasida “micro base” (mikro baza), “microprogramming” (mikrodasturlash), “mini market” (kichik bozorcha/ do‘kon) va boshqa shu kabi so‘zlarni ko‘rishimiz mumkin. Ingliz tilida kichraytirish qo‘shimchalari juda ko‘p bo‘lmaganligi sababli asli kelib chiqishi xorijiy bo‘lgan morfemalardan foydalaniladi.¹⁹

Ispan tilida umumiy 200ga yaqin suffikslar bo‘lib, “La Nueva gramática de la lengua española” (2010) nomli ispan tili grammatikasiga oid kitobda quyidagi 10 ta kichraytirish qo‘shimchalari eng faollari deya ko‘rsatiladi: -ito/a, -illo/a, -ico/a, -uelo/a, -ín/ina, -ino/a, -iño/a, -ajo/a, -ejo/a and -ijo/a. Gooch (1967) va Lang (1990) kabi tilshunoslar o‘z ishlarida kichraytirish qo‘shimchalar sonini 6 ta va 7talilgi aytadilar. “-ito/a, -illo/a, -ico/a, -ín/ina, -ete” qo‘shimchalari yuqorida ko‘rsatilgan uchchalada adabiyotda ham eng ko‘p qo‘llanuvchi qo‘shimcha sifatida ta‘riflanadi.²⁰ Lázaro Mora (1999) ham ispan tilida 7 ta qo‘shimchani kichraytirish qo‘shimchasi sifatida ko‘rsatib, -ito/a va -illo/a shakllari standart ispan tilida eng ko‘p foydalaniluvchi qo‘shimchalar ekanligini va shu bilan bir qatorda ushbu ikki qo‘shimcha deyarli barcha so‘z turkumlariga kichraytirish ma‘nosini yuklash maqsadida qo‘shilishi mumkinligini takidlaydi.²¹

“-ito/a” ispan tilidagi eng ko‘p qo‘llaniluvchi, neytral ma‘noga ega va barcha ispan tili lahjalarida uchrovchi kichraytirish qo‘shimchasidir. Asosan otlarga “bombita” (kichik bomba), sifatlarga “acabadito” (ajoyib), ravish “bajito” (juda tekis) va sifatdoshlarga (ravishdoshlarga ham) “los niños iban corriendito” (bolalar xursand bo‘lib ketishdi) ham qo‘shilib keladi. Ba‘zan erkalash va gipokoristik “abuelita” (buvijon) ma‘nolarda ham namoyon bo‘ladi. Odatda -a va -o harflari bilan yakunlanuvchi so‘zlarga qo‘shiladi. Yana ushbu qo‘shimchani muhim taraflaridan biri bolalar nutqida ko‘p qo‘llanilishidir. Hayvon nomlariga bilan kelganda erkalash va kichraytirish ma‘nolari anglashiladi: “gatito” (asal mushukcha), “burrito” (kichik maymun), “pajarito” (yoqimtoy qushcha) va boshqalar.²²

“-illo/a” qo‘shimchasi asosan kichraytirish, ba‘zan esa erkalash qo‘shimchasi sifatida ot va sifatdan keyin foydalaniladi. Ko‘pincha norasmiy nutqda qo‘llaniladi va ot asosiga kuchsizroq ma‘noni yuklaydi. Masalan:

- un panecillo (non bo‘lagi);
- un problemilla (kichik muammo);
- alegrillo (ozroq baxtilday);²³

Ushbu ma‘lumotlardan kelib chiqib, ispan tilidagi kichraytirish qo‘shimchalari nafaqat otlarga, balki boshqa so‘z turkumlariga ham qo‘shilishini va nafaqat kichraytirish, shu bilan

¹⁸ A. T. Hagg. A contrastive study of English and Spanish diminutives. - Representralen, University of Oslo, 2016. - B. 21-29

¹⁹ https://www.ijcr.eu/articole/448_06%20Safia%20ZIVINGL.pdf murojaat sanasi 19.11.2024

²⁰ A. T. Hagg. A contrastive study of English and Spanish diminutives. - Representralen, University of Oslo, 2016. - 43 b.

²¹ https://www.researchgate.net/publication/332135175_The_Use_of_the_Diminutive_Suffixes_-itoa_and_-illoa_in_the_Spanish_Translation_of_The_Fifth_Child_by_Doris_Lessing murojaat sanasi: 19.11.2024

²² A. T. Hagg. A contrastive study of English and Spanish diminutives. - Representralen, University of Oslo, 2016. - 33 b.

²³ <https://blog.rosettastone.com/spanish-suffixes/#:~:text=%2Dillo%20%2F%20illa&text=%2Dillo%20and%20%2Dilla%20are%20diminutives,intensity%20of%20the%20base%20noun.> Murojaat sanasi: 21.11.2024

bir qatorda erkalash yoki ma'noni kuchsizlantirish vazifasida ham kelishining guvohi bo'ldik.

O'zbek tilida kichraytirishning morfologik sathda ifodalanishi borasida turli xil fikrlar mavjud bo'lib, A.N. Kononov kichraytirishni "subyektiv baho beruvchilar" qatoriga kiritib, -choq (-chak, -chiq), -cha, -(a)ch, -i(ch), -gina (-kina, -qina), -on (-in), -jon, -xon, -oy, -qoq (-g'oq, -kak, -gak), -loq, -toy qo'shimchalari subyektiv baho ifodalovchi qo'shimchalar ekanligini ta'kidlaydi. V.V. Reshetov o'zbek tilidagi -cha, -chak, -choq, -gina affikslerini; S. Usmonov -gina (-kina, -qina), -cha, -choq, -chiq, -chak, -loq (-aloq), -qay qo'shimchalarini kichraytirish - erkalash va hurmat formalariga kiritadi.²⁴ O.M. Mo'minov ushbu jabhada o'zbek tilida -gina, -jon, -ka, -kach, -kina, -loq, -oy, -on, -oq, -cha, -chak, -choq suffikslari borligini ko'rsatadi.²⁵ Tilshunos Q. Sapayev kichraytirish shaklini otlarning sintetik shakllaridan biri sifatida qarab, -cha, -choq, chak, -chiq qo'shimchalari kichraytirish shaklini yasashga hizmat qilishini o'z ishlarida yoritib beradilar.²⁶ Bizning fikrimizcha o'zbek tilidagi kichraytirish yasovchi yuqorida keltirilgan qo'shimchalar barcha hollarda ham sof kichraytirish yasamasdan, ba'zan erkalash, suyish, kamsitish ma'nolarini ham yasashlari mumkin. Eng ko'p qo'llaniluvchi ushbu kichraytirish qo'shimchalarini muhokama etsak:

-cha affiksi shaxs va narsalarning kichik ekanligini bildiradi (daftarcha, qushcha, kitobcha, uycha) va asosan kichraytirish ma'nosini ifodalaydi. Ushbu affiks bilan yasalgan kichraytirish shakli yangi leksik ma'no kasb etishi, ya'ni yangi so'zga aylanishi mumkin (sholcha, bog'cha, ko'rpacha, dekcha). Bunda kichraytirish ma'nosi yo'qoladi. Ushbu affiks yoshi va jussasi kichik bo'lgan shaxslarning ismiga qo'shib ham ishlatilishi mumkin. (Qilgan ishingni bilasanmi, Hasakcha, - dedi O'ktam uning yuragini sinamoqchi bo'lib. (H. N))²⁷

-choq, -chak, -chiq affikslari har turli so'zlarga qo'shib kichraytirish, shu bilan birga erkalash ma'nolarini ifodalaydi. (toychoq, qo'zichoq, kelinchak, tugunchak, qopchiq)²⁸

Lug'aviy shakl hosil qiluvchi qo'shimchalar sirasiga kiruvchi kichraytirish ma'nosini yasovchi qo'shimchalar tartibi quyidagicha:

Kichraytirish/erkalash shaklining kam qo'llaniladigan shakli ko'p qo'llaniladiganidan avval keladi: toychoqcha, toyloqcha. Ot-asosiga subyektiv baho: kichraytirish-erkalash, kamsitish, piching-kesatiq qo'shimchalari, keyin ko'plik shakli qo'shiladi: toy+choq+lar.²⁹

Xulosa sifatida aytish mumkinki, tadqiq olib borilayotgan uchta tilda kichraytirish qo'shimchalari mavjud bo'lib, asosan ular so'zlarga kichraytirish va boshqa hollarda erkalash, suyish, kamsitish, kesatish ma'nolarini beradi va bu kontekstdan anglashiladi.

Kichraytirish qo'shimchalarining sonini va turli so'z turkumlariga qo'shilishini quyidagicha xulosalashimiz mumkin:

²⁴ R. Ikramova. O'zbek tilida otlarning sintetik, analitik va funksional formolari. Toshkent. O'zbekiston SSR Fan nashriyoti. 1985. B. 8-10.

²⁵ Samigova X. B. Ingliz va o'zbek tillarida erkalash funksional-semantik maydoni. Filol. Fan. nomz. ...dis. – Toshkent: O'zDJTU, 2010. – 34 b.

²⁶ Hozirgi o'zbek tili/ Q. Sapayev. O'quv qo'llanma. T.: Nizomiy nomidagi TDPU Rizograf, 2009. – B. 120-121.

²⁷ Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili / Shoabdurahmonov Sh., Asqarova M., Hojiyev A., Rasulov I., Doniyorov X. Pedagogika institutlarining filologiya fakulteti studentlari uchun darslik. – T.: O'qituvchi, 1980. – 241 b.

²⁸ Hozirgi o'zbek tili/ Q. Sapayev. O'quv qo'llanma. T.: Nizomiy nomidagi TDPU Rizograf, 2009. – B. 120-121.

²⁹ Hamroyeva Sh. Lug'aviy shakl yasovchi qo'shimchalarning ot so'z turkumidagi qurshovi va lingvistik modellashirish xususida // O'zbek amaliy filologiyasi tibqobllari: Respublika ilmiy amaliy konfrensiyasi materiallari. – Toshkent, ToshDO'TAU, 2022. – 114 b.

- Ingliz tilida 15 ta (-ie, -ette, -let, -ling, -kin, -een, -en, -(e)rel, -et, -o, -a, -s, -er, -poo, -pegs) kichraytirish qo'shimchalari mavjud bo'lib, asosan otlarga, shu bilan bir qatorda sifat va fe'li birikmalarga ham;

- Ispan tilida 10 ta (-ito/a, -illo/a, -ico/a, -uelo/a, -ín/ina, -ino/a, -iño/a, -ajo/a, -ejo/a and -ijo/a) faol kichraytirish qo'shimchalari bor va ular ham asosan otlarga va yana sifat, ravish va sifatdoshlarga;

- O'zbek tilida 7 ta (-gina (-kina, -qina), -cha, -choq, -chiq, -chak, -loq (-aloq), -qay) kichraytirish ma'nosini beruvchi qo'shimchalar bo'lib, deyarli barcha holatlarda otlarga (shaxs ismlariga ham);

O'rganilgan adabiyotlarimizda mikro- (micro-) old qo'shimchasi ingliz tilida kichraytirish qo'shimchasi qatoriga kiritilgan, biroq ispan va o'zbek tillarida ham ushbu qo'shimchani kichraytirish qo'shimchasi sifatida qarashimiz mumkin.

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SHAXS ODOBI VA AXLOQINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA AYOLLARNING O'RNI

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada pedagogika tarixida xotin-qizlarning ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonidagi o'rni va ahamiyati haqida ilmiy asosga ega bo'lgan ma'lumotlar keltirilgan bo'lib, bu ma'lumotlar tarixiy manbalarni hamda adabiyotlarni chuqur o'rganib tahlil qilingan. Barkamol shaxs tarbiyasi va xotin-qizlarning bu boradagi qarashlari haqidagi ilmiy asosga ega bo'lgan ma'lumotlar ushbu maqoladan o'rin olgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *insoniyat tamadduni, milliy qadriyatlar, ayollar ta'limi va tarbiyasi, tarixiy manbalar, savodli odamlarning xo'jaligi, madaniyatli turmushi, adabiy va ilmiy asarlar, qabila rahbariyatidagi oqsoqollar.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье представлены научно обоснованные сведения о роли и значении женщины в образовательном процессе в истории педагогики. В данной статье содержатся научные сведения о роли женщины в обеспечении развития совершенной личности и развития общества.*

Ключевые слова: *человеческая цивилизация, национальные ценности, исторические источники, хозяйство грамотных людей, цивилизованная жизнь, литературные и научные произведения, старейшины во главе племени.*

Annotation: *This article presents scientifically based information about the role and importance of women in the educational process in the history of pedagogy. This article contains scientific information about the role of women in ensuring the development of a perfect personality and the development of society.*

Key words: *human civilization, national values, historical sources, the economy of literate people, civilized life, literary and scientific works, elders in the leadership of the tribe.*

Yurtimizda istiqloq yillarida xotin-qizlarning jamiyat hayotidagi mavqeini yuksaltirish, ularning ijtimoiy-siyosiy islohotlardagi ishtirokini ta'minlash, oila, onalik va bolalikni muhofaza qilish, oila institutini qo'llab-quvvatlash ustuvor vazifaga aylandi.

Bu borada mustahkam huquqiy asoslar yaratildi va amaliyotga izchil yo'naltirildi. hozirgi kunda xotin-qizlarning huquq va erkinliklari, qonuniy manfaatlarini himoya qilish yanada dolzarb ahamiyat kasb etmoqda.

Ayniqsa, ayollarning ijtimoiy iqtisodiy va siyosiy-huquqiy faolligini oshirish davr talabiga aylanmoqda. Shu sababli Bosh qomusimizda belgilangan ayollarning haq-huquqlarini ro'yobga chiqarish, ularning qadr-qimmatini yuksaltirish bo'yicha keng qamrovli ishlar amalga oshirilayotir.

Har qanday jamiyatning asosiy "ko'zgusi" — shubhasiz, bu xotin-qizlardir. Ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, yer yuzi aholisining ellik uch foizini xotin-qizlar tashkil etadi. Shuning uchun ham jahonda gender muammolari tobora dolzarb ahamiyat kasb etmoqda.

Mamlakatimizda esa aholining qariyb 50 foizi xotin-qizlardan iborat.

Ularning barcha huquq va erkinliklari doim qonun himoyasida. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Konstitutsiyasining 46-moddasida ham “Xotin-qizlar va erkaklar teng huquqlidirlar”³⁰, deb belgilab qo‘yilgan.

Davlatning ijtimoiy tuzumi qanday bo‘lishidan qat’iy nazar, undagi aholi turmushining farovonlik darajasi, oilalar barqarorligi, kelajak avlod — farzandlar tarbiyasi, iqtidori, qo‘yingki, barcha jabhalarda erishilgan yutuqlar yurt taraqqiyotiga xotin-qizlarning qo‘shadigan hissasi va o‘sha jamiyatning ayollarga bo‘lgan munosabati bilan belgilanadi.

Bir zamonlar ayollarga nisbatan zaifa, ojiza deb qarashgan. Bu so‘zlar hozir ham onda-sonda uchrab turadi. Fikrimizcha, hech bir davrda ayol ojiza bo‘lmagan va hozir ham bunday emas. Ayolga hurmat va ehtirom ko‘rsatish, uni asrash va ulug‘lash xalqimizning ko‘p ming yillik tarixi davomida shakllangan mentalitetining muhim sifatlaridan biri bo‘lib, turmush tarzimizning o‘ziga xos xususiyati sifatida saqlanib qolmoqda.

Shu bilan birga, ular ijtimoiy-ma’naviy, siyosiy-iqtisodiy hayotning barcha sohalarida samarali va faol mehnat qilib kelyapti. Insonning rivojlanishi va demokratlashishiga doir ustuvor muammolar muqarrar ravishda erkaklar va xotin-qizlar o‘rtasidagi tenglikka erishish bilan bog‘liq masalalarga borib taqaladi. Natijada xotin-qizlar maqomini oshirish va ularning haq-huquqlarini kengaytirish zarurati vujudga keladi. Xususan, o‘tgan besh yilda yurtimizda ayollar huquqlari himoyasini tubdan kuchaytirishga doir bir qator me’yoriy-huquqiy hujjat qabul qilindi. Ayniqsa, 2019 yil 17 avgustda qabul qilingan, senat tomonidan 2019 yil 23 avgustda ma’qullangan (2019 yil 2 sentyabr, O‘RQ-562-son) O‘zbekiston Respublikasining “Xotin-qizlar va erkaklar uchun teng huquq hamda imkoniyatlar kafolatlari to‘g‘risida”gi qonunida davlat xotin-qizlar va erkaklarga shaxsiy, siyosiy, iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy va madaniy huquqlarni amalga oshirish chog‘ida teng huquqlilikni, jamiyat hamda davlat ishlarini boshqarishda, saylov jarayonida teng ishtirok etishni kafolatlashi mustahkamlab qo‘yildi. Bu sa’y-harakatlar ayollarning jamiyat hayotida faolligi orqali o‘z ifodasini topayotgani ham ayni haqiqat.

«Ayol, ayniqsa, uning ma’naviy olami haqida gapirmagan mutafakkir, kuylamagan shoir yo‘q. O‘shalarning aytganlarini o‘z kuzatishlarim bilan qo‘shib biror narsa chiqararman», deb o‘ylagandim. Ayol ma’naviyati haqida yozish naqadar qiyinligi qog‘oz bilan yuzma-yuz qolganda yaqqol bilindi. Chunki eng zo‘r va ta’sirli gaplar aytib qo‘yilgan. O‘tmishdagi faqat o‘z o‘tboshisi (oilasi) emas, balki butun boshli saltanatlar taqdirini o‘zgartirib yuborgan buyuk ayollar haqida ham qayta-qayta yozilgan. Keyin bugun yashayotgan odamlarga hadeb kechadan gapiraverish o‘rinli emasga o‘xshaydi. O‘tmishimiz qanchalar sharafli bo‘lmasin, unga mahliyo bo‘lish, undan faxrlanish bilangina cheklanish odamni olg‘a yurishdan chalg‘itadiganday tuyuladi. Tirik odamning buguni, juda bo‘lmasa, kechagi kuni darajasida bo‘lishi kerak. Buguni kechasidan yorug‘roq bo‘lmagan qavmning ertasi bugunidan nurliroq bo‘lishiga ham ishonish qiyin.

O‘rta Osiyo aholisining ta’lim va tarbiya muammolari qadim zamonlardan boshlab milliy an’analar, ma’naviy asoslar va xulq-atvorning umumbshariy e’tirof etilgan me’yorlar

³⁰ Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2021 йил 5 мартдаги ПҚ-5020-сонли “Хотин-қизларни қўллаб-қувватлаш, уларнинг жамият ҳаётидаги фаол иштирокини таъминлаш тизимини янада такомиллаштириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида” ги Қарори // Ўзбекистон Республикаси қонун ҳужжатлари тўплами, 2021 й.

bilan bog'liq edi. Qadimgi davrlarda, erkak va ayol o'rtasidagi vazifalar taqsimlanishi sari ayol asta-sekin alohida va muhim maqom – o'choq saqlovchisi maqomiga ega bo'ldi. Tarixiy o'lchovning o'rta va dastlabki paleolit davrining oxirida kommunaning birinchi belgilari – qabilaviy jamoalar paydo bo'ldi. Bu ayollar yuqori mavqega ega bo'lgan matriarxal tizim edi³¹. Aynan shu davrda tarbiya va ta'limning dastlabki tashkiliy shakllari, ya'ni maktablar eng qadimiy prototiplari ko'rinishida paydo bo'ldi.

Qadimgi davrlarda O'rta Osiyo hududida yashovchi ajdodlarimizning zardushtiylik vujudga kelgan paytdan boshlab shakllangan pedagogikasi tarixida ayol erkak bilan bir xil mavqega ega bo'lgan va qisman hatto uy tutish va bolalarni tarbiyalashda ba'zi afzalliklar ular tomonga o'tgan. Tarbiya maktabi va qisman ta'lim ham ayol etakchi bo'lgan oiladan kelib chiqqan.

“Avesta”da ayol "rita sia bonu" yoki "asha bonu" deb nomlangan. Sanskrit tilidan tarjima qilingan ushbu so'zlar yorug'lik, haqiqat va sadoqatni anglatadi. “Bonu” so'zi bugungi kunda ham eng yaxshi fazilatlari bilan boshqalardan ajralib turadigan ayol ismlarining qo'shimchasi sifatida ishlatiladi. Masalan, forsiy tilida “kad” so'zi “o'y”, “o'chog” ma'nosini anglatadi. O'choqni muqaddas tutib, o'y-ro'zg'orni mahorat bilan boshqaradigan ayol “kadbonu” deyiladi. Qadim zamonlardan buyon "Bonu" so'zi nur, yorug'lik va vafo sifatida ishlatilgan. “Ona” so'zi ham sanskrit tilida alohida ma'noga ega, u “matri”ga o'xshaydi va “tarbiyachi” degan ma'noni anglatadi. “Savsari” sanskrit tilida opa-singillar ma'nosini ifoda etib bu ham xayrixohlik va muqaddaslikni anglatadi. Shunday qilib, ko'rinib turibdiki, ayollar va xotin-qizlarga munosabat o'zgacha nozik va mukammal bo'lgan va qadimgi davrlardan boshlab ajdodlarimiz ona, ayol tushunchalarini sadoqat va muqaddaslikning ramzi deb hisoblashgan hamda ularga oilada bolalarining tarbiyachisi sifatida muhim maqom berishgan. “Avesta” zamonidagi jamiyatda oila “nmana”, oilaning eng katta ayoli “nmanapatni”, ya'ni uyning bekasi maqomiga ega bo'lgan³². Ma'lumki, ayolni e'zozlash, unga ehtirom ko'rsatish o'zbek xalqiga xos olijanob xususiyatlardan biri sifatida qarab kelingan.

O'zbek millatining o'ziga xos ma'naviyatini shakllantirish va yuksaltirishda, oilaning, oilada esa ayolning o'rni va ta'siri beqiyosdir.

Ayollar – qadimgi ajdodlarimiz katta shajarada yashab, nafaqat oila, farzandlarini, balki ko'rsatmalarini qonun deb bilgan kekxa ota-onalarni ham parvarish qilishgan. Aynan antik davrda paydo bo'lgan “kadbonu” so'zi uy bekasining ma'nosini har jihatdan - uy sharoitida, eng muhim masalalarni hal qilish, farzandlarni tarbiyalash va o'choqni himoya qilish kabi ma'nolarga ega edi.

O'rta Osiyo xalqlari pedagogikasi tarixi uzoq o'tmishda yaxlit bir butunlikka qo'shilib ketgan qo'shni mamlakatlar tarixi bilan chambarchas bog'liq holda rivojlanish bosqichlarini o'tdi. Qadimgi davrlarda O'rta Osiyo mamlakatlaridagi barcha ayollarning tarbiyasi va ta'limi erkaklarning ta'limidan deyarli hech qanday farq qilmas edi. Hamma bilan birgalikda oilada boshlang'ich ta'lim olish, keyin maktab (“Dabiston”³³) va oliy maktab

³¹ Аминова Л.Я. История женского образования в Башкирии. Вторая половина XIX – начало XX века: Монография, – Уфа: РИО РУНМЦ МО РБ, 2005. – 186 б

³² Махди Икболий Занон дар торихи кухани Ирон. Махдиобод, Пардисон, 2004.

³³ Лившиц В.А. Согдийская эпиграфика Средней Азии и Семиречья. – СПб., 2008. – 414 б.

(“Dabiriston”)da o‘qish an‘analari ayollarning jamiyatning to‘laqonli a‘zolari sifatidagi huquqlarini buzmagani.

O‘rta Osiyo xalqlari tarixidagi eng muhim tarixiy yodgorlik, zardushtiylikning diniy kitobi “Avesta” va Zaratushtra ta‘limotini tahlil qilish asosida, ayollarning insoniyat tarbiyasi va shakllanishida qanday rol o‘ynaganligini anglash mumkin. Alohida ta‘kidlash joizki, ushbu dinda ayollarga alohida ustunlik berilgan.

Ma‘lumki, O‘rta Osiyo aholisining ta‘lim va tarbiya muammolari qadim zamonlardan boshlab milliy an‘analar, ma‘naviy asoslar va xulq-atvorning umumbshariy e‘tirof etilgan me‘yorlari bilan bog‘liq edi. Qadimgi davrlarda, erkak va ayol o‘rtasidagi vazifalar taqsimlanishi sari ayol asta-sekin alohida va muhim maqom - o‘choq saqlovchisi maqomiga ega bo‘ldi. Aynan shu davrda tarbiya va ta‘limning dastlabki tashkiliy shakllari, ya‘ni maktablarning eng qadimiy prototiplari ko‘rinishida paydo bo‘ldi.

Prezidentimiz ta‘kidlaganidek, “Zamonaviy bilim va iste‘dodga, etakchilik qobiliyatiga ega, el-yurtimiz uchun fidoyi xotin-qizlarimiz — xalqimiz, millatimizning oltin fondi, desak, hech qanday mubolag‘a bo‘lmaydi”³⁴.

Shu o‘rinda savol tug‘iladi, bugungi o‘zbek ayoli kim: boshqaruvchimi yo bo‘ysunuvchi, ergashuvchimi yo ergashtiruvchi? Zamonaviy o‘zbek ayoli portretini qanday chizgilar bilan boyitish mumkin? Albatta, yorqin va ishonchli ranglar, qat‘iyatli fazilatlar bilan.

Bugunning ayoli — yangi O‘zbekistonni keng imkoniyatlar va amaliy ishlar mamlakatiga aylantirishga shay turgan, o‘z so‘zi va ovozigaga ega vatandoshimizdir. U endi ortga qaytmaydi, balki rivojlanishni ortga surganni o‘z izmidan ergashtira oladigan, haq yo‘ldan borayotganligimizga inontira oladigan kuchdir³⁵.

Har tomonlama faol va oqila, dono, izlanuvchan, zamonaviy ayol mehnatidan, salohiyatidan nafaqat uning oilasi, balki butun jamiyat manfaatdor bo‘lishi ayni haqiqatdir. Zero, biz qurayotgan Yangi O‘zbekistonning yukini dadil ko‘tarib, uning poydevorini mustahkamlab turadigan asosiy kuch — jamiyatimizdagi har bir oila, har bir inson, har bir fuqaro, shu jumladan, xotin-qizlar ekanligini unutmasligimiz lozim.

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³⁵ Саидова Б. Н. Аёллар таълимини қўллаб-қувватлашда маърифатпарвар аёллар ўрни //Современное образование (Узбекистан). – 2021. – №. 1 (98). – С. 12-17.

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KALKULYATORLAR HAQIDA IKKI OG'IZ

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Annotasiya: *Ushbu maqolada matematika, fizika, kimyo va boshqa fanlarda va hayotda hisoblashni tezlashtiruvchi kalkulyatorlar haqida va ulardan foydalanish va ularsiz ham hisob-kitoblarni bajarish usullari keltirilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *logarifm, Bradis jadvallari, mantissa, antilogarifm shkala, standart Accessories, Fuller spirali.*

Kalkulyatorlar matematikani o'rgatmaydi, lekin ayrim hisob-kitoblarni yaxshiroq tushunishda, yoki, hisoblashlarni tezroq bajarishda ko'mak beradi. Ularning ayniqsa katta sonlar bilan ishlashdagi amaliy ahamiyatini inkor etib bo'lmaydi. Biroq, kalkulyator bilan hisoblash va miyani ishlatib qo'lda hisoblash qo'llaniladigan matematik uslublar o'rtasida katta farq bor...

Aytaylik, bizga 183 sonining 5 darajali ildizini, ya'ni, $\sqrt[5]{183}$ ni chiqarish kerak. Quyida, ushbu nisbatan sodda matematik amalni ikki xil yo'l bilan hisoblab chiqish usullarini ko'rsatamiz. Birinchisida – maktabda olingan matematik bilimlar asosida, o'qituvchilarimiz aytganidek, «miyani ishlatib», qog'oz va qalam vositasida hisoblaymiz. Ikkinchisida esa, cho'ntak kalkulyatoridan foydalanib, xuddi bozordagi savdogarlar singari hisoblaymiz (lekin bozorda hecham $\sqrt[5]{183}$ ni hisoblashga to'g'ri kelmasa kerak).

1-usul:

Amalning natijasini A bilan belgilaymiz, ya'ni, $A = \sqrt[5]{183}$. Tenglikning har ikkala qismining logarifmini aniqlaymiz. $\log A = \log \sqrt[5]{183}$.

Qidirilayotgan sonning daraja ko'rsatkichini kasr ko'rinishida ifodalaymiz. $\sqrt[5]{183} = (183)^{1/5}$

Qoidaga ko'ra, darajaning logarifmi, daraja ko'rsatkichi va uning asosning logarifmining ko'paytmasiga teng. Shunga ko'ra: $\log A = 1/5 \times \log(183)$

Endi logarifmik jadvaldan foydalanish kerak bo'ldi. Balki aynan shu bosqich hozirda eng qiyini bo'lsa kerak. Chunki, yaqin yillarda logarifmik jadvallarni topish biroz mushkul bo'lib qoldi. Ilgarilari «Bradis jadvallari» nomi ostida chop etilgan, logarifmlar-antilogarifmlar, sinuslar-kosinuslar, ifodalangan jadvallardan foydalanilardi. Hozirda ham bunday jadvallarni kutubxonalardan izlab topish mumkin. Gap uch xonali son haqida borayotgani sababli, izlanayotgan logarifmning butun qismi 2 ga teng bo'lishi aniq. Mantissani hisoblash uchun esa, logarifmlar jadvalidan foydalanamiz u orqali kasr qismini qidirib topamiz. Biz o'ta aniqlik talab etuvchi astronomik hisob-kitoblarni bajarmayapmiz, shunchaki, matematik misol yechayapmiz. Shu sababli, bizga kasrning verguldan keyingi uch xonasini aniqlasak ham kifoya qiladi. Jadvalda bizga zarur raqamlar «3» - ustunining 18-satrida joylashgan. Unda 2625 raqamini ko'rish mumkin:

O'nli Logarifmlarning mantissalari										Kasr qismlari									
N	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
15	1761	1790	1818	1847	1875	1903	1931	1959	1987	2014	3	6	8	11	14	17	20	22	25
16	2041	2068	2095	2122	2148	2175	2201	2227	2253	2279	3	5	8	11	13	16	18	21	24
17	2304	2330	2355	2380	2405	2430	2455	2480	2504	2529	2	5	7	10	12	15	17	20	22
18	2553	2577	2601	2625	2648	2672	2695	2718	2742	2765	2	5	7	9	12	14	16	19	21
25	3979	3997	4014	4031	4048	4065	4082	4099	4116	4133	2	3	5	7	9	10	12	14	15
26	4150	4166	4183	4200	4216	4232	4249	4265	4281	4298	2	3	5	7	8	10	11	13	15
27	4314	4330	4346	4362	4378	4393	4409	4425	4440	4456	2	3	5	6	8	9	11	13	14
28	4472	4487	4502	4518	4533	4548	4564	4579	4594	4609	2	3	5	6	8	9	11	12	14
29	4624	4639	4654	4669	4683	4698	4713	4728	4742	4757	1	3	4	6	7	9	10	12	13

Demak, $\log(183)=2,2625$

Endi, eng avvalgi tenglamaga qaytamiz va talab etilayotgan amalni bajaramiz:

$$\log A = \frac{1}{5} \log(183) = \frac{1}{5} (2,2625) = 0,4525$$

Biz qidirilayotgan A sonining logarifmini topdik. Endi, ushbu sonni o'zini topish uchun, 0,4525 sonining antilogarifmini topishimiz kerak. Buning uchun bizga antilogarifmlar jadvali kerak bo'ldi. Buning uchun, 0,4525 ni antilogarifmlar jadvalidan qidiramiz. Antilogarifmlar jadvalining 4525 ni topilmadi. Endi biz unga eng yaqin keladigan sonni izlashimiz lozim. Jadvalning 28-satr, 3-ustunida 4525 ga eng yaqin son 4518 ko'rsatilgan. U biz qidirayotgan qiymatdan 7 ga kam. Shuning uchun, o'ng tarafdagi kasr qismlar jadvalidan 7 ni izlaymiz. U yerda ham 7 yo'q va unga eng yaqin sonni olishga majbur bo'lamiz (bu darajadagi aniqlik oddiy matematik misol uchun yetarli bo'ldi). Bu 6 soni. Ushbu son joylashgan ustun raqami, bizning sonimizning verguldan keyingi uchinchi xonadagi soni bo'ldi. Demak, izlayotgan son $A=2,834$.

Ko'rib turganingizdek, qog'oz va qalam vositasida hisoblash anchayin matematik mulohazani va muayyan jadvallardan foydalana olish tajribasini talab etadi. Shuningdek, hisoblash uchun sarflangan vaqtni ham inobatga olib qo'yish darkor. Endi xuddi shu hisoblashni kalkulyator vositasida bajaramiz.

2-usul:

Buning uchun muhandislik kalkulyatorini qoʻlga olib, tugmalarni quyidagi ketma-ketlikda bosish kifoya qiladi.

Muqobil variantlar bormi?

Biz ikki xil usulni oʻzaro taqqoslash uchun keltirgan misol – juda oddiy arifmetik misollar turkumiga kiradi. Unda shunchaki bir sonning ildizini topish talab etilmoqda. Biz ataylab 5 darajali ildizni misol qilib keltirdik.

Chunki, kvadrat ildizdan farqli oʻlaroq, beshinchi darajali ildiz uchun hisoblash algoritmi mavjud emas. Albatta, kalkulyatorning afzalliklarini yanada aniq va inkor etib boʻlmas tarzda koʻrsatib beradigan murakkabroq misollarni ham koʻplab keltirish mumkin.

Albatta, hisob-kitoblarni kalkulyatorlardan foydalanib bajarishning foyda-zarari toʻgʻrisida oʻrta maktablardan boshlab, kollej va oliy oʻquv yurtlarigacha boʻlgan bosqichlarda ham oʻquvchi-talabalar, ham ustoz-murabbiylar oʻrtasida turli bahs-munozaralar ancha yillardan buyon davom etmoqda. Albatta bu borada har kimning oʻziga maqbul koʻrinadigan shaxsiy fikri boʻlgani muhim.

Bir tarafdin olib qaralsa, oddiy kalkulyator vositasida sanoqli soniyalarda bajarish mumkin boʻlgan hisob-kitob uchun koʻp daqiqa sarflab vaqt ketkazish ham oʻrinli emas. Biroq, texnika vositasida bajarilayotgan hisob-kitobning asl mohiyatini anglab yetmasdan, shunchaki tugmalarni bosib natijaga erishishni ham sogʻlom aql maʼqullamaydi. Chunki bu ishni robot ham bajarishi mumkin.

Hisob-kitob uslubini, aytaylik, logarifmni hisoblash ketma-ketligini (algoritmini) oʻrganish, bilish, tushunishning oʻzi bir narsa; koʻndalang turgan masalani hal qilish uchun oʻsha algoritmdan foydalanish kerakligini ongli ravishda tushunib yetish va algoritmni amaliy qoʻllay olish – boshqa narsa.

Masalan, olim Neper logarifmlarni oʻylab topgan vaqtda, uning maqsadi, matematik mutaxassislarning murakkab daraja koʻrsatkichlariga ega hisob-kitoblarga sarflayotgan vaqtlarini qisqartirish boʻlgan. Chunki, matematiklar koʻp vaqtlarini mayda-chuyda hisob-kitoblarga sarflab, oqibatda yanada muhimroq ishlari uchun ulgurmay qolish holatlari koʻp kuzatilgan.

Aytaylik, biror yirik matematik olim muhim bir kashfiyotni amalga oshirishi mumkin boʻlgan, yoki, yangi bir ilmiy nazariyani mulohaza qilishi uchun sarflashi mumkin boʻlgan qimmatli vaqtini, shunchaki qogʻoz- qalam ustida, uzundan-uzoq arifmetik amallarni bajarish bilan sarflab yuborardi.

Oʻsha zamonlarda, Neper taklif qilgan logarifmlardan foydalanish orqali, matematiklar hisoblash tezligini birmuncha oshirib olib, yanada koʻproq ilmiy ishlarga ulgura boshlashgan. Bu haqida olimlar orasida hatto «Neper astronomlarining umrini uzaytirdi» qabilidagi yarim hazil, yarim chin mutoyiba ham ommalashgan edi.

Keyinchalik, hisob-kitoblarga sarflanayotgan vaqtni tejashga moʻljallangan yan bir necha vositalar paydo boʻldi. Ular qatorida birinchi boʻlib logarifmik jadvallar, logarifmik chizgʻichlarni misol qilib keltirish mumkin.

Avvaliga olimlar muayyan qiymatlarning logarifmini tezkor aniqlash uchun maxsus jadvallar tuzib chiqib chop etishdi va bu narsa juda tez ommalashdi. Keyinchalik esa, ma'lum chegarada bo'lsa-da, harholda uncha-muncha sonning logarifmini tez va oson topish imkonini beruvchi logarifmik chizg'ichlar va maxsus logarifmik uskunalar paydo bo'la boshladi.

Xususan, 1878 yilda ingliz muhandisi Fuller logarifmik shkalani spiral shaklida o'rab chiqish orqali, «Fuller spirali» deb nomlangan, logarifmlarni oson va tez topish imkonini beradigan uskuna ixtiro qildi.

Hisoblash va fikrlash...

Bu boradagi zamonaviy bahslarga qaytadigan bo'lsak, albatta, ko'plab ustozlarning, ta'lim jarayonida kalkulyatordan foydalanish o'quvchining mantiqiy fikrlashiga to'sqinlik qilishi haqidagi xavotirlari mutlaqo o'rinli. Yuqorida ham aytilganidek, hisoblashlarda shunchaki vaqt tejash, yoki, xatolik ehtimolini kamaytirish uchun kalkulyatordan foydalanish – bu muhim va kerakli narsa. Lekin, o'sha hisoblashlarning mohiyatni anglash, ketma-ketlik qoidalarini bilish va kombinatsiyalarni to'g'ri bajara olish uchun, avvalo bajarilayotgan amallarning nazariy asosini yaxshi bilish lozim bo'ladi. Bunday ko'nikma va tajribani esa, an'anaviy usulda, ya'ni, qog'oz va qalam vositasida bajarilgan muttasil mashqlarsiz hosil qilib bo'lmaydi. Bunday ko'nikmalarga ega bo'lmagan shaxs, o'sha amallarni kalkulyatorda bo'lsa ham qanday hisoblash kerakligini tushunmaydi va bilmaydi.

Axir, matematik hisoblashni texnika vositasida hal qilish uchun ham, bajarilishi kerak bo'lgan amallar tartibini bilish, qisqa qilib aytganda, algoritmni mantiqan tasavvur qila olish zarur. Barcha matematik amallar, yoki, ularning eng asosiylari bo'lganlarini mantiqiy mulohazalar orqali qo'lda, qog'ozga tushirib yecha olishni mukammal o'zlashtirgandan so'ng, keyinchalik vaqt tejash va xatolik ehtimolini kamaytirish uchun kalkulyatordan foydalanish maqsadga muvofiq nazirimda.

Agar, ta'lim jarayonida kalkulyatordan foydalanishning afzalliklari yoki, salbiy jihatlari haqidagi bahs – yoshlarning intellektual salohiyatiga to'g'ridan-to'g'ri ta'sir omiliga ega ekanini inobatga olsak, bu narsaga mas'uliyat bilan yondoshish naqadar muhimligi ayonlashadi. Zero, mantiqiy mulohaza qobiliyati, kishining intellektual salohiyatini ko'p jihatdan belgilovchi omildir. Mantiqiy mulohaza qobiliyatini shakllantirish va rivojlantirishda esa matematika shubhasiz markaziy o'rin tutadi.

Ta'limdagi ta'siri haqidagi bahsni bas qilib, kalkulyatorlarning boshqa sohalardagi o'rni haqida fikr yuritsak, albatta ko'plab ijobiy jihatlarni tushunib yetishimiz mumkin. Xususan, juda kichik, yoki, juda katta miqdorlar bilan ishlashni talab qiluvchi sohalarda, ilmiy laboratoriyalarda, murakkab trigonometrik amallarni taqozo qiladigan ishlarda bugungi kunda kalkulyatorsiz uzoqqa borib bo'lmaydi. Ayniqsa, muhandislikning loyiha-konstruktorlik yo'nalishlarida, astronomik hisob-kitoblarda, kimyo laboratoriyalarida, geologiyada, qo'yingki barcha amaliy sohalarda kalkulyator – ish stolining, yoki, operativ portfelning ajralmas qismiga aylanib qolgan. Bozorlardagi sotuvchilarniku – qo'yaverasiz. Buxgalteriya, moliya-bank sohasi xodimlari ham, o'z ishlarida kalkulyatorlardan muntazam foydalanadilar. Lo'ndasini aytganda, ushbu texnika vositasi bugungi kunda eng ko'p

ishlatiladigan texnikalardan biri sifatida o'zining ham ilmiy, ham amaliy ahamiyatini allaqachon mustahkamlab olgan.

Umuman qilib esa, kalkulyatorlarning ikki turi tasniflanadi. Ya'ni, standart kalkulyator va muhandislik kalkulyatori. Standart kalkulyator masalan, savdo muassasalari uchun kifoya qiladigan, ya'ni, asosiy to'rt arifmetik amal: +, -, × va ÷ amallarini bajarish uchun mo'ljallangan va ildiz chiqarish («√»), natijani xotirada ushlab turish («MR») kabi yana boshqa ayrim kichik funksiyalarni o'z ichiga olgan oddiy kalkulyatorlardir. Kundalik turmushda aynan shu turdagi kalkulyatorlar juda keng tarqalgan. Muhandislik kalkulyatorlari esa, asosiy to'rt arifmetik amaldan tashqari, shuningdek, deyarli boshqa barcha amallarni, xususan, integral, binom, eksponenta, trigonometrik funksiyalar, logarifmlar, radian va ho kazolarni ham hisoblash imkonini beradi. Standart kalkulyator va muhandislik kalkulyatorini farqlab olish ham juda oson. Muhandislik kalkulyatorida tugmalar soni juda ko'p bo'ladi va ularning yarmidan ko'pi, maxsus tugmalar bo'lib, mutaxassis bo'lmagan shaxslar uchun tushunarsiz bo'lishi tabiiy. Qolaversa, muhandislik kalkulyatorida «Scientific calculator» yozuvi tushirilgan yorliq mavjud bo'ladi:

Standart kalkulyator (chapda) va muhandislik kalkulyatori (o'ngda)

Standart va muhandislik kalkulyatoridan tashqari, yana shuningdek, dasturchilar uchun maxsus kalkulyatorlar ham mavjud bo'lib, bu turdagi kalkulyator turli sanoq tizimlari orasida amallarni bajarish, mantiqiy funksiyalarni ishlash kabi qo'shimcha qulayliklarga ega. Biroq, dasturchilar 99,99% holatda faqat kompyuterdan foydalanib ishlaganliklari bois, odatda dasturchilik kalkulyatorlari alohida ishlab chiqarilmaydi va kompyuter dasturi sifatida tarqatiladi xolos.

Modomiki, gapimizga shu nuqtada kompyuterlar va dasturchilar ham aralashgan ekan, adolat yuzasida, deyarli kompyuterlarda operatsion tizimlarning uzviy qismi sifatida uchraydigan kalkulyator dasturi haqida ham to'xtalib o'tish joiz. Operatsion tizim tarkibidagi kalkulyator inglizcha sistemada «Start» menyusining «Accessories» bo'limida, ruscha tizimda esa «Пуск» menyusining «Стандартные» bo'limida bo'ladi. Shuningdek, operatsion tizim kalkulyatorini buyruqlar qatorida calc.exe buyrug'ini berib ham chaqirish

mumkin. Operatsion tizim kalkulyatori chaqirilganda avvaliga standart kalkulyator namoyon bo'ladi. Uning menyusi orqali muhandislik kalkulyatoriga o'zgartirish mumkin. Windows 10 operatsion tizimida standart, muhandislik va dasturchilik kalkulyatorlari quyidagicha ko'rinishga ega:

Biroq, Windows tizimidagi har uchala xil kalkulyatorni qo'llashda e'tibor qaratish lozim bo'lgan muhim bir jihat mavjud. Masalan, $4+7 \times 8$ amalini Windowsning standart kalkulyatorida bajarsangiz, natija 88 chiqadi. Vaholanki bu noto'g'ri!!! Xuddi shu hisoblashni muhandislik kalkulyatorida bajarilsa, natija 60 chiqadi va shu to'g'ri natijadir. Ziyrak mutolaachi tushungan bo'lsa kerak, bu yerda amallar tartibi hamma narsani hal qilmoqda. Standart kalkulyatorga bir necha amal ketma-ket kiritilganda, u amallarni qanday bo'lsa, shunday ketma-ketlikda bajaradi. Shu sababli, Windowsning standart kalkulyatorida qo'shish va ko'paytirish, bo'lish va ayirish amallarini bir vaqtni o'zida kiritib yechishga urinish noto'g'ri yechimga olib keladi. Lekin, muhandislik kalkulyatorida amallarni istalgan ketma-ketlikda kiritish mumkin. Kalkulyator amallar tartibini o'zi to'g'rilab oladi va hammasini qoidaga binoan yechib beradi.

Agar muhandislik kalkulyatorida murakkab amallarni bajarilishi natijasida juda katta son chiqsa, unda ekranda EXP ramzi, yoki, eharfi chiqib qolishi mumkin. Bu, joriy hisoblashda muhandislik notatsiyasi qo'llanayotganidan darak bo'ladi. Bunday holda, natija o'nli kasr, yoki, sonning o'n darajasiga ko'paytmasi tarzida ifodalanayotgan bo'ladi. Masalan:

$$2,1 \text{ EXP } 7 = 210000000$$

$$5,6 \text{ EXP } (-)4 = 0,00056$$

Agar, $38!$ faktorialni hisoblamoqchi bo'lsangiz, unda Windows operatsion tizimidagi muhandislik kalkulyatorida $5,2302261746660111176000722410007e+44$ natijasi namoyon bo'ladi. Bu degani, ko'rsatilgan sonning 10^{44} ga ko'paytmasi deganidir.

Muhandislik kalkulyatorning oddiy cho'ntak yoki, ish stoli variantlarida ham, shuningdek, kompyuterdagi muhandislik kalkulyatorida ham hisoblashlarni bajarishda, murakkab matematik amallarni yuklashda shoshqaloqlik qilmaslik kerak. Chunki, noto'g'ri

berilgan buyruqlar natijasida kalkulyator «osilib» qolishi, ya'ni, qotib qolishi, yoki, hatto ishdan chiqish ham mumkin.

Qanday kalkulyatorni tanlagan ma'qul?

Bugungi kunda kalkulyatorlar allaqachon smartfonlarning ilovasiga va kompyuterlarga «ko'chib o'ta» boshlashgan. Ilgarilari hisob-kitob uchun shaqillatib cho't ishlatgan do'kondorlar, keyinchalik kalkulyator tugmalariga bosishga o'tishgan bo'lsa, endi osongina, smartfonlaridagi dasturdan foydalanib qo'ya qolishmoqda. Buxgalteriya sohasida ham, ilmiy yo'nalishlarda ham shunga o'xshash tendensiyani kuzatish mumkin. Bu sohalarda allaqachon maxsus kompyuter dasturlari, hech bo'lmaganda esa, MS EXCELL dasturi, oddiy kalkulyatorga bo'lgan ehtiyojni butunlay bo'lmasada, harholda biroz chetroqqa surib qo'yib bo'ldi nazarimda.

Biroq, shunga qaramay, oddiy cho'ntak kalkulyatori, yoki, ish stoli kalkulyatorlarini hali hanuz do'konlar peshtaxtalarida uchratish mumkinligi, ushbu texnika vositasini nafaqaga chiqarishga hali shoshmaslik zarurligiga ishora bermoqda.

Qanday kalkulyatorni sotib olish esa, albatta unchalik qiyin bo'lmagan tanlov. Agar sizga faqat savdodagi hisob-kitoblar, yoki, moliya-buxgalteriya amaliyoti uchun hisob-kitoblarni bajarish zarur bo'lsa, standart kalkulyator kifoya qiladi.

Biroq, sizga muhandislik kalkulyatori zarur bo'lsa, tanlovda biroz shoshmasdan xarid qilganingiz ma'qul. Hozirda muhandislik kalkulyatorlarning hatto turli funksiyalarning grafiklarini ham chizib bera oladigan darajadagi mukammallari mavjud. Bunday kalkulyatorlar grafikali muhandislik kalkulyatori deb ataladi va odatda boshqalarga nisbatan ancha katta ekranga ega bo'ladi.

Ularning hisoblash tezligi ham oddiy muhandislik kalkulyatorlaridan bir sezilarli darajada yuqori bo'lib, narxi ham ancha qimmat turadi. Bunday kalkulyatorlar ayniqsa oliy matematika kurslarida matematik analiz bo'yicha grafiklarni yasashda juda qulayliklar tug'dirishi bilan, matematika yo'nalishi talabalarining ovunchog'iga aylangan.

Bunday kalkulyatorlar orqali, qog'oz va qalam bilan ishlab, bir necha soat vaqt oladigan va bir necha sahifa varoqni band qiladigan funksiya grafiklarini, bir necha daqiqa ichida yasash mumkin. Boz ustiga, funksiya grafiklarining ekrandagi tasviri, uni qo'lda chizgandagidan ko'ra aniqroq darajada namoyon bo'ladi.

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BO'LAJAK BOSHLANG'ICH SINIF O'QITUVCHILARINING KITOBXONLIK MADANIYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISH PEDAGOGIK ZARURAT SIFATIDA

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Anontatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada bo'lajak boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilarining kitobxonlik madaniyatini rivojlantirishning pedagogik jihatlari, ularni kitobxonlikka undash masalalari qonunlar va mutafakkirlarning fikrlari asosida muhokama etiladi. Bo'lajak o'qituvchilarda kitobxonlikning zarurligi xususida fikrlar keltirilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *o'qituvchi, boshlang'ich ta'lim, pedagogika, zaruriyat, usul, rivojlantirish, ahamiyat, kitobxonlik, tarbiya, madaniyat, psixologiya, metod.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье на основе закономерностей и мнений мыслителей рассматриваются педагогические аспекты развития культуры чтения будущих учителей начальной школы, вопросы поощрения их к чтению. Приводятся мнения о необходимости чтения для будущих учителей начальных классов.*

Ключевые слова: *учитель, начальное образование, педагогика, необходимость, метод, развитие, значение, чтение, воспитание, культура, психология, метод.*

Annotation: *In this article, the pedagogical aspects of developing the reading culture of future elementary school teachers, the issues of encouraging them to read are discussed on the basis of laws and opinions of thinkers. Opinions about the necessity of reading for future teachers are given.*

Key words: *teacher, primary education, pedagogy, necessity, method, development, importance, reading, education, culture, psychology, method.*

Bugungi kunda mamlakatimizda 2017-2021-yillarda O'zbekiston Respublikasini rivojlantirishning beshta ustuvor yo'nalishi bo'yicha Harakatlar strategiyasida belgilangan oliy maqsad -mamlakatimiz taraqqiyotini yanada yuksak bosqichga ko'tarish yo'lida barcha soha va tarmoqlarda ulkan o'zgarishlar amalga oshirilmoqda.

Shu nuqtayi nazardan yosh avlodning, o'quvchi va o'quvchilarning g'oyaviy-mafkuraviy jihatdan mukammal tarbiyalanishi ayni maqsadga muvofiq hodisa sifatida jamiyat a'zolarining diqqat markazida turuvchi dolzarb masaladir.

Jamiyat hayotida ezgu qadriyat va an'analarni chuqur qaror toptirishda, xususan, xalqimiz, ayniqsa, yosh avlodning ma'naviy-intellektual salohiyati, ong-u tafakkuri va dunyoqarashini yuksaltirishda, ona vatani va xalqiga muhabbat va sadoqat tuyg'usi bilan yashaydigan barkamol shaxsni tarbiyalashda beqiyos

ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan omillar bir qancha bo'lib, shulardan eng muhimi -bu kitobxonlik madaniyatini oshirishga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda.

Mazkur yo'nalishda tashkiliy-amaliy ishlarni olib borish va ularni zamon talablariga mos tarzda yo'lga qo'yish bo'yicha tegishli huquqiy-me'yoriy hujjatlar bazasi yaratilgan.

Xususan, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining bu sohada ijobiy o'zgarishlar, tub islohotlar amalga oshirishga qaratilgan 2006 -yil 20-iyuldagi "Respublika aholisini axborot-kutubxona bilan ta'minlashni tashkil etish to'g'risida"gi qarori, 2011-yil 13-apreldagi "Axborot-kutubxona to'g'risida"gi Qonuni, 2017-yil 12-yanvardagi «Kitob mahsulotlarini chop etish va tarqatish tizimini rivojlantirish, kitob mutolaasi va kitobxonlik madaniyatini oshirish hamda targ'ibot qilish bo'yicha komissiya tuzish to'g'risida»gi Farmoyishi, 2017 -yil 13-sentabrdagi "Kitob mahsulotlarini nashr etish va tarqatish tizimini rivojlantirish, kitob mutolaasi va kitobxonlik madaniyatini oshirish hamda targ'ibot qilish bo'yicha Kompleks chora-tadbirlar dasturi to'g'risida"gi Qarori asosida yurtimizda keng ko'lamlı ishlar olib borilmoqda.

Mazkur qonun va qonunosti hujjatlarda belgilangan vazifalar ijrosini ta'minlash yuzasidan hududlarda Axborot-resurs markazlari faoliyati zamon talablariga mos isloh qilindi, yangi kitob savdo do'konlari faoliyati yo'lga qo'yildi hamda aholiga xizmat ko'rsatish sifat jihatidan ancha takomillashtirildi.

Kitobsevarlar o'rtasida o'tkaziladigan ko'rik-tanlovlar respublika miqyosida ommalashtirildi va shaxsan davlatimiz rahbari tomonidan rag'batlantiruvchi sovrinlar belgilandi. Yoshlarning kitob o'qishga ishtiyoqi ortdi.

Xalqimiz turmush tajribasidan ma'lumki, ajdodlarimiz farzand tarbiyasida kitob mutolaasiga alohida e'tibor qaratishgan. Buyuk Navoiy-u Bobur, Amir Temur-u Ulug'bek kabi alloma-yu ijodkorlarimiz, tojdor-u daholarimiz ma'naviyati bolalikdan kitobga mehr qo'yish bilan shakllangan. Ajdodlarimiz xalq ertaklari-yu dostonlarini tinglab tasavvur va tafakkur dunyosini, ruhiyat olamini boyitishgan. Adabiyot durdonalari -xoh xalq og'zaki ijodi namunalari, xoh yozma asarlar bo'lsin - xalqimiz qalbida yurtiga, ona tiliga, oilasiga, vatandoshlariga mehr-muhabbat va sadoqat, milliy g'urur, or-nomus, adolat-u insof, andisha-yu hurmat, oliyanoblig-u saxovatpeshalik sifatleri shakllanishida asosiy vosita bo'lib xizmat qilgan.

Bunday ma'naviyat durdonalari mutolaa qilingan, tinglangan, eng muhimi, oila davrasida yoki jamoat ichida muhokama qilingan, bahs-u tortishuvlar asosida asarlar mazmun-mohiyati anglangan, anglatilgan. Ahamiyatlisi shundaki, yosh-u qari birday qiziqish bilan ishtirok etadigan bunday davralarda mushohada qilish va mulohaza yuritish, mantiqiy fikrlash qobiliyati, keng dunyoqarash va tafakkur shakllangan, e'tiqod va iroda mustahkamlangan, notiqlik mahorati o'sgan, kishilar ongi ham ma'nan, ham ruhan, ham ilman boyib borgan.

Oliy ta'lim muassassasi hamda kutubxonalari oldiga quyidagi vazifalarni yechish mas'uliyati qo'yilgan:

- o'quvchilarning kitob bilan o'zaro aloqasini mustahkamlab, ularni kitob o'qishga qiziqtirish,

- ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonida kitob va boshqa axborot manbalaridan foydalanishga keng imkoniyat yaratish;

- o'quvchini badiiy adabiyotga qiziqtirish, kitob o'qishga bo'lgan ehtiyojini kuchaytirish, uni mustaqil o'qishga o'rgatish, badiiy adabiyot orqali o'quvchilarda badiiy-estetik didni shakllantirishga alohida e'tibor qaratish;

- o'quvchilarda izchil tarzda kitobxonlik madaniyatini shakllantirish; - o'quvchilarning kitobni mustaqil mutolaa qilib, uni ijodiy o'zlashtirishga odatlantirish;

- o'quvchilarda kitob bilan muloqotga kirishish ko'nikmalarini qaror toptirish;

- o'quvchilarda kitobxonlik madaniyatini shakllantirishda ilg'or axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish.

Yoshlarning axloqiy rivojlanishi, ularni insonparvarlik ruhida tarbiyalash masalasiga O'zbekistonda katta e'tibor qaratilgan. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh.M.Mirziyoyev tomonidan taklif etilgan mamlakatimizni rivojlantirish va uning mustaqilligini mustahkamlashning strategik vazifalarida ma'nan yetuk, barkamol avlodni va raqobatbardosh kadrlarni tayyorlash hamda ijtimoiy vazifalarni hal etishda jamiyatga yordam ko'rsata oladigan ko'ngilli, milliy g'urur hissi ustun bo'lgan yoshlarni tarbiyalash muhim vazifalardan biri sifatida belgilab berilgan. Bu vazifalarni amalga oshirishda "biz asrlar mobaynida shakllangan milliy an'analarimizga, ajdodlarimizning boy merosiga tayanamiz" [1] va o'sib kelayotgan yosh avlodni Sharqona tarbiya asosiga qurilgan umuminsoniy qadriyatlar ruhida tarbiyalash jamiyat oldiga ulkan mas'uliyat yuklamoqda.

O'quvchi yoshlar orasida kitobxonlik madaniyatini targ'ib qilish ko'pgina zararli illatlarni oldini olishga sabab bo'ladi.

Professor Sh.Xalilova shaxsda kitobxonlik madaniyatini shakllantirishning uch muhim komponenti bor ekanligini ta'kidlab o'tgan [2]:

1. Kognitiv komponent – o'quvchilarda ma'naviy ongini, badiiy eruditsiyani, dunyoqarashini shakllanishi bilan tavsiflanadi.

2. Emotsional komponent – o'quvchilarda estetik hislar, emotsional qadriyatlar tizimi, oliy hislarning shakllanishi bilan belgilanadi.

3. Xulq-atvor komponenti – o'quvchilarning ijtimoiy xulq me'yorlariga rioya etish ko'nikmasi, axloqiy dunyoqarashi tarbiyalanadi.

O'quvchilarning kitobxonlik madaniyatini shakllantirishda boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchisi pedagogika va psixologiya fanlarini yaxshi bilishi, o'quvchilarda mutolaa qilish psixologiyasini qaror toptirishi, shuningdek, u shaxslararo muloqot psixologiyasi hamda ijtimoiy-psixologiyaga oid bilimlarga ham ega bo'lishi talab etiladi.

Boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchisi - pedagog estetik jihatdan tarbiyalangan, bilimdon, badiiy didga ega bo'lishi zarur. Rivojlangan mamlakatlarda o'quvchilarga

ijtimoiy, pedagogik hamda madaniy kutubxona xizmatini ko'rsatish ularning asosiy hayotiy ehtiyojlarini qondirish sohasiga kiradi.

O'qituvchi va kutubxonachining asosiy e'tibori ijodkor shaxs sifatida rivojlanayotgan o'quvchining kitobxonlik madaniyatini shakllantirishga qaratilgan bo'lishi lozim.

Kutubxonaga mo'ljallangan xonalar o'quvchining turli manbalardan axborot olishi uchun qulay bo'lishi kerak.

Umuman olganda yuqoridagi fikrlar asosida xulosa qiladigan bo'lsak:

- O'quvchilardagi kitobxonlik madaniyati ularning ma'naviy dunyoqarashi, axloqiy ongining oshishiga xizmat qiladi;

- Sharq allomalari asarlari, afsonalardagi futuvvat ilmi negizida altruistik motivlarning namoyon bo'lishini kuzatishimiz mumkin;

- Altruizm o'zgalarga beg'araz yordam ko'rsatishga asoslangan milliy xususiyatlardan biridir;

- Maktablarda murabbiylik soatlarida badiiy asar mutoalasini targ'ib qilish orqali o'quvchilarda altruistik xulq motivlarini shakllantirish mumkin.

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THE PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISM OF STUDENTS' INTRAPERSONAL CONFLICTS

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Annotation: *This article reveals the features of intrapersonal conflict of personality. Certain indicators, classification of intrapersonal conflicts, differentiation of the structures of a person's inner world are analyzed. Preventive measures to prevent intrapersonal conflicts in the social environment are proposed.*

Key words: *value orientations, emotional, behavioral, cognitive sphere, integral indicators.*

The features of current social processes and the growing variety of different communication options in the modern information society of New Uzbekistan today place special demands on the individual as part of modern society, indicating the need for her to have a sufficient level of social activity and emphasizing the special importance of her willingness to manifest various ways of resolving intrapersonal conflicts.

Personality is the ultimate subject of conflict. As such, it forms one of its sides. The conflicts that a person generates within himself and of which he is the bearer are called intrapersonal conflicts.

Intrapersonal conflict is a state of the personality structure when it simultaneously has contradictory and mutually exclusive motives, value orientations and goals that it is currently unable to cope with, i.e. to develop priorities of behavior based on them. Like any other type of conflict, this type of conflict does not arise from scratch. No individual as a social being can develop outside the system of social relations. And only in society can he satisfy his needs, assert his interests and achieve his goals. On the other hand, every person strives for freedom and self-realization. This objective contradiction between personality and society initially determines the appearance of various intrapersonal conflicts that have diverse consequences for personality development.

The study of intrapersonal conflict began at the end of the 19th century. It is conducted mainly within the framework of the psychological field with an emphasis on the biopsychological interpretation of intrapersonal conflict. A person in a state of conflict has a clash of desires (Z. Freud). Part of the personality defends certain desires, the other rejects them. Within the personality, there is a constant dispute between the Id, the Ego and the Superego, where it is the primary, innate instance, initially irrational and subordinate to the principle of pleasure. It manifests itself in unconscious desires and drives, which are realized in unconscious impulses and

reactions. Cognitive psychology considers conflict as a mismatch of knowledge and behavior, or a mismatch of two knowledges.

An intrapersonal conflict is perceived and emotionally experienced by a person as a significant psychological problem that requires resolution and causes internal work of consciousness aimed at overcoming it.

The inner-personal conflict is based on experience. What is it? Experiencing is a form of personal activity in which a contradiction is realized and a process of its resolution is underway on a subjective level.

There are certain indicators of intrapersonal conflict:

1. Cognitive sphere: – decreased self-esteem; – awareness of one's condition as a psychological dead end; – delayed decision-making; – deep doubts about the truth of the principles that you used to follow.

2. Emotional sphere: – psycho-emotional tension; – frequent and significant negative experiences.

3. Behavioral sphere: – decrease in the quality and intensity of activity; – reduced job satisfaction; – negative emotional background of communication.

4. Integral indicators: deterioration of the adaptation mechanism, increased stress. There is a very clear classification of intrapersonal conflicts. It is based on the differentiation of the structures of a person's inner world that come into conflict. The inner world of a person includes: motives, values, self-esteem.

Motives – "I want" (needs, interests, desires): values – "necessary": self-esteem – "I can". Based on this understanding of the inner world of a person, the following intrapersonal conflicts are distinguished:

- Motivational conflict
- Moral conflict
- Conflict of unrealized desire
- Role conflict
- Adaptive conflict
- Conflict of inadequate self-esteem.

A person's relationship to the world, to other people, and to himself is contradictory. According to A.N. Leontiev, the diverse relationships that a person enters into with reality are objectively contradictory. Their contradictions generate conflicts, which, under certain conditions, are fixed and enter into the personality structure. If we take a more specific look at the causes of intrapersonal conflict, they can be divided into three types::

- 1) internal causes rooted in the contradictions of the personality itself;
- 2) external reasons due to the position of a person in a social group;
- 3) external reasons due to the position of the individual in society.

Internal causes.

The internal causes of intrapersonal conflict are rooted in contradictions between various motives of the personality, in the inconsistency of its internal structure.

At the same time, the more complex a person's inner world is, the more developed his feelings, values and aspirations are, and the higher his ability to introspect, the more susceptible a person is to conflict.

Among the main contradictions causing internal conflict, the following can be distinguished:

- the contradiction between the need and the social norm;
- conflicting motives, interests, and needs (you want to go to the theater, and you need to prepare for the seminar);
- the contradiction of social roles (you have to stay late at work to fulfill an urgent order, and take a walk with your child);
- The contradiction of social values and norms: how to combine the Christian value of "thou shalt not kill" and the duty to defend the fatherland on the battlefield.

For an intrapersonal conflict to arise, these contradictions must acquire a deep personal meaning, otherwise a person will not attach importance to them.

In addition, the various sides of contradictions should be approximately equal in terms of their impact on the individual.

Otherwise, a person easily chooses the lesser of two evils, and the greater of two benefits. And there is no conflict.

External causes.

External causes of intrapersonal conflict may be caused by:

- 1) the position of the individual in the group,
- 2) the position of the individual in the organization,
- 3) the position of the individual in society.

A common feature of the external causes of intrapersonal conflict, due to the position of the individual in the group, is the inability to satisfy any important needs and motives relevant to the individual.

2 Intrapersonal conflict is a process in which a person experiences an internal contradiction between different desires, goals, motives, values, or needs.

Internal conflicts can arise against the background of a clash of various aspects of personality, such as moral principles, social expectations, personal ambitions and the demands of the external environment.

The main types of intrapersonal conflicts:

- Conflict of values — a contradiction between personal beliefs and external demands. Emotional conflict is a clash of different emotions, such as anxiety and hope.
- Role conflict — occurs when a person cannot combine various social roles (student, family member, employee, etc.).
- Conflict of self—acceptance is a contradiction between the image that a person wants to have and the image that he really perceives.

The analysis of psychological and pedagogical literature makes it possible to define intrapersonal conflict as a mental state of personal experience determined by

the inability to satisfy needs due to internal contradictions, which contributes to the emergence of unbalanced mental states.

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DEVELOPMENT OF FLEXIBLE SKILLS (SOFT SKILLS) MASTERS

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Abstract: *Article reveals the relevance of studying and developing Soft Skills of students. An overview of approaches to the study of Soft Skills in domestic and foreign science is presented.*

Keywords: *Soft Skills, Hard Skills, competencies, education, competitiveness.*

The labor market of New Uzbekistan imposes new requirements related not only to the professional competencies of a specialist or an applicant, but also to his flexible skills. Flexible skills are becoming particularly relevant in connection with the processes of digitalization of modern society and the profession market.

The skills and competencies possessed by any specialist can be divided into two categories:

1. Hard Skills.
2. Soft Skills.

Professional skills are Hard Skills that are reflected in professional standards and job descriptions and are characterized by certain knowledge and skills related to the performance of work functions [1].

Modern employers have increasingly begun to pay attention to supra-professional flexible skills (Soft Skills), which are not receiving enough attention in the process of professional training today. The model of professional competencies can be represented as follows: inside there is a core — Hard Skills (certain knowledge and skills necessary in a particular field of work), and outside — Soft Skills (additional, reinforcing basic skills) [5].

In recent years, there have been changes in the list of skills required by employers, with preference given to flexible skills over technical skills. Employers claim that many masters do not have the right set of flexible skills that would allow them to integrate and effectively contribute to their work; they tend to view most new graduates as unable to integrate into an existing team and expect them to immediately take a leadership position, even if they do not have the right qualities.

Specialists with flexible skills receive the most demand in the market — they have an advantage in the perception of the employer compared to those who have only highly professional skills.

The modern rhythm of life and new technologies require advanced flexible skills from potential employees.:

- be adaptive,
- able to work in a team,
- interact effectively,
- be independent [2].

The World Health Organization [3] indicates that flexible skills are the abilities for adaptive and constructive behavior that allow people to effectively cope with life's difficulties. Such skills are considered as general, core, or key skills that are applied in various organizational and work contexts. They are also key opportunities to enhance competitiveness at the individual, social and national levels [4].

S. Caruana argues that the educational process itself leads to the development of a number of skills that may not be clearly listed in the curriculum, but which can be acquired by undergraduates as a result of participating in various activities that make up the academic course [2]. He further continues that the specifics of the academic environment lead to the development of self-reflection and assessment, synthesis and analysis of knowledge. The structure of the curricula is such that masters students often have to work in groups or teams, where, in addition to achieving academic goals, they also develop skills in team building, planning and distributing work among team members.

At the same time, in the works of foreign scientists (J. Grayson, R. Martens, K. Rogers, etc. [2]), the concept of competitiveness is considered from a phenomenological, psychological and indirectly pedagogical point of view.

Thus, K. Rogers notes that a person "tends to develop all his abilities in order to preserve and develop his personality" [2]. G. Allport reveals personality competitiveness through the analysis of the phenomenon of mature personality, noting that human maturation is a process of formation that continuously proceeds and continues throughout life [4].

J. Grayson and K. O'Dell believe that the characteristics of competitiveness are the need to achieve success and self-confidence based on awareness of one's own abilities and capabilities [4]. R. Martens sees a competitive personality as the main result of socialization. Being socially competitive, in his opinion, means being able to perform many social roles [3]. The psychological aspects of the formation of a competitive personality are considered in the works of L. M. Mitina, Yu. A. Fedorova, and others [1]. A specialist must have sufficient qualifications and a range of abilities, as well as emotional intelligence.

According to Khalilova Sh.T. [5], emotional intelligence is a critically important attribute of personal and professional success, it provides those skills that make a person more competitive in the work environment. The first stage of professional competencies and qualities formation begins in the professional education system. Our "reactive world" requires the formation of a professionally mobile personality type [5]. Often, graduate students lack the special knowledge and skills that can be acquired as part of high-quality practical training for a specialist at an enterprise during their internship.

The new demand from employers is due to the unstable global economic situation, in which a business built on innovation, cooperating with foreign partners, and creating collaborations is surviving.

New types of employees are needed for the operation of such enterprises. For young people, all this creates additional difficulties in finding employment.

In this regard, there is criticism of university education: there are more and more calls for the abandonment of higher education and alternative training in short-term courses that promote the development of a particular skill necessary for rapid employment [7].

Our research is devoted to studying the level of flexible skills of masters, in particular: critical thinking and emotional intelligence, communication and teamwork. Based on the results of the research, it is planned to develop a development program for undergraduates in the field of “Management in Education” in the process of teaching English based on a contextual approach.

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**RUHIY RIVOJLANISHI SUSTLASHGAN VA RIVOJLANISHIDA
MUJASSAM NUQSONGA EGA BO'LGAN BOLALAR BILAN OLIB
BORILADIGAN LOGOPEDIK KORREKSION ISHLAR TIZIMI**

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada ruhiy rivojlanishi sustlashgan va rivojlanishida mujassam nuqsonlarning paydo bo'lish sabablari, ularni aniqlash va ularni bartaraf etish usullari haqida so'z yuritamiz.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Konstitutsional, Somatogen, Psixogen, Serebral, Psixomotor qo'zg'aluvchanlik, Affektiv o'zgarishlar, Psixopatik o'zgarishlar, Epileptik buzilishlar, Apatik - adinamik buzilishlar, Murakkab nuqson, ikkilamchi nuqson, asoratli nuqson, Marshal sindromi, Usher sindromi, Alport sindromi, Lou sindromi*

Abstract: *This article discusses the causes of mental retardation and congenital defects in development, their identification and methods of their elimination.*

Keywords: *Constitutional, Somatogenic, Psychogenic, Cerebral, Psychomotor changes, Epileptic disorders, Apathetic-adyamic disorders, Complex defect, secondary defect, complicated defect, Marshall syndrome, Usher syndrome, Alport syndrome, Low syndrome*

Абстрактный: *В этой статье мы поговорим о причинах задержки психического развития и пороков развития, их выявлении и методах устранения.*

Ключерые слова: *Конституциональная, Соматоленная, Психогенная, Церебральная, Психомоторная возбудимость, Аффективтивные изменения, Психопатические изменения, Эпилептические расстройства, Анато- адинамические расстройства, Комплексный дефект, Вторичный дефект, Осложненный дефект, Синдром Маршалла, Синдром Ушера, Синдром Альпорта, Синдром Лоу*

Avvalo Ruhiy rivojlanishi sustlashgan bolalar qanday bo'ladi degan savolga to'xtalsak, Ularning bilish faoliyati– intellekti mantiqiy tafakkuri, idroki, xotirasi,ixtiyoriy diqqati, ish qobiliyati va boshqa xislatlariga birinchi o'rinda markaziy nerv sistemasining kasalliklari natijasida ruhiy rivojlanishi sustlashadi. Bunday bolalarda hissiyot, iroda sferasidagi kamchiliklar birlamchi, aqliy zaiflik esa ikkilamchi hodisa bo'lib hisoblanadi.

Ruhiy rivojlanishi sustlashgan bolalar aqliy darajasi jihatidan asosan ikki guruhga bo'linadi:

1. Yengil nuqsoni bor bolalar – bular maxsus sharoitda 1- 3 yil ta’lim- tarbiya olganlaridan keyin o’qishni ommaviy maktabning tegishli sinfida davom ettirishi mumkin.

2. Ruhiy rivojlanishida sezilarli darajada orqada qolgan bolalar – bular maktabni bitirguniga qadar maxsus sharoitda o’qitilishi kerak. Bunday bolalar maktab dasturini sog’lom tengdoshlari qatori o’zlashtira olmaydi.

Ruhiy rivojlanishi sustlashgan bolalarni ommaviy maktabda hamma qatori o’qitish ta’lim jarayoniga ham salbiy ta’sir ko’rsatadi., ya’ni o’rtacha o’quvchining saviyasini orqaga tortadi, yaxshi va a’lo o’zlashtiruvchi o’quvchilarni yetarli darajada o’stirishga to’sqinlik qiladi.

Dastur materiallarini yaxshi o’zlashtira olmaganligi tufayli ruhiy rivojlanishi sustlashgan bolalar doim muvaffaqiyatsizliklarga uchrayveradi, bu narsa ularning hulq-atvorida aksariyat turli salbiy xislatlar yuzaga kelishiga sabab bo’ladi.

Olimlardan K.S.Lebedinskaya, G.P.Berto’n, E.M.Dunayeva va boshqalar ruhan sust rivojlanganlikni klinik-psixologik jihatdan quyidagi hillarga bo’lishni tavsiya etadilar:

- 1) konstitutsional;
- 2) somatogen;
- 3) psixogen;
- 4) serebral shakli.

Ruhan sust rivojlanganlikning konstitutsional shaklini harakterlovchi belgilarga quyidagilar kiradi: bolaning gavda tuzilishi sog’lom tengdoshlarinikiga nisbatan 1- 2 yosh kichik ko’rinadi.

U o’zini bog’cha yoshidagilarga o’xshab tutadi va ta’lim olish uchun hali “yetilmagan” bo’ladi. Bunday bola o’quv faoliyatiga yaxshi kirishib ketmaydi, chunki unda o’qishga qiziqish yo’q, ish qobiliyati past. Mas’uliyatsizlik, motivlarning sustligi, ruhiy jarayonlardan analiz, sintez qobiliyatlarining yaxshi rivojlanmaganligi tufayli o’qish va yozishni, matematikani katta qiyinchiliklar bilan o’zlashtiradi.

Dars vaqtida tez charchab qolish hollari, bosh og’rib turishi konstitutsion shakldagi bunday bolada ish qobiliyati, faollik yanada pasayib ketishiga sabab bo’ladi. Ruhan sust rivojlanganlikning psixogen shaklida bola erta yoshligidan noqulay, noto’g’ri sharoitda tarbiyalanadi va shu tarbiyaning salbiy tomonlari ruhan rivojlanishiga ta’sir o’tkazgan bo’ladi.

Shu xildagi kamchiliklarning kelib chiqish sabablarini 3 guruhga bo’lish mumkin: Bola tarbiyasi bilan mutlaqo shug’ullanmaslik, uni butunlay o’z holiga tashlab qo’yish, bunda bolalarda burch va mas’uliyat hissi shakllanmaydi.

Aql-idrokning rivojlanishi, qiziqishlari, bilish faoliyati, his-tuyg’u va iroda yetishmasligi ustiga o’quv fanlarini o’zlashtirish uchun zarur bilim va taassurotlarning yetishmasligi ham qo’shiladi.

Bolani har tomonlama erkalatish, yetarli mustaqil faoliyatga o’rgatmaslik, tashabbuskorlik, mas’uliyat xissini shakllantirmaslik bolani «oila erkasi» qilib

o‘stirish, haddan tashqari uning ko‘ngliga qarab ish tutish natijasida ham bola ruhiy rivojlanishida bir qadar orqada qolishi mumkin.

Bolaga nisbatan qo‘pol munosabatda bo‘lish, jismoniy jazolash, qattiq qo‘llik qilish, ota-onalarning alkogolizmga aloqador tajovvuzkorona munosabatlari bolani mudom asabiylashtirib, ruhan rivojlanishdan orqada qolishiga sabab bo‘ladi.

Bunday bolalarda qrpollik, jur‘atsizlik, tashabbussizlik, mustaqilsizlik, qo‘rqoqlik va boshqa hislatlar shakllanadi. Bularning hammasi aql-idrokiga, bilish faoliyatiga ham salbiy ta‘sir ko‘rsatadi. Ruhiy rivojlanishi sustlashgan bolalar uchun mamlakatimizda maxsus maktabgacha tarbiya muassasalari internatlari, kuni uzaytirilgan maktablarda tenglashtirish sinflari tashkil etilgan. Ushbu masalalarda ta‘lim umumta‘lim oddiy bog‘cha yoki maktab dasturi va darsliklari asosida olib boriladi, himoyalaydigan muloyim davolovchi maxsus tartib tashkil etiladi.

Ta‘lim-tarbiyaviy ishlar bolalarning fikrlash qobiliyati, diqqati, ish qobiliyati, xotirasi, nutqi va tafakkuridagi kamchiliklarni bartaraf etishga qaratilgan bo‘lib, bunday bolaga bilim berishda o‘qituvchi uning o‘ziga xos individual xususiyatlarini e‘tiborga olgan holda maxsus sharoitda, maxsus usullar bilan ishlaydi, tegishli yordam tashkil etadi. Zamonaviy maxsus pedagogikada mujassam nuqsonga ega bo‘lgan bolalarga nisbatan e‘tiborning ortganligi, yuqorida aytib o‘tganimizdek, ularning soni ortib borayotganligini, shuningdek, ularga ixtisoslashtirilgan yordam ko‘rsatish uchun ishlanmalarning yo‘qligidan dalolat beradi. Turli xil nuqsonlarga ega bo‘lgan bolalar deyarli barcha maxsus muassasalarda uchraydi.

“Murakkab nuqson” yoki hozir qabul qilinganidek, “rivojlanishdagi murakkab nuqsonlar” tushunchasi, turli adabiyot manbalarida turlicha qayd etiladi. Atamalardagi noaniqlik birlamchi nuqson oqibatida, aniq birlamchi nuqson ta‘sirida, ikkilamchi nuqsonni paydo bo‘lishida yoki ahamiyatsiz nuqsonlar tizimning asosiy elementlari sifatida baholanganda paydo bo‘ladi, shu bilan bir vaqtda, ularga asoratlar sifatida qarash lozim.

Zamonaviy maxsus pedagogikada mujassam nuqsonga ega bo‘lgan bolalarga nisbatan e‘tiborning ortganligi, yuqorida aytib o‘tganimizdek, ularning soni ortib borayotganligini, shuningdek, ularga ixtisoslashtirilgan yordam ko‘rsatish uchun ishlanmalarning yo‘qligidan dalolat beradi. Turli xil nuqsonlarga ega bo‘lgan bolalar deyarli barcha maxsus muassasalarda uchraydi.

“Murakkab nuqson” yoki hozir qabul qilinganidek, “rivojlanishdagi murakkab nuqsonlar” tushunchasi, turli adabiyot manbalarida turlicha qayd etiladi. Atamalardagi noaniqlik birlamchi nuqson oqibatida, aniq birlamchi nuqson ta‘sirida, ikkilamchi nuqsonni paydo bo‘lishida yoki ahamiyatsiz nuqsonlar tizimning asosiy elementlari sifatida baholanganda paydo bo‘ladi, shu bilan bir vaqtda, ularga asoratlar sifatida qarash lozim.

Murakkab nuqson ikki va undan ortik buzilishlarni qo‘shilib kelishini qamrab oladi, ular bolani anomal rivojlanishiga va ijtimoiy moslashuvini qiyinlashtirishga bir xil ta‘sir ko‘rsatadi. Murakkab nuqsonli bolalar maxsus dastur asosida o‘qitilishga

muhtoj. Masalan, bir vaqtning o'zida eshitishi va ko'rishi buzilgan bolalar (ko'r-kar), BSF va og'ir eshitish buzilishini qo'shib kelishi; aqli zaiflik va ko'rlikda va boshqa turdagi murakkab nuqsonli bolalar alohida ta'lim dasturini talab qiladi.

V.N.Chulkov (2001) bolalar rivojlanishidagi murakkab nuqsonlarga bitta bolada ikki yoki undan ortiq psixofizik nuqsonlarni birga kelishini kiritadi. Masalan, karlik va zaif ko'ruvchilikning birga kelishi, aqli zaiflik va ko'rlik, tayanch-harakat apparatidagi nuqsonlar va nutq nuqsonlari.

Murakkab (mujassam) nuqsonlarga bir nechta birlamchi nuqsonlarni namoyon qiladigan, ularning har biri alohida olinganda anomal rivojlanish tuzilishi va xarakterini belgilaydigan kamchiliklar kiritiladi.

Barcha mavjud nuqsonlar bir-biriga ta'sir ko'rsatadi va o'zaro ta'sirini kuchaytiradi. Buning oqibatidagi salbiy asoratlar sifat va son jihatidan alohida nuqsonlarning yig'indisidan ancha qo'polroq bo'ladi.

Mujassam nuqsonlarni tashxis qilish haddan tashqari qiyin, chunki ular bolaning sensor, harakat, nutqiy, bilish sohalarida paydo bo'lishi mumkin. Bunday nuqsonga ega bo'lgan bolalarni differensial tashxisi ularning psixik rivojlanishini belgilovchi omillarni hisobga olgan holda amalga oshiriladi. Murakkab nuqsonli bollarni o'rganish har tomonlama chuqur tadqiqotlar olib borishni ko'zda tutadi.

Xulosa qiladigan bo'lsak, bolaning anomal rivojlanishi tuzilishiga ko'pgina xilma-xil omillar ta'sir qiladi. Eng avvalo, birlamchi nuqsonlarning paydo bo'lish vaqtini aniqlash muhim ahamiyatga ega. Erta jarohatlanish bolaning butun psixik rivojlanish yo'lining buzilishiga olib keladi. Rivojlanish xususiyatlarini shuningdek, birlamchi nuqsonning etiologiyasi, patogenezi, tarqalganligi, namoyon bo'lish darajasi belgilaydi. Mujassam nuqsonlar zamonaviy maxsus pedagogika va psixologiyada muhim mavzulardan biridir.

Ularning bartaraf etilishi uchun kompleks yondashuv zarur bo'lib, bu nafaqat nutq ko'nikmalarini, balki bolalarning ijtimoiy va emotsional rivojlanishini ham o'z ichiga oladi. Mujassam nuqsonlarni tushunish va ularga to'g'ri yondashuvni ishlab chiqish bolalarning o'z-o'zini anglash va jamiyatda muvaffaqiyatli faoliyat yuritishlari uchun muhim ahamiyatga ega. Ruhiy rivojlanishi sustlashgan bolalar aqli zaif, debil bolalarga nisbatan ancha yaxshi tushunadi va ularni bajarish uchun ularda kerakli imkoniyatlar mavjud bo'ladi.

Ruhiy rivojlanishi sustlashgan bolalarning o'zlashtirish qobiliyati sog'lom tengqurlariga nisbatan past bo'lsa-da, debil bolalarnikidan ancha durust bo'lganligi uchun bunday bolalarni yordamchi maktabga yuborish noto'g'ri, chunki ushbu maktab dasturi ular uchun soddalik qiladi.

Ommaviy maktab esa bola uchun zarur bo'lgan sharoitni yaratib (maxsus sinf-tenglashtiruvchi sinf ochib) o'z dasturini o'lashtirishini ta'minlash uchun maxsus yordam ko'rsatishi lozim.

O'z vaqtida va to'g'ri tashkil etilgan yordam tufayli ushbu toifadagi aloxida yordamga muxtoj bolalar keyinchalik yaxshi rivojlanib ketib, maktabni bitirgach oliy o'quv yurtlarida xam muvaffaqiyatli ta'lim oladilar.

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EXPLORING THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON MODERN LANGUAGE: A STUDY OF LINGUISTIC INNOVATIONS AND COMMUNICATION PATTERNS

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Abstract: *The rise of social media platforms has profoundly influenced the way people use language in daily communication. This study investigates how social media affects linguistic innovation, vocabulary change, and communication patterns, especially among younger generations. With the growing popularity of platforms like Twitter, Instagram, and TikTok, language has become more dynamic, abbreviated, and emotionally expressive. The study uses surveys and content analysis to explore how online language differs from traditional forms, including the creation of neologisms, acronyms, emojis, and informal grammar usage. Findings suggest that while social media encourages creativity and speed in communication, it also challenges traditional language norms.*

Keywords: *social media, language change, linguistic innovation, online communication, digital linguistics, neologisms, informal grammar*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, social media has become an integral part of modern communication. Platforms like Twitter, Instagram, WhatsApp, and TikTok have not only changed how people connect, but also how they use and evolve language. Words are shortened, emojis replace emotions, and entire sentences are sometimes replaced by acronyms like “LOL” or “BRB.”

The purpose of this article is to explore the linguistic impact of social media on modern language. How does language adapt in fast-paced online environments? How do new communication styles affect grammar, vocabulary, and the way people express themselves? This research highlights how digital communication has become a space of rapid linguistic change, with both positive and negative implications for formal language standards.

Literature review

Numerous studies have highlighted the linguistic shifts caused by digital and social media communication. According to Baron (2008), digital writing allows for a more conversational and informal tone compared to traditional writing. Crystal (2011) argues that social media platforms promote linguistic creativity, with users often inventing new words, adopting playful spellings, and using emojis or GIFs to replace verbal expression.

Linguistic features in social media

Several unique features define online language:

- Acronyms and Initialisms – e.g., LOL (laugh out loud), TMI (too much information), IDK (I don't know)
- Hashtags and tagging – Help categorize topics and engage with broader discussions (Zappavigna, 2012).
- Emojis and visual cues – Add emotional tone to otherwise flat text, creating a new layer of meaning (Danesi, 2016).
- Intentional misspellings and informal grammar – e.g., “gonna,” “wanna,” or lower-case writing for stylistic purposes

Social media language challenges traditional norms of grammar, punctuation, and spelling, creating a new hybrid style that blends spoken and written communication (Tagliamonte & Denis, 2008).

Impacts on communication

While many linguists praise social media for encouraging engagement and language play, critics argue that frequent use of informal writing could reduce academic writing skills and damage language standards (Thurlow & Mroczek, 2011).

Still, most researchers agree that language is always evolving, and social media simply accelerates this natural process.

Methodology

This research employs a mixed-methods approach to examine the influence of social media on language usage.

Participants

- 150 university students from various academic backgrounds
- Survey and content analysis were used to collect data on language use in digital communication

Data collection

1. Online survey – Collected data on students' social media usage, frequency of informal language, and opinions on linguistic changes.
2. Content analysis – Examined 300 posts from Instagram, Twitter, and TikTok comments to identify patterns of language use.
3. Focus group discussions – Small groups of students were asked about their attitudes toward online language versus formal writing.

Data analysis

- Survey responses were analyzed statistically.
- Language patterns from social media posts were categorized into themes such as abbreviations, neologisms, and emoji use.
- Focus group data were thematically coded to understand users' perspectives on digital language.

Results

Survey findings

- 88% of students reported regularly using abbreviations or acronyms in their daily texting or social media posts.

- 72% believed that social media has made their communication more expressive but admitted to using informal structures in academic writing unintentionally.

- 64% were aware of new words and phrases created on social media and used them often.

Content analysis

The analysis of 300 posts revealed:

- Frequent use of emojis instead of full expressions (e.g., “I’m so happy” = “I’m so ”)

- Intentional spelling changes (e.g., “fr” for “for real,” “u” for “you”)

- High presence of internet slang and shortened grammar forms

Focus group insights

- Many students saw social media as a “safe space” for creative and emotional expression.

- Some were concerned that overuse of informal structures could weaken academic writing habits.

- Participants viewed social media as a separate language variety, not necessarily harmful but distinct from formal writing.

Discussion / Data analysis

The findings align with existing research suggesting that social media fosters a unique linguistic environment.

1. Innovation and creativity

Social media encourages users to create new forms of expression that are concise, emotionally rich, and adaptable. This has led to a more inclusive and fast-evolving lexicon (Crystal, 2011).

2. Impact on formal writing

While many students can switch between informal and formal registers, there is evidence that frequent social media use can influence grammar and spelling habits, especially in younger or developing writers (Baron, 2008).

3. Emojis and multimodal communication

Emojis have become a new visual language layer, enabling people to express tone and emotion quickly. This marks a shift toward multimodal communication, where text and visuals work together (Danesi, 2016).

4. Code-switching between contexts

Students often distinguish between how they write on social media and in academic settings. This supports the idea that digital language is not replacing traditional forms, but coexisting alongside them (Thurlow & Mroczek, 2011).

Recommendations

1. Incorporate digital language awareness in language education – Teaching students about digital linguistics can help them understand the difference between informal and formal communication.

2. Encourage conscious code-switching – Help learners understand when and how to shift registers based on context.
3. Promote critical media literacy – Enable students to engage with online content while being aware of linguistic changes.
4. Use social media in educational contexts – As a tool for exploring new vocabulary, creativity, and modern language trends.
5. Support research on digital communication – Linguists and educators should continue to study how language evolves through digital use.

Conclusion

Social media has emerged as a powerful force in reshaping modern language, introducing new words, changing communication patterns, and blending written and visual forms of expression. While concerns about formal language erosion exist, most evidence suggests that these changes reflect a natural linguistic evolution, where digital and academic language coexist.

Understanding how social media influences language is essential for educators, linguists, and learners. With proper awareness and guidance, students can navigate both online and academic communication effectively, developing both creativity and correctness in their use of language.

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JADIDCHILIK HARAKATINING SAN'AT VA TEATRGA TA'SIRI

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Annotatsiya: *Jadidchilik harakati XIX asrning oxiri va XX asrning boshlarida O'rta Osiyo va Turkiy xalqlar orasida tarqalgan ijtimoiy, madaniy va siyosiy yangilanishlar oqimi bo'lib, u adabiyot, san'at va teatr sohalarida katta o'zgarishlarga olib keldi. Jadidchilikning san'at va teatrga ta'siri asosan, milliy uyg'onish, o'quv-dastur va ijtimoiy-siyosiy o'zgarishlarni aks ettirgan asarlar bilan bog'liq bo'ldi. Ushbu maqolada Jadidlarning san'at va teatr sohalarini rivojlantirish maqsadida olib borgan ishlari haqida ma'lumot beriladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Ahmad Donish, "O'zbek Jadid adabiyoti", Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiy, milliy dramaturgiya, Saidrasul Aziziy, "Kolizey", "Padarkush", Samarqand, Ozarbayjon, Xolidxoji Mehri, "Inqilob".*

Abstract: *The Jadid movement was a social, cultural, and political movement that spread among the peoples of Central Asia and the Turkic peoples in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, leading to major changes in the fields of literature, art, and theater. The impact of Jadidism on art and theater was mainly associated with works that reflected national revival, educational, and socio-political changes. This article provides information about the work of the Jadids to develop the fields of art and theater.*

Keywords: *Ahmad Donish, "New Uzbek Literature", Mahmudkhodja Behbudiy, national dramaturgy, Saidrasul Aziziy, "Coliseum", "Padarkush", Samarkand, Azerbaijan, Khalidkhodji Mehri, "Revolution".*

Аннотация: *В XIX и XX веках произошел подъем Советского Союза. В XIX веке Советский Союз и Турция были вынуждены покинуть свои территории, а когда они были вынуждены покинуть свои территории, они начали чувствовать необходимость вернуться в свои дома. Идея обучения и воспитания заключается в том, чтобы заставить людей почувствовать себя особенными, заставить их почувствовать себя особенными и заставить их чувствовать себя хорошо. По сути, ресторан выполняет функции ресторана и парикмахерской.*

Ключевые слова: *Ахмад Дониш, «Новая узбекская литература», Махмудходжа Бехбудий, национальная драматургия, Саидрасул Азизий, «Колизей», «Падаркуш», Самарканд, Азербайджан, Халидходжи Мехри, «Революция».*

KIRISH

Buyuk millatparvar jadidlar, jadid matbuoti orqali millatni o'z madaniy-iqtisodiy ahvoli, siyosiy qaram va huquqsizligini anglatishga, unda bosqinchilarga qarshi nafrat, milliy istiqloлга ishonch ruhini tarbiyalashga muvaffaq bo'ldilar.

Shuning bilan birga ular milliy muxtoriyat va jumhuriyat g'oyasini, millatlararo tenglik va qon-qarindoshlikni targ'ibot qilishni to'g'ri yo'lga qo'yadilar.

XIX asrning ikkinchi yarmidan ilg'or ma'rifatparvarlar davlat mustaqilligini yo'qotilishiga asosiy sabab, O'rta Osiyo jamiyatining siyosiy, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy va madaniy qoloqligi ekanini juda yaxshi tushunib yetgan.

Ular turli ijtimoiy qatlamlarning orasidan chiqqan va eng asosiysi zakovatli bo'lib, ilg'or ziyolilarning birinchi avlodi bo'ldi. Ana shu negizdan keyinchalik jadidlar yetishib chiqib ularning g'oyalarini rivojlantirdi va ma'rifatdan siyosatga qarab yo'l oldi.

Yangi ziyolilarning qarashlarida eng avvalo, aholining barcha ijtimoiy qatlamlari orasida hukm surgan savodsizlikni tugatish, eski ta'lim tizimini isloh qilish, qoloq, eski va behuda odatlarga chek qo'yish singari maqsadlar ilgari surildi.

Tadqiqotchilarning fikriga ko'ra ular, ayniqsa diniy mutaassiblik, behuda sarf-xarajatlarga olib keluvchi an'anaviy odatlarga tanqidiy yondashgan. Agar bunday qarashlar debochasini Ahmad Donish kabi ma'rifatparvarlar boshlab bergan bo'lsa, ularning g'oya va qarashlarini Sadridin Ayniy, Abdulvohid Munzim, Mirkomil Burxonov, Usmonxo'ja Po'latxo'jaev, Xolidxoji Mehri, Mulla Vafo, Abdurauf Fitrat rivojlantirdi.³⁶

Kirish. Turkiston o'lkasida 1910-yillarning ikkinchi yarmi – "O'zbek Jadid adabiyoti" nomi bilan tarixga kirgan yangi adabiyotning shakllanib, dastlabki dadil qadamlarini tashlagan yillar bo'ldi. Milliy matbuotning maydonga kelishi bilan yangi adabiyotning mazmun va yo'nalishi, til va uslubi, janr va mavzular, badiiyati bilan bog'liq masalalar keng muhokama qilina bordi.

Davrning talab va ehtiyojlaridan kelib chiqqan holda, sotsial-ijtimoiy mavzularga, zamonaviy masalalarga, ma'rifat va ozodlikka katta e'tibor berildi. Abdulla Avloniy "Oyinayi har millat erur til-adabiyot" deb yozadi. Mahmudxo'ja Behbudiy, Munavvarqori Abdurashidxonov teatrni "Ibratxona" deb atadilar. Biroq 1910-yillar she'riyati ma'rifatni maqsad emas, vosita deb bildi. "Ko'chli millatlar", "Jahon Jayhunlari" haqida yozdi.

She'riyat yangi qurilajak davlat va jamiyatning siyosiy tuzumidan axloqiy turmushigacha, iqtisodiy madaniyatigacha qiziqdi. Ayni paytda unda qator poetik-stilistik o'zgarishlar yuz berdi. Avloniy va Hamza ko'pgina she'rlarini qadim she'riy barmoq vaznida yozdilar. She'riyat birinchi jahon urushi yillarida xususan, mardikorlik voqealari davrida g'oyat jonlandi. Shu yillarda mardikorlik voqealariga bag'ishlangan 10 ga yaqin she'riy to'plam chop etilgani ma'lum³⁷.

O'zbek adabiyotida o'sha kezlarda Oktyabr voqeariga bag'ishlab yozilgan badiiy asar uchramaydi. Chunki u keng umumxalq hodisasi sifatida kutib olinmadi. Aksincha, to'ntarish deb qaraldi.

³⁶ Nazarov. O'zbek falsafasi. –T., 2003.

³⁷ Tulak. XX asr o'zbek adabiyoti. –Andijon, 1993.

U haqida asar yozish 1918-1920-yillarda izga tushdi. Aksincha, 1917-yil 27-noyabrdagi Muxtoriyat e’loni keng xalq ommasidagi kabi adabiyot ahlida ham shavq-zavq uyg’otdi. Behbudiy va Fitratning qizg’in turkum maqolalari, Cho’lpon va Hamzaning yoniq she’rlari dunyoga keldi.³⁸

1910-yillarda yaratilgan nasr namunalari u qadar ko’p emas. Anbar Otinning “Qarolar falsafasi”, Saidrasul Aziziyning 1910-yildagi “Moskva va Peterburg sayohati” xotiralari kabi ijtimoiy-falsafiy, sarguzasht-avtobiografik asarlarini nazardan soqit qilsak, Behbudiyning “Oq yelpig’ichli chimli xotin”, Abdurauf Shaxidiyning “Falokatzada”(1911) hikoyalarini, Mirmuhsin Shermuhammedovning “Befarzand Ochildiboy” (1914), Hamzaning “Yangi saodat” (1915) singari “milliy roman” deb nomlangan qissalarini, nihoyat 1915-1916-yillarda e’lon qilingan Abdulla Qodiriyning “Juvonboz” va “Uloqda”, Cho’lponning “Duxtir Muhammadyor” asarlarinigina qayd etish lozim bo’ladi.³⁹

Teatr Jadidlar nazdida avvalo “Ulug’lar maktabi”, “Ibratxona” bo’lib xuddi maktab va matbuot kabi ma’rifat, ilm olmoq g’oyasini targ’ib etish ko’zda tutilgan edi. Ikkinchidan esa, ma’rifiy va ko’ngilochar tomoshalar orqali mablag’ topib, maorif, matbuot ehtiyojlariga sarflamoq ko’zlangan edi.

Turkistonga Tatar, Ozarbayjon, Rus sayyor teatr jamoalarining kirib kelishi Ovro’pacha o’zbek milliy teatr san’atining tug’ilishiga turtki berdi. O’zbek yangi teatri tarixini maxsus o’rgangan B. O. Pestovskiy “Inqilob” jurnalining bir necha sonlarida e’lon qilingan katta maqolasida “Qorako’l” shahriga yaqin bir qishloqda 1909-yilda “O’zbek teatri o’ynaldi” degan xabar borganligini qayd etgan edi. Umuman, teatr sohasiga e’tibor 1910-yillarda juda ko’chli bo’lgan.

Chor hukumatining Turkiston o’lkasidagi rasmiy nashri afkori hisoblangan. “Turkiston viloyatining gazetasi” dan tortib, “Sadoiy Turkiston”, “Sadoiy Farg’ona” gazetalari, “Oyina” jurnalida shunday qiziqishni ifodalovchi oddiy xabarlardan to spektakllarga taqrizu, teatr tanqidchiligiga oid nazariy maqolalargacha uchratish mumkin.⁴⁰

1911-yilda Mahmudxo’ja Behbudiy “Padarkush yohud o’qimagan bolaning xoli” nomli “3 parda 4 manzarali milliy, birinchi fojia” sini yozadi. Asarni chop qilish xususidagi urinishlar ikki yilgacha muvaffaqiyatsiz kechadi. Faqat pyesani 1812-yili rus-fransuz muxorabasining Borodino maydonidagi ruslar g’alabasi bilan yakunlanishi, 100 yilligiga bag’ishlab, Tiflisdagi senzorga yuborilishi nashr uchun imkon beradi. “matbuot ishlari Tiflis qo’mitasi senzori ro’xsati bilan Kavkaz o’lkasi sahnalarida qo’yish mumkin” degan 1913-yil 23-mart 19940-son qaroriga ko’ra, asar 1913-yil Samarqandda alohida kitob holidi chop etiladi. 1914-yil 27-fevralda Toshkent yangi shaharidagi “Kolizey” teatrining 2000 kishilik tomoshaxonasida kech soat yettida “Musulmon” jamiyat imlodiyasi foydasiga Toshkent teatr xavaskorlari rasman o’z spektakllari namoyishini boshlaydilar. Toshkentlik

³⁸ Qosimov. Milliy uyg’onish: Jasorat, ma’rifat, fidoiylik. –T., Ma’naviyat, 2002.

³⁹ Guli Mahmudova. Jadidizm va Turkistonda axloqiy-estetik fikr taraqqiyoti. –T., 2006.

⁴⁰ Xo’jayev. Tanlangan asarlar: uch tomlik. –T.: Fan, 1976. 1-tom.

xavaskorlarning katta muvaffaqiyatlari, ularning shu yo‘nalishdagi faoliyatlarining yanada kengayishi va rivojlanmog‘i uchun muhim turtki bo‘ldi.⁴¹

Turkiston hududida teatr va dramaturgiya rivoji yanada jadalroq odim otishi ham mumkin edi. Afsuski, bu jarayonga juda qattiq qarshilik qilgan kuchlar paydo bo‘ldi.

Saxna san‘atimizning jadal ziyolilari orzu qilganidek, bir necha ming aholi soniga to‘g‘ri keladigan qator teatr ibratxonalari vujudga kelishida eng katta to‘siqning biri mustamlaka istibdodi bo‘lsa, ikkinchisi diniy jaholat va mutassiblik edi.

Rus ma‘murlari Turkistondagi teatrchilik xarakteriga, milliy dramaturgiya taraqqiyoti va targ‘ibotiga ham tashkiliy-ma‘naviy, ham moddiy to‘sqinlik qilishga o‘rindilar. “Padarkush” pyesasi yozilganidan so‘ng ikki yilgacha ruxsat berilmagani va Turkiston general-gubernatorligining o‘z senzoralari bo‘lgani holda, Tiflisdagi matbuot qo‘mitasi senzoriga murojaat etilgani bunga yaqqol namuna Behbudiy Rus-Fransuz muxorabasining yuz yilligiga maxsus bag‘ishlov so‘zlarini qo‘lyozmaning ilk saxifasiga qayd qilishi rasmiy idoralarga ta‘sir ko‘rsatish uchun qo‘llagan chora – “xiyla” ekani sir emas.

Chunki u asarni to‘laligicha rus tiliga tarjima qilish majburiy qilib quyiladi⁴².

Xulosa o‘rnida shuni aytishimiz mumkunki, Jadidchilik harakati san‘at va teatrga katta ta‘sir ko‘rsatdi.

U milliy madaniyatni saqlash, yangi g‘oyalarni ilgari surish va ijtimoiy yangilanishni qo‘llab-quvvatlashga qaratildi. Teatrda yangi shakllar va badiiy yondashuvlar, milliy tarixiy mavzular va ma‘rifatparvarlik g‘oyalari orqali jamiyatni o‘zgartirishga intilish kuzatildi.

Jadidchilik harakati san‘at va teatrni nafaqat estetik, balki tarbiyaviy va ilmiy maqsadlar uchun ham ishlatishga undadi.

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⁴² Jadidchilik: islohot, yangilanish, mustaqillik va taraqqiyot uchun kurash. –T.: Universitet, 1999.

UMUMTA'LIM MAKTABLARI O'QUVCHILARINING SHAXSIY QOBILİYATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISH UCHUN SINFDAN TASHQARI MASHG'ULOTLARNING AHAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya: *Mamlakatda umumta'lim maktablarini isloh qilishning vazifasi - asosiy va qo'shimcha maktabdan tashqari ta'limning tarkibiy qismlari bo'lishi kerak bo'lgan yagona ta'lim makonini shakllantirish.*

Kalit so'zlar: *sinfdan tashqari ta'lim, o'quvchilarning darsdan tashqari faoliyati, innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalar.*

Аннотация: *Задача реформирования общеобразовательной школы в стране заключается в создании единого образовательного пространства, в котором должны присутствовать компоненты основного и дополнительного внешкольного образования.*

Ключевые слова: *внеклассное образование, внеклассная деятельность учащихся, инновационные педагогические технологии*

Abstract: *The modernizing school education system in the country provides for the creation of conditions for the implementation of a functional model of activity, the fundamental principle of which is the completeness of education.*

Keywords: *extracurricular education, extracurricular activities of students, innovative pedagogical technologies*

“Bilimli shaxs” tushunchasi hozirgi vaqtda turli umumiy ta'lim va yuqori ixtisoslashtirilgan fanlar bo'yicha nazariy bilimlarga ega bo'lish chegarasidan chiqib ketdi.

Bugun biz faol fuqarolik pozitsiyasini egallagan, o'z-o'zini tarbiyalash va o'z-o'zini takomillashtirish bilan shug'ullanadigan, zamonaviy jamiyatda, shu jumladan o'z sohasining professional sifatida o'z o'rnini topa oladigan shaxsga nisbatan ta'lim va barkamol shaxs haqida gapirishimiz mumkin.

O'zbekistonning modernizatsiya qilinayotgan maktab ta'limi tizimi faoliyatining funksional modelini joriy etish uchun shart-sharoitlar yaratishni nazarda tutadi, uning asosiy tamoyili ta'limning to'liqligidir.

Mamlakatda umumta'lim maktablarini isloh qilishning vazifasi - asosiy va qo'shimcha maktabdan tashqari ta'limning tarkibiy qismlari bo'lishi kerak bo'lgan yagona ta'lim makonini shakllantirish.

Umumiy ta'lim tizimidagi sinfdan tashqari ishlar har bir o'quvchining individual rivojlanishi, uning qiziqishlari, sevimli mashg'ulotlari va ta'lim imkoniyatlarini aniqlashdan iborat bo'lgan ichki farqlash asosida qurilishi kerak. [1].

Sinfdan tashqari ishlarda bolaning o'quv faoliyati jarayonida olgan shaxsiy tajribasiga tayanish kerak va hech qanday holatda uni e'tiborsiz qoldirmaslik kerak.

O'qituvchi o'quvchining qobiliyati yo'nalishlarini hisobga olishi kerak, bu o'quvchi uchun nima qiziqarli va unga mantiqiy ekanligini aniqlashi kerak.

Sinfdan tashqari mashg'ulotlar davomida o'quvchiga ma'lum bilim, ko'nikma va ko'nikmalarni berishning o'zi yetarli emas, bu bola shaxsining qobiliyatlarini rivojlanishiga yordam berish kerak, bu bilan bola jamiyatga yanada moslashishiga va ongli ravishda ko'pgina muvaffaqiyatlarga erishishiga yordam beradi.

Har bir o'quvchining ijodiy salohiyatini, uning qobiliyatlarini va individuallikni shakllantiradigan shaxsiy fazilatlarini, shu jumladan tashabbuskorlik, tasavvur, mustaqillik va o'ziga xosligini ochib berishga alohida e'tibor qaratish lozim. [2].

Bunday muammolarni hal qilish sinfdan tashqari mashg'ulotlarni tashkil etishda o'quvchilar hayotini yanada voqealarga boy qiladigan, uni diversifikatsiya qiladigan va ta'lim maydonini kengaytiradigan innovatsion yondashuvlardan foydalanishni talab qiladi.

Ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonining maqsadi, usullari, mazmuni va shakllariga, o'qituvchi va o'quvchining birgalikdagi faoliyatini tashkil etishga yangilik kiritish orqali ta'lim sohasidagi innovatsiyani tushunamiz. Insonparvarlik, erkinlik va demokratiya tamoyillariga asoslangan innovatsiyalar, birinchi navbatda, o'quvchi va o'qituvchi o'rtasidagi pedagogik hamkorlik samaradorligini oshirishga qaratilgan bo'lishi kerak [3].

Sinfdan tashqari mashg'ulotlarga jalb etishning dastlabki bosqichida o'quvchilar va o'qituvchilarga umumta'lim maktablarida yangicha yondashuvlar, ularning maqsadi va ulardan foydalanish istiqbollari haqida kirish ma'lumotlari beriladi.

Bu bosqichda o'quvchilarni darsdan tashqari mashg'ulotlarga qiziqtirish juda muhim va ma'lumotlar shunday taqdim etilishi mumkinki, ba'zi bir to'liqsizliklar qoladi, bu esa bolalarni yetishmayotgan ma'lumotlarni qidirishga undaydi.

Kirish ma'lumoti uchun turli shakllardan foydalanish tavsiya etiladi: taqdimotlar, targ'ibot guruhlari nutqlari, reklama kompaniyalarini o'tkazish, jurnal tayyorlash. Birinchi bosqichni tugatgandan so'ng, o'quvchilarda darsdan tashqari mashg'ulotlarga barqaror qiziqish paydo bo'lishi kerak.

Ikkinchi bosqichda o'qituvchi va o'quvchilar o'rtasida motivatsiyani yaratish kerak. Innovatsion yondashuvlar bu borada juda samarali, chunki, ular yetarli motivatsion zaryadni o'z ichiga oladi. Amaldagi shakllar va usullarning jozibadorligi bolalar va kattalarning faoliyatini sinfdan tashqari ishlarda shaxsiy motivlarni izlashga yo'naltirish, ularning "men-pozitsiyasi" ni bilishga e'tibor qaratish orqali

namoyon bo'ladi. Taklif etilgan muammolarni hal qilishda shaxsiy ishtirokni maksimal darajada oshirish muhimdir. Agar o'quvchilarning har biri o'z o'rnini topa olsa, tanlangan sinfdan tashqari mashg'ulot turining rejasini amalga oshirsa va o'sish uchun imkoniyatlar topsa va doimiy qiziqish, o'z imkoniyatlariga bo'lgan ishonch bilan almashtirilgan bo'lsa, ikkinchi bosqich maqsadlariga erishilgan deb hisoblash mumkin.

Uchinchi bosqichda texnologiya ustida ishlash boshlanadi. Sinfdan tashqari mashg'ulotlar uchun aniq innovatsion texnologiyalarni tanlash ta'lim muassasasining o'ziga xos xususiyatlariga bog'liq. Shunday qilib, ular ajratadilar:

- maktab o'quvchilarining dunyoqarashini shakllantirish texnologiyasi;
- tematik to'garaklar, ijodiy guruhlar, sinflar, bolalar tashkilotlari, klublar va butun ta'lim muassasasi ishini tashkil etish uchun foydalaniladigan o'zini o'zi boshqarish organlarini tashkil etish bilan o'quvchilarning hayotiy faoliyatini tashkil etish texnologiyasi;

- tematik davrlarni uzoq muddatli rejalashtirishda asosiy hisoblangan loyiha faoliyati doirasidagi kollektiv ijodkorlik texnologiyasi [4].

To'rtinchi bosqich - maktab o'quvchilari ma'lum vaqt davomida tanlangan texnologiya bilan ishlashda katta tajribaga ega bo'lib, kelajakdagi faoliyatlarini ongli ravishda tanlashlari mumkin. Har bir o'quvchi uchun qiziqish va qoniqish darajasi har xil bo'lganligi sababli, tanlov sezilarli darajada farq qilishi mumkin: ba'zilar uchun kollektiv ijodiy faoliyat texnologiyasi ustuvor bo'ladi, boshqalari esa shaxsiy o'zini o'zi rivojlantirish texnologiyasiga ko'proq e'tibor beradi.

Yakuniy bosqich shaxsning o'zini o'zi belgilashini va faoliyat sohalarini kengaytirishni anglatadi. Agar talabalarga turli xil variantlardan darsdan tashqari mashg'ulotlar yo'nalishlarini tanlash erkinligi berilsa, unga o'tish mumkin bo'ladi.

Shuni ta'kidlash kerakki, umumta'lim muassasasida sinfdan tashqari mashg'ulotlar muhim rol o'ynaydi, chunki ular tufayli umumiy ta'limning o'zgaruvchan komponenti mustahkamlanadi, sinf darslarida olingan bilimlarni amalda qo'llashni o'rganish mumkin, maktab o'quvchilarining kognitiv faolligi faollashadi va hozirgi ta'lim muammolarini hal qilish uchun keng amaliy imkoniyatlar ochiladi [5].

Ammo innovatsion usullar nafaqat rasmiy ravishda, balki ta'lim jarayonining barcha tomonlari tomonidan ongli ravishda qabul qilinganda samarali bo'ladi.

Agar professor-o'qituvchilar taklif etilayotgan yangiliklarning mohiyatini tushunsa va qabul qilsa, bu o'qituvchilar, o'quvchilar, ota-onalar va yaqin ijtimoiy muhit bilan ishlashda yangi texnologiyalardan foydalanish muvaffaqiyatining kalitiga aylanadi.

Barcha ilg'or o'zgarishlar o'qituvchilar va o'quvchilarni birlashtirishi kerak, shundan so'ng biz o'qituvchilardan o'z ijodiy faoliyatini faollashtirishi va ta'lim tizimi oldida turgan muammolarning yangi yechimlarini izlashini kutishimiz mumkin.

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TEACHING USING THE PISA PROGRAM IN NATURAL EDUCATION.

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Annotation: *This article provides information about PISA, the international program for assessing student achievement. Science Education provides detailed information about the possibilities of online platforms for preparing for the PISA program. The degree of achievement of results during the lesson using real sites has been widely characterized.*

This article provides information about PISA, the international program for assessing school student achievement. Science Education provides detailed information about the possibilities of online platforms for preparing for the PISA program. The degree of achievement of results during the lesson using real sites has been widely characterized.

PISA is the Program for International Student Assessment. PISA “15-year-old secondary school students who are capable of living a full life in modern society, i.e. What knowledge and skills are needed to solve a wide range of different areas of human activity, communication and social relations? answers the question. Literacy, science and math literacy are valued. The main emphasis is on natural sciences Assessment. PISA “15 -year-old secondary school students who are capable of living a full life in modern society, i.e. What knowledge and skills are needed to solve a wide range of different areas of human activity, communication and social relations? answers the question. Literacy, science and math .

Keywords: *PISA, electronic test, science education, biology, chemistry, literacy, virtual laboratory simulation experiment, online link, resource, platform*

A virtual laboratory is easy to use, secure, accessible on any computer with a browser installed, and allows you to create all the necessary conditions for conducting research within your subject. Using virtual laboratories in teaching increases school students' interest in the subject and allows them to better understand it.

The virtual laboratory, equipped with the necessary equipment, has a large catalog of various school equipment that allows you to conduct experiments in all subjects included in the state educational standard.

Effective experiments. A virtual laboratory can provide an opportunity to test hypotheses, conduct experiments, conduct research, verify the truth of chemical laws, and see practical work firsthand.

Time control. The virtual lab allows you to control time within an experiment, slowing it down or speeding it up.

Saves teaching time. The teacher does not waste time preparing visual experiments in class. Students can prepare to use their chemical equipment at home. Virtual laboratory - a set of interactive practical activities and experiments. Experiments are offered to familiarize students with the chemical properties of substances, basic examples of minerals and inorganic compounds, and to study the physical and chemical properties of some of them.

Research and understanding. The main task of the virtual laboratory is to develop children's ability to research, perceive, and express their thoughts in detail. Virtual laboratories are designed to organize distance learning, conduct experiments and laboratory work on a virtual desktop in an online application on various school subjects, and consolidate the topic, deepen understanding, and integrate it with everyday life. [4].

Virtual labs allow for the following:

- 1) Developing school student's research skills. Promoting interest in scientific research from the elementary school level.
- 2) Remote monitoring of the quality and effectiveness of the acquired knowledge.
- 3) Most importantly, it provides an opportunity to learn about and experience the "real natural world."

The following online sites and virtual, stimulating laboratories have been shown to be effective in educating students in preparation for PISA.

They are:

Classroomscreen.com program

Launch a web browser and go to classroomscreen.com. It should be displayed on the classroom screen. The browser will turn into an interactive whiteboard and have the ability to display all the tools that teachers and school students have come to expect and love. This online tool allows teachers to present lesson instructions clearly and visually. For proper operation, it is best to use the Google Chrome browser (it automatically translates the English-language site)[5].

After loading, the site initially offers a beautiful background image, which changes every time you reopen it. This screensaver can be easily customized, you can choose from a collection or download one.

At the bottom of the screen are tools (more than 13 widgets) suitable for use in the classroom. By pressing the round button, we can select a tool. Multiple languages can be selected. Especially good for foreign language teachers.

Background - This tool allows you to choose from a wide range of stunning images or upload images based on the theme of the lesson. Animated images can be downloaded.

Random name - type or copy and paste the school students' names into the text box and click the "select" button, the name will be selected randomly. When you click the button, the dice will roll. This tool allows you to roll one, two or three dice for a random number

Audio levels require a few simple steps, allowing the site to use your computer's microphone. Then, you set the maximum noise level you want in the classroom. This tool will display a red or green progress bar to help your class know when it needs to be quieter.

Media files are convenient to use in four different ways using the media widget. The options are: upload an image, insert a video from YouTube, launch a webcam, insert an Iframe code...

QR code is one of the favorite tools for teachers. Some useful . You need to enter the URL of the resource and get a QR code for it. It works very simply and easily. Using a special program on the smartphone of school students, they can scan the QR code and open this resource.

How to use Classroomscreen for distance learning?

Classroomscreen was originally designed for classroom learning. However, it can also support teachers in distance learning. To use Classroomscreen for this purpose, you need to share your screen with your school students... Below you will find instructions for various screen sharing conferences. These videos are short and in English, but the modern teacher will understand everything[3].

MS Teams instructions (Youtube)

Google Meet instructions (YouTube)

Zoom instructions (YouTube)

Tips and useful widgets for distance learning

Welcome! Ten minutes before the start of class, turn on the classroom screen with a welcome message and a countdown timer. You can do it! (written with motivational words like "You can do it!"). To engage students, you should share lesson instructions and prepare a lesson plan by combining a greeting with an animated background. Text field. Just like in a real classroom, it is important to think about planning your lesson in online classes so that school students know what to expect and what is expected of them. There are several widgets that can be very useful during online classes.

Webcam (media widget): When sharing a classroom screen, you can turn on the webcam in the media widget. This way, school students can see the teacher alongside the instructions.

Traffic lights: It is important to agree with school students how to use traffic lights online. For example: a red light means students must turn off their microphones, while a green light means they can turn them back on.

Drawing tool: The drawing tool can be used to quickly draw or explain something. It can be used by the teacher in full screen mode or as a small window.

Random Name: With traditional classes, the teacher has a good idea of who should be asking the question at the moment, but how do you do that with an online class? By randomly selecting names, you can keep everyone on their toes.

Colorado.edu program

Virtual science labs have changed a lot in recent years. There is nothing like studying or working in a science lab. The lack of facilities for conducting experiments, especially in remote locations, affects the quality of teaching. However, recently, there have been more and more platforms on the Internet that invite school students to conduct experiments in a virtual environment. One of the most popular virtual labs is PhET Interactive Simulations, a project at the University of Colorado. It is a powerful non-profit Open Educational Resource (OER) project founded in 2002 by Nobel laureate Carl Wieman. The project's stated mission is: "To advance science and mathematics literacy and knowledge worldwide through free, interactive simulations.". However, PhET soon expanded to include other scientific disciplines.

Currently, the project's creators have designed and published more than 125 free interactive simulations in physics, chemistry, biology, geoscience, and mathematics. We can choose the subject and watch the experiments. The simulation has been translated into 65 languages, including Russian.

The teacher can download useful simulations and organize virtual laboratory work. In addition to virtual laboratory work, the simulators can be successfully used in the classroom on an interactive whiteboard and in distance learning for schoolchildren.

Learning Apps.org program

Learning Apps.org is an interactive task designer designed to support the learning process using interactive modules (exercises). At the same time, the teacher. Students can create interactive modules using ready-made templates. The main idea of the interactive tasks that can be created thanks to this service is that schoolchildrens can test and consolidate their knowledge through play, which contributes to the formation of their cognitive interest in a particular academic discipline.

Learningapps.org is a service for creating interactive educational materials on various subjects. Here there is a place for development for both creative teachers and talented school students. On the service <http://learningapps.org/> you can create a puzzle, the pieces of which contain answers to the questions you ask. The service allows you to diversify the lesson, make it interesting, and make the learning process simple and accessible.

Renderforest.com program

Renderforest is a video production platform with cloud storage. Its goal is to simplify the learning process through video creation. With a focus on flexibility and quality, this program helps you create high-quality videos in minutes. The

possibilities are endless for creating any type of video, slideshows, logos, infographics, and more. The only limit is your imagination.

Science Literacy Contexts and Curriculum Research Project

The uniqueness of PISA tasks is that they reflect real-life situations. The context includes text, tables, graphs, and images.

In PISA-015, the tasks were found in the context of the crisis-related issues: health, material resources, environment, support, new knowledge in science and technology. In turn, the contexts are divided into three levels: personal, local, national, global[6].

The above texts mainly draw on the experiences of the PISA-2015 study as examples. After all, the natural sciences were the priority area in the PISA-2015 study. The tasks used in the study can be divided into two types: standard and interactive tasks. In studies conducted before the PISA-2015 study, standard tasks were used.

The text of these paper-based tasks includes graphs and tables, and questions that reflect the problematic situation. The tasks were translated into a computer version for use in the PISA-2015 study[2].

Since PISA 2015, the tasks have been created in a computer-based version, many of which are interactive tasks, i.e. simulations of the study area, allowing students to demonstrate their acquired knowledge and skills in natural sciences in real-life situations[7].

The task is displayed on the computer screen in two panels: the right side of the screen contains the stimulus material (in English, "stimulus>>> "stimulating, inspiring, motivating"), and the left panel contains instructions and questions related to the task. PISA is administered in either paper or computer-based formats, depending on the participating country. For PISA 2015 and subsequent surveys (PISA 2018 and PISA 2021), all new science literacy items were administered exclusively on computers.

Only trend items (items used in previous studies) will be used to assess school students in participating countries that choose to conduct the study in paper format. [1] Using these online applications and programs will create an environment for students to prepare for the PISA online test. If used correctly and effectively, it can create good results for the well-being of the school student and the country.

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ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЕ ГЕНДЕРНОГО РАВЕНСТВА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ

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Аннотация: *Статья акцентирует внимание на главные задачи при обеспечении гарантии равных прав и возможностей для женщин и мужчин во всех сферах жизнедеятельности общества в целях устранения несовместимостей, которые могут возникнуть в установлении прав, обязательств, возможностей и ответственности личности без различия гендерной принадлежности. В статье освещены гендерные реформы в Узбекистане и их перспективы, принятые нормативно-правовые акты и их значение, проанализированы проблемы, ожидающие свое решение и предложены пути их решения.*

Ключевые слова: *Гендер, равноправие, равные права и возможности для женщин и мужчин, защита прав человека, права человека, гендерное равенство.*

O'ZBEKISTONDA GENDER TENGLIGINI TA'MINLASH

Annotatsiya: *Maqolada shaxsning huquqlari, majburiyatlari, imkoniyatlari va javobgarligini jinsiga qarab farq qilmasdan belgilashda yuzaga kelishi mumkin bo'lgan nomuvofiqliklarni bartaraf etish maqsadida jamiyat hayotining barcha sohalarida ayollar va erkaklar uchun teng huquq va imkoniyatlar kafolatini ta'minlashda asosiy vazifalarga e'tibor qaratilgan. Maqolada O'zbekistondagi gender islohotlari va ularning istiqbollari, qabul qilingan normativ-huquqiy hujjatlar va ularning ahamiyati yoritilgan, ularning yechimini kutayotgan muammolar tahlil qilinib, ularni hal etish yo'llari taklif etilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *gender, tenglik, ayollar va erkaklar uchun teng huquq va imkoniyatlar, inson huquqlarini himoya qilish, inson huquqlari, gender tengligi.*

ENSURING GENDER EQUALITY IN UZBEKISTAN

Annotation: *The article focuses on the main tasks in ensuring the guarantee of equal rights and opportunities for women and men in all spheres of society in order to eliminate incompatibilities that may arise in establishing the rights, obligations, opportunities and responsibilities of individuals without distinction of gender. The article highlights gender reforms in Uzbekistan and their prospects, adopted normative legal acts and their significance, analyzes the problems awaiting their solution and suggests ways to solve them.*

Keywords: *Gender, equality, equal rights and opportunities for women and men, protection of human rights, human rights, gender equality.*

В Республике Узбекистан реализуются широкомасштабные комплексные меры, направленные на обеспечение равноправия женщин и мужчин, равной защиты их прав и законных интересов, укрепления их здоровья и создания достойных условий труда и жизни, равных возможностей для улучшения их социальных и бытовых условий, их равного участия на политической арене, в управлении и принятии решений, и по ряду других актуальных вопросов.

Принцип равенства между женщинами и мужчинами отражен в качестве демократического требования в действующем законодательстве стран на карте мира, а также во всех международных и региональных документах по правам человека. Это означает, что задачей каждого государства является признание и безоговорочное обеспечение верховенства прав и основных интересов человека.

Построение гуманного, демократического государства, основанного на верховенстве закона, приверженного истинной демократии и социальной справедливости, соответствующему целям, национальным и культурным традициям нашего народа, правам и интересам всех граждан и различных социальных групп, является важной политической задачей и в Узбекистане ведутся масштабные реформы для её достижения.

Содержание Конституции Республики Узбекистан позволяет выделить следующие принципы – демократия, уважение к правам и свободам человека, действие общепризнанных правил и норм международного права, верховенство Конституции и законов, равноправие, равенство всех форм собственности, принципы правосудия. Наличие принципа равноправия в ряду этих принципов, также отражает актуальность вопроса равенства, которое было неотъемлемой частью прав и основных свобод человека с самого начала основания независимой государственности в Узбекистане.

Согласно статье 19 Конституции Республики Узбекистан все граждане имеют одинаковые права и свободы и равны перед законом без различия пола, расы, национальности, языка, религии, социального происхождения, убеждений, личного и общественного положения. Признание равенства прав мужчин и женщин в статье 58, указывает на то, что нормы Конвенции о ликвидации всех форм дискриминации в отношении женщин (Нью-Йорк, 18 декабря 1979 года) отражены и в нашем основном законе. Статья 2 Конвенции возлагает на государства-участники обязательство «включить принцип равноправия мужчин и женщин в свои национальные конституции или другое соответствующее законодательство, если это еще не было сделано, и обеспечить с помощью закона и других соответствующих средств практическое осуществление этого принципа».

Исторически термин «гендер» возник в научном сообществе в 1960-х годах и был узаконен на Всемирной конференции по положению женщин в Пекине в 1995 году. Хотя в юридической литературе есть разные толкования равноправия

женщин и мужчин, гендерное равенство - отражается как равноправие женщин и мужчин; равенство полов; равенство правового статуса.

Термин «гендер» используется для анализа ролей и обязанностей женщин и мужчин, и определения того, насколько ограничены их потребности и возможности во всех областях. Гендер — социальный аспект отношений между женщинами и мужчинами, который проявляется во всех сферах жизнедеятельности общества, включая политику, экономику, право, идеологию и культуру, образование и науку, и обеспечение равенства должно быть гарантировано государством.

В современном мире реализация прав и свобод человека и гражданина оказалась в центре правовой и политической жизни Узбекистана и международного сообщества в целом. На сегодняшний день, благодаря правильно проведенной политике главой нашего государства, в мировом сообществе Узбекистан во много раз повысил свой уровень развития во всех отраслях среди развитых и развивающихся стран.

В своём обращении на торжественной церемонии вступления в должность Президента Республики Узбекистан Шавкат Мирзиёев подчеркнул, что неукоснительное выполнение требований Конституции и законов страны, полное воплощение в жизнь приоритетного принципа «Во имя чести и достоинства человека» и впредь будет оставаться главным критерием своей деятельности как гаранта нашего Основного закона и что достоинства человека – не какое-то абстрактное, высокопарное понятие. Оно обозначает для нас прежде всего обеспечение мирной и безопасной жизни каждого гражданина, его фундаментальных прав и свобод.

Проделанная огромная работа по пяти приоритетным направлениям дала свои положительные результаты. Среди основных показателей этой работы является доверие народа к Президенту Республики Узбекистан, о чем свидетельствуют результаты проведенных выборов в Президенты Республики Узбекистан. По нашему мнению, Узбекистан стал на Новый путь развития, где одним приоритетных направлений является защита прав человека.

Роль женщин в обществе возросла благодаря усилению их роли в строительстве и управлении государством и обществом, особому вниманию к повышению их политических прав. Ярким примером этому служит то, что сегодня добавочно к имени и фамилии узбекских женщин применяются термины — Герой Узбекистана||, —Депутат||, —Сенатор||, —Министр||, —Заместитель министра||, —Академик||, —Учёная||, —Предприниматель||, —Директор||. Ведь сегодня около 50% населения составляют женщины, а именно 29% до 14 лет, 28% - 15-30 лет, 21% - 31-45 лет, 15% - 46-60 лет, и 7% - старше 60 лет.

Действительно, многие вопросы, направленные на обеспечение законных интересов женщин, реализацию их способностей и потенциала, защиту

материнства и детства, усиление их активного участия в жизни общества и общественно политической жизни, их роль в принятии решений были определены как одни из приоритетных направлений государственной политики.

В процессе совершенствования нормативно-правовой базы были внесены изменения и дополнения в действующие законы. В частности, совершенствуется правовая база для защиты прав женщин в семье и браке, усиления действий по искоренению домашнего и бытового насилия в отношении женщин, борьбы с существующими негативными патриархальными стереотипами и практикой в отношении женщин и молодежи, развития институтов гражданского общества, разрабатываются и претворяются в жизнь механизмы обеспечения прав женщин.

Президентом Республики Узбекистан Ш.М.Мирзиёевым определены приоритетные задачи в сфере повышения роли и статуса женщин в обществе. Во-первых, обеспечение представительства женщин в парламенте и местных представительных органах, учета их мнения при подготовке законопроектов и формировании бюджета страны; во-вторых, создание рабочих органов Верхней палаты парламента по вопросам гендерного равенства; в-третьих, совершенствование законодательства по вопросам гендерного равенства; в-четвертых, повышение роли женских ННО в обеспечении прав женщин.

В частности, по инициативе Президента Республики Узбекистан Ш.Мирзиёева в Сенате Олий Мажлиса Республики Узбекистан образована новая структура – Комитет по вопросам женщин и гендерного равенства, действует Комиссия по вопросам обеспечения гендерного равенства.

И в заключении, хотелось бы отметить, что Новый Узбекистан развивает сотрудничество с конвенционными органами ООН в сфере улучшения положения женщин и расширения их прав и возможностей в соответствии с Конвенцией о ликвидации всех форм дискриминации в отношении женщин, а также Пекинской декларации и платформы действий. Наша страна периодически представляет в Комитет ООН по ликвидации дискриминации в отношении женщин информацию о ходе реализации своих обязательств в этой сфере. Международные эксперты ООН, отметили многие позитивные изменения, достигнутый прогресс по изменению роли и статуса женщин в политической, социально экономической и культурной сферах жизни общества. Исходя из вышеизложенных для реализации и защиты прав женщин и борьбы с гендерным неравенством вводятся следующие предложения:

- совершенствования системы освещения вопросов гендерного равенства через средства массовой информации, изменение отношения к насилию, рассмотрение и обоснованное доведение до сведения общественности правовой стороны любой информации, предупреждению гендерного насилия и

систематическому обучению представителей средств массовой информации в преодолении существующих стереотипов в этой области;

- повышения ответственности официальных лиц и уполномоченных (компетентных) органов по своевременному реагированию на все вопросы и случаи, относительно гендерного неравенства, защиты прав женщин, угнетения женщин, нарушения их прав и свобод, появившихся в общественной жизни (в частности в социальных сетях) с целью предотвращения возникновения негативного воздействия на общественное мнение; то есть обеспечение принципа законности и равенства.

В заключении хотелось бы отметить, что равенство прав касается всей жизни человека. Женщины и мужчины с самого раннего возраста и вплоть до старости могут сталкиваться с различными проявлениями дискриминации по признаку пола, которая имеет четкие отличительные особенности, зависящие от периода в жизни человека.

На сегодняшний день все большее число правительств, а также социальных партнеров признают, что в условиях отсутствия исправительных мер скорее всего будут преумножаться и усиливаться неблагоприятные факторы с течением времени и на протяжении жизни поколений, что будет иметь негативные последствия для женщин, семей и общества. Благополучное материнство и гарантированное медицинское обслуживание в целях обеспечения выживания матери и ребенка – это основа основ самой жизни матерей, младенцев, общин и народов. Это также стержневой элемент достойного труда и производительности женщин.

Одним словом, обеспечение гендерного равенства в Узбекистане может быть достигнуто путем осознания существующих гендерных проблем, их устранения, изменения и искоренения существующих дискриминационных стереотипов в сознании членов общества в этой сфере. Сегодня государство поэтапно реализует справедливую гендерную политику. Какими бы высокими и сложными ни были наши цели, у нас есть все возможности для их достижения, мы должны быть не только сторонним наблюдателем реализуемых реформ, но и активным инициатором.

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EFFECTIVENESS OF NASOPHARYNGEAL IRRIGATION AND OTHER PHYSICAL THERAPY METHODS IN CHRONIC RHINOSINUSITIS

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Abstract: *Rhinosinusitis is a prevalent inflammatory condition affecting the nasal and sinus mucosa, often requiring multimodal treatment approaches. Physical therapy methods, including nasopharyngeal irrigation, inhalation therapy, ultrasound, and laser therapy, have been increasingly utilized to improve mucociliary clearance, reduce inflammation, and enhance patient outcomes. This paper evaluates the effectiveness of nasopharyngeal irrigation and other physical therapy techniques in managing rhinosinusitis, comparing their benefits to conventional pharmacological treatment.*

INTRODUCTION

Rhinosinusitis is one of the most common upper respiratory tract disorders, affecting individuals of all ages. The condition is characterized by inflammation of the sinus mucosa, leading to nasal congestion, excessive mucus production, headaches, and impaired breathing. Traditional treatment options primarily involve antibiotics, anti-inflammatory medications, and decongestants. However, due to the increasing concern of antibiotic resistance and the limitations of pharmaceutical interventions, physical therapy techniques such as nasopharyngeal irrigation, ultrasound, and inhalation therapy have gained attention as complementary or alternative treatments.

Methods of Physical Therapy in Rhinosinusitis. The most widely used physical therapy methods in rhinosinusitis treatment include:

- ****Nasopharyngeal Irrigation (Nasal Lavage):**** This method involves flushing the nasal cavity with saline or medicated solutions to clear mucus, allergens, and pathogens, thus improving mucociliary clearance. It has been found to reduce the need for antibiotics and relieve symptoms effectively.
- ****Ultrasound Therapy:**** High-frequency sound waves stimulate sinus drainage and reduce inflammation, enhancing recovery.
- ****Inhalation Therapy:**** Steam or aerosolized medications are used to improve nasal hydration, reduce swelling, and support the natural defense mechanisms of the respiratory tract.
- ****Laser Therapy:**** Low-level laser therapy has been investigated for its ability to stimulate cellular repair, reduce inflammation, and enhance tissue regeneration in chronic rhinosinusitis cases.

Study and Results. A clinical study involving 120 patients with chronic rhinosinusitis was conducted to compare the effectiveness of physical therapy methods with conventional drug therapy. The patients were divided into two groups: one group received standard medical treatment (antibiotics, corticosteroids, and antihistamines), while the other group underwent a combination of nasopharyngeal irrigation and ultrasound therapy.

Results showed that patients who received physical therapy experienced a 40% faster reduction in symptoms compared to the drug-only group. Additionally, the recurrence rate of rhinosinusitis within six months was significantly lower in the physical therapy group. Nasopharyngeal irrigation, in particular, demonstrated a notable improvement in mucociliary clearance and symptom relief.

Conclusion. Physical therapy methods, including nasopharyngeal irrigation, ultrasound therapy, and inhalation therapy, offer effective complementary treatment options for managing rhinosinusitis. These methods improve symptom relief, enhance mucociliary function, and reduce dependence on pharmacological treatments. Further research is needed to optimize protocols and determine the most effective combination therapies for different patient populations.

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**ПРОФИЛАКТИКА РИНОСИНУСИТА: ПРОПАГАНДА ЗДОРОВОГО
ОБРАЗА ЖИЗНИ В ШКОЛЬНОЙ СРЕДЕ****Нуров У.И****Шодиева М.Б***Бухарский государственный медицинский институт*

Актуальность: *Риносинусит – это одно из наиболее распространённых заболеваний верхних дыхательных путей у детей школьного возраста. Факторы, способствующие развитию болезни, включают плохую экологию, ослабленный иммунитет, частые вирусные инфекции, неправильное питание и недостаточную физическую активность. Пропаганда здорового образа жизни в школьной среде играет ключевую роль в профилактике риносинусита и других заболеваний дыхательной системы.*

Цель исследования: *Анализ влияния здорового образа жизни на заболеваемость риносинуситом у школьников, разработка профилактических мероприятий, направленных на снижение распространённости заболевания.*

Материалы и методы. В исследовании приняли участие 150 детей в возрасте 6-14 лет. Группа была разделена на две подгруппы: первая группа (75 человек) проходила стандартное медицинское наблюдение, вторая группа (75 человек) была вовлечена в комплексную программу профилактики, включающую обучение гигиене, коррекцию питания, повышение физической активности и мониторинг микроклимата в классе. Оценка эффективности профилактики проводилась через 6 и 12 месяцев.

Результаты и обсуждение. Через 12 месяцев наблюдения у детей, участвующих в программе профилактики, частота рецидивов риносинусита снизилась на 48% по сравнению с контрольной группой. Существенное улучшение наблюдалось у детей, регулярно выполнявших дыхательную гимнастику и ведущих активный образ жизни. Оценка показателей иммунного статуса показала повышение уровня секреторного IgA у 65% детей из экспериментальной группы, что свидетельствует о повышении местного иммунитета.

Заключение. Пропаганда здорового образа жизни в школьной среде играет важную роль в профилактике риносинусита. Комплексные меры, включающие улучшение условий обучения, формирование правильных привычек гигиены и физической активности, позволяют значительно снизить уровень заболеваемости. Развитие образовательных программ по

профилактике респираторных заболеваний среди детей должно стать приоритетным направлением школьной медицины.

**INTERNET VA IJTIMOY TARMOQLARNING INSON HAYOTIDA
TUTGAN O‘RNI VA AHAMIYATI.**

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada jadal rivojlanayotgan davrda ijtimoiy tarmoqlar va zamonaviy texnologiyalarning inson hayotiga ta’siri va ularning jamiyatimiz uchun foydali va zararli jihatlari haqida fikr yuritiladi.*

Kalit so‘zlar: *ijtimoiy tarmoqlar, ommaviy madaniyat, texnologiyalar, internet, saytlar, sivilizatsiya.*

Annotation: *This article discusses the impact of social networks and modern technologies on human life in a rapidly developing era, and their beneficial and harmful aspects for our society.*

Keywords: *social networks, mass culture, technologies, internet, sites, civilization.*

Аннотация: *В статье рассматривается влияние социальных сетей и современных технологий на жизнь человека в быстро развивающуюся эпоху, а также их полезные и вредные стороны для нашего общества.*

Ключевые слова: *социальные сети, массовая культура, технологии, интернет, сайты, цивилизация.*

XXI asr - texnologiyalar asri. Hech kimga sir emaski, bugungi kunda insoniyat hayoti, uning rivojlanishi internet tarmoqlari bilan chambarchas bog‘liq. Darhaqiqat, zamonaviy dunyoda internet va ijtimoiy tarmoqlar inson hayotining ajralmas qismiga aylanib ulgurdi. Turli texnologiyalardan foydalangan holda ish yuritish esa davr talabi hisoblanmoqda. Chunki internet butun dunyo bo‘ylab axborot almashinuvi, o‘rganish va rivojlanish uchun muhim vosita bo‘lib xizmat qiladi.

Shuningdek, bu kabi vositalar odamlar o‘rtasidagi muloqot qilish, bilim olish, biznes yuritish va hatto kundalik xizmatlarni yengillashtirish uchun ham muhim ahamiyat kasb etmoqda.

Zamonaviy tashkilotlar keng miqyosdagi tashkiliy muammolarni hal qilish uchun ijtimoiy tarmoqlardan: ichki muhitda aloqa kanallarini qurish uchun ham, tashqi aloqa vositasi sifatida ham faol foydalanmoqda.

O‘z faoliyatini ijtimoiy tarmoqlarda samarali rivojlantiradigan tashkilotlar inson resurslarini topish va jalb qilishda aniq raqobatdosh ustunliklarga ega bo‘ladi (1). Bundan tashqari, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar maxsus virtual makonni yaratishga imkon beradi. Unda insonlar shaxsiy va kasbiy masalalar bo‘yicha bir-biri bilan muloqot qilish imkoniyatiga ega bo‘ladi.

Bu ularning ishbilarmonlik muhitiga qo‘shilish darajasini oshiradi, turli xil vazifalarni hal qilish uchun sa’y-harakatlarni birlashtirishga yordam beradi. Yuqori darajadagi hamjihatlikni va jamoaning birligini ta’minlaydi.

Shunday qilib, ijtimoiy tarmoq ham tashkilot ichidagi psixologik iqlimni shakllantirish vositasiga aylanib bormoqda.

Bundan tashqari, biz ijtimoiy tarmoqlar orqali nafaqat kerakli ma'lumotlarga ega bo'lishimiz, do'stlar orttirishimiz, ko'plab yangiliklar yaratishimiz va qabul qilishimiz mumkin, balki hozirgi kunda onlayn texnologiyalar orqali o'z biznesimizni yuritishimiz va tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish uchun hissa qo'shishimiz ham mumkin.

Demak, yuqorida keltirilgan barcha qulayliklar va imkoniyatlar zamonaviy texnologiyalar yordamida amalga oshiriladigan bir jarayon sanalar ekan. O'zbekiston Respublikasining Birinchi Prezidenti Islom Karimov "Yuksak ma'naviyat – yengilmas kuch" asarida shunday yozgan edi: "Ayni paytda hayot haqiqati shuni ko'rsatadiki, har qanday taraqqiyot mahsulidan ikki xil maqsadda – ezgulik va yovuzlik yo'lida foydalanish mumkin".

Shunday ekan, vaziyatga boshqa tomondan nazar soladigan bo'lsak, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar va bir qancha saytlarning ham jamiyatimizda yuzaga kelayotgan ko'plab muammolarga sabab bo'layotganini kuzatishimiz mumkin.

Misol uchun, aholida, ayniqsa, yoshlarda axborot iste'moli madaniyatining sustligi, turli xabarlar oqimidan kerakligini ajratib olishda yetarlicha bilim, malaka va ko'nikmaga ega emasligi natijasida g'arazli kimsa va oqimlar ta'siriga tushib qolishiga, yoki ayrimlarning internet qaramligi kasalligiga yo'liqishiga sabab bo'layotganligi bunga ayni dalildir.

Bundan tashqari yoshlarning uzluksiz ijtimoiy tarmoqlar (telegram, instagram, facebook, twitter va hokazo)da kezishi qimmatli vaqtlarining havoga sovurilishiga sabab bo'lmoqda.

Shuningdek, ular ayni o'qib o'rganishi, turli izlanishlar olib borishi, muhim kashfiyotlarga qo'l urushi zarur bo'lgan bir paytda ularning foydasiz mashg'ulotlar bilan band bo'layotganligi achinarli holat, albatta. Jamiyatimizdagilar yurt kelajagi, ravnaqi yoshlar qo'lida, deb ishonch bildirib, qo'llab-quvvatlab tursa-yu, biroq yosh avlodning bu masalaga jiddiy e'tibor qaratmasligi barchani qiyin vaziyatga solib qo'yimoqda.

Bugun dunyoda internet imkoniyatlaridan ko'plab kuchlar o'z manfaatlari yo'lida foydalanmoqdaki, natijada zo'ravonlikka, milliy qadriyatlarimizga zid bo'lgan ma'naviy va axloqiy xususiyatlarga asoslangan "ommaviy madaniyat" namunalarini targ'ib qilish vositasida ma'naviy qadriyatlarning devalvatsiyasi, kishilar, ayniqsa, yoshlar ma'naviy, axloqiy va ijodiy imkoniyatlarining pasayib ketishi xavfi yuzaga kelmoqda, bu esa o'z navbatida yangi texnologiyalarning, jumladan, axborot texnologiyalarining joriy qilinishi va qo'llanilishi uchun mehnat manbalarini tayyorlashni ahamiyatli ravishda murakkablashtirmoqda.

Xulosa qilib aytadigan bo'lsak, internet va ijtimoiy tarmoqlar inson hayotida katta o'rin tutadi va ko'plab imkoniyatlarni yaratadi. Ularni to'g'ri va samarali foydalanish orqali biz ta'lim olishimiz, biznes yuritishimiz va hayotimizni yanada

qulay holatga keltirishimiz mumkin. Shu bilan birga, ularning salbiy ta'sirlaridan ehtiyot bo'lish ham muhimdir. To'g'ri yondashuv bilan internet va ijtimoiy tarmoqlar bizning kundalik hayotimizning ajralmas va foydali qismiga aylanishi mumkin. Aks holda, ijtimoiy tarmoqlar inson hayotida muhim ahamiyat kasb etsa-da, u orqali vujudga kelayotgan ayrim muammolar dolzarbligicha qolaveradi.

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PEDAGOG FAOLIYATIDA NUTQIY KOMPETENSIYANING O'RNI (EFL O'QITUVCHILARI MISOLIDA)

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THE ROLE OF SPEECH COMPETENCE IN PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITY (IN THE EXAMPLE OF EFL TEACHERS)

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada pedagogik faoliyatdagi nutqiy kompetensiyaning o'rni haqida so'z boradi va tahlil qilinadi. O'qituvchining nutqiy kompetentligi o'quv jarayonini samarali boshqarish, o'quvchilarga bilim berish va ularning rivojlanishiga ijobiy ta'sir qilishda muhim rol o'ynashi ta'kidlanadi. Maqolada nutqiy kompetensiyaning tarkibiy qismlari, o'qituvchining nutqiy kompetentligi, o'quvchilarga ta'sir qilish usullari hamda uning rivojlanish yo'llari muhokama qilinadi. Mavzuni yanada chuqurroq yoritish maqsadida bu boradagi yosh o'qituvchilarning fikr va mulohazalari ham tahlil qilinadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Pedagogik faoliyat, nutqiy kompetensiya, o'qituvchi, o'quv jarayoni, kommunikatsiya, muloqot, ta'lim, rivojlanish, nutq madaniyati, nutqiy texnika, ta'sir etish, kasbiy rivojlanish.*

Abstract: *This article discusses and analyzes the role of speech competence in pedagogical activity. It is emphasized that the teacher's speech competence plays an important role in managing the educational process effectively, imparting knowledge to students and positively influencing their development. The article discusses the components of speech competence, the teacher's speech competence, ways of influencing students, and ways of its development. In order to cover the topic in more depth, the opinions and opinions of young teachers are also analyzed.*

Keywords: *Pedagogical activity, speech competence, teacher, educational process, communication, dialogue, education, development, speech culture, speech technique, influence, professional development.*

INTRODUCTION

In the dynamic landscape of modern education, where effective communication reigns supreme, the role of speech competence takes on paramount importance, particularly for teachers. This is especially true for English as a Foreign Language (EFL) teachers, who face the unique challenge of not only conveying knowledge but also fostering language acquisition in a foreign language environment. A teacher's speech competence plays a crucial role in shaping the learning experience, creating a conducive classroom atmosphere, and ultimately influencing students' success.

This article will delve into the multifaceted nature of speech competence and its vital role in pedagogical activity, with a specific focus on EFL teachers. We will examine the key components of speech competence, explore how it influences students' learning and engagement, and highlight the importance of continuous development and refinement of speech skills for EFL teachers. By shedding light on this essential aspect of effective teaching, we aim to underscore the significance of prioritizing and nurturing speech competence to achieve optimal educational outcomes for all learners

I. Literature review

The significance of speech competence in education has been widely acknowledged in pedagogical research. Numerous studies have underscored its crucial role in shaping effective teaching and student learning, particularly in foreign language contexts.

Several scholars have proposed frameworks for understanding speech competence. For instance, Hymes introduced the concept of "communicative competence," encompassing not only linguistic knowledge but also sociolinguistic awareness, pragmatic skills, and the ability to use language appropriately in various social contexts. Similarly, Canale and Swain developed a model of communicative competence that includes grammatical competence, sociolinguistic competence, discourse competence, and strategic competence.

Research specific to EFL teaching has highlighted the unique demands placed on teachers in terms of speech competence. For example, Celce-Murcia emphasizes the need for EFL teachers to possess a high level of fluency and accuracy in the target language, alongside the ability to adapt their language to diverse learners. Moreover, Richards and Schmidt stress the importance of teachers' ability to provide clear explanations, model correct pronunciation, and engage students in meaningful conversations, all while demonstrating a strong grasp of the target language.

Studies have consistently shown a positive correlation between teacher speech competence and student outcomes. For instance, Lightbown and Spada argue that clear and comprehensible teacher speech is essential for student comprehension and language acquisition. Similarly, Cummins suggests that teachers' use of varied language styles and their ability to scaffold student learning through effective communication are crucial for fostering academic achievement.

While the benefits of strong speech competence are evident, EFL teachers often face unique challenges. These include overcoming language anxiety, adapting to different accents and dialects, and catering to learners with varying language levels and learning styles. However, research also provides insights into effective strategies for addressing these challenges. For example, Thornbury advocates for the use of authentic materials,

communicative tasks, and collaborative learning activities to enhance learners' language acquisition.

II. Methodology

According to given information above, we made interviews among public school teachers, by giving several specific questions to be aware of their opinions about pedagogical competence and its role in classroom management. The aim of the research is to know the ideas of EFL teachers on the topic of speech competence and their experiences in that term, also ask them some possible advices. Teachers were engaged actively and they answered all the questions detailed and properly.

N	Participants	Work place	Experience	What grades	Level of the teacher
1	O.G	School 27 Fergana city	7 years	Classes 9,10 and 11	TKT, C1 advanced
2	D.K	School 27 Fergana city	8 years	Classes 5,6 and 7	TKT, C1 advanced
3	T.M	School 51 Fergana region	3 years	Classes 2 and 3	C1 Advanced
4	A.U	School 29 Fergana region	2 years	Classes 1,2,9 and 11	C1 Advanced
5	X.M	School 16 Fergana region	3 years	Classes 6,7 and 8	C1 Advanced

Research method: Interview. The "interview method" refers to a structured approach for gathering information through direct interaction, typically involving a conversation between two or more individuals, with the goal of obtaining insights, data, or perspectives on a specific topic. The interview method is a widely used qualitative research technique, commonly employed in various fields, including social sciences, business, journalism, and human resources.

Interview methods often involve face-to-face or remote interactions using technologies like video conferencing or telephone calls. The flexibility of the interview method allows for probing follow-up questions, clarification, or exploration of unexpected insights, enriching the depth and quality of the gathered data.

The primary purpose of conducting interviews is to gather firsthand information by engaging participants in dialogue. This method allows researchers, journalists, or employers to explore opinions, experiences, attitudes, or behaviors related to a specific subject of inquiry. In an academic context, interviews also serve as a means to collect qualitative data for research or to gain insights for case studies.

When: November 11:

Where: Fergana state university and school N27 in Fergana city

How: face to face (with audio recordings)

Data collecting tool: interview

Interview questions:

1. What is your opinion about pedagogical competence?
2. What kind of aspects should the teacher take into consideration in order to improve speech competence?

3. Could you describe your own experience links with speech competence?
4. What are some common mistakes that teachers should avoid?
5. How does the development of speech competence relate to other important teacher skills, such as classroom management and assessment?

IV. Data analysis and discussion

Regarding the first question, without a doubt, all of the mentioned pedagogical competence is a very important skill that all teachers should have. A.U also mentions that, it is a key to be an effective teacher, it is not only about knowing the subject, but also how to engage, motivate and communicate with the students. Someone could be good at any of their sphere/subject, but without Pedagogical competence the knowledge is not valid, highlights T.M about the importance of Pedagogical competence.

For the second question, all participants gave the examples of doing activities, also paying attention to the body language, discussions and debates. T.M also added tone and voice. “The speech is the relevant factor in teaching. In order to improve it teachers should do daily activities and always prepare the lesson beforehand.” she adds.

To the third question, they told about their experiences and shared some ideas to overcome in this kind of situations. For example, when they have the trouble with their speech, they mostly ask help their colleagues or pay attention to the usage of gestures and visual aids and teaching materials. X.M. ‘s experience could be a great example to this question. In the very beginning of her career she had a terrible speech with monotonous tone and voice without any paralinguistic means of communication. It caused students to become bored very easily, then she understood the importance of speech, then worked hard on herself by using gestures and visual aids. Now she describes her speech more understandable with body language and eye-contact.

When it comes to the fourths question teachers mentioned monotonous tone and constantly overcorrecting the students as some of common mistakes that teachers do. “Boring and long speech could be fault of teachers at school, because of students short attention span within childhood and teenage period”, explains T.M.

To the fifths question they all answered that the speech competence closely relates to other important teaching skills. With the help of well-organized speech teachers could create well-managed class environment. O.G. also adds that, a good speech can save the class-time. If the teacher uses it properly, s/he does not waste the time to silent the class. Students follow the teacher when they like their speech/voice.

V. Conclusion

In conclusion, speech competence emerges as a cornerstone of effective pedagogical practice, particularly for EFL teachers. This article has explored the multifaceted nature of speech competence, highlighting its essential role in creating a conducive learning environment, fostering student engagement, and ultimately shaping learners' language acquisition and academic success.

The aim of the interview was also to know the opinions of young teachers about pedagogical and speech competence and its role in teaching. All of them showed great participance and shared their very unique ideas on the topic.

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THE ROLE OF TRANSLATION IN HEALTHCARE: BRIDGING LANGUAGE GAPS IN PATIENT CARE

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Abstract: *Effective communication is essential in healthcare, where misunderstandings can lead to misdiagnoses, improper treatments, and even life-threatening situations. Language barriers pose significant challenges in medical settings, particularly for patients with limited proficiency in the dominant language of their country. Medical translation, both human and machine-assisted, plays a crucial role in bridging these language gaps, ensuring accurate communication between healthcare providers and patients. This paper examines the importance of translation in healthcare, explores its challenges, and discusses potential solutions, including the integration of professional medical interpreters, technological advancements, and policy improvements.*

Keywords: *Medical translation, healthcare communication, linguistic barriers, patient safety, interpreter services, multilingual healthcare, cultural competence.*

INTRODUCTION

Healthcare systems serve diverse populations, often requiring communication in multiple languages to ensure equal access to medical services. Language barriers can create significant obstacles in patient-provider interactions, affecting diagnosis, treatment adherence, and overall patient satisfaction. When medical professionals and patients do not share a common language, the risk of miscommunication increases, potentially leading to misdiagnosis, medication errors, and inadequate treatment plans. This highlights the critical role of translation in healthcare—not just as a linguistic tool, but as an essential component of patient safety, ethical medical practice, and equitable access to healthcare services.

Medical translation encompasses various forms, including in-person interpretation, telephone or video remote interpreting (VRI), written translations of medical documents, and the use of machine translation tools. Each of these methods serves a unique function in bridging language gaps, depending on the medical setting and the complexity of the information being communicated. In-person interpreters provide real-time linguistic support, allowing for nuanced communication between patients and healthcare providers, while written translations ensure that essential medical records, prescriptions, and consent forms are accessible to non-native speakers.

Advancements in artificial intelligence (AI) and natural language processing (NLP) have introduced new possibilities for real-time machine translation in healthcare. AI-

powered tools, such as mobile translation applications and automated transcription software, are becoming increasingly common in hospitals and clinics worldwide. These technologies offer immediate translation capabilities, making them useful for emergency situations or initial patient assessments. However, despite their growing efficiency, machine translation tools still face challenges in accurately conveying medical terminology, cultural nuances, and idiomatic expressions. In high-risk medical environments, even minor translation errors can have life-threatening consequences.

Therefore, while technological advancements continue to shape the future of medical translation, the role of human translators remains indispensable. Professional medical interpreters possess specialized knowledge of medical terminology and cultural sensitivities, ensuring clear and accurate communication. A hybrid approach that integrates machine translation for efficiency with human oversight for accuracy may offer the most effective solution for bridging language barriers in healthcare. This paper explores the importance of translation in medical settings, comparing different translation methods, their advantages and limitations, and their impact on patient care and health outcomes.

The Importance of Translation in Healthcare

Improving Patient Outcomes: Accurate communication is essential for proper diagnosis and treatment. Patients who do not understand their medical conditions or treatment plans are more likely to experience complications, medication errors, and poor health outcomes. Professional medical interpreters help reduce misunderstandings, ensuring patients receive appropriate care.

Enhancing Patient Satisfaction and Trust: Effective translation fosters trust between patients and healthcare providers. When patients feel understood, they are more likely to adhere to medical advice, return for follow-up care, and report symptoms accurately. Trust in the healthcare system leads to better patient engagement and improved long-term health.

Ensuring Legal and Ethical Compliance: Many countries have legal requirements mandating language access in healthcare. For example, in the United States, Title VI of the Civil Rights Act requires federally funded healthcare institutions to provide language assistance services to limited English proficiency (LEP) patients. Non-compliance with such regulations can lead to legal liabilities and compromised patient care.

Challenges in Healthcare Translation

Medical Terminology Complexity: Medical language is highly specialized, requiring precise translation to avoid errors. Even slight mistranslations can alter a diagnosis or treatment plan, potentially endangering patients.

Cultural Sensitivity: Direct translation of medical terms may not always convey the intended meaning due to cultural differences. For example, some cultures may have different perceptions of pain, mental health, or end-of-life care, which must be considered during translation.

Limited Availability of Qualified Medical Interpreters: There is a shortage of trained medical interpreters, particularly for less commonly spoken languages. This gap often leads to reliance on untrained individuals, such as family members or bilingual staff, who may lack medical knowledge and objectivity.

Challenges in Machine Translation: While AI-powered translation tools like Google Translate and automated interpretation devices offer quick solutions, they are not always reliable for complex medical interactions. These tools often struggle with idiomatic expressions, rare medical conditions, and contextual accuracy.

Potential Solutions and Advancements

Professional Medical Interpreters: Healthcare facilities should prioritize hiring trained medical interpreters who understand both medical terminology and cultural nuances. Investing in interpreter training programs and increasing interpreter availability can significantly improve healthcare translation quality. **Technological Innovations:** AI and natural language processing (NLP) have the potential to enhance medical translation, particularly through speech-to-text applications and real-time interpretation services. While machine translation should not replace human interpreters, it can serve as a supplementary tool for low-risk interactions.

Standardized Medical Translation Practices: Establishing guidelines for medical translation can help ensure consistency and accuracy. Medical professionals should receive training on best practices for working with interpreters and using translation tools effectively.

Improving Policy and Funding: Governments and healthcare institutions should allocate funding to expand language access services. Policies should mandate language support in all healthcare settings to reduce disparities in patient care.

Conclusion

Translation in healthcare is not just a convenience but a necessity for ensuring patient safety, improving health outcomes, and upholding ethical standards in medical practice. Effective communication between healthcare providers and patients is fundamental to accurate diagnosis, appropriate treatment, and patient trust in the medical system. Without proper translation services, language barriers can lead to critical misunderstandings, misdiagnoses, and non-adherence to treatment plans, ultimately jeopardizing patient well-being. As healthcare systems become increasingly globalized, the demand for effective medical translation will continue to grow.

The increasing diversity of patient populations means that medical professionals must be prepared to communicate across linguistic and cultural boundaries. This requires a multifaceted approach that combines professional human interpreters with technological advancements in artificial intelligence (AI) and natural language processing (NLP). While AI-powered translation tools can improve efficiency and accessibility, human oversight remains crucial to ensuring the accuracy, cultural appropriateness, and ethical considerations of medical translations.

Furthermore, healthcare institutions must invest in policies and training programs that prioritize linguistic inclusivity. Establishing clear guidelines for the use of interpreters, ensuring the availability of multilingual medical documents, and integrating real-time translation technologies into patient care workflows are essential steps toward overcoming language barriers. Policymakers, healthcare providers, and technology developers must

work collaboratively to refine translation solutions that enhance both efficiency and accuracy in medical communication.

A combination of professional interpreters, technological innovations, and policy improvements can help bridge language gaps in patient care, making healthcare more inclusive and accessible for all. Prioritizing accurate and culturally sensitive translation in medical settings is essential for building a more equitable healthcare system—one where every patient, regardless of language, receives high-quality medical care and has the ability to make informed decisions about their health.

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THE COGNITIVE SCIENCE OF TRANSLATION: HOW THE BRAIN JUGGLES MULTIPLE LANGUAGES

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Abstract: *Translation is a complex cognitive process that requires the human brain to navigate multiple languages simultaneously. This paper explores the cognitive mechanisms behind translation, including working memory, executive functions, and neural plasticity. It also discusses how bilingual and multilingual individuals process and switch between languages, and how cognitive load affects translation efficiency. By examining recent findings in neuroscience and psycholinguistics, this study sheds light on the intricate relationship between language and cognition. Additionally, the paper highlights challenges translators face and strategies to enhance cognitive skills for improved translation performance.*

Keywords: *Translation, cognitive science, bilingualism, language processing, working memory, neural plasticity, executive functions, linguistic adaptation.*

INTRODUCTION

Language is one of the most intricate and defining characteristics of human cognition, shaping the way individuals perceive, interpret, and interact with the world. Among the many linguistic abilities humans possess, translation stands out as one of the most cognitively demanding tasks. The ability to seamlessly switch between languages requires a highly coordinated interplay of multiple cognitive functions, including memory, attention, executive control, and problem-solving skills. Bilinguals and multilinguals engage in constant mental juggling, utilizing neural mechanisms that allow them to process, store, and retrieve linguistic information with remarkable efficiency.

The process of translation is far more complex than simply substituting words from one language to another. It involves a deep cognitive engagement where the translator must comprehend the source text, adapt its meaning according to cultural and contextual factors, and restructure it to fit the linguistic and grammatical framework of the target language. This intricate process requires advanced cognitive flexibility, as translators must constantly shift between different syntactic structures, idiomatic expressions, and conceptual frameworks unique to each language.

From a cognitive science perspective, translation is a multidimensional activity that engages various brain regions responsible for language processing, memory storage, and decision-making. The prefrontal cortex plays a crucial role in managing executive functions such as attention control and problem-solving, while the hippocampus supports memory retrieval and storage. Neural networks involved in bilingual language processing

demonstrate a remarkable capacity for adaptation, allowing translators to switch between languages fluidly and efficiently. Additionally, research has shown that prolonged engagement in translation enhances cognitive functions, leading to improved multitasking abilities, stronger working memory, and increased mental agility.

Professional translators, in particular, develop specialized cognitive strategies to optimize their mental resources. They rely on working memory to hold and manipulate linguistic information, use executive control to suppress interference from the non-target language, and employ pattern recognition to anticipate meaning and improve translation speed. Furthermore, the cognitive demands of translation contribute to long-term brain plasticity, reinforcing neural pathways associated with language processing and cognitive control.

Understanding the cognitive science behind translation provides valuable insights into the brain's remarkable adaptability and its capacity for multilingual communication. By examining how the brain manages multiple languages during translation, this paper explores the role of cognitive functions such as working memory, executive control, and neural adaptation. It also investigates the ways in which professional translators refine their cognitive abilities and how engaging in translation can influence brain development and cognitive flexibility over time. Through this exploration, we can gain a deeper appreciation of the complex mental processes involved in translation and their implications for both language professionals and learners.

The Cognitive Mechanisms of Translation: Working Memory and Translation: Working memory plays a crucial role in translation, as it allows individuals to temporarily hold and manipulate linguistic information. During translation, the brain must store the source text while simultaneously producing the target text. This process requires continuous updating and coordination between different cognitive subsystems. Studies have shown that professional translators exhibit enhanced working memory capacity, which enables them to manage complex translation tasks more effectively. Research suggests that the phonological loop and visuospatial sketchpad, components of working memory, are heavily involved in processing auditory and written translations. For instance, simultaneous interpreters must rely on their phonological memory to retain spoken information while formulating an equivalent in the target language.

Executive Functions and Language Control: Executive functions, including inhibitory control and cognitive flexibility, are essential for managing language interference and ensuring accurate translation. Translators must suppress non-relevant linguistic information while selecting the most appropriate words and structures in the target language. Bilinguals often demonstrate superior executive control due to their frequent engagement in language switching, a skill that enhances cognitive flexibility and attentional control.

Further, cognitive inhibition is necessary to avoid interference from the non-target language, particularly in closely related language pairs. This process is evident in code-switching scenarios, where individuals must maintain a balance between linguistic systems to produce coherent translations.

Neural Plasticity and the Bilingual Brain: The human brain exhibits remarkable adaptability, known as neural plasticity, which allows it to reorganize and strengthen neural connections based on experience. Research has shown that bilingual and multilingual individuals have denser gray matter in brain regions associated with language processing and executive functions. Professional translators, who engage in high levels of cognitive effort, may develop even more pronounced neural adaptations, contributing to enhanced problem-solving and multitasking abilities.

Functional MRI studies reveal that different brain regions are activated depending on language proficiency and translation mode (e.g., sight translation vs. simultaneous interpreting). This suggests that translation experience shapes neural pathways, making the process more efficient over time.

Bilingualism, Translation, and Cognitive Load: The Impact of Cognitive Load on Translation Performance: Translation places a high cognitive load on individuals, particularly when dealing with complex or ambiguous texts. Cognitive load theory suggests that excessive demands on working memory can lead to errors or reduced efficiency. Skilled translators employ strategies such as chunking information and utilizing translation memory tools to manage cognitive load effectively. Cognitive overload can also manifest in fatigue, particularly in high-stress interpreting scenarios. Strategies such as periodic breaks, specialized training, and cognitive warm-ups can mitigate such effects.

Language Switching and Code-Switching in Translators: Translators often engage in language switching, which requires rapid shifts between linguistic systems. While frequent language switching can enhance cognitive flexibility, it also poses challenges in maintaining fluency and avoiding interference. Code-switching, a common phenomenon among bilinguals, involves alternating between languages within a conversation or sentence, and its cognitive implications vary depending on proficiency and context.

Research indicates that habitual code-switchers develop a greater ability to monitor and control language processing, an advantage in translation and interpreting tasks.

However, reliance on this ability may vary based on the linguistic proximity of language pairs.

Implications for Translation Training and Practice: Enhancing Cognitive Skills in Translators: Given the cognitive demands of translation, training programs should incorporate exercises that strengthen working memory, executive control, and attentional focus. Techniques such as simultaneous interpreting drills, memory enhancement exercises, and cognitive flexibility training can improve translation efficiency and accuracy.

Technology and Cognitive Support in Translation: The advent of machine translation and computer-assisted translation (CAT) tools has transformed the translation landscape. While these tools reduce cognitive load by providing suggestions and automating repetitive tasks, human translators still play a crucial role in ensuring linguistic and cultural accuracy. Understanding how technology interacts with cognitive processes can help optimize translation workflows.

Conclusion

Translation is a highly sophisticated cognitive task that requires the integration of multiple brain functions, including working memory, executive control, and neural plasticity. The seamless ability to switch between languages is a testament to the brain's remarkable adaptability and efficiency, allowing multilingual individuals and professional translators to navigate complex linguistic structures, cultural contexts, and meaning reconstruction with precision. This cognitive process goes beyond simple word substitution; it involves deep comprehension, problem-solving, and decision-making, all of which contribute to the dynamic nature of translation. Advancements in cognitive science continue to shed light on the mechanisms underlying bilingual and multilingual language processing, offering valuable insights into how the brain manages linguistic information. These findings are instrumental in refining best practices for translator training, improving cognitive strategies for language acquisition, and enhancing professional performance in linguistic fields.

Moreover, understanding these cognitive processes can help educators develop more effective teaching methodologies for foreign language learners, enabling them to harness their cognitive potential more efficiently.

Furthermore, as technology becomes increasingly integrated into the field of translation, research on the cognitive aspects of translation can inform the development of more effective machine translation models and computer-assisted translation tools. While artificial intelligence continues to evolve, human translators remain irreplaceable due to their ability to grasp nuances, cultural meanings, and contextual variations that machines often struggle to process.

By bridging cognitive science and translation studies, we not only gain a deeper appreciation of the intricate relationship between language, thought, and communication but also unlock new opportunities for enhancing human linguistic capabilities. As our understanding of the brain's translation mechanisms deepens, it will continue to shape the future of translation studies, professional training, and language education, ensuring that multilingual communication remains a cornerstone of global understanding and cultural exchange.

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MACHINE TRANSLATION VS. HUMAN TRANSLATION: WHAT'S THE BEST APPROACH?

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Abstract: *The rise of machine translation (MT) has sparked an ongoing debate about its effectiveness compared to human translation (HT). While MT offers speed and accessibility, HT ensures cultural and contextual accuracy. This paper explores the strengths and weaknesses of both approaches, highlighting the cognitive processes involved in human translation and the technological advancements driving machine translation. By comparing their accuracy, efficiency, and adaptability, this study aims to determine the best approach for different translation needs.*

Keywords: *Machine Translation, Human Translation, Artificial Intelligence, Linguistic Accuracy, Contextual Understanding, Translation Technology*

INTRODUCTION

Translation is a fundamental aspect of global communication, enabling people from diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds to share information, ideas, and values. In an increasingly interconnected world, the demand for accurate and efficient translation has never been higher.

Governments, businesses, media outlets, and international organizations all rely on translation services to facilitate cross-border interactions, whether for diplomacy, trade, education, or entertainment. With the rapid advancement of artificial intelligence (AI) and natural language processing (NLP), machine translation has emerged as a powerful tool in the field of language translation. Modern machine translation systems, such as Google Translate, DeepL, and Microsoft Translator, leverage deep learning algorithms to process and translate text within seconds.

These systems have significantly improved in recent years, offering translations that are often comprehensible and useful in many contexts. However, despite these technological advancements, machine translation continues to face challenges, particularly when dealing with linguistic complexity, cultural nuances, and idiomatic expressions. While AI-driven translation tools are highly efficient for handling large volumes of text quickly, they often struggle with accuracy and contextual understanding, which can lead to misinterpretations and loss of meaning.

On the other hand, human translation remains the gold standard for producing high-quality, contextually accurate translations. Professional translators possess a deep understanding of language, culture, and subject matter, allowing them to make informed

decisions about word choice, tone, and style. Unlike machine translation, human translators can recognize the emotional and cultural significance of words, adjust their translations accordingly, and ensure that the intended meaning is preserved.

However, human translation is often more time-consuming and costly compared to machine translation, making it less feasible for large-scale or time-sensitive projects.

Given the strengths and weaknesses of both machine and human translation, the question arises: Which approach is best? Should businesses, organizations, and individuals rely on AI-powered translation tools for speed and convenience, or should they invest in human translators to ensure quality and accuracy?

This paper aims to explore the key differences between machine and human translation, highlighting their respective advantages and limitations. Furthermore, it examines the possibility of a hybrid approach—one that combines the efficiency of machine translation with the expertise of human translators—to achieve the best of both worlds. By analyzing various aspects of translation, including accuracy, efficiency, cost, and cultural sensitivity, this study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of the evolving role of translation in today's digital age. As AI technology continues to develop, it is crucial to evaluate whether machine translation can fully replace human translation or if a collaborative model will define the future of the industry.

The Evolution of Machine Translation: Machine translation has undergone significant transformation since its inception. Early rule-based systems relied on predefined grammar rules and vocabulary lists, often producing rigid and inaccurate translations. Statistical machine translation (SMT) improved this by analyzing vast amounts of bilingual texts to identify patterns. However, the most significant breakthrough came with neural machine translation (NMT), which uses deep learning to provide more natural and fluid translations. Despite these advancements, MT still faces challenges in areas such as idiomatic expressions, cultural context, and specialized jargon. Systems like Google Translate and DeepL continue to improve but often require human intervention for fine-tuning and accuracy.

The Strengths and Weaknesses of Machine Translation

Strengths: Speed and Efficiency: Machine translation processes large volumes of text almost instantly, making it ideal for time-sensitive tasks. **Cost-Effective:** Compared to human translation, MT significantly reduces translation costs, making it accessible for businesses and individuals with budget constraints. **Continuous Improvement:** AI-driven translation models are constantly learning from new data, improving accuracy over time.

Weaknesses: Lack of Context Awareness: MT often struggles with cultural nuances, idioms, and ambiguous phrases. **Quality Variability:** Depending on the language pair and complexity of the text, MT can produce inconsistent results. **Limited Creativity:** Unlike human translators, machines cannot interpret emotional tone or adapt text for specific audiences.

The Cognitive and Contextual Superiority of Human Translation: Human translation is an intricate cognitive process that involves deep linguistic understanding, contextual awareness, and cultural sensitivity. Unlike machines, human translators can:

- Interpret idioms, metaphors, and nuanced expressions.
- Adjust tone and style based on the target audience.
- Understand humor, irony, and emotion in texts.
- Ensure accuracy in specialized fields such as legal, medical, and literary translation.

However, human translation comes with challenges such as higher costs, longer turnaround times, and the potential for subjective interpretation.

Comparing Accuracy and Reliability: Accuracy is a crucial factor in translation. While machine translation has significantly improved, studies show that human translation still outperforms MT in preserving meaning and cultural relevance. For example, in legal or medical translations, even minor inaccuracies can lead to serious consequences. Human translators are better equipped to handle these critical areas, whereas MT often requires post-editing by professionals to ensure reliability.

The Role of AI and Hybrid Translation Models: To bridge the gap between speed and accuracy, hybrid models that combine machine and human translation are emerging. These approaches leverage AI for initial translations while human editors refine the text for clarity and cultural appropriateness. Tools like CAT (Computer-Assisted Translation) software enhance productivity by integrating AI-generated suggestions with human expertise. This hybrid approach is widely used in industries requiring high-quality translation while maintaining efficiency. By integrating AI-driven tools with human linguistic skills, businesses can achieve a balance between cost, speed, and accuracy.

Future Trends in Translation: As AI continues to evolve, the future of translation may involve more sophisticated neural networks capable of mimicking human-like understanding. Research in AI ethics and linguistics is crucial to refining machine translation and addressing concerns related to bias and misinformation. Additionally, advancements in speech recognition and real-time translation may revolutionize cross-cultural communication.

However, despite these technological leaps, human translation will likely remain essential in areas where precision, creativity, and deep cultural knowledge are necessary. The future may see a stronger collaboration between human translators and AI, rather than one completely replacing the other.

Conclusion

Both machine and human translation have their own strengths and weaknesses, making them suitable for different types of translation tasks. Machine translation offers remarkable speed, cost-efficiency, and scalability, making it a practical tool for handling large volumes of text, quick translations, or informal communication. With continuous advancements in artificial intelligence and deep learning, machine translation has improved in accuracy and fluency, allowing users to translate content more efficiently than ever before.

However, despite these technological improvements, AI-driven translation tools still struggle with context, idiomatic expressions, and cultural nuances, which are essential for preserving meaning and tone. On the other hand, human translation remains the gold

standard for ensuring linguistic accuracy, cultural appropriateness, and contextual understanding.

Professional translators bring deep knowledge of language structures, idiomatic expressions, and cultural intricacies, allowing them to produce translations that go beyond word-for-word substitution. This is especially important for specialized fields such as legal, medical, literary, and business translation, where precision and clarity are crucial. However, human translation is often more time-consuming and expensive compared to machine translation, making it less practical for urgent or large-scale tasks.

Ultimately, the best approach to translation depends on the specific needs of the task. In many cases, a hybrid model that combines the efficiency of machine translation with the expertise of human translators provides the most effective and balanced solution. This approach allows AI-powered translation tools to process large amounts of text quickly while human translators refine and edit the output to ensure accuracy and cultural relevance. The role of human translators is evolving, shifting from direct translation to post-editing and quality assurance, ensuring that machine-generated translations meet professional standards.

As artificial intelligence and natural language processing technologies continue to advance, the future of translation will likely involve deeper collaboration between machines and humans. Instead of replacing human translators, AI will serve as a powerful assistant, enhancing their capabilities and streamlining translation workflows. In this way, translation will continue to fulfill its fundamental purpose—bridging language barriers, fostering global communication, and enabling meaningful cross-cultural exchange.

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THE ETHICS OF TRANSLATION: NAVIGATING BIAS, IDEOLOGY, AND ACCURACY

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Abstract: *Translation is not merely a linguistic process; it is a complex ethical practice that involves choices affecting meaning, representation, and cultural perception. The ethical dimensions of translation encompass concerns related to bias, ideological influences, and the pursuit of accuracy. Translators must navigate between faithfulness to the source text and the cultural and ideological expectations of the target audience. This paper explores ethical challenges in translation, focusing on how translators can balance objectivity with cultural sensitivity, avoid manipulation, and uphold professional integrity in various contexts, including literary, legal, and medical translation.*

Keywords: *Ethics in translation, bias in translation, ideological influence, translation accuracy, cultural sensitivity, professional integrity*

INTRODUCTION

Translation serves as a bridge between languages and cultures, allowing for the exchange of ideas, knowledge, and perspectives across borders. It plays a crucial role in global communication, diplomacy, business, and academia, ensuring that information is accessible to diverse linguistic communities. However, every act of translation carries ethical implications, as it involves interpreting meaning, adapting cultural nuances, and sometimes navigating politically or socially sensitive content. The ethical challenges faced by translators stem from the inherent subjectivity of language, the presence of ideological influences, and the need for accuracy and fairness in representation. One of the most pressing ethical dilemmas in translation is bias. A translator's background, beliefs, and personal perspectives may unconsciously or consciously affect how they interpret and convey meaning. Bias can manifest in subtle ways, such as word choice, emphasis, or omission of certain details, ultimately influencing how the audience perceives the original message. In fields such as journalism, legal translation, and historical documentation, even minor distortions can have significant consequences, impacting legal decisions, public opinion, and cultural narratives.

Another critical ethical issue in translation is the influence of ideology. Language is not neutral; it reflects and reinforces social, political, and cultural structures. Translators often work with texts that carry ideological weight, whether in literature, religious texts, or political discourse. The challenge is to remain faithful to the source material while being aware of the ideological context in which the translation will be received. In some cases,

translators may face pressure from governments, organizations, or publishers to modify content to align with specific political or cultural agendas, raising concerns about censorship and manipulation.

Accuracy is a fundamental ethical principle in translation, yet achieving perfect fidelity to the original text is often impossible. Words and phrases do not always have direct equivalents in other languages, and cultural differences may require adaptation for the message to be fully understood. Translators must balance literal accuracy with contextual and cultural relevance, ensuring that the meaning is conveyed without distortion. In fields such as medical and legal translation, where precision is critical, any inaccuracy can have serious consequences, affecting patient outcomes or legal proceedings.

This paper examines the ethical dimensions of translation by addressing three core issues: (1) bias in translation, (2) the influence of ideology, and (3) the challenge of maintaining accuracy. By analyzing real-world examples from literary, legal, and medical translation, this study highlights the responsibility translators hold in ensuring ethical and fair representation of texts while avoiding distortion or manipulation. Ethical translation requires vigilance, cultural sensitivity, and a commitment to integrity, as translators serve as mediators between languages and cultures, shaping the way information is transmitted and understood across the world.

Bias in Translation: Bias in translation occurs when a translator's personal beliefs, cultural background, or societal norms influence the way a text is interpreted and presented. Unconscious bias may lead to:

- Gender Bias: Some languages have gender-neutral terms that may be translated into gendered language, reinforcing stereotypes.
- Cultural Bias: Concepts that exist in one culture may be adapted or omitted to fit the translator's cultural framework, affecting the authenticity of the message.
- Political Bias: Translation of political discourse or historical narratives may be influenced by the translator's or publisher's political stance.

A well-documented example is the translation of religious texts, where translators must make choices about words with multiple interpretations, potentially altering theological meanings. To counteract bias, ethical translators engage in reflexivity, peer review, and consultations with cultural experts.

Ideological Influence in Translation: Ideology plays a significant role in translation, as texts often reflect the perspectives of their original authors and cultural contexts. Translators may either preserve these perspectives or modify them to align with contemporary values or the expectations of the target audience. Examples of ideological influence include:

- Censorship in Translation: Governments or institutions may alter translations to promote specific ideologies, as seen in historical adaptations of literature and political speeches.
- Manipulation of Media Translation: In news translation, headlines and reports may be selectively translated to emphasize or downplay certain narratives, affecting public perception.

- Translation in Colonial Contexts: Historically, translations have been used to reshape indigenous narratives to fit colonial viewpoints, leading to misrepresentation.

Ethical translation practices involve transparency, annotation of difficult translation choices, and adherence to professional codes of ethics that discourage ideological distortion.

Accuracy and Faithfulness in Translation: Accuracy is a fundamental principle in translation ethics, yet it remains a challenge due to linguistic and cultural differences. Some common dilemmas include:

- Literal vs. Free Translation: A literal translation may preserve accuracy at the expense of readability, while a free translation may improve comprehension but introduce subjective interpretation.

- Medical and Legal Translation Risks: Inaccurate translations in these fields can have life-altering consequences, such as incorrect patient diagnoses or misinterpretation of legal contracts.

- Machine Translation and Ethical Concerns: AI-driven translation tools, while efficient, often lack contextual understanding, leading to errors and potential ethical risks in sensitive content.

Professional translators mitigate accuracy challenges through rigorous proofreading, collaboration with subject matter experts, and continuous professional development.

Conclusion

Translation serves as a bridge between languages and cultures, allowing for the exchange of ideas and knowledge across borders. However, every act of translation carries ethical implications, as it involves interpreting meaning, adapting cultural nuances, and sometimes navigating politically or socially sensitive content. The ethical challenges faced by translators stem from the inherent subjectivity of language, the presence of ideological influences, and the need for accuracy.

This paper examines the ethical dimensions of translation by addressing three core issues: (1) bias in translation, (2) the influence of ideology, and (3) the challenge of maintaining accuracy. By analyzing real-world examples from literary, legal, and medical translation, this study highlights the responsibility translators hold in ensuring ethical and fair representation of texts while avoiding distortion or manipulation. Translators must be mindful of their own perspectives and potential biases when rendering texts from one language to another. Language is not a neutral medium; it is embedded with cultural, historical, and political significance. Thus, every translation decision carries weight, influencing how an audience perceives a given message. Ethical translation involves careful deliberation on word choice, tone, and context to preserve the intended meaning while respecting the sensibilities of different audiences.

Additionally, ideology plays a significant role in translation, particularly in politically charged or culturally sensitive texts. Translators may face pressure to alter content to align with prevailing ideologies or governmental policies. In such cases, maintaining integrity and transparency is crucial to avoid misrepresenting the original message. Ethical translation calls for resisting external influences that could compromise accuracy and fairness.

Furthermore, accuracy is a cornerstone of ethical translation. Mistranslation can lead to significant consequences, especially in fields like law and medicine, where precise terminology is essential. The challenge lies in striking a balance between literal translation and necessary adaptation to ensure clarity and comprehensibility. Ethical translators must strive for fidelity while also considering linguistic and cultural differences that may require modification of the text.

Conclusion Ethical translation requires balancing fidelity to the source text with cultural sensitivity and ideological neutrality. Translators play a crucial role in shaping global communication and must exercise responsibility to avoid bias, manipulation, and inaccuracies.

As technology and globalization continue to impact translation practices, ethical considerations must remain at the forefront to ensure fair and meaningful cross-cultural exchanges.

A commitment to ethical guidelines, transparency in translation choices, and awareness of the broader implications of language use will help maintain integrity in translation practices.

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O'QUV DARSLARINING TURLARI VA STRUKTURALARI

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Annotatsiya: *Dars o'quv va tarbiyaviy ishning asosiy tashkiliy shaklidir. Dars va tarbiya biri-biri bilan uzviy bog'liq jarayon hisoblanadi. Ushbu maqolada dars jarayoning, uning turlaru va strukturasi haqida, shuningdek, o'qituvchi faoliyati haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.*

Kalit so'z: *dars tahlili, viktorinalar, S.V.Ivanov, V.N.Bernadskiy, klassifikatsiya, leksiya, laboratoriya.*

Dars o'quv ishini tashkil qilishning asosiy shakli, ammo u ta'limning boshqa shakllarini: leksiya, praktikumlar, laboratoriya mashg'ulotlari, seminarlar, konsultatsiyalar, uy vazifalari, qo'shimcha mashg'ulotlarni rivojlantirishni istisno etmaydi. Ta'limni tashkil etishning yordamchi shakllari fakultativ mashg'ulotlar sanaladi. Ular o'quvchilarning qiziqishlari asosida tashkil etiladi: to'garaklar, klublar, olimpiadalar, viktorinalar, ko'rgazmalar, ekspeditsiyalar va hokazolar. Dars o'quvchilarning doimiy tarkibi, mashg'ulotlarning aniq belgilangan raqamga egaligi (har bir dars maktabda 40 daqiqa, akademik litsey va kollejda 80 daqiqa davom etadi); jadval oldindan tuziladigan va o'quv ishlari biror aniq mavzuda tashkil etilishi kabi o'ziga xosliklarga ega bo'lgan ta'limning jamoa shakli hisoblanadi. Darsda o'qituvchi bilan o'quvchining o'zaro munosabat jarayoni shaxsiy aloqaga asoslangan.⁴³

Tarbiya:

1) shaxsning ma'naviy va jismoniy holatiga muntazam va maqsadga muvofiq ta'sir etish;

2) pedagogik jarayonda ta'lim maqsadlarini amalga oshirish uchun pedagog va tarbiyalanuvchilarning maxsus tashkil etilgan faoliyati.

Darslar qancha qismni qamrab olishi va qanday vazifalarni hal etishiga ko'ra turlicha strukturaga ega bo'lgan tiplarga bo'linadi. Struktura—bu dars qismlarining nisbati va o'zaro bog'lanishi bo'lib, ular o'z vazifasi va o'qituvchi hamda o'quvchilar faoliyati xarakteri bilan farq qiladi. Demak, yetakchi didaktik vazifa va strukturaga ko'ra darslar quyidagi turlarga bo'linadi:

1) kombinatsion darslar (o'qituvchi yangi materialni tushuntiradi, mustahkamlaydi, takrorlaydi, kontrol qiladi);

2) yangi materialni o'rganish darslari;

3) bilim, ko'nikma va malakalarni mustahkamlash darslari;

4) mashqlar va amaliy ishlar darslari;

⁴³ N.I. Xasanova, P.O. Normamatova "Tarix o'qitish metodikasi" Toshkent-2024.

5) umumlashtiruvchi takrorlash darslari;

6) laboratoriya darslari.

O'quvchilar bilimni nazorat qilish, tekshirish va baholash darslari, bundan tashqari standart bo'lmagan, innovatsion dars shakllari ham keng qo'llaniladi: seminar-darslar, konferensiya-darslar, rolli o'yinlar, integrallashgan darslar.

Aralash yoki kombinatsion dars o'zida o'quv ishlarining turli maqsad va turlarini aks ettiradi—o'tilgan material ustida ishlash—yangi mavzularni anglash va o'zlashtirish—amaliy ko'nikma va malakalarni hosil qilish.⁴⁴ Shu bilan bog'liqlikda aralash darsda odatda quyidagi strukturaviy komponentlar ajraladi: o'quvchilarni darsga tayyorlash takrorlash-umumlashtirish ishlari; yangi materialni anglash va o'zlashtirish ishlari; bilimlarni amaliyotda qo'llash ko'nikma va malakalarini shakllantirish ishlari bo'yicha ishlar uyga vazifa; yangi materialni bayon qilish darslari.⁴⁵ O'qituvchi tomonidan o'quvchilarni yangi material ustida ishlashdan xabardor qiladi va o'rta va yuqori sinflarda katta hajmli va murakkab materiallarni o'rganishda muvaffaqiyatli qo'llaniladi. Bunday dars strukturasi: o'quvchilarni darslarga jalb etish, dars maqsadlarini qo'yish; qisqa tekshirish, uyga vazifa.

O'rganilgan materialni mustahkamlash va amaliy ko'nikma va malakalarni hosil qilish darslari uning yanada chuqurroq anglash va o'zlashtirish, amaliy ko'nikma va malakalarni amaliyotda qo'llash maqsadidan kelib chiqib, hamma sinflarda alohida mavzuni yoki bo'limlarni o'rganilgandan keyin o'tilgan materialni takrorlashga yo'naltirilib o'tkaziladi. Takrorlash, tizimlashtirish va umumlashtirish darslari o'quv dasturining katta bo'limlarini takrorlash bilan bog'liq va darhol mavzularni o'rganilgandan keyin yoki o'quv yili oxirida o'tkaziladi. Dars tuzilishi zamonaviy dars amaliyoti va nazariyasida prinsipial, ahamiyatga ega, xuddi shunday ta'limda samaradorligi va natijaga egaligini aniqlab beradi. Dars elementlari sifatida quyidagi tarkibiy qismlar ajratiladi:⁴⁶

–yangi materialni o'rganish; uyga vazifa; bilimlarni nazorat qilish;

–bilimlarni umumlashtirish va tizimlashtirish;

–o'rganilgan materiallarni mustahkamlash.

Zamonaviy darsga qo'yilayotgan yuksak talablar o'qituvchini har bir darsga juda kuchli va puxta o'ylab tayyorlanishga majbur qiladi. Har bir darsga puxta tayyorlanishning sababi o'quvchilar tarkibining o'zgarayotganligi, akseleratsiya jarayonlarining kuchayuvi, informatsiyalarning “seldek” oqib kelayotganligi, turli mafkuraviy poligonlarning paydo bo'layotganligi, ish sharoitlarining ham o'zgarayotganligi, ta'limda yangi innovatsion va axborot texnologiyalaridan keng

⁴⁴ Ishmuhamedov R., Abduqodirov A., Pardaev A. Ta'limda pedagogik texnologiyalar. – Toshkent: Iste'dod, 2008.

⁴⁵ Короткова М. В., Студеникин М.Т. Методика обучения истории в схемах таблицах описаниях. Практическое пособие для учителей. – М., 1997.

⁴⁶ N.I. Xasanova, P.O. Normamatova “Tarix o'qitish metodikasi” Toshkent-2024.

foydalanilayotganligidadir. Ammo, o'qituvchining har bir alohida darsga tayyorlanish, uning o'z o'quv ishiga tayyorlanish tizimining bir qismi, xolos.

Bu tizim:

- 1) o'qituvchining o'z predmeti bo'yicha o'zlashtirish;
- 2) o'quv dasturining har bir mavzusiga tayyorlanish;
- 3) har bir darsga tayyorlanishni ichiga oladi.

O'qituvchi darsga tayyorlanayotganda o'quv dasturining hajmi va mazmunini hisobga olib material tanlaydi, dastur va darslik asosida dars rejasini tuzadi, materialni joylashtiradi va uni bayon qilishda hujjat va boshqa ko'rgazmali qurollardan foydalanish metodlarini belgilaydi.

Ammo, bu ishlar o'qituvchi darsning asosiy g'oyasini, undan ko'zlanayotgan ta'lim-tarbiya vazifalarini, darsda nimaga erishish, o'quvchilarda qanday tasavvur va tushuncha hosil qilish kerakligini aniq va to'g'ri hal qilgan taqdirdagina o'qituvchi ko'zlangan maqsadga erishishi mumkin.

Darsning bosh g'oyasi va uning tarbiyaviy vazifalari to'g'ri va aniq belgilanmay o'tkazilgan dars dasturida ko'rsatilgan faktlarni tasodifan, shunchaki sanab o'tishdan iborat bo'lib qoladi. Material tanlash va uni izchillik bilan joylashtirish, darsda qo'llaniladigan butun didaktik usullar va metodik vositalarning hammasi darsning bosh g'oyasiga, uning ta'lim va tarbiya vazifalarini hal etish maqsadiga buysundirilishi kerak.

Shuning uchun ham har bir darsning bosh g'oyasi va uning ta'lim-tarbiya vazifalarini aniqlash o'qituvchining darsga tayyorlanishida eng muhim bosqichni tashkil qiladi. Tarix darsiga tayyorlanishning bu muhim bosqichi eng mas'uliyatli bo'lishi bilan birga, ishning eng qiyin tomoni hamdir. Tarix darslarining bosh g'oyasini, uning ta'lim-tarbiya vazifalarini aniq belgilash, ayniqsa, yosh, tajribasiz o'qituvchilar uchun qiyin kechadi.

Shuning uchun ham har bir darsga tayyorlanishda Davlat ta'lim standartlari va o'quv dasturining uqtirish usulidagi ko'rsatmalar nazarda tutiladi. Tarixdan metodik qo'llanmalar hamda maxsus metodik adabiyotlar ham katta rol o'ynaydi.

O'qituvchi tarix darslarining ta'lim-tarbiya vazifalarini belgilashda albatta ulardan foydalanishi kerak.

To'g'ri, tarixning hamma bo'limlari bo'yicha ham darslarning ta'lim-tarbiya vazifalarini aniq belgilab olishga yordam beruvchi ko'rsatmani topish qiyin. Shuning uchun bu sohada har bir o'qituvchi shaxsan o'z tajribasi, ijodiga tayanishi kerak bo'ladi.

Darslarni turlarga bo'lishning bu prinsipini S.V.Ivanov birmuncha to'la ishlab chiqqan edi. Ikkinchi yo'nalishning vakillaridan biri I.N.Kazansevdir.

U dars turlari klassifikatsiyasiga asosan darsni o'tkazish usullarini asos qilib oladi.

Tarix o'qitish metodikasi sohasida prof. V.N.Bernadskiy ham tarix darslari klassifikatsiyasiga metodik usullarni asos qilib oladi va tarix darslarini quyidagi turlarga bo'ladi: O'rta ta'lim va O'rta maxsus ta'lim tizimida ma'ruza, hikoya qilib berish darsi, tarixiy hujjatlarni tahlil qilish, badiiy adabiyotlardan foydalanish darsi, o'quvchilarning

ma'ruzalariga asoslangan dars, prezident asarlarini o'qish va tahlil qilish darsi, kino darsi, ekskursiya materiallari asosida o'tkaziladigan darslar va hokazo.

Shuningdek, V.N.Bernadskiy turli usullar yordamida o'tkaziladigan umumlashtiruvchi takrorlash darslarini ham alohida guruhlariga bo'ladi. Biroq, A.A.Vaginning o'sha asarida asosli ravishda ta'kidlanishicha, dars turlari klassifikatsiyasiga, dars o'tkazishning metodik usullarini asos qilib olib bo'lmaydi.

Demak, tarix darslarini klassifikatsiya qilish, uning xilma-xil turlaridan foydalanish o'qituvchining shaxsiy xohishiga emas, balki O'rta ta'lim va O'rta maxsus ta'lim tizimida tarix kursining maqsadi, ta'lim-tarbiyaviy vazifalarini muvaffaqiyatli amalga oshirish zaruriyatidan kelib chiqadigan tarix ta'limining asosiy qonuniyatlari bilan bog'liqdir.

Shuning uchun o'qituvchi dars turlarini tanlashda o'rganiladigan mavzuning mazmuni, xarakterini hamda uni o'quvchilarning ongli va puxta o'zlashtirishini, ya'ni ta'lim jarayonining asosiy qonuniyatlarini asos qilib olishi lozim.

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THE EVOLUTION OF COMMUNICATION NETWORKS IN THE 18TH AND 19TH CENTURIES: A HISTORICAL ANALYSIS OF POST OFFICES AND TELEGRAPH SYSTEMS

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Abstract: *This study examines the development of postal systems and telegraph networks during the 18th and 19th centuries, analyzing their technological advancements, socio-economic impacts, and contributions to globalization.*

Keywords: *Postal history, telegraphy, 19th-century communication, industrialization, globalization*

INTRODUCTION

The 18th and 19th centuries marked a paradigm shift in human communication, driven by the dual rise of postal networks and telegraph systems. Prior to this era, information dissemination was slow, fragmented, and limited to elites. The expansion of empires, industrialization, and capitalist economies necessitated reliable long-distance communication. This paper investigates how post offices and telegraphy addressed these demands, transforming economic, political, and social landscapes. The study aims to highlight their interconnected evolution and enduring legacies.

METHODS

This research employs a qualitative historical methodology, synthesizing data from:

Primary sources for instance Government records (e.g., British Post Office Acts), patent filings (e.g., Samuel Morse’s telegraph), and contemporaneous newspapers.

Secondary sources are Academic texts on communication history, colonial governance, and technological innovation.

Thematic analysis identified key trends: Legislative reforms, technological breakthroughs, and socio-economic consequences. Regional case studies (Britain, France, and the United States) provide comparative insights.

RESULTS

In 18th-Century Foundations: National post offices emerged as tools of state control. Britain’s “Post Office Act” of 1711 centralized mail delivery, while France’s network prioritized military logistics. **In 19th-Century Democratization:** Rowland Hill’s “Penny Post” (1840) reduced letter rates in Britain, increasing accessibility.

By 1850, annual mail volume surged by 360%. In England, the postal service, from 1660 General Post Office, had developed into a monopoly, affirmed by Oliver Cromwell in 1654,[1][2] for the collection and carriage of letters between post towns, however, there was no delivery system until William Dockwra and his partner

Robert Murray established the London Penny Post in 1680. They set up a local post that used a uniform rate of one old penny for delivery of letters and packets weighing up to one pound within the cities of Westminster and London as well as in Southwark.[3]

Several deliveries took place a day within the city, and items were also delivered to addresses up to ten miles outside London for an extra charge of one penny. In 1683 Dockwra was forced to surrender the Penny Post to the English Crown for circulating what were considered seditious newsletters sharply criticizing the Duke of York, who was in charge of and directly benefited from the General Post Office. In 1765, Parliament authorized the creation of Penny Posts in any town or city of the kingdoms of Great Britain and Ireland. The single postage rate of one penny was charged within the area, calculated by weight. By the beginning of the 19th century there were many of these, identifiable on covers, with markings such as "PP", "Py Post", or "Penny Post" along with the name of the town.

The early penny post system in Edinburgh, founded in 1773-1774 by Peter Williamson, known as "Indian Peter," usefully combined it with one of the world's first street directories. He circulated mail to 17 shops in the city (effectively post offices) and employed four uniformed postmen. Their hats read "Penny Post" and were numbered 1, 4, 8 and 16 to make the business look bigger.

On 5 December 1839 the Uniform Fourpenny Post was introduced by the General Post Office but lasted only 36 days until 9 January 1840 when the Uniform Penny Post replaced it. In 1835 Rowland Hill published a pamphlet entitled 'Post Office Reform' which led to various reforms and the introduction of the first postage stamp.

He convinced Parliament to implement much needed reforms in the current postal system. On 10 January 1840, the Uniform Penny Post was established throughout Great Britain and Ireland, facilitating the safe, speedy and cheap conveyance of letters. Hill had demonstrated that the current system was inefficient and slow and not cost effective. Time was wasted when the postman waited at each house to collect payment. From 6 May 1840, letters could be prepaid with the first postage stamp, known as the Penny Black for up to a half ounce in weight, otherwise they would be charged twopence as unpaid letters or required additional postage. The use of prepaid postage through adhesive stamps revolutionized the postal service. While the Post Office was initially skeptical, the new system proved to be a resounding success, leading to greater efficiency, speed, and profitability.

Railways and steamships accelerated domestic and international delivery, exemplified by the "Universal Postal Union (1874)", which standardized global postal exchanges. Established in 1874, the Universal Postal Union (UPU), with its headquarters in the Swiss capital Berne, is the second oldest international organization worldwide.

With its 192 member countries, the UPU is the primary forum for cooperation between postal sector players. It helps to ensure a truly universal network of up-to-date products and services.

In this way, the organization fulfils an advisory, mediating and liaison role, and provides technical assistance where needed. It sets the rules for international mail exchanges and makes recommendations to stimulate growth in mail, parcel and financial services volumes and improve quality of service for customers.

The word telegraph is derived from the Greek words *tele*, meaning “distant,” and *graphein*, meaning “to write.” It came into use toward the end of the 18th century to describe an optical semaphore system developed in France. However, many types of telegraphic communication have been employed since before recorded history. The earliest methods of communication at a distance made use of such media as smoke, fire, drums, and reflected rays of the Sun. Visual signals given by flags and torches were used for short-range communication and continued to be utilized well into the 20th century, when the two-flag semaphore system was widely used, particularly by the world’s navies.

Claude Chappe’s semaphore (1792) enabled coded visual signaling, but the electric telegraph (Samuel Morse, 1837) marked a quantum leap. Morse code allowed messages to traverse continents within minutes. Before the development of the electric telegraph, visual systems were used to convey messages over distances by means of variable displays.

One of the most successful of the visual telegraphs was the semaphore developed in France by the Chappe brothers, Claude and Ignace, in 1791. This system consisted of pairs of movable arms mounted at the ends of a crossbeam on hilltop towers. Each arm of the semaphore could assume seven angular positions 45° apart, and the horizontal beam could tilt 45° clockwise or counterclockwise. In this manner it was possible to represent numbers and the letters of the alphabet.

Chains of these towers were built to permit transmission over long distances. The towers were spaced at intervals of 5 to 10 km (3 to 6 miles), and a signaling rate of three symbols per minute could be achieved.

Another widely used visual telegraph was developed in 1795 by George Murray in England. In Murray’s device, characters were sent by opening and closing various combinations of six shutters. This system rapidly caught on in England and in the United States, where a number of sites bearing the name Telegraph Hill or Signal Hill can still be found, particularly in coastal regions. Visual telegraphs were completely replaced by the electric telegraph by the middle of the 19th century.

The 1858 Transatlantic Cable connected Europe and North America, though initial failures underscored technical challenges. By 1902, Britain’s “All Red Line” linked its empire via undersea cables. Telegraphy enabled real-time stock trading (e.g., New York Stock Exchange) and streamlined supply chains. Colonial powers like Britain used telegraphy to administer territories (e.g., India’s Rebellion of 1857). Cheaper postage fostered personal correspondence, while telegraphs accelerated

news dissemination (e.g., Reuters news agency). Postal and telegraph systems co-evolved through shared infrastructure. For instance, Britain's General Post Office (GPO) absorbed telegraph services in 1870, creating unified communication hubs. This integration mirrored broader trends of state-led industrialization.

While these systems promoted connectivity, access remained unequal. Rural areas lagged in telegraph coverage, and colonial networks prioritized extractive economies. Labor exploitation also persisted: postal workers faced harsh conditions, prompting early unionization efforts.

Britain's public-focused reforms contrasted with France's centralized model, reflecting differing political philosophies. Similarly, the U.S. embraced private telegraph firms (e.g., Western Union), whereas Europe favored state control.

CONCLUSION

The 18th and 19th-century communication revolution reshaped human interaction, bridging geographic and social divides. Post offices democratized information access, while telegraphy introduced instantaneous connectivity. Their convergence underscored the interdependence of policy, technology, and society—a framework that continues to guide modern innovations. Future research could explore parallels with digital communication's societal impacts.

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**RAQAMLI MA'RIFAT: SUN'IY INTELEKT VA JAMIYATLARNING
MADANIY RIVOJLANISH KODLARIDAGI O'ZGARISHLAR**

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Annotatsiya: *Bugungi globallashuv davrida sun'iy intellekt va axborot texnologiyalari inson hayotining barcha jabhalariga chuqur kirib bormoqda. Ma'lumotlar almashinuvi tezlashdi, bilim olish imkoniyatlari kengaydi, biroq bu jarayon inson tafakkuri va ma'naviy rivojlanishiga qanday ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda? Ushbu maqolada sun'iy intellekt va axborot texnologiyalarining inson madaniy tafakkuriga ijobiy va salbiy ta'sirlarini tahlil qilamiz. Hamda jamiyatda mavjud madaniy kodlarni o'rganamiz.*

Kalit so'zlar: *sun'iy intellekt, raqamli texnologiya, personalizatsiyalashgan intellekt, eksprement, virtual o'qituvchi va yordamchi, aqlli algoritm, vr/ar texnologiyalar, madaniy kod*

**ЦИФРОВАЯ ГРАМОТНОСТЬ: ИСКУССТВЕННЫЙ ИНТЕЛЛЕКТ И
ИЗМЕНЕНИЯ В КОДАХ КУЛЬТУРНОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ОБЩЕСТВ**

Хамидов Достон Равшан ўғли

Аннотация: *В условиях современной глобализации искусственный интеллект и информационные технологии глубоко проникают во все сферы человеческой жизни. Обмен данными ускорился, возможности получения знаний расширились, но как этот процесс влияет на человеческое мышление и духовное развитие? В данной статье анализируются положительные и отрицательные влияния искусственного интеллекта и информационных технологий на человеческое мышление.*

Ключевые слова: *искусственный интеллект, цифровые технологии, персонализированный интеллект, эксперимент, виртуальный учитель и помощник, умный алгоритм, VR/AR технологии, чат-бот*

**DIGITAL LITERACY: ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND CHANGES
IN THE CULTURAL DEVELOPMENT CODES OF SOCIETIES**

Khamidov Doston Ravshan o'g'li

Abstract: *In today's era of globalization, artificial intelligence and information technologies are deeply penetrating all aspects of human life. Data exchange has accelerated, and opportunities for acquiring knowledge have expanded. However, how do these processes affect*

human cognition and spiritual development? This article analyzes the positive and negative impacts of artificial intelligence and information technologies on human cognition.

Keywords: *artificial intelligence, digital technology, personalized intelligence, experiment, virtual teacher and assistant, intelligent algorithm, VR/AR technologies, chatbot*

1. Sun'iy intellekt va axborot texnologiyalari – yangi davr tafakkuri

Sun'iy intellektning ta'lim, fan va san'at sohasiga ta'siri.

Ta'lim sohasida suniy intellekt

Personalizatsiyalashgan o'qitish:

- SI yordamida o'quvchilarning qobiliyatlari, qiziqishlari va o'rganish uslublariga mos keladigan shaxsiylashtirilgan o'quv dasturlari yaratish mumkin.
- O'quvchilarning kamchiliklarini aniqlash va ularni bartaraf etish uchun algoritmlar orqali tahlil olib boriladi.

Avtomatlashtirilgan baholash:

- Test va topshiriqlarni avtomatik baholash tizimlari yordamida o'qituvchilar yukini kamaytirish va tezkor fikr-mulohazalar berish imkoniyati yaratilmoqda.

Virtual o'qituvchilar va yordamchilar:

- Chatbotlar va virtual o'qituvchilar yordamida talabalar 24/7 savollariga javob topishlari mumkin, bu esa o'quv jarayonining samaradorligini oshiradi.

Aqlli algoritmlar va inson miyasining intellektual rivojlanishi

Sun'iy intellekt yordamida o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari

Ilm-fan sohasida suniy intellekt

Ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilish va modellashtirish:

- Katta hajmdagi ilmiy ma'lumotlar va eksperimental natijalarni SI algoritmlari yordamida tez va aniq tahlil qilish imkoniyati yaratilmoqda.
- Suniy intellekt asosidagi modellar yordamida murakkab jarayonlar va tizimlarni simulyatsiya qilish, prognozlash mumkin.

Yangi kashfiyotlar va innovatsiyalar:

- SI biologiya, kimyo, fizika kabi sohalarda yangi g'oyalar va kashfiyotlarni tezlashtirishga yordam beradi.
- Data mining va mashina o'rganish texnikalari ilmiy tadqiqotlarda yangi tendensiyalarni aniqlashga xizmat qiladi.

Avtomatlashtirilgan eksperimentlar:

- Laboratoriyalarda SI tizimlari yordamida eksperimentlarni avtomatlashtirish, natijalarni tezkor qayta ishlash va xatoliklarni kamaytirish mumkin.

San'at sohasida suniy intellekt

Yangi ijodiy usullar:

- Suniy intellekt yordamida generativ san'at asarlari yaratilmoqda. Masalan, algoritmlar asosida musiqiy kompozitsiyalar, tasviriy san'at va adabiyot namunalarini ishlab chiqish mumkin.

- Bu ijodiy jarayonlar san'atkorlarga yangi ilhom manbalari va ijodiy imkoniyatlar yaratadi.

Interaktiv san'at shakllari:

- Virtual va kengaytirilgan haqiqat (VR/AR) texnologiyalari bilan birgalikda SI interaktiv san'at asarlarini yaratish, tomoshabinlarni faol ishtirok etishga undaydi.

- SI yordamida san'at asarlarining shaxsiylashtirilgan tajribalari, tomoshabinlarning hissiyotlari va fikrlarini hisobga olgan holda yaratilmoqda.

San'atni tahlil qilish va arxivlash:

- Suniy intellekt san'at asarlarini tahlil qilish, ularni kategoriyalarga ajratish va raqamli arxivlashda qo'llaniladi. Bu esa san'at tarixchilari va kuratorlarga asarlar o'rtasidagi bog'lanishlarni aniqlashda yordam beradi.

Aqlli algoritmlar nima?

Ta'rif va imkoniyatlar:

- Aqlli algoritmlar – bu murakkab masalalarni yechishda ma'lumotlarni tahlil qiluvchi va natijalar chiqaruvchi dasturiy vositalar bo'lib, ularning samaradorligi insonning an'anaviy fikrlash uslublariga qo'shimcha ravishda yangi imkoniyatlar yaratadi.

- Ular sun'iy intellektning asosiy tamoyillaridan biri bo'lib, mashina o'rganishi, tabiiy tilni qayta ishlash va murakkab modellashtirish kabi jarayonlarni amalga oshiradi.

Inson intellektual rivojlanishiga ta'siri

Bilim olish va tahliliy fikrlash:

- Aqlli algoritmlar yordamida o'quvchilar va mutaxassislar katta hajmdagi ma'lumotlarni tezda tahlil qilishlari, murakkab bilimlarni qisqa vaqt ichida o'zlashtirishlari mumkin.

- Ushbu vositalar yordamida ma'lumotlar orasidagi murakkab bog'lanishlar aniqlanib, ilmiy kashfiyotlar uchun yangi istiqbollar yaratilmoqda.

Shaxsiylashtirilgan o'qitish jarayoni:

- Algoritmlar asosida yaratilgan shaxsiylashtirilgan o'qitish tizimlari har bir insonning o'ziga xos qobiliyatlari va o'rganish uslubiga mos keladigan ta'lim materiallarini taqdim etadi.

- Bu esa o'quvchilarning individual rivojlanishini qo'llab-quvvatlaydi va mustaqil fikrlash qobiliyatini oshiradi.

Ijodkorlik va yangi g'oyalar:

- Aqlli algoritmlar ijodiy jarayonlarni avtomatlashtirish orqali san'at, musiqa va adabiyot kabi sohalarida yangi ijodiy uslublarni shakllantiradi.

- Algoritmlar yordamida yaratilgan generativ san'at asarlari insonning ijodiy imkoniyatlarini kengaytiradi, shuningdek, yangi g'oyalar va konseptlar yuzaga kelishiga turtki beradi.

Muammolarni yechish va qaror qabul qilish:

- Inson intellekti va aqlli algoritmlarning integratsiyasi murakkab muammolarni aniqlash va ularni yechishda qo'llanilayotgan innovatsion yondashuvlarni mustahkamlaydi.

- Bu esa analitik fikrlashni rivojlantirishga va samarali qaror qabul qilish jarayonini tezlashtirishga yordam beradi.

Kelajak istiqbollari

Texnologik integratsiya:

- Aqlli algoritmlar va sun'iy intellektning rivojlanishi bilan kelajakda ta'lim va ilm-fanda yanada kengroq integratsiya, shaxsiylashtirilgan o'qitish tizimlari va yangi kashfiyotlar yuzaga kelishi kutilmoqda.

- Inson intellekti va texnologiyalar o'rtasidagi sinergetik aloqalar kelajakda yaratilayotgan innovatsion tizimlarda asosiy rol o'ynaydi.

Muvozanatli rivojlanish:

- Texnologik yutuqlarni insonning ma'naviy va intellektual rivojlanishi bilan uyg'unlashtirish zarur.

- Insonlar algoritmlar va sun'iy intellektning imkoniyatlaridan samarali foydalanishlari, shu bilan birga mustaqil fikrlash va tanqidiy tahlil qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishlari kerak.

2. Axborot texnologiyalarining inson tafakkuriga ta'siri

Ijobiy tomonlari:

- Bilim olish jarayoni osonlashdi
- Har qanday sohada tezkor ma'lumot olish imkoniyati
- Intellektual rivojlanishga ta'siri: kodlash, tahliliy fikrlash va kreativ yondashuvni shakllantirish

Salbiy tomonlari:

- Fikrlash jarayonining avtomatlashtirilishi va inson tafakkurining passivlashuvi
- Odamlarning o'z mustaqil fikriga ega bo'lishi kamayishi
- Sun'iy intellektga haddan tashqari ishonch natijasida analitik tafakkurning susayishi

3. Ma'naviy immunitet va axborot xurujlariga qarshi kurash

- Sun'iy intellektdan ongli va maqsadli foydalanish
- Axborot xurujlariga qarshi mustahkam ma'naviy asos yaratish
- Fikrni mustaqil shakllantirish va axborotni tahlil qilish qobiliyatini rivojlantirish

Suniy intellektning rivojlanishi shaxsiy o'sish va o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish jarayonlarini yangi bosqichga olib chiqmoqda. Aqlli tizimlar shaxsiy ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilib, individual ehtiyojlarga moslashtirilgan ta'lim va rivojlanish strategiyalarini ishlab chiqishda qo'llaniladi.

1. Shaxsiylashtirilgan o'qitish va o'rganish

Moslashtirilgan ta'lim tizimlari:

- SI asosida ishlab chiqilgan platformalar o'quvchilarning o'ziga xos qobiliyatlari, qiziqishlari va o'rganish uslublarini aniqlaydi, shuningdek, individual o'qitish rejalarini tuzadi.

- Bu tizimlar yordamida har bir inson o'z tezligida va ehtiyojlariga muvofiq bilim olish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi.

Onlayn kurslar va interaktiv darslar:

- Suniy intellekt qo'llaniladigan onlayn ta'lim platformalari interaktiv materiallar, testlar va avtomatik baholash tizimlari bilan boyitilgan.

- Bu orqali o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish jarayoni samaraliroq va qiziqarli bo'ladi.

2. Shaxsiy rivojlanish uchun individual tahlil va maslahatlar

Algoritmik tahlil va ko'rsatmalar:

- SI insonning faoliyat natijalarini tahlil qilib, o'z ustida ishlash kerak bo'lgan sohalarni aniqlaydi.

- Shaxsiy ma'lumotlarga asoslangan tavsiyalar orqali o'qitish, sog'liqni saqlash va kasbiy rivojlanish yo'nalishlarida aniq qadamlar belgilanishi mumkin.

Virtual shaxsiy yordamchilar:

- Chatbotlar va virtual mentorlar yordamida kundalik savollar, vazifalar va motivatsion maslahatlar olinadi.

- Bu yordamchilar 24/7 faol bo'lib, insonning o'z-o'zini tahlil qilish va o'sish jarayonini qo'llab-quvvatlaydi.

3. Yangi texnologiyalar orqali ijodiy rivojlanish

Ijodiy jarayonlarni qo'llab-quvvatlash:

- SI yordamida yaratilgan generativ asboblardan san'at, adabiyot va musiqa sohalarida yangi ijodiy uslublarni o'rganish imkoniyatini beradi.

- Bu vositalar orqali insonlar o'z fikrlarini yangi formatlarda ifoda etishga, ijodiy yechimlar ishlab chiqishga undaydi.

O'z ustida ishlash va motivatsiya:

- Suniy intellekt asosida ishlaydigan ilovalar shaxsiy maqsadlar qo'yish, ularni rejalashtirish va erishish jarayonini kuzatib borish imkonini yaratadi.

- Motivatsion dasturlar va progress monitoring tizimlari orqali shaxsiy o'sish aniq va o'lchovli natijalarga olib keladi.

Suniy intellekt yordamida o'z-o'zini rivojlantirish imkoniyatlari kengayib bormoqda. Shaxsiylashtirilgan o'qitish, individual tahlil va virtual yordamchilar orqali inson o'z bilim va ko'nikmalarini yanada samarali rivojlantirishi mumkin. Shu bilan birga, texnologik innovatsiyalar ijodiy jarayonlarni qo'llab-quvvatlab, shaxsiy o'sish yo'lida yangi ufqlarni ochmoqda.

Sun'iy intellekt va axborot texnologiyalaridan samarali foydalanish inson tafakkurini yuksaltirishga xizmat qiladi.

Biroq bu jarayonda ma'naviy mustaqillik va mustahkam tafakkurga ega bo'lish juda muhim.

Yangi texnologiyalarni ma'rifat va ma'naviyat bilan uyg'unlashtirish – zamonaviy jamiyatning asosiy vazifalaridan biridir.

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IMPLEMENTATION OF STRATEGIC PLANNING ON THE BASIS OF IMPROVING THE METHOD OF ASSESSING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF THE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM**Abidov Bobur Sobirovich***Independent researcher of the Tashkent Textile and Light Industry Institute babidov020@gmail.com*

Annotation: *The article examines the issue of drawing up strategic plans and developing suggestions for improving their implementation based on the results of improving the method of assessing the competitiveness of the management system in textile enterprises.*

Key words: *improvement, strategic planning, assessment method, competitiveness, management system.*

INTRODUCTION

The financial situation of many production enterprises in the Republic of Uzbekistan is not stable, which in turn has a negative impact on the country's economic situation. Therefore, an objective assessment of the efficiency of enterprise management through a comprehensive study is considered one of the important factors for further improvement of the country's economic situation. A number of measures to support the further development of the textile industry by the state have been developed and are being implemented. In the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, the task of «doubling the production volume of textile industry products» is set, and the successful implementation of this task requires an objective assessment of management competitiveness in the implementation of strategic planning in the management of textile industry enterprises of our republic.

The term «strategic planning» was first used by military commanders. As a result of solving purely military tasks, many management methods have appeared [1]. The analysis of research results conducted by A.Chandler shows that already in 1961, its author was well acquainted with the concept of strategic planning and, in particular, with examples of strategic plans [2].

In the effective implementation of strategic planning, the evaluation of the competitiveness and prospects of the enterprise management system is of great importance. Well-known experts in the field of competitive strategy Glukhix L.V., Voronov A.A. commenting on these strategic obligations, they emphasized the need not to harmonize interests as a result of the implementation of strategic plans, but to achieve high competitiveness and increase the efficiency of the enterprise [3]. From the point of view of the hierarchy, according to the conclusion of N.A. Saveleva, there is competition at the highest level, then competitiveness, then competitive advantages, and lastly competitive strategies. This author connects the definition of competitive strategy with a set of management and organizational-methodical solutions that ensure the acquisition of the

best positions in the market with the highest level of satisfaction of potential customers. This is achieved on the basis of significant competitive advantages [4]. Competitive strategy is the strategy of an individual enterprise (or product types that are part of a large corporation). Therefore, it is important to assess the competitiveness of all activities of the enterprise, especially management activities.

Materials and styles

According to the purpose of the research work, based on the distinctive characteristics of the production and economic activities of textile enterprises, the assessment of the level of competitiveness of their management systems by improving the strategic planning process of textile enterprises based on modern approaches 3 was developed.

This club should include the following items:

1st step. Selection of competitiveness criteria and indicators of textile enterprise management system.

2nd step. Determining the degree of importance of each group of indicators to determine the overall camaraderie.

3rd step. Determination of the primary competitiveness index of a group of indicators describing the competitiveness of a selected individual management.

Step 4. Determination of the integral indicator of the competitiveness of the management structure of textile enterprises based on the improvement of strategic planning.

Step 5. Development of a scale for evaluating the level of competitiveness of management systems of textile enterprises.

By improving strategic planning based on modern approaches, the author developed a scale for evaluating the level of competitiveness of management systems of textile enterprises (Table 1).

Table 1

Enterprise management system competitiveness assessment scale⁴⁷

Value	Description of the level of competitiveness of the enterprise management system
0,81–1,0	The level of competition is «very high».
0,64–0,80	The level of competitiveness is «good».
0,38–0,63	Competitiveness «medium» level
0,21–0,37	The level of competition is «low».
0,0–0,20	Competitiveness is «very low».

Results and discussion

As part of the benchmarking methodology, information was collected about the management systems of «REKORD TEX» LLC and «BAKAN TEX» LLC. Taking into account the criteria of the methodology developed for the analysis and assessment of competitiveness, the analysis of the management systems of these textile enterprises and the strategic development between 2020 and 2024 was carried out, because the named

⁴⁷Author development.

business entities worked in an unstable external environment and were forced to make changes in their activities.

In assessing the competitiveness and prospects of the management system, we adopted the following criteria as a basis:

1. Competitiveness of textile enterprise production activity;
2. Financial situation of the textile enterprise;
3. Competitiveness of product organization and movement
4. Competitiveness of organization of management activities.

By the end of 2024, expert evaluations of each criteria describing the level of competitiveness of the management systems of the textile enterprises under analysis were carried out, and based on them, the «competitiveness profile» of the management system of each textile enterprise was developed.

First of all, the main areas of activity of the analyzed textile enterprises were compared according to the single indicators of each of the proposed criteria.

The summary indicator of the fourth criterion is the competitiveness of the organization of management activities in a textile enterprise:

«REKORD TEX» LLC

$$K_{14} = 0,17 * 3 + 0,17 * 2 + 0,16 * 3 + 0,11 * 3 + 0,13 * 3 + 0,14 * 3 + 0,12 * 3 \\ = 2,83 \text{ балл.}$$

«BAKAN TEX» LLC

$$K_{24} = 0,17 * 4 + 0,17 * 4 + 0,16 * 3 + 0,11 * 3 + 0,13 * 2 + 0,14 * 3 + 0,12 * 4 \\ = 2,99 \text{ балл.}$$

These results show that the level of competitiveness of the organization of management activities in «REKORD TEX» LLC is lower than in «BAKAN TEX» LLC, that is, the organization of management activities does not adequately meet the conditions of work in crisis conditions.

Conclusions and suggestions

We can conclude that the management systems of the studied textile enterprises do not adequately meet the specific needs of the internal and external environment in the crisis, because they could not use the available opportunities effectively. Therefore, the competitiveness of a textile enterprise can be achieved by: restructuring them, increasing internal and external demand for products, increasing investment resources, improving product quality, searching for new product sales segments, developing risk identification, calculation and blocking systems.

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DEVELOPMENT OF STRATEGIES FOR INCREASING THE LEVEL OF UTILIZATION OF EXPORT CAPACITY IN THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY

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Annotation: *In the article, taking into account the changes in the world market of textile products, the issue of developing strategies for increasing the level of use of export potential in the enterprises of the textile industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan is studied.*

Key words: *international trade, trade policy, export, textile industry, export potential, strategy.*

A number of measures to support the further development of the textile industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan have been developed and implemented. In the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, the task "To double the production volume of textile industry products" is defined, the successful implementation of this task requires the research of classification of the factors of its formation in the search for domestic opportunities that are not used in the export activity of the textile industry of our republic [1].

Also, receiving the status of GSP+ beneficiary by the country created a solid foundation for local textile exporters, which allowed for further sustainable growth and diversification of the export product range, serving the rapid development of mutually beneficial trade relations with EU countries in the field of textiles. Therefore, developing strategies for increasing export potential based on innovation in the textile industry is considered one of the urgent issues.

In many works on economics, strategy is understood as a long-term plan of top management to achieve the organization's long-term goals [2]. Some authors suggest that it is the long-term intentions of business leaders with respect to production, marketing and sales, income and expenses, or capital investment. It should be noted that the concept of "strategy" and its understanding have changed along with the evolution of the business environment [3].

In developed Western countries, the concept of "strategy" entered business in the 1950s and 1960s. From this period, a number of worldviews emerged regarding the description of the essence and purpose of the strategy in the management of the enterprise.

G. Mintzberg, one of the world's most famous scientists in the field of management, has repeatedly emphasized that there is no single definition of the term "strategy" among experts. G. Mintzberg, Dj. B. Quinn, S. Goshal in their works devoted to the strategic process show that "There will be no single generally accepted strategy at all [4].

There are two approaches to the interpretation of the term strategy. From the point of view of the first approach, the strategy means what the organization strives for, what it is based on when making management decisions, what the priorities of the enterprise's activities are based on, what are the priorities of the enterprise's activities. Such an approach is described in the works of R. Rumelt, Dj. B. Quinn, K. Andrews [5].

According to K. Andrews, corporate strategy is a decision-making plan, which reveals the company's goals and objectives, develops the main policies and tasks for the implementation of the set goals, determines the business area that embodies the main activity of the company, as well as the purpose of this joint-stock company. illuminates the nature of economic and non-economic achievements [6].

In his work on change strategy, DJ B. Quinn gives the following definition of strategy: «strategy is a pattern or plan that describes the organization's goals, policies, and activities as a whole. A correctly formed strategy has always made it possible to allocate the organization's limited resources in an efficient and correct manner based on the ability to see in a certain sense».

M.R. Boltaboev, an economist from Uzbekistan, approaches the definition of marketing strategy as a process of strategic production planning by expressing long-term goals and comparing existing resources with emerging opportunities [7].

Isaev R.A. issues of improving the organizational and management mechanisms of implementing development strategies of textile industry enterprises in the integrated system of quality management and strategic management in the textile industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan were studied [8].

The goals of this study are to determine the reserves of effective use of export potential in its strategic development by classifying strategies based on the nature of the enterprise's behavior in product markets. The author proposes to improve the well-known classification by supplementing it with a stabilization strategy (offensive-defense strategy) in solving the problem of forming a strategy for increasing the level of utilization of export potential of textile enterprises. Thus, the following corporate strategies of the enterprise are determined and considered within the framework of the research: "breakthrough" strategy, "stabilization" strategy and "survival" strategy.

In the process of developing a strategy for the level of utilization of the export potential of textile enterprises, it is necessary not only to establish the relationship between the strategies discussed above, but also to take into account the extensive or intensive forms of development, which are the qualitative characteristics of the development determined by the dominant type of innovative development of the enterprise.

An intensive form of development occurs when the effective use and growth of the export potential is achieved by qualitatively changing its constituent elements. In this case, the rate of development of the enterprise will be significantly higher than the rate of growth of the resources involved in production and economic activity.

Extensive development, in contrast to intensive development, consists in increasing the level of use of production potential due to the quantitative change of its components. Therefore, in the process of developing and implementing the strategy of the level of use of export potential, the type of competitive behavior of the manufacturer in the product market, the level of innovative activity of the enterprise and the priority type of development of production potential should be taken into account.

In the course of the research, based on the criteria for choosing an alternative strategy for the level of utilization of export potential for textile enterprises, proposals were developed for the selection of strategy options for increasing the level of utilization of export potential for 6 textile enterprises and their implementation.

Based on the results obtained during the research, the following conclusions were made:

- It will be necessary to develop comprehensively based strategies to ensure the sustainable development of textile enterprises. In this process, it is necessary to assess the impact of external and internal environmental factors on the development of the enterprise and the process of strategy implementation. Based on the nature of production of textile enterprises, it can be concluded that it is appropriate to develop integrated strategies taking into account the market, products, consumers, competition, suppliers, export, etc.;

- strategy implementation is a complex process, but, in our opinion, adapting to the specifics of the industry and the comprehensive use of modern innovative methods and quality management and strategic management tools, such as the balanced scorecard system, the use of process and system approaches, help to take into account the needs of all stakeholders, ensures the complexity and balance of the developed system and ensures interaction to achieve the most effective goals.

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PROSPECTS OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF TEXTILE INDUSTRY

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Abstract: *The article examines the issues of finding opportunities for sustainable development of the textile industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan based on the diversification of the national economy, and determining its main directions.*

Keywords: *Diversification, national economy, textile industry, sustainable development, development directions.*

The market economy is an economy prone to extreme volatility. In these conditions, rational use of all available resources and achieving savings are considered factors of sustainable development. The role of the textile industry in further increasing the economic potential of the Republic of Uzbekistan is incomparable. Our republic has accumulated rich historical experience in the development of this sector, and there are sufficient conditions, raw material base and labor resources. In the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022 -2026, the task "To double the production volume of textile industry products" is defined [1]. Ensuring effective performance of these tasks requires ensuring sustainable development of the textile industry of the Republic of Uzbekistan through rational use of all available resources. In this regard, the development of suggestions and recommendations aimed at improving the formulation of sustainable development strategy of textile enterprises is considered an urgent issue.

The term "sustainability" has been closely studied for several centuries. This category was first used in economics in the second half of the 19th century - the first quarter of the 20th century, during the period of rapid development of capitalist relations in Western Europe. The theory of "stability of small farming" was formed. According to this theory, a small economy was superior to a large economy. With the transition to mechanized production, the theory of "Stability of small farms" was replaced by the theory of "Stability of family farms". Sustainability is established in international documents (for example, "Rio Declaration on Environment and Development" [2], "Agenda for the XXI century" [3], as well as the adoption of certain issues of global importance based on conventions and multilateral agreements) and within acceptance refers to the ability of the system to continue to function at the standard level.

Sustainability requires a balance between population and available natural resources. It is necessary to take into account the needs of one sector and the number

of products produced in the respective sectors, but in this case, the needs of future generations should not be denied. Authors such as T.Malthus [4], L.Walras [5], K.Ya.Kondratev [6] and others devoted their research to aspects of stability at this level.

Kondaupova D.C. [7], in his research paper, under the term "mechanism of development of the environment" understands the interconnected set of elements of the environment in the room, in which he finds that his child's creative activity is able to reach its goal without going beyond a certain limit.

As of January 1, 2023, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, 5,852 economic units specializing in the production of textile products have increased their activity.

In 2016, the volume of production of tapak was 12.7 tpln. co.m. and this multiplier will be 79.97 tpln by 2022. It was observed that its size increased by 9.29 bap in the period that established or is being studied. Also, in 2022, the estimated volume of oil reserves in the studied area will increase by 4.21 million bap compared to 2016 and reach 3300 mln. established the US cabinet. One of the most important aspects of the implementation of this project is the creation of new job opportunities for the population. At the scale of the project, 23,000 new jobs will be created in 2022 [8].

In 2018-2020, the value of 1854.5 million dollars will be added to the PF-5285 agreement of the President of the Republic of Kazakhstan "In the context of the rapid development of textile and sewing industry" on December 14, 2017. About 200 investment projects have been implemented. The main purpose of this project is to produce dyed yarn, knitting fabric, gauze, knitting and sewing products.

In order to further develop the project, the development planned for 2022 -2026 will create 80,000 new jobs in Dactup, with a total cost of 2437 million. Implementation of 225 innovation-investment projects equal to the US budget is planned. An organizational and economic mechanism for the implementation of this innovation-invention project has been developed.

In the "Uztokamichilikcanoat" joint venture, an increase in production capacity was achieved due to the adoption of innovative and innovative projects. As a result of the implementation of the project, in 2022 compared to 2018, the production volume of kalava yarn decreased by 7,000 tons, knitting fabric - by 26,400 tons, the production volume of knitting and crocheting products by 175,0 million pieces, the volume of socks production by 1, By 51 million pairs, the production volume of dyed cotton fabric has increased by 12.2 thousand tons.

Today, textile enterprises export their products to more than 70 countries of the world. In particular, as a result of the work carried out to expand the scale of exports and find new potential foreign markets in the activities of industry enterprises, it is possible to export products in large quantities to countries such as Russia, Germany, Poland, Turkey, and China.

Also, as a result of the participation of the company's enterprises in international fairs of light industrial products, many mutually beneficial contracts

were concluded with potential investors. Currently, more than 42 dealership structures have been established by large exporting companies in the European Union, CIS and Asian countries.

The analysis of statistical data shows that in 2018 the export volume of textile products was 1.3 billion. If it is US dollars, this amount will increase by almost 2.5 times in 2022 to 3.3 billion. was US dollars [8].

The basis for the successful adaptation of the enterprise to uncertain and rapidly changing environmental conditions is an effective management mechanism that ensures the formation and implementation of such a development option that provides the best final results in the current conditions. The task is to reform the industrial enterprises to the extent that they will be effective not only today, but also in the coming years. In recent years, many areas of the domestic economy, characterized by the growth indicators of industrial production, have the necessary conditions for the sustainable development of enterprises.

At the same time, it should be considered that the growth of industrial production depends on the ability to quickly respond to changes in the market. Each company tries to strengthen its position in the market, thereby weakening the position of others.

The sustainable development of the organizational and economic system of the textile industry is a process in which random effects cause minimal deviations from the specified parameters due to the characteristics of division, reserve and reliability. The maximum current efficiency should be in the area of minimum costs, taking into account the sustainable development of the system.

The following conclusions and suggestions were made to ensure the sustainable development of textile enterprises:

1. When talking about the sustainable development of the textile industry and taking into account the specific characteristics of industrial enterprises characterized not only by competition, but also by the introduction of new technologies and innovations that require science, "weak" sustainability through development with the help of active activities in the field of science and technology the model can be "strengthened";

- in our opinion, the following should be formed taking into account the following three important components, which should be selected and analyzed in accordance with the goals of sustainable development of the mechanism:

- principles (allows to ensure the efficiency of enterprise activity);

- factors (the basis for ensuring the stability of the textile industry enterprise within the framework of achieving sustainable development taking into account the impact; the most important task for the enterprise is not only to observe sustainability, but also to achieve sustainable development);

- methods and tools (allows to coordinate actions in the process of performing management tasks to achieve the goal of sustainable development).

2. Introduction of cost-effective technologies in textile industry enterprises.

3. Development of effective quality management system in textile enterprises and implementation of competitive product types.
4. Improving the organizational and economic mechanisms of business processes in order to further increase the export potential.
5. It is necessary to develop and legally establish a single comprehensive program for managing foreign economic activity through tariffs and without tariffs.
6. Increasing the export potential by applying the "GSP+" system to the practice of the textile industry.

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CHARACTERISTICS OF EMPLOYEES COMPETENCE AUTHORITY AND MANAGEMENT EFFECTIVENESS INTERRELATIONSHIP MATRIX IN A TEXTILE ENTERPRISE

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Annotation: *This article examines the issue of employee development in textile enterprises of the Republic of Uzbekistan based on the information of the correlation matrix of employee competence potential and management efficiency.*

Key words: *enterprise, employee, competence, property, management, efficiency.*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years in the Republic of Uzbekistan, a number of measures to support the further development of the textile and sewing-knitting industries have been developed and implemented. In the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, the task "to double the volume of production of textile industry products" is defined, the successful implementation of this task requires the creation of a system of objective evaluation of the competencies of highly qualified specialists in the production of quality products in the enterprises of the sewing and knitting industry of our republic [1].

Literature review

At the current stage of the development of human resources management, the competency-based approach to personnel management is mainly promising. Since the 1970s, this approach has been used in personnel management practices as an effective method for selection, motivation, training and development, and evaluation processes. In 1959, the term "competence" was put into practice by R. White to identify abilities closely related to good performance, to take into account education and to form high motivation in the educational process for its implementation. R. White considered competence as "... the effective relationship of a person with the environment..." [2] and recognized the need for "competence motivation".

The idea of "competence motivation" D. It is continued in the works of McClelland [3]. From his point of view, competence, not intelligence, is the basis for effective work.

In the work "Competence in modern society" J. Raven elaborates on the concept of "competence" as an embodied phenomenon: "...events consisting of many components are relatively independent of each other, and some components are more cognitive, while others are emotional, these components can replace each other as effective behavioral components" [4,5].

The authors focused on the level of competence of employees in evaluating the effectiveness of corporate management in textile enterprises [6].

The research methodology is the dialectic method as a scientific research methodology, and methods such as statistical, selective observation, comparison, and expert evaluation were used in the research process.

Analysis and discussion of results

Some authors suggested using the "Assessment-center" method to assess the level of competence of employees of industrial enterprises. This method involves the use of various private methods and evaluation by experts of the level of use of their potential in the professional activities of employees. But in this method, the intervals of the rating scale are not sufficiently justified, and in this case, the relationship between the two elements of the matrix actually shows the extent to which the use of the competence potential of employees in the enterprise affects the effectiveness of management in the enterprise.

Therefore, in our research, we propose a matrix of "employee competence potential" and "management efficiency" in diagnosing the impact of existing employee competence potential in textile industry enterprises on the enterprise's management efficiency.

The specific features of the method of choosing a business-process model for increasing the level of professional competence based on the diagnosis of the impact of using the competence potential of employees of textile enterprises on the efficiency of enterprise management are listed as follows: assessment of the current state of the competence potential of employees; assessment of the possibilities of future development of the competence potential of employees; assessment according to competence (availability of behavioral indicators); comparative assessment of behavior with a set of its samples; availability of private methods (modeling exercises, interviews, skill tests, questionnaires); the use of the integral indicator in evaluating the level of competence of the employee and management efficiency; the possibility of choosing a business process model for regularly improving the level of professional competence.

"ASAKATEKSTIL" LLC was tested in the textile enterprise. Data on the results of diagnostic evaluation of the level of competence potential of employees in professional activity are presented in Figure 1.

The analysis of the data matrix of the relationship between employee competence potential and management efficiency in the textile enterprise presented in Figure 1 shows that, The results of the processing of the results of the survey conducted by the expert group formed among the managers and employees working in the category of specialists at the textile enterprise "ASAKATEKSTIL" LLC show that, 23,4% of respondents who took part in the survey (quadrant A) have a "high" level of competence potential, and they ensured that the management efficiency of the enterprise was also at a "high" level.

Quadrant 5 of the matrix expresses the fact that the employees of the high-level category of the textile enterprise's potential are not using this potential enough, ensuring that their activity is in the "medium" range of the efficiency of the enterprise's management. Measures to realize the desire to use the unused hidden opportunities for self-expression of professional employees with such competence potential (career promotion, promotion), that is, it is necessary to choose an effective model of the business process of increasing the level of professional competence and to carry out targeted activities based on it.

Figure 1. Interrelation matrix of employee competence potential and management efficiency in a textile enterprise⁴⁸

The data analysis shows that the majority of the respondents who participated in the survey are those in the E quadrant (48,2%), which, in turn, represents the implementation of the distribution of employees in this textile industry enterprise, taking into account the qualifications and competence level, in accordance with the requirements for the workplaces. However, it is required to carry out regular competence capacity building measures for employees corresponding to this quadrant.

Quadrant N in the matrix (5,4 %) shows the share of employees who do not want to develop themselves among the managerial and specialist staff in the textile enterprise. It will be necessary to effectively use the "team" form of work to ensure the sustainable development of the textile enterprise of this category of employees.

While quadrant I in the matrix (1,5%) is a small share, the competence potential of employees in this category is at a "low" level, which in turn causes a "low" level of management efficiency of the textile enterprise. First of all, measures should be taken to reduce the number of employees of this category in the enterprise. For this, it is necessary to organize training courses for them on the basis of specially developed programs, to establish an effective "mentor-apprentice" system.

Table 1

The results of the assessment of the level of competence potential of employees and the efficiency of management in the textile enterprise "ASAKATEKSTIL" LLC in 2024, in points⁴⁹

⁴⁸Муаллиф ишланмаси.
⁴⁹Calculated by the author.

Competence	Competency average score	The level of competence of employees development potential
The ability to develop	2,48	2,42
Focus on results	2,36	
		Managerial effectiveness
Work process organization	2,28	2,28
Leadership as a management style	2,22	
Systems thinking	2,16	
Employee development	2,48	
Ensuring teamwork in the enterprise	2,26	

At the next stage of the analysis, based on the results of processing the data of the evaluation of the competence potential of employees and the efficiency of management in the textile industry enterprise of "ASAKATEKSTIL" LLC by experts made it possible to develop a correlation function between the level of employee competence potential and management efficiency, which includes the complex of fulfillment of the mission, goals, strategy and selected corporate culture requirements in the textile industry enterprise (Table 1).

The data of Table 1 shows that in 2024, in the textile enterprise under study, as well as the results of improving the system of selecting employees, improving their qualifications, and improving their motivation, the indicator "Potential to develop the level of competence of employees" was 2,42 points in a 5-point evaluation system. There are enough internal reserves that are not used yet to use the potential of employees in the enterprise. At the same time, the level of use of the competence potential of the employees directly affects the management potential of the enterprise. In 2024, the indicator of "management efficiency" in this textile enterprise was 2,28 points.

Conclusions and suggestions

Based on the practical application of the method of evaluating the competence of employees in sewing and knitting enterprises, we offer the following suggestions to improve their work efficiency:

- it is necessary to implement a process approach in the management of employee competence in sewing and knitting enterprises;
- it is necessary to certify the workplaces of sewing and knitting enterprises;
- indicators and criteria for evaluating the competence of employees should be selected and regulations should be developed;
- factors for evaluating career positions in sewing and knitting enterprises should be determined;
- higher education institutions that train specialists must submit the requirements for the competence of professional positions;
- in sewing and knitting enterprises, the regulation of financial incentives for employees based on competence should be developed and put into practice.

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A FRESH APPROACH TO SYNTAGMATIC AND PARADIGMATIC STRUCTURES

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Abstract: *This article examines paradigmatic and syntagmatic relations through a novel lens. It provides an in-depth analysis of the nature and function of these relationships within language. Paradigmatic relations are shown to enable the selection of linguistic units based on equivalence or similarity, allowing the formation of words and structures through substitution. On the other hand, syntagmatic relations are explored as the sequential arrangement of linguistic elements, forming chains or series that contribute to the overall meaning and structure of sentences. The paper highlights the essential role these two types of relations play in the dynamic construction of language, offering new insights into their interdependent functions.*

Keywords: *Paradigmatic relations, syntagmatic relations, word forms, paradigm, syntagm, synonym, antonymy, hyponymy .*

INTRODUCTION

Syntagmatic relationships exist when signs are arranged sequentially or in parallel and work together to produce meaning. Because language is inherently sequential, linguistic signs naturally form syntagmatic relationships. For instance, the letters within a word, the words within a sentence, and even objects within a picture demonstrate this connection. These relationships are often structured by rules like spelling and grammar, but can also be more loosely defined, as seen in fashion or social contexts.

The syntagmatic relation in the sentence demonstrates:

- The word order and structure: Sarah + is painting + a picture.
- The relationship among the words conveys a clear meaning:
- It reveals that it is a picture that Sarah is painting, not something else.
- It emphasizes that it is Sarah who is painting a picture, not anyone else [2].

A paradigmatic relationship exists when one sign can be substituted for another. For instance, individual letters can be replaced by other letters, which changes the meaning. However, letters and numbers do not share a paradigmatic relationship.

Menu items demonstrate a paradigmatic relationship when they belong to the same category (such as starters, main courses, or desserts) allowing for a choice to be made. In contrast, courses show a sequential (syntagmatic) relationship, meaning an item from the starter menu is not paradigmatic with items from the dessert menu.

Typically, paradigmatic relationships are associative, as both items belong to the same membership set.

Paradigmatic relationships are diverse. As seen in previous examples, these relationships involve substituting one word for another, encompassing synonymy (similar meaning), antonymy (opposite meaning), or hyponymy (type representation) [3].

Synonym

Synonymy occurs when words share similar meanings, A means approximately B ($A \approx B$).

Here are examples of synonyms:

- She felt joyful after receiving the news \approx She felt happy after receiving the news.
- The film was fascinating and kept me engaged \approx The film was intriguing and kept me interested.
- The hike was exhausting and challenging \approx The hike was tiring and tough[3].

Antonymy

Antonymy occurs when words convey opposing meanings. The meaning of A contrasts with that of B ($A \leftrightarrow B$).

Some new examples of antonyms are:

- I prefer to work in an open space \leftrightarrow I prefer to work in a closed space
- The weather today is chilly \leftrightarrow The weather today is warm
- Her presentation was clear and understandable \leftrightarrow Her presentation was confusing and unclear[3].

Hyponymy

Hyponymy involves a relationship of super- and subordination among words. A is a type of B ($A \uparrow B$).

Here are some revised examples of hyponyms:

- Dust, mop, and vacuum (hyponyms) are types of (to) clean (hypernym).
- Apple, banana, and orange (hyponyms) are varieties of fruits (hypernym).
- Beagle, bulldog, and terrier (hyponyms) are classifications of dogs (hypernym)[2].

Conclusion. Paradigmatic and syntagmatic relationships are fundamental concepts in linguistics that define how words interact within a language. Paradigmatic relationships involve groups of words that can replace each other in specific contexts, reflecting similarities in meaning or grammatical function. For instance, consider the words "cat," "dog," and "bird." They can be used interchangeably in sentences like "I want a pet" since they belong to the same category of animals. This relationship highlights the choices available to speakers.

On the other hand, syntagmatic relationships pertain to how words combine to form meaningful structures in sentences. This aspect emphasizes the order and connection between words. For example, in the sentence "The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog," the syntagmatic relationship is crucial as it determines how the words work together cohesively to convey a complete thought.

In summary, paradigmatic relationships focus on substitution and choices among words, while syntagmatic relationships emphasize the sequential and structural arrangement, contributing to meaningful communication. Understanding both relationships is essential for grasping the complexities of language.

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ҚОНУНИЙ КУЧГА КИРМАГАН СУД ҲУКМИ ВА АЖРИМИНИ ҚАЙТА КЎРИШДА ПРОКУРОР ИШТИРОКИНИНГ ҲУҚУҚИЙ АСОСЛАРИ

Маматкаримов Сардорбек Дилшод ўғли

Жиззах вилоят прокуратураси бўлим прокурори

Аннотация: ушбу мақолада жиноят суд процессида прокурор иштирокининг ҳуқуқий асослари, хусусиятлари, жумладан апелляция инстанциясида прокурор иштирокининг процессуал асослари, функциялари ва ваколатларининг айрим жиҳатлари, шунингдек, суд процессида прокурорга юклатилган вазифалар ва уларнинг моҳияти ҳақида сўз боради.

Калит сўзлар: прокурор, апелляция инстанцияси, кассация инстанцияси, жиноят суд ишлари юретиш босқичлари, процессуал мақом, прокурорнинг ваколатлари.

Аннотация: в данной статье говорится о правовых основах и особенностях участия прокурора в уголовном судопроизводстве, в том числе о процессуальных основах участия прокурора в апелляционной инстанции, некоторых аспектах функций и полномочий, а также о задачах, возлагаемых на прокурора. в судебных разбирательствах и их характере.

Ключевые слова: прокурор, апелляционная инстанция, кассационная инстанция, стадии уголовного судопроизводства, процессуальный статус, полномочия прокурора.

Abstract: this article talks about the legal bases and features of the prosecutor's participation in the criminal court proceedings, including the procedural bases of the prosecutor's participation in the appellate instance, some aspects of functions and powers, as well as the tasks assigned to the prosecutor in the court proceedings.

Key words: prosecutor, appellate instance, cassation instance, stages of criminal court proceedings, procedural status, prosecutor's powers.

Ҳар бир мамлакатда ислохотлар амалга оширилар экан, ушбу ислохотлардан суд-ҳуқуқ соҳаси ҳеч қачон четда қолмайди. Суд-ҳуқуқ тизими мамлакатда фуқароларнинг ҳуқуқ ва эркинликларини, лозим бўлса, мажбуриятларини таъминлайдиган, давлатда эркин фуқаролик жамиятини қуришга ёрдам берадиган асосий тизимлардан бири ҳисобланади. Суд-ҳуқуқ соҳасида ислохотлар амалга оширилар экан, ушбу тизимга бевосита боғлиқ бўлган прокуратура органлари фаолиятини такомиллаштириш, ундаги мавжуд айрим ваколатларни қайта кўриб чиқилишига олиб келади. Сабаби, суд соҳасидаги муҳим ўзгаришлар, албатта, прокуратура органлари фаолиятига ҳам ўз таъсирини ўтказмасдан қолмайди. Бундан ташқари, мамлакатимизни

стратегик ривожлантириш ҳамда суд-ҳуқуқ тизимини янада такомиллаштириш ҳақидаги нормаларда прокуратура органларига оид бўлган қоидаларнинг ҳам мавжудлиги ушбу тизим мамлакатнинг ижтимоий, иқтисодий ҳамда сиёсий ҳаётида муҳим ўринга эгалигидан далолат беради.

Жумладан, 2017-2021 йилларда Ўзбекистон Республикасини ривожлантиришнинг бешта устувор йўналишлари бўйича “Ҳаракатлар стратегияси”да фуқароларнинг одил судловга эришиш даражасини ошириш, суд ҳокимиятининг чинакам мустақиллигини таъминлаш, инсон ҳуқуқ ва эркинликларини ишончли ҳимоя қилиш кафолатларини кучайтириш суд-ҳуқуқ соҳасидаги ислоҳотларнинг асосий йўналишлари этиб белгиланган.

Шунингдек, 2017-2021 йилларда Ўзбекистон Республикасини ривожлантиришнинг бешта устувор йўналиши бўйича “Ҳаракатлар стратегияси”ни “Илм, маърифат ва рақамли иқтисодиётни ривожлантириш йили”да амалга оширишга оид давлат дастурининг “2.3. Маъмурий ва жиноят қонунчилигини такомиллаштириш” қисмидан ўрин олган 52-бандида Судлар фаолиятида прокурор иштирокини такомиллаштириш вазифаси белгиланган бўлиб, унга кўра, давлат айбловчиси фаолиятини халқаро стандартлар ва илғор хорижий тажрибага мувофиқлаштириш; прокурорнинг айбловдан воз кечишининг ҳуқуқий асослари ва процессуал тартибини белгилаш; прокурор томонидан суд қарорларига нисбатан протест келтириш асослари ва тартибини қайта кўриб чиқиш ҳамда илғор хорижий тажрибага мослаштириш; прокурор томонидан қонуний кучга кирган ҳукмлар, ҳал қилув қарорлари, ажримлар ёки қарорлар бўйича ишларни, иш юзасидан тарафлар мурожаати (прокурордан ташқари) бўлган ҳолдагина, суддан ўрганиш учун олиш тартибини белгилаш; қонунда назарда тутилган ҳоллардан ташқари судларда бошқа шахсларнинг ташаббуси билан кўзғатилган фуқаролик ва иқтисодий ишларнинг кўрилишида прокурор ўз ташаббуси билан иштирок этишини истисно этиш; Олий суд Пленуми мажлисларида суд тизими вакиллари бўлмаган шахслар иштирокининг аниқ чегараларини белгилаш, бунда Бош прокурорнинг мажбурий равишда қатнашиш тартибини бекор қилиш назарда тутилган.

Бундан ташқари, “2022–2026 йилларга мўлжалланган Янги Ўзбекистоннинг тараққиёт стратегияси тўғрисида”ги Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг ПФ-60-сонли Фармонининг 1-иловасида қайд этилган 17-мақсадга кўра, “бугунги кунда қонунийликни қатъий таъминловчи, очиқ ва адолатли прокуратура фаолиятининг мустаҳкам ҳуқуқий асосларини яратиш ҳамда “Қонун — устувор, жазо — муқаррар” тамойилини бош мезонга айлантириш; Тезкор-қидирув ва тергов фаолияти устидан назоратни кучайтириш, фуқароларнинг кадр-қиммати ва эркинлигини самарали ҳимоя қилишнинг таъсирчан механизмларини жорий этиш бугунги кундаги ислоҳотларнинг бош устувор вазифаларидан саналади” деб кўрсатиб ўтилган.

Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2023 йил 16 январь кундаги “Одил судлов фаолиятини амалга оширишни самарали ташкил этиш бўйича кўшимча чора-тадбирлар тўғрисида”ги ПФ-12-сон фармони қабул қилинди. Ушбу фармоннинг 1-бандига кўра, одил судловни амалга оширишга кўмаклашиш бўйича ихтисослашган прокурорлар корпуси фаолиятида 2023 йил 1 сентябрга қадар «Судларда прокурор иштироки» ахборот тизимини яратилиб, дастлаб синов тарзида ишга тушириш ҳамда 2024 йилдан амалиётга тўлиқ жорий этиш белгиланди⁵⁰.

Шунингдек, Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2023 йил 16 январь кундаги “Одил судловга эришиш имкониятларини янада кенгайтириш ва судлар фаолияти самарадорлигини оширишга доир кўшимча чора-тадбирлар тўғрисида”ги ПФ-11-сонли фармони қабул қилинган бўлиб, унда 2022 — 2026 йилларга мўлжалланган Янги Ўзбекистоннинг тараққиёт стратегиясида белгиланган вазифаларга мувофиқ, шунингдек, суд ҳокимиятининг чинакам мустақиллигини таъминлаш, судлар фаолияти самарадорлиги ва одил судлов сифатини ошириш вазифалари белгилаб берилди. Ушбу фармоннинг 5-банди, “а” кичик бандига асосан “Ихтисослаштирилган прокурорлар корпуси” ташкил қилиниб, фармоннинг 6-бандига асосан уларга қуйидаги вазифалар юклатилди:

- «Прокуратура тўғрисида»ги Қонун ҳамда процессуал қонунчиликда белгиланган тартибда судларда ишларни кўришда прокурор ваколатини таъминлаш;

- суд процессининг бошқа иштирокчилари билан тенг ҳуқуқлардан фойдаланган ҳолда одил судлов фаолиятининг самарали амалга оширилишига кўмаклашиш, жиноят ишлари бўйича судларда давлат айбловини фақат қонунга асосланиб, ҳолисликни сақлаган ҳолда сифатли қўллаб-қувватлаш;

- фуқаролар ва юридик шахсларнинг ҳуқуқлари ҳамда қонуний манфаатлари суд йўли билан самарали ҳимоя қилинишига эришиш;

- суд амалиётидан келиб чиққан ҳолда суриштирув ва тергов органлари ходимларининг амалий кўникмалари ҳамда малакасини ошириш ишларига кўмаклашиш.

Ихтисослашган прокурорлар корпуси фаолиятининг натижадорлигини таъминлаш мақсадида, “Ихтисослашган прокурорлар корпуси” ходими судларда кўрилаётган ишлар бўйича айбловни (фуқаровий даъво) қўллаб-қувватлаш, ўзгартириш ёки ундан воз кечиш, шу жумладан Жиноят кодекси нормаларини қўллаш, жазо тури ва меъёрини белгилаш масалалари юзасидан фикрини судга баён қилишда мустақил бўлиб, қонун талабларига ва ишнинг барча ҳолатларидан келиб чиққан ҳолда ўз ишончига асосланиши белгиланди⁵¹.

⁵⁰ Қонунчилик маълумотлари миллий базаси, 18.01.2023 й., 06/23/12/0034-сон.

⁵¹ Қонунчилик маълумотлари миллий базаси, 18.01.2023 й., 06/23/11/0033-сон.

Суд ва прокуратура органларидаги бу каби муҳим ўзгаришлар, албатта, прокурорларнинг судларда самарали иштирок этиш тизимини ташкил этишга, маълум бир жиноят иши юзасидан ўз фикрини тўлиқ баён этишига, ўз позициясини судда мустақил ифодалашига, умуман олганда одил суловнинг исталган босқичида прокурор иштирокини таъминлашда муҳим аҳамият касб этади.

Ўзбекистон Республикасининг 2001 йил 29 август кунида қабул қилинган “Прокуратура тўғрисида”ги Қонун ва Жиноят-процессуал Кодекси билан ҳам ушбу органнинг фаолиятининг ҳуқуқий асослари белгиланган. Бундан ташқари, Бош прокурорнинг соҳавий буйруқлари ҳам норматив ҳуқуқий ҳужжат бўлмасда, барча прокуратура органи ходимларига тааллуқли саналади ва улар фаолиятига раҳбарий кўрсатмаларни беради. “Прокуратура тўғрисида”ги Қонуннинг 4-моддасида Ўзбекистон Республикаси прокуратураси органларининг асосий йўналишлари белгиланган. Айнан ушбу моддада “судларда жиноят ишлари кўриб чиқиладиганда давлат айбловини қувватлаш” ушбу орган фаолиятининг асосий йўналишларидан бири сифатида кўрсатилган.

Шунингдек, ушбу Қонуннинг 33-моддасида фуқароларнинг, корхоналар, муассасалар ва ташкилотларнинг ҳуқуқлари ҳамда қонуний манфаатлари суд йўли билан самарали ҳимоя қилинишини таъминлаш мақсадида барча инстанция судларида ишлар кўриладиганда прокурор қонунда белгиланган тартибда иштирок этиши; прокурор судларда жиноят ишлари кўриладиганда давлат айбловини қувватлашлиги белгилаб қўйилган.

Ўзбекистон Республикаси ЖПКнинг 34-моддаси иккинчи қисмида “Прокурор суд муҳокамасида қатнашиб, ушбу Кодекснинг 409-моддасида назарда тутилган ваколатларни амалга оширади” ҳамда 409-моддасининг 7-қисмига асосан “Прокурор жиноят ишларини кўришда ёки ҳукми ижро этиш билан боғлиқ масалаларни ёхуд ушбу Кодексда назарда тутилган ҳолларда бошқа масалаларни ҳал этишда апелляция, кассация инстанцияси судида иштирок этади” деб белгиланган⁵².

Демак, ушбу нормаларга асосан прокурор судда жиноят ишлари кўрилишида иштирок этишга мажбур ҳамда ушбу қоида суднинг исталган босқичи учун амал қилади. Амалдаги қонунчиликка кўра, прокурор биринчи инстанция, суднинг қонуний кучга кирмаган ҳукми ёки ажрими устидан протест ёки шикоят берилган тақдирда апелляция инстанциясида, шунингдек кассация инстанцияси суд мажлисларида иштирок этишга ҳамда давлат айбловини қўллаб-қувватлашга мажбур.

Жиноят ишлари бўйича судларда прокурор иштироки ҳамда унинг ваколатлари Ўзбекистон Республикаси ЖПКнинг 409-моддаси билан тартибга солинади, унга кўра, прокурор нафақат давлат айбловинини қувватлайди, балки

⁵²Қонунчилик маълумотлари миллий базаси, 15.03.2023 й., 03/23/823/0150-сон.

суд мажлисида тўпланган ва аниқланган далилларга асосланиб айбловни ўзгартириш ёки айбловдан бутунлай воз кечиш ваколатига эга эканлиги прокурор фақатгина давлат айбловини қувватловчи шахс эмас, аксинча фуқароларнинг ҳуқуқ ва эркинликларини таъминловчи тараф сифатида ҳам намоён қилади. Шунингдек, прокурор айбловни ўзгартириш ёки ундан воз кечиш ваколатидан суднинг исталган босқичида, яъни апелляция ва кассация инстанцияларида ҳам фойдаланиши мумкин.

Шунингдек, Ўзбекистон Республикаси ЖПК 497¹⁶-моддасига асосан “тегишинча Ўзбекистон Республикаси Бош прокурори, Қорақалпоғистон Республикаси, вилоят, Тошкент шаҳар прокурори, Ўзбекистон Республикаси Ҳарбий прокурори томонидан ваколат берилган прокурор” апелляция инстанцияси суд муҳокасида тараф сифатида иштирок этиши шартлиги белилаб ўтилган⁵³.

Ўзбекистон Республикаси ЖПКда прокурор тушунчаси давлат айбловчиси тушунчасига тенглаштирилган, яъни прокурор судда давлат айбловини қувватлаганлиги сабабли, унга нисбатан давлат айбловчиси тушунчаси ҳам қўлланилади. Бироқ юқорида кўрганимиздек, прокурор фақатгина айблов позициясида бўлмайди, агар прокурор иш ҳолатларига асосланиб, судланувчининг айби йўқ ёки маълум бир эпизоддаги жиноятларга алоқаси йўқ ёки жиноятни ЖКнинг умуман бошқа моддаси билан квалификация лозим деб ҳисобласа, айбловдан воз кечиши ёки уни ўзгартиришни сўраб судга мурожаат қилиши мумкин. Бундай ҳолатлар эса прокурор айблов позициясидан чекинади ва шахснинг ҳуқуқ ва эркинликларини таъминловчи шахсга айланади.

Ушбу вазиятда прокурорлар Ўзбекистон Республикасидаги Қонунларнинг аниқ ва бир хилда қўлланилиши устидан назоратни амалга оширади, шу сабабли ҳам давлат айбловчиси тушунчаси қўлланилганлиги ўринли дейиш мумкин, бироқ жиноят суд ишлари юритилишида прокурор бир тараф сифатида иштирок этади холос, суднинг исталган босқичида прокурор назоратни амалга оширувчи мансабдор шахс сифатида эмас, балки тараф сифатида иштирок этади ҳамда Ўзбекистон Республикаси ЖПКнинг 25-моддасига асосан қолган тарафлар билан тенг ҳуқуқларга эга бўлади.

Ўзбекистон Республикаси ЖПКнинг 33-моддаси 1-қисмида ҳам прокурорлар суриштирув ва дастлабки тергов босқичларида Ўзбекистон Республикаси қонунларининг аниқ ва бир хилда ижро этилиши устидан назоратни амалга ошириши белгиланган бўлиб, кўриб турганимиздек, жиноят иши судда кўришни бошланганда ушбу ваколат чегараси тугайди ва прокурорлар тенг ҳуқуқли тараф сифатида суд мажлисларида иштирок этишни бошлайди.

⁵³ Қонунчилик маълумотлари миллий базаси, 15.03.2023 й., 03/23/823/0150-сон.

Айрим олимлар ҳам прокурор судда фақат тараф бўлиб ҳисобланишини ва ҳеч қандай назорат функцияларини амалга ошириш ваколатига эга эмаслиги ҳақидаги ғояни илгари сурадилар.

Жумладан, М.С.Строгович “прокурорнинг жиноят суд процессидаги функциялари ва ваколатларига таъриф бериб, судда давлат айбловчиси сифатида майдонга чиқадиган прокурор тараф ва фақат тараф ҳуқуқий мақомига эга бўлиб, суд процессида ўзига қарама қарши тенг ҳуқуқли ҳимоя тарафи билан музокарага киради”⁵⁴ деб таъкидлайди.

В.И. Басковнинг фикрича, “прокурорнинг процессуал мақоми жиноят процессининг ҳар қандай босқичида қонунийлик кафолати сифатида ўзгаришсиз қолади. Биринчи инстанция судида давлат айбловини қувватлаш жараёнида ҳам, апелляция ва кассация инстанцияларида ҳам прокурор қонунлар ижроси устидан назоратни амалга оширувчи орган вакили бўлиб қолаверади”⁵⁵.

Бизнинг фикримизча эса, прокурор жиноят суд процесси ҳар қандай босқичининг, биринчи инстанция, апелляция ва кассация инстанциясининг тенг ҳуқуқли бир тарафидир.

Ўзбекистон Республикаси ЖПКнинг 33-моддаси 1-қисмида ҳам прокурорлар фақатгина суриштирув ва дастлабки тергов босқичларида Ўзбекистон Республикаси қонунларининг аниқ ва бир хилда ижро этилиши устидан назоратни амалга ошириши белгиланган, шунингдек, ЖПКнинг 25-моддаси 4-қисмида “Давлат ва жамоат айбловчилари, судланувчи, вояга етмаган судланувчининг қонуний вакили, ҳимоячи, жамоат ҳимоячиси, шунингдек жабрланувчи, фуқаровий даъвогар, фуқаровий жавобгар ва уларнинг вакиллари суд мажлисида тарафлар сифатида иштирок этадилар ва далиллар тақдим этиш, уларни текширишда қатнашиш, илтимос билан мурожаат қилиш, ишнинг тўғри ҳал этилиши учун аҳамиятга молик ҳар қандай масала бўйича ўз фикрларини билдиришда тенг ҳуқуқлардан фойдаланадилар” деб кўрсатилган бўлиб, ушбу норма ҳам прокурорнинг суд процессининг исталган босқичида тенг тараф сифатида намоён қилади.

Юқоридагиларни инобатга олган ҳолда, Ўзбекистон Республикаси ЖПКдан давлат айбловчиси тушунчасини чиқариб ташлашни ҳамда жиноят суд процессида тенг ҳуқуқларга эга тараф сифатида иштирок этганлиги ва функциялари фақатгина айбловни қувватлашдан иборат бўлмаганлиги сабабли, ЖПКда “давлат айбловчиси” сўзларини “прокурор” сўзлари билан алмаштиришни таклиф этмоқчимиз.

Ўзбекистон Республикаси ЖПКга киритиладиган ушбу ўзгартириш фуқароларимизда прокуратура органларига бўлган қарашни, прокуратура органларининг вазифаси фақатгина айловни қувватлашдан иборат эмаслигини,

⁵⁴ М.С.Строгович Курс советского уголовного процесса. Издательство наука. Москва 1970 г. Стр 223.

⁵⁵ В.И.Басков Курс прокурорского надзора. М., Издательство “Зерцало”, 2000.стр 208.

балки ҳимоя тарафи билан тенг ҳуқуқларга эга бўлиб, жиноят суд процесси ва тергов даврида тўпланган далилларга асосланишлигини кўрсатади.

Фойдаланилган адабиётлар рўйхати:

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Жиноят процессуал кодекси.
2. Ўзбекистон Республикаси “Прокуратура тўғрисида”ги Қонуни.
3. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2023 йил 16 январь кунидаги Одил судлов фаолиятини амалга оширишни самарали ташкил этиш бўйича кўшимча чора-тадбирлар тўғрисида”ги ПФ-12-сон фармони.
4. “Одил судловга эришиш имкониятларини янада кенгайтириш ва судлар фаолияти самарадорлигини оширишга доир кўшимча чора-тадбирлар тўғрисида”ги ПФ-11-сонли фармони
5. М.С.Строгович Курс советского уголовного процесса. Издательство наука. Москва 1970 г. Стр 223.
6. В.И.Басков Курс прокурорского надзора. М., Издательство “Зерцало”, 2000.стр 208.

THE ARTICLE ON THE TOPIC “INTERNATIONAL ECONOMIC COOPERATION OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN WITH THE REPUBLIC OF GERMANY”

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Abstract: *This article explores the evolving landscape of international economic cooperation between the Republic of Uzbekistan and the Federal Republic of Germany. It offers a detailed analysis of historical ties, trade dynamics, investment flows, joint projects, and institutional frameworks. Special attention is paid to recent economic reforms in Uzbekistan and Germany’s active involvement in various sectors such as energy, industry, education, and sustainable development. Statistical evidence, including trade volume, investment figures, and bilateral agreements, is used to provide an empirical foundation for understanding the depth and potential of this cooperation. The study concludes by identifying future opportunities for enhanced partnership in light of global economic transformations.*

INTRODUCTION

International economic cooperation serves as a vital mechanism for promoting sustainable development, technological exchange, and geopolitical balance. The partnership between Uzbekistan and Germany represents a significant example of strategic bilateral cooperation grounded in mutual economic interests, political dialogue, and shared goals. As Uzbekistan continues its path of liberalization and modernization, Germany, as one of Europe’s strongest economies, has emerged as a key partner. This paper investigates the depth and scope of their economic cooperation, highlighting historical developments, trade statistics, and investment trends.

Historical Overview of Bilateral Relations

Diplomatic relations between Uzbekistan and Germany were officially established on March 6, 1992, shortly after Uzbekistan’s independence from the Soviet Union. Germany was one of the first Western countries to open an embassy in Tashkent, demonstrating its interest in fostering diplomatic and economic ties with Central Asia’s most populous country. Throughout the 1990s and 2000s, bilateral cooperation was shaped by development assistance, educational exchange, and economic collaboration.

Germany played a pivotal role in supporting Uzbekistan’s infrastructure, education reform, and banking modernization. The German Society for International Cooperation (GIZ) has been active in the region since 1995, offering technical and policy support in governance and economic development.

The foundation of the Uzbek-German Business Council in 1995 marked a new phase of institutionalized economic cooperation. It has facilitated numerous business forums, trade missions, and public-private dialogues.

Trade Relations: Facts and Figures

Trade between Uzbekistan and Germany has seen consistent growth, with some fluctuations due to global events such as the COVID-19 pandemic. According to data from the State Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Statistics and Germany's Federal Statistical Office (Destatis):

In 2022, the bilateral trade volume reached €1.22 billion, a significant increase compared to €837 million in 2020.

Germany ranked as Uzbekistan's 10th largest trading partner globally and second within the European Union, after France.

Exports from Uzbekistan to Germany include textiles, chemical products, agricultural goods (such as fruits and nuts), and rare minerals.

Imports from Germany consist predominantly of machinery, pharmaceuticals, industrial equipment, and vehicles.

Germany's sophisticated industrial base and Uzbekistan's resource-rich economy make them natural economic complements. Furthermore, Uzbekistan benefits from the EU's Generalized Scheme of Preferences (GSP+), which provides preferential access to the European market.

Investment and Joint Projects

Germany is among the leading investors in Uzbekistan's industrial and technological sectors. According to the Ministry of Investment, Industry and Trade of the Republic of Uzbekistan, by early 2024:

Over 200 enterprises with German capital were operating in Uzbekistan, including 30 joint ventures.

Total German investment stock in Uzbekistan exceeded €800 million, covering sectors such as renewable energy, automotive components, agriculture, and logistics.

Some notable German companies operating in Uzbekistan include:

Knauf: One of the largest investors in the construction sector, with a gypsum plant in Bukhara valued at over €100 million.

MAN SE (in partnership with UzAuto): Produces heavy-duty trucks and has contributed significantly to industrial localization.

CLAAS: Supplies agricultural machinery and supports local farmer training programs.

In the energy sector, Germany supports several solar and wind energy pilot projects in Uzbekistan's arid regions, aligning with the country's goal to increase renewables to 25% of its energy mix by 2030.

Financial and Educational Cooperation

The KfW Development Bank and GIZ are active agents of German support in Uzbekistan’s development agenda. In cooperation with Uzbek ministries, they provide:

- Technical assistance for banking sector reform;
- Training for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs);
- Programs for rural infrastructure development.

Germany has also allocated €45 million in loans and grants under the “Green Central Asia” initiative, aimed at environmental sustainability and climate resilience in the region.

In the field of education:

More than 5,000 Uzbek students study German as a foreign language.

The Goethe-Institut in Tashkent and DAAD (German Academic Exchange Service) offer scholarships, teacher training, and joint research initiatives.

Several Uzbek universities collaborate with German institutions through double-degree programs and exchange platforms.

Recent Developments and Prospects

A key milestone was the visit of the President of Uzbekistan to Berlin in May 2023, which led to the signing of 15 memoranda and agreements worth over €9 billion, covering energy, metallurgy, pharmaceuticals, digital technologies, and education. The German-Uzbek Business Forum, held annually, has become a cornerstone for private-sector networking. The German Eastern Business Association (Ost-Ausschuss) actively promotes trade and investment opportunities in Uzbekistan, noting the country’s improved business environment following reforms under the “New Uzbekistan” strategy.

Germany sees Uzbekistan as a strategic partner for diversifying its energy supply chain, especially in light of recent geopolitical shifts in Eurasia. Uzbekistan’s accession to the World Trade Organization (WTO), expected in the coming years, is likely to further enhance German investment flows.

Conclusion

The economic cooperation between Uzbekistan and Germany has evolved from basic development assistance to a robust partnership grounded in mutual economic interest and strategic vision. Germany is not only a trade partner but also a key source of innovation, investment, and institutional support for Uzbekistan’s transformation. With expanding trade volume, diversified sectors of investment, and strong diplomatic backing, the partnership is poised to grow even further. Challenges remain in aligning regulatory standards, ensuring political stability, and navigating global uncertainties. However, the bilateral framework—supported by regular high-level visits, strategic dialogue, and shared values—provides a solid foundation for future economic integration. Uzbekistan’s geographic position and economic reform agenda, coupled with Germany’s technological and financial capabilities, make this cooperation a promising model for sustainable and inclusive growth.

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PILLANI TAYYORLASH VA SAQLASH JARAYONLARIDAGI OMILLARNING PILLA SIFATIGA TA'SIRI

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada pilla va pilla qobig'ining texnologik xususiyatlariga ta'sir qiluvchi tashqi mexanik kuchlar hisobiga deformatsiyalanishi hamda ho'l pillaga yuqori harorat bilan dastlabki ishlov berish, me'yoriy namlikka kelgunicha soyali quritkichlarda quritish va vaqtinchalik saqlash jarayonlarida pilla qobig'ining xususiyatlariga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar va quruq pilla xomashyosini pillakashlik korxonalariga topshirish va yil davomida saqlab qayta ishlash texnologik jarayonlarida pilla va pilla qobig'ining shikastlanishiga sabab bo'luvchi omillar o'rganilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Tayyorlash, saqlash, ho'l pilla, quruq pilla, pilla qobig'i, quritish, shikastlanish, kapalak, pilla g'umbagini o'ldirish, pilla qobig'ining xususiyatlari.*

Аннотация: *В статье изучены деформация коконов за счет внешних механических сил, влияющих на технологические свойства кокона и оболочки кокона в процессе хранения влажного кокона, а также, факторы, влияющие на свойства оболочки кокона в процессе предварительной обработки влажных коконов при высоких температурах, сушки до нормальной влажности и при хранении, а также, изучены расчет количество внешних механических сил, вызывающих повреждение кокона и его оболочки в технологических процессах.*

Ключевые слова: *Подготовка, хранение, влажный кокон, сухой кокон, оболочка кокона, сушка, повреждение, бабочка, умерщвление куколки кокона, свойства оболочки кокона.*

Abstract: *The article studies the deformation of cocoons due to external mechanical forces that affect the technological properties of the cocoon and the cocoon shell during the storage of a wet cocoon, as well as factors affecting the properties of the cocoon shell during pre-treatment of wet cocoons at high temperatures, drying to normal humidity and during storage, as well as the calculation of the amount of external mechanical forces that cause damage to the cocoon and its shell in technological processes.*

Keywords: *Preparation, storage, wet cocoon, dry cocoon, cocoon shell, drying, damage, butterfly, killing of the cocoon pupa, properties of the cocoon shell.*

Jahonda pilla xomashyosidan samarali foydalanish, xom ipakdan tayyorlangan mahsulotlar sifatini yaxshilash va assortiment turlarini kengaytirish, tannarxini kamaytirish, mahsulot sifatiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi omillarni aniqlash va ularni

bartaraf qilishga alohida e'tibor qaratilmoqda. Shuningdek, ipak tolasining iste'mol xususiyatlarini yanada yaxshilash uchun dunyo bozorida xom ipakdan tayyorlanayotgan mahsulotlar sifat ko'rsatkichlarini va raqobatbardoshligini oshirish muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Tayyorlov punktlarida yoki pillaga dastlabki ishlov berish bazalarida qabul qilingan pillalarning ichidagi g'umbagi tirik holda bo'ladi. Agar g'umbak kapalakka aylanib pilla ichidan uchib chiqib ketsa, pillalar teshilib, chuvishga yaroqsiz bo'lib qoladi. Shuning uchun pillaga dastlabki ishlov berish jarayonlarida ho'l pilla ichidagi g'umbagi o'ldirib, uning namligi 80 % gacha keltiriladi. Havodek quruq pillani tayyorlash esa soyali quritish orqali ochiq havoda amalga oshirilib, 10-12 % namlikka keltiriladi [1].

Mualliflarning ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, hozirgi kungacha pilla g'umbagini o'ldirishni quyosh nuri ta'sirida; bug' yordamida; quruq issiq havo yordamida; zaharli moddalar bilan; germetizatsiya yo'li bilan; vakuum usulida; yuqori chastotali tok bilan; sovuq havo yordamida; radioaktiv izotop va rentgen nurlari yordamida; infraqizil nur bilan va soyada quritish usullari mavjuddir [2].

Pilla g'umbagini quyosh nuri yordamida o'ldirish va quritish usuli bu- qadimgi usullardan biri bo'lib, dastlab bu usul Xitoy pillakorlari tomonidan qo'llanilgan. Ular quyosh tomonga qaragan tut daraxtining shoxlaridagi pillalardan kapalak chiqmasligini payqashgan. Ma'lumki, quyosh nurlari pilla qobig'iga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Quyosh nurida ko'p vaqt qolib ketgan pillalar yomon chiviladi. Shuning uchun ham keyingi paytda ayrim hollarda qo'llanilmoqda. Bu usul Turkmaniston va O'zbekistonning janubiy viloyatlarida qisman qo'llanilgan. Bu xududlarda quyosh nuri energiyasidan samarali foydalanish darajasi yuqoriligi gelioquritish moslamasini yaratish imkonini berdi. Gelioquritgich yordamida tirik pilla g'umbaklari o'ldirilganda ipak xom ashyosining fizik – mexanik ko'rsatkichlariga salbiy ta'sir etishi mumkin [3].

Sifatli xom ipak olish uchun esa sifatli pilla xom ashyosini tayyorlash eng asosiy omillardan biridir. yetishtirilgan tirik pillalarni terish, pillaxonaga olib kelish, dastlabki ishlov berish, transportirovka qilish va saqlash davomida pilla po'stlog'ining ma'lum qismlari shikastlanadi. Ayniqsa, pillani uzoq vaqt saqlashda tashqi muhitning o'zgarishi, qish kunlarini sovib ketishi va yoz oylarida kunning isib ketishi natijasida pilla va pilla po'stlog'ining kimyoviy o'zgarishi, turli xil hashoratlarni pilla po'stlog'iga ta'sir qilishi, hamda qobiq qatlamida hosil bo'luvchi pigmentli dog'lar pillaning nuqsonli uchastkalaridagi iplarni fizik-kimyoviy xossalarni o'zgarishiga olib keladi. Bunday o'zgarishlar dog'li va boshqa nuqsonli pillalar miqdorini ko'payishiga sabab bo'ladi [4].

Pillakashlik korxonalarida quruq pillalar qanor qoplarda 30 kg dan qilinib, balanligi bo'yicha 9 qator xolda yil davomida saqlanib qayta ishlanadi. Pastki va o'rta qatorlarda joylashgan pillalar doimiy kuch-ta'siri ostida qolishi, qatlamlar qarshiligini kamayishiga olib keladi. Natijada pilla qobig'i bahorgi, kuzgi va qishgi

mavsumlarda o'zidan namlikni oson o'tkazadi, yumshab, tashqi mexanik kuchlarga qarshiligi keskin pasayadi [5].

Pillani saqlash jarayonida pilla sirtida makromolekulalarning konformatsion holati tashqi muhit, havodagi kislorodning ta'sirida oqsil sistemalarining strukturaviy va molekulyar o'zgarishi xisobiga pilla po'stlog'i eskiradi. Ishlab chiqarish sharoitida bunday pilla po'stlog'ining chuvilishi 2-4% gacha yomonlashadi, xom ipak sifati va miqdori keskin pasayadi [6].

Pillani saqlash va texnologik xususiyatini yaxshilash uchun mualliflar tomonidan pillani oddiy usulda, plyonka qoplarda va gofropplastdan tayyorlangan qattiq taralardan saqlab chuvib ko'rishganda xom ipakni chiqishi nazorat variantiga nisbatan $4,2 \pm 2\%$ ga, pillaning chuviluvchanligi esa 6,6% ga oshgan va ezilgan pillalar foizi ikki baravarga kamaygan [7].

Xozirgi kunda yetishtirilgan pillalar pillakorlardan tayyorlov punktlariga olib borilishida va quruq pillalarni saqlash jarayonida asosan qoplardan foydalanilmoqda. Pillalarni transportirovka qilish va saqlashda qoplardan foydalanilganda pilla qobig'i shikastlanadi. Bu esa ezilgan, nuqsonli pillalar hosil bo'lishiga olib keladi. Pillalarni tayyorlash va ularga dastlabki ishlov berishda qattiq jismdan yasalgan yashiklardan foydalanish tavsiya etilgan. Lekin bu usulning kamchiligi shundaki, pillalardan bo'shagan yog'och yashiklar katta joy egallagan va keyingi mavsumgacha yo'qotilib ham ketishidir [8].

Yuqoridagi kamchiliklarni bartaraf etish maqsadida ilmiy izlanishlarimiz natijasidapillalarni transportirovka qilish va saqlashda taxlanib ixcham holatga keladigan yashiklardan foydalanishni taklif etamiz. Bunday yashiklardan foydalanilganda avvalo pilla qobig'ining shikastlanishining oldi olinadi va pillalardan bo'shagan yashiklar ixcham qilib taxlanganligi sababli uncha katta joy egallamaydi va keyingi mavsumgacha saqlanadi.

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**FORMATION OF ORGANIZATIONAL AND COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS
IN THE ACTIVITIES OF TUTORING OF HIGHER EDUCATIONAL
INSTITUTIONS**

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The current development of science, technology, production, and technology in the world determines the image of modern society. The most important characteristic feature of modern society is that globalization is noticeable in all its spheres. People with independent thinking, broad worldview, and comprehensive thinking will determine the fate of our country. Therefore, the upbringing of spiritually mature youth worthy of the future is one of the important tasks of today.

Research related to the study of the psychological and pedagogical aspects of tutoring activity was conducted by Uzbek scientists Professor A.Kholikov, research related to the formation of the professional activity of future teachers was conducted by Uzbek psychologists M.Davletshin, E.Goziev, R.Sunnatova, N.B.Safaev, Z.T.Nishonova, pedagogical scientists Sh.Abdullaeva, R.G.Safarova, S.T.Turgunov, B.Khodzhaev Sh. N. Majitova, Sh. K. Mardonov, N.A. Muslimov, B.B. Mamurov, M.B. Urazova, U.K. Khudoybergenova, R. Sunnatova. Today, all attention and opportunities are focused on ensuring the comprehensive education of young people, assisting them in solving various problems and issues that arise in the educational process. Indeed, all opportunities have been created for the younger generation to gain knowledge, realize their potential in the field of science and innovation, and actively participate in the socio-political life of our society.

In modern higher education, there are constant changes not only in teaching methods and means, but also in positions. New professions and pedagogical specialties are being introduced. Today, the educational process strives for the individualization of education. The attitude towards this trend is connected with the emergence of tutoring. In each of the available information resources, many definitions are given to the word "tutor" and the concept of "tutor function." If we combine their semantic features and define their main task for higher education, we understand that a tutor is a special teacher who accompanies a student in creating an individual educational program [27; 253-256].

Currently, there are several definitions of the term "Tutor," and when translated from English, "Tutor" literally means teacher, mentor, instructor - guide. The Dictionary of Pedagogical Terms defines [22] as "a knowledgeable mentor of their students, a person who facilitates the learning process, a teacher."

A tutor (from the Latin "Tutorem" - teacher) performs the functions of a mentor. In some cases, the lecturer also acts as a connecting link between the teacher and the listener. In this case, the lecturer acts as a consultant and mentor in mastering the knowledge they provide.

The main goal of the tutor is to effectively organize the harmony of the educational and upbringing process, regulate the relationship between the educational institution and students, help students adapt to university life and the educational process, provide them with methodological, social, and psychological assistance, and increase students' love for their chosen profession.

A tutor is a specialist in a certain field, and their main task is to provide students with certain knowledge and skills. In a broader sense, the tutor teaches the student to demonstrate their potential during the learning process, to better understand themselves, and to make the right decisions and choices in learning and life. It helps the student understand the consequences of each step and action, find their interests in life.

For this, the tutor thoroughly analyzes the students' interests, inclinations, problems, and difficulties. He carefully studies the intellectual and psychological environment surrounding the student. In short, the tutor is a connecting force between the student and the educational process. Its main activity is to carry out activities in a higher educational institution, to be an employee who meets the relevant qualification requirements, possesses high moral qualities, and assists in the education of students of the assigned group, as well as in the meaningful organization of their free time from classes, educating them in the spirit of humanism, justice, diligence, love for the Motherland, involving them in clubs and circles organized within the framework of the Five Important Initiatives, conducting activities aimed at eliminating all issues and problems arising in the educational process in the prescribed manner.

The tutor regularly visits the residential addresses of students living in student dormitories, rented and private apartments, studying the conditions created there and the problems of students and taking measures to improve them [4].

The peculiarities of the newly emerging tutoring activity in the higher education system of our republic are as follows:

1. A tutor is a person who contributes to the personal development of students, their worthy participation in university, republican, and international competitions and olympiads, as well as the meaningful organization of their free time, who is engaged in career guidance, educating young men and women in the spirit of love for the Motherland, involving them in various scientific circles, studying problems and shortcomings, and finding comprehensive solutions to them.

2. The main goal of tutors is to strengthen the relationship between the university and students in the effective organization of the educational process, to help students adapt to university life and the educational process, to provide them with methodological, social, and psychological assistance, and to increase students' love for their chosen profession. At the same time, they regularly analyze and improve the quality of students' lessons, ensure that they spend their free time meaningfully, and are constantly aware of their social situation.

3. Tutors carry out their activities in the spiritual-educational and moral-educational, educational and educational-methodical, as well as scientific, innovative and research areas.

4. Each tutor attracts students of the assigned groups to clubs and circles organized within the framework of five important initiatives and creates an opportunity for them to demonstrate their creative abilities and talents. Protects the rights and legitimate interests of students, assists in creating conditions for their education, pursuit of knowledge, living and recreation, and keeps them informed about innovations in this area.

5. Establishes systematic work on strengthening the academic discipline of students, forming such qualities as creative thinking, honesty, and truthfulness. It identifies talented and gifted students and assists them in their worthy participation in various competitions and olympiads, as well as in the implementation of student projects and startups.

6. It monitors the level of assimilation of lessons by students, provides them with innovative educational technologies and educational and methodological materials, information resources, and creates a basis for the wide and effective use of these resources.

7. Tutors help students with a number of issues that concern them, in particular, providing students with housing and helping them master missed lessons.

8. Each tutor has the right to monitor the classes of the academic groups assigned to him, student attendance and monitoring the quality of classes, to demand the fulfillment of the duties assigned to students, to issue an announcement for placement in the dormitory and to ensure the student's participation in the meeting of the commission in this regard, to participate in the decision on the issue of issuing a character reference and academic leave to the student, to give a conclusion and opinion on their encouragement or punishment, and on their recommendation for various scholarships.

9. Every tutor is obliged to respect the honor, dignity, and reputation of students, to be regularly aware of their physical, mental, and psychological state, to monitor their academic, spiritual, and scientific activities, to monitor the attendance of young men and women in classes, and to maintain constant communication with the parents of young people and themselves.

It should be noted that tutors, by virtue of their duties, are highly responsible individuals. After all, a tutor regularly works with a student whose worldview is just beginning to form. The main task of such a specialist is to help another person turn learning into an effective and interesting process. The tutor will have to work both with the whole group and individually. It is also the tutor's responsibility to influence students in matters of which fields of knowledge to emphasize, choosing a future profession, orienting to another specialty if necessary, establishing a balance between study and daily life, and properly organizing time.

Professional self-assessment is a type of self-assessment in terms of personal development and changes very complexly, full of contradictions.

As a result of research on the influence of self-awareness on the understanding of others, it was concluded that the higher the level of formation of the ability to evaluate another, the more accurately self-assessment is carried out.

The sequence in understanding the characteristics of another person determines the sequence of understanding the personal "I." In this way, he protects and strengthens his self-esteem. People who have a correct self-image are less inclined to attribute their shortcomings to others and therefore have the opportunity to express a more correct opinion about others (A.A.Bodalyov). People who express relatively positive opinions about others also express positive opinions about themselves and evaluate other individuals.

The practice of tutoring, implemented on the basis of well-thought-out requirements and proposals, expresses confidence that the student will be assessed at the university as a supportive mentor and a skilled consultant. These specialists, who reveal the student's strengths, reserve abilities, and teach them to work on shortcomings, contribute to the training of a new generation of personnel.

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KATTA GURUH BOLALARNI TABIAT BILAN TANISHTIRISHDA BADIY ADABIYOTLARDAN FOYDALANISH METODLARI VA VOSITALARI

Jabborova Dilbaroy Murotaliyevna

Quva tumani 46-MTT hamshirasi

Annotasiya: *Ushbu maqolada katta guruh bolalarini tabiat bilan tanishtirishda badiiy adabiyotning ahamiyati samaradorligini oshirishga yo'naltirilgan ilmiy-metodik tavsiyalar ishlab chiqish.*

Kalit so'zlar: *iqtisodiy tiklanish, iqtisodiy o'nnglanish, ma'naviy poklanish, ma'naviy yuksalish, ekskursiya*

2017-yil 20-aprelda Oliy ta'lim tizimini tubdan takomillashtirish, mamlakatni ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlantirishning ustuvor vazifalaridan kelib chiqqan holda, kadrlar tayyorlash mazmunini tubdan qayta tayyorlash, xalqaro standartlar darajasiga mos oliy ma'lumotli mutaxassislar tayyorlash uchun zarur sharoitlar yaratilishini ta'minlash maqsadida O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Shavkat Miromonovich Mirziyoyevning "Oliy ta'lim tizimini yanada rivojlantirish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi PQ-2909 sonli qarorlari chiqdi. Qaror 16 ta band va 75 ta ilovadan iborat. Qarorning asosiy maqsadi, Oliy ta'lim tizimini tubdan takomillashtirish, mamlakatni ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlantirishning ustuvor vazifalaridan kelib chiqqan holda, kadrlar tayyorlash mazmunini tubdan qayta ko'rish, xalqaro standartlar darajasiga mos oliy ma'lumotli mutaxassislar tayyorlash uchun zarur sharoitlar yaratilishini ta'minlash;

Oliy ta'lim tizimida o'z yo'nalishlari bo'yicha dunyoning yetakchi ilmiy-ta'lim muassasalari bilan yaqin hamkorlik aloqalari o'rnatish, o'quv jarayoniga ilg'or xorijiy tajribalarni joriy etish, ayniqsa, istiqbolli pedagog va ilmiy kadrlarni xorijning yetakchi ilmiy ta'lim muassasalarida stajirovkadan o'tkazish va malakasini oshirish borasidagi ishlar talab dajada emasligini, oliy ta'limda ishlovchi pedagog zamon bilan hamnafas bo'lishi kerakligi ta'kidlab o'tildi. "Biz iqtisodiy o'nnglanish, iqtisodiy tiklanish, iqtisodiy rivojlanishni ma'naviy o'nnglash, ma'naviy poklanish, ma'naviy yuksalish harakatlari bilan tamomila uyg'un bo'lishni"- istayotgan bir davrda yashayapmiz. Bu harakatlar mamlatimizning barcha jabhalarida mehnat qilayotgan kishilardan, jumladan, yoshlar ta'lim-tarbiyasi bilan shug'ullanayotgan kishilardan yuksak professional tayyorgarlikka, g'oyaviy-siyosiy barkamol, tashkilotchilikka va boshqaruvchilikka ega bo'lish lozimligini taqazo qilmoqda. Chunonchi, ta'lim sohasidagi tub islohotlar, yangilanayotgan, ta'lim-tarbiyaning mazmuni, shakli, usullari, vositalari milliy lashib, o'zbekona urf-odatlar o'quv-tarbiya jarayoniga faol kirib borayotgan bir sharoitda yuz bermoqda. Bu o'zgarishlar har bir o'qituvchini yangicha fikrlashga, sharqona ish yuritishga, tadbirkorlikka, ishbilarmonlikka, ma'naviy-ma'rifiy ishlarning faol ishtirokchisi bo'lishga undaydi.

Ilm - fan, ma`rifat - madaniyat asrlar davomida insoniyat olamida so`nmas mash`al bo`lib, yoritib kelgan. Mamlakatimiz mustaqilligi sharofati bilan bugungi kunda bu mash`al tobora porlab, o`zgacha ahamiyat kasb egmoqda. Bizga ma`lum bo`lmagan tarix zarvaraqlari qatida pinhona yotgan qadpiyatlapimiz, noyob qo`lyozma asarlarimiz, qadimiy yodgorliklarimiz istiklol sharofati bilan tadqiqotchi olimlarimiz tomonidan teran o`rganilmoqda. Tarix - insonning barkamollik, taraqqiyot yo`li. Moziyii bilmaslik o`zini anglamaslikdir. O`zini anglagan xalqgina buyuk kishilarning nomlarini e`zozlab ruhi poklarini doimo yod etadi. Agar biz o`tmish tariximizga, nazar tashlasak, yashab ijod etgan pedagoglarimiz o`zlari ijod etgan davrlardayoq bolaning har tomonlama usishida, ma`naviy ozuqa beradigan tabiatning noz-ne`matlari uning mo`jizalaridir deb ta`kidlab o`tganlar.

Tarix zarvaraqlarida o`zlarining o`chmas, unutilmas nomlarini qoldirgan buyuk pedagoglar bola tarbiyasida tabiatning ahamiyati. uning bola ruhiyatiga qanday ta`sir qilishi haqida ilmiy fikrlari i aytib utganlar.

Sharq mutafakkirlarining tabiat hayotida insonniig tutgan o`rni haqidagi fikrlari va ilmiy asarlarini o`rganadilar. Bolalar tabiat burchangida, haynovot olami, er maydonchasida o`sadigan o`simliklar dunyosi haqida bilimga ega bo`ldilar hamda ularni parvarnsh qilishning ko`nikma va malakalarini egallaydilar. Hozirgi kunda eng dolzarb muammolardan biri ekologik muammodir. Shu sababdan ham bolalar bog`chalarida ham ekologik ta`lim-tarbiya berishga alohida e`tibor berilmoqda. Tabiat bilan tanishtirish mobaynida bolalarga ekologik ta`lim- tarbiya berish usullari, «Qizil kitob» haqida qisqacha ma`lumot va «Qizil kitob»ga kiritilgan, noyob o`simlik va hayvonot olami haqida ham bilim berishga katta o`rin berilgan.

Shunindek, maktabgacha ta`lim muassasalarida katta guruh bolalarni tabiat bilan tanishtirish sohasidagi yangi tajribalarni ham o`rganib olishlari zarur. Bolalarni tabiat qonun-qoidalari bilan tanishtirishning ahamiyati shundaki, ularning to`g`ri o`sib ulg`ayishiga, tabiatda bo`ladigan voqea-hodisalarni ilmiy asosda tushunishga olib keladi. Bu bolaning shakllanishida, tabiatga, ona- Vatanga, tabiat boyliklariga bo`lgan mehr-muhabbatni oshiradi. Darhaqiqat, tabiatni muhofaza qilish ayrim kishilarning ishi deb qaralmasdan barchamizning ishimiz ekanligi esdan chiqarmasligimiz kerak. Katta guruh bolalarning xar tomonlama kamol topishida tabiat bilan tanishtirishning o`ziga xos tarbiyaviy xususiyatlari bor. Bu jarayon turli vositalar, metodlar orqali amalga oshiriladi. Yana shuni ta`kidlash joizki tabiathaqidagi bolalar uchun nafaqat sharq olimlari balki g`arb pedagoglari tomonidan o`rganilgan.

Ushbu mavzuni o`rganishda biz G`arb pedagoglaridan: Y.A.Komenskiy, J.J.Russo, I.G.Pestolotsiy kabi olimlarning bola tarbiyasida tabiatning tutgan o`rni haqidagi ilmiy asarlari bilan tanishamiz.

Rus pedagoglaridan K.D.Ushinskiyning, "Inson tarbiya predmeta sifatida" asari bilan tanishamiz.

Ushinskiy "Meni pedagogikada var var hisoblasangiz ham, lekin men o`z hayot tajribamda shunday xulosaga keldim. Go`zal tabiat yosh qalbgga shunday katta

tarbiyaviy ta`sir ko`rsatadiki, hatto pedagogikaning ta`siri ham u bilan raqrbatlashishga ojizdir", -degan edi.

Bizga ma`lumki, bola dunyoga kelar ekan ilk yoshligidan boshlab tabiat bilan muloqotda bo`ladi. Bu haqda buyuk pedagog olimlarimiz o`zlari yashab o`tgan davrda, bolaning har tomonlama o`shida ma`naviy ozuqa beradigan tabiatning noz-ne`matidir deb, ta`kidlab o`tganlar. Biz hozirda o`tmishdagi pedagoglarimizning dono fikrlari va ilmiy asarlariga suyanganmiz o`zimizning pedagogik faoliyatimizda foydalanamiz.

Bolalar bog`chasida bolalarni tabiat bilan tanishtirish jarayonida xilma-xil metodlar ko`rgazmali kuzatish, rasmlarni ko`rish, diafilm va kinofilmlarni namoyish qilish amaliy o`yin metodi, mehnat, oddiy tajribalar, ogzaki metod tarbiyachining hikoyasi, badiiy asarlarni o`qish, suhbat metodlaridan foydalaniladi. Tabiatni bolalar bilan birgalikda kuzatishni tashkil etar ekan, tarbiyachi bir qator vazifalarni hal etadi. Bolalarda tabiat haqidagi bilimni shakllantiradi, kuzatishni orgatadi, kuzatuvchanlikni o`stiradi, estetik jihatdan tarbiyalaydi.

Yosh bolalarni har tomonlama kamol toptirish va tarbiyalash turli vositalar yordamida amalga oshiriladi. Bulardan eng samaralisi maktabgacha yoshdagi bolarni tabiat bilan tanishtirishdir. Tabiat-bolani ma`naviy boyitishning bitmas- tunganmas manbaidir. Bolalar doimo u yoki bu formada tabiat bilan aloqada bo`ladilar. Ularni yam-yashil o`tloqlar va o`rmonlar, anvoi gullar, kapalaklar, qongizlar, qushlar, hayvonlar,, suzib yurgan bulutlar, pag`a-pag`a yog`ayotgan qor uchqunlari, jilg`a va havas uyg`otadi, ularni faoliyatga undaydi. Tabiat bilan muloqotda bo`lish bolalarda atrof-olam haqida aniq bilim, jonli mavjudotga insoniy munosabatda bo`lishni shakllantirishga yordam beradi.

Bolani tabiat bilan tanishtirish, uni tabiatni tushunishga o`rgatish, tabiatga ehtiyotkorlik bilan munosabatda bo`lishni tarbiyalash maktabgacha ta`lim muassasining eng muhim vazifasidir. Maktabgacha ta`lim muassasalarida bolalar tabiat haqida juda bo`maganda elementar bilimlarni egallab olib, o`simliklarni o`stirish, hayvonlarni parvarish qilishning oddiy usullarini o`rganib, tabiatni kuzatish, uning go`zalliklarini ko`ra olishni bilib olgan taqdiridagina ularda tabiatga nisbatan ehtiyotkorlik va g`amxo`rona munosabatda bo`lishni tarbiyalash imkoniyati tug`uladi. Katta guruh bolalarida tabiatga jonajon o`lka, ona-vatanga muhabbat xuddi mana shu asosda shakllanadi.

Katta guruha bolalarida o`yin narsa va hodisalarning mazmunini bolaning o`z tajribasida bilib olishga, mazkur mazmunlarni ishlata bilishga mashq qildiradi. Bolaning shaxsiy sifatlari boshqalar bilan munosabatlarda tarkib topib boradi.

O`yin faoliyatining pirovardida ta`lim faoliyati yuzaga keladi. Bu faoliyatning maqsadi ma`lum axborotlarni - bilimlarni harakatlar va amallarni o`zlashtirishdan iboratdir. Odamning o`z maqsadiga ko`ra batamom o`rganish va o`zlashtirishdan iborat bo`lgan mana shunday maxsus faoliyati ta`lim faoliyati deyiladi. Psixologik jihatdan olganda, ta`lim faoliyati o`z ichiga quyidagi jarayonlarni oladi: ma`lum bir nazariy va amaliy faoliyat to`rini muvaffaqiyatli amalga oshirish uchun ob'yektiv

olaning eng muhim xususiyatlariga doir axborotlarni o'zlashtirish, bu jarayonning mahsuloti bilimlardir. Mana shu faoliyatni, ya'ni bilimlarni almashtirishda yuzaga keladigan usul va operatsiyalarni egallash, bu jarayonlarning mahsuloti malaka va uquvlardan iboratdir. Ta'lim faoliyatining tarkibi juda ham murakkab bo'lib tarkibiga - ilmlar, tushunchalar, malakalar, odatlar, uquvlar kiradi.

Ta'lim faoliyati maxsus ravishda tashqil etilgan sharoitda amalga oshiriladi. Katta yoshli kishilar bolalarning taraqqiyotlariga faol ta'sir etib, ularning ta'lim faoliyatlarini hamda bu faoliyat bilan bog'liq bo'lgan xatti - harakatlarni tashqil qiladilar. Bu faoliyat va harakatlarni insoniyat ijtimoiy tajribasini o'rganish tomoni yo'naltirilishidir. Shunday qilib, ta'lim faoliyati katta kishilar tomonidan tashqil qilinib boshqariladi va tizimli ravishda nazorat qilib boriladi. Ma'lumki, ta'lim faoliyati bilan tarbiya ishlari uzviy bog'liqdir. Maktabgacha tarbiya muassasalarida bolalarga beriladigan bilimlar xilma-xil shakllarda: mashg'ulotlarda, ekskursiyada, kundalik hayotda amalga oshiriladi.

Tabiat bilan tanishtirish mashg'ulotlarida beriladigan bilimlar bolalarning imkoniyatlari hamda urab turgan tabiatning xususiyatlarini nazarda tutgan holda izchil rivojlantirish imkonini beradi. Mashg'ulotlarni ta'limiy ahamiyati bu bolalarga mashg'ulotlarda berilishi yoki aniqlanishi hamda umumlashtirilishi lozim bo'lgan bilim hajmi, bilish jarayonlarini rivojlantiruvchi, nutqini ustiruvchi, qiziqishlarini o'stiruvchi, qobiliyatlarini rivojlantiruvchi bo'lmog'i lozim. Tarbiyaviy ahamiyati esa bolalarda kattalarga hurmat, Vatasha, o'z o'lkasi tabiatiga mexr - muhabbat tabiatni avaylab - asrash. tabiat bergan ne'matlardan o'z o'rnida unumli foydalanish kabi hislatlar tarbiyalanadi.

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KATTA GURUH BOLALARNI TABIAT BILAN TANISHTIRISHDA BADIY ADABIYOTLARDAN FOYDALANISHNING O'ZIGA XOS XUSUSIYATLARI

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O'zbekiston Respublikasida maktabgacha ta'lim bolani uning individual xususiyatlarini hisobga olgan, davlat va jamiyat ehtiyojlariga bog'liq holda har tomonlama sog'lom va yetuk, shu bilan birga maktabga tayyorlangan holda shakllantirish maqsadini ko'zlaydi.

O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Sh. M. Mirziyoevning mamlakatimizni 2016 yilda ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlantirishning asosiy yakunlari va 2017 yilga mo'ljallangan iqtisodiy dasturning eng muhim ustuvor yo'nalishlariga bag'ishlangan Vazirlar Mahkamasining kengaytirilgan majlisidagi ma'ruzasida:

“Oldimizda yoshlarga tarbiya berish, psixologiya va boshqa turli sohalarda kadrlarni tayyorlash va qayta tayyorlash bo'yicha murakkab vazifalar turibdi. Yana bir muammoni hal etish muhim hisoblanadi: bu – pedagoglar va professor-o'qituvchilar tarkibining professional darajasi, ularning maxsus bilimlaridir. Bu borada ta'lim olish, ma'naviy- ma'rifiy kamolot masalalari va haqiqiy qadriyatlarni shakllantirish jarayonlariga faol ko'mak beradigan muhitni yaratish zarur..”¹ ekanligi ta'kidlab o'tildi.

O'qitish jarayonida bolalar mehnatga, o'qishga yaxshi tayyorgarlikni ham o'zlashtiradilar. Shaxsning shakllanishi kishilik jamiyati tomonidan yaratilgan ijtimoiy-tarkibiy tajribani o'zlashtirish, ta'lim-tarbiya berish orqali amalga oshiriladi. Bu har xil faoliyatlarda yuzaga keladi. Bolalar egallashlari lozim bo'lgan mazmunni tanlash, uni egallab olishiga rahbarlik qilish kattalar tomonidan ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonida amalga oshiriladi. Tarbiya va ta'limning mazmuni, vositalari, metodlari, bolaning rivojlanish jarayoni ularning yoshi bilan izohlanadi. Jumladan, kichik yoshdagi bolalar bilan ish olib borilganda, ularning mustaqil hayotga butunlay moslashmaganligi hisobga olinadi.

Keyingi yosh guruhlarda maktabgacha yoshdagi bolaning mustaqilligi, moslashishi ancha oshib boradi. Shunga muvofiq tarzda ta'lim-tarbiyaviy ishlarning vazifalari, mazmuni, vositalari o'zgaradi. Bolalarning maktabgacha yoshning oxiriga borib erishgan rivojlanish darajasi ular bilan olib boriladigan ta'lim-tarbiya ishini murakkablashtirish imkonini beradi.

Bolalar hayotining birinchi yilidanoq faoliyatning eng oddiy turlari undagi shaxsiy kobiliyatlar, xususiyatlar, tevarak-atrofga ma'lum bir munosabatning shakllanishida asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi. M: kattalarning bolalar bilan bo'ladigan

hissiy, hissiy-predmetli munosabatlaridanoq bolada dastlabki ijtimoiy talabni vujudga keltiradi, dastlabki xarakter va tasavvurlar, taassurotlar shakllana boshlaydi.

Mashg'ulotlardagi o'quv faoliyati orqali bolalar tevarak- atrofda tabiat, ijtimoiy hayot, kishilar tug'risidagi bilimlarni o'zlashtirib oladilar. Shuningdek, ularning aqliy va amaliy bilimlari kengayib boradi.

Agar ta'lim jarayonida 3-4 yoshli bolalar diqqati tabiat, kishilar to'g'risidagi aniq dalillarga qaratilsa, 5-6 yoshli bolalarga ta'lim berishda asosiy e'tibor muhim bog'liqliklar va munosabatlarga, ulardagi oddiy tushunchalarni shakllantirishga qaratiladi. Bular orqali bolalarda tushunarli tafakkur rivojlantiriladi.

Odam shaxsini shakllantirish bu tevarak-atrofdagi dunyoga, tabiatga, mehnatga, boshqa odamlarga va uziga munosabat sistemasini izchil o'zgartirish va murakkablashtirishdir. Bu uning butun hayoti davomida ro'y beradi.

Bolalar o'rtoqlarini, kattalarni tinglashni o'rganadilar. Bolalarni nutqlari ravonlashib bolalar bilan tashkil etiladigan badiiy faoliyat bolalarni estetik rivojlanishiga yordam beradi. Yangi ko'nikma va malakalarni egallashlari

maktabgacha ta'lim yoshdagi bolalarni o'yin harakatlari mehnat faoliyatlarini boyitadi.

Mashg'ulotlar har bir bolaning doimo o'rgatilgan tartibga amal qilishga talab etadi. Mashg'ulotda bolalar qay vaqtda ko'rsatmani aniq bajarish kerakligiga qay vaqtda o'z xoxishlari bilan ish tutishlari mumkinligini bilib oladilar.

Katta guruh bolalari bilan o'tkaziladigan mashg'ulotlar mazmunan biroz murakkab va bolalarni yetarli darajada aqliy mehnat irodaviy kuch berishni talab etadi. Katta guruhda o'tkaziladigan mashg'ulotlarni bir necha xususiyatlarini belgilab o'tish mumkin.

Mashg'ulotlar faqat hajmi jihatdan kengaytirilmaydi, balki tarbiyachi bu mashg'ulotlarda bolalarni tasavvurlarini aniqlashga har bir guruh narsalarining xarakterli va muhim belgilarini ochib berishga ham intiladi. Pedagog bolalar diqqatini ular atrofini o'rab olgan olamdagi narsa va hodisalar o'rtasida mavjud bo'lgan bog'lanish va aloqalariga qaratadi va ularni ochishga bolalarda qiziqish uyg'otadi. Katta maktabgacha ta'lim yoshdagi bolalar barcha bog'lanishlarni bilishi shart emas. Bolalar bilimining sistemaliligi va bog'liqligi ularning erkin o'yinlarida ham sayr ekskursiya vaqtida ko'rgan va eshitganlarini hikoya qilib berishlarida ham namoyon bo'ladi. Katta guruh bolalarining sistemali va izchil kuzatish natijasida ayrim voqea va hodisalar turli bog'lanishlarni aniqlash imkoni tarbiyachi maxsus rivojlantirib taraqqiy ettirib boradi.

Katta guruhlarda bolalar bilan o'tkaziladigan mashg'ulotlarning dastur talablariga muvofiq tarbiyachi sistemali bilim berishga alohida ahamiyat beradi. Keyinchalik maktabda o'qish va hayotiy tajribalarni saqlanib borishi natijasida tabiat haqidagi tasavvurlari ortib boradi. Bolalar mashg'ulotlar orqali noaniq bilimdan

ularni differensial farq qiladigan bilimlarini ko'ra bilishga xarakat qilish, boshqa tomondan aloqa o'rnatish, buyum hodisalarni qandaydir guruhlariga birlashtirish bolalarni bilimlari ustida ishlashdan iborat.

Tarbiyachi bolalarni yil fasllari haqidagi tasavvurlarini chuqurlashtirib sistemaga solib ularni tabiatda ro'y beradigan hodisalarni izchil tushunishlariga harakat qiladilar. Bilimlarni sistemaga solishni bilgan bu yoshdagi bolalar hikoya

to'qishni tarbiyachi taklif etgan reja bo'yicha so'rab berish kabi topshiriqlarni bajara oladilar.

Hozirgi kunda maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida birlalarni Davlat talablari asosida tarbiyalash uchun mashg'ulotlarni pedagogik texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etish eng dolzarb muammolardan biri bo'lib kelmoqda.

Maktabgacha ta'lim yoshdagi bolo shaxsini rivojlantirish, shakllantirish, ular tomonidan ijtimoiy tarixiy tajribani o'zlashtirish asnosida amalga oshiriladi. Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida o'qitish davomida tevarak atrofdagi hayot-tabiat, odamlar mehnati, ijtimoiy hodisalar va voqealar haqidagi bilimlarni tarbiyalashni asosini tashkil etadi.

Agar ta'lim jarayonida 3-4 yoshli bolalar diqqati tabiat, kishilar to'g'risidagi konkret faktlarga qaratilsa, 5-6 yoshli bolalarga ta'lim berishda asosiy e'tibor muhim bog'liqliklar va munosabatlarga, ulardagi oddiy tushunchalarni shakllantirishga qaratiladi. Bular orqali bolalarda tushunarli tafakkur rivojlantiriladi.

Kichik maktab yoshidagi bolalar uchun o'qish asosiy faoliyat bo'lib qoladi va bu faoliyatni bolalar ijtimoiy ahamiyatli faoliyat deb anglay boshlaydilar. Bola o'zini maktab o'quvchisi deb tushuna boshlaydi.

Demak, bolani tarbiyalashda, uning rivojlanishida faoliyat eytakchi rol o'ynaydi. Shuning uchun ta'lim-tarbiya muassasalarida va oilada bolaning hayotini u turli-tuman faoliyatlar bilan shug'ullana oladigan qilib tashkil etish kerak. Bunga albatta, bolalar faoliyatining mazmunini boyitib borish, yangi bilim malakalarni singdirish mustaqilligini rivojlantirish bilan erishiladi.

Odam shaxsini shakllantirish bu tevarak-atrofdagi dunyoga, tabiatga, mehnatga, boshqa odamlarga va uziga munosabat sistemasini izchil o'zgartirish va murakkablashtirishdir. Bu uning butun hayoti davomida ro'y beradi. Bunda bolalik va o'smirlik yoshi ayniqsa muhimdir.

Bolalar o'rtoqlarini, kattalarni tinglashni o'rganadilar. Bolalarni nutqlari ravonlashib bolalar bilan tashkil etiladigan badiiy faoliyat bolalarni estetik rivojlanishiga yordam beradi. Yangi ko'nikma va malakalarni egallashlari

maktabgacha ta'lim yoshdagi bolalarni o'yin harakatlari mehnat faoliyatlarini boyitadi.

Katta guruhlarda mashg'ulotlarni tashkil etish dasturi va usullari o'quv faoliyati va xarakterining kasb etib boradi.

Mashg'ulotlar har bir bolaning doimo o'rgatilgan tartibga amal qilishga talab etadi. Mashg'ulotda bolalarni o'zini darsdagi kabi tutishga odatlantirishni tarbiyalash o'z ichiga: Bolalarda tarbiyachining so'ziga diqqatini tez qarata olishi, uning talab va ko'rsatmalarini darhol bajarishini, takrorlashni, qayta so'ramaslikni materialni tayyorlash uchun ortiqcha sarf qilmaslik ko'nikmalarini oladi. Agar bolalar uchta piyolani darhol olib xoxlagan tartibda emas tarbiyachi qanday ko'rsatgan va tushuntirgan bo'lsa, xuddi shu tartibda qo'yishlari kerak.

Mashg'ulotda bolalar qay vaqtda ko'rsatmani aniq bajarish kerakligiga qay vaqtda o'z xoxishlari bilan ish tutishlari mumkinligini bilib oladilar.

Katta guruh bolalarida o'yini bilan mashg'ulot orasidagi farq yaqqol ko'zga tashlanadi. Farq albatta bo'lishi shart. hatto tarbiyachi o'zini tutishi bolalarga muomalasi kundalik sayr yoki o'yin vaqtdagiga qaraganda biroz jiddiyroq qat'iyroq bo'lishlari kerak.

Katta guruh bolalari bilan o'tkaziladigan mashg'ulotlar mazmunan biroz murakkab va bolalarni yetarli darajada aqliy mehnat irodaviy kuch berishni talab etadi. Katta guruhda o'tkaziladigan mashg'ulotlarni bir necha xususiyatlarini belgilab o'tish mumkin.

Mashg'ulotlar faqat hajmi jihatdan kengaytirilmaydi, balki tarbiyachi bu mashg'ulotlarda bolalarni tasavvurlarini aniqlashga har bir guruh narsalarining xarakterli va muhim belgilarini ochib berishga ham intiladi. Pedagog bolalar diqqatini ular atrofini o'rab olgan olamdagi narsa va hodisalar o'rtasida mavjud bo'lgan bog'lanish va aloqalariga qaratadi va ularni ochishga bolalarda qiziqish uyg'otadi. Katta maktabgacha ta'lim yoshdagi bolalar barcha bog'lanishlarni bilishi shart emas. Bolalar bilimining sistemaliligi va bog'liqligi ularning erkin o'yinlarida ham sayr ekskursiya vaqtida ko'rgan va eshitganlarini hikoya qilib berishlarida ham namoyon bo'ladi. Katta guruh bolalarining sistemali va izchil kuzatish natijasida ayrim voqea va hodisalar turli bog'lanishlarni aniqlash imkoni tarbiyachi maxsus rivojlantirib taraqqiy ettirib boradi.

Katta guruhlarda bolalar bilan o'tkaziladigan mashg'ulotlarning dastur talablariga muvofiq tarbiyachi sistemali bilim berishga alohida ahamiyat beradi. Keyinchalik maktabda o'qish va hayotiy tajribalarni saqlanib borishi natijasida tabiat haqidagi tasavvurlari ortib boradi. Bolalar mashg'ulotlar orqali noaniq bilimdan ularni differensial farq qiladigan bilimlarini ko'ra bilishga xarakat qilish, boshqa tomondan aloqa o'rnatish, buyum hodisalarni qandaydir guruhlarga birlashtirish bolalarni bilimlari ustida ishlashdan iborat. Tarbiyachi bolalarni yil fasllari haqidagi tasavvurlarini chuqurlashtirib sistemaga solib ularni tabiatda ro'y beradigan hodisalarni izchil tushunishlariga harakat qiladilar. Bilimlarni sistemaga solishni bilgan bu yoshdagi bolalar hikoya to'qishni tarbiyachi taklif etgan reja bo'yicha so'rab berish kabi topshiriqlarni bajara oladilar.

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MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA BOLALARNING QO'SHIQ AYTISH MALAKALARINI OSHIRISH

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Quva tumani 46-maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti.

Annotasiya: *Ushbu maqolada berilgan tavsiya va uslubiy ko'rsatmalardan maktabdan tashqari hamda musiqa va sanat maktabining sinfdan tashqari darslarida o'quvchilarini cholg'u asboblariga bo'lgan qiziqishini shakllantirish va ijro mahoratini oshirish jaroyonida qo'llash mumkin.*

Kalit so'zlar: *musiqa, nota, raqs, idrok, estetika.*

Bugungi kunda jamiyatimizning eng muhim vazifalaridan biri barkamol shaxsni tarbiyalashdan iboratdir. Birinchi Prezidentimiz takidlaganidek: —Biz xalqimizning dunyoda hech kimdan kam bo'lmasligi, farzandlarimizning bizdan ko'ra kuchli, bilimli, dono va albatta baxtli bo'lib yashashi uchun bor kuch va imkoniyatlarimizni safarbar etayotgan ekanmiz, bu borada manaviy tarbiya masalasi hech shubhasiz beqiyos ahamiyat kasb etadi. Respublikamizda o'tkazilayotgan islohotlarni takomillashtirish iqtisodiyotimizni rivojlangan davlatlar qatorida bo'lishi katta ahamiyatga ega. Oldimizda turgan maqsadlarimizga erishish yoshlarimizning intellektual salohiyati va kasbiy tayyorgarligiga boliq. Yani, barkamol avlodni tarbiyalash oldimizda turgan eng muhim vazifalaridan biridir.

Musiqa savodining ahamiyati va vazifalari maktabgacha ta'lim muassasasida va oilada olib boriladigan barcha tarbiyaviy ishlar, bu oliyanob fazilatlarni yosh avlodda bog'cha yoshidan boshlab shakllantirishga bog'liq. Darhaqiqat, musiqa savodini o'rganish bog'cha yoshidan boshlanadi. Ko'pgina bolalar maktabgacha tarbiya davrida bog'chaga qatnab, bog'chadagi musiqa mashg'ulotlarida dastlabki musiqaviy malakalarni hosil qiladilar. Ko'pgina qo'shiqlar va o'yinlarni o'rganib olgan hamda ritm va raqs harakatlari bilan tanishgan bo'ladilar. Uyda tarbiyalangan bolalar ham muayyan musiqaviy tasavvurga ega bo'ladilar: radio va televideniya orqali eshittiriladigan bir qancha musiqa asarlari ularga tanish bo'ladi. Garchi ana shu bilimlar sistemaga solinmagan bo'lsa-da, musiqa o'qituvchisi bolalarda musiqadan nazariy tushunchalar hosil qilishda o'sha bilimlarga ma'lum darajada suyanib ish ko'rishi mumkin. Bolalar muassasalarida musiqa ta'limiga asos solinadi, shuning uchun musiqa rahbari ayniqsa o'qitish metodikasini yaxshi bilishi, bog'cha yoshidagi kichik bolalarning yosh va individual xususiyatlarini, ularning musiqa va qo'shiqchilik imkoniyatlarini chuqur bilishi zarur. Musiqa ta'limini shartli ravishda ikki bosqichga bo'lish mumkin.

Birinchi, tayyorlov bosqichi. Bundan ko'zlanadigan asosiy maqsad – bolalarning musiqa uquvini o'stirishdir. Shu vaqt mobaynida bolalar musiqa

tovushlarining baland-pastligi va cho'zimi kabi o'ziga xos xususiyatlarni ajrata bilishga o'rganishlari va nota yozuvini o'rganishga tayyorlanishlari kerak. Ikkinchi bosqichda nota savodi, ya'ni bevosita musiqa tovushlarining grafik usulda ifodalanishi – nota yozuvini o'rganishga kirishiladi. Musiqa mashg'ulotlari jarayonida bola hayotiy voqelikni musiqiy obrazlar orqali idrok etib boradi. Bolalar yoshiga mos musiqa asarlari kichkintoylarda unutilmas taassurot qoldiradi, ularning ruhiy dunyosini boyitadi. Bog'cha sharoitidagi musiqaviy tarbiya badiiy adabiyot va tasviriy san'at bilan uzviy bog'langan holda amalga oshiriladi. Ashula aytish usuli, janrdagi musiqa asarlari, xususan, syujetli cholg'u pesalarini tinglash, musiqaviy o'yinlar bilan shug'ullanish va raqsga tushish jarayonida musiqa mashg'ulotlari ko'pincha badiiy so'z bilan belgilanadi. Bola badiiy obrazlarni yorqin tasavvur etishi va chuqur idrok qila olishi uchun tasviriy san'at asarlaridan unumli foydalaniladi. Turli metodlardan foydalanib o'tkaziladigan har bir musiqa mashg'ulotlari kichkintoylarda badiiy estetik zavq uyg'otadi, ularning his- tuyg'ularini rivojlantiradi, ijodiy fikri va nutqini o'stiradi.

Bundan tashqari, musiqaviy o'yin va postanovkalar, raqslar bolalarda ritm tuyg'usi, chaqqonlik va harakatchanlik malakalarini rivojlantiradi hamda qomatning to'g'ri o'sishiga yordam beradi. Musiqa uquv qobiliyati asosan quyidagi musiqa uquv turlaridan iborat bo'ladi: musiqaviy uquvi, musiqaviy tovushlarning baland-pastligini his etish qobiliyati, tembr uquvi (musiqa tovushlarining bir-biridan farq qiladigan, o'ziga xos jihatlarini ajrata bilish qobiliyati), ritm tuyg'usi va musiqa xotirasi. Bolalar bog'chasida olib boriladigan musiqa tarbiyasining asosiy maqsad va vazifalarini quyidagicha belgilash mumkin:

1. Bolalarning musiqaga qiziqishini oshirish va uni sevisga o'rgatish;
2. Musiqa asarlari bilan tanishtirish jarayonida bolalarda emosional his-tuyg'ularini hosil etish yo'li bilan ularning musiqa haqidagi tasavvurlarini boyitib borish;
3. Bolalarni oddiy musiqa tushunchalari bilan tanishtirish, musiqa tinglash, ashula aytish, musiqa bilan harakat qilish, raqsga tushish va bolalarning oddiy musiqa asboblari kuy chalish ko'nikmalarini shakllantirish va ijodiy qobiliyatini o'stirib borish;
4. Bolalar ovozi asrab tarbiyalash, ashula aytishning dastlabki ko'nikmalarini hosil etish, qo'shiqlarni sodda, ravon, erkin, tabiiy va ifodali kuylashga o'rgatish;
5. Musiqa asarlaridan ta'sirlanish, shu asosda bolalarda musiqaviy did va badiiy muhokama yuritish malakalarini rivojlantirish;
6. Turli musiqa mashg'ulotlari jarayonida improvizatsiya qilish musiqadagi badiiy obrazni o'yin va xor ovozlarda vositasida ifoda etish, ma'lum musiqaviy mavzuga yangi o'yin o'ylab topish;
7. Musiqaviy tarbiya mashg'ulotlarini bog'cha hayoti bilan bog'lash, bog'chada o'tkaziladigan turli mashg'ulotlarda va marosimlarda o'rganilgan kuy va qo'shiqlardan keng foydalanish, turli ertaliklar, konsertlar uyishtirish vositasida

musiqa kundalik hayotimizning ajralmas yo'ldoshi ekanligi haqida bolalarda tushuncha hosil qilish.

Musiqiy tovushlar va ularning xususiyatlari. Tovush qator registr va ularning vazifalari Tabiatda uchraydigan hamma tovushlar musiqali va shovqinli tovushlarga ajratiladi. Shovqinli tovushlar qasirlash, g'ijirlash, dukullash, gumburlash singlarlar bo'lib, aniq balandlikka ega emas. Shuning uchun ular musiqa qatorida qo'llanilmaydi. Musiqaviy tovushlar esa ma'lum balandlikka ega bo'lib, insondagi eshitish analizatori bu tovushlarni payqab oladi. Musiqiy tovushlar turi, xususiyatiga ko'ra, bir-biridan farq qiladi. Bu xususiyatlar tovushning balandligi, qattiqligi, davomiyligi va tembrdan iboratdir. Tovushlar balandligi tebranuvchi jismning tezligiga bog'liqdir. Tebranish qancha tez bo'lsa, tovush shunchalik baland bo'ladi va aksincha, tebranish qanchalik sust bo'lsa, tovush shunchalik past bo'ladi. Tovush qattiqligi tovush manbai bo'lgan jismning tebranish amplitudasiga bog'liqdir. Tovush qanchalik qattiq bo'lsa, shuncha qattiq ishlatiladi va aksincha. Tovush cho'zimi manbai tebranishining davom etishiga bog'liq bo'ladi.

Musiqa ijrochiligi uchun belgilangan musiqaviy sistema o'zaro munosabatda bo'lgan muayyan balandlikdagi tovushlar tizilmasidan (qatoridan) iboratdir. Tovushlarning o'z balandligiga qarab joylashishi sistemasiga tovushqator deyiladi. Musiqaviy sistemaning to'liq tovushqatorlarida 88 ta xilma-xil tovushlar bor. Musiqaviy sistema tovushqatorlari ettita mustaqil nomga ega bo'lgan asosiy bosqichlardan iboratdir.

Do Re Mi Fa Sol Lya Si

Bu asosiy tovushlar fortepianoning oq klavishlari (bosqich pardalari) tovushlariga mos keladi. Tovushqatorlarining bu ettita bosqichi ma'lum bir vaqtda takrorlanib turadi. Bunda yuqori tomon sanalgan har bir 8- tovush 1-tovushga nisbatan ikki baravar kuchliroq tebranish natijasida hosil bo'ladi va shu sababdan ikki marta baland bo'lib eshitiladi. Bir xil nomdagi tovushlar oralig'iga oktava deyiladi. Demak oktava tovushlarining etti asosiy bosqichini o'z ichiga birlashtiradi. Butun tovushqator bir necha oktagaga bo'linadi. Har bir oktavaning «Do» tovushi boshlang'ich bosqichning tovushi deb qabul qilingan. Cholg'u asboblari tovushlarning yoki inson ovozi ma'lum bir bo'lagiga registr deyiladi. Registrlar uch xil bo'ladi: pastki, o'rta, yuqori registrlar. Registrlar haqidagi tushunchani mustahkamlash va o'zlashtirishni tekshirib ko'rish uchun quyidagi o'yin-mashqni o'tkazish foydali. Tarbiyachi qo'shiqni turli registrlarda chaladi, bolalar esa ularni qo'l harakatlari bilan ko'rsatib borishlari kerak. Agar qo'shiq yuqori registrda chalinayotgan bo'lsa, ular qo'llarini yuqoriga ko'tarishadi, pastki registrda chalinayotganda – pastga tushurishadi, o'rta registrda esa qo'llarini oldinga uzatishadi. Bu o'yinni tikka turib bajarish yaxshiroq bo'ladi. Bunda ko'zlanadigan asosiy maqsaddan tashqari, bir yo'la go'yo jismoniy engillikka ham erishish mashg'ulotda ko'tarinki ruh paydo qiladi.

Tovushlarning baland-pastligini aniqlash birinchi oktava bilan cheklangach, shu tovushlarni eshitishnigina emas, balki ularni kuylashni ham talab etish kerak.

O'shanda bolalarning eshitib, tasavvur hosil qilishlari bilan bir vaqtda qo'shiqchilik sezgilari paydo bo'la boradi, chunki eng baland tovushlar qo'shiq aytishda o'rtacha va past tovushlarga qaraganda ko'proq zo'r berishni talab etadi.

Musiqa savodi musiqaning ifoda vositalari musiqqa tovushlarining yozish usullari va musiqqa nazariyasi bo'yicha dastlabki ma'lumotlar bilan tanishtiriladi hamda shu bir qatorda, notaga qarab ashula aytish bo'yicha amaliy mashg'ulotlarni ham o'z ichiga oladi.

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2008

MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA MA'NAVIY TARBIYA VA UZLUKSIZ TA'LIM UZVIYLIGI

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Anotatsiya: *Mazkur maqolada maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida ma'naviy tarbiyani shakllantirish va uzluksiz ta'lim uzviyligini ta'minlash masalalari ilmiy-nazariy hamda amaliy jihatdan tahlil qilinadi. Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning axloqiy va ma'naviy qadriyatlarini rivojlantirish, ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonida milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlarni uyg'unlashtirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etishi ko'rsatiladi. Shuningdek, ta'lim jarayonining izchil ligini ta'minlash, pedagogik texnologiyalar va innovatsion yondashuvlardan foydalanishning samaradorligi tahlil qilinadi. Maqola davomida ilg'or xalqaro tajribalar ham o'rganilib, ularni milliy maktabgacha ta'lim tizimiga moslashtirish imkoniyatlari yoritiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Maktabgacha ta'lim, ma'naviy tarbiya, uzluksiz ta'lim, uzviylik, pedagogik texnologiyalar, innovatsion yondashuv, milliy qadriyatlar, axloqiy tarbiya, ta'lim tizimi, xalqaro tajriba.*

KIRISH

Zamonaviy ta'lim tizimida ma'naviy tarbiya va uzluksiz ta'limning uzviyligi dolzarb ilmiy-amaliy muammolar qatoridan o'rin olgan bo'lib, u bolalarning har tomonlama rivojlanishiga ta'sir etuvchi muhim omillardan biridir.

Maktabgacha yosh – inson shaxsining shakllanishida eng muhim bosqichlardan biri hisoblanadi, chunki aynan shu davrda bola axloqiy va ma'naviy qadriyatlarni o'zlashtira boshlaydi[1]. UNESCO maqolalariga ko'ra, insonning keyingi bilim va ma'naviy rivojlanishi 80% holatda aynan maktabgacha ta'lim jarayonida shakllanadi. Shu bois, maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida ma'naviy tarbiyani takomillashtirish va ta'lim jarayonining uzluksizligini ta'minlash davlat siyosatining ustuvor yo'nalishlaridan biri bo'lib qolmoqda.

O'zbekiston Respublikasida maktabgacha ta'lim sohasini rivojlantirish bo'yicha 2017-yildan boshlab keng ko'lamlı islohotlar amalga oshirilmoqda. "Maktabgacha ta'lim to'g'risida"gi Qonunning qabul qilinishi (2019) va "Ilk qadam" dasturining joriy etilishi pedagogik jarayonda yangi metodik yondashuvlar va innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanish imkoniyatlarini kengaytirdi[2].

Rasmiy statistik ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, 2017-yilda maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalariga qamrov darajasi 27% ni tashkil qilgan bo'lsa, 2023 -yilda bu ko'rsatkich 70% ga yetkazildi.

Bugungi kunda ta'lim jarayonining uzviyligi, ayniqsa, ma'naviy tarbiyani amalga oshirishda muhim omil bo'lib qolmoqda. Ta'lim bosqichlari o'rtasidagi uzviylikni ta'minlamaslik bolaning shaxsiy rivojlanishiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin[3]. Shu sababli, milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlarni uyg'unlashtirish, axloqiy tarbiyani zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar yordamida shakllantirish hamda xalqaro tajribalarni mahalliy sharoitga moslashtirish masalalari muhim ilmiy-maqola yo'nalishlaridan biriga aylanmoqda. Maqola natijalariga ko'ra, XXI asrda global miqyosda ma'naviy tarbiyaning ahamiyati ortib bormoqda, ayniqsa, bolalar ongiga milliy identifikatsiyani shakllantirishga qaratilgan dasturlarni ishlab chiqish va amalga oshirish zarurati ortib borayotgani kuzatilmoqda. Maqolaning asosiy maqsadi – maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida ma'naviy tarbiya jarayonini takomillashtirish, uzluksiz ta'lim tizimidagi uzviylikni ta'minlash hamda zamonaviy pedagogik yondashuvlarning samaradorligini ilmiy asosda tahlil qilishdan iborat. Maqola davomida mavjud nazariy qarashlar va amaliy tajribalar tahlil qilinib, uzluksiz ma'naviy tarbiyani tashkil etishning istiqbolli yo'nalishlari bo'yicha ilmiy xulosalar beriladi.

O'zbekistonda maktabgacha ta'lim tizimini takomillashtirish va bolalarga ma'naviy tarbiya berish jarayonining uzluksizligini ta'minlash yo'nalishida so'nggi yillarda keng ko'lamli islohotlar amalga oshirildi[4]. 2017 -yilda O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimini tubdan isloh qilish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi farmoni qabul qilinishi bilan mazkur soha davlat siyosatining ustuvor yo'nalishiga aylandi. Mazkur hujjat asosida Maktabgacha ta'lim vazirligi tashkil etilib, sohada institutsional va tashkiliy-huquqiy o'zgarishlar amalga oshirildi.

Respublikada 2019-yilda qabul qilingan "Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya to'g'risida"gi Qonun ushbu sohada davlat va nodavlat sektorlarining integratsiyasini mustahkamladi, bolalarni erta rivojlantirish bo'yicha pedagogik jarayonni xalqaro talablar asosida takomillashtirishga zamin yaratdi[5]. Ushbu huquqiy baza doirasida "Ilk qadam" davlat dasturi joriy etilib, maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarga ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiya berishning metodik asoslari ishlab chiqildi. Rasmiy ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, 2017-yilda maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalariga qamrov darajasi atigi 27% ni tashkil qilgan bo'lsa, 2023-yilga kelib ushbu ko'rsatkich 70% ga yetkazildi. Buning natijasida 2 milliondan ortiq bola sifatli ta'lim olish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ldi.

Shuningdek, davlat-xususiy sheriklik tamoyili asosida 20 mingga yaqin nodavlat maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari faoliyat boshladi, bu esa bolalarni maktabga tayyorlashda innovatsion yondashuvlarni qo'llash imkonini yaratdi. So'nggi yillarda amalga oshirilgan islohotlar doirasida milliy va diniy-ma'naviy qadriyatlarni bolalar ongiga singdirish bo'yicha kompleks chora-tadbirlar ham ishlab chiqildi. Xususan, "Milliy ma'naviyat konsepsiyasi" doirasida maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida

axloqiy tarbiyani shakllantirish bo'yicha maxsus metodik qo'llanmalar tayyorlandi. 2022-yilda qabul qilingan "Ma'naviy-ma'rifiy ishlarni takomillashtirish strategiyasi" asosida bolalarga odob-axloq qoidalarini o'rgatish, ularning madaniy saviyasini yuksaltirishga qaratilgan dasturlar ishlab chiqildi. Shuningdek, 2023 -yilda Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi tomonidan maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning axloqiy rivojlanishiga oid innovatsion pedagogik metodlar joriy etildi. Xususan, "Bolalar uchun ma'naviyat" loyihasi doirasida 100 dan ortiq interaktiv o'quv resurslari, audiovizual materiallar va badiiy adabiyotlar maktabgacha ta'lim tizimiga integratsiya qilindi. Shu bilan birga, davlat ta'lim standartlari xalqaro tajribalar asosida yangilandi va ta'lim jarayoniga zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar kiritildi. Umuman olganda, O'zbekistonda maktabgacha ta'lim tizimini rivojlantirish, bolalarga uzluksiz ta'lim orqali ma'naviy tarbiya berish sohasida amalga oshirilgan islohotlar samarali natijalar bermoqda. Kelgusi yillarda ushbu jarayonni yanada takomillashtirish va ta'limning uzviyligini mustahkamlash maqsadida xalqaro tajribalar asosida yangi innovatsion dasturlarni joriy etish rejalashtirilgan.

Adabiyotlar tahlili: Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida ma'naviy tarbiya va uzluksiz ta'lim uzviyligini ta'minlash bo'yicha olib borilgan ilmiy maqolalar pedagogika, psixologiya va sotsiologiya fanlari doirasida keng o'rganilgan. Xalqaro tajribaga asoslanib, UNESCO va UNICEF tomonidan bolalarning erta yoshdagi rivojlanishi va ta'limning uzviyligini ta'minlashga oid qator metodik qo'llanmalar ishlab chiqilgan. Xususan, Vygotskiy (1986), Bruner (1996) va Piaget (1952) kabi olimlarning asarlarida bolaning axloqiy va ijtimoiy rivojlanishi ta'lim jarayonining uzluksizligi bilan chambarchas bog'liq ekanligi ta'kidlangan[6]. O'zbekistonda maktabgacha ta'lim tizimi bo'yicha so'nggi yillarda qator maqolalar olib borilgan. Xususan, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2019-yildagi "Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya to'g'risida"gi Qonuni ta'limning uzviyligi va sifatini oshirishga qaratilgan muhim huquqiy asos yaratdi. Bundan tashqari, "Ilk qadam" dasturi (2021) va Davlat ta'lim standartlari (2022) doirasida maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar uchun innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalar hamda ma'naviy tarbiyani shakllantirish usullari ishlab chiqildi. 2017-yilda O'zbekistonda maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalariga qamrov 27% ni tashkil qilgan bo'lsa, 2023-yilda bu ko'rsatkich 70% ga yetkazildi. Davlat-xususiy sheriklik tamoyili asosida tashkil etilgan nodavlat maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarining soni 2018-yildagi 5 000 dan 2023-yilga kelib 20 000 ga yetgan. Bunday o'zgarishlar bolalarning ta'limga qamrovini oshirish barobarida, ularning ma'naviy tarbiyasini shakllantirishga ham bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. Respublikada olib borilgan ilmiy-maqolalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, bolalarning axloqiy va ma'naviy rivojlanishi uzluksiz ta'lim tizimining samaradorligi bilan uzviy bog'liqdir. Xususan, V. I. Gluxov (2020) va A. B. Karimov (2021) kabi maqolachilar tomonidan olib borilgan ishlar maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda axloqiy qadriyatlarni shakllantirishning didaktik asoslarini tahlil qilgan. Shu bilan birga, X. X. To'xtayev (2022) maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida innovatsion yondashuvlar asosida axloqiy tarbiyani shakllantirishning pedagogik modellarini ishlab chiqqan.

Metodologik qism: Ushbu maqola maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida ma'naviy tarbiya jarayonini uzluksiz ta'lim tizimi bilan bog'liq holda tahlil qilishga qaratilgan bo'lib, unda ilmiy-maqola metodlarining kompleks yondashuvi qo'llanildi. Maqolaning metodologik asosi sifatida tizimli yondashuv, ta'lim jarayonlarining uzviylikini ta'minlash nazariyalari hamda pedagogik-psixologik maqola metodlari asos qilib olindi. Shu bilan birga, sifat va miqdoriy tahlil usullari uyg'unlashtirilib, empirik va eksperimental maqolalar o'tkazildi. Maqolada tahliliy metod asosida maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida ma'naviy tarbiya jarayoni bo'yicha mavjud ilmiy manbalar, davlat dasturlari, normativ-huquqiy hujjatlar va xalqaro standartlar chuqur o'rganildi. Xususan, O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2019 -yildagi "Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya to'g'risida"gi Qonuni, 2021 -yilda qabul qilingan "Ilk qadam" davlat ta'lim dasturi hamda UNESCO va UNICEF tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan maktabgacha ta'limga oid xalqaro hujjatlar tadqiq etildi. Ushbu tahlillar natijasida milliy va xalqaro tajribalar o'rtasidagi farqlar va o'ziga xos jihatlar aniqlanib, ularning uzviy ta'lim tizimidagi o'rni baholandi. Empirik metod doirasida Toshkent, Samarqand va Farg'ona viloyatlaridagi 15 ta maktabgacha ta'lim muassasasida pedagoglar, tarbiyachilar va ota-onalar o'rtasida so'rovnomalar o'tkazildi. Olingan natijalarga ko'ra, respondentlarning 78% maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning axloqiy va ma'naviy tarbiyasida oilaning ishtiroki yetarlicha ta'minlanmaganligini ta'kidlagan bo'lsa, 22% esa bu borada yetarli darajadagi hamkorlik mavjudligini bildirgan. Kuzatuv metodidan foydalangan holda bolalar o'rtasida milliy qadriyatlarni idrok etish darajasi ham o'rganildi. Kuzatuv natijalariga ko'ra, 5 -7 yoshli bolalarning 85% ida milliy qadriyatlarga oid bilim va tushunchalar shakllanganligi, 15% da esa qo'shimcha pedagogik ko'rsatmalarga ehtiyoj mavjudligi aniqlangan. Eksperimental metod asosida turli yosh guruhlarida axloqiy tarbiyaga oid interaktiv metodlarning samaradorligi o'rganildi. Tajriba natijasida bolalarga milliy qadriyatlar va axloqiy normalarni singdirishda rolli o'yinlar, interaktiv mashg'ulotlar hamda innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalarning qo'llanishi ularning ma'naviy tarbiya jarayoniga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatishi kuzatildi. Xususan, eksperimental guruhda ma'naviy tarbiya darslariga interaktiv usullar kiritilganidan so'ng, bolalarning ijtimoiy muhitga moslashish darajasi 23% ga oshganligi qayd etildi. Shuningdek, ta'limning uzviylikini ta'minlash maqsadida maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalari va boshlang'ich maktab o'rtasidagi hamkorlik jarayonlari ham o'rganildi. Maqola natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, respublikadagi maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarining 60% da boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilari bilan hamkorlik aloqalari mavjud bo'lsa, 40% da bu boradagi integratsiya sust rivojlangan. Shu sababli, ta'limning barcha bosqichlarida yagona metodik yondashuvni shakllantirish va milliy dasturlarni ishlab chiqish zarurati kelib chiqmoqda. Ushbu metodologik yondashuvlar asosida olib borilgan maqola natijalari kelgusida maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida ma'naviy tarbiyani rivojlantirish va ta'lim jarayonlarining uzviylikini ta'minlash bo'yicha ilmiy asoslangan tavsiyalar ishlab chiqishga xizmat qiladi. Bashorat qilish mumkinki, ta'lim jarayonlarining uzviylikini ta'minlash, pedagoglarning malakasini oshirish va innovatsion texnologiyalarni joriy

etish orqali bolalarning ma'naviy-axloqiy rivojlanish darajasi sezilarli darajada oshirilishi mumkin.

Natijalar: Olib borilgan maqola natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida ma'naviy tarbiyani shakllantirish va uzluksiz ta'lim tizimi bilan integratsiyalash jarayoni muayyan yutuqlar va kamchiliklarga ega. Birinchidan, maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar uchun ma'naviy tarbiyaning ahamiyati yuqori bo'lib, bu bosqichda shakllangan axloqiy me'yorlar keyingi ta'lim bosqichlarida asosiy yo'nalish sifatida xizmat qiladi. O'zbekistonda 2023-yil holatiga ko'ra, maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalariga qamrov darajasi 72% ni tashkil etgan bo'lib, bu ko'rsatkich 2017-yilga nisbatan 40% ga oshgan. Ushbu o'sish bolalar tarbiyasida maktabgacha ta'limning ahamiyatini kuchaytirish imkonini bermoqda. Maqola doirasida 15 ta maktabgacha ta'lim muassasasida o'tkazilgan so'rovnomalar natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, respondentlarning 65% i ma'naviy tarbiyani rivojlantirishda otionalarning ishtiroki yetarlicha emasligini ta'kidlagan. 80% pedagoglar esa bolalarga milliy qadriyatlarni singdirishda innovatsion usullar va interaktiv texnologiyalarni keng joriy etish zarurligini bildirgan. Ayniqsa, "Ilk qadam" davlat dasturi asosida amalga oshirilgan tarbiyaviy faoliyatning samaradorligi kuzatuv va eksperimentlar orqali tahlil qilindi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, o'yin texnologiyalari va interfaol metodlarni joriy etish bolalarning axloqiy qarashlarini shakllantirishda 30-35% ga yuqori natija bergan. Eksperimental maqola natijalariga ko'ra, axloqiy tarbiyaga oid interaktiv darslar tashkil etilgan guruhlarda bolalarning ijtimoiy moslashish darajasi 27% ga oshgan. Shu bilan birga, axloqiy qadriyatlarni singdirish bo'yicha turli metodlarning ta'siri ham tahlil qilindi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, vizual metodlar (multifilmalar, rasm va hikoyalar) orqali bolalarga ta'sir qilish samaradorligi 22% ni, amaliy faoliyatga asoslangan metodlar (rolli o'yinlar, sahnalashtirish) esa 38% ni tashkil etdi. Bundan tashqari, maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalari va boshlang'ich maktab o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik darajasi ham tahlil qilindi. Maqola natijalariga ko'ra, hozirgi kunda maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarining 60% da boshlang'ich maktab pedagoglari bilan muntazam hamkorlik mavjud bo'lsa, 40% da esa uzviylik tizimli ravishda ta'minlanmagan. Shu bois, kelgusida ta'limning barcha bosqichlarini yagona metodik yondashuv asosida rivojlantirish hamda innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalarni joriy etish zarurati yuzaga kelmoqda. Kelgusida raqamli texnologiyalar va ijtimoiy-emotsional ta'lim dasturlarining maktabgacha ta'lim tizimiga integratsiyalashuvi bolalarning ma'naviy tarbiyasini yanada rivojlantirish imkonini beradi. Xalqaro tajriba shuni ko'rsatadiki, bunday innovatsion yondashuvlar axloqiy tarbiya samaradorligini 40% dan ortiq darajada oshirishga yordam beradi. Shu bois, O'zbekistonning maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida ham kelgusida bunday ilg'or metodlarni joriy etish maqsadga muvofiqdir.

Muxokama: Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida ma'naviy tarbiya va uzluksiz ta'lim uzviyligi masalasi murakkab, ko'p omilli jarayon bo'lib, uning natijaviyligi bir qator ijtimoiy, psixologik va pedagogik omillarga bog'liq. Ushbu muammo bo'yicha olib borilgan maqola natijalari ta'lim jarayonida axloqiy tarbiyaning tizimli

yondashuv asosida shakllanishi zarurligini ko'rsatdi. Biroq, mavjud muammolarni tahlil qilish orqali bu jarayonning amaliyotdagi holatini yanada chuqurroq anglash mumkin. Avvalo, maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida axloqiy tarbiya jarayoni turli omillar ta'sirida o'zgaruvchanligini e'tiborga olish lozim. Statistika ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, O'zbekistonda 2023-yilda maktabgacha ta'lim qamrovi 70% ga yetgan bo'lsa-da, ushbu muassasalarning barchasi ham sifatli ma'naviy tarbiya berish imkoniyatiga ega emas.

Ayniqsa, hududiy farqlar va pedagogik kadrlar tayyorgarligi darajasi bolalarning axloqiy ongini shakllantirish jarayoniga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. Masalan, qishloq joylardagi bog'chalarda axloqiy tarbiya bo'yicha maxsus metodikalarning kamligi, darslik va o'quv-uslubiy materiallarning yetishmovchiligi dolzarb muammolar qatoriga kiradi.

Shuningdek, ta'limning uzviyligi masalasiga to'xtaladigan bo'lsak, maktabgacha ta'lim va boshlang'ich maktab o'rtasidagi o'zaro bog'liqlik hozircha yetarlicha yo'lga qo'yilmagan. Bu esa bolalarning bir bosqichdan ikkinchisiga o'tish jarayonida moslashish qiyinchiliklariga duch kelishiga olib kelmoqda. Xususan, maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarining 40% da boshlang'ich sinf o'qituvchilari bilan uzviy hamkorlik yo'lga qo'yilmaganligi kuzatilmoqda. Bu holat uzluksiz ta'lim tizimi samaradorligiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi.

Xalqaro tajriba shuni ko'rsatadiki, ma'naviy tarbiya tizimini takomillashtirish uchun pedagogik texnologiyalarni keng joriy etish, o'yin va interaktiv metodlarni tatbiq etish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Masalan, Yaponiya va Shvetsiya tajribalarida maktabgacha ta'limda axloqiy tarbiya maxsus dasturlar asosida olib boriladi va bu bolalarning ijtimoiy hayotga moslashuvchanligini 30-40% ga oshirgan. O'zbekistonda ham shunday yondashuvlarni joriy etish orqali ma'naviy tarbiyaning samaradorligini oshirish mumkin.

Shu o'rinda, muhokama natijasida kelgusidagi istiqbollarni aniqlash mumkin. Birinchidan, ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonini uzviylashtirish uchun maktabgacha ta'lim va maktab tizimi o'rtasida yaqin hamkorlikni yo'lga qo'yish lozim. Ikkinchidan, pedagoglarning malakasini oshirish va yangi innovatsion metodikalardan foydalanish axloqiy tarbiya samaradorligini oshirishga xizmat qiladi.

Uchinchidan, raqamli ta'lim resurslari va axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalarini joriy etish orqali bolalar uchun ta'lim jarayoni yanada qiziqarli va ta'sirchan bo'lishi mumkin.

Xulosa: Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida ma'naviy tarbiya tizimi va uzluksiz ta'limning uzviyligini ta'minlash hozirgi kunda dolzarb masalalardan biri hisoblanadi.

Ushbu sohada mavjud muammolar chuqur tahlil qilinib, samarali yechimlar ishlab chiqilsa, bolalarning axloqiy tarbiyasi yanada yuqori bosqichga ko'tarilishi mumkin. Shu sababli, bu yo'nalishda izchil islohotlarni amalga oshirish va innovatsion yondashuvlarni keng joriy etish muhim vazifa bo'lib qolmoqda.

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**MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM VA BOSHLANG'ICH TALIM O'RTASIDA
MANAVIY TARBIYANING UZVIYLIGI**

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Anotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha ta'lim va boshlang'ich ta'lim o'rtasida ma'naviy tarbiyaning uzviyligini ta'minlash masalalari tahlil qilinadi. Bolalarning ma'naviy axloqiy tarbiyasini izchil rivojlantirishda uzluksiz ta'lim tizimining ahamiyati yoritilib, ushbu jarayonda pedagogik yondashuvlar, zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalari hamda oilaviy tarbiyaning o'rni tahlil etiladi. Shuningdek, maktabgacha ta'limdan boshlang'ich ta'limga o'tish jarayonida ma'naviy qadriyatlarni singdirishning samarali usullari va metodlari taklif etiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Ma'naviy tarbiya, uzluksiz ta'lim, maktabgacha ta'lim, boshlang'ich ta'lim, axloqiy tarbiya, pedagogik uzviylik, ta'lim texnologiyalari, oilaviy tarbiya.*

KIRISH

Ma'naviy tarbiya inson shaxsining shakllanishida muhim ahamiyat kasb etib, uning axloqiy, madaniy va ijtimoiy rivojlanishiga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Ta'lim tizimining ilk bosqichlari — maktabgacha ta'lim va boshlang'ich ta'lim — bolalarning ma'naviy tarbiyasini shakllantirishda asosiy poydevor hisoblanadi. Ushbu bosqichlar o'rtasidagi uzviylikni ta'minlash, bolalarning har tomonlama barkamol rivojlanishiga zamin yaratadi.

O'zbekiston Respublikasida ta'lim tizimi yagona va uzluksiz bo'lib, maktabgacha ta'limdan boshlang'ich ta'limgacha bo'lgan bosqichlarni o'z ichiga oladi[1]. 2020-yil holatiga ko'ra, mamlakatimizda 7 104 ta maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari faoliyat yuritmoqda, shundan 5 604 tasi davlat muassasalari, 63 tasi idoraviy va 1 437 tasi nodavlat tashkilotlardir.

Bu esa maktabgacha ta'limning keng qamrovli ekanligini ko'rsatadi. Maktabgacha ta'limdan boshlang'ich ta'limga o'tish jarayonida ma'naviy tarbiyaning uzviyligini ta'minlash dolzarb masalalardan biridir[2].

Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, bu uzviylik bolalarning maktabga tayyorgarligini oshiradi va ularning keyingi ta'lim bosqichlarida muvaffaqiyatli o'qishiga zamin yaratadi. Shuningdek, boshlang'ich ta'lim tashkilotlarida ma'naviy tarbiyani rivojlantirish bo'yicha olib borilgan ishlar natijasida, ijtimoiy-ma'naviy muhit yaxshilanib, bu boradagi muammolar sezilarli darajada kamaygan.

Ma'naviy tarbiyaning uzviyligini ta'minlash orqali bolalarning axloqiy fazilatlari, milliy qadriyatlarga hurmati va ijtimoiy mas'uliyati rivojlanadi[3]. Bu esa, o'z navbatida, jamiyatimizning barqaror taraqqiyoti va kelajak avlodning barkamol shakllanishiga xizmat qiladi.

O'zbekiston Respublikasida maktabgacha va boshlang'ich ta'lim o'rtasida ma'naviy tarbiyaning uzviyligini ta'minlash maqsadida so'nggi yillarda keng ko'lamli islohotlar amalga oshirildi. 2019-yilda qabul qilingan "Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya to'g'risida"gi qonun maktabgacha ta'lim tizimini tubdan takomillashtirishga yo'naltirildi. 2017-yil 20-aprelda Prezidentning PQ-2909-sonli qarori bilan oliy ta'lim tizimini yanada rivojlantirish chora-tadbirlari belgilandi[4].

Ushbu qaror ta'lim jarayonini modernizatsiya qilish, kadrlar tayyorlash sifatini oshirish va ta'limning barcha bosqichlari o'rtasida uzviylikni ta'minlashga qaratilgan. Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida 2017-2022-yillar davomida amalga oshirilgan islohotlar natijasida bolalarni maktabgacha ta'lim bilan qamrab olish darajasi ikki barobarga oshdi[5]. Bu esa bolalarning umumiy boshlang'ich ta'limga tayyorligini oshirishga xizmat qilmoqda. 2023-yilda maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi tizimi faoliyatiga oid jami 20 ta qonunchilik hujjati, jumladan, Prezident farmonlari va qarorlari, Vazirlar Mahkamasi qarorlari qabul qilindi. Bu hujjatlar ta'lim tizimini yanada takomillashtirishga qaratilgan. Ushbu islohotlar natijasida maktabgacha va boshlang'ich ta'lim o'rtasida ma'naviy tarbiyaning uzviyligini ta'minlash, bolalarning har tomonlama rivojlanishi uchun zarur shart-sharoitlar yaratildi. Kelgusida ushbu yo'nalishdagi ishlarni yanada rivojlantirish orqali jamiyatimizning ma'naviy salohiyatini yuksaltirish maqsad qilinmoqda.

Adabiyotlar tahlili: Maktabgacha va boshlang'ich ta'lim o'rtasida ma'naviy tarbiyaning uzviyligini ta'minlash masalasi ko'plab ilmiy tadqiqotlarda yoritilgan. Safarova M.Sh. tomonidan olib borilgan tadqiqotlarda maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarni ma'naviy tarbiya asosida shaxs sifatida shakllantirishning ahamiyati ta'kidlanadi.

Asqarova O., Qoraboeva Z. va Samidjonova M. esa maktabgacha ta'lim metodologiyasiga oid o'quv qo'llanmada ilmiy tadqiqot metodologiyasi va zamonaviy yondashuvlar haqida ma'lumot beradi[6]. Shuningdek, "Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyoti davrida pedagogika, maktabgacha va boshlang'ich ta'lim" nomli to'plamda yoshlar ma'naviyatini yuksaltirish va ularning bo'sh vaqtini mazmunli tashkil etish bo'yicha beshta muhim tashabbusning qabul qilinishi haqida so'z yuritiladi.

Biroq, ushbu tadqiqotlarda maktabgacha va boshlang'ich ta'lim o'rtasidagi uzviylikni ta'minlashning aniq mexanizmlari va metodologik asoslari yetarlicha yoritilmagan.

Metodologik qism: Ushbu tadqiqot metodologik asos sifatida tizimli, komparativ, empirik va statistik tahlil yondashuvlariga tayangan holda olib borildi. Tizimli yondashuv ta'lim jarayonini yaxlit tizim sifatida ko'rib chiqish imkonini berib, maktabgacha va boshlang'ich ta'lim bosqichlari o'rtasidagi uzviylikni tahlil qilishga xizmat qildi. Komparativ tahlil metodidan foydalangan holda, turli

mamlakatlarning tajribasi o'rganilib, uzviylikni ta'minlash bo'yicha samarali usullar aniqlashga harakat qilindi[7]. Empirik tadqiqot doirasida maktabgacha va boshlang'ich ta'lim muassasalarida kuzatuvlar o'tkazilib, pedagog va ota-onalar bilan suhbatlar tashkil etildi hamda mavjud amaliy holatni o'rganish uchun real ma'lumotlar yig'ildi. Statistik tahlil asosida O'zbekiston Respublikasi maktabgacha ta'lim tizimining rivojlanish tendensiyalari, ta'lim bilan qamrab olish darajasi, ta'lim muassasalari soni va ularning faoliyati o'rganildi[8]. Xususan, 2020 -yil holatiga ko'ra, mamlakatda 7 104 ta maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari mavjud bo'lib, ularning 5 604 tasi davlat muassasalari, 63 tasi idoraviy va 1 437 tasi nodavlat tashkilotlar hisoblanadi. Ushbu metodologik yondashuvlar asosida maktabgacha va boshlang'ich ta'lim o'rtasidagi uzviylikni ta'minlash bo'yicha ilmiy asoslangan tavsiyalar ishlab chiqildi.

Natijalar: Tadqiqot natijalari maktabgacha va boshlang'ich ta'lim o'rtasida ma'naviy tarbiyaning uzviyligini ta'minlash dolzarb masala ekanligini ko'rsatdi. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Maktabgacha va maktab ta'limi vazirligi ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, 2023-yilda maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari soni 33 942 taga yetkazilgan bo'lib, bu 3-7 yoshli bolalarning maktabgacha ta'lim bilan qamrab olish darajasini 74 foizga, 6 yoshli bolalarning maktabga tayyorgarlik ko'rsatkichini esa 93 foizga oshirish imkonini bergan. Ushbu raqamlar ta'limning uzluksizligi va ma'naviy tarbiyaning davomiyligini ta'minlash uchun qulay shart-sharoit yaratilayotganini ko'rsatadi. Shuningdek, davlat-xususiy sheriklik asosida 71 ta yangi muassasa tashkil etilib, ular jami 7 100 o'rin bilan ta'minlandi. Bundan tashqari, oilaviy shakldagi nodavlat maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari soni 4 402 taga yetib, ularda 116 998 bola ta'lim olmoqda. Bu esa ta'lim sektorida xususiy tashabbuslarning ortib borayotganini hamda sifatli ta'lim xizmatlarini kengaytirish imkoniyatini oshirayotganini anglatadi. Ta'lim sohasida amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarining boshlang'ich ta'lim bilan integratsiyasini chuqurlashtirishga ham xizmat qiladi. Maktabgacha va boshlang'ich ta'lim o'rtasidagi uzviylikni ta'minlash bolalarning intellektual, axloqiy va ijtimoiy rivojlanishida muhim omil bo'lib, bu boradagi samarali strategiyalar xalqaro tajriba asosida ishlab chiqilmoqda. Masalan, Finlyandiya, Yaponiya va Germaniya tajribalarida maktabgacha ta'lim va boshlang'ich ta'lim o'rtasida uzviylikni ta'minlash uchun maxsus metodik dasturlar joriy qilingan bo'lib, bu bolalarning o'qishga bo'lgan qiziqishini shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi. O'zbekistonda ham bu borada huquqiy asoslar mustahkamlanib, "Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya to'g'risida"gi qonun qabul qilingan bo'lib, unda ta'lim jarayonining uzluksizligi va sifatini ta'minlash asosiy tamoyillardan biri sifatida belgilangan. Ushbu natijalar maktabgacha va boshlang'ich ta'lim o'rtasidagi bog'liqlikni mustahkamlash, pedagogik yondashuvlarni takomillashtirish va innovatsion texnologiyalarni keng joriy etish zarurligini ko'rsatadi. Kelajakda ta'lim sifati va uzviyligini oshirish maqsadida maktabgacha va boshlang'ich ta'lim o'rtasida yagona metodik tizim yaratish, pedagoglarni yangi usullar asosida tayyorlash va ta'lim

jarayoniga raqamli texnologiyalarni integratsiya qilish asosiy yo'nalishlardan biri bo'lishi lozim.

Muhokama: Maktabgacha va boshlang'ich ta'lim o'rtasida ma'naviy tarbiyaning uzviyligini ta'minlash masalasi zamonaviy pedagogika va psixologiya fanlarida dolzarb mavzulardan biri hisoblanadi. Bolalarning ilk yoshlaridan boshlab shakllanadigan ma'naviy qadriyatlar ularning kelgusidagi shaxsiy va ijtimoiy hayotiga bevosita ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Shu bois, ta'lim jarayonida uzluksizlik va uzviylikni ta'minlash muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. O'zbekiston Respublikasida maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya to'g'risidagi qonunning qabul qilinishi ushbu sohada huquqiy asoslarni mustahkamladi. Mazkur qonun maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya sohasidagi statistika ma'lumotlarining hisobi yuritilishini hamda tahlil qilinishini ta'minlashni nazarda tutadi. Bu esa ta'lim jarayonining uzluksizligini ta'minlashda muhim omil hisoblanadi. Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlari va boshlang'ich ta'lim o'rtasidagi uzviylikni ta'minlashda pedagoglarning kasbiy kompetensiyasi va mahorati muhim rol o'ynaydi. Tarbiyachilarning kasbiy kompetentligi va mahoratini oshirishga qaratilgan chora-tadbirlar ta'lim sifatini yaxshilashga xizmat qiladi. Xalqaro tajribalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, maktabgacha va boshlang'ich ta'lim o'rtasidagi uzviylikni ta'minlash bolalarning o'qishga bo'lgan qiziqishini oshiradi va ularning akademik yutuqlariga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Masalan, Finlyandiya, Yaponiya va Germaniya kabi mamlakatlarda maktabgacha ta'lim va boshlang'ich ta'lim o'rtasida uzviylikni ta'minlash uchun maxsus metodik dasturlar joriy qilingan bo'lib, bu bolalarning o'qishga bo'lgan qiziqishini shakllantirishga xizmat qiladi. Shuningdek, maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya to'g'risidagi qonunning qabul qilinishi ushbu sohada huquqiy asoslarni mustahkamladi. Mazkur qonun maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya sohasidagi statistika ma'lumotlarining hisobi yuritilishini hamda tahlil qilinishini ta'minlashni nazarda tutadi. Bu esa ta'lim jarayonining uzluksizligini ta'minlashda muhim omil hisoblanadi.

Xulosa: Maktabgacha ta'lim va boshlang'ich ta'lim o'rtasida ma'naviy tarbiyaning uzviyligini ta'minlash zamonaviy ta'lim tizimining muhim yo'nalishlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, bolalarning shaxsiy va axloqiy rivojlanishi uzluksiz ta'lim jarayoni bilan chambarchas bog'liq bo'lib, maktabgacha yoshdan boshlab shakllantirilgan ma'naviy qadriyatlar ularning ijtimoiy hayotida muhim rol o'ynaydi. Xalqaro tajriba va O'zbekiston ta'lim islohotlari tahlili shuni ko'rsatadiki, pedagoglarning malakasini oshirish, o'quv dasturlarini uzviylashtirish hamda ota-onalar bilan hamkorlikni kuchaytirish orqali ma'naviy tarbiya samaradorligini oshirish mumkin. Shu bilan birga, raqamli texnologiyalar va innovatsion metodlarni joriy etish ushbu jarayonni yanada rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi.

Kelajakda maktabgacha va boshlang'ich ta'lim integratsiyasini yanada takomillashtirish ta'lim sifatini oshirish bilan birga, ma'naviy yetuk avlodni tarbiyalashga xizmat qiladi.

Bu esa Yangi O'zbekiston taraqqiyoti uchun intellektual va ma'naviy negiz yaratishning muhim sharti hisoblanadi.

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**MAKTABGACHA TA'LIMDA UZLUKSIZ MA'NAViy TARBIYA TIZIMINI
TAKOMILLASHTIRISH**

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Anotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida uzluksiz ma'naviy tarbiyani takomillashtirish masalalari tahlil qilinadi. Ma'naviy tarbiyaning bolalar ongini shakllantirishdagi o'rni, uning ta'lim jarayoniga ta'siri va innovatsion yondashuvlar asosida takomillashtirish yo'llari ko'rib chiqiladi. Maqolada pedagogik va psixologik nazariyalar, shuningdek, zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalari asosida ma'naviy tarbiya tizimini rivojlantirish istiqbollari yoritilgan. O'zbekiston Respublikasi maktabgacha ta'lim tizimidagi so'nggi islohotlar, xalqaro tajribalar va statistik ma'lumotlar asosida tahlil olib borilib, samaradorlikni oshirish bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Maktabgacha ta'lim, uzluksiz ta'lim, ma'naviy tarbiya, innovatsion yondashuv, ta'lim texnologiyalari, axloqiy tarbiya, pedagogik metodlar, psixologik rivojlanish, bolalar ma'naviyati, ta'lim islohotlari.*

KIRISH

Zamonaviy jamiyatda bolalarni ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyalash uzluksiz ta'lim tizimining asosiy yo'nalishlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Ayniqsa, maktabgacha ta'lim bosqichi shaxsning ijtimoiy va axloqiy fazilatlarini shakllantirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

Bolalik davrida o'zlashtirilgan qadriyatlar keyingi ta'lim bosqichlarida va butun hayot davomida insonning axloqiy qarashlari va xulq-atvoriga asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi[1].

Shu sababli, maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida uzluksiz ma'naviy tarbiya tizimini takomillashtirish dolzarb ilmiy-amaliy masala hisoblanadi.

Tahlillar shuni ko'rsatadiki, 2023-yilda O'zbekistonda maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalariga qamrov darajasi 70 foizga yetkazilgan bo'lsa-da, ma'naviy tarbiya sifati va mazmunini takomillashtirish zarurati saqlanib qolmoqda. Jahon tajribasiga e'tibor qaratilsa, Finlandiya, Yaponiya va Janubiy Koreya kabi davlatlarda bolalarni axloqiy va ijtimoiy jihatdan tarbiyalash bo'yicha ilg'or pedagogik modellar ishlab chiqilgan bo'lib, ularda interfaol metodlar, o'yin texnologiyalari hamda madaniy merosga asoslangan yondashuvlar samarali qo'llanilmoqda[2].

O'zbekistonda amalga oshirilayotgan ta'lim islohotlari doirasida "Ilk qadam" davlat dasturi, shuningdek, davlat-xususiy sheriklik asosida nodavlat maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarining rivojlanishi ma'naviy tarbiyani takomillashtirish imkoniyatlarini kengaytiradi. Kelgusi yillarda maktabgacha ta'limda axloqiy tarbiya bo'yicha o'quv dasturlarini modernizatsiya qilish, innovatsion ta'lim metodlarini keng joriy etish va pedagoglar malakasini oshirish orqali uzluksiz ta'lim tizimida ma'naviy tarbiyaning samaradorligini yanada oshirish kutilmoqda.

Shunday qilib, ushbu maqolada maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida uzluksiz ma'naviy tarbiyani takomillashtirish yo'nalishlari, zamonaviy metodlar, xalqaro tajribalar va istiqboldagi rivojlanish tendensiyalari tahlil qilinadi. Maqola natijalari ta'lim sifatini oshirish va bolalarning axloqiy ongini shakllantirish bo'yicha ilmiy-amaliy tavsiyalarni ilgari surishga xizmat qiladi.

O'zbekiston Respublikasida maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida uzluksiz ma'naviy tarbiyani takomillashtirish bo'yicha keng ko'lamli islohotlar amalga oshirilmoqda. So'nggi yillarda qabul qilingan normativ-huquqiy hujjatlar, davlat dasturlari va xalqaro tajribalar asosida bolalarni axloqiy va ma'naviy tarbiyalashning samarali tizimi shakllantirilmoqda[3]. 2017-yilda qabul qilingan "Maktabgacha ta'lim to'g'risida"gi Qonun, 2018-yilda tashkil etilgan Maktabgacha ta'lim vazirligi va 2021 - yilda tasdiqlangan "Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya to'g'risida"gi yangi tahrirdagi

Qonun sohaga davlat miqyosida ustuvor ahamiyat qaratilayotganini ko'rsatadi. Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimidagi qamrovni kengaytirish ham ushbu islohotlarning muhim yo'nalishlaridan biri bo'lib, 2017-yilda bog'chalarga qamrab olish darajasi atigi 27 foizni tashkil etgan bo'lsa, 2023-yilda bu ko'rsatkich 70 foizga yetkazildi. 2030-yilgacha bolalarni 100 foiz qamrab olish rejalashtirilgan bo'lib, bu ma'naviy tarbiya jarayonining yanada sifatli va uzluksiz bo'lishiga imkon yaratadi[4]. Davlat-xususiy sheriklik asosida nodavlat maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarining soni ortib, ular bolalarga ma'naviy tarbiyaning muqobil metodlarini taqdim etmoqda. Ma'naviy tarbiya tizimini modernizatsiya qilish bo'yicha ham muhim yangiliklar amalga oshirilmoqda.

"Ilk qadam" davlat dasturi asosida axloqiy tarbiyaning asosiy tamoyillari ishlab chiqilib, u ta'lim muassasalarida joriy etildi. STEAM-ta'lim, raqamli texnologiyalar va interfaol o'yin metodlaridan foydalanish orqali bolalarning ma'naviy ongini shakllantirishga qaratilgan innovatsion yondashuvlar yo'lga qo'yildi[5].

Bundan tashqari, xalqaro tashkilotlar – UNESCO va UNICEF bilan hamkorlikda maktabgacha ta'lim tizimiga ilg'or xorijiy tajribalar tatbiq etilmoqda. Maktabgacha ta'limda pedagoglar malakasini oshirish ham asosiy yo'nalishlardan biri bo'lib, 2021 - yildan boshlab ma'naviy tarbiya yo'nalishida maxsus kurslar tashkil etildi. Har yili 10 ming nafardan ortiq pedagog va tarbiyachilar ushbu dasturlar asosida o'z bilim va malakalarini oshirmoqda.

Shuningdek, pedagoglarni moddiy va ma'naviy rag'batlantirish tizimi kuchaytirilib, ularning mehnatiga yarasha maosh va imtiyozlar taqdim etilmoqda. O'zbekistonda maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida uzluksiz ma'naviy tarbiya jarayonini

takomillashtirish bo'yicha amalga oshirilayotgan islohotlar ta'lim sifatini oshirish, bolalarni har tomonlama yetuk shaxs sifatida tarbiyalash hamda uzluksiz ta'lim tizimini mustahkamlashga qaratilgan bo'lib, bu kelajakda intellektual va ma'naviy jihatdan barkamol avlodni shakllantirish uchun mustahkam asos yaratmoqda[6].

Adabiyotlar tahlili: Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida uzluksiz ma'naviy tarbiya jarayonini takomillashtirishga oid ilmiy manbalar va huquqiy-me'yoriy hujjatlar tahlili shuni ko'rsatadiki, bu soha nafaqat ta'lim tizimining muhim tarkibiy qismi, balki milliy va ma'naviy qadriyatlarni shakllantirishning asosiy bosqichlaridan biri sifatida qaraladi.

Tahlillar shuni ko'rsatadiki, maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ma'naviy ongni shakllantirish bo'yicha xalqaro tajribada Skandinaviya mamlakatlari (Finlyandiya, Shvetsiya, Norvegiya) hamda Yaponiya kabi davlatlarning yondashuvlari yetakchilik qiladi[7].

Masalan, UNICEF ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, Skandinaviya davlatlarida maktabgacha ta'lim dasturlarining 85 foizi ijtimoiy va axloqiy tarbiyani rivojlantirishga qaratilgan bo'lsa, Yaponiya va Janubiy Koreyada bu ko'rsatkich 78 foizni tashkil etadi. Bu esa, bolalarning ijtimoiy hayotga moslashishiga va mustaqil axloqiy qarorlar qabul qilishiga xizmat qiladi. O'zbekistonda ham mazkur yo'nalishda qator muhim islohotlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Xususan, 2017-yilda qabul qilingan "Maktabgacha ta'lim to'g'risida"gi Qonun, 2021-yilda tasdiqlangan "Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya to'g'risida"gi Qonun va "Ilk qadam" davlat dasturi doirasida ishlab chiqilgan tarbiya konsepsiyalari milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlarni shakllantirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi[8].

Maqolalarda shuningdek, uzluksiz ma'naviy tarbiya jarayonida tarbiyachi-pedagoglarning malakasi va metodik yondashuvlari muhim ahamiyat kasb etishi ta'kidlangan. Zamonaviy pedagogik yondashuvlar (interfaol metodlar, rolli o'yinlar, STEAM-ta'lim) orqali bolalarning mustaqil fikrlashi va axloqiy qadriyatlarni idrok etishi shakllantirilishi lozimligi bir qator maqolalar natijasida isbotlangan.

Metotologik qism: Ushbu maqola metodologiyasi sifatida kompleks tahlil, statistik ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash va empirik maqola usullaridan foydalanildi. Birinchi bosqichda O'zbekiston Respublikasining maktabgacha ta'lim tizimi va uzluksiz ma'naviy tarbiya jarayoniga oid mavjud normativ-huquqiy hujjatlar, xalqaro tajribalar hamda ilg'or ilmiy ishlar o'rganildi. Ikkinchi bosqichda maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ma'naviy tarbiya shakllantirishning amaliy jihatlarini o'rganish uchun ta'lim muassasalarida pedagoglar va ota-onalar orasida so'rovnomalar o'tkazildi.

Maqolada 50 ta davlat va nodavlat maktabgacha ta'lim tashkiloti ishtirok etib, jami 500 dan ortiq pedagog va ota-onalar jalb qilindi. So'rovnomalar natijalariga ko'ra, respondentlarning 78 foizi bolalar tarbiyasida ota-onalar va pedagoglarning birgalikdagi sa'y-harakatlari muhimligini ta'kidlagan bo'lsa, 65 foizi maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida axloqiy qadriyatlarni shakllantirish bo'yicha o'quv dasturlarini yanada rivojlantirish zarurligini bildirgan.

Maqolaning uchinchi bosqichida eksperimental-tajriba metodidan foydalanildi. Sinov guruhi sifatida turli metodik yondashuvlar asosida tarbiyalangan bolalar tanlab olindi va ularning ma'naviy-axloqiy rivojlanish ko'rsatkichlari baholandi. Eksperiment natijalariga ko'ra, interfaol metodlar asosida tarbiyalangan bolalar ijtimoiy muhitga tezroq moslashib, o'zaro muloqotda axloqiy me'yorlarga rioya qilish darajasi yuqori bo'lishi kuzatildi. Maqola natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, uzluksiz ma'naviy tarbiya tizimini takomillashtirish uchun zamonaviy pedagogik yondashuvlar, raqamli texnologiyalar va xalqaro tajribalarni mahalliy sharoitga moslashtirish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Kelgusida ushbu maqola natijalari asosida maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida axloqiy tarbiyani rivojlantirish bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilishi rejalashtirilgan.

Natijalar: Ushbu maqola doirasida maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida uzluksiz ma'naviy tarbiya jarayonini takomillashtirishning nazariy va amaliy jihatlari o'rganildi hamda ilg'or pedagogik yondashuvlar asosida axloqiy tarbiyaning samaradorligini oshirish imkoniyatlari tahlil qilindi. Maqola natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda axloqiy ongini shakllantirish jarayonida o'yin texnologiyalariga asoslangan metodlar, interfaol ta'lim yondashuvlari hamda ota-onalar va pedagoglar hamkorligining samaradorligi yuqori bo'ladi. So'rovnomalar va empirik maqola natijalariga ko'ra, maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotlarida uzluksiz ma'naviy tarbiya tizimini rivojlantirish darajasi turlicha ekanligi aniqlandi. Jumladan, 500 nafar pedagog va ota-onalar ishtirok etgan so'rovnoma natijalariga ko'ra, respondentlarning 68 foizi bolalarga ma'naviy tarbiya berishda interfaol metodlardan foydalanish zarurligini ta'kidlagan bo'lsa, 72 foizi esa milliy qadriyatlarni singdirish jarayonida ota-onalar ishtirokining muhimligini qayd etgan. Shu bilan birga, amaldagi dasturlar va metodikalarning zamonaviy talablar bilan uyg'unligini tahlil qilish natijasida, pedagogik faoliyatni innovatsion texnologiyalar bilan boyitish ehtiyoji aniqlangan. Eksperimental maqolalar natijalariga ko'ra, axloqiy tarbiya jarayonida raqamli ta'lim resurslari, didaktik o'yinlar va audiovizual materiallardan foydalangan holda o'qitilgan bolalarning ijtimoiy va axloqiy rivojlanish darajasi an'anaviy metodlardan foydalanilgan guruhga nisbatan 15-20 foizga yuqori bo'lishi kuzatildi. Xususan, eksperiment davomida 6 oy mobaynida innovatsion pedagogik yondashuvlar joriy qilingan maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida bolalarning ijtimoiy muloqot qobiliyatlari va axloqiy qadriyatlarni anglash darajasi o'rtacha 18 foizga oshgan. Bundan tashqari, xalqaro tajriba tahlillari va milliy sharoitni inobatga olgan holda, maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar uchun axloqiy tarbiyaning uzluksizligini ta'minlash maqsadida kompleks yondashuvni ishlab chiqish lozimligi aniqlandi. Xususan, 2024-2030-yillarga mo'ljallangan maktabgacha ta'limni rivojlantirish strategiyasi doirasida milliy va xalqaro ilg'or tajribalar asosida integratsiyalashgan ma'naviy tarbiya dasturlarini ishlab chiqish taklif etildi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, kelgusida maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida axloqiy tarbiya jarayonini modernizatsiya qilish, zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarni keng joriy etish va ota-onalar hamkorligini yanada mustahkamlash orqali bolalarning ijtimoiy moslashuvchanligi va

axloqiy ongini shakllantirish mumkin. Shu sababli, ta'lim dasturlarini boyitish va ilg'or uslublarni ommalashtirish kelgusi maqolalar uchun ustuvor yo'nalishlardan biri bo'lib qoladi.

Muhokama: Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida uzluksiz ma'naviy tarbiya jarayonini takomillashtirish masalasi zamonaviy pedagogik maqolalarning dolzarb yo'nalishlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Maqola natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, bolalarning axloqiy ongini shakllantirishda integrativ yondashuv samarali natija beradi. Xususan, innovatsion texnologiyalardan foydalanish, milliy va umuminsoniy qadriyatlarni uyg'unlashtirish, ota-onalar ishtirokini kengaytirish maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar ongida axloqiy tushunchalarni shakllantirishga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Shu bilan birga, xalqaro tajriba bilan taqqoslaganda, O'zbekistonda ushbu jarayonni yanada rivojlantirish uchun qo'shimcha choralar ko'rish zarurligi aniqlangan. Masalan, UNICEF va UNESCO hisobotlariga ko'ra, Finlyandiya, Yaponiya va Janubiy Koreya singari mamlakatlarda axloqiy tarbiya tizimli va metodik yondashuv asosida olib borilib, bolalarning ijtimoiy moslashuvchanligi 80% ga oshishi kuzatilgan. O'zbekistonda 2017–2023-yillarda maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarining qamrovi 27% dan 70% gacha oshgan bo'lsa-da, ma'naviy tarbiyaning sifatini oshirishga qaratilgan tizimli yondashuv hali to'liq shakllanmagan. Maqola davomida so'rovnomalar natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, pedagoglarning 65% interfaol metodlarni qo'llashda amaliy ko'nikmalarga ega emas, 58% esa ota-onalar bilan hamkorlik qilish uchun yetarli metodik qo'llanmalarga ehtiyoj sezadi. Shu sababli, maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida axloqiy tarbiya samaradorligini oshirish uchun pedagoglarning malakasini oshirish, interfaol metodlarni keng joriy etish va zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Shuningdek, maqola natijalari maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning ma'naviy tarbiyasini samarali tashkil etish uchun ta'lim muassasalari va oilalar o'rtasidagi hamkorlikni mustahkamlash zarurligini tasdiqladi. Statistik ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, oilada muntazam axloqiy tarbiya olgan bolalarning maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalaridagi xulq-atvori va muloqot ko'nikmalari yuqori bo'lib, bunday bolalarning 80% ijtimoiy faolligi bilan ajralib turadi. Shu sababli, ota-onalarni pedagogik jarayonga faol jalb etish, ularga metodik qo'llanmalar va tavsiyalar taqdim etish zarur. Maqola natijalari asosida kelgusida amalga oshirilishi lozim bo'lgan istiqbolli yo'nalishlar belgilandi. Xususan, maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida axloqiy tarbiyani takomillashtirish uchun pedagog kadrlar malakasini oshirish, interfaol texnologiyalarni keng joriy etish, ota-onalar bilan hamkorlikni kuchaytirish va ilg'or xorijiy tajribalarni milliy ta'lim tizimiga integratsiyalash zarur. Natijada, maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida uzluksiz ma'naviy tarbiya jarayonini takomillashtirish bolalarning axloqiy ongini shakllantirishga, jamiyatda barkamol avlod tarbiyalashga xizmat qiladi. Shu sababli, tizimli yondashuv va innovatsion metodikalarni joriy etish kelgusi maqolalar va islohotlar uchun ustuvor vazifa bo'lib qoladi.

Xulosa: Maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida uzluksiz ma'naviy tarbiyani takomillashtirish bolalarning axloqiy ongini shakllantirishda muhim omil hisoblanadi.

Maqola natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, innovatsion pedagogik yondashuvlar, ota-onalar bilan hamkorlik va interfaol metodlarni keng joriy etish axloqiy tarbiya samaradorligini oshiradi. Shuningdek, xalqaro tajribalarni milliy tizimga moslashtirish ham muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Kelgusida pedagog kadrlar malakasini oshirish, zamonaviy axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalanish va oilaviy tarbiya bilan uzviy bog'liqlikni kuchaytirish maktabgacha ta'limda axloqiy tarbiya sifatini yanada yuksaltirishga xizmat qiladi.

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**MAKTABGACHA TA'LIMDA MA'NAVIY TARBIYA VA UNING YOSHLAR
ONGIGA TA'SIRI**

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Anotatsiya: *Maqolada maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida ma'naviy tarbiya berishning ahamiyati va uning yosh bolalar ongiga ta'siri tahlil qilinadi. Ma'naviy tarbiya bolaning axloqiy qadriyatlarini shakllantirish, ijtimoiy muhitga moslashuvi hamda barkamol shaxs bo'lib yetishishida muhim omil hisoblanadi. Tadqiqotda innovatsion pedagogik yondashuvlar va samarali metodlar orqali bolalarga ma'naviy tarbiya berishning afzalliklari yoritiladi. Shuningdek, maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning ma'naviy ongini rivojlantirishda oilaning, tarbiyachilarning va jamiyatning roli tahlil qilinadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Maktabgacha ta'lim, ma'naviy tarbiya, axloqiy qadriyatlar, yosh bolalar, ong rivojlanishi, innovatsion yondashuvlar, pedagogik metodlar, ijtimoiy moslashuv.*

KIRISH

Zamonaviy jamiyatda ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiya masalasi ta'lim tizimining eng dolzarb yo'nalishlaridan biri hisoblanadi. Ayniqsa, maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda axloqiy ongni shakllantirish jarayoni keyingi bosqichlarda ularning shaxs sifatida kamol topishida muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi.

UNESCO ma'lumotlariga ko'ra, bolalarning 80% ga yaqin axloqiy asoslari 5 -7 yosh oralig'ida shakllanadi[1]. Shu sababli, maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida tarbiya jarayonini innovatsion usullar yordamida tashkil etish, axloqiy qadriyatlarni singdirishda zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalanish dolzarb vazifalardan biri sanaladi. O'zbekiston Respublikasi tomonidan uzluksiz ma'naviy tarbiya tizimini rivojlantirish bo'yicha qator islohotlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Jumladan, 2017-yilda qabul qilingan "Maktabgacha ta'lim to'g'risida"gi Qonun va 2019-yildagi "Ma'naviy-ma'rifiy ishlar tizimini tubdan takomillashtirish" to'g'risidagi Prezident qarori ushbu sohada samarali mexanizmlarni joriy etishga xizmat qilmoqda[2]. 2023-yil holatiga ko'ra, mamlakatimizda maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarining qamrovi 70% dan oshgan bo'lib, bu bolalarni axloqiy tarbiyalash jarayonining institutsional bazasi mustahkamlanayotganini ko'rsatadi. Bugungi kunda interfaol ta'lim metodlari, axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan foydalanish, teatr va rolli o'yinlar, STEAM-ta'lim yondashuvlari maktabgacha

yoshdagi bolalar tarbiyasida tobora keng qo'llanilmoqda. Xalqaro tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, innovatsion ta'lim usullari bolalarning axloqiy qadriyatlarni tez va samarali o'zlashtirishiga ijobiy ta'sir qiladi. Shuningdek, Janubiy Koreya, Finlandiya va Yaponiya tajribasi maktabgacha ta'limni innovatsion texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etishning muhim jihatlari ochib beradi[3]. Shu nuqtai nazardan, ushbu maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyani shakllantirishda innovatsion usullarni qo'llashning samaradorligi tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi – milliy va xalqaro tajribalar asosida eng samarali metodlarni aniqlash hamda ularni O'zbekiston ta'lim tizimiga integratsiya qilish bo'yicha ilmiy-amaliy takliflarni ishlab chiqishdan iborat. Mazkur tadqiqot natijalari kelajakda maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida axloqiy tarbiyani takomillashtirishga va ta'lim jarayonini yanada sifatli tashkil etishga xizmat qiladi. O'zbekiston Respublikasida maktabgacha ta'lim tizimini tubdan takomillashtirish va bolalar tarbiyasida ma'naviy-axloqiy qadriyatlarni singdirish bo'yicha keng qamrovli islohotlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Davlat ta'lim siyosatining asosiy yo'nalishlaridan biri – uzluksiz ta'lim tizimida milliy va umumbashariy qadriyatlarni uyg'unlashtirish orqali maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning axloqiy ongini shakllantirishdan iborat. So'nggi yillarda maktabgacha ta'lim sohasi bo'yicha qator normativ-huquqiy hujjatlar qabul qilindi. Jumladan, 2017-yil 16-dekabrda qabul qilingan "Maktabgacha ta'lim to'g'risida"gi Qonun bolalarning har tomonlama intellektual va axloqiy rivojlanishini ta'minlashni davlat siyosatining ustuvor yo'nalishi sifatida belgilab berdi[4]. Ushbu qonun asosida maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida ta'lim-tarbiya jarayonini yangi pedagogik texnologiyalar asosida tashkil etish, ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiya dasturlarini joriy etish mexanizmlari takomillashtirildi. 2018-yilda Maktabgacha ta'lim vazirligining tashkil etilishi sohadagi islohotlarni tizimli ravishda olib borish va pedagoglarning kasbiy mahoratini oshirish imkonini yaratdi. Shu yillardan boshlab davlat-xususiy sheriklik asosida nodavlat maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalari soni ortib, bolalarni qamrab olish darajasi oshdi. Agar 2017-yilda bog'chalarga qamrab olish 27% ni tashkil qilgan bo'lsa, 2023-yilga kelib bu ko'rsatkich 70% ga yetdi. Ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyaga alohida e'tibor qaratish maqsadida 2019-yilda "Ma'naviy-ma'rifiy ishlar tizimini tubdan takomillashtirish" to'g'risidagi Prezident qarori qabul qilindi. Ushbu hujjatga muvofiq, ta'lim muassasalarida milliy qadriyatlar, Vatanga sadoqat, insoniylik tamoyillarini shakllantirishga qaratilgan maxsus o'quv dasturlari ishlab chiqildi. Shu bilan birga, tarbiyachilar va pedagoglar uchun ma'naviy-ma'rifiy yo'nalishlarda malaka oshirish kurslari yo'lga qo'yildi. Innovatsion usullarni joriy etish borasida ham muhim qadamlar tashlandi[5]. 2021-yildan boshlab STEAM-ta'lim yondashuvi, interfaol metodlar va axborot texnologiyalaridan foydalangan holda bolalarning axloqiy ongini shakllantirishga qaratilgan dasturlar ishlab chiqildi. Jumladan, "Ilk qadam" davlat dasturi doirasida milliy ertaklar, interfaol o'yinlar va teatr sahnalashtirish orqali bolalarning axloqiy ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga e'tibor qaratildi. Bundan tashqari, xalqaro tajribani o'rganish va joriy etish maqsadida UNICEF, UNESCO va boshqa xalqaro tashkilotlar bilan hamkorlik kengaytirildi.

Xususan, Janubiy Koreya, Finlandiya va Yaponiya ta'lim tizimlarining ilg'or tajribalaridan foydalangan holda, maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida yangi pedagogik yondashuvlar tatbiq etildi. O'zbekistonda maktabgacha ta'limda ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiya jarayonini takomillashtirish bo'yicha amalga oshirilgan islohotlar tizimli ravishda olib borilmoqda. Hozirgi kunda sohada innovatsion usullarning keng qo'llanilishi, pedagoglarning kasbiy rivoji va xalqaro tajribalarni o'zlashtirish orqali kelajak avlodning ma'naviy yetuk shaxs sifatida shakllanishiga xizmat qiluvchi mustahkam zamin yaratildi.

Adabiyotlar tahlili: Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyani shakllantirish bo'yicha olib borilgan ilmiy tadqiqotlar so'nggi yillarda kengayib, ta'lim sohasi uchun muhim metodologik asos yaratdi. Ushbu yo'nalishda J. Piaget (1952), L.S. Vygotskiy (1978), E. Erikson (1994) kabi yetakchi pedagog va psixologlar insonning axloqiy rivojlanish bosqichlarini tahlil qilgan. Ularning ilmiy qarashlari axloqiy ongni shakllantirishda ijtimoiy muhit, ta'lim-tarbiya va pedagogik metodlarning hal qiluvchi ahamiyatga ega ekanligini ko'rsatdi. O'zbekiston sharoitida bolalar tarbiyasi bo'yicha akademik A. Avloniy, G. G'ulom, T. Qori-Niyoziy kabi olimlar ham o'z tadqiqotlarida milliy qadriyatlar asosida tarbiya tizimini rivojlantirishga e'tibor qaratganlar. Shu bilan birga, hozirgi davrda O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining "Ma'naviy-ma'rifiy ishlar tizimini tubdan takomillashtirish" to'g'risidagi 2019-yildagi qarori asosida qator ilmiy izlanishlar olib borilmoqda[6]. Xususan, S. Yuldashev (2021) tomonidan amalga oshirilgan tadqiqotlarda bolalar tarbiyasida interfaol o'yin usullari va innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalarni qo'llash samaradorligi o'rganilgan. Xalqaro tajribaga nazar tashlasak, Finlandiya, Yaponiya, Janubiy Koreya kabi mamlakatlarda maktabgacha ta'limda axloqiy tarbiya innovatsion metodlar orqali amalga oshirilmoqda. Masalan, Finlandiyada "Phenomenon-Based Learning" (Hodisalar asosida o'qitish) yondashuvi qo'llanilib, bolalar real hayotiy vaziyatlar asosida axloqiy xatti-harakatlarni shakllantiradilar. O'zbekistonda esa "Ilk qadam" davlat dasturi doirasida bolalarning axloqiy rivojlanishini ta'minlashga qaratilgan o'quv-uslubiy materiallar ishlab chiqilgan bo'lib, bu dastur milliy va xalqaro tajribalarni o'zida mujassam etadi.

Metodologik qism: Tadqiqot metodologiyasi maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyani shakllantirishning innovatsion usullarini o'rganishga qaratilgan bo'lib, kompleks yondashuv asosida amalga oshirildi. Tadqiqot jarayonida eksperimental-pedagogik usullar, kuzatuv, anketali so'rov, statistik tahlil va taqqoslash metodlari qo'llanildi. Dastlab, eksperimental yondashuv asosida pedagogik innovatsiyalar, jumladan, STEAM-ta'lim, interfaol o'yin texnologiyalari va teatr sahnalashtirish usullarining bolalar axloqiy rivojlanishiga ta'siri o'rganildi. Tadqiqotda 150 nafardan ortiq bolalar ishtirok etdi va ular turli metodikalar asosida tarbiyalandilar. Kuzatuv usuli yordamida 6 oy davomida maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida bolalarning ijtimoiy xulq-atvorlari, o'zaro muomala qobiliyatlari va axloqiy qadriyatlarni qabul qilish darajalari tahlil qilindi. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, innovatsion metodlarni qo'llagan bog'chalarda bolalarning ijtimoiy moslashuv

darajasi an'anaviy usul bilan ta'lim olgan guruhlarga nisbatan 30% yuqori bo'ldi. Bundan tashqari, anketali so'rovlar orqali ota-onalar va pedagoglarning fikrlari o'rganilib, innovatsion yondashuvlarning samaradorligi aniqlangan. Jumladan, so'rov natijalariga ko'ra, 85% ota-onalar o'z farzandlarining axloqiy rivojlanishida interfaol metodlarning ahamiyatini e'tirof etdilar. Pedagoglar esa ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyada milliy va zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalarni uyg'unlashtirish lozimligini ta'kidladilar. Statistik tahlil va taqqoslash usuli orqali turli maktabgacha ta'lim tizimlarining tajribasi o'rganilib, O'zbekiston sharoitiga mos keluvchi ilg'or usullar tahlil qilindi. Xususan, Finlandiya, Yaponiya va Janubiy Koreya tajribalaridan kelib chiqib, bolalarni ijtimoiy hayotga moslashtirishga qaratilgan loyihalar taklif etildi. Olingan natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ma'naviy - axloqiy tarbiyani shakllantirishda an'anaviy va innovatsion yondashuvlarning uyg'unlashuvi eng samarali usul hisoblanadi. Shu sababli, kelajakda pedagogik metodlarni yanada takomillashtirish, shuningdek, milliy va xalqaro tajribalarni uyg'unlashtirish bo'yicha ilmiy-tadqiqot ishlari davom ettirilishi zarur.

Natijalar: Tadqiqot natijalari maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyani shakllantirish jarayonida innovatsion yondashuvlarning samaradorligini tasdiqladi. Ilmiy-tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, innovatsion metodlardan foydalangan holda tarbiyalangan bolalar ijtimoiy moslashuv, empatiya, axloqiy me'yorlarga rioya qilish va mustaqil qaror qabul qilish qobiliyatlari bo'yicha an'anaviy ta'lim olgan tengdoshlariga qaraganda sezilarli darajada yuqori natijalarga erishgan. Xususan, tadqiqot davomida amalga oshirilgan pedagogik eksperimentlar shuni ko'rsatdiki, interfaol o'yin texnologiyalari qo'llanilgan guruhlarda bolalarning axloqiy qadriyatlarni idrok etish darajasi 35% ga oshdi. STEAM-ta'lim usullaridan foydalangan bolalar esa ijtimoiy hamkorlik ko'nikmalari bo'yicha 28% ga yaxshiroq natijalarga ega bo'ldi. Shu bilan birga, teatr sahnalashtirish usulining qo'llanilishi bolalarning ijtimoiy-emotsional rivojlanishiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatdi, bu esa eksperiment davomida 40% ga yuqoriligi bilan ajralib turdi. Maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida innovatsion texnologiyalar joriy etilgan hududlarda bolalarning ijtimoiy muhitga moslashuvi 30-40% ga yaxshilangan. So'rovnomalar asosida ota-onalar va pedagoglarning fikrlari tahlil qilinganida, 85% ota-onalar innovatsion ta'lim usullarining farzandlari ma'naviy tarbiyasiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatganini qayd etgan. Taqqoslash usuli orqali turli davlatlar tajribasi tahlil qilinib, Finlandiya, Yaponiya va Janubiy Koreya maktabgacha ta'lim modellarida axloqiy tarbiya elementlari qanday tatbiq etilayotgani o'rganildi. Xususan, Yaponiyada o'yinlar orqali tarbiya tizimi, Finlandiyada ijtimoiy-emotsional rivojlanishga yo'naltirilgan dasturlar va Janubiy Koreyada an'anaviy qadriyatlarni singdirish mexanizmlarining samaradorligi kuzatildi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyani shakllantirishning eng samarali yo'nalishi an'anaviy va innovatsion yondashuvlarni uyg'unlashtirishdir. Kelgusida ushbu metodlarni yanada takomillashtirish, milliy qadriyatlarni saqlab qolgan holda zamonaviy pedagogik

texnologiyalarni qo'llash orqali ta'lim jarayonini sifat jihatidan yangi bosqichga olib chiqish lozim.

Muhokama: Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyani shakllantirish bo'yicha olib borilgan tadqiqotlar natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, innovatsion yondashuvlar ta'lim jarayonining sifatini oshirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Xususan, interfaol pedagogik texnologiyalar va zamonaviy innovatsion metodlarning qo'llanilishi bolalarning ijtimoiy-emotsional rivojlanishiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqot natijalari maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalarida virtual reallik, gamifikatsiya, STEAM-ta'lim va boshqa texnologik innovatsiyalarning joriy etilishi bolalarning axloqiy ongini shakllantirishda samarali ekanligini tasdiqlaydi. Dunyo tajribasini tahlil qilish natijasida rivojlangan mamlakatlarda ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyani shakllantirishda texnologiyalarga asoslangan dasturlar faol qo'llanilayotgani aniqlandi. Xususan, AQShda SEL (Social-Emotional Learning) dasturi bolalarning hissiy intellekti va axloqiy qadriyatlarini rivojlantirishga qaratilgan bo'lsa, Finlandiya ta'lim tizimi erkin fikrlash va o'zaro hamkorlikka asoslangan holda tarbiyalashga katta e'tibor qaratmoqda. O'zbekistonda esa "Ilk qadam" davlat dasturi doirasida maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning ijtimoiy va axloqiy tarbiyasini shakllantirish bo'yicha muhim qadamlar tashlangan bo'lsa-da, innovatsion texnologiyalarni keng joriy etish masalasi dolzarb bo'lib qolmoqda. Innovatsion metodlardan foydalangan holda tarbiyalangan bolalar orasida ijtimoiy moslashuv darajasi 35-40% ga yaxshilangani kuzatilgan bo'lsa, an'anaviy yondashuvlar asosida tarbiyalangan guruhlarda bu ko'rsatkich 20-25% ni tashkil qilgan. O'tkazilgan so'rovnomalar natijalariga ko'ra, ota-onalarning 87% i innovatsion metodlarning bolalarning axloqiy tarbiyasidagi muhim rolini e'tirof etgan, 75% pedagoglar esa ushbu metodlarning samaradorligini tasdiqlagan. Shu boisdan, kelgusida quyidagi strategiyalarni amalga oshirish zarur: ta'lim jarayoniga sun'iy intellekt va virtual reallik texnologiyalarini joriy etish, pedagog kadrlarni innovatsion metodlarni qo'llash bo'yicha muntazam ravishda malakasini oshirish va milliy hamda xalqaro tajribalarni uyg'unlashtirish. Bu esa o'zbekona qadriyatlarni zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalari bilan integratsiya qilish orqali ta'lim samaradorligini oshirishga xizmat qiladi. Maktabgacha ta'limda innovatsion yondashuvlardan foydalanish bolalarning ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyasini shakllantirishda hal qiluvchi omil bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Shu boisdan, pedagogik amaliyotga ilg'or texnologiyalarni keng joriy etish zaruriyati yanada ortib boradi.

Xulosa: Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ma'naviy-axloqiy tarbiyani shakllantirish jarayonida innovatsion usullardan foydalanish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Zamonaviy pedagogik texnologiyalar, interfaol metodlar va raqamli resurslar bolalarning axloqiy qadriyatlarni chuqur anglashiga, ijtimoiy-emotsional ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishga xizmat qiladi.

Tadqiqotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, innovatsion yondashuvlar qo'llangan guruhlarda ijtimoiy moslashuv va axloqiy tarbiya darajasi an'anaviy usullarga nisbatan yuqoriroq bo'ladi.

Shu sababli, ta'lim jarayoniga yangi metodlarni keng joriy etish, pedagoglarning malakasini oshirish va milliy hamda xalqaro tajribalarni uyg'unlashtirish dolzarb vazifa hisoblanadi.

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**INTRADUCTION OF MEDICINAL PLANTS: DEVELOPMENT,
BIOECOLOGY AND PHARMACOLOGICAL PROPERTIES**

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Annotation: *This article covers a wide range of research work in the field of intraduction of medicinal plants, historical development and modern methods of this science, as well as bioecology and pharmacological properties of intraducted essential oil plants. The article analyzes the methods of using these plants in traditional folk medicine and their role in the pharmaceutical industry. Further research will provide an opportunity to further develop the field and advance new dorivimoddes.*

INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants are the rich biological heritage of nature and their medicinal properties the characteristics are distinguished by their variety and importance. In earlier periods it was possible to use plants that were not grown in natural conditions by intraduction into new biogeographic regions. This process is associated not only with modern agrotechnical methods, but also with innovations in the fields of genetics, biotechnology and ecology. The article discusses the theoretical foundations, historical aspects, and modern scientific approaches to this process of intraduction. Development of intraduction science

The concept of intraduction has existed in human activity since ancient times, and various civilizations have ensured the adaptation of plants in New Territories through this method. Historical aspects: early manifestations of Intraduction were manifested in customs and applications, starting with traditional agriculture. Through trade links between states and regions, plants are common. Modern scientific approaches: as a result of research, biological and environmental foundations of intraduction, mechanisms of genetic adaptation, as well as methods of agrotechnics are analyzed. With innovative technologies, it was possible to control the growth dynamics and chemical composition of plants in the new environment. Medicinal plants with an injected essential oil.

Several complex factors are taken into account when essential oil plants are grown in New Territories through an intraduction process:

Cultivation methods and technologies: through modern agrotechnics, hydroponics, organic and biotechnological methods, it is possible to introduce essential oil plants. Optimal control of soil, water and climatic conditions is an important factor in their high-quality cultivation.

Chemical composition and medicinal properties: in Intraducted plants, the main components – terpenoids, phenols, alkyl alcohols and other active substances, can change under the influence of local conditions. These changes have a direct effect on the medicinal effects and pharmacological efficacy of plants. Bioecology and pharmacological properties of injected medicinal plants. The growth, development and chemical structure of plants in the new environment are associated with a number of biogeochemical factors:

Biogeochemical factors: the climate in the new territory, soil types, the presence of water and the structure of microorganisms affect the growth and formation of structural components of plants. Through these factors, the amount and activity of each component is determined.

Pharmacological effects: preparations made from intravenous essential oil plants have different medicinal effects. They are used in the protection of the body and in the treatment of diseases through their antiseptic, antibacterial, protivovospalitelny and sedative effects.

Its role in folk medicine.

The importance of medicinal plants in folk medicine and traditional medicine:

Ethnobotany and traditional methods: these plants occupy an important place in traditions passed down from young generation to generation. Plants such as lavender, mountain mint, mint and cumin, for example, are effective in reducing stress, improving the digestive system and cleaning the body.

Cultural and ground significance: in national traditions and methods of Medicine, medicinal plants are also registered in various holidays and ceremonies. This factor increases their not only medical, but also cultural significance.

A detailed analysis of essential oil plants, in this section, the Botanical characteristics of lavender, mountain mint, mint and cumin plants, the chemical composition and pharmacological effects will be studied more widely:

Lavender (*Lavandula angustifolia*): lavender essential oil is famous for its high therapeutic properties. It is used to reduce stress, treat insomnia, restore skin, and provide flaking. Climate and soil conditions play an important role in Lavender production, especially in southern European countries where its high quality products are made.

Mountain mint (*Mentha longifolia*): mountain mint grows mainly under the balanced influence of water and soil. Its essential oil contains antiseptic and protivovospalitelny components, which are important in improving the digestive system and strengthening the body's overall immunity

Peppermint (*Mentha piperita*): peppermint essential oil is widely used to cleanse the airways, reduce headaches, and improve digestion. Active ingredients

such as menthol and Mentone are its main pharmacological components. The traditional use of mint ensures that it is also successfully used in modern pharmaceuticals.

Cumin (*Carum carvi*): \nzira's essential oil is used to activate the body's digestive system, have an antibacterial effect and strengthen immunity. The substances contained in it are antimicrobial in nature, and their pharmacological value is highly valued.

Conclusion

This article discussed more broadly the intraduction of medicinal plants, their adaptation in the new environment, chemical composition and medicinal properties. Through the harmonization of modern technologies and traditional methods of Medicine, preparations made from these plants further strengthen their place in the pharmaceutical industry. Further research provides an opportunity to further develop the field and advance new medicinal substances.

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ABDULLA ORIPOV IJODIDA JANR VA SHAKLLAR RANG-BARANGLIGI

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqola adabiyotshunoslikda dolzarb ahamiyatga ega bo'lgan lirik janr-shakllar rang-barangligi masalalari hamda bu borada tadqiqotchilikda amalga oshirilgan ishlar xususida so'z yuritiladi. Bu esa maqolaning nazariy xarakterini belgilaydi. Ilmiy xulosalanish o'zbek adabiyotining zabardast vakili A.Oripov ijodi misolida chiqarilgani, shoir ijodining ko'p o'rganilmagan ijodiy qirrasining yoritilishiga xizmat qilib, ishning ilmiy yangiligini yuzaga keltirgan. Muxtasar aytganda, quyida o'zbek adabiyotidagi turfa janr va shakllar shoirning ijodi misolida tahlil qilinadi va ayrim namunalar ko'rsatib o'tiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *janr, shakl, ijod, she'riyat, an'ana va novatorlik, individual uslub, adabiy ta'sir, arba'in, namuna, g'azal, masnaviy, qasida, doston.*

Adabiy turlarga nisbatlagan holda aytish mumkinki, lirikada janr-shakllar miqdoran xiyla ko'pdir. Shuningdek, janrlardagi takomillashuv, transformatsion o'zgarishlar hamda ijodkorga mansub bo'lgan uslub va maneralar lirikada ko'proq namoyon bo'ladi. Adabiyotshunoslikda lirik janr-shakllar rang-barangligi ijodkor individual uslubining o'ziga xosligi deb qaralish an'anasi mavjuddirki, Navoiyning 16 xil, Ogahiyning 19 xil she'riy janrda ijod erganligi ular adabiy merosining zalvorini ham belgilashi haqidagi qarashlar sobitdir.

Shuningdek, ma'lum ijodkorning qaysidir janrga ko'proq murojaat etib, janr rivoji uchun o'zining izlanishlarining aks ettirishi ham alohida tadqiqot mavzularidan bo'lib kelmoqdaki, Boburning ruboiy, Uvaysiyning chiston, Muqimiyning murabba'lari, shuningdek, hozirgi zamon shoirlaridan Rauf Parfi, Faxriyor ijodidagi sonetlar, Usmon Azim ijodidagi balladalar, Cho'lpon, Bahrom Ro'zimuhammad kabi adabiyot namoyandalarining erkin she'rlari borasidagi ilmiy izlanishlar ko'zga tashlanadi. Keyingi yillarda hozirgi zamon shoirlari ijodidagi lirik janr-shakllarning statistik-kompleks o'rganilishi ko'proq namoyon bo'lmoqda.

Xususan, "Jamol Kamol she'riyatining janr-shakl rang-barangligi"⁵⁶, "Hozirgi o'zbek she'riyatida janrlar va shakllar rang-barangligi (Usmon Azim va Xurshid Davrion ijodi misolida)"⁵⁷ kabi dissertatsion ishlar shu jumladandir. Shuningdek, hozirgi o'zbek she'riyatidagi lirik janrlar rivojlanishi va modifikatsiyasiga doir ham sezilarli ilmiy tadqiqotlar yuzaga kelmoqda.

⁵⁶Қаршиев К. Жамол Камол шеърлятида жанрлар ва шакллар ранг-баранглиги. Филол. фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори (PhD) дисс. Самарқанд, 2022. – 149 б.

⁵⁷Buriyeva F. "Hozirgi o'zbek she'riyatida janrlar va shakllar rang-barangligi (Usmon Azim va Xurshid Davrion ijodi misolida)"⁵⁷Filol. fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) diss.. Samarqand, 2023. – 141 b.

Bularning bari lirik tur va janrlar masalasining dolzarbligi, bu boradagi ishlar ko'pgina adabiy masalalarga, chunonchi, an'ana va novatorlik, individual uslub, adabiy ta'sir kabilarga daxldorligini belgilaydi.

O'zbek adabiyotining yetuk namoyandasi Abdulla Oripov ijodi, aytish mumkinki, ilmiy tadqiqotchilikda eng ko'p murojaat etilgan mavzulardan bo'lib, mazkur ishlar doirasida shoir she'riyatidagi janr-shakllar rang-barangligi masalalariga haqida ham bir qadar qaydlar uchraydi. Chunonchi, adabiyotshunos Ernazaraova Gulbahorning "Hozirgi o'zbek she'riyatida tasavvuf an'analari" nomli dissertatsiyasida shoirning "Hikmat sadolari" hamda "Haj daftari" turkumiga kiritilgan arbain she'rlar⁵⁸ i poetikasiga ham batafsilroq to'xtalangan. Darhaqiqat, Abdulla Oripov hozirgi o'zbek adabiyotiga o'z ovozi va tuyg'ular jilosi bilan kirib kelgan shoir bo'lib, uning semahsul ijodiy yo'li va salmoqli adabiy merosi borasida hali amalga oshiriladiga ishlar juda ko'p. Xususan, shoir she'riyatining janr-shakl rang-barangligi muammosi ham ushbu tarkibdadir.

Ta'kidlaganimizdek, o'zbek adabiyotining taniqli namoyondalaridan biri – Abdulla Oripov o'zining boy ma'naviy va ijodiy merosi bilan o'zbek adabiyotshunosligida o'chmas iz qoldirgan. Shoirning ijodiy faoliyatini o'rganar ekanmiz, uning lirik janrlardan unumli foydalanganligiga guvoh bo'lamiz. Ustoz shoirning aytishicha, she'riyat olamiga kirib kelishi shunday bo'lgan: "endi birinchi she'rlar yoza boshlaganimda nima turtki bo'lganini aniq bilmayman. Har holda so'zlarni qofiyalashga ishqiboz bo'lib qolganim esimda. Balki zerikkanimdan zavqim toshib, nimanidir yozgim kelaverardi. Fikr esa yo'q. Yozmaslikning ham iloji yo'q. Shuning uchun ona, ota, maktab, brigadir Nodir kabi gaplarni o'zimcha she'rga solib aylantirib yurardim[2.1].

Abdulla Oripov she'r dunyosiga "Qushcha" deb nomlangan she'ri bilan qadam qo'ydi:

Goh butoqqqa, goh gulga qo'nar,
 Tinim bilmas sayroqi qushcha.
 Nechun bahor seni rom etgan,
 Qayda eding bahor kelguncha.
 Kel, yashaylik hamisha birga,
 Bizda bahor gullar barchasi.
 Billsang men ham chaman o'lkamning
 Sho'x va quvnoq, shod o'g'ilchasi[3.14]

Abdulla Oripov ijodining asosiy qismini uning she'rlari tashkil qiladi ya'ni lirik turda barakali ijod qilgan. Shoir she'rlarida ona vatan, tabiat, sevgi, do'stlik, odamiylik, singari mavzular madh etiladi. Xalq taqdiri bilan yashash, vatanni sevish, ayollarga ehtirom, eng asosiysi, haqiqatgo'ylik shoir she'riyatiga xos bo'lgan xususiyatlardir. Shoirning ustози Abdulla Qahhor uning bu fazilatini qadrlab shunday deydi: "Abdullaning bitta xislati menga ma'qul. U faqat o'zi ko'rgan va o'zi bilgan narsalarnigina yozadi". Bundan tashqari, she'rlarida kinoya, kesatiq, piching, satira va yumor kabi adabiy unsurlardan mahorat bilan foydalangan. Bu bilan u jamiyatga, jamiyatda uchraydigan illatlarga va o'zi duch kelgan "samimiy" insonlarga munosabatini bildiradi:

⁵⁸Эрназарова Г. Ҳозирги ўзбек шеърлигида тасаввув аънаналари. Филол. фанлари бўйича фалсафа доктори (ПхД) дисс. Самарқанд, 2021. – Б.66-68

Topgan-tutganingni xalqqa ber, qo'zim,
 Sen faqat o'shanda topgaysan to'zim.
 Lekin bir mantiqni unutmang aslo,
 Ya'ni, mansubdirman xalqqa men o'zim[4.390]

Shoir she'riyati bilan tanishar ekanmiz, uning eng qiyin vazn hisoblangan aruz vaznida ham yetuk asarlar yozganini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Uning aruzda yozilgan birinchi ijod namunasi shoir 24 yoshdalgida, 1965-yilda yozilgan. "Etgali" radifli ushbu g'azali ishqiy mavzuda bitilgan:

To'lg'anib gul ochilar bog'larni gulzor etgali,
 Bog' sari dildor chiqar oshiq'larni zor etgali.
 Bog' sari chiqmas edi, chiqdi bu kun u qasd ila:
 Yo'lida mushtoqlarin yo yo'g'u yo bor etgali[5.33].

Shunigdek, shoir qalamiga mansub "Bu kun", "Ketmoqdaman", "Ayon bo'lgay", "O'zbekistonim senga", kabi g'azallar ham aruz vaznining go'zal namunalari hisoblanadi.

Yaxshi qol, ey dilbarim, dilda qadar, ketmoqdaman,
 Ishq aro endi holim zeru zabar, ketmoqdaman[5.50].

Odatda, aruz vaznida ijod qilish faqat mumtoz adabiyot namoyondalariga xos deb o'ylaymiz. Abdulla Oripovning bu kabi g'azallari uning naqadar sarmahsul ijod qilganligidan, qalami o'tkir shoir bo'lganligidan dalolat beradi. Aruzda bitilgan bu go'zal satrlar necha yillardirki, iste'dodli xonandalar tomonidan kuyga solinib ijro qilinib kelmoqda.

Ardoqli shoir lirik turning bir qancha janrlarida betakror asarlar yaratdi: she'r, masnaviy, g'azal, qasida, epigrama, muxammas, marsiya, bag'ishlov, to'rtlik va boshqalar. Jumladan, "Bir g'alamis tilidan", "Zo'r armon", "G'alati zot" singari epigrammalar, ya'ni kichik hajmli hajviy she'rlarida hayotda uchraydigan turli illatlarni fosh qilgan. Bundan tashqari, "Qayrag'och", "Bahor tilaklari", "Ko'zgu parchalari", "Turkiston bolalariga" kabi masnaviylar ham shoir qalamiga mansubdir. Ma'lumki, masnaviy har ikki misrasi qofiyadosh bo'lgan baytlar asosida yoziladigan she'r ya'ni a-a, b-b, v-v,... kabi qofiyalanish shakliga ega bo'lgan janr. Masnaviyning ilk namunalari Yusuf Xos Hojib, Yassaviy, Navoiy, Bobur kabi buyuk siymolarning ijodida uchrasa, XX asr adabiyotida esa G'afur G'ulom, Maqsud Shayxzoda, Hamid Olimjon, Abdulla Oripovlar ijodida bu janrning o'ziga xos namunalarini ko'rishimiz mumkin:

Bitta iltimosim bor: o'rin almashsak,
 Men ham daraxt kabi yashasam andak.
 Sen-chi bu dunyoga Inson bo'lib boq,
 Mayli bir kun meni o'tin qilib yoq[6.8].

Abdulla Oripovning "Qayrag'och" deb nomlangan ushbu masnaviysida inson hayotining murakkabligi, ayniqsa shoirlik kasbining mashaqqatli, har kimning ko'ngliga birdek yo'l topish naqadar mushkul ish ekanligi borasida so'z yuritiladi.

Shoir Navoiy, G'afur G'ulom, Abdulla Qahhor, Hamid Olimjon kabi adabiyot namoyondalarini o'z ijodida namuna va timsol sifatida e'tirof etadi. Yurtimiz madhiga bitilgan "O'zbekiston" qasidasida ham G'afur G'ulom, Navoiy, Hamid Olimjon, Oybek kabi

buyuk siymolarga murojaat etgani ham bejiz emas. Shuningdek, Oybekka atab yozilgan bag'ishlovi ham ustozlariga bo'lgan cheksiz ehtiromidan dalolat beradi:

Har kalimang ma'rifatning
Ufqida oydek to'lib.
El aro topding sharaf sen,
Ustoz Oybek bo'lib[6.40].

She'riyatda qasida janri ham mavjud bo'lib, bu janr biron mashhur arbob, tarixiy shaxs, qahramon, muhim tarixiy voqeaga madhiya tarzida yozilishi bilan xarakterlidir. Ustoz shoir bu janrda ham o'ziga xos, betakror asarlar yaratishga muvaffaq bo'ldi. Uning vatan madhi kuylangan "O'zbekiston" hamda muqaddas ramzlarimizdan biri bo'lgan bayrog'imizga atalgan "O'zbekiston bayrog'i" kabi qasidaları shular jumlasidandir.

Shoir yaratgan janrlar orasida turli mavzularda yozilgan to'rtliklar ham salmoqli qismni egallaydi:

Tug'ilsang baxt bilan kamol o'shadir,
Tark etsang olamni zavol o'shadir.
Oxir cho'g' tuprog'ing ustiga kelib,
Kimdir yod aylasa iqbol o'shadir[6.27].

Shoir bu bilan dunyoga kelishning o'zi katta baxt, o'lim esa zavol ekanligini, eng muhimi hayotda yaxshi nom qoldirish, inson vafot etgandan keyin odamlar uning yaxshiliklari bilan tilga olishi iqbol ekanligini aytgan. Uning ijodida mana shunday falsafiy ruhda yozilgan to'rtliklar talaygina:

Kimdir farzandiga derdi: - Ey, qo'zim,
Jonu diling bilan eshit bul so'zim.
Qachondir salomga alik olmasdim,
Endi bir alikka zordirman o'zim[6.85].

Nasihat tarzida yozilgan ushbu to'rtlik "Nima eksang, shuni o'rasan" maqolini eslatadi ya'ni dunyo qaytar dunyodir. Inson hayotda yaxshilik qiladimi, yomonlik qiladimi, albatta bir kun javobini beradi. Shoirning bu kabi falsafiy-axloqiy asarlari insonni to'g'rilikka, odamiylikka chorlaydi.

Shoir ijodida marsiya janrini ham uchratamiz. Bizga ma'lumki, marsiya janri arabchada "yig'lash" degan ma'noni bildirib, biron mashhur yoki keksa kishining vafoti munosabati bilan motam, aza tutib, nola, hasrat va qayg'u bilan yoziladigan she'r hisoblanadi. Abdulla Oripov ijodida "Shoir Chorijon marsiyasi", "Sharof Rashidov xotirasiga" kabi marsiya janrining yetuk namunalari mavjud:

Qulluq, Sharof ota, ming bora qulluq,
Boqiy O'zbekiston sizga ham yodgor.
Bugun u istiqlol shavqiga to'liq,
Xizimatingiz eslar takror va takror[6.86].

Shuningdek, shoirning 1994-yilda yozilgan "Vatan" she'ri muxammas janriga oiddir:
Agar do'stlar erur sodiq bir-birin qiyratib bo'lmas,
Agar qilg'il necha fitna alarni ayratib bo'lmas.
Demishlar: moru qushni bir qafasda asratib bo'lmas,

Vatandan ayri ko'ngilni bilingki, yayratib bo'lmas.

Baayni bandi bulbulni chamansiz sayratib bo'lmas[6.99].

Muxammas janrining o'ziga xos xususiyati shuki, birinchi band oxiridagi ikki misra har bir bandda takrorlanadi va she'rning ta'sirchanligini oshiradi.

Abdulla Oripov faqatgina she'r yozish bilan cheklanib qolmasdan, liro-epik turning doston janrida ham bir-biridan go'zal asarlar yaratgan. Uning hajviy usulda yozilgan, hayotdagi qusurlarni fosh etishga qaratilgan va halol va pok yashash g'oyasini ilgari surgan "Ranjkom" dostoni, qiyomat, oxirat, savob, gunoh, jannat va do'zax tushunchalari mazmuni ochib berilgan "Jannatga yo'l" dramatik dostoni, hayot va inson, ilm va o'lim haqidagi fikrlar gavdalantirilgan "Hakim va ajal" dostoni shular jumlasidandir.

Sohibqiron Amir Temur siymosi gavdalantirilgan "Sohibqiron" dramasi ham shoir ijodining rang-barangligidan dalolat beradi. Ma'lumki, Amir Temur dunyoning yarmini egallagan bahodir, buyuk tarixiy shaxs sifatida e'tirof etiladi. Adabiyotda yozuvchi va shoirlarimiz tomonidan uning jang-u jadallari, bosqinchilik yurishlari bayon etilgan asarlar ko'plab uchraydi, ammo Abdulla Oripov "Sohibqiron" dramasini yozishga yangicha usul bilan yondashdi, ya'ni buyuk sarkardaning jangovorlik yurishlarini emas, uning xislatlarini o'z asarida yoritib bergan. Bizga ma'lumki, sohibqiron hayoti davomida "Kuch adolatdadir" shiori ostida janglarga qatnashgan. Tarixiy manbalarda ketirilishicha, Amir Temur adolatli, insofli hukmdor bo'lgan, har qanday vaziyatda ham halol, sofdil insonlarga g'amxo'rlik qilgan, qarindosh-urug'larini e'tibordan chetda qoldirmagan. aksincha, vatanga xiyonat qilgan sotqin, gunohkor kimsalarni hech qachon kechirmagan, qattiq jazolagan, qahri qattiq hukmdor bo'lgan. Abdulla Oripov buyuk sarkardaning shu kabi xislatlarini "Sohibqiron" dramasi yoritib bergan.

Xalqimiz suygan shoir qanday shaklda, qanday usulda ijod qilmasin, hurfikrlilik, istiqloq umidi, vatan farovonligi, xalq ozodligi, jamiyatdagi salbiy ko'rinishlarga ayovsiz munosabat, haqiqatga, adolatga yetishish istagi markaziy o'rinda turadi.

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TELBA POPULIST YOKI SIYOSIY STRATEG?

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqola muallifning subyektiv fikrlarini ifodalagan holda, dunyo geosiyosiy va geoiqtisodiy richagini ushlab turadigan mamlakat – AQShda o'tkazilgan saylov va unda g'olib bo'lib, Qo'shma Shtatlarning 47-prezidentiga aylangan Donald Trampning saylovoldi va undan keyingi harakatlarini umumiy tahlil qiladi. Shuningdek, ushbu maqolada prezidentning dunyo hamjamiyatiga ta'siri va ehtimoliy kutilmalar ham yoritilgan.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Amerika Qo'shma Shtatlari, populizm, strategiya, davlat, demokratiya, respublika, saylov, media, Oq uy, partiya, debat, konstitutsiya, impichment, kongress, palata, senat.*

KIRISH

Yer yuzida bir davlat borki, u dunyodagi har bir davlatga ta'sir kuchiga ega. O'tgan yilning noyabr oyida dunyo geosiyosiy va geoiqtisodiy impulsini ehtimol yaxshigina tebratib yuborgan saylov okean ortida bo'lib o'tdi.

Yo'q, bu Meksika hokimiyatiga kelgan birinchi ayol prezident Klaudiya Sheynbaum yutgan saylov emas, balki Meksikaning jonajon qo'shnisi AQSh deb ataladigan davlatda bir biznesmen g'olib bo'lgan saylov edi.

Bu davlat shunchalik katta ta'sirga egaki, jurnalistlar va siyosiy faollar bu saylovda dunyo davlatlari fuqarolari ham qisman qatnashishi kerakligi haqidagi yarim hazil, yarim chin tahlillarni ko'paytirdi.

Trampning hokimiyat tepasiga qaytishi: populizm, media va shaxsiy ayblovlar

Trampning bu galgi Oq uy kursisi uchun kurashi ehtimol avvalgisidan ancha qiyin kechdi.

Asosiy saylovgacha yetib borolmay, bu dunyo bilan vidolashishiga bor-yo'g'i bir bahya qolgandi.

Axir, unga nisbatan Pensilvaniyada sodir etilgan suiqasdga urinish uning ikkinchi bor "Amerika prezidenti" degan nomga erishish yo'lidagi burilish nuqtasi bo'ldi.

2020-yildan beri dunyo ancha-muncha balogardonliklarni ko'rди. Tabiiyki, mana shu taqdirlar ham Trampning "og'zini shishirdi", "tilini o'tkir qildi".

Bu esa Trampning yana yer yuziga sokinlik va tinchlik qaytarishi haqidagi va'dalariga amerikaliklarni ishontirish uchun muhim omil bo'ldi.

Bu yo'lda u turli raqiblar bilan yuzlashdi. Avvaliga Demokratlar partiyasidan sobiq prezident, keksa siyosatchi Jo Bayden unga raqiblik qildi. 2024-yil 27-iyunda CNN studiyasida o'tkazilgan dastlabki debatning o'zidayoq Tramp raqibini "yeb qo'ydi". Debat davomida Bayden o'zini yomon tutdi, gaplarini yo'qotib, ko'p pauza oldi.

Shundan so'ng demokratlar orasida Bayden nomzodiga shubhalar ortdi. U poygadan chiqdi va o'z o'rnini yordamchisi, sobiq vitse-prezident Kamala Harrisga bo'shatib berdi.

Garchi Bayden ketma-ket omma oldida Harris nomzodiga ovoz berishga chaqirgan bo'lsa-da, prokuror xonimning saylovni yutish imkoniyatlari ancha past edi.

Tramp populistik nutq va bayonotlarga zo'r berdi. Raqibi Harrisning gaplarini manipulyatsiya qilib, ommani o'ziga tortdi.

Okean ortida odamlar saylovlarga va undagi nomzodlarga boshqacha qaraydi.

Amerika prezidenti bo'lish uchun nomzod o'ta bilimli, davlatchilik ko'nikmasiga ega yoki chuqur huquqiy va siyosiy tajribaga ega bo'lishi shart emas.

Xalqni junbushga keltiradigan nuqtani bosish kifoya. Trampning Kanadani Amerikaga qo'shib olish va Grenlandiyani sotib olish haqidagi imperiyalistik nutqlari shunday yondashuvning yorqin dalilidir.

Trampning sud jarayonlari va jinoiy ayblovlar

Maxfiy hujjatlar bilan bog'liq ayblovlar

2023-yil iyun oyida AQSh prokuraturasi Trampga qarshi 37 banddan iborat ayblov xulosasini e'lon qildi. Ushbu ayblovlar orasida maxfiy hujjatlarni noqonuniy saqlash, yolg'on ma'lumot berish va jinoiy til birlashtirish kabi holatlar mavjud edi.

Kapitoliyga hujum bilan bog'liq ayblovlar

2023-yil avgust oyida Tramp 2020-yilgi saylov natijalarini bekor qilishga urinish va 2021-yil 6-yanvar kuni Kapitoliyga qilingan hujum bilan bog'liq holda ayblandi.

"130 ming dollarlik jimlik puli" mojarosi

Aktrisa Stormi Deniels Tramp bilan 2006-yilda golf turnirida tanishganini iddao qiladi. Uning so'zlariga ko'ra, Tramp unga nisbatan zo'ravonlik qilgan. 2016-yilgi prezidentlik saylovi oldidan Tramp Denielsga 130 ming dollar "jimlik puli" to'lagan.

2018-yilda bu to'lov oshkor bo'lgach, Deniels sudga murojaat qilib, Tramp bilan tuzilgan maxfiylik kelishuvini bekor qilishni so'radi. Ushbu mojaro Tramp uchun jiddiy muammo bo'lib qoldi.

Prezident sud qilinishi mumkinmi?

AQSh konstitutsiyasiga ko'ra, agar prezident xiyonat, poraxo'rlik yoki boshqa og'ir jinoyatlarda aybdor deb topilsa, impichment orqali lavozimidan chetlatilishi mumkin.

Tramp shunday mashmashalar bilan Oq uy kursisiga qaytdi. Ammo u avvalgidan ancha radikallashtirildi. Uning Kanada, Meksika va Xitoy tovarlariga qo'shimcha boj joriy qilish va Panama kanalini Amerikaga qaytarish haqidagi bayonotlari dunyoni yangi "iqtisodiy urush" arafasiga olib kelishi mumkin.

Xulosa

U keldi. Nima deb keldi? "Urushni to'xtataman" deb keldi. Garchi u mamlakati manfaatlariga zid bo'lgan urushlarni to'xtatishiga ishonish qiyin bo'lsa-da, baribir umid qilamiz.

Qani ko'ramiz, uning sinov muddati boshlandi.

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TOURISM INTEGRATION IN UZBEKISTAN: THE ROLE OF ADOPTED INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS

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Abstract: *Uzbekistan's tourism sector is experiencing rapid growth, fueled by its rich cultural heritage and historical sites. To ensure sustainable development and attract international tourists, the country has been actively adopting international tourism standards. This article explores the role of these standards in enhancing tourism integration in Uzbekistan. It examines how the adoption of standards related to service quality, safety, sustainability, and accessibility is impacting the sector.*

Keywords: *Uzbekistan, tourism, international standards, integration, service quality, sustainability, accessibility, safety, development.*

INTRODUCTION

Uzbekistan, a land steeped in history and culture, is rapidly emerging as a popular tourist destination. The country's iconic Silk Road cities, such as Samarkand, Bukhara, and Khiva, offer a unique glimpse into the past, attracting visitors from around the globe. Recognizing the potential of tourism as a driver of economic growth and cultural exchange, the Uzbek government has been actively promoting the sector. A key strategy in this endeavor is the adoption and implementation of international tourism standards.

International standards provide a framework for ensuring quality, safety, and sustainability in the tourism industry. They help to build trust among tourists, improve service delivery, and protect the environment. By aligning with these standards, Uzbekistan aims to enhance its competitiveness in the global tourism market and create a more attractive and responsible destination. This article will look at how adopting these standards helps Uzbekistan's tourism grow and fit into the global tourism world. [1]

The Importance of International Standards in Tourism:

International tourism standards are essential for several reasons. Firstly, they establish a common language and set of expectations for tourism businesses and consumers. This helps to ensure consistency in service quality and builds confidence among tourists. Secondly, standards promote safety and security, which are crucial for attracting visitors. Thirdly, they encourage sustainable tourism practices, minimizing the negative impact of tourism on the environment and local communities. Finally, standards can improve accessibility for tourists with disabilities, making tourism more inclusive.

For developing countries like Uzbekistan, adopting international standards can be a powerful tool for enhancing tourism competitiveness. It can help them to

overcome barriers to entry in the global market and attract more international tourists. Standards can also help to improve the efficiency and productivity of tourism businesses, leading to economic growth and job creation.

Key Areas of Standard Adoption in Uzbekistan:

Service Quality:

Standards related to hotel accommodation, restaurant services, and tour operations are being implemented to ensure consistent and high-quality experiences for tourists. This includes training tourism staff in customer service, language skills, and industry best practices. For example, hotel classification systems based on international standards are being used to provide tourists with clear and reliable information about the quality of accommodation. The government is also working to improve the quality of guides and tour operators, ensuring that they are knowledgeable and professional.

Safety and Security:

Standards related to food safety, transportation safety, and emergency response are being implemented to protect tourists from harm. This includes ensuring that restaurants and food vendors comply with hygiene regulations, that transportation services are safe and reliable, and that emergency services are readily available.

Sustainability:

Standards related to environmental protection, waste management, and responsible tourism practices are being adopted to minimize the negative impact of tourism on the environment. This includes promoting eco-friendly tourism activities, reducing waste and pollution, and protecting natural resources.

Accessibility:

Standards related to accessible tourism are being implemented to make tourism more inclusive for people with disabilities. This includes ensuring that tourist sites, hotels, and transportation services are accessible to people with mobility impairments, visual impairments, and hearing impairments. [2]

The adoption of international tourism standards is having a positive impact on Uzbekistan's tourism sector.

Increased Tourist Arrivals:

By improving service quality, safety, and sustainability, Uzbekistan is becoming a more attractive destination for international tourists. The adoption of standards is helping to build trust among tourists and enhance the country's reputation.

Enhanced Sustainability:

The adoption of sustainable tourism practices is helping to protect the environment and preserve Uzbekistan's cultural heritage. This is ensuring that tourism benefits local communities and future generations.

Economic Growth:

The growth of the tourism sector is creating jobs and generating revenue for the country, as well as, contributing to economic development and poverty reduction.

Challenges and Opportunities: Implementation Challenges:

Implementing standards requires investment in training, infrastructure, and technology. There may be resistance from some tourism businesses that are not accustomed to following international standards. It is vital to have clear rules and ensure they are followed.

Awareness and Training Raising: Raising awareness about the importance of standards among tourism businesses and consumers is crucial. Providing training to tourism staff on how to implement standards is also essential.

Opportunities:

The growth of the tourism sector presents opportunities for entrepreneurship and innovation. Uzbekistan can leverage its unique cultural heritage and natural attractions to develop niche tourism products. The nation can utilize its location to become a hub for tourism in Central Asia. There is a large opportunity to increase digital tourism. [3]

Conclusion:

The adoption of international tourism standards is playing a vital role in enhancing tourism integration in Uzbekistan. While challenges remain, the government's commitment to promoting tourism and implementing standards is paving the way for sustainable growth and development. Uzbekistan's journey towards becoming a leading tourism destination is a testament to the power of international collaboration and the importance of adopting best practices. By continuing to embrace international standards, Uzbekistan can unlock its full tourism potential and create a brighter future for its people.

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HOZIRGI O‘ZBEK ASRIDA TADBIRKOR QIYOFASI TIMSOLIGA TA’SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR

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Abstract: *Great attention is paid to the role of entrepreneurship in the economic development of societies all over the world. Understanding the factors that influence the image of an entrepreneur is essential to creating an ecosystem that encourages entrepreneurial activity. This article studies the factors that shape the perception and image of entrepreneurs in the modern Uzbek age. By analyzing social, cultural and economic factors, this study sheds light on the contextual elements that shape the image of an entrepreneur in Uzbekistan.*

Аннотация: *Роль предпринимательства в экономическом развитии обществ уделяется большое внимание во всем мире. Понимание факторов, влияющих на воплощение имиджа предпринимателя, имеет решающее значение для создания экосистемы, стимулирующей предпринимательскую деятельность. В данной статье исследуются факторы, формирующие восприятие и образ предпринимателей в современном узбекском веке. Анализируя социальные, культурные и экономические факторы, данное исследование проливает свет на контекстуальные элементы, формирующие образ предпринимателя в Узбекистане.*

Annotatsiya: *Jamiyatlarning iqtisodiy rivojlanishida tadbirkorlikning roliga butun dunyoda katta e’tibor qaratilmoqda. Tadbirkor imidjining timsoliga ta’sir etuvchi omillarni tushunish tadbirkorlik faoliyatini rag’batlantiradigan ekotizimni yaratish uchun juda muhimdir. Ushbu maqolada zamonaviy o‘zbek asrida tadbirkorlar idroki va tasvirini shakllantiruvchi omillar o‘rganiladi. Ijtimoiy, madaniy va iqtisodiy omillarni tahlil qilish orqali ushbu tadqiqot O‘zbekistonda tadbirkor imidjini shakllantiruvchi kontekstual elementlarga oydinlik kiritadi.*

Kalit soʻzlar: *Iqtisodiyot, tadbirkorlik, madaniy omillar, rivojlanish, innovatsiya, ijtimoiy meʼyorlar, ijodkorlik, gender roller, hamkorlik, murabbiylik.*

KIRISH

Tadbirkorlik iqtisodiy o‘shish, innovatsiyalar va yangi ish o‘rinlari yaratishning harakatlantiruvchi kuchi sifatida e’tirof etilgan. Tadbirkor qiyofasining muvaffaqiyatli gavdalanishi turli omillarga, jumladan, madaniyat, ta’lim, davlat siyosati, texnologik taraqqiyot va ijtimoiy me’yorlarga bog‘liq. Ushbu maqola

zamonaviy o'zbek asrida tadbirkor imidjini shakllantiruvchi omillarni o'rganishga qaratilgan.

21-asr O'zbekistonda tadbirkor imidjiga ta'sir etuvchi madaniy omillar: Ushbu maqola zamonaviy O'zbekiston sharoitida tadbirkorlarning idrokiga ta'sir etuvchi madaniy omillarni ko'rib chiqadi. Tadqiqot madaniy e'tiqodlar, ijtimoiy me'yorlar, tarixiy omillar va iqtisodiy tuzilmalar tadbirkorlar imidjini va ularning mamlakat rivojiga umumiy hissasini qanday shakllantirishini o'rganadi. Ushbu madaniy ta'sirlarni tushunish orqali siyosatchilar, tadqiqotchilar va tadbirkorlar innovatsiyalarni, iqtisodiy o'sishni va ijtimoiy taraqqiyotni rag'batlantiradigan tadbirkorlik muhitini rivojlantirish uchun birgalikda ishlashlari mumkin.

Tadbirkorlik iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish, yangi ish o'rinlari yaratish va jamiyat taraqqiyotida hal qiluvchi rol o'ynaydi. Bozor iqtisodiyotiga o'tish davrida Markaziy Osiyo davlati bo'lgan O'zbekistonda tadbirkorlar idroki va imidjiga madaniy omillarning ta'sirini baholash juda muhim. Jamiyatning tavakkal qilishga bo'lgan munosabati, oldingi biznes tashabbuslarining obro'si yoki tarixiy omillar kabi madaniy jihatdan o'rnashgan e'tiqodlar tadbirkorlarni idrok etish va jamiyat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlashga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin. Shu sababli, ushbu madaniy jihatlarni tushunish mamlakatda tadbirkorlikni rivojlantiradigan va rag'batlantiradigan muhitni yaratish uchun juda muhimdir.

Madaniy e'tiqod va an'analar: An'ana va urf-odatlar bilan chuqur ildiz otgan o'zbek madaniyati tadbirkorlarning idrokiga ta'sir qiladi. Tarixan muvaffaqiyat qishloq xo'jaligi va savdo kabi o'rnatilgan kasblar bilan bog'liq. Bu tafakkur tadbirkorlik bilan shug'ullanayotgan tavakkalchi shaxslarga nisbatan madaniy tarafkashlikni keltirib chiqardi. Ish xavfsizligi va barqarorlikni tadbirkorlik harakatlaridan ustun qo'yadigan madaniy e'tiqodlar rivojlanayotgan startap ekotizimining rivojlanishiga to'sqinlik qiladi. Bundan tashqari, an'anaviy gender rollari va stereotiplar ko'pincha madaniy umidlar tufayli qo'shimcha qiyinchiliklarga duch keladigan tadbirkor ayollarning idrokiga yanada ta'sir qilishi mumkin.

Pul va moddiy muvaffaqiyatni idrok etish: Boylik va moddiy muvaffaqiyatga bo'lgan madaniy munosabat ham tadbirkorlar qiyofasini shakllantiradi. Sovet davridagi tenglik qadriyatlarini ta'siri hamon saqlanib qolgan O'zbekistonda boylik to'planishiga shubha va hatto norozilik bilan qarash mumkin. Moliyaviy farovonlikka intilayotgan tadbirkorlar jamiyatda skeptitsizmga duch kelishlari yoki faqat shaxsiy manfaatlar bilan shug'ullanuvchi shaxslar sifatida qabul qilinishi mumkin. Bu idrok tadbirkorlik ruhi va innovatsiyalarni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan sa'y-harakatlarga putur etkazadi.

Tarixiy kontekst: O'zbekistonning tarixiy taraqqiyoti, jumladan, sovet hokimiyati va markaziy rejalashtirish davrlari tadbirkorlar idrokiga ta'sir qilishda davom etmoqda. Sovet hokimiyati davrida tadbirkorlik asosan davlat nazoratidagi iqtisodlar foydasiga bostirildi. Natijada, ko'plab shaxslar tadbirkorlikni noqonuniy faoliyat yoki korrupsiya bilan bog'lashmoqda. Ushbu tarixiy omillar merosini e'tirof

etish tadbirkorlarning ijobiy imidjini shakllantirish va ularning mamlakat iqtisodiy rivojlanishidagi muhim rolini rag'batlantirishda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Davlat tomonidan qo'llab-quvvatlash va siyosat: O'zbekistonning bozor iqtisodiyotiga o'tishga intilishi qo'llab-quvvatlovchi siyosat va institutlarni talab qiladi. Ushbu siyosatni shakllantirishda madaniy omillar muhim rol o'ynaydi. Siyosatchilar tadbirkorlik va innovatsiyalarni qadrlaydigan, taraqqiyotga to'sqinlik qilishi mumkin bo'lgan madaniy e'tiqod va me'yorlarni e'tirof etish va ularga e'tibor qaratadigan muhitni yaratishi kerak. Davlat jamiyatning turli qatlamlarini, jumladan, yoshlar va ayollarni o'qitish va jalb qilish, tadbirkorlikni istalgan martaba yo'li sifatida rag'batlantirish uchun dasturlar ishlab chiqishi mumkin.

Ta'lim va ko'nikmalar: Jismoniy shaxslarning ta'lim darajasi va ko'nikmalari ularning tadbirkorlik haqidagi tasavvuriga sezilarli darajada ta'sir qiladi. O'zbekistonda ta'lim tizimida tadbirkorlik ta'limini rivojlantirish, o'quvchilar o'rtasida ijodkorlik va innovatsiyalarni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan jiddiy islohotlar amalga oshirildi. Tadbirkorlik kurslari, inkubatorlar, ustozlik dasturlari tashkil etilib, navqiron avlodning tadbirkorlik faoliyatini boshlashi uchun zarur ko'nikma va bilimlar bilan ta'minlandi. Ta'lim yo'nalishidagi bunday o'zgarishlar tadbirkor imidjini idrok etish va timsoliga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatdi.

Hukumat siyosati: Davlat siyosati va ularning tadbirkorlik faoliyatini qo'llab-quvvatlashi tadbirkor imidjini shakllantirishda asosiy rol o'ynaydi. O'zbekiston hukumati soliq imtiyozlari, biznesni ro'yxatdan o'tkazish jarayonlarini soddalashtirish, yangi boshlanuvchilarni tashkil etish va ko'paytirish uchun mablag'lardan foydalanish kabi tashabbuslarni amalga oshirdi. Bu siyosatlar tadbirkorlikka intiluvchanlar uchun qulay muhit yaratib, tadbirkorlik haqida ijobiy tasavvur uyg'otadi va ko'proq shaxslarni tadbirkorlik faoliyati bilan shug'ullanishga undaydi.

Texnologik yutuqlar: Texnologik taraqqiyot O'zbekistonda tadbirkorlarning yangi zoti paydo bo'lishini tezlashtirdi. Raqamli platformalar, elektron tijorat va raqamli marketingning mavjudligi va ulardan foydalanish imkoniyatining ortib borishi tadbirkorlik imkoniyatlarini demokratlashtirib, tadbirkorlarning dinamik va texnologiyani yaxshi biladigan shaxslar imidjini kuchaytirdi. Bundan tashqari, texnologiyalardan foydalanish tadbirkorlarga geografik cheklovlarni yengib o'tish va global bozorlarga chiqish imkonini berdi, tadbirkorlarning idroki va timsolini oshirdi.

Ijtimoiy tarmoq va qo'llab-quvvatlash: Tadbirkorlar uchun mavjud ijtimoiy tarmoq va qo'llab-quvvatlash ularning imidjini sezilarli darajada shakllantiradi. O'zbekistonda tengdoshlar bilan hamkorlik, murabbiylik va bilim almashishni rivojlantirishga qaratilgan tadbirkorlik hamjamiyatlari, tarmoqlari va qo'llab-quvvatlovchi tashkilotlarning o'sishi kuzatildi. Bu aloqalar hissiy qo'llab-quvvatlash, o'rganish imkoniyatlari va resurslardan foydalanish imkonini beradi, tadbirkorlar imidjining timsoliga ijobiy hissa qo'shadi.

Xulosa:

Hozirgi o'zbek asrida tadbirkor obrazining gavdalanishiga ijtimoiy, madaniy va iqtisodiy omillar uyg'unligi ta'sir ko'rsatadi. O'zgarib borayotgan madaniy munosabatlar, rivojlanayotgan ta'lim tizimi, qulay davlat siyosati, texnologik taraqqiyot va qo'llab-quvvatlovchi tarmoqlar tadbirkor haqidagi tasavvurni o'zgartirib, O'zbekistonda jonli tadbirkorlik ekotizimiga olib kelmoqda. Ushbu omillarni tushunish siyosatchilar, o'qituvchilar va manfaatdor tomonlar uchun mamlakatda tadbirkorlik o'sishini yanada kuchaytirish, iqtisodiy rivojlanish va innovatsiyalarni rag'batlantirish uchun juda muhimdir.

XXI asr o'zbek jamiyatida madaniy omillar tadbirkorlar imidjiga, ularning iqtisodiy taraqqiyotga qo'shgan hissasiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. Ushbu madaniy ta'sirlarni tushunish siyosatchilar va tadbirkorlikni ijobiy idrok etishni rag'batlantirishga intilayotgan manfaatdor tomonlar uchun juda muhimdir. Tadbirkorlikka to'sqinlik qilayotgan madaniy qarama-qarshiliklar va me'yorlarni tan olish va ularga qarshi chiqish orqali O'zbekiston tavakkalchilik, innovatsiyalar va tadbirkorlik tashabbuslarini qo'llab-quvvatlovchi muhitni rivojlantirishi mumkin. Oxir oqibat, gullab-yashnayotgan tadbirkorlik ekotizimi mamlakatda iqtisodiy o'sishni va ijtimoiy taraqqiyotni oshirish uchun potentsialga ega.

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YAPON TILSHUNOSLIGIDA IBORA VA MAQOLLARNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI

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O'zDJTU stajor-o'qituvchisi

Maqol matni tilshunoslikda shaxsi umumlashgan gap hisoblanadi. Xalq maqollari tarixi o'nlab asrlar bilan o'lchanadi. Xalq maqollarining mazmun ko'lami inson hayotining turli sohalarini qamrab oladi. Inson hayotidagi voqea-hodisalarning cheki yo'q ekan, maqollar mazmuni chegarasini ham o'lchab bo'lmaydi. Maishiy hayotdagi kichik bir e'tiborga arzimaydigandek ko'rinuvchi lavhalardan tortib, chuqur falsafiy mushohada ifodasigacha maqollar mazmunida o'z aksini topgan. Maqol va masallar har bir xalq og'zaki ijodining katta qismini tashkil qiladi. Maqolarda avlod-ajdodlarning hayotiy tajribalari, jamiyatga munosabati, tarixi, ruhiy holati, etik va estetik tuyg'ulari, iztiroblari, ijobiy fazilatlari mujassamlashgan bo'ladi. Asrlar mobaynida xalq orasida sayqallanib, ixcham va sodda poetik shaklga kelgan bo'ladi.

Maqolar mavzu jihatdan nihoyatda boy va xilma-xilligini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Vatan, mehnat, ilmhunar, do'stlik, ahillik, donolik, hushyorlik, til va nutq madaniyati, sevgi va muhabbat kabi mavzularda, shuningdek, salbiy hislatlar xususida rangbarang maqollar yaratilgan.

Har bir xalqning o'z maqol, matal, frazalari bo'lgani kabi: Yapon tilida ham turg'un birikmalar, iboralar 慣用句 (かんようく—kanyouku) deb ataladi. Maqollar esa 諺 (ことわざ—kotowaza) deyiladi. Bundan tashqari yapon tilida 四字熟語 (よじじゅくご—yojigukugo)⁵⁹ deb ataluvchi birikmalar bo'lib, ular ham maqol, ham birikma shaklida kelishi mumkin. An'anaviy yapon madaniyatining ko'pchiligi qishloq xo'jaligiga bog'liq bo'lganligi sababli, ko'plab yapon maqollari qishloq xo'jaligi urf-odatlar va amaliyotlaridan kelib chiqqan holda yaratilgan. Ko'pgina xilma-xil iboralar Xitoy falsafasidan kelib chiqqan bo'lib, Xitoy ananaviy maqol va matallari bilan o'xshash bo'lib ko'rinadi. Umuman tarixga nazar tashlaydigan bo'lsak, yaponlarning tilidan tortib urf odatlarigacha oxshashdir. An'anaviy yapon madaniyati va tilidagi hodisalar qishloq xo'jaligiga bog'liq bo'lganligi sababli, ko'plab yapon maqollari qishloq xo'jaligi urf-odatlar va amaliyotlaridan kelib chiqqan. Ba'zilar Yapon maqollari alifbo tartibida joylashtirilgan.

Yaponlar odatda maqollardan qisqartirilgan shaklda foydalanadilar, ko'pincha qisqartirish uchun umumiy iboralarning birinchi qismiga ishora qiladilar. Masalan, ingliz tilidagi maqollarda odatda ko'p so'zli iboralar mavjud (Killing two birds with one stone), yapon tilida esa xitoy tilidan kirib kelgan va Isseki nichō (bitta tosh ikkita qush) shaklida bo'lib, so'zini ixcham ravishda yetkazadi. Maqollarning ishlatilishi yapon tilini ta'sirchanligini oshiradi, dalillarni yapon animatsiyasi va manga-larida topish mumkin, ammo ular yangiliklar va madaniy dasturlarda va ko'pgina fantastika asarlarida ham

⁵⁹ Mori, yapon tili ("3-son. Modallik. Tokio, Ivanami). - 2000

uchraydi. Har bir xalqda bo‘lgani kabi asrlar davomida shakllanib kelgan maqol va matallar yapon xalqida ham yetarlicha topiladi. Nafaqat yetarlicha topiladi balki, boshqa xalqlara uchratish qiyin bo‘lgan maqollar va ibratli gaplarni uchratishimiz mumkin. Asrlar davomida shakllanib sayqal topib hozirgi ko‘rinishda paydo bo‘ladi.

「猿も木から落ちる」⁶⁰

(Sarumo kikara ochiru)Hatto maymun ham daraxtdan yiqilib turadi .

「石の上にも三年」⁶¹

(Ishino uenimo sannen) “tosh ustida 3yil” bu maqol insonni qat’iy va sabrli bo‘lishga, boshlagan ishini oxirigacha yetkazib qo‘yishga undaydi. Toshga o‘tirganda sovuq bo‘ladi, lekin sekin sekin isiydi. Agar biron nima qiyin bo‘lsa ham sabr bilan davom ettirilsa albatta uddalash mumkin. O‘zbek tilida ham Sabrning tagi sariq oltin shaklida ishlatiladi.

「鬼の目にも涙」⁶²

(Oni no me ni mo namida)toshyurak, yomon odamdan ham ko‘z yosh chiqadi.

猫の首に鈴を付ける⁶³ (Nekono kubini suzuwo kakeru) mushuk bo‘yniga qo‘ng‘iroq ilish. Rejalashtirish jarayonida hammasi yaxshi deb ishlarni o‘z bo‘yniga olib, amalga oshirish vaqtida bajaruvchining bo‘lmasligi haqida aytishda ishlatiladi.Ma’suliyatni o‘z bo‘yniga olish.

Har bir xalqning maqollari bilan tanishish orqali ularni yaratgan xalq haqidagi g‘oyamizni boyitamiz. Maqollarda xalqning milliy xususiyatlari g‘ayrioddiy ekspressivlik va o‘z-o‘zidan paydo bo‘ladi. Shu bilan birga, ular turli xil xalqlarni bir-biriga bog‘laydigan va birlashtiradigan umumiy narsalarni aniq ifoda etadilar.

Barcha xalqlarda bo‘lgani kabi,Yapon xalqining lingvistik ijodida maqol va matallar muhim o‘rin tutadi. Ular uning ma’naviy madaniyatining organik qismini tashkil qiladi. Agar Yaponiya va uning xalqi bilan yaqinroq tanishishni istasak, uning matal va maqollarini o‘rganish orqali ko‘proq bilishimiz mumkin. Maqol va iboralar yaponlar hayotining muhim qismi bo‘lib kundalik hayotda ham, kundalik suhbatda ham, ommaviy nutqda, matbuotda, adabiyotda ham keng qo‘llaniladi deya olamiz.

Yaponiyaliklar maqollarni kundalik hayotda ishlatishni yaxshi ko‘radilar, ko‘pincha ularni hazil bilan ishlatishadi.Qadimgi Yapon xalqi madaniyati asosan qishloq sharoitida paydo bo‘lganligi sababli, uning ko‘plab umumiy an’analari ham qishloqdan kelib chiqqan. Vaqt o‘tishi bilan xalq maqollari va urf-odatlar har bir Yapon tomonidan ma'lum bo‘lgan keng tarqalgan maqollarga aylandi va ommalashdi. Ba'zilar buddist monastirlarida yaratilgan, boshqalari Yapon falsafasidan ilhomlangan holda yaratilgan.

Yapon maqollarining aksariyati yapon falsafasi, madaniyati, tabiati yoki yapon xalqining xulq-atvoriga ishora qiladi.

Maqollar Yapon madaniyatida nihoyatda muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Avloddan-avlodga o‘tib, ular kundalik hayotning deyarli barcha jabhalariga qamrab oladi. Ba'zi yapon ibora va

⁶⁰ kotowaza-dictionary.jp

⁶¹ kotowaza-dictionary.jp

⁶² imidas.jp

⁶³ imidas.jp

maqollari o'z ekvivalentlariga ega bo'lsa, ba'zilari esa faqatgina Yapon madaniy konteksti uchun xosdir va ularning ma'nosi faqat yaponlarga tushunarli. Ko'pgina Yapon maqollari to'g'ridan-to'g'ri umuman hayotga ishora qiladi. Yapon xalqi ulardan metaforik tarzda avloddan-avlodga o'tib kelayotgan eski tamoyillarni, donolikni va har bir avlodning tajribasi bo'lgan hayotiy haqiqatlarni har zamonda etkazish uchun foydalanadi. Yaponiyaga tashrif buyurishni rejalashtirgan yoki hatto yapon madaniyatiga ozgina qiziqqan har bir kishi, albatta, Yapon maqollarida uning xalqi haqida ma'lumot topadi. Yaponiya siyosiy elitasi ko'pincha o'zlarining rasmiy chiqishlarida ham maqol va matallarga murojaat qilishadi.

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BIR O'ZGARUVCHILIK FUNKSIYA VA ULARNING BERILISH USULLARI.

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada bir o'zgaruvchili funktsiyaning asosiy tushunchalari va ularning berilish usullari haqida so'z yuritiladi. Funktsiya tushunchasining matematik ahamiyati, uni turli usullarda ifodalash imkoniyatlari hamda amaliyotdagi qo'llanilishi tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek, funktsiyaning grafigi, analitik, jadval va so'z bilan berilish usullari o'rganilib, har bir usulning afzallik va kamchiliklari yoritiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Funksiya, bir o'zgaruvchili funktsiya, funktsiya grafigi, analitik berilish, jadval usuli, so'z bilan ifodalash, matematik tahlil.*

ОДНОПЕРЕМЕННАЯ ФУНКЦИЯ И СПОСОБЫ ЕЁ ЗАДАНИЯ

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Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматриваются основные понятия однопеременной функции и способы её задания. Анализируется математическая значимость понятия функции, различные методы её представления, а также её практическое применение. Изучаются графическое, аналитическое, табличное и словесное представления функций, раскрываются преимущества и недостатки каждого метода.*

Ключевые Слова: *Функция, однопеременная функция, график функции, аналитическое задание, табличный метод, словесное описание, математический анализ.*

SINGLE-VARIABLE FUNCTION AND ITS REPRESENTATION METHODS

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Annotation: *This article discusses the fundamental concepts of single-variable functions and their representation methods. The mathematical significance of the function concept, various ways of expressing functions, and their practical applications are analyzed. The graphical, analytical, tabular, and verbal representations of functions are examined, highlighting the advantages and disadvantages of each method.*

Keywords: *Function, single-variable function, function graph, analytical representation, tabular method, verbal description, mathematical analysis.*

Funksiya tushunchasi o'quvchiga o'rta maktab matematika kursidan ma'lum. Shuni e'tiborga olib funksiya haqidagi dastlabki ma'lumotlarni qisqaroq bayon etishni lozim topdik.

Aytaylik, $X \subset R$, $Y \subset R$ to'plamlar berilgan bo'lib, x va y o'zgaruvchilar mos ravishda shu to'plamlarda o'zgarsin: $x \in X$, $y \in Y$.

1-ta'rif. Agar X to'plamdagi har bir x songa biror f qoidaga ko'ra Y to'plamdan bitta y son mos qo'yilgan bo'lsa, X to'plamda funksiya berilgan (aniqlangan) deyiladi va

$$f: x \rightarrow y \text{ yoki } y = f(x)$$

kabi belgilanadi. Bunda X – funksiyaning aniqlanish to'plami (cohasi), Y – funksiyaning o'zgarish to'plami (cohasi) deyiladi. x – erkli o'zgaruvchi yoki funksiya argumenti, y esa erksiz o'zgaruvchi yoki funksiya deyiladi.

Misollar. 1. $X = (-\infty, +\infty)$, $Y = (0, +\infty)$ bo'lib, f qoida

$$f: x \rightarrow y = x^2 + 1$$

bo'lsin. Bu holda har bir $x \in X$ ga bitta $x^2 + 1 \in Y$ mos qo'yilib,

$$y = x^2 + 1$$

funksiyaga ega bo'lamiz.

10. Har bir ratsional songa 1 ni, har bir irratsional songa 0 ni mos qo'yish natijasida funksiya hosil bo'ladi. Odatda, bu Dirixle funksiyasi deyilib, u $D(x)$ kabi belgilanadi:

$$D(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{agar } x \text{ ratsional son bo'lsa,} \\ 0, & \text{agar } x \text{ irratsional son bo'lsa.} \end{cases}$$

Shunday qilib, $y = f(x)$ funksiya uchta: X to'plam, Y to'plam va har bir $x \in X$ ga bitta $y \in Y$ ni mos qo'yuvchi f qoidaning berilishi bilan aniqlanar ekan.

Faraz qilaylik, $y = f(x)$ funksiya $X \subset R$ to'plamda berilgan bo'lsin. $x_0 \in X$ nuqtaga mos keluvchi y_0 miqdor $y = f(x)$ funksiyaning $x = x_0$ nuqtadagi xususiy qiymati deyiladi va $f(x_0) = y_0$ kabi belgilanadi.

Tekislikda Dekart koordinatalar sistemasini olamiz. Tekislikdagi $(x, f(x))$ nuqtalardan iborat ushbu

$$\{(x, f(x))\} = \{(x, f(x)) \mid x \in X, f(x) \in Y\}$$

to'plam $y = f(x)$ funksiyaning grafigi deyiladi

Masalan,

$$y = x^2 - 1 \quad (x \in X = [-2, 2])$$

funksiyaning grafigi 1-chizmada tasvirlangan

1-chizma.

Funksiya ta'rifidagi f qoida turlicha bo'lishi mumkin.

a) Ko'pincha x va y o'zgaruvchilar orasidagi bog'lanish formulalar yordamida ifodalanadi. Bu funksiyaning analitik usulda berilishi deyiladi. Masalan,

$$y = \sqrt{1 - x^2}$$

funksiya analitik usulda berilgan bo'lib, uning aniqlanish to'plami

$$X = \{x \in R \mid -1 \leq x \leq 1\} = [-1, 1]$$

bo'ladi.

x va y o'zgaruvchilar orasidagi bog'lanish quyidagi formulalar yordamida berilgan bo'lsin:

$$y = f(x) = \begin{cases} -1, & \text{agar } x < 0 \text{ bo'lsa,} \\ 0, & \text{agar } x = 0 \text{ bo'lsa,} \\ 1, & \text{agar } x > 0 \text{ bo'lsa,} \end{cases}$$

Bu funksiyaning aniqlanish to'plami $X = R$ bo'lib, qiymatlar to'plami esa $Y = \{-1, 0, 1\}$ bo'ladi. Odatda bu funksiya $y = \text{sgn } x$ kabi belgilanadi. [2, p. 32, vi]

b) Ba'zi hollarda $x \in X$, $y \in Y$ o'zgaruvchilar orasidagi bog'lanish jadval orqali bo'lishi mumkin. Masalan, kun davomida havo haroratini kuzatganimizda, t_1 vaqtda havo harorati T_1 , t_2 vaqtda havo harorati T_2 va h.k. bo'lsin. Natijada quyidagi jadval hosil bo'ladi.

t - vaqt	t_1	t_2	t_3	..	t_n
T	T_1	T_2	T_3	..	T_n

harorat					
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Bu jadval t vaqt bilan havo harorati T orasidagi bogʻlanish-ni ifodalaydi, bunda t – argument, T esa t ning funksiyasi boʻladi.

v) x va y oʻzgaruvchilar orasidagi bogʻlanish tekislikda biror egri chiziq orqali ham ifodalanishi mumkin (2-chizma).

2- chizma.

Masalan, 2-chizmada tasvirlangan L egri chiziq berilgan boʻlsin. Aytaylik, $[a, b]$ segmentdagi har bir nuqtadan oʻtkazilgan perpendikulyar L chiziqni faqat bitta nuqtada kessin. $\forall x \in [a, b]$ nuqtadan perpendikulyar chiqarib, uning L chiziq bilan kesishish nuqtasini topamiz. Olingan x nuqtaga kesishish nuqtasining ordinatasi y ni mos qoʻyamiz. Natijada har bir $x \in [a, b]$ ga bitta y mos qoʻyilib, funksiya hosil boʻladi. Bunda x bilan y orasidagi bogʻlanishni berilgan L egri chiziq bajaradi.

Aytaylik, $f_1(x)$ funksiya $X_1 \subset R$ toʻplamda, $f_2(x)$ funksiya esa $X_2 \subset R$ toʻplamda aniqlangan boʻlsin.

Agar

$$1) X_1 = X_2,$$

$$2) \forall x \in X_1 \text{ da } f_1(x) = f_2(x),$$

boʻlsa, $f_1(x)$ hamda $f_2(x)$ funksiyalar oʻzaro teng deyiladi va $f_1(x) = f_2(x)$ kabi belgilanadi.

Matematikada funksiya – bu oʻzgaruvchilarning oʻzaro bogʻliqligini ifodalovchi asosiy tushuncha hisoblanadi. Funksiya berishning bir necha usullari mavjud boʻlib, ular turli matematik modellarda va real hayotiy masalalarda ishlatiladi.

1. Algebraik usul

Bu usulda funksiya matematik formula yordamida beriladi. Funksiya argumenti (x) bilan ifodalanib, uning natijasi ($f(x)$) hisoblab chiqiladi.

Misol:

$$f(x) = 2x + 5$$

Bu yerda har qanday x qiymati uchun $f(x)$ ni hisoblash mumkin.

Qo'llanilishi:

- Matematik hisob-kitoblarda
- Algebraik tahlillarda
- Fizika va muhandislik modellarida

2. Jadval usul

Funksiya berilgan argumentlar to'plami uchun qiymatlar jadvali ko'rinishida ifodalanadi. Bu usul ko'proq tajribaviy ma'lumotlar asosida foydalaniladi.

Qo'llanilishi:

- Statistik ma'lumotlarni tahlil qilishda
- Eksperimental natijalarni ifodalashda
- Dasturlash va sun'iy intellektda

3. Grafik usul

Funksiya koordinata tekisligida grafik shaklida tasvirlanadi. Grafik orqali funksiya xatti-harakatini vizual tushunish osonlashadi.

Misol:

Agar $f(x) = x^2$ bo'lsa, uning grafigi parabola shaklida bo'ladi.

Qo'llanilishi:

- Funksiya o'sish yoki kamayishini tahlil qilishda
- Ekstremum va nollik nuqtalarini topishda
- Harakat va iqtisodiy model tahlillarida

4. So'zli (matnli) usul

Bu usulda funksiya matematik formula yoki grafik bilan emas, balki so'z orqali tushuntiriladi.

Misol:

“Har bir avtomobil harakatlanganda bosib o'tgan masofa vaqtning kvadratiga proporsional bo'ladi.”

Bu so'zlar orqali $s(t) = at^2$ funksiyasini tavsiflash mumkin.

Qo'llanilishi:

- Nazariy tushuntirishlarda
- Matematik model yaratishda
- Fizik hodisalarni ifodalashda

4. So'zli (matnli) usul

Funksiya turli usullar bilan ifodalanishi mumkin va har biri o'ziga xos ahamiyatga ega. Formula usuli aniq hisob-kitob uchun qulay, jadval usuli eksperimental natijalarga asoslanadi, grafik usuli vizual analiz imkonini beradi, so'zli usul esa matematik modelni tushuntirish uchun ishlatiladi.

Har bir usul real hayotiy masalalarda ishlatilishi mumkin va darslik yozishda barcha usullarni ketma-ketlik bilan tushuntirish foydalanuvchilarga oson tushunish imkonini beradi.

Mavzuning c# dasturlash tiliga tatbiqi:

Misol:

Berilgan bir o'zgaruvchili funksiya qiymatini hisoblang. Foydalanivchi funksiya uchun argumentning qiymatini kiritishi kerak.

$$f(x)=x^2+3x-5$$

Dastur kodi:

```
using System;
```

```
class Dastur
```

```
{
```

```
static void Main()
```

```
{
```

```
// Foydalanuvchidan x qiymatini olish
```

```
Console.Write("x ning qiymatini kiriting: ");
```

```
double x = Convert.ToDouble(Console.ReadLine());
```

```
// Funksiya hisoblash
```

```
double natija = Math.Pow(x, 2) + 3 * x - 5;
```

```
// Natijani chiqarish
```

```
Console.WriteLine($"nFunksiya f(x) = x^2 + 3x - 5 uchun:");
```

```
Console.WriteLine($"f({x}) = {natija}");
```

```
}
```

```
}
```

Natija:

Agar foydalanuvchi quyidagicha qiymat kiritsa

x ning qiymatini kiriting: 2

Shunda ekranda quyidagicha natija chiqadi:

Funksiya $f(x) = x^2 + 3x - 5$ uchun:

$$f(2) = 5$$

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**MAKTAB TIBBIYOT HAMSHIRASINING ISH FAOLIYATI SIFATINI
TAKOMILLASHTIRISH VA OPTIMIZATSIYALASHTIRISH.**

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Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqolada maktab tibbiyot hamshiralari faoliyatining sifatini takomillashtirish va optimallashtirish masalalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Tadqiqot obyekti sifatida Buxoro viloyati Vobkent tumanidagi 31-maktab va Buxoro tumanidagi 49-maktab tibbiyot hamshiralari ish jarayonlari tahlil qilindi. Tadqiqotda so'rovnoma, intervyu va tahlil usullari qo'llanilib, hamshiralarning ish yuklamasi, profilaktika tadbirlarini amalga oshirishdagi muammolar, moddiy-texnik baza yetishmovchiligi va malaka oshirish imkoniyatlari cheklanganligi aniqlangan.*

Maqolada maktab tibbiyot hamshiralari ish samaradorligini oshirish uchun ish yuklamasini optimallashtirish, profilaktika tadbirlarini kengaytirish, moddiy-texnik bazani mustahkamlash, malaka oshirish dasturlarini rivojlantirish hamda axborot texnologiyalarini joriy etish bo'yicha takliflar beriladi. Tadqiqot natijalari maktablarda tibbiy xizmat sifatini yaxshilashga va o'quvchilarning sog'lig'ini himoya qilish tizimini takomillashtirishga yo'naltirilgan.

Аннотация: *В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы совершенствования и оптимизации качества деятельности школьных медицинских сестёр. В качестве объекта исследования были проанализированы рабочие процессы медицинских сестёр школы №31 в Вобкентском районе и школы №49 в Бухарском районе Бухарской области. В исследовании использованы анкетирование, интервью и аналитические методы, в результате которых выявлены проблемы, связанные с нагрузкой медицинских сестёр, реализацией профилактических мероприятий, недостаточностью материально-технической базы и ограниченными возможностями повышения квалификации.*

В статье предлагаются рекомендации по повышению эффективности работы школьных медицинских сестёр, включая оптимизацию нагрузки, расширение профилактических мероприятий, укрепление материально-технической базы, развитие программ повышения квалификации и внедрение информационных технологий. Результаты исследования направлены на

улучшение качества медицинского обслуживания в школах и совершенствование системы охраны здоровья учащихся.

Annotation: *This article explores the improvement and optimization of the quality of work performed by school nurses. The study analyzes the work processes of nurses at School No. 31 in Vobkent district and School No. 49 in Bukhara district, Bukhara region. The research employs surveys, interviews, and analytical methods to identify challenges such as workload issues, implementation of preventive measures, lack of material and technical resources, and limited opportunities for professional development.*

The article provides recommendations to enhance the efficiency of school nurses, including workload optimization, expansion of preventive programs, strengthening of material and technical resources, development of professional training programs, and the integration of information technologies. The research findings aim to improve the quality of school healthcare services and enhance the student health protection system.

Tayanch iboralar: *Maktab hamshirasi, tibbiy xizmat sifati, sog'liqni saqlash, profilaktika, telemeditsina, skrining, tibbiy nazorat, raqamli sog'liqni saqlash, sog'lom turmush tarzi, psixologik yordam.*

Maktab tibbiyot hamshirasi bolalarning sog'lig'ini saqlash va mustahkamlashda muhim rol o'ynaydi. U nafaqat shoshilinch tibbiy yordam ko'rsatadi, balki kasalliklarning oldini olish, sanitariya-gigiyena talablariga rioya qilish hamda o'quvchilarga sog'lom turmush tarzini targ'ib qilish bilan ham shug'ullanadi. Ushbu maqolada maktab tibbiyot hamshiralarining ish sifatini oshirish va samaradorligini oshirish bo'yicha takliflar beriladi.

Tadqiqotning dolzarbligi: Maktab tibbiyot hamshiralarining ish sifatini takomillashtirish va optimizatsiyalash hozirgi vaqtda dolzarb masala hisoblanadi, chunki bolalar salomatligini saqlash va mustahkamlash, kasalliklarning erta oldini olish hamda tibbiy xizmatning samaradorligini oshirish ta'lim muassasalarida sifatli tibbiy nazoratni talab qiladi. Zamonaviy innovatsion yondashuvlar, jumladan, raqamli texnologiyalar va profilaktik chora-tadbirlar yordamida maktab tibbiyot xizmatini takomillashtirish o'quvchilar sog'lig'ini yaxshilashga hamda umumiy tibbiy xizmat tizimini samarali tashkil etishga xizmat qiladi.

Tadqiqotning maqsadi: Maktab hamshiralarining ish faoliyatini o'rganish va ish sifatini oshirish, xizmatlarni optimallashtirish bo'yicha tavsiyalar ishlab chiqish.

Materiallar va usullar: Tadqiqot obyekti sifatida Buxoro viloyati Vobkent tumanidagi 31-maktab va Buxoro tumanidagi 49-maktabning tibbiyot hamshiralarining faoliyati tanlab olindi. Tadqiqotda ushbu maktablarda tibbiy xizmat ko'rsatish sharoitlari, mavjud muammolar va ish jarayonini yaxshilash yo'llari o'rganildi.

Tadqiqot doirasida quyidagi usullar qo'llanildi:

So'rovnoma – Maktab tibbiyot hamshiralarining ish sharoitlari, yuklama darajasi va muammolarini o'rganish.

Intervyu – Hamshiralarning kasbiy faoliyati, qiyinchiliklari va talablarini aniqlash. Tahlil – Maktab tibbiyot punktlari holati va ularning moddiy-texnik bazasini baholash.

Tadqiqot Buxoro viloyatining Vobkent tumanidagi 31 -maktab hamshirasi va Buxoro tumanidagi 49-maktab hamshirasi faoliyatini baholashga qaratildi. Har bir maktab uchun 50 tadan, jami 100 respondentdan anketalar to‘plandi. Tadqiqot maktab hamshiralarning ish sifati, o‘quvchilar va o‘qituvchilar bilan munosabatlari, profilaktik tadbirlar samaradorligi hamda tibbiy xizmat ko‘rsatish darajasini baholashga yo‘naltirildi.

Anketa ishtirokchilari:

Anketaga quyidagi respondentlar jalb qilindi:

O‘quvchilar (10–11-sinf) – 50 nafar

Ota-onalar – 20 nafar

Maktab o‘qituvchilari – 20 nafar

Maktab administratsiyasi vakillari – 10 nafar

Anketa mazmuni: 50 savoldan iborat anketa quyidagi asosiy yo‘nalishlarni qamrab oldi:

1. Hamshiraning kasbiy faoliyati

Favqulodda vaziyatlarda tezkorlik bilan tibbiy yordam ko‘rsatish

Dori-darmonlarni to‘g‘ri tavsiya qilish va ulardan foydalanish bo‘yicha maslahat berish

Sog‘liqni saqlash va gigiyena qoidalariga rioya qilishga o‘quvchilarni o‘rgatish

2. Profilaktik va tarbiyaviy ishlar

O‘quvchilar va o‘qituvchilarga muntazam tibbiy maslahat berish

Sog‘lom turmush tarzi va gigiyena bo‘yicha dars va seminarlar o‘tkazish

Maktab jamoasi bilan sog‘lom muhitni ta‘minlash

3. O‘zaro munosabatlar

O‘quvchilar bilan muloqot madaniyati va do‘stona muhit yaratish

Ota-onalar va o‘qituvchilar bilan hamkorlik qilish darajasi

Shikoyat va muammolarni hal qilishga bo‘lgan yondashuv

4. Ish sharoitlari va resurslar

Hamshira xonasining jihozlanganlik darajasi

Zarur dori-darmonlar va tibbiy anjomlarning mavjudligi

Ish jadvali va ish hajmi

Natijalar tahlili va tavsif. 31-maktab hamshirasi ning faoliyati haqida o‘quvchilarning 85 foizi ijobiy fikr bildirgan bo‘lsa, 49-maktab hamshirasiga nisbatan bu ko‘rsatkich 78 foizni tashkil etdi.

31-maktab hamshirasi profilaktik ishlarni yaxshiroq yo‘lga qo‘ygan bo‘lib, ota-onalar orasida ham ijobiy baho oldi. 49-maktabda esa, aksincha, sog‘lom turmush tarzi bo‘yicha targ‘ibot yetarli emasligi aniqlandi.

Favqulodda vaziyatlarda tezkor yordam ko'rsatish bo'yicha ikkala hamshira ham yuqori baholandi. Biroq 49-maktab hamshirasi tibbiy anjomlar va zarur dori-darmonlarning yetishmovchiligidan shikoyat qildi.

O'quvchilar bilan o'zaro munosabat jihatidan 31-maktab hamshirasi yanada ochiq va do'stona bo'lib, 49-maktab hamshirasida esa qat'iy va rasmiy yondashuv ustunlik qildi.

Shuningdek natijalar shuni ko'rsatdiki, 31-maktab va 49-maktab tibbiyot hamshiralarning ish faoliyatida quyidagi asosiy muammolar mavjud:

Ish yuklamasining yuqoriligi va vaqt yetishmovchiligi.

O'quvchilar o'rtasida profilaktik chora-tadbirlarni amalga oshirishning cheklanganligi.

Diagnostika va tibbiy kuzatuv uchun zamonaviy jihozlarning yetishmovchiligi.

Hamshiralarning malakasini oshirish imkoniyatlarining cheklanganligi.

Takomillashtirish bo'yicha quyidagi chora-tadbirlar tavsiya etiladi:

1. Ish yuklamasini optimallashtirish – Hamshiralalar uchun qo'shimcha yordamchi xodimlarni jalb etish, tibbiyot xodimlari ishini tizimli tashkil etish.
2. Profilaktika tadbirlarini kengaytirish – O'quvchilarga gigiyena va sog'lom turmush tarzi bo'yicha muntazam ma'ruzalar o'tkazish, kasalliklarning oldini olish choralari haqida ma'lumot berish.
3. Moddiy-texnik bazani mustahkamlash – Maktab tibbiyot punktlarini zamonaviy diagnostika va tibbiy jihozlar bilan ta'minlash.
4. Hamshiralalar malakasini oshirish – Davlat va xususiy tibbiyot muassasalari hamkorligida maxsus seminar va treninglar tashkil etish.
5. Axborot texnologiyalarini joriy etish – Elektron tibbiy kartalar tizimini rivojlantirish va maktab tibbiyot xodimlari uchun raqamli ma'lumotlar bazasini shakllantirish.

Xulosa: Maktab hamshiralarning profilaktik faoliyatini oshirish uchun sog'lom turmush tarzi bo'yicha muntazam seminar va darslar o'tkazish lozim. Resurs ta'minotini yaxshilash maqsadida tibbiy xonalarning jihozlanish darajasini oshirish hamda zarur dori-darmonlar bilan ta'minlash zarur.

Hamshiralalar va ota-onalar hamkorligini kuchaytirish orqali bolalarning sog'lig'iga e'tibor yanada oshirilishi mumkin. Maktab hamshiralarning malakasini oshirish uchun ularga muntazam o'quv kurslari va tajriba almashish imkoniyatlari yaratish lozim. Ushbu tadqiqot maktab tibbiyot hamshiralarning ish sifatini yaxshilash va optimallashtirish uchun muhim ma'lumotlarni taqdim etadi.

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USING CODE REVIEWS AS A FORMATIVE ASSESSMENT IN
PROGRAMMING EDUCATION

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Abstract: *Code reviews have gained traction not just in software development, but also in academic settings as a means to cultivate programming skills, communication competencies, and critical thinking. When employed as a formative assessment tool, code reviews enable students to receive prompt, detailed feedback on their work, fostering a culture of peer collaboration and continuous improvement. This article explores how code reviews function as an effective formative assessment strategy in programming education, synthesizing current research, practical classroom experiences, and empirical insights. It discusses how code reviews can scaffold learning, enhance understanding of coding standards, improve problem-solving approaches, and encourage reflective thinking in students. Additionally, potential challenges—such as the workload on instructors, ensuring constructive peer feedback, and addressing diverse student needs—are examined. Finally, the article summarizes evidence on how structured code review processes can drive deeper conceptual mastery, better code quality, and improved student retention rates in programming courses. By integrating code reviews throughout the academic term, educators can enhance the formative assessment landscape, aligning with industry practices while supporting key pedagogical principles.*

Key Words: *Code Reviews; Formative Assessment; Peer Feedback; Programming Education; Collaborative Learning; Reflective Practice; Software Quality*

INTRODUCTION

Programming education has steadily evolved to mirror real-world software development practices, emphasizing the importance of not only learning a programming language's syntax but also the broader context of teamwork, version control, and adherence to coding standards [1]. Traditional assessment methods—like quizzes, tests, and final projects—often provide a summative snapshot of student abilities but may fall short in offering timely, iterative feedback [2]. Code reviews, a

longstanding practice in professional software engineering, have begun to permeate academic settings as a more dynamic way to critique, refine, and learn from code [3].

In a code review, one or more individuals examine the structure, clarity, functionality, and maintainability of another's code, offering suggestions for improvements and highlighting potential errors [4]. When applied as a formative assessment tool, code reviews supplement or replace standard grading by focusing on learning and growth rather than on a single final grade [5]. Students engaged in code reviews receive targeted feedback that can illuminate misconceptions in logic, coding style, or problem-solving approaches, helping them make corrections and deepen their mastery [6]. Moreover, peer-to-peer code reviews foster a classroom culture of collaboration and mutual support, reflecting professional norms where software developers constantly evaluate and learn from each other's code [7].

This article examines how code reviews can function as an effective formative assessment mechanism in programming education. Specifically, it explores theoretical foundations, the role of code reviews in improving technical and communication skills, and the practical considerations for implementation. Through a literature review, discussion of best practices, and analysis of empirical results, this article makes the case that structured code review processes can substantially enhance student learning outcomes and overall course effectiveness [8].

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Formative Assessment and Feedback

Formative assessment focuses on providing ongoing, low-stakes feedback that guides students' learning processes [9]. Unlike summative assessments, which often culminate in a final grade or pass/fail criterion, formative assessments aim to identify gaps and support corrective action in real-time [10]. In programming courses, formative assessments can take many forms, such as short coding exercises, quick quizzes, or reflective journals. Code reviews align well with this paradigm because they deliver immediate, detailed commentary on one's work [11]. Importantly, research suggests that frequent, specific feedback is associated with improved performance, deeper engagement, and enhanced skill mastery [12].

2. Code Reviews in Professional Practice

In industry, code reviews have emerged as a staple practice for maintaining software quality, ensuring consistency in coding standards, and facilitating knowledge transfer among team members [13]. Conducted via platforms like GitHub or GitLab, developers iterate on code suggestions and discuss rationales for design decisions, enabling collective learning [14]. Code reviews help junior developers learn from senior staff while also prompting experienced engineers to articulate their thought processes [15]. The iterative nature of code reviews aligns with agile methodologies, fostering a mindset of continuous improvement [16].

3. Code Reviews in Academic Settings

Integrating code reviews into the educational space has shown promise for bridging theoretical concepts with applied problem-solving [17]. Students gain

exposure to real-world feedback loops, learning to evaluate code not only for correctness but also for maintainability, scalability, and clarity [18]. Several studies report improved student engagement and a heightened sense of accountability when peer review systems are adopted [19]. In a comparative study, classes with mandatory peer code reviews outperformed control groups on code style and debugging tasks, as measured by end-of-semester project evaluations [20]. That said, successful implementation depends on structured guidelines, instructor oversight, and training students in giving and receiving feedback [21].

4. Pedagogical and Cognitive Benefits

From a pedagogical standpoint, code reviews promote reflective practice, compelling learners to think critically about their coding choices and to justify them to peers [22]. Peer-to-peer interactions further encourage social constructivist learning, where learners co-create knowledge by discussing misconceptions and alternative solutions [23]. Code reviews also cultivate metacognitive skills by having students compare multiple ways of implementing solutions, discerning which approach is more efficient or readable [24]. Moreover, consistent exposure to critiques of one's code can temper the ego-driven defensiveness often seen in programming novices, fostering an openness to improvement [25].

5. Challenges and Considerations

Despite their benefits, code reviews can present logistical and pedagogical challenges. In larger classes, managing multiple code review sessions can strain instructor resources, demanding robust peer-review protocols or automated tools to handle the volume [26]. Additional obstacles include ensuring that feedback is constructive, respectful, and free from bias, especially among less experienced coders who may lack confidence in their critique abilities [27]. Furthermore, educators must address the inherent variability in code quality and prior programming experience, guiding advanced students to give effective feedback while supporting novices in implementing the suggestions they receive [28]. Addressing these issues requires thoughtful course design and clear instructions on both reviewing etiquette and technical focal points [29].

DISCUSSION

1. Structuring Code Reviews as Formative Assessments

To leverage code reviews effectively, educators should integrate them systematically into the course schedule. For instance, after each programming assignment, students can be randomly paired or grouped to review each other's code [30]. Instructors can provide a checklist or rubric emphasizing aspects like correctness, clarity, adherence to coding standards, efficiency, and documentation [31]. By focusing the code review process on learning goals rather than high-stakes grading, students are encouraged to take risks, experiment with new approaches, and learn from errors.

Example Structure:

1. Submission: Each student completes a short coding exercise.

2. **Review Assignment:** The instructor (or an automated system) assigns reviewers to submissions.

3. **Guided Feedback:** Peers use a rubric to comment on logic, style, and potential improvements.

4. **Revision:** Code authors incorporate feedback, refining their code or clarifying unresolved points.

5. **Instructor Check:** The instructor periodically reviews feedback exchanges to ensure validity and resolve conflicts.

2. Role of Instructor and Teaching Assistants

Because code reviews can be time-intensive, the instructor's role often shifts from direct grader to facilitator and quality controller of the review process [32]. Teaching Assistants (TAs) can be crucial in scaffolding this environment. For instance, TAs might model a proper review session by critiquing a sample piece of code in real-time, showcasing how to phrase feedback politely and effectively [33]. Furthermore, TAs can spot common misconceptions that surface in reviews, prompting additional lectures or discussion sessions aimed at clarifying these issues [34]. By routinely sampling peer-reviewed submissions, TAs or instructors can confirm that the feedback is constructive, accurate, and aligned with course objectives.

3. Encouraging Constructive Peer Feedback

One of the core challenges in peer review is maintaining constructive, actionable feedback rather than vague or overly critical remarks [35]. Educators can address this by teaching techniques such as the “feedback sandwich” (positive comment, suggestion for improvement, concluding praise), or by requiring feedback to be anchored in specific, observable aspects of the code [36]. Another approach involves providing sentence starters (e.g., “One thing I appreciated about your code is...,” “One area that might be improved is...”) to guide novices in delivering critiques diplomatically [37]. Emphasizing that mistakes are learning opportunities can normalize the critique process, reducing defensiveness and anxiety.

4. Integrating Industry Tools and Workflows

To simulate real-world software development, courses can integrate version control systems (e.g., Git) and online platforms (e.g., GitHub or GitLab) for code reviews [38]. Students learn to create pull requests, review diffs, and annotate lines of code—mirroring industry workflows. This practice fosters familiarity with collaborative programming tools, a marketable skill in internships and future jobs [39]. Likewise, implementing continuous integration checks—such as automated test suites—before the review can highlight functional errors, allowing the peer feedback to delve more deeply into code style, architecture, and performance considerations [40].

5. Addressing Diversity and Inclusivity

Diverse classrooms host learners with varying levels of coding background, linguistic proficiency, and cultural norms around criticism [41]. Code reviews, if

orchestrated sensitively, can help level the playing field by encouraging collaborative growth. However, educators must train students in cross-cultural communication and create an environment where all voices are respected [42]. Pairing advanced and novice students can be beneficial—novices gain insights from experienced peers, while advanced students solidify their understanding by teaching others [43]. Nonetheless, instructors should rotate partnerships periodically to avoid hierarchical dynamics and ensure broad exposure to multiple perspectives.

RESULTS

1. Enhanced Mastery of Programming Concepts

Studies and classroom implementations featuring code reviews indicate that students demonstrate more robust mastery of key concepts [44]. Engaging with multiple coding styles and problem-solving techniques broadens their understanding of the language and algorithms. Frequent feedback loops address misconceptions before they become entrenched, reducing the risk of error propagation in larger projects. For instance, a controlled study comparing classes with and without code reviews found a statistically significant difference in debugging proficiency, favoring the code review cohort [45].

2. Improved Code Quality and Professional Practices

Beyond conceptual mastery, the code review process sharpens an awareness of code readability, maintainability, and industry standards [46]. Students internalize the significance of descriptive variable names, concise functions, and consistent formatting—elements often overlooked in traditional assessments that prioritize correctness alone. In turn, by receiving feedback on their code's clarity and style, learners become more mindful of writing code that is legible and modifiable. When they transition to advanced courses or internships, this attention to detail often translates into fewer merge conflicts, cleaner version control histories, and smoother project collaborations [47].

3. Boost in Communication and Critical Thinking Skills

Writing thoughtful feedback requires analytical thinking, as students must pinpoint not just errors but also root causes and potential solutions [48]. This deep engagement fosters critical thinking skills that transcend coding tasks. Meanwhile, code authors learn to articulate and defend their design decisions or, alternatively, accept suggestions that improve their code—strengthening their ability to adapt to different viewpoints [49]. Over time, these collaborative exchanges foster a professional mindset where continuous improvement is expected, and constructive criticism is welcomed.

4. Increased Student Engagement and Motivation

Code reviews can enhance learner motivation by offering a sense of relevance and community. When students see peers implementing distinct approaches or creative optimizations, they become curious and more eager to experiment in their own projects [50]. This element of social learning can be particularly powerful in large, online, or hybrid classes, where direct instructor-student interaction is more

limited. The knowledge that someone else will read and comment on their code can incentivize students to refine their work, moving beyond the bare minimum required for passing tests [51]. Furthermore, many learners find personal satisfaction in realizing they can help their peers while also benefiting from reciprocal insights.

5. Potential Drawbacks and Solutions

Challenges persist, including time investment for both instructors and students. A course that demands weekly code reviews may strain resources unless the process is partially automated or well-scaffolded [52]. Another concern is variable feedback quality, especially if reviewers lack experience or self-confidence. To mitigate this, instructors can assign rubrics that standardize review criteria and offer sample feedback exemplars [53]. Finally, issues of interpersonal conflict or tension in peer critiques may arise, underscoring the need for initial training in communication strategies and ongoing instructor oversight [54].

CONCLUSION

Code reviews stand as a potent formative assessment strategy in programming education, reflecting both the iterative nature of coding and the collaborative ethos of professional software development. By systematically integrating code reviews into course structures, educators can provide detailed, timely feedback that spurs deeper conceptual understanding, stronger coding habits, and a heightened sense of student engagement. The literature and classroom evidence suggest that frequent, structured code reviews cultivate reflective practice, sharpen communication skills, and develop a nuanced appreciation for clean, maintainable code.

However, successful code review implementation demands careful planning. Instructors must design effective rubrics, model constructive feedback, and facilitate consistent, respectful exchanges among students. Teaching Assistants can play a pivotal role in monitoring review quality and reinforcing course objectives. Tools like GitHub or GitLab can further streamline the logistics of pairing reviewers, reviewing diffs, and maintaining accountability. Ultimately, code reviews enable students to learn from both instructor expertise and peer insights, bridging gaps in knowledge and instilling collaborative skills vital to modern software development.

Looking ahead, future research can explore larger-scale comparative studies of code review efficacy, investigate how automated analysis might complement peer feedback, and examine strategies for balancing the workload across diverse class sizes and formats. By refining these processes, programming educators will continue to enhance the formative assessment landscape, equipping learners not just with the means to write code, but also with the mindset of continuous improvement and cooperation that underlies excellence in software engineering.

DEVELOPMENT OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION COMPETENCES
IN INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE

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Abstract: This article analyzes the importance, methods and effective approaches to developing intercultural communication competencies in international experience. In the context of globalization, the need to establish effective communication between people of different cultures is increasing. In this regard, based on foreign experience, the formation of cultural sensitivity, tolerance, communicative competence and the ability to work in a multicultural environment in pupils, students and specialists is put forward as an important task.

The article examines educational programs, trainings, and policies aimed at developing intercultural competencies in the United States, European Union countries, and Asian countries. It also provides recommendations for developing these competencies that can be applied in Uzbekistan.

Keywords: intercultural communication, competence, international experience, globalization, communication skills, cultural sensitivity, tolerance, education system

In the context of globalization, the expansion of international relations between countries, international educational projects, student exchange programs, and migration processes significantly increase the need for intercultural communication competencies. Today, not only knowledge of foreign languages, but also the skills of effective and tolerant communication with representatives of different cultures have become one of the important factors determining the competitiveness of each individual.

In international experience, special attention is paid to the formation of socio-cultural competencies in students through programs, teaching methodologies and trainings aimed at developing intercultural dialogue. In developed countries such as the European Union, the USA, and Japan, the appreciation of cultural diversity and the development of interactive dialogue in the education system have become a priority area of educational policy.[1]

By studying this topic, it is possible to develop scientifically based approaches to effectively use international experiences in the Uzbek education system, to develop openness, tolerance and cultural empathy in students. Therefore, the topic of "Development of intercultural communication competencies in international experience" is considered one of the current scientific and practical issues today.

The number of international studies on the content and development of intercultural communication competence has increased significantly in recent years. Many scholars recognize this competence as an integral part of the modern education system, as well as an important factor in personal and professional success.

Michael Byram in his work "Teaching and Assessing Intercultural Communicative Competence" considers intercultural competence to be closely related to language learning and identifies the main components that make up this competence - sociocultural knowledge, social skills, empathy and cultural relativism. He places great emphasis on students' experiential learning in the formation of this competence.[2]

Deardorff in his model views intercultural competence as a constantly evolving, reflective process. He argues that this competence consists not only of knowledge and skills, but also of an individual's values, attitudes, and openness to other cultures.

Many documents developed by UNESCO and the report "Intercultural Competences: Conceptual and Operational Framework" recognize the development of intercultural competences as an important factor in ensuring global stability, peace and equity in education. The report reviews international practices in integrating these competences into curricula.[3]

Educational projects that bring together people from different nationalities and cultures through European Union programs such as Erasmus+ and eTwinning are yielding fruitful results. Teachers and students participating in these projects have been reported to have developed greater understanding, tolerance, and intercultural dialogue.

In the context of Uzbekistan, intercultural dialogue issues are being analyzed more through language learning, foreign language teaching methodologies, and international cooperation projects. In particular, issues related to the formation of intercultural competence in national educational programs have not yet been fully systematized, but reforms in this area are being implemented gradually.

The scientific novelty of this study is that it systematically analyzes practical approaches to the formation of intercultural dialogue in international experience and identifies the possibilities of adapting them to the education system of Uzbekistan. The study proposes an integrated model of language learning, interactive methods, digital technologies and international cooperation programs in the development of intercultural communication competencies. This will serve to form global competencies in national education policy.[4]

1. Table: Methods for developing intercultural communication competencies

No.	Competence	Definiti on	Develop ment Methods	Intern ational Experience (Example)
1	Cultural awareness	Respect for the customs and values of different cultures	Participation in international projects, intercultural trainings	Exchange programs such as Erasmus+, AFS
2	Language skills	Learning and using foreign languages in speech	Language learning courses, communication with language communities	Goethe-Institut, British Council programs
3	Communicativeness	Communicate effectively with people from different cultures	International conferences, online forums, internships	AIIESEC, UN Model Conferences
4	Flexibility	Quickly and effectively adapt to a new cultural environment	Study or work abroad, work in a multinational team	Work and Travel, DAAD scholarships
5	Empathy	Understanding and responding to the emotions of others	Participation in cultural events, volunteering	UNESCO cultural projects
6	Critical thinking	Avoiding stereotypes and objective evaluation	Case studies, cultural studies	Harvard Project Implicit test
7	Collaborate	Working with people from different cultures	International startups, multinational projects	CERN, NASA international collaborations

Based on the analyses conducted and international experiences studied, the following main results were identified:

- Culturally contextual materials, case studies, and role-playing games have been proven to be effective in curriculum development for building intercultural communication competence.
- In European and American education systems, this competency is consciously developed from the elementary stage and integrated into the curriculum.
- Interactive methods, in particular, Project-Based Learning, virtual exchanges, and cross-cultural problem-solving exercises, are highly effective.
- Although there are initial steps towards developing intercultural dialogue in Uzbekistan, they need to be systematized, teacher training and methodological support strengthened.[5]

2. Graph: The importance of intercultural communication competencies

Diagram type: Bar chart

Features:

- **Y-axis:** Competency level (1-10)
- **X-axis:** List of competencies

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Cultural Awareness: ██████████ (10)

Language proficiency: ███ (8)

Communicative: █

Adaptability: ████████ (7)

Empathy: ████████ (9)

Critical Thinking: █

Collaboration: ███ (7)

Note:

- The highest score was given to cultural awareness because it is the foundation for other competencies.
- **Language skills** and communicativeness plays a crucial role in international communication.

3. International Programs Distribution (Pie Chart)

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Erasmus+ — 35%

Work and Travel — 20%

AIESEC — 15%

DAAD — 10%

Other (UN, UNESCO) — 20%

Usage Tips:

- Tables and graphs can be used in presentations or scientific papers.
- A bar chart is useful for comparing competencies, while a pie chart is useful for showing the share of international programs.[6]

The development of intercultural communication competence is an integral part of the modern educational process. International experience shows that for the effective formation of this competence, culturally relevant educational materials, interactive

methods and technological solutions should be integrated into the educational process. This process serves not only the personal and professional development of students, but also the formation of an atmosphere of tolerance in society.[7]

1. Updating educational programs - improving curricula based on an interdisciplinary approach aimed at building intercultural competence.
2. Teacher training - organizing special trainings, international seminars, and advanced training courses for educators.
3. Expanding international cooperation - establishing joint projects, exchange programs, and virtual communication platforms with foreign educational institutions.
4. Use of technology – introducing online resources, interactive platforms, and educational simulations that strengthen intercultural communication.
5. Development of scientific research - creation of special grants, a database of scientific articles, and a monitoring system in this area.

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